

Social disinvestment and vulnerable groups in Europe in the aftermath of the financial crisis

The case of older job seekers in Austria

Elisabeth Buchner & Ortrud Leßmann

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Executive summary

This report is prepared in the framework of the Europe H2020 project ‘Rebuilding an inclusive, value based Europe of solidarity and trust through social investments’ (RE-InVEST). The project aims to evaluate the social investment strategy of the European Commission implemented in 2013 in response to the social damage of the financial crisis in 2008. The RE-InVEST consortium assesses the social damage of the crisis from human rights and capability based approaches with an eye to those vulnerable groups affected the most by the crisis in the 12 countries (and 13 regions) covered by the consortium. The analyses are carried out by the local partners, who consist of NGOs and/or researchers.

In comparison to other European countries, Austria has gotten well through the crisis. Mainly the banking sector and exporters – in particular manufacturing trade – have been affected by the crisis. The government helped the former by bail out policies. The latter has recovered quickly. Unemployment increased only moderately at first, but since 2013 unemployment rates are rising. The group of older unemployed (aged 45 and more) is particularly affected for various reasons: The effect of the demographic trend of an aging society is reinforced by the politics of lifting the retirement age. Further, older unemployed have to search longer for new employment. In sum, these effects lead to an increasing share of older unemployed. For this reason the group was identified as particularly affected by the crisis.

The RE-InVEST consortium has jointly developed the PAHRCA-methodology that combines principles of Participatory Action research with Human Rights and Capability Approaches. This qualitative, participatory research does not generate representative results but rather aims at an in-depth understanding of the economic, social, cultural and political impacts of the crisis on the lives of vulnerable people and giving them a voice in the co-creation of knowledge process between researchers, professionals and target group. In Austria six women and three men aged 45 to 60 years and unemployed despite their qualification participated in the study.

The biographies of K. and L. illustrate the marks of the crisis on individual life courses. The situation of K. was characterised by the close interdependency of private and professional life so that the economic impact of the crisis on her husband’s consultancy firm has far reaching consequences:

‘Our life has been practically devastated. The firm gone, house gone, livelihood gone, son has given up school and I have started from scratch.’

In contrast to that the narrative of L. tells the story of the creeping process of growing pressure and competition that was reinforced by the financial crisis and has led to her burnout:

‘Of course for me, 2015 was an utterly miserable year, but in the end I got out well. Sooner or later I would have had to do it anyway, to get out of there before I lost my mind.’

While the biographies exemplify the effects of the crisis in the course of time, the analysis is based on contributions of all participants and is arranged thematically. The financial crisis was perceived by the participants as a sneaking process that aggravated the situation. For instance, temporary agency workers lost their jobs during the crisis and even though the employment level in the sector recovered soon, their salaries have not reached the pre-crisis level again. The most dramatic change in the lives of the participants was becoming unemployed and having to look for new employment. The new strategic orientation of social investment has not trickled down to Austrian employment policies yet: Participants report that the treatment at the Public Employment Service varies a great deal depending on the clerk in charge of the individual case.

Often they have not received the information they wanted. They have had little say in setting up their 'support agreement' or in choosing training courses or in determining the volume of their future employment. Many regulations impede pro-active behaviour by the unemployed as the example of visiting other countries shows: Unemployed need to give notice of their traveling and register anew on return – even for one day. Apart from what they call *'living in standby-mode'* participants suffer the most from deteriorating social contacts and lacking social recognition: They have lost friends and their families are affected as well. They are depressed by the way people ask how they are doing since it is less an inquiry on their well-being than an inquiry on their professional activity. That employment is the foundation of social recognition is also obvious in the derogative way politicians talk about unemployment and the unemployed. However, older unemployed do not lack in qualification or enthusiasm, they are simply aged around 50 and are thus judged by enterprises to be close to retirement although politics aims at lifting retirement age.

Participants have had support from various parties: their friends and families as well as doctors and psychotherapists. Beyond medical treatment and psychotherapy the latter gave them time and opportunity to recover before their first contact with the Public Employment Service. Finally, participants view all opportunities for actively participating in society as important instances of social recognition and bases of self-respect.

In conclusion while the financial crisis has not hit Austria as strong as other countries, it has had effects: Unemployment is on the rise, in particular among people aged 45 and more. Austerity policy has continued and undermined trust in politics and existing institutions. The core idea of the social investment strategy of the European Commission - 'investing in people' - has not gotten to older unemployed in Salzburg. They have rather been impeded to invest in lifelong learning and training. Furthermore, legal security is undermined insofar as the information and support provided by the Public Employment Service varies with the clerk in charge and because integrated case-management of multiple problems is missing. Participants have noticed the development of a culture of competition and distrust. They are concerned about raising inequality and increasing visibility of poverty. However, they also ask if the crisis may be seen as a chance to solve the problems that have been lingering since long.

Preface

The research consortium RE-InVEST decided to follow a participatory approach that is able both to reflect the current thinking of people affected by (social) policy as well as to inspire action to change it. This research methodology is challenging in many ways, but first and foremost requires trust between researchers and participants. We are most grateful to the participants in our group who lived up to the ideal of co-researchers in the course of the first stage of the project that is the subject of this report. Many thanks to them for sharing their experience and giving their thoughts on the findings!

We would also like to thank all those who have enabled the project to become a success so far: The Alliance for Jobs for Best Ager (Bündnis Arbeit für Best Ager, our partner NGO for this project), Frau & Arbeit (Woman & Work), Kirche und Arbeitswelt (Church and Working Life) and Bewohnerservice Salzburg (publicly funded district work in the city of Salzburg) that helped in recruiting participants for the project and participated in our steering committee. Furthermore, the exchange with our RE-InVEST colleagues was crucial in developing the methodology. Finally, financial support by the European Commission is gratefully acknowledged.

Contents

List of figures	9
Introduction	10
1. National context	13
1.1 Austria and the crisis	13
1.1.1 Background	13
1.1.2 The crisis in Austria: impact and political reaction	14
1.2 Salzburg and the crisis	16
1.3 Older job-seekers particularly affected	16
2. Theoretical and Methodological Approach	18
3. Two selected biographies	21
3.1 First biography	21
3.2 Second biography	23
4. Analysis	27
4.1 Which crisis?	27
4.2 Searching for employment	28
4.3 More effects of the crisis and unemployment	31
4.3.1 Effects on social networks	31
4.3.2 Effects on society	33
4.3.3 Effects on the political climate	33
4.3.4 Effects on health care arrangements	35
4.4 Support and help	35
5. Conclusion	36
appendix 1 Rules of Conduct of the Group	39
appendix 2 What constitutes a good life? List of elements	40
Bibliography	43

List of figures

Figure 2.1	Resources, conversion factors, capability set and achieved functionings	18
Figure 2.2	Merging of knowledge	19
Figure 4.1	Drawing on the relationship to the government I	34
Figure 4.2	Drawing on the relationship to the government II	34
Figure A1.	Agreed rules of conduct	39
Figure A2.	List of elements of a good life	40
Figure A3.	Capability grid	41
Figure A4.	Perceived achievements in the dimensions of the good life	42

Introduction

Although ‘inclusive growth’ is one of the pillars of the Europe 2020 strategy, the social dimension of the strategy has lost momentum with the (Euro) crisis and the ensuing priority given to macro-economic stabilisation policies. The agreed target of alleviating poverty by 20 million poor in 10 years cannot be reached anymore due to the crisis. Instead, inequalities are growing, unemployment and poverty are reaching new records, particularly in the peripheral regions of the EU. In 2013, the Commission launched a major endeavour to rebalance economic and social progress: the Social Investment Package (SIP).

Whereas the trends in - and causes of - increased inequality and social exclusion have already been extensively studied, the economic, social, cultural and political consequences of this growing divide are less clear. RE-InVEST aims to fill this gap by evaluating the SIP from a human rights and capability perspective. The first step in this endeavour is a diagnosis of the social damage of the crisis in terms of (the erosion of) human rights, social (dis)investment, loss of (collective) capabilities, and loss of trust. This national report analyses the impact of the crisis on unemployed people in Austria aged 45 and older.

The research builds on prior work on the consequences of growing inequality. For example Wilkinson and Pickett (2010) argue that inequality affects people’s psychological health, trust, the overall social climate, and indirectly also boosts violence, racism, mental illness, infant mortality, suicide etc. Moreover, this seems to apply to rich as well as poor people. One of the most worrying trends since the outbreak of the crisis is the dramatic decline of trust in institutions, including the European Union. This link deserves further investigation. Other alarming symptoms are massive homelessness, youth unemployment, and emigration of young people as well as resurgence of contagious diseases or indeed suicide rates among the poor (Nicaise and Schepers 2013).

Hence, a first key working assumption of RE-InVEST is that growing distrust and indeed resentment among the population towards institutions in general and European institutions in particular may be attributed to (a rejection of) the neoliberal policies employed by national as well as European elites in recent years. As shown by social capital experts such as Uslaner (2003), Kumlin (2004) and Larsen (2007) countries with higher social-expenditure-to-GDP ratios tend to generate more trust among their population through the achievement of more equal opportunities. Furthermore it is well known that trust is positively correlated with income or socio-economic status (Finsveen & Van Oorschot, 2008; EC, 2007). Hence, it seems quite plausible that the retrenchment of the state, in conjunction with rising inequality and income insecurity, may have undermined trust, especially among the poor and the ‘precariat’ (Standing 2011).

However, these developments do not provoke solidarity with the poor or a collective reaction reclaiming the welfare state as a guarantee of social inclusion. This is partly due to the asymmetries in the effects on different social groups, and partly because of the shift in social capital and cultural values (focus on individual responsibility, reduction of the ‘tax burden’, downsizing of unions and NGOs, etc.) to which neoliberal policies have contributed. Further developments may help explain why European citizens remain divided such as the erosion of the middle-class, uncertainty among workers and the rise of precarity, internalisation of the obsession with austerity and the pressure of internal and external migration. In order to rebuild a consensus about the social dimension of European policies, there is a need for a diagnosis of the social crisis that can be shared by large Sections of the population: the socially excluded, the peripheral regions, the labour movement and the ‘average citizen’ (Deneulin, Nebel, and Sagovsky 2006; Dubois 2009).

A second key working assumption of RE-InVEST is that this integrated diagnosis can build on the idea of the erosion of basic social rights and the disinvestment in capabilities of individuals and groups in the EU. This means that experiences of insecurity, poverty and social degradation need to be re-analysed from

those perspectives. Human rights (and basic economic, social and cultural rights in particular) can be seen as the cornerstone of European values and thus an essential part of our European heritage (Hart 2010). By fragmenting and weakening public services as well as civil society organisations, trade unions etc. solidarity is undermined and the role of collectivities in enhancing individual capabilities is constrained. RE-InVEST aims at giving vulnerable people a voice and therefore has opted for using a participatory research approach. Researchers and participants jointly analyse the impact of the crisis on capabilities and human rights. This report summarises the diagnosis of social damage of the crisis for Austria. The next Section describes the national context in Austria and motivates the choice of the target group: People in the age of 45 to 65 have experienced a sharp increase in unemployment in the aftermath of the crisis. Not only is their absolute number as well as their share in unemployment growing, they also have particular difficulties in finding new employment once they have become unemployed. Section 2 briefly introduces the theoretical framework and the methodology of Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach (PAHRCA) developed by RE-InVEST. Further, the implementation of PAHRCA in Austria is described. Section 3 comprises the two biographies from Austria. In Section 4 these and the testimonies of the other participants in the group are analysed with regard to the impact of the crisis on social investment, human rights and capabilities: ‘Which crisis?’ has been a frequent reaction to the presentation of RE-InVEST, indicating that the crisis in 2008 has not been imprinted on Austrian’s memories. The participants of the Austrian group have of course mostly suffered from being unemployed and searching for a job. But this has had further impacts on social networks, social recognition on a larger scale, politics and the health care system. Section 5 summarises the impact of the crisis on human rights, capabilities and social cohesion and presents some conclusions.

1. National context

1.1 Austria and the crisis

1.1.1 Background

The Austrian economy has benefited immensely from the EU Eastern enlargement and the introduction of the Euro. After two decades of comparably low economic and real wage growth, gradually rising unemployment and several austerity packages including welfare cuts and privatisation, Austria entered a period of economic upturn in 2003. Real wages grew significantly in 2006 and 2007 and unemployment fell below 4% in 2008. (Hermann and Flecker 2015) Especially the recently privatised banking sector benefited from large-scale and in part highly risky investments in Eastern Europe. However, while profits rose in booming sectors, the wage share decreased from 75% in 1998 to 66% in 2007. The long term trend shows an increasing tax burden on labour compared to other types of income. (Glocker et al. 2014: 254–56)

As a result of these developments the already high export orientation and reliance on external demand of the Austrian economy increased even further, making it particularly prone to the effects of the crisis. (Hermann & Flecker 2015)

Compared to EU average, unemployment remained low throughout the last decades though. Retaining high employment rates has been a political priority, especially for the Austrian social partners, who dominated Austrian policy making in the first decades of the Second Republic and still exert considerable political influence. As labour market problems began to increase since the 70s, early retirement provisions were used extensively to prevent unemployment. As a result, the de facto retirement age is still below EU-average and spending for early retirement pensions has grown strongly until the turn of the century. (BMASK 2014: 227) Despite a sharp increase in unemployment rates since 2012/2013, until the end of 2015 Austria still had the lowest unemployment rate in the EU.

Modernisation, liberalisation and economic integration led to changes on the Austrian labour market corresponding to trends in many other EU countries. Although no large scale deregulation took place, atypical and precarious forms of employment have grown. Between 2004 and 2014 the part-time quote increased from 19,9% to 26,9%. (Eurostat o.J.) There is a tendency of polarisation of the labour force, meaning that precarious jobs and long-term unemployment are concentrated on certain groups who are at risk of more or less permanent exclusion from stable standard employment and corresponding rights and entitlements. (Eichmann & Saupe 2014: 62–63; Atzmüller 2009: 142) This group comprises people with a migration background, low formal qualification, women, single parents and people with disabilities. People with a migrant background for example work significantly more often below their qualification level, in low wage sectors or in jobs with low professional prestige. (Eppel, Horvath, und Mahringer 2013) Almost half of female workers are part-time employed. If women change from part-time work to another labour market position, they have a 100% higher risk than men of ending up in the low wage sector, earning less than two thirds of medium income. (Eppel, Horvath & Mahringer 2013: 89–90) Childcare obligations are the main reason why women decide to work only part-time. (Knittler 2015) The predominance of non-standard employment among women reflects the highly unequal distribution of paid and unpaid work between the sexes in Austria. As a consequence women face a much higher poverty risk than men, especially after they retire. Also the gender pay gap between men and women is above EU average, despite a slight decrease between 2008 and 2009. (Statistik Austria 2015b)

Unemployment constitutes a high poverty risk, because in the Austrian conservative welfare state with its 'Bismarckian system' and its high proportion of cash benefits instead of public services, labour market participation is crucial for integration into social security systems. Welfare institutions continue to discriminate against people with discontinuous working careers, especially women and low income earners. (Hermann and Flecker 2015: 196; Fink et al. 2010: 85) Unemployment benefits are calculated on the basis of previous income without a minimum allowance so that those strata of the working population are most severely affected who do not manage to enter into lasting employment. As a consequence workers with low income are not entitled to sufficient benefits to cover their living expenses in case of unemployment, although their risk of becoming unemployed is much higher than for others. As Fink states, the number of people for whom '*unemployment is just interspersed by rather short spells of employment (or illness) (...) increased from ca. 34,500 in 2008 to ca. 82,000¹ in 2014.*' (Fink 2015a: 10)

While unemployment is rising sharply, the working population is growing as well. Between 1994 and 2013 the workforce rose from 3.7 to 4.1 million. (Statistik Austria 2016a) The reasons are increasing labour market participation of women, longer working-life due to the gradual increase of the retirement age and immigration, especially from Eastern Europe. However, the volume of work is not increasing correspondingly which leads to more part-time and insignificant employment, flexible under-employment and both periodic and structural unemployment.

1.1.2 The crisis in Austria: impact and political reaction

In 2009 Austria experienced the sharpest recession since 1945. GDP contracted by 3.6%. Two sectors of the Austrian economy were particularly affected by the financial crisis: banking and exporters, especially manufacturing companies. Exports plummeted by 20% in 2009. (Hermann & Flecker 2015)

The immediate anti-crisis measures of the Austrian government followed the Keynesian approach and included stabilisation programmes for particularly affected sectors and budgetary stimulus measures (tax cuts, a car-scrapping scheme to boost new car sales, public investment in infrastructure and state-supported loans for Small and Medium Enterprises). For the staggering banking sector a rescue package with a size of up to 100 billion Euros was put in place (until the end of 2014 7.3 billion were spent on shares and liabilities of Austrian banks).

The budgetary burden of bailouts for banks is huge. Public debt soared by 4.3%, when federal government had to take over the liabilities of the 'Bad Bank' Heta in 2014. (Bundesministerium für Finanzen 2015: 98–99).

Another important feature of Austrian anti-crisis policies was the re-vitalisation of social partnership. Two labour market packages were set up with the support of the social partners. The most important measure was the reform of temporary short-time working as an alternative to job cuts. Wide use of short-time work is considered as the most important factor for the only moderate increase of unemployment (+1.4%). Other changes with respect to training and life-long learning were less widely used.

At the end of 2009 exports had almost recovered to pre-crisis levels. The budget deficit had increased because of the anti-crisis policies (2008: -1.4%; 2009: -5.3%; 2010: -4.4%). (Statistik Austria 2015c) Therefore the federal budget for 2011 foresaw savings of 1.6 billion Euro through an increase in consumption taxes and cuts in the education and research sector, in care and family allowances and to a lesser extent in pensions. Further, a bank levy was introduced for a limited period of time. For the period between 2012 and 2016 an austerity package was designed with budgeted savings amounting to 19 billion Euro, thereof 7.3 billion in the pension system and 1.4 billion in healthcare. (Wirtschaftsblatt 2010)

1 Defined by the number of people registered with the PES, who have been unemployed for at least one year, with an interruption of up to 62 days because of illness or employment not taken into account. These persons are categorised as 'long-term unoccupied'.

However in conclusion cuts in social services were limited to certain specific measures in line with previous welfare reform paths. As Fink puts it: *‘Contrary to many other EU-Member States no large-scale or structural retrenchment took place in most social policy areas in Austria during the last years.’* (Fink 2015b)

The proportion of people affected by poverty and social exclusion has not increased at household level (Lamei u.a. 2014: 342), although the unemployment rate has increased and the market income distribution has become more unequal during the last years. (Eichmann and Saupe 2014, 120). The lowest income decile of workers in 2013 earned only 56% of the comparative value in 1998 (Rechnungshof 2014: 21; 32–42) However, at the household level various entitlements such as family and care allowances, unemployment and housing benefits and progressive income taxation contribute to reach an equivalent income above the poverty threshold. The redistributive features of the Austrian welfare state have reduced the risk of poverty from 44% (household income without pensions and social benefits) to 14% in 2015. (Statistik Austria 2015a: 70; Obinger 2015)

Also, around 90% of all unemployed registered with the Public Employment Service (PES in the following for Arbeitsmarktservice or AMS) receive unemployment benefits, although it is not clear how many are unemployed and do not get benefits, because they do not register with PES for various reasons. (Fink 2015b)

Unemployment is rising steadily since 2013. In particular persons who are not Austrian citizens and people aged 50 or more years are affected, while youth unemployment has decreased slightly. (Arbeitsmarktservice Österreich 2015) The average duration of unemployment has increased sharply and long-term unemployment has more than doubled between 2008 and 2014. Around one third of all registered unemployed persons are long-term unemployed, meaning they are out of work for more than one year. (Höller 2015) The at-risk-of poverty rate of long-term unemployed persons is high. According to EU-SILC data, 45.7% of those with ‘unemployment’ as the most frequent activity status in the previous year were at risk of poverty in 2013. (Fink 2015a, 6)

Due to these developments, demand for Active Labour Market Policy has increased both quantitatively and qualitatively, while the budget for ALMP has not. As a result, the available funding per person has decreased and cuts were made to certain qualification measures. For 2016 and 2017 retraining grants for low skilled workers or unemployed people were put on hold (Pfleger 2015).

Newly created jobs are often precarious. This means, that *‘(...) the crisis has prolonged and accelerated the long-term trend of flexibilisation and precarisation, which has become an important feature of the Austrian labour market.’* (Hermann and Flecker 2015: 204). The growth of labour market segmentation and social inequality are major problems of the Austrian system, which are not countered by adequate social investment. As Hermann and Flecker (2015: 207) put it: *‘(...) while Austria seems to be able to hold on to existing achievements, it is not making the investments needed to cope with future challenges, including long overdue investments in public infrastructure and research, as well as in a profound social and ecological modernisation.’*

Many Austrians feel that they have been directly affected by the crisis. Public opinion polls indicate an increasing feeling of uncertainty and distrust in political actors and institutions. Opinion polls after the parliamentary elections in 2013 showed that almost half of the voters think that Austrian politics is failing frequently on crucial issues. (Ullram 2013) The grand coalition between the Social and the Conservative Party (SPÖ and ÖVP) that is governing Austria since 2006, is losing support and the party system is changing: new parties emerge on the political landscape and the right-wing populist, EU-sceptic Freedom Party (FPÖ) is gaining more and more support. The FPÖ managed to triple their percentage of vote in the elections to the European Parliament in 2014 and won more than 30% of the votes in two out of three state elections in 2015. Trust in national and EU institutions decreased further and the assessment of economic and labour market development deteriorated, according to Eurobarometer results. Only 13% of Austrian respondents agree that things are going into the right direction in the EU, while 56% disagree. Also, more than half of the respondents in 2015 are fairly or very pessimistic about the future of the EU and think that the worst impact of the crisis is still to come. (Europäische Kommission 2015)

1.2 Salzburg and the crisis

The federal state of Salzburg had engaged in highly speculative trades before the crisis. This led to huge speculative losses after the financial crisis hit the Eurozone. After the scandal came to light in 2012 the government was replaced by early elections. The new government adopted an austerity budget in 2014, after the budget deficit rose sharply in 2013. (orf.at 2013)

While the political scope for social investment was reduced thereby, living costs have been rising and real wages stagnating. Compared to all other federal states wages are lower in Salzburg in 2014, due to low average wages and a high share of part-time and seasonal work in the disproportionately large service sector (tourism, especially accommodation, gastronomy and trade). (Arbeiterkammer Salzburg 2016) Rents increased in Austria by 15.1% between 2010 and 2014. In Salzburg the increase in rents was the highest throughout Austria. Between 2004 and 2015 rents increased by 36.2%. (orf.at 2016; *news.ORF.at* 2015) Similarly, real estate prices have risen. Single-family houses are more expensive in Salzburg than in other Austrian federal states. Between 2009 and 2014 market prices for real estate in the city of Salzburg have increased by almost 40%. (Arbeiterkammer Salzburg o.J.)

The high costs of living especially for housing lead to more applications for social assistance. Between 2010 and 2014 unemployment has risen by 27.8% in the federal state of Salzburg and by 42.7% in the city of Salzburg. One quarter of the unemployed needs additional social assistance (means-tested income support), because the unemployment benefit is too low. The number of recipients of means-tested income support has increased by 8% between 2013 and 2014. 70% of them have some sort of income, but are unable to support themselves due to the rising living costs. (Land Salzburg, Abteilung Soziales 2015)

Food banks in Salzburg experienced a rise in demand in 2009, the first crisis year in Austria, by 20% (countryside) respectively 10% (city of Salzburg). (APA - Austria Presse Agentur 2009)

Asked about future prospects concerning economic development, poverty and inequality, the people of Salzburg give rather pessimistic answers. One survey from 2013 found that 84% of respondents agree with the statement that the gaps between the rich and the poor in Salzburg will increase (92% of unemployed respondents) and 80% agree that the economic upward mobility will be more difficult in the future. (Nowotny 2013)

1.3 Older job-seekers particularly affected

After a small recovery from crisis-related labour market problems in 2011, unemployment has been rising steadily in Austria since 2012/2013. Whereas at the beginning of the crisis in 2009 young people between 15 and 24 were disproportionately affected by the rise in unemployment, the age based risk has been reversed in the following years. In April 2015 already one in four unemployed persons was aged above 50 – this marks an increase of 17.2% compared with the same month in 2014. In Salzburg, one out of three unemployed persons is aged 45 or older. In no other age group unemployment has been rising faster. Together with migrants, people with low formal qualification and people with disabilities older people are hit the hardest. (see Austrian Ministry for Employment 2014, 373; *Wirtschaftsblatt* 2015/05/05)

Due to the demographic transition this age group is growing in numbers and as a consequence of various pension reforms since 1992 they have to be available on the labour market longer, though real employment opportunities look grim.

In February 2016 unemployment in the federal state of Salzburg decreased slightly compared to the previous year, for the first time since almost four years. Only in the age group 50+ unemployment continued to grow (+2,9%). (Arbeitsmarktservice Salzburg 2016)

Especially after the turn of the century comprehensive early retirement provisions have been reduced, attempting to adapt the factual retirement age to the statutory one. Older people who become unemployed experience considerably more difficulties in finding new employment in Austria than younger persons. Job loss at an older age constitutes a huge risk to lose access to the labour market once and for all. This is especially problematic because in the Austrian conservative welfare state with its 'Bismarckian system' and

its high proportion of cash benefits instead of public services, labour market participation is key to integration into social security systems.

Early retirement schemes have been used since the 70s as a political strategy to address labour market problems. Therefore the Austrian labour market is still ill-equipped for the participation and especially the (re)integration of older workers after a gap in employment. Consequently the labour market participation of older persons has been low. Despite a steep increase since the turn of the century, in 2008 the employment rate of people aged 55 to 64 was 41% only. By 2015 this has increased marginally to 45.1%, which is still low compared to EU-average (50.8%). (Statistik Austria 2016b; Famira-Mühlberger, Huemer & Mayrhuber 2015: 3)

Therefore the average period of unemployment is much higher for older workers and they account for more than one third of all long-term unoccupied and almost half of the long-term unemployed. (Arbeitsmarktservice Österreich 2015) This group faces a considerably higher risk of persistent unemployment and impoverishment.

Also the structure and dynamic of unemployment for older people differs from the younger generation in that they have a significantly higher risk of long-term unemployment if they become unemployed. (WIFO, AMS 2013: 3) Their situation can be described as a double trap: on the one hand, unemployment among them is severely rising; on the other hand, they are much less likely to find another job.

For 2016 and 2017 the budget for Active Labour Market Policy has been increased considerably for the target group 50+. However most of the funding is being spent on temporary wage subsidies ('integration allowances'), rather than on qualification and training. High quality training is difficult to access. Still 8% of the total budget for ALMP is spent on measures for exiting the labour market prematurely (semiretirement programs, transitional allowance, advance on future pensions from the unemployment insurance scheme). (Bock-Schappelwein et al. 2014: 83)

Summing up, older people are hit by the crisis and crisis-related policies in two ways: There is more pressure on them than before to work until they reach retirement age. In times of high unemployment they are disadvantaged by the ill-preparedness of Austrian politics and economy to (re)-integrate older job-seekers in the labour market. Although many of the outlined effects of the crisis and crisis-related policies affect broader strata or the Austrian population as a whole, the labour market related capabilities of older people are particularly diminished as a result of this double effect. Therefore, the Austrian part of RE-InVEST focuses on this target group and their view on the social damage by the financial crisis in Austria.

2. Theoretical and Methodological Approach

RE-InVEST aims at investigating the philosophical, institutional and empirical foundations of an inclusive Europe of solidarity and trust. To this end it draws on capability and human rights based participatory approaches. *Human rights* form a common European basis of values and describe at the same time core elements of what constitutes well-being and a good life. Further, human rights are transformative by empowering people. Human rights are the basic rights and freedoms that belong to everyone. International law, including treaties, contain the provisions which give human rights legal effect. Ideas about human rights have evolved over many centuries and gained strong support after World War II when the United Nations adopted the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights - which set out for the first time the human rights and fundamental freedoms shared by all human beings without discrimination of any kind. Human Rights are universally agreed basic standards that aim to ensure that every person is treated with dignity and respect; they are interdependent and indivisible, meaning that rights are linked and not protecting one right may impact on another, they belong to all people without discrimination. Usually set out in law, through international or regional treaties, or national legislation, they form a legal statement of universally accepted principles of how the state should treat its citizens and other people living within its jurisdiction. Human Rights include Civil and Political Rights, such as the right to life, the right to a fair trial and the right not to be subjected to torture; and Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, such as the right to work, to join a trade union, to health, to education, and to an adequate standard of living. Specific groups are protected in specific treaties such as women, children, people with disabilities, minorities, and migrants. For vulnerable people the usage of a rights-terminology has proven to change their perspective by making them aware of their rights and the ways in which their current situation compromises these rights. The *capability approach* as developed by Sen (1999) and Nussbaum (2011) defines a person's well-being in terms of the beings and doings (the functionings) a person achieves and her capability to choose among different combinations of such functionings. For leading a life one values and has reason to value resources and conversion factors are preconditions (Figure 2.1). Resources refer to the material conditions of a person: her income, the goods and services she disposes of. Conversion factors help her converting resources into doing and being well. There are personal conversion factors such as skills and bodily features, social conversion factors such as social norms and social institutions and environmental conversion factors such as climate and geography. In the end both the achieved functionings as well as the freedom to choose a life one values matters.

Figure 2.1 Resources, conversion factors, capability set and achieved functionings

For assessing the capabilities of vulnerable people RE-InVEST aims at giving them a voice. Their participation is fostered by relying on *participatory action research* that directly results in policy recommendations.

Participatory action research views participants as co-researchers who have special knowledge about their own situation. Hence they are not only asked or interviewed on their views but take part in research by engaging in, examining, interpreting, and reflecting on their own social world, shaping their sense of identity. It is a circle of knowledge generation that emerges from this method and includes the steps of knowledge production and sharing, empowerment by participation, newly generated knowledge and action that builds upon this knowledge (figure 2.2). Crucial for this kind of knowledge generation is the ‘merging’ or ‘crossing of knowledge’ that comes from three parts: scientific knowledge as gained by researchers; knowledge which the poor and excluded have, from their firsthand experience, of the twin realities of poverty and the surrounding world which imposes it on them; and the knowledge of those who work among and with these vulnerable people in places of poverty and social exclusion (figure 2.3).

Figure 2.2 Merging of knowledge

These are the core elements of the Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach (PAHRCA) developed in RE-InVEST. PAHRCA entails seven steps (Toolkit, 44-45):

1. identify and meet partner NGO/gatekeeper;
2. preliminary ‘meet ups’ (for trust building if necessary);
3. first meeting with participants – trust building;
4. developmental: implement developmental human rights & capability approach;
5. inquiry/data gathering;
6. identifying patterns (key issues and themes of concern to the group) and
7. undertake action/outcome using one or combination of approaches.

In Salzburg, Austria we decided to work with older unemployed people (aged 45 to 60) after analysing the situation in Austria (see Section 2). The ‘Alliance for Jobs for Best Agers’ (Bündnis Arbeit für Best Ager) serves as gatekeeper (step 1). It is a grassroots initiative of older unemployed people who aim at making their situation known publicly, work as a pressure group and help older unemployed to find employment. After two preliminary meetings with the founder and some core members of the group (step 2) we launched a call for participation that was published by some other stakeholders as well (‘Frau & Arbeit’, a non-profit private limited company, supported by public funds and ‘Kirche & Arbeitswelt’ funded by the Catholic church). Six women and three men of the targeted age group came to our first meeting in November, two with caring responsibilities for their parents and two with children under 18, all with some health problems, all with some qualification (vocational training or university degree) and yet unemployed. (step 3). For trust building we did some sociographic line-ups, explained PAHRCA and the context of RE-InVEST to the

group (including the content of the informed consent form) and agreed on some rules of conduct within the group (see Appendix, Figure a.1.1): confidentiality, respect and recognition of limits, no advice unasked for, no discouraging story-telling, punctuality, reliability, and honesty.

Finally we used drawing as an ice-breaker, asking how the participants view their relation to the government (see Figure. 4.1 and 4.2). Following this first meeting with participants of the target group, there were two more group meetings in December 2015 and January 2016 that mainly aimed at implementing the capability and human rights approach (step 4) and data gathering (step 5). For the former we asked the participants at the second meeting to indicate the three most important elements of a good life. This method was used by Clark (2005) for generating a list of capabilities. The resulting list (see appendix) was put in contrast to the human rights based capability list developed by Burchardt and Vizard (2011a). Coming back to this at the third meeting we asked the participants to indicate the levels they achieved in the dimensions listed by Burchardt and Vizard and the trends they envision concerning these dimensions (see Appendix 2, Figures a.2.1-3). For data gathering we employed some of the methods described in detail in the PAHRCA-toolkit: both the individual snake concerning the last ten years in their lives and the collective snake concerning economic, social and political developments in Salzburg, Austria and Europe during the last ten years. Further, we used biographical story telling – a method introduced to us by Dressel and Novy (2009). The crucial point about story telling is that the stories have to be respected and cannot be judged as true or false. The focus is on life-histories rather than discussions and debate and the participants tell whatever they want to tell the others (voluntariness). A core group of three participants engaged in story telling as response to the prompts by the facilitator, the other members of the group listened and commented afterwards on the biographies. The story telling was also the main exercise for data-gathering for the biographies. Besides volunteering for this exercise, the stories for the biographies were chosen on the ground of having more problems in common with other participants of the group than the third one. Partly, the conversation following the biographical story telling was a first step in identifying matters of main concerns for the group (step 6). Further, the resulting findings have been discussed with the group in a meeting in February 2016.

Additionally to the meetings with the group we formed a steering committee for benefitting as well from the knowledge of practitioners in the field of unemployment of older people in Austria (see Figure 2.2 on merging of knowledge above). The steering committee met twice (in November 2015 and end of January 2016) to discuss the process and the first findings of RE-InVEST in Salzburg. The steering committee is composed of two participants, the founder of 'Bündnis Arbeit für Best Ager' (Alliance for Jobs for Best Agers), social workers of 'Frau & Arbeit' (woman & work) and 'Kirche und Arbeitswelt' (church & labour life) as well as the two researchers.

3. Two selected biographies²

3.1 First biography³

Our life has been practically devastated. The firm gone, house gone, livelihood gone, son has given up school and I have started from scratch.

K.'s life as she had known it, has fallen to pieces in the last few years. In 2006 she was still looking optimistically into the future: She had been married for 20 years, lived with her husband and her then 14 year-old son in a large house in an attractive district of Salzburg and worked in her husband's consulting firm— even if it gave her little pleasure:

'The usual: a job for housewives, part-time as an office worker, doing simple tasks mostly – but it worked and the firm was halfway successful.'

She had no financial worries although self-employment in the consultancy business was challenging. Her son went to a good school and they assumed he would go on to university after completing school as his parents had done. She could not imagine that her life could change so radically.

In 2005 order books in the consultancy-business were beginning to decline:

'There was an insane hype about things! Every other Tom, Dick or Harry had or needed some kind of consultancy and there was good money to be had in the business; and then when the crisis started, you realise: aha, the deals are drying up, firms can no longer really afford these expensive consulting services. And I discovered that our own firm was going downhill continuously.'

Looking back, K. nevertheless is convinced that they could have made it. However, her husband could not cope with the aggravating situation and in 2007 began to build a second family and domestic home in Germany with another woman about whom K. and her son were ignorant. In 2009/2010 they separated and fought a terrible divorce war. Her husband moved in with his new partner in Germany and declared the firm bankrupt. *'That was the moment my struggle for survival started and it has not ended yet.'*

K.'s son was in his adolescence and fell into a deep crisis after his parents' separation and his father's breaking off contact. He started playing truant and held K partly responsible for the break-up of the family.

A year later they had to sell the joint house when her husband stopped paying alimony. The house was heavily mortgaged so that after the sale, only a few ten thousand Euros remained at her disposal for subsistence. The money did not last long.

'In good times the bank had showered us with their money, 3 parallel credits, easily repayable, and then the business stops flourishing and you are on your own.'

She was faced with economic ruin, having lost her house, her job at her husband's firm and the alimony at one fell swoop and had to continue covering the fees for her son's private school. Between 2010 and 2012 she had to move house four times, one smaller and cheaper than the other. When all the savings had been eaten up, she had to ask for help from the county's school administrator (Landesschulrat) to cover her son's tuition fees.

2 Many thanks to the participants for agreeing to tell their story! Both participants have carefully read the English version of their respective biography and kindly agreed to publish it as part of this report.

3 Many thanks to Jeremy Leaman for brushing up the English translation of the biography!

'I had never thought that I would be unable to pay the school fees for my child. It was inconceivable that that would ever become an issue.'

Additionally she had to apply for social welfare benefits for cover her living costs.

'In 2012 I applied for social welfare benefits for the first time in my life and it was only then I knew where I stood. It really was a black hole in its purest form. (...) Only low-life have to apply for social welfare benefits! I come from an academic background, I'd been to university and so on. Does this help me? Not in the least!'

The situation in the labour market has tightened during this time, in particular for older job seekers/wage earners. K. had just turned 50 and was eking out a living by taking on occasional jobs and seasonal work in gastronomy. To cut costs and avoid social insurance contributions, her husband had employed her only a few hours of work (in a so-called mini-job)⁴. She thus has insufficient social security credit in terms of gross contributions and qualification period. This is now creating difficulties:

'I took on any occasional job I could get. And, well, where is that possible? In gastronomy. Because I had just turned 50. I was too old for most of the other jobs. And for most employers. (...) and so I took anything that was going in restaurant business. But these are mostly temporary jobs. Seasonal work and so on. And that's the way it's been all along.'

It costs K. quite an effort to work as a seasonal waitress in a location where her former neighbours from the smart districts of Salzburg spend their leisure time: *'That was a test of courage for me.'*

Her circle of friends provided little support since most of them had not reacted well to her changed circumstances:

'... and even then you have to be careful what you say! People seem shocked if you tell the truth about being devastated and are almost forced to sleep rough (under the bridge) – this is shocking for them!'

As a consequence of all these changes, K. lost her frame of reference. She felt put down as a woman 'not fit for life', someone who might well end up sleeping rough or in the loony bin.

'My whole social network – with the exception of my family – has changed completely. There is no one left from my former circle of friends.'

Her identity and self-respect were completely shattered. Between 2011 and 2013 she suffered from a massive bout of depression. She had to undergo psychotherapy and consequently had frequent breaks from work due to illness. At the same time she tried to keep the period of days off work as short as possible. Starting in 2012 she worked for her brother as an office worker for one year, in order *'to do anything and have the right to live; in particular in the eyes of the institutions.'* However, for financial reasons her brother had to relocate his firm to a rural area, so that she lost that job too.

In 2012 and 2013 she hit rock bottom. At that time two of K's best friends died. At the suggestion of her brother she was committed to a psychiatric clinic and had to stay there for six weeks. She saw this as a terrible loss of autonomy due to the therapy being forced upon her. She does not want this to happen again and has sworn to herself to do everything to avoid it. She also felt that not even the psychiatrists and doctors in the clinic took her seriously.

K.'s son left secondary school without any qualifications in 2014 and enrolled in the army (Bundesheer).

'My son has dropped out of school and enrolled in the army for the next couple of years. This way he earns money at least. (...) He would have liked to study, of course. Even if he was no good at school, he could have managed his Matura (school-leaving certificate post-18 tr.). But under these conditions I can't even finance his studies anyway. (laughing) Goodbye, school. So turning his back on school was that much easier.'

⁴ Mini-jobs are excluded from social security; no contribution is necessary, but this means that the time does not contribute to the qualifying period for retirement payments as well.

Currently he is on duty at the Austrian border where thousands of refugees arrive every day. K. is worried about her son since he is barely twenty. The way she sees it, he has had insufficient training for this operation, especially since it is psychologically demanding.

The consequences of her problems for her son have placed a particular strain on her: *'You reproach yourself for not being competent as a mother. You don't expect something like this.'* Her parents are also concerned about K's situation and that of her son. Meanwhile K. has to look after her parents since both are in need of care, particularly her mother who suffers from progressive dementia. K. has made use of caregiver-leave several times during the last few years and will apply for another period shortly. Although she is happy to provide care for her parents, the absence of social recognition for care duties is stressful for her.

K. sees interaction with public institutions as largely unpleasant and not really helpful.

'(...) you will not be empowered by dealing with these institutions in my experience. There may be others who have fared better, but in my case, these encounters have always been like another kick in the shins.'

Her psychological problems have not been taken into account by the public job agency but rather dismissed by the simple proposal not to work full time.

'They are very insensitive, they are not bothered if you are suffering from severe psychological stress or not. I got no end of medical certificates from my doctor stating that she had been suffering from the rarest forms of depression, but the staff at the employment agency are just not bothered.'

She felt abandoned and assumes that the staff at the public job agency were as overwhelmed by her situation as she was since so many areas of concern – material survival, employment, health, family – had to be dealt with simultaneously.

'They send you round and round in circles, nobody is responsible for your case, you have to seek your own way in the end and stick at it with all public authorities. And you yourself need to carve out the deal which suits you best personally'

Looking back, she sees the economic crisis as a gradual process during which all certainties have begun to totter and her 'ideal world' has crumbled bit by bit:

'(...) politically, economically, from things that happened a long way away from me to my very own private problems. Naively, I never would have thought any of this possible. Everything that has rolled our way recently. That is both at the personal level and like the whole EU-crisis, the economy, the refugee issues. Never, ever would I have thought that my child would be keeping guard at the border calming down refugees.'

What has helped her to be up and about again, was a timeout of one month which she spent in India in 2014. She has old friends there who support her by reassuring her. Back in Salzburg she met P. an old school mate and became involved in the NGO 'Alliance for Jobs for Bestagers' (Bündnis Arbeit für Best-Ager, BABA). Together with the other members of this group she aims to improve the opportunities for older unemployed people and to develop ideas and strategies to this end. Not until then did she realise that she is not the only one in such a situation. This insight has helped her overcome the shame of her situation and restore her courage.

Her depression has not receded completely since she continues to be concerned about her material well-being on a monthly basis. However, currently things are brightening up for her.

3.2 Second biography⁵

'In 2008 the Lehman Brothers Collapse happened, and since then it's been going downhill.'

⁵ Many thanks to Anna Ramsebener for her excellent translation of the biography!

For 18 years, L. was employed in an international, mainly family-owned company in the cosmetics sector. As head of the outsourced division for telephone-marketing in two countries she had a well-paid and challenging position. After being a single mother for a couple of years, she met her current partner and gave birth to another child in 2007.

Starting at the end of the 1990s, the company lowered costs by outsourcing various departments in order to avoid closing branch offices in Austria. It was the company's general policy to close non-profitable branches.

The economic crisis hit her company from 2008 on: they lost customers and the sales declined due to shrinking demand. L. thinks the reason for losing customers is because cosmetics are considered as kind of 'luxury products', which people tend to save on first, moving from the company's medium price brand to low price brands.

As a consequence, the company followed an even stricter policy of lowering costs which lead to a noticeable deterioration of working conditions. For example, overtime during business trips was not compensated anymore and the standard of hotel accommodations was lowered. The annual objectives in terms of sales and contribution to profit that determined the variable part of her salary were set at unfeasible high levels. From 2007 onwards the variable part of her salary was not adjusted anymore, just the part complying with the collective agreement increased slightly. As a result, the overall increase of L.'s salary has been way below the inflation rate.

'If you had 60 hours overtime from business trips, they were not compensated anymore: it drains you of course.'

While in other departments sales and profit have been shrinking since 2008, L's department could still increase its profits until 2011. L. says that the crisis subtly crept into her team, because at first they were merely affected by the company's policy of lowering costs without having a breakdown in sales. Even in 2011 to 2013 when the sales were stagnating, they still managed to increase contribution to profits. Not until 2014 did the crisis hit her department, leading to a breakdown.

'In 2009 we increased our sales and then we still increased our contribution to profits by making brutal cost cuts - so in my department we increased profit despite decreasing sales. I say that the cost cuts were brutal because I was responsible for the external call-centre: I've been overseeing them for over 15 years, I knew all the employees and I knew that we had not increased their salaries for 15 years. In the end those employees who did not receive any pay raise in 15 years got nothing but more and more pressure.'

The sales call centre under her responsibility had already been outsourced to external service providers in 2001. Most of the call centre workers were employed as freelance employees, with the consequence that labour law and collective contracts did not apply to them. Consequently, it was possible to never raise their pay. The costs cuts lead to a steady increase of pressure to lower costs and work more. At the top management level so-called 'crisis managers' had the job to reduce the number of employees and raise the objectives in operational planning at the same time. This decreased the conditions for economic success and quality of working conditions further.

'(...) all this pressure without budget! I mean without any money you can't do much! It is like squeezing a lemon further and further. (...) I also earned less in the course of time due to the variable part of my salary. Not motivating at all: You have to work more and more every year, travel more, hassling and bustling, with more and more pressure (...).'

As an executive officer, L. was in a difficult position since she had not only to deal with the pressure herself but also put it on the call centre workers by raising the performance requirements and lowering costs at their expenses. Measures ranged from reducing trainings and further outsourcing to layoffs.

'There was even the idea to do the calls from the Ukraine or from Poland - the situation got more and more outrageous!'

Yet L. had to implement the policy she despised on her own team. However, she still tried to find a balanced solution for layoffs in contrast to the dominant practice in the company:

My last line manager was proud of firing colleagues ‘cost-effectively’ by instant dismissals. (...) Stabbing others in the back for saving 10,000 Euro at their expense – I couldn’t cope with this mentality in the company.’

This mentality is best caught in the following memory:

‘Did they get a bunch of flowers?’ was the internal jargon for layoffs because a well-recognised and dedicated senior executive got his instant dismissal shortly after the celebration of his 25 year anniversary in the company (with flowers).’

L. did not dare to resign since the situation on the labour market had deteriorated in the meantime.

I could have resigned any time over the years, yes that is true. But the situation on the labour market held me back. What actually kept me in this unhealthy position was the precarious situation on the labour market.’

Therefore, she continued working until she had developed a burnout at the end of 2014. After being on sick leave for eight weeks, L. was dismissed without notice – after 18 years of working for the company. A small error served as pretext for justifying the dismissal. However, the error had occurred six months earlier and caused only minor damage to the company. L. felt that this way of dealing with her was like a slap in the face. However, in retrospect L. is glad to have escaped the treadmill.

I really got pushed into it. Of course for me, 2015 was an utterly miserable year, but in the end I got out well. Sooner or later I would have had to do it anyway, to get out of there before I lost my mind.’

In the beginning, her state of health was very poor: L. was in a serious psychological crisis.

If you had seen me half a year ago ... my nerves were at breaking point. Half a year ago I would not have been able to apply for a new job. I could not have done it. I had exceeded the limit. This was the end. I didn’t want to do anything anymore. There was this big hole.’

L. got a lot of support and encouragement from a doctor, who focused on her individual situation, took time for her and brought her attention to an ambulant group therapy for burnout patients. L. went to group therapy sessions for six weeks and gained strength again from the structured activities, psychological aid and support from other patients.

*I had a great doctor who supported me all the time. I saw her every three weeks (...), she was my tower of strength, this doctor. However, she was a *Wahlärztin* [in Austria: a doctor you can choose, who has no contract with the national health insurance] I think this contributed to the fact that she could take so much time for me.’*

She tried to avoid getting in contact with public institutions like the job centre and health insurance institute as much as possible after having experienced bad situations:

*‘She [her doctor] kind of sheltered me from the national health insurance [in Austria: *Gebietskrankenkasse*]. I mean, I could not get out of going to my appointments there. They do have sympathetic doctors, who are nice and give you advice, but then there are others (...), one brought me to tears twice.’*

L. also heard a lot of bad experiences concerning the job centre (German acronym: PES) from group therapy colleagues: *‘Patients lost their job, went to the PES, and the PES finished them off.’*

Thanks to her partner who was still employed, L’s layoff did not lead to drastic financial problems. However, her sick pay (60% of her prior pay) was not enough to keep up with her expenses. Consequently, she cancelled additional insurances and reduced her consumption expenditures. She used her savings to maintain the financial support for her daughter’s studies.

I also have a grown up daughter who goes to university. I always supported her financially, also at that time [the time of being unemployed], using my savings. That was also important for the quality of my life, for me as a mother. I mean, I brought my child so far, and then saying – so shortly before the end – no, I cannot pay you aliments anymore: this hurts. But nobody understands this. Everybody says that the girl is 23, she can work herself. Why do you finance her? I have to say: She is a working student, yes. But giving this support is important to me.’

L was very concerned with keeping the consequences of her unemployment away from her children:

'Often, this is the most crucial point: making life easy for your children. You reduce yourself automatically.'

Aside from her occupational situation, the European Economic Crisis also had serious repercussions on another aspect of L's life. Due to the steady increase of prices for properties in Salzburg since 2009, L. and her husband have not yet been able to buy their own flat, as they had planned.

'Today I am still in a flat in which I don't want to live any longer. But it wasn't possible to find something adequate.'

L. experienced the rapid increase of prices for properties herself: A flat which she and her family nearly bought was more than 60% more expensive after three years:

'In 2008 we signed a contract for a flat, a new building for 340.000€. But then I got cold feet. I mean, we did have equity, but we would have had 200.000€ debts, so I wanted to get rid of the flat. Three years later it was bought for 550.000€, the same flat, sold by the person to whom we sold it. From 340.000 to 550.000, that's insane. 340.000 was already such a huge amount for me.'

Around 10 years ago, L. could have never foreseen the Economic Crisis with its impacts on her life:

'In 2007 I gave birth to my second child – at this time I could have never thought that this all would happen. In 2008 the Lehman Brothers Collapse happened, and since then it's been going downhill. I mean I never thought that I would stay forever at [her old work place]. I already used to be stressed back then. [But] I thought I could always easily get a new job, a better job. So I never thought that life would go this way.'

The most formative experience from this time was the ongoing loss of security and assurance on which L has relied until then:

'I had the feeling that I was treading on very thin ice. As long as you've got a job, you've got everything. Everything's fine. But as soon as this falls away, you crack. This is terrible. Unless you have reserves, have inherited something – then it is fine too. But building up reserves has also gotten more and more difficult. I mean, when I look at my parents' life and compare it to mine ... they could buy a flat from scratch. This is something which my generation cannot do.'

Before L. was unemployed, many political and social problems barely caught her attention. Now, after having experienced it herself, she is aware of all these topics. L. sees the long-term effects of the Economic Crisis as quite negative, as now everyone is more self-responsible and there is less security. Also because of her age (L. is 44 years old) she cannot imagine herself physically enduring this intense (working) conditions:

'I couldn't have expected it [the crisis and consequently being unemployed]. Had it happened earlier - when I was younger - then I would have made provisions. When I was younger, and full of beans, I guess I would have tried extra hard to save more money.'

By now, her state of health has improved a lot. In order to prevent a relapse, she still regularly attends a burnout group. In spite of still increasing unemployment figures she found a job: since the beginning of 2016, she has been working for a governmental institution. She considers the working conditions (range of duties, volume of work, working hours and atmosphere in her team) to be very good. The only pitfall is her pay: in her new position she earns markedly less than in her previous job.

4. Analysis

As explained in Section 2 the findings have been discussed with participants at the fourth meeting. The discussion was organised in two parts: the first part was dedicated to discussing the impact of the crisis on the labour market in Austria, the second part focused on unemployment, search for employment and their social impact. The analysis follows the structure of this discussion and the participants' presentation of the problems. In view of the working assumptions of this research (see introduction) and its theoretical framework, it is geared towards answering the questions if and how the crisis has lowered the trust of citizens into institutions further and has led to further erosion of human rights and social disinvestment.

4.1 Which crisis?

As explained in Section 1 on the national context, Austria has not been hit as hard as other European countries by the financial crisis in 2007 and 2008. In consequence, 2008 has not been imprinted as the year of the crisis on people's memories. They rather experienced it as part of an ongoing process that started much earlier. While researchers determine the beginning of this process with the first austerity measures in 1987 (Hermann & Flecker 2015) participants refer to economic problems in the 1990ies. Austria's accession of the European Union has both mitigated some of the problems as well as created new pressures of adjusting to European standards. Participants further reflected on the dot-com collapse at the turn of the century and distinguish various more temporary crises such as the housing crisis, the banking crisis and bank bailouts, public debt crisis, the Greek crisis and the recent refugee-crisis. Despite this general perception of the financial crisis as only a step in an ongoing process, it is possible to trace the impact of the financial crisis on the course of life of participants.

For example, K. (Section 3.1) worked in a consultancy firm of her husband and links the bankruptcy of the firm to the decline of orders in the aftermaths of the crisis. Similarly, L. (Section 3.2) worked in one of the sectors hit directly by the financial crisis. She describes how the decline in orders for cosmetics has increased the pressure within the firm. Furthermore, two other participants have worked for temporary employment agencies. Temporary agency work has also been affected by the crisis: H. and M. have both been trained in mechanical art. Prior to the crisis temporary agency work was attractive insofar as it was well paid in order to account for the necessary flexibility. After 2008, however, the conditions worsened and wages decreased. For H. temporary agency work has been part of a downward spiral in employment. The first firm moved abroad so that he lost employment. In 2005 he found a new permanent position as a toolmaker matching his qualification, but this firm, too, went bankrupt. In this situation he found temporary agency work an attractive alternative: *'They did pay well because that was my profession even if it was less than I had before ...'* However, due to unclear arrangements between the temporary employment agency and the firms where he actually worked, there were gaps in employment:

'Once I started to work on Monday and on Tuesday my boss said he would not need me from the next day onwards ... In temporary agency work this means you are kicked out and need to register anew at the PES. ... Then the PES-clerk asked me: Why have you been laid off so soon?'

H. has never received a real note of dismissal since he has never been employed more than a year by a temporary employment agency. In 2011 he worked for a year in security business. Since 2012 he has worked as a temporary agency worker for several firms but never permanently. Recently he has taken up marginal employment in the security sector – and would appreciate the opportunity to do this full time.

Further effects of the crisis on the labour market as described on a general level in Section 1 appear on the individual level in the life stories of participants as well. Participants summarise the impact as follows: *'(Labour) life has come apart at the seams, but nobody strikes back!'*

In more detail L. notes that from 2002 to 2012 salaries have increased only in the fixed fraction resulting from collective bargaining. Before the variable fraction reflecting individual performance had been adjusted, too, and bonuses paid. Without any increase in the individual fraction of the salary real wages have stagnated. At the same time Z. and L. witnessed an increase in pressure concerning working time: employees have been laid off while the pressure on the others increased to work overtime without being paid. From the year 2000 onwards so-called 'all-inclusive contracts' have come into use that comprise a passage stating that there is no compensation for overtime work – neither in terms of leisure nor monetary payments.

Being in charge for call centres L. has seen how her company has shifted the risk to employees: After outsourcing the service to independently working call centres the employees were not offered permanent positions but forced to work as freelancers. The contracts with these freelancers do not foresee full social security benefits and rather cover only insurance for health, retirement payments and vacancy. Freelancers are not entitled to vacancy or unemployment benefits. The contracts follow the idea that freelancers are self-employed and hence have to take care of social security themselves even though the payments do not allow doing so. The effect is growing precarity (Kraemer 2009) and is the background of the struggle of social partners about flexibility and distribution of work among employees described in Section 1.1.

These developments on the labour market have been enhanced by the crisis. Although Hermann and Flecker (2015) claim that the financial crisis has quickly turned into a labour market crisis, the increase in unemployment has risen substantially since 2013. *'The fight for employment becomes harder. Applicants sell their labour below value and accept any wage.'* Participants thus agree in their analysis with the sociologist Burzan (2009) who states that unemployment has reached the mid of society.

Thinking about the effects of the current refugee crisis on the labour market, participants see both positive and negative effects: On the one hand refugees will eventually also search for jobs and increase competition on the labour market. On the other hand crisis demands an immediate response that creates a lot of jobs in the construction trade, in social work, teaching and training both in the public and private sector.

The financial crisis has had effects beyond the labour market as well. In particular, the rise in housing prices in Salzburg has gained momentum since 2008. Some of the participants have been affected either because they wanted to buy a flat - and refrained from doing so due to the prices (see Section 3.2) - or because they have been forced to move into cheaper housing in order to make ends meet (see Section 3.1).

'In this affluent city so many people live on the breadline for various reasons. It happens fast and there are so many ways of slipping off.'

Poverty has not increased in Austria after the crisis as displayed in statistics (Section 1.1), but at least in Salzburg poverty has become more visible in the course of the last 10 years with increasing numbers of beggars (Dines et al. 2015) and the flow of refugees that reached its preliminary peak in autumn 2015. The participants report that they have become more sensitive to social problems and their interest in politics has increased since they have become affected themselves. They are afraid of the future and fear for their pensions. Yet, they also care for the younger generation and are worried about their future without much prospects.

In sum, the financial crisis is perceived as part of an ongoing deterioration of conditions of life in general and a rise of competition on the labour market in particular. Individual capabilities are decreased in the course of this process.

4.2 Searching for employment

All participants of the group in Salzburg are aged 45 to 60 and have lost their jobs and are now looking for new employment. Hence, this experience is crucial for them and they have a lot to tell about their encounters with the Public Employment Service (PES) as well as about changes in the labour market.

PES is the most important public agency for unemployed people in Austria. It has a twofold function: On the one hand it is a public administrative body that implements the regulation concerning unemployment benefits. On the other hand it is meant to help unemployed to find a job similarly to an employment agency. The participants have mixed feelings about PES. H. characterises his experience: *'Treatment quality varies a great deal! If you behave well they let you alone. If not, they bully you.'* Some participants have received good advice, for instance G. got support in dealing with her health problems. Some characterise the PES clerks as competent and committed to their work who give valuable advice and sometimes have resigned themselves: *'I don't have a single job! Neither for younger nor for older persons.'* However, the participants also report about frequent changes of the person in charge. Thus they are forced to tell their story of life once and again. Sometimes the clerks are much younger than they are and do not know many rules. Hence, they all have been in the situation that instead of receiving advice they had to teach their advisors about e.g. care leave and wage/benefit protection for older unemployed⁶. Often participants had to ask specific questions in order to get the information they wanted. It is not clear if this disinformation is a political strategy of PES in order to stay within the budget or whether it is a genuine lack of knowledge of the particular clerks. In contrast the consequence of the varying quality in service is obvious: lacking or confusing information undermines legal security and violates the right to good governance of the European Charta of Rights.

The participants further would like to have a say in interaction with PES. For example, the unemployed have to sign a 'support agreement' ('Betreuungsplan') by PES. It is called an 'agreement' even though in fact, in many instances the PES-clerks unilaterally define the measures. The clerks tell their clients to sign the proposition else they would stop being entitled to benefits – although this is not true in the judicial sense. Information on the rights and duties of jobseekers vis-à-vis PES is not clearly - and sometimes even not accurately - communicated. By the same token the measures are often defined by the clerks without any explicit reasoning unless the clients vigorously demand to know why these measures are taken.

There is not much opportunity for giving substantive feedback with regard to the service quality of PES since quality management is done by help of questionnaires that do not offer the opportunity to insert comments and targeted feedback in a safe way.

All in all participants have got the feeling that they do not have a right to unemployment benefits but rather have to ask for charitable donations. This is humiliating insofar as they have contributed to social security. Furthermore, they see various practices of PES as a form of harassment such as e.g. having no choice concerning the numbers of hours of work. They are urged to apply for full-time positions and to skip all other activities they started during their unemployment if necessary. These **activities are an important part of their coping strategy**. Activities provide a pattern for the days and facilitate returning to the schedule of a working day (Jahoda, Lazarsfeld & Zeisel 2014; Bednarek-Gilland 2015). Yet, PES sees the wish to work part time and do further training as balking their placement service. Unemployed also have to notify PES in case of travelling across the border: They are not entitled to benefits for the days they spend abroad even though this is a frequent practice in Salzburg that is situated at the border to Germany. Hence, participants criticise the policies of PES as 'activation at all costs'. They argue for more focused approaches that provide individual support.

However, individual support is one of the big problems in Austrian social security assistance. The problem has been addressed in the literature (Fink 2015a) and by participants. For instance, there is no real one-stop shop (Fink 2015a: 11) as is illustrated by the case of K. (Section 3.1): She needed to see various agencies about her various problems – collecting the Guaranteed Minimum Income ('Mindestsicherung'), demanding the alimonies from her former husband, asking for help for the tuition fees for her son, finding smaller and cheaper accommodation, searching employment, applying for care allowances for her parents and elder care leave ... She did not receive any advice what to do first or how to coordinate the various needs. As Fink (2015a: 11) states the 'co-operation between the PES-offices and the welfare offices may at best be termed

⁶ Unemployment benefits are calculated in relation to the wage of their last job. In case of older unemployed this rule does not apply if the job they took up after a spell of unemployment is paid worse than the one before. In that case the same amount of benefits is paid as during this first spell of unemployment.

semi-formalised' so that K. had to visit both agencies and tell her story. Other participants point to the positive example of the old-age pension insurance agency ('Pensionsversicherungsanstalt' PVA) that offers case-management with an individual care scheme.

Many participants report positive experience with regard to health promotion: During her burnout L. (Section 3.2) was saved from seeing PES about her unemployment by her doctor. G. got good advice from the rehabilitation department of PES concerning her combined health and employment problems. A doctor pointed B. to the program 'fit2work' that is financed by various agencies - the pension insurance agency among others - and aims to counter health problems early on in order to maintain the employability of workers. B. had suffered a herniated disc in his back and was thus unable to continue working in his former job. 'fit2work' analysed his skills and interests and financed vocational training for B. However, some of the tests and analyses done for 'fit2work' had to be repeated for PES since they did not accept the results from the program at the beginning (spring 2013). In the meantime PES supports 'fit2work' and recommended it recently to another participant (who struggles with other difficulties, however).

PES also finances further training but the participants remain rather sceptical against their policies in this regard: Currently these policies undergo change due to the raising pressure by rising unemployment. Participants have the impression that PES now has a more targeted approach. PES does not urge their clients to do useless courses as has been the case before (see (orf.at 2015) on the new strategies of PES). Yet, participants have many stories to tell about their aspirations for further training and PES policies: They call standardised training courses 'useless' since clients are enrolled regardless of their previous knowledge about software or application procedures (Fink 2015a; Lechner & Wetzel 2015; Riesenfelder & Wetzel 2009). H. asked for more specialised training with regard to a specific software program used in inventory management, but did not get it although a firm promised to hire him afterwards. *'In PES I need years to get a training course!'*

Participants also report about age discrimination with regard to further training: 'This will only balk you!' a clerk said to one participant implicitly hinting at his conviction that the training would be in vain. Another participant was told to wait for two or three years. After such a long time of unemployment PES might be willing to finance further training for her. Unemployed are only given limited say in choosing training courses (Riesenfelder & Wetzel 2009). It remains to be seen whether the new strategy of PES concerning training courses has induced lasting changes.

In line with these experiences of the participants the Austrian ombudsman ('Volksanwaltschaft') for fundamental human rights registered an increase of 70% in complaints concerning PES in 2014 comparing to the preceding year. Hence, the low quality of PES service is acknowledged as a **violation of the rights to good administration and to an effective remedy and to a fair trial** as guaranteed by the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (Arts. 41, 47). Complaints mainly concerned the legitimacy of being assigned to training courses, the quality of measures and the competence of PES clerks (derStandard.at 2015). This increase in complaints happened in line with rising unemployment and hence can be seen as a consequence of the crisis.

While it is difficult to receive funding for training courses by PES, there is little recognition for further training by potential employers (Lechner and Wetzel 2015): Participants are assessed on the basis of their first professional training even though they graduated long ago (ca. 30 years). Professional re-orientation is difficult under these conditions. Even after completing a second vocational training, B. had trouble to find a position because of his age in combination with lacking experience in this branch of work. He had to work as an (unpaid) intern first in order to gain professional experience. Practitioners in the field know that his experience is by no means exceptional. Nowadays it is even difficult to find an internship so that professional re-orientation is almost impossible. Furthermore, working as an intern and receiving benefits is only possible if the internship is part of the professional training financed by PES – as had been the case with B.

'Privately owned job agencies do not know it better!' is the conclusion of a participant concerning private firms that compete with PES. For instance, the profile of the job seeker in their system is often inaccurate and incomplete. They forward only a short summary instead of the full application file to potential employers so that the job offers the clients receive do not match their profile.

In general participants have the impression that work life has changed a lot in the course of their career. While at the beginning of the 1990ies new employees were granted a long period of vocational adjustment (up to two years), employers now expect that new employees - temporary agency workers in particular - know what to do right from the beginning. This expectation exerts a lot of pressure on newcomers so that they make mistakes. It is an erroneous strategy to save time or money in this way. Saving time is the aim of rules for clocking in and out as well: There was no need to clock out for celebrating birthdays of co-workers or small coffee breaks in the past. Nowadays employees have to clock out at these occasions so that there is no informal exchange at the coffee table any more. In contrast to that one participant reports from her new job in the public administration that the old practices prevail: *'It is as it was in my old company 20 years ago!'*

A general trend participants see is that firms reify people and replace them as if they were mere tools. In this context the latest policy measure - a subsidy for employing older workers - has the effect of a subsidy for companies rather than for workers. Participants presume that companies will behave as free-riders: employing the older workers only for the time they receive the subsidy. Contrary to this presumption of the majority, one participant is confident that PES has to keep an eye to the budget and will grant the subsidy only to those firms they trust to behave in line with the objectives of the policy measure.

For better qualified jobs participants have observed delays in refilling vacant positions in order to comply with the strategy of cutting down the number of positions. Hence, unemployed need more time for the application procedures and are at risk of de-skilling at the same time. In addition, younger people are often preferred – be it that they can pay less because of their lack of professional experience, be it that companies aim at a high fluctuation and count on the inclination of younger workers to resign due to career ambitions or family building.

Despite their disadvantageous position as older job seekers, participants consider carefully what positions they are willing to accept. On the one hand they have often been caught in the treadmill long enough to have health issues. On the other hand they have started to do other work such as voluntary or care work. They have learned to appreciate this freedom and do not want to quit all these activities. Asked what they value most in life Z. wrote: *'Living my own life'* and another participant has phrased her desire for autonomy by wishing *'not to lose my dignity and visions!'*

In summary, the service of PES does not match the idea of good administration as laid down in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union. The right to an effective remedy and to a fair trial is violated insofar as the service quality varies with the person in charge. There is only minor investment in unemployed people (e.g. training courses). Furthermore, their own investment in their human capital is often undermined by active labour market policy regulations. In consequence their capabilities are diminished rather than enhanced by labour market administration.

4.3 More effects of the crisis and unemployment

4.3.1 Effects on social networks

'... the first question is not: How are you? But rather: What are you doing (for work)?' The question about professional occupation has taken centre stage in our time. Those who do not have an employment 'fall through the cracks': They have to explain and justify their status as unemployed. Friends do not know how to react if they tell them about their situation (Section 3.1). Supposedly, various factors contribute to changes in the social networks after becoming unemployed: Friends draw back because they do not know what to say or because it reminds them of their own vulnerability. They may also need to quit or change their prejudices on unemployed people if they know a particular unemployed person. The image of the 'benefits gravy train' (unemployed people do not do anything but enjoy their life at the cost of society) is hard to apply to personal acquaintances who have lost their jobs and are worn down. Anyway, the social networks of participants have changed a lot, but the friends who stayed are a major source of support.

Usually, family ties are stronger than friendships. However, the extent of support participants got from members of their families (spouses, siblings and parents) varies a great deal: Often the separation from their spouse is an aggravating factor in participants' life stories as K.'s biography illustrates. The partner of G. became estranged in the short period of a training course she did for a new job. The separation was the trigger to a deep personal crisis. B. has lost first his wife and then his father to death by cancer. He started psychotherapy in order to cope with these losses. That helped afterwards to cope with his health problems and the resulting difficulties searching for employment. Two participants relocated for living together with their partners. It is unclear whether it would have been easier to find a job in an environment they knew better. Anyway, some participants still have the same partners and have found a lot of support in them.

Some participants relate that their siblings helped in coping with their situation: K. (Section 3.1) was institutionalised by her brother for her own protection. Though she was appalled by the loss of autonomy and wants to avoid a second institutionalisation by all means, she appreciates that her brother later on gave her a job in his firm for some time. Similarly, G. had a lot of help by her brother who convinced her to get psychological treatment in a hospital and kept her from demanding too much from herself. In contrast to that, one participant has become estranged from her sister in the course of an inheritance battle after their mother died.

Parents also provide support – both mental as well as monetary – but they also need care if they get older. At least two participants have cared for their parents. In their accounts of this work they both report on the exhaustion caused by care work, the remorse if they entrust the care of their parent to someone else. Hence, it is difficult as well to take days off though taking a break is important for gathering strength for this work that may take a good while. Yet, the participants in this situation also do not want to miss a single day of this time with their parents. The relationship to their parents is good while not free from conflict. While K. had already been unemployed when her parents have become in need of care, F. needed to give up her self-employment in order to care for her parents. A first political response to the growing number of elderly in need of care is the right to elder care leave ('Pflegekarenz') introduced in January 2014. However, this has not induced much change since care work is still not recognised in society as an important and difficult kind of work. The two participants report that care work is not valued. For example it is not seen as a sufficient answer to the question noted at the beginning of this Section (*What are you doing?*). Care is not seen as taking the whole day or constituting a worthwhile contribution to society. When applying for elder care leave, participants found that PES does not know about this new regulation and firms do not accept the application.

In an interview the Austrian Minister for Education and Women Heinisch-Hosek pointed out that women still do most of the care work, not only with respect to the elderly but also concerning child care and other care work. The time women spend doing all this care work adds in the course of their life and keeps them from advancing in their jobs. As a consequence their pension entitlements are low. The biography of K. illustrates this detrimental interaction between professional and family life well.

In general, spouses, siblings and parents are expected to provide support while participants with children want to provide support for their children. It is especially distressing for them that they have to cut down their care and cannot do more due to their own difficulties. For example, for K. (Section 3.1) it is especially burdening to see that her son left school early in order to earn money instead of causing costs. Although less dramatically L. (Section 3.2) has been distressed by the prospect of having to cut down her financial support for her daughter who is studying. While she was out of work she used her reserves for this purpose. In contrast to her, O. has been a single mum in a precarious situation all the time: She did not get alimonies for her daughter, had three jobs and was self-employed as a nursery school teacher. When her daughter started studying in Germany, she was proud of her achievements but the situation has not changed much since they do not get any financial support and still have to scrape money together to make ends meet. M. reports that his daughter has successfully applied for a grant at a private school. He is very proud of her initiative that convinced the schoolboard to give her the grant. Yet, he is also conscious about his own inability to grant her such opportunities. Even though it is not a real failure in provision for their children, participants with children are sorry for being constraint in supporting them.

4.3.2 Effects on society

The effects of unemployment on social networks described above are part of a broader **loss of social recognition**. The response of friends and acquaintances are in line with social climate: Unemployment is not seen as a failure of politics, the economy and society on the whole but rather as individual incompetency. Z. characterises unemployment as *'living in stand-by mode'*. This mode takes its toll in terms of vigour and spirit. Autonomy and freedom of choice – the capability of people – is heavily constrained by the demand of being available for the labour market full time. In contrast to the German regulation (Hartz IV) unemployed people in Austria are not entitled to benefits if they leave the country. Austrian regulation demands to notify PES of being abroad each time and register again afterwards because benefits are not paid during this time (if both is done on the same day, at least they do not lose any benefits). Participants see this regulation as especially constraining their freedom of movement since in Salzburg people often go across the border to visit friends and family in Germany or for benefiting from the lower prices for some goods. Hence it is a **violation of the right to liberty and security** (European Union 2000, para. 6; Council of Europe 2010, para. 5) as well as **the respect for private and family life** (European Union 2000, para. 7; Council of Europe 2010, para. 8).

These constraints on autonomy, capability and rights lower the self-respect of the unemployed. They feel unfairly pressured to justify their wishes and practices. Further, they are sometimes ashamed for their situation - as K. has described so tellingly - when they meet old acquaintances and neighbours or when they become aware of their limited abilities to support their children. They cannot live a life they value and do not meet their own standards. But since society pictures their unemployment and the resulting constraints as individual failures, they have internalised this view - this blaming-the-victim culture- and have difficulties to point to the structural reasons for their situation. Thus, participants emphasise the importance of raising the public awareness of the lack of social recognition for unemployed persons and initiating a public debate on the individualisation of public risks. Their aim is to reveal the offending nature of this individualisation of risks and to place the responsibility for high unemployment back on politicians, the economy and society.

Participants further highlight that there are two sides of the coin as Z. says:

'I regard it as anti-social behaviour if someone regularly works 60 hours a week - working 20 hours unpaid overtime – because this keeps others from getting employed!' The downside of the high esteem for work and labour in the contemporary world is the increasing competition for the scarce "good" of employment.

4.3.3 Effects on the political climate

Some participants have always been interested in politics and social problems, but others report that becoming unemployed has raised their sensitivity in this regard (see Section 3). Yet, they think that apart from their increased awareness some real changes have happened: the growing visibility of poverty in Salzburg, growing inequality between rich and poor or employed and unemployed as well as the inflow of refugees that has reached a preliminary peak in 2015. L. asks: *'How can beggars from Rumania think of themselves as European citizens if they are treated worse than asylum seekers?'*

The drawing exercise in the first workshop has shown that participants distrust politicians and the political system. Participants have portrayed politics as a slimy wall and the political institutions as separated from the population (Figure 4.1). They view politics as a circus that exhibits vulnerable people in its ring (Figure 4.2) and are worried that politics engulfs society in the abyss. B. voices his opinion that some reforms are overdue (privileges of retired persons and senior civil servants ...). He thinks politicians have known since the 1990ies that they have to do something about it. Now payday has arrived ...

M. thinks that politicians do not know what to do about unemployment. In general participants regard social policy as not social at all. For example, instead of lifting minimum wage when the gap between minimum wage and guaranteed minimum income diminishes, politicians have lowered minimum income. At the same time they spent money on bailouts for banks. Participants are further offended by some pejorative remarks of politicians about unemployed people. Some yearns for politicians of the old school such as

Kreisky, Kirchschrager, Klima, and Pühringer. Participants find it difficult to respect politicians today. They do not do enough, need too much time or do the wrong things.

Figure 4.1 Drawing on the relationship to the government I

Figure 4.2 Drawing on the relationship to the government II

Participants concede that this impression may be partly caused by media. Newspapers and TV journals tend to give centre stage to bad news and convey the impression that the world changes to the worse. Further, participants think that media shifts attention from interior to exterior matters as for example in the refugee crisis. Thus they have played down internal Austrian matters such as growing unemployment.

Finally, participants have observed that age is seen as a positive characteristic in case of the candidates for presidency in Austria while it is seen as a negative characteristic in applications of normal workers. Four of the five candidates currently running for election as president are retired. They present their age as an indicator of their experience, independency and wisdom. No one raises doubts about this or makes the usual point that older people are less productive and not able to adjust to new circumstances.

4.3.4 Effects on health care arrangements

The health care system in Austria is characterised by making a sharp distinction between public health service patients and those who have a private health insurance (additionally or only). Public health service patients have to accept long waiting periods and do not receive all relevant information as the example of B. shows: He had to wait two months for magnetic resonance imaging since the number of examinations allotted to public health service patients was already exhausted. The doctor did not tell him about the opportunity of paying himself and getting an appointment immediately. He would have done so in order to receive the results as early as possible.

Unemployed persons often have to withdraw from their private health insurance contracts in order to save money. As a consequence they can only turn to a doctor under contract with the public health service. Their freedom of choice with regard to medical treatment is thus constraint.

In summary social networks are shrinking as a consequence of unemployment, but worse than that is the loss of social recognition and public opinion towards unemployed people. The widespread view that unemployed get on the benefits gravy train, are lazy and do not contribute to society in any important way hurts the feelings of the unemployed and undermines their self-esteem. At the same time participants report an increased sensitivity for politics and social problems.

4.4 Support and help

Several sources of support and help have already been mentioned in the preceding Sections: Family and friends have supported participants financially, morally and practically (Section 4.3.1). Medical practitioners and psychotherapists have helped them to cope not only with the health problems but with facing the administrative hurdles as well (Section 4.2).

Participants have further described their involvement in the grass root organisation ‘Alliance for Jobs for Best Ager’ (Bündnis für Arbeit für Best Ager) as an important source of support or even ‘*as a kind of therapy*’. They discovered that they are not the only ones who have lost their jobs and have trouble to find a new one, indicating that it is not their individual failure but rather a structural problem particularly concerning older workers.

Overall participants view all opportunities for participation in society and all indicators of their social affiliation as helpful. Apart from the aforementioned social networks and health related support they also highlight the importance of membership in clubs and associations, participation in adult education classes and self-help groups. They also appreciate practical help by the ‘cultural passport’ (Kulturpass) that enables persons with low income to attend (some) cultural events free of charge.

To sum up participation in society is mainly ensured by agency, i.e. by being an active member of society. Employment constitutes one form of agency, but other activities constitute agency just as well. In conclusion it is most important to enable unemployed people becoming agents of their own well-being and countering the loss of social recognition – both on the individual as well as on the collective level.

5. Conclusion

This report aims at deepening understanding of how the financial crisis and austerity measures have impacted rights and capabilities of job seekers aged 45 or more years in Salzburg.

The qualitative, participatory research design is not suitable as a means to ‘validate’ or ‘prove’ hypotheses, but rather it provides an in-depth analysis by combining different types of knowledge in order to co-create new knowledge

The research is guided by the working assumption that the crisis and anti-crisis policies have contributed to the erosion of basic social rights and disinvestment in capabilities of individuals and groups in the EU. The research has shown that the participants of the group did **not perceive of ‘the crisis’ as a turning point** for Austria, but rather as another step in a slow process that has started already before the turn of the century. This corresponds to the findings of Fink (2015b) who explained that no large scale or structural cuts in public services and social expenditure have taken place in the wake of the crisis.

The general impression of participants is that life in Austria has become more difficult. Regarding labour market integration they hold the view that older workers face multiple challenges that are not really acknowledged. They have the feeling that neither employers nor the state is investing comprehensively in older workers and that professional reorientation or further training is not well recognised and oftentimes only accessible against considerable resistance. Even if one manages to get re-training, it is very difficult or almost impossible to enter the labour market without prior professional experience in the field. The Public Employment Service (PES) focuses more on wage subsidies for firms than on qualification for re-integrating older workers into the labour market. Two participants have found a job in the public sector during the research phase though. However, both of them state that this could not be expected but rather was a matter of good luck.

The gradual increase in retirement age in combination with a very tight labour market and highly selective Active Labour Market measures lead to poor prospects for older workers in the job market. They often find themselves locked in over a longer period of time between unemployment, (temporary and often precarious) re-integration into the labour market and the prospect of retirement.

Their labour market related capabilities are being restricted by a **lack of public investment** (in high quality qualification and training), (hidden) age-discrimination and inadequate service quality of the public employment service. As a result of their status as ‘unemployed’ the participants have to adhere to a lot of **rules and obligations that restrict their choices** with negative effects on their non-work related capabilities.

The participants stress that they are not (any longer) willing to accept any job under any conditions, as they have a lot of experience with the **adverse effects of bad working conditions on their health and wellbeing**. The participants are well aware of the risk of cuts or temporary suspension of their benefits in case they act in a way, which the PES regards as ‘impediment to employment’. PES with its double function of providing employment services and monitoring entitlements to social benefits is regarded as not helpful by most and threatening by some participants. The latter try to keep as much distance as possible by displaying a cooperative but reserved attitude and complying with formal obligations. From the point of human rights and capabilities the pressure to accept bad or even harmful jobs after a certain period of being unemployed is ethically questionable. Accordingly participants demand a greater say regarding their professional development and job search in order to consider their talents, wishes and needs, less restrictive conditions for unemployment benefits and the right to refuse to take up bad quality jobs.

The second key working assumption of RE-InVEST is that the crisis and crisis-related policies have weakened social cohesion and trust in political institutions and social relations in general. The research process revealed that **the level of trust in political actors and institutions is indeed very low** among the participants. The attitude towards the Austrian government is partly ambivalent ('Could we or others do better?'), but mainly negative. They perceive political leaders as ignorant, incompetent and detached from ordinary citizens. The general sentiment is that we live in times of uncertainty, for which the current political leaders are ill equipped, as they seem to be clueless themselves.

The participants see the underlying causes of the current crisis phenomena in the gradual turn to neoliberal policies starting about three decades ago and perceive of present developments as another climax of this long-term trend. The strong influx of refugees since 2015 is referred to as another important factor that boosts feelings of insecurity and crisis.

These perceptions of the participants are in line with the Austrian-wide development of public opinion as revealed by Eurobarometer data from autumn 2015 (see 1.1.2): The trust in national and EU institutions is at an all time low level. (Europäische Kommission 2015) However, one can assume that additional to the economic crisis the 'refugee crisis' contributes to this result.

The participants feel that **inequality is on the rise**: between the rich and the poor, between private and public patients in the health care system, between those people who have a job and those who do not. Some criticise the one-sided focus on the losers at the bottom, instead of shedding light on those, who benefit from this polarisation. They emphasise that for the last two decades the discourse has been centred primarily on austerity: where to save and what to reform next, but they do not see any betterment and wonder who benefits from all these cuts ultimately. The bailouts for banks are perceived as unfair since they led to cuts in the social domain to reduce public debts. The participants feel that these savings are marginal compared to the damage affected people suffer from. Some express the opinion that the small proportion of people, who really do not want to work, is negligible: *'The state can afford to drag along those few.'*

At a micro-level participants see an **increase in competitive and divisive attitudes** as well as resignation on part of those who are unable to keep up. They feel that social security and recognition more and more are available only to those who manage to stay within the system of gainful employment – with no place for the disadvantaged. This reveals a contradiction between the still dominant reference to fulltime employment on the one hand and a labour market that offers less and less of this traditional standard employment on the other hand. They also address the unequal distribution of work and lack of solidarity among workers (e.g. they criticise regular voluntary unpaid overtime by employees while so many do not find work).

The individual social network of most participants is still strong although for some it has changed heavily due to the difficult situation of being unemployed.

The participants also agreed that the social climate has become increasingly rough and more polarised. In this context they mention the higher **visibility of poverty** in the public space of Salzburg due to the strong presence of beggars and street paper vendors from Eastern Europe. Some of the poverty-driven migrants who have come to Salzburg during the last years used to worked in other EU countries (primarily in Southern Europe) before the crisis. They evoke ambivalent feelings of empathy, resentment and fear of social relegation amongst participants. Awareness of their own vulnerability and social inequality is high within the group. Some admit that this altered perception only emerged when they became unemployed themselves.

The stigmatising character of the public discourse about unemployed people discomfits participants because it gives rise to a **'culture of distrust'**. Current political reform proposals by certain parties, ministers and representatives of the influential Chamber of Commerce (Wirtschaftskammer) focus on tightening eligibility criteria and preventing misuse of social benefits. The discussions about creating stronger incentives for work is viewed as mockery, as the participants have made the experience that there is no or not enough work right now.

Participants feel that the pressure (on the part of the public discussion, in their circles of acquaintances and of course the PES) to take up 'any job, at any cost' is increasing. Unemployment is primarily defined as

an individual failure, although they would define it essentially as a collective and structural failure – of politics, the economy and social structures.

Some contributions also relate to **crisis as a chance** for addressing the perceived need for comprehensive social, economic and political change.

This diagnosis of the damage of the crisis for certain vulnerable groups was the first step within the participatory research process. The findings from all participating countries will be presented in a synthesis report. The participatory research process in Austria is entering into a second phase starting in autumn 2016. In this second phase researchers, vulnerable people and experts will jointly analyse the features of (and recent changes to) Austrian Active Labour Market Policy and Social Security on the basis of the findings of the first phase. Special attention will be given to effects of institutions, regulations and measures on actual rights and capabilities of vulnerable people. This thematic focus corresponds well with the priorities of the Austrian group: the participants have identified labour market policy as the core issue regarding threats to their human rights and capabilities. The aim of the upcoming research is to reach conclusions on the state of Active Labour Market Policy in Austria and make concrete proposals for changes at country level and for the further development of the social dimension of the European Union.

appendix 1 Rules of Conduct of the Group

Figure A1. Agreed rules of conduct

appendix 2 What constitutes a good life? List of elements

Figure A2. List of elements of a good life

Participants listed the following dimensions:

- Health (also a precondition for everything else), both mental and physical
- Family and friends, social network, social environment

- A home
- Financial and material security, financial freedom; job and social security
- Quality of life
- Human dignity, visionary power
- Cultural need
- Environment
- Satisfaction
- Right to live, social and societal recognition
- Opportunity to be oneself and live one's life
- Success (in what one is doing: job, partnership and so on)

In a second step, participants were asked to indicate their achievements and trends in their achievements in the following grid (referring to the human rights dimensions identified by (Burchardt and Vizard 2011b):

Figure A3. Capability grid

Figure A4. Perceived achievements in the dimensions of the good life

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Social disinvestment and vulnerable groups in Europe in the aftermath of the financial crisis

The case of newly arrived immigrants in Flanders

Newcomers, documented and undocumented migrants, and study service of beweging vzw

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Executive summary

This report is prepared in the framework of the Europe H2020 project ‘Rebuilding an inclusive, value based Europe of solidarity and trust through social investments’ (RE-InVEST). The project aims to evaluate the social investment strategy of the European Commission implemented in 2013 in response to the social damage of the financial crisis in 2008. The RE-InVEST consortium assesses the social damage of the crisis from human rights and capability based approaches with an eye to those vulnerable groups affected the most by the crisis in the 12 countries (and 13 regions) covered by the consortium. The analyses are carried out by the local partners, who consist of NGOs and/or researchers.

The crisis of 2008 didn’t affected Belgium in the same way as other European countries. Belgium was one of the first countries that linked up again with growth. But this revival was temporarily. From 2012 on, the backlash hit Belgium. Economic growth became negative intensified by higher unemployment rates. This backlash was also translated into electoral choices. A conservative inspired government took form and installed a neoliberal agenda with a lot of austerity measures.

Among vulnerable people in Belgium people with a history of migration tend to be the most exposed. Poverty among them is high, much higher than among native people. Within this group undocumented migrants and newcomers are the most affected, but they are nearly invisible in statistics and official reports. Due to the harsher political climate they feel more than others the impact of the crisis and the anti-crisis measures. The harsher political climate is also translated into more restrictive policies towards people with a history of migration. For this reason the group was identified as particularly affected by the crisis.

The RE-InVEST consortium has jointly developed the PAHRCA-methodology that combines principles of Participatory Action research with Human Rights and Capability Approaches. This qualitative, participatory research does not generate representative results but rather aims at deepening the understanding of the economic, social, cultural and political impacts of the crisis on the lives of vulnerable people and giving them a voice.

The biographies of Anna and Souma illustrate the marks of the crisis on individual life courses. The situation of Anna was characterised by her struggle to integrate, to have legal papers, to find a decent job, to find a decent house, and a struggle to survive. These struggles have a negative impact on her family life. *Life became that expensive that it is very hard to survive with only one family member having a job.* She fears the future, life has become harder, and more and more people have to live on the street. Souma’s story reflects the struggle to get legal papers and to be a part of the Belgian society. Without legal papers she’s nothing, has no rights, not even her child. *It became harder to search for favours, it takes a lot of energy. It’s unfair, society asks to integrate which I did, but I do not get any chances.*

While the biographies exemplify the effects of the crisis for a newcomer with and one without legal papers, the analysis is based on contributions of all participants. A loss of trust can be detected among newcomers. Participants experienced this loss of trust at a general level but also on the personal level. They expressed vividly their distrust or loss of trust in governments and key institutions. There is also a loss in trust in people. They live quite isolated and have no friends. They were afraid that with the recent refugee crisis they will lose again. Some participants express anti-refugee sentiments.

But at the same time they have high levels of gratitude to Belgium and the institutions. They want to ‘give back’ to our society. Their gratitude is a positive stepping stone for their integration. The loss of trust undermines on the long term this stepping stone. These high levels of gratitude also apply to NGO’s and schools. There they find help and support that others, like social institutions, refuse to give. NGO’s and schools strengthen their resilience.

Our analysis confirms the erosion of social rights. This erosion, partly due to disinvestment, partly due to the neo-liberal ideology, has a tremendous impact on newcomers. Their rights are not granted anymore, they have to fight each time for their rights. The access to social protection, income security, jobs, decent housing has diminished. For undocumented migrants the erosion of social rights has an indirect impact: more than ever they are not welcome. Social services and NGO's are being forbidden to help. As a consequence of the erosion of social rights the collective capability has diminished. Their capacity to support, their capacity to choose, their resources have been diminished. The erosion of social rights has real consequences for people's individual capability. They admit that it is too late for them. They can't make any more plans, choices, progress. The only hope they have is for their children.

In conclusion while the crisis has not hit Belgium as strong as other countries, it has had effects: poverty among people and especially among people with a history of migration has risen. Austerity policies have started from 2012 on and undermined trust in politics and existing institutions. The core idea of the social investment strategy of the European Commission – “investing in people” – has not reached people with a history of migration. On the contrary, newcomers admit the loss of support, the loss of rights, and the loss of freedom. Participants have noticed the development of a culture of distrust and discrimination. They are becoming *little people*. Little people are not heard, they have no voice. Participants are concerned about rising inequality and increasing visibility of poverty. However, they also ask to invest in little people, because they want to be part of the Belgian society. *We wanted to be a part of this society, so give us a chance to be part of it.*

Contents

List of figures	9
Introduction	11
1. Poverty and social exclusion among people with a history of migration and the effects of the austerity measures	13
1.1 An overview of the evolution of poverty and social exclusion in the group of people with a history of migration in Belgium (Flanders)	13
1.2 Poverty and social exclusion among 'people with a history of migration' has only recently come to the attention of researchers. The first major study on poverty among dates from 2007: "de kleur van armoede". It was the first study that identified the problem of poverty among people with a history of migration. The results of this study were breathtaking: more than half of the people with a history of migration coming from Morocco and Turkey, is living with an income below the AROP-poverty-line.	13
1.3 The austerity measures and their effects on poverty and social exclusion among people with a history of migration	14
2. The participatory research approach	16
2.1 Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach	16
2.2 The making of a group of participants	17
2.3 The process: the people with a history of migration valuated as contributor in the project	18
2.4 The hypotheses	18
3. "Our life is not normal"	19
3.1 Anna's story	19
3.2 Souma's story	20
4. Analysis: what newcomers said	23
4.1 Crisis as a daily experience	23
4.1.1 Their struggle for wellbeing	23
4.1.2 Their struggle for their rights	24
4.1.3 A daily struggle to rebound	25
5. Conclusion	28
5.1 Introduction	28
5.2 Two hypotheses	28
5.3 A petition	29
5.3.1 Build on their resilience	29
5.3.2 Strengthen their resilience, creating a more human society	30
Bibliography	33

List of figures

Figure 2.1	Resources, conversion factors, capability set and achieved functionings	16
Figure 2.2	Merging of Knowledge	17

Introduction

This report is prepared in the framework of the Europe H2020 project ‘Rebuilding an inclusive, value based Europe of solidarity and trust through social investments’ (RE-InVEST). The RE-InVEST project aims to contribute to an EU offering more solidarity and inclusion, through an inclusive, powerful and effective social investment strategy at the EU level. Moreover, the project itself adopts a participative approach that lends a voice to vulnerable groups and civil society organisations. The RE-InVEST consortium consists of members of the informal network ‘the Alliances to fight Poverty’, a network of civil society organisations, trade unions, policy makers and academics co-ordinated by the Flemish Christian labour movement ‘beweging.net’, and committed to a more inclusive Europe. The consortium covers a broad range of European countries, both geographically (12 countries, 13 regions) and in terms of representation of different welfare and labour market traditions. The analyses are carried out by the local partners, who consist of NGOs and/or researchers.

In particular, this report is one of the 13 national reports that make up the qualitative research of the RE-InVEST work package ‘The social damage of the crisis’. This work package focuses on the authentic experience of vulnerable people, the impact of the crisis (and crisis-related policy reform) on vulnerable groups as well as the impact of growing inequality and social vulnerability on trust. Our two key hypotheses in this regard are: 1. That growing distrust and indeed resentment among the population may be attributed to (a rejection of) the neoliberal policies employed by national as well as European elites in recent years; 2. That this integrated diagnosis can build on the idea of the erosion of/disinvestment in (individual and collective) capabilities and basic social rights in the EU. This means that experiences of insecurity, poverty and social degradation need to be re-analysed from those perspectives.

Next to the 13 qualitative case studies, this work package consists of a cross-validation with a report describing trends in selected quantitative indicators that reflect the relation between socio-economic vulnerability, human rights and capabilities. A third element consists of a statistical analysis of the dynamic relationship between vulnerability, shifts in social policies and trust: in which sections of the population has the trust in institutions declined most? Can different patterns between countries be observed, and can they be explained by differences in policy shifts and differences in resilience of civil society? A European synthesis report will combine the main findings from the three types of analyses.

The qualitative research focuses on the experience of vulnerable groups in each of the 12 countries (13 regions) participating in RE-InVEST. Mixed teams of researchers, NGO and union workers, practitioners and people from vulnerable groups jointly analysed cases where the crisis has impacted on human rights and (individual as well as collective) capabilities.

This Belgium-Flemish qualitative case study focuses on the ‘newcomers’ that arrived in Belgium within the last 12 years. It should be noted that newcomers are one of the blind spots in all quantitative and qualitative research. The newcomers arrive here full of hope to build a new life. They are still ‘resilient’ and still have the power to build a new life. What is the impact of the crisis (and crisis-related policy reform) on their life? And, more specifically, what is the impact on their resilience? The Belgian case study seeks answers to this question. Answers that can impact and refocus policies.

We would like to thank all participants and the NGO that hosted us, for their hospitality and their passion in the fight for their rights and the rights of all those who are excluded.

1. Poverty and social exclusion among people with a history of migration and the effects of the austerity measures

1.1 An overview of the evolution of poverty and social exclusion in the group of people with a history of migration in Belgium (Flanders)

1.2 Poverty and social exclusion among ‘people with a history of migration’ has only recently come to the attention of researchers. The first major study on poverty among dates from 2007: “de kleur van armoede”¹. It was the first study that identified the problem of poverty among people with a history of migration. The results of this study were breathtaking: more than half of the people with a history of migration coming from Morocco and Turkey, is living with an income below the AROP-poverty-line²

The Flemish government has been publishing the ‘Flemish Monitor of Migration and Integration’ since 2013. This monitor collects all data on participation, social cohesion, position, on integration and migration.³ The conclusion of the Flemish Monitor is stringent: poverty and social exclusion as defined by EU2020⁴ among PMH is 34 percentage point higher than for native people⁵: In 2013, 13% of people born in Belgium are poor and/or socially excluded next to 47% of people born outside the EU, but living in Belgium.

Each study exposed two blind spots. The first being the problem of poverty among ‘undocumented migrants’ (undocumented migrants). The problem is well-known, but because of their status the undocumented migrant do not show up in most of the data. The ‘Centre of Expertise on Migration’⁶ estimates the population of people living without legal papers in Belgium at 100,000 in 2007. This estimation has not been updated since then. PICUM⁷ (Platform for international cooperation on undocumented migrants) argues that due to the irregularity of their situation undocumented migrants are more vulnerable than others.

Another blind spot is the situation of newcomers. Newcomers have to follow a path to a legal status. Once they have obtained the necessary papers, they become part of the group of people with a history of migration and become invisible as a subgroup. Only one quantitative indication of the extreme vulnerability of newcomers could be found: the 2015 report of Eurostat on poverty concluded that 1 upon 7 newcomers are living in poverty⁸.

The conclusion of all reports⁹ indicates that people with a history of migration are more vulnerable than native people. There are indications that undocumented migrants and newcomers, because of their invisibility, are more vulnerable than others.

1 Translation: “The colour of poverty”. Bea Van Robaeys, Jan Vranken, Nathalie Perrin en Marco Martiniello. De Kleur van Armoede, armoede bij personen van buitenlandse herkomst. Acco Leuven. 2007.

2 http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/Europe_2020_indicators_-_poverty_and_social_exclusion

3 Monitor.

4 This means that these people were at least in one of the following conditions: at-risk-of-poverty after social transfers (income poverty); severely materially deprived or living in households with very low work intensity.

5 Vlaamse Migratie- en Integratiemonitor, 2015. P. 208-209.

6 <http://www.kruispuntmi.be/thema/bijzondere-groepen/mensen-zonder-wettig-verblijf>

7 <http://picum.org/en/>

8 <https://www.vlaamsparlement.be/commissies/commissievergaderingen/1019576/verslag/1030778>;

9 Verschillende rapporten opsommen.

1.3 The austerity measures and their effects on poverty and social exclusion among people with a history of migration

Belgium is one of the countries that showed more resilience to the crisis than other members of the Eurozone. Yet, all governments under the guidance of the 'Growth and Stability Pact'¹⁰ accepted adjustment plans with a view to restoring the health of public finances. The first years after the crisis, the Flemish government developed an anti crisis plan based on investment and raising the household budgets¹¹. From 2012 onwards the backlash of the crisis was felt. For the first time since the crisis a small negative growth was noted¹². Also in 2012, a new government was composed after an electoral victory of the Nationalist conservative party. This party controlled the federal and Flemish governments. New and tighter anti-crisis measures based on a more conservative and neo-liberal ideology were implemented¹³. Anti-crisis measures initially focusing on positive investment plans, gave way to austerity and adjustment.

In this chapter we give an overview of the anti-crisis measures that have had a negative impact on people with a history of migration. There are measures that have an impact on the whole population and measures with a more specific impact on people with a history of migration. These last measures are not always conceived from the viewpoint of an anti-crisis policy. A more stringent integration policy is notable from 2007/8, but it is not necessarily related to the economic crisis. The policy reflects a harsher society, that became even harsher after the crisis.

The anti-crisis measures with an overall negative impact can be grouped into four categories: more conditionality (i.e. restricted access to social housing), cuts in public services (i.e. 900 million EUR less expenditures for education), higher personal contributions for basic needs and provisions (i.e. higher personal contribution for day care centres or public transport), and restrictive policies (restricted access to unemployment allowances)¹⁴. Almost all measures have a negative effect on people, irrespective of their origin. But due to the vulnerability of people with a history of migration, the impact of the austerity measures are more severe for them than for others. Some specific measures aimed at people with a history of migration on integration were introduced, accompanied with a reform of the integration service sector as a whole.

All these recently introduced policies have a heavy impact on people living in poverty. At the end of 2015 the municipal social services (OCMWs) applied for a raise in social benefits budgets to answer the desperate need of many households.¹⁵

The impact on people with a migration background is grave. Our collaborating NGO testified how people with a history of migration became more vulnerable. They saw the number of their number increase by 30% from 2013 to 2014. They were obliged to extend the opening hours of their social grocery. In the near future they expect again an important rise due to the integration of new refugees and even more important, the present huge rise of the energy cost in Flanders.

The NGO has been obliged to shift its policy towards undocumented migrants, due to the more restrictive attitude of the municipality and its services towards undocumented migrants.

10 The Stability and Growth Pact (SGP) is a set of rules designed to ensure that countries in the European Union pursue sound public finances and coordinate their fiscal policies.

http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/economic_governance/sgp/index_en.htm

11 DE VLAAMSE BEGROTING 2009. P. 3 and 4.

http://fin.vlaanderen.be/nlapps/data/docattachments/nhoora_Vlaamse_Begroting_2009.pdf

12 The Belgium economy showed a greater resilience than the rest of the Eurozone. In 2010 and 2011 the economy grew with 2.3% and 1.8%. a gradual slowdown in activity began in the second quarter of 2011 and continue in 2012. 2012 noticed an economic growth of -0.1%. From 2013 on there is a small recovery (+0.2%). Dalila Ghailana. The impact of the crisis on fundamental rights across Member States of the EU. Country Report on Belgium. Study for the LIBE Committee. Brussels. 2015

13 <http://www.dewereldmorgen.be/artikel/2014/10/15/regering-michel-krijgt-al-meteen-een-betoging-en-vier-stakingen-op-het-bord>

14 An overview of the austerity measures of the Flemish government: <http://www.demorgen.be/binnenland/exclusief-dit-is-de-rekening-van-bourgeois-i-be6ec2f7/>. An overview of the austerity measures of the Federal government: <http://trends.knack.be/economie/beleid/waar-haalt-michel-i-1-2-miljard-euro-10-maatregelen/article-normal-443859.html>

15 Natalie Debast. Wonen en energie voor veel mensen onbetaalbaar. Brussel 2015.

<http://www.vvsg.be/nieuws/Paginas/OCMW%E2%80%99s---Wonen-en-energie-voor-veel-mensen-onbetaalbaar-in-2016%E2%80%99.aspx>

All indicators show the vulnerability of people with a migration background and especially the undocumented migrants. Because of their vulnerability, austerity measures have a tremendous negative impact. However, in all the statistics and reports undocumented migrants and newcomers stay invisible. Therefore we decided to focus on these groups in this case study.

2. The participatory research approach

2.1 Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach

RE-InVEST aims at investigating the philosophical, institutional and empirical foundations of an inclusive Europe of solidarity and trust. To this end it draws on capability and human rights based participatory approaches. Human rights form a common European basis of values and describe at the same time core elements of what constitutes well-being and a good life. Further, human rights are transformative by empowering people.

Human rights are the basic rights and freedoms that belong to everyone. International law, including treaties, contain the provisions which give human rights legal effect. Ideas about human rights have evolved over many centuries and gained strong support after World War II when the United Nations adopted the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights - which set out for the first time the human rights and fundamental freedoms shared by all human beings without discrimination of any kind.

Human Rights are universally agreed basic standards that aim to ensure that every person is treated with dignity and respect; they are interdependent and indivisible, they belong to all people without discrimination. Usually set out in law, through international or regional treaties, or national legislation, they form a legal statement of universally accepted principles of how the state should treat its citizens and other people living within its jurisdiction. Human Rights include Civil and Political Rights, such as the right to life, the right to a fair trial and the right not to be subjected to torture; and Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, such as the right to work, to join a trade union, to health, to education, and to an adequate standard of living.

Specific groups are protected in specific treaties such as women, children, and people with disabilities, minorities, and migrants. For vulnerable people the usage of a rights-terminology has proven to change their perspective by making them aware of their rights and the ways in which their current situation compromises these rights.

Figure 2.1 Resources, conversion factors, capability set and achieved functionings

The capability approach as developed by Sen (1999) and Nussbaum (2011) defines a person’s well-being in terms of the beings and doings (the functionings) a person achieves and his capability to choose among different combinations of such functionings. For leading a life one values and has reason to value, resources and conversion factors are preconditions (Figure 2.1). Resources refer to the material conditions of a person: his income, the goods and services she disposes of. Conversion factors help him converting resources into doing and being well. There are personal conversion factors such as skills and bodily features, social conversion factors such as social norms and social institutions and environmental conversion factors such as climate and geography. In the end both the achieved functionings as well as the freedom to choose a life one values matters.

For assessing the capabilities of vulnerable people RE-InVEST aims at giving them a voice. Their participation is fostered by relying on participatory action research that directly results in policy recommendations. Participatory action research views participants as co-researchers who have special knowledge about their own situation. Hence they are not only asked or interviewed on their views, but take part in research by engaging in, examining, interpreting, and reflecting on their own social world, shaping their sense of identity.

It is a circle of knowledge generation that emerges from this method and includes the steps of knowledge production and sharing, empowerment by participation, newly generated knowledge and action that builds upon this knowledge (Figure 2.2). Crucial for this kind of knowledge generation is the “merging” or “crossing of knowledge” that comes from three parts: scientific knowledge as gained by researchers; knowledge which the poor and excluded have, from their first-hand experience, of the twin realities of poverty and the surrounding world which imposes it on them; and the knowledge of those who work among and with these victims in places of poverty and social exclusion (Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2 Merging of Knowledge

Those are the core elements of the ‘Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach’ (PAHRCA) developed in RE-InVEST. PAHRCA proposes seven steps (Toolkit, 44-45): 1. Identify and meet partner NGO/gatekeeper, 2. Preliminary ‘meet ups’ (for trust building if necessary), 3. First meeting with participants – trust building, 4. Developmental: implement developmental human rights & capability approach, 5. Inquiry/data gathering, 6. Identifying patterns (key issues and themes of concern to the group) and 7. Undertake action/outcome using one or combination of approaches.

2.2 The making of a group of participants

The people with a history of migration in our case study are all newcomers. The ‘oldest’ have lived here for 10 years. Their stories are about their struggle to integrate and to survive during their integration period. All of them are vulnerable.

From September 2015 till mid-February 2016 we organised 10 group sessions. These were complemented with individual sessions. All sessions were initiated and supported by the two ‘Beweging vzw’ researchers responsible for the RE-InVEST project. A social worker from the involved NGO involved attended the first 2 group sessions as well as the presentation of the first draft results to the participants.

The total number of participants being involved was 15. 11 out of 15 participants were present during all sessions. Two male participants stopped participating after 2 group sessions without offering any reason. Women are clearly overrepresented in the group: 9 out of 15. The core group of 11 people only counts 1 male. There was also a quite diverse nationality range within the focus group: Cameroon, Iraq, Afghanistan, Albania, Armenia, Morocco, Russia,

The main common characteristic was that all participants were involved in volunteering work. That resulted in a quite resilient and emancipated focus group.

2.3 The process: the people with a history of migration valued as contributor in the project

Participants spontaneously started talking about their previous experiences with research projects and questionnaires. They stressed that they wanted more than just telling their story again. They wanted a their situation to change. For this reason, we decided to involve them strongly in the process of policy making. We asked them to develop, by constructed reasoning, policy recommendations. Finally, we submitted our draft report to them for feedback and amendments.

Within the scope of the project, participants chose the subjects and themes they wanted to discuss. Important themes that were selected by the participants were ‘their rights’, ‘work’, ‘education’ and ‘social services’. We decided to maximise the emancipatory and critical aspect of the ‘Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach’ (PAHRCA) and not just discussing these themes, but emphasizing on their way of dealing within these scopes. Key concepts we used to develop this method were ‘trust’, ‘well-being’, ‘future plans’, ‘the role of their children’.

At the end of the project, the participants will be invited to the final conference where their voice will also be heard.

2.4 The hypotheses

This qualitative research focuses on the lived experience of vulnerable people, the impact of the crisis (and crisis-related policy reform) on vulnerable groups as well as the impact of growing inequality and social vulnerability on distrust. The main lesson we draw from the discussions with the NGOs is that for newcomers ‘the crisis’ means something else than the crisis of 2008. *“They live permanently in crisis”* said their representatives.

The consequence is that we need to look what ‘crisis’ means for the focus group. They already experienced a feeling of ‘crisis’ in their home country. Because of this traumatic experience they fled to Belgium. This traumatic experience colours their emotions and their evaluation of their daily life in Belgium.

Next there is the definition of crisis as a daily experience. The answers produce a picture of how a society deals with newcomers and of what changed in time. The hypotheses on disinvestment can find here some answers.

Newcomers have initially hopes for themselves and in the end mainly for their children. Actually, this is a matter of resilience. Is their resilience affected by the crisis? Resilience is linked with trust. Trust is necessary to rebound. The discussion about trust and resilience is connected with the first questions. Trust, resilience, investment, support, all these concepts are intertwined.

The biographies and the group discussions gave a new insight into the lives of newcomers.

3. “Our life is not normal”

3.1 Anna’s story

Anna arrived in Belgium in 2010 with the help of an Italian acquaintance. She is originally from Morocco. She has two small children, born in Belgium. She started taking Dutch courses and was granted allowances? for 1 year allowances by the OCMW. Afterwards she benefited during 2 years from a VDAB (Flemish employment office) support. As her basis knowledge of the Dutch language was insufficient, the VDAB did not offer her a training. *“Suddenly, in 2013, our papers have been stopped, we were not notified”*. She doesn’t know or isn’t informed of the reason why her own and her husband’s papers have been stopped. Also her child benefits were stopped. *“All support measures stopped, there was nothing left”*. She finds it so very difficult to understand that, first you are entitled to certain things, and then, suddenly, it all stops, without any transition period or any alert mechanism. All of this provoked great stress and anger in the family. Last month, they followed the same procedure as in 2013 and were granted again legal papers.

Anna’s social worker encourages her to find a job. It is not easy to find a job without a diploma. Sometimes she finds a job for a week, two weeks, but never a long term commitment. Currently, her husband has an interim job as a seasonal worker and as a ‘paperboy’. He is 47 years old and finds it hard to find a full-time contract. The CAW (private social service) helped her with her administration for the child benefits. She was also helped by “De Huizen van het Kind”.

Anna takes Dutch language courses and she also took internet courses. Having to take care of two small children, she doesn’t find the time to do anything more for the time being. All the trainings are beyond her present level. In Morocco, she worked for 14 years in a textile factory, in the marketing sector and the food inspection sector. Here, she hopes to find a half time job in 6 months’ time, when the youngest child will go to the day care centre. But she is afraid that she will not find a job at all, because there is not much demand, not even in the cleaning sector. At VDAB, she insisted to have a counsellor. In the meanwhile, she tries to improve her Dutch. She speaks fluently Greek, Turkish, Arabic and French. But she finds the Dutch grammar particularly difficult.

Anna is overwhelmed by stress and finds it hard to rest because of the tense situation at home. A lot of arguing is going on there and there is too much stress caused by work and money related problems. The cost of living (rent, gas/electricity and a car) is as high as 1200 EUR/month. There is only 200 EUR left for food, clothes, the children, for 4 persons. For food, Anna goes to the Social Grocery. Often she does not get sufficient healthy food. They have to pay a 800 EUR rent for an apartment in an old house, which is in a very bad state. There are severe humidity problems and both mother and the children show allergic reactions. Nothing in the house is finished. The walls haven’t been painted, there’s no wallpaper, there are no skirting boards in the house. The youngest child is beginning to crawl and likes to put his hands against the wall. Each time his hands come back full of chalk and he has to be stopped putting his hands into his mouth. They are on the waiting list for a social house, but they were informed they would have to wait 5 to 6 years to obtain one. She asked for a rental allowance, but she received until now only a letter with the waiting lists.

The first apartment they lived in, suffered from the same problems as the present one: a high rent and a bad state. In the first apartment, they asked help from the ‘Huurdersbond’ to carry out some inspections. The result was that she had to sleep in a separate place from her husband and that afterwards they had to leave the house. Anna does not want to contact the ‘Huurdersbond’ regarding her present apartment: they are too afraid to be expelled from the apartment and to become homeless. She even knows a woman in her

neighbourhood who has been homeless for 2 months now. She very much afraid to end up in the same situation. They are looking for another apartment, but they are hard to find.

Finding a day care centre and a school for the children did not present any major difficulties. She registered in the crèche while she was pregnant and following an integration trajectory. She was helped in a proper way by the social workers of the Integration Centre, where she took Dutch courses and reached level 2.1. Afterwards she continued her Dutch courses at VDAB.

Anna doesn't feel discriminated. *"I follow my own path, I do what I have to do. I encounter friendly and unfriendly people. But that's the same in my own country"*.

What has changed during the last years in Belgium?

Life becomes harder: a lot of people are seeking a job and a good home and there aren't enough jobs and good houses available. She also points at the rising number of homeless people. Anna also mentions the rise of the gas and electricity cost. *"Life became so expensive that it is really hard to survive with only one family member having a job. Both parents need to go to work to survive now."* She also fears the consequences for society after the Paris attacks. *"People who do not believe in a democratic world, bode ill for all of us. This is for nobody a good and healthy situation"*.

3.2 Souma's story

Souma starts her biographical interview by pointing out that, at home, she had reflected a lot on what she would tell today. Eventually she decided not to tell her whole life story, because it would make her too depressed. It would remind her of the bad choices she made in her life and their consequences.

She's originally from Morocco and arrived here in 2009. She came to Europe for economic reasons. Her two sisters were already in Europe (one in the Netherlands and one in France) when she arrived. They are happily married and have all the necessary legal papers. She could only visit her sister in France once, but sometimes her sister comes over to visit her in Belgium. Souma is only visiting her sister in the Netherlands from time to time. She takes the bus, because travelling by train, involves a higher risk for identity controls and she does not have legal papers. *"I thought it would be easier to build a life in Europe; if I had known beforehand what I would have to endure, I would not have come to Europe. But now, with all the time and efforts I have put into this life, impossible to give up, especially because of my son."*

In her first year in Europe, she stayed in the Netherlands with a Belgian visa for one year. Souma puts a lot of effort in her study of the Dutch language. With temporary papers, she lived together with a man for one year. The relationship didn't work out well: the man did not see the need for her to develop herself. He did not offer Souma any time to discover her new world. The relationship collapsed.

Souma appealed for regularisation, but received a negative answer because she was not long enough in Belgium. In Belgium, she started a relationship with a man going through a regularisation procedure. But when his labour contract expired and also due to an administrative mistake, the procedure was interrupted. At that moment, her visa was expired as well.

Souma got pregnant and now has a son of 5 years. She is living separated from the father of her son. The man married another woman and is now living in the same neighbourhood she and their son are living. He is a good father to the child. Souma and the father have a good contact for raising the child. *"I did not choose the right moment, the right place, the right persons. I have to pay now for my bad choices."* She blames herself for that.

Souma decided not to delve too deep in her past and starts talking about her observations and feelings. *"I feel good because I became independent, only thanks to my own efforts and strengths. I survived thanks to the search for rights I undertook myself. By oral communication I have searched for information to see what rights or benefits I could claim. Services never provided me any help. Their overall reaction was very unfriendly because of the language barrier or because of ID-questions."* *"They just tell you that you don't have any rights. You have to search yourself for possibilities until you find useful information"*.

Her son was a very active baby. He always wanted to crawl, he didn't sleep well. At that time, Souma didn't have any work at all and suffered from a deep depression. She went to 'Kind and Gezin' and asked for psychological assistance. *"I wanted to search for my strength."* They refused to help her because she does not

have legal papers. A friend suggested she went to a church where they provide food aid packages. The woman who was working in the church called the CAW, because at that time Souma could not pay her rent. The CAW stated that they could not be of any help because she could not claim housing help or call on financial support. Eventually, she was asked to come over for a consultation: they could provide help only for the child, but not for her, because she's not a political refugee. The CAW has called 'Kind and Gezin' asking to arrange a day care centre for the son although he is not registered anywhere. The solution was to bring the son to the day care centre of the OCMW. Bringing her baby to the day care centre was a relief for her because she needed rest. Now, her son is in his first year at the kindergarten. To register your child via the computer at school, you need to fill in a registration number, which he does not have. Souma asked 'Kind and Gezin' what to do. They told her that there were some specific registration moments. Finally she succeeded to enrol her son in a day care centre where he really feels good.

Through 'Kind and Gezin' her son eventually received a 'child code'. This was arranged through the OCMW, but it was a very difficult procedure. She wonders how people manage this when they don't understand the language sufficiently. She could also work with the 'Inloopteam' (initiation team) of 'Kind and Gezin' and that was a positive experience. For Souma it is of a vital importance to learn and improve her Dutch. *"I have to learn Dutch to exist"*. However, due to a 2012 Belgian law, it is forbidden for schools to allow adults without legal papers. Eventually, she found a teacher who teaches Dutch on a voluntary basis and who organises initiation courses for undocumented people. She takes courses twice a week and now speaks fluently Dutch. She tries to correct her language mistakes and to fine-tune her grammar. To her, learning Dutch, is an important way of organizing her time in a positive way. She had to seek profoundly to exercise her language. She also does volunteer work in order to speak the language as often as possible and she follows the news.

Souma has a diploma of accounting. Until now, she has never practiced. *"I am sometimes shocked when someone asks me, 'did you go to school'. It is not because I have to clean over here that I do not have a diploma."* Currently, she does undeclared cleaning work in the week and over the weekend she gives private lessons of Arabic. She earns about 600 EUR per month. Additionally she gets 150 EUR of alimention from the father of her son. Next to that, she receives a monthly 150 EUR from someone for allowing that person to have his domicile registered her place. Per month she pays a rent of 550 EUR and 70 EUR for gas and electricity and other house related costs. That leaves her and her son with about 150 EUR per month to eat, buy clothes, school stuff, toys, etc. She doesn't pay for the internet, and she uses the code of a friend. Souma goes to the social grocery and receives food aid packages. For her, it is very important to have healthy food. Sometimes the food dates have expired and she does not trust that kind of food. She sometimes gets help from her sister.

The state of the apartment is good. The only problem is that the bathroom is in the corridor; her son copes with allergic and asthma problems, and often suffers from colds.

Did life became harder in Belgium?

"If someone would come to North-Africa without any legal documents, he or she would not be able to have access to the benefits I have sought out. I can go to the hospital when I need to. My son can go to school. I can find some undeclared work."
"The search for benefits became increasingly harder. It takes up a lot of energy. Sometimes I have to deal with unfriendly people. People that do not value me and only see me as a cleaning lady. I am not happy with my life. I want to have a decent job and a good life". *"The only solution I see, is that I start living together with a Belgian man or that I get married. I have had 2 failed relationships. I do not make any more efforts for the moment. I do volunteer work and take Dutch courses, but in the meanwhile, I forget myself. I need to reflect on my future, but I fail to do so. I am waiting for a solution, but when and how that will come, I do not know. I have to do my best."* *"It is unfair, society wants me to integrate, which I did, but I do not get a fair chance."*

Souma went to the OCMW because of a debt with the day care centre that she needs to cover. The OCMW told her they could not help because she is not entitled to debt mediation. Some days ago, she received a phone call inviting her to go to a rights centre.

Souma's plans for the future

Souma wants her son to have rights so that he can build a decent life here. For herself, when she's old, she wants to go back to North-Africa. *"I did not achieve my dream. Where do I get my strength? My psychologist gives me strength to move on, as well as my volunteer work. My volunteer work makes me feel for a moment that I am a person worthy of this society"*. She receives also help from her doctor who provides free medication. He was also the one who directed her to a psychologist, whom she pays 15 EUR. She had to stop the consultations because it was too expensive for her. She confirms that she needs psychological assistance to release herself and for advice. *"How can I overcome my depressed feelings? I need to search for my strength and my power. I do not have time for a depression."*

Souma is determined to continue her fight and to take responsibility over her future life. *"I don't expect any financial aid, but I do expect to be given an opportunity to work, so that I am able to go to the hospital whenever I need to go, so that I can take courses. I am a fighter and I am used to struggle for everything, that is the way I was raised."*

Souma is not afraid to be recognised by third people who will be reading this biography: *"I am not a criminal, I have not committed any crime and neither am I doing any harm."*

Reading her biographical story has given her strength: *"I realised that I am indeed making progress and that I can be proud of myself."*

4. Analysis: what newcomers said

What can I do and what will I be? This basic question summarises the capability and human rights approach. In its naivety it opens a whole world of feelings, experiences, wishes and potentialities. It opens a window on how people want to organise their lives, how they can have their voice heard, how they can build their future. At the same time the question emphasises the importance of the societal context. It focusses on the obstacles, the hurdles and the opportunities society creates.

‘What can I do to do and what will I be’ is a permanent concern for people with a history of migration and especially for the newcomers among them. Having left their country, generally for urgent reasons, they are now confronted with the question how ‘to be’, how to exist in another society, how to integrate the Belgian society, how to live and seek a new future. Their story tells their struggle for integration in a society that itself is struggling with a crisis.

4.1 Crisis as a daily experience

Every day the participants fight for their survival. ‘Crisis’ is an on-going, daily experience. An experience that has become harsher than ever before. Harsher because society seems to be pulling back. And instead of being able to claim rights, one has to fight for rights. This struggle constitutes a major obstacle for a full integration.

4.1.1 Their struggle for wellbeing

Once they reached Belgium, all the participants were very much relieved. Their gratitude towards the Belgium society is immense. And they want to express this gratitude by doing something in return for the society they are living in: ‘*returning the favour*’ is a recurrent theme in their stories.

I come from Asia. The capital was nearly destroyed, I simply had to move out, run away with the children. In the beginning, we tried to find refuge in the country. When that was no longer possible, we came to Belgium. When I arrived in Belgium, I was first put in a refugee centre. I was happy that I did not have to be afraid of bombing and the like. I was just happy to be able to sleep, that my children could play soccer. After a while, I received a positive response to my requests - I could stay here.’

This gratitude is one part of their story. The other part is the struggle for their well-being. There is a permanent feeling of stress: the struggle to survive, to give their children a future, to fight for their rights. And there is this permanent anxiety of not being able to fulfil the demands of social services.

*When people do not have an income or do not find work, it puts pressure on them. I sometimes tell my social worker that their severity and strictness push people ending into prostitution or criminality.
It became harder the last years to look for benefits. It takes a lot of energy.
It’s unfair: society requires us to integrate, which we did, but we are not given a fair chance.’*

A majority of the participants are depressed and looking for psychological help. Often they are obliged to stop their treatment for lack of resources.

She stresses that she has reached the limits of what she can take and that she feels her physical and mental health gradually deteriorating. The never-ending fight for survival and the on-going fight for obtaining minimum rights for her son (and herself),

simply takes up all the energy she is left with. She is now on the verge of a break-down. She's absolutely unable to make any progress in life.

She affirms that she needs psychological assistance. 'How can I overcome my feelings of depression? I need to find back my strength and my power. I simply do not have time for a depression.'

When your head is filled with worries about debts and bills, it is very difficult to think about anything else.'

They don't want to use the word 'poverty' to describe their situation. They feel that, should they start using this word, it would only add to their misery. It adds to the precarity of their existence. They are very poor indeed, but refuse to admit it.

'We don't want to use a negative word to describe our situation, and using the word 'poverty' is depressing, it plunges us even deeper into our misery.'

4.1.2 Their struggle for their rights

When discussing their rights, it became obvious how their struggle has become harsher over the last years. The participants were very much aware of the fact that they have a feeble claim to rights, they know that for a fact. They have indicated that their rights are not disclosed in a transparent way. They cannot simply claim their rights, and always do they have to put up a fight.

I feel good because I became an autonomous person, thanks to my own efforts and strength. I survived because I searched and found my rights. It is by talking to people that I came up with the information that finally put me on the track of the rights or benefits I could claim. Social services never provided me any help. Their overall reaction was very unfriendly, mainly because of the language barrier.'

4.1.2.1 The right to an income

All the participants are living in extreme poverty. They have to make do with a small daily amount of money, and they have to find the strength to cope with their poverty.

'One respondent tells us that at the end of the month, he is left with very little money. He pays 480 EUR/month (without energy and water expenses) for his apartment. He puts aside 25 EUR at the beginning of the month and has to limit his spendings to a maximum of 5 EUR/day for the last week. 5 years ago, he was able to save about 100 EUR a month: he could put his housing allowance aside for unexpected expenses. This is no longer possible.

Asking another respondent how much money is left after having paid the rent and the bills, she says that she used to have 'a piggy bank'. 'But with children growing up, becoming adults, they need more food and more clothes, more than I can afford'. Sometimes family and friends help when I cannot pay the bills, but not always. They don't have much either.'

4.1.2.2 The right to work

Most participants are doing undeclared work. We are generally talking about cleaning work.

Finding a job, that is my plan. After our last meeting, I worked for 3 weeks. But now I am out of work, my job was a temporary job. There is little work to be found for the moment. In my line of work, the problem is not the language, the language is not important. On the work floor, I don't meet a lot of people speaking Dutch. So that is not the problem, the problem is all about finding work.

In my home country I graduated as a lawyer. But here, my diploma is not recognised. If I wanted to get a lawyer's degree in Belgium, I needed to do another 3 years of law study. However, I couldn't study because I had to take care of my child who was 3 years old at the time. For a child at that age it does not matter whether her mother is a cleaning woman or a lawyer. I arrived in Belgium in 2004. I was lucky because I quickly received the necessary papers. I studied a lot, but it was hard to find a job that fits my profile. In my country, I had a good job: I was a journalist. Upon my arrival in Belgium, I started as a cleaning lady. I like to clean, but not as a job. I was traumatised, was overwhelmed with stress, and was ill a lot of the time.

She stresses that it is impossible for her to find a flexible part time job over here due to language constraints. Employers give priority to higher skilled staff. There are simply not enough job offers on the market.

Sometimes I have to deal with unfriendly people. People that do not value me and only see me as a cleaning lady. I am not satisfied with my life. I want to have a decent job and a good life.'

4.1.2.3 The right to housing

All participants are renting a place to live, two of them are renting a council house. The rent on the private market is very high. Most of their income is spent on paying the rent and public utilities.

My son needs internet and television for school, but with a total income of 800 EUR, there is not enough left for food. Moreover, taxes on electricity have just increased in Belgium because of the taxes, so she has to cough up an additional 150 EUR. As she cannot pay the total amount in one go, she has asked the electricity provider to be allowed to pay in instalments.'

Almost every participant lives in a poorly conditioned house. The pressure on the house market is enormous, and getting stronger by the day. This pressure results into higher rents and in a housing market that is less and less accessible to newcomers and people with a history of migration. Good-quality houses are manifestly not available to them.

'One participant has already moved 4 times since arriving in Belgium. Now, having been on a waiting list for two and a half years, she was allocated a council house that comes with a rent of 300 EUR. 'She was lucky', she confirms. Her first apartment has been declared uninhabitable, the second was too expensive for her. The third one had very poor living conditions: there was a bad smell, humidity problems and insects were crawling on the floor and walls.

They have to pay 800 EUR per month for an apartment in a big old house which is in a very bad state. There are serious humidity problems and both mother and the children have recently been showing allergic reactions. No efforts whatsoever have been put in the house. The walls have not been painted, there is no wallpaper, and there are no plinths. The youngest child is starting to crawl and loves putting his hands against the wall. Each time his hands are full of chalk and he must be kept from putting his hands into his mouth.

She is frightened to be expelled from the apartment and to become homeless. She knows a woman in her neighbourhood who has been homeless for 2 months now. She is so very much afraid of ending up the same way. They are looking for another apartment, but it is hard to find a suitable one.'

4.1.3 A daily struggle to rebound

Each participant has hopes and wishes for themselves and especially for their children. These hopes give them the strength to go on fighting every day. Their daily fight is a matter of falling and getting back up again, going for a rebound that is heavily jeopardised by a society in crisis.

Life becomes harder: a lot of people are seeking for a job and a good home and there aren't enough jobs and good houses available. She emphasises the rising number of homeless people and the rise of the gas and electricity costs. Life became so expensive that it is very hard to survive with only one family member having a job.'

4.1.3.1 Their struggle to integrate

All participants are very grateful to the Belgian society, they want to pay back what they received. Being part of Belgium, that is what they really want.

I trust everyone and everything in this country. I am so very much aware of a huge difference with my own country, where I had no one to trust. I'm very grateful to be here and I thank Belgium for the opportunity I was given.

Having been in Belgium for 8 years, her life has become harder, everything has become more difficult and more expensive. But she feels she understands the Belgian state: their budget decreased as well, she reasons.'

NGOs and other organisations, that is where they feel connected with the Belgian society. There they can build a network. Most participants are doing volunteer work. Volunteer work opens the door to our society.

I do volunteer work to get to know people. I like to learn from people. I like to learn new things in the social restaurant, through social work, volunteer work. I obtain new ideas and reach solutions by getting to know new people.

My volunteer work makes me feel for a moment that I'm a person worthy of this society.'

They know a lot of people, but their relations are mostly superficial ones. Poverty is why.

'Although she finds it important to go out, she mentions not having any real friends out here in Belgium yet, just some superficial contacts with people while doing their hair.

I have no money to go to the pub and to get to know friends.

I've been through so many negative experiences, situations in which people, even so called best friends and organisations, stabbed me in the back. In order to survive, it was necessary for me to build a wall between myself and the others. I'm vigilant all the time. My first reaction towards an organisation or a person will always be one of distrust. Afterwards, little by little, I may start allow my distrust to be replaced by a more open attitude.'

Most participants emphasise the importance of trust and how trust was undermined by the crisis.

'But there many persons and mechanisms in society (i.e. erroneous publicity) that are misleading. Because of these misleading mechanisms, people start doing the wrong things. This is worsened by the crisis. The crisis created 'bad' situations that generated distrust. People lie and mislead to survive.'

More than ever before they are exposed to discrimination. They also admit that discrimination has become more manifest. Discrimination makes it even more difficult to get connected.

'We never get the first opportunity.

I am sometimes shocked when someone ask me 'did you go to school?' It is not because I have to clean that I do not hold a degree.

Sometimes I have to deal with unfriendly people. People that do not value me and only see me as a cleaning lady.'

4.1.3.2 A daily struggle for support

All participants have had and still have multiple contacts with social services. Even undocumented migrants have (limited) access to social services.

They all show their gratitude for the help they get, but ... they are quick to add that they have to fight every step of the way. They all complain about the rudeness and the arbitrary and quite inhumane behaviour of social workers. They feel as if they have no rights at all. The help they eventually receive feels more like a kind of personal favour than a true right. They complain about the bureaucratic rules and the lack of transparency of these rules.

'If I find myself in the situation I have reached now, and if I have achieved the things I have achieved up until now, that is not thanks to the OCMW (public assistance services), but rather thanks to other organisations or informal contacts or thanks to my own efforts.

I often offer translating services to people during their contacts with the OCMW or with their social worker. I have come to see there are major differences between the various cases. Sometimes the social worker dictates the rules. It all seems to depend on the people in front of him.

For the social services, we are merely an administrative number: they do not take into account individual situations.

For me, dealing with the OCMW is always a struggle. I do what I can, I never say 'no' to anything. For medical reasons, I can only work part time, and my social worker knows that. But the OCMW refuses to offer part time work. Sometimes the OCMW does not want to pay me, I always have to put up a fight. But they do not tell me why, I do not receive any explanation at all. Last year, I had to stay in the hospital 3 times. I had a notice from my doctor, but my social worker refused to arrange for payment. Always a fight.'

They all mention that this rudeness has become more obvious in recent years. They see it as a result of general budgetary constraints, a result of the crisis: *'When the government has less money, then everyone has to economise.'*

Especially the undocumented migrants complain about the lack of minimum support.

'They just tell you that you do not have any rights (says an undocumented migrant. You have to seek out the necessary information yourself.'

When problems of physical abuse did occur in the life of mother and child, social services refused to help, because the situation was found to be too complex. It is deemed too difficult to find a way to deal with the stringent bureaucratic rules in a flexible manner within their own services system, and so, in certain cases, all help is refused. In one story of a undocumented migrants we learned how social services time and again refused to lend a helping hand to a mother and son in need.'

They mention also the important work the NGOs are doing: they fill in the gaps that social workers create. Without NGOs, newcomers would be lost. However, they fear that recent policy restrictions will have a negative impact on the potential help offered by the NGOs.

'Again social services declare themselves 'unfit' to help a mother (undocumented migrants) and her son. X, the non-profit organisation where she works as a volunteer, contacted more than 10 shelters. They all refused help. Eventually, the non-profit organisation itself provided an apartment for mother and son. It was vital and urgent for mother and son to be placed in a secure environment.'

4.1.3.3 Their struggle for their children

Children are the reason why they fight. They don't expect anything for themselves, but they expect and hope for a better future for their children.

'The future of my children. A good education, a good diploma and next a good job. That is what is important for me and for my future life. My children need to have a good job, they should not be submitted to discrimination. I want to raise my children as good citizens, so that they can offer a positive contribution to Belgium. That is the way I can show my gratitude towards Belgium.'

A respondent hopes that her daughter succeeds in obtaining a good diploma and a successful job. It is her daughter's dream to buy a house for the holidays in Greece, because she was born there. She wishes to take her daughter to Greece.

They understand that for them it is too late, but not for their children, they hope.'

4.1.3.4 Their struggle to be heard

All participants want to be heard. They highlight the importance of politics. They identify politicians as being responsible for their situation. In their home countries basically all the politicians were corrupt. Here, the situation is different. But since the new government came into power, everything has changed. Their trust in politics depends on their individual situation. Now they don't trust politics anymore. The politicians made it worse for them. The refugee crisis make it altogether worse. They became 'little people'. And nobody listens to little people. But still they believe that change is possible.

'What with the new conservative government, things have changed. For us, strangers, life became harsher, people are becoming more anti-refugee.'

I trust Belgian politicians. In my country everyone looks only after his or her own interest; here they look after the common good.

Another person answers: I don't trust politicians anymore. What do people want: decent food, a decent shelter, decent public transport, ... but it is all changing for the worst. They come and take the money from us, not from the rich citizens. People become poorer all the time.

Now we only have money for buying food. Yesterday we could even save some money, but today that is out of the question. And tomorrow, we won't be able to buy food anymore. And they are to blame.

There used to be trust among people. Nowadays there is less democracy, there is less freedom. We cannot speak freely anymore. Politicians are destroying everything. They transform us into little people, and nobody listens to little people.

We must learn to speak with one voice and vote for the right party. Some parties are still willing to listen to us, and together with them we might still have a go at equal chances, at equal rights. We are doing it for our children.'

5. Conclusion

5.1 Introduction

RE-InVEST wants to emphasise the true experience of vulnerable people, the impact of the crisis (and crisis-related policy reform) on vulnerable groups as well as the impact of growing inequality and social vulnerability on distrust. Our two key hypotheses in this regard are: 1. That growing distrust and indeed resentment among the population may be attributed to (a rejection of) the neoliberal policies employed by national as well as European elites in recent years; 2. That this integrated diagnosis builds on the idea of the erosion of/disinvestment in (individual and collective) capabilities and basic social rights in the EU. This means that experiences of insecurity, poverty and social degradation need to be re-analysed from those perspectives.

In this report we have translated the two hypotheses into the following question: what can the participants do and what can they become? This basic question summarises the capability and human rights approach. At the same time, this basic question gave the participants room (freedom) to explore their story and to find ways to tell said story.

This first part summarises the main findings within the framework of the two key hypotheses.

The second part can be read as a petition. By means of this report, the participants wanted to go beyond a simple description of their life. They want their story to be translated into political demands and into a request for other (social) policies. They want their story to encourage politicians and other stakeholders to acknowledge the existence of vulnerable people and to take account of the social damage of the crisis. Therefore this petition is an integral part of their story.

5.2 Two hypotheses

The first hypothesis was that retrenchment by the state, in conjunction with rising inequality and income insecurity, may very well have undermined trust, especially among the vulnerable people.

Our analysis confirms the hypothesis of a loss of trust among newcomers. Participants experienced this loss of trust on a general level, but also on a personal level. They expressed vividly their distrust or loss of trust in governments and key institutions. There is also a loss of trust in people. The participants live quite isolated and have no friends. They expressed their fear of losing out again, because of the recent refugee crisis. Some participants expressed anti-refugee sentiments.

But at the same time they show a high degree of gratitude towards Belgium and its institutions. They want to 'give back' to our society what they were given themselves. Their gratitude is a positive stepping stone for their integration. Yet, in the long run, the loss of trust undermines this stepping stone.

This high degree of gratitude is also expressed towards NGOs and schools. That is where they find help and support that other parties, such as social institutions, appear unwilling to offer. NGOs and schools strengthen their resilience.

The second hypothesis explores the concept of erosion of (or disinvestment in) social rights and capabilities within the EU and its impact on vulnerability. Our analysis confirms the erosion of social rights. This erosion, partly due to disinvestment, partly due to the neo-liberal ideology, has a tremendous impact on newcomers. Their rights are not granted anymore, they actually have to fight for each individual right. The access to social protection, income security, jobs, decent housing, have all been reduced. The erosion of social rights has an indirect impact on undocumented migrants as well: more than ever they are not welcome.

Social services and NGOs are forbidden to help. As a consequence of the erosion of social rights the collective capability has diminished. Their capacity to support, their capacity to choose, their resources: they have all been truncated.

The erosion of social rights has thus real consequences for people's individual capabilities. The participants are aware that it is too late for them. They can no longer make plans or progress, they are left without choices. The only hope they have left is for their children.

5.3 A petition

One of the requests of the participants was that their life stories would be heard and have a political impact. The participants wanted to speak on behalf of all those who are struggling to survive and fighting for integration. This petition is a plea for them to become true members of our society.

5.3.1 Build on their resilience

Build upon the resilience of the newcomers, do not discourage them. One of the common threads in their stories is the one about resilience, about wishing to become partners of our society, about building a future for their children. Their resilience is still brisk, even if they have to struggle. Their resilience is worthy of a positive welcome.

The newcomers want to become part and parcel of the Belgium society. They are grateful, and they want to offer something in return. They have all taken language courses and are still trying to improve their knowledge of the Dutch language. Integration is seen by them as a normal task for everyone that comes to live here. But at the same time, they are all (more or less) isolated from the Belgium society. Poverty is one reason. Another reason is an unfriendly, un-welcoming society. NGOs and schools are sometimes the only places where they can enter into contact with the Belgian society. Because of their isolation, they do not experience severe discrimination or racism. But they confirm the existence of discrimination and they go on to add that discrimination is becoming more and more obvious.

Inclusion should be more than learning the language and the culture; inclusion requires our society to welcome newcomers and to provide a (decent) place for them. Inclusion is in the first place a challenging task for our society, rather than for newcomers. Our society has to learn to welcome and to integrate them.

A welcoming society is also a society that combats discrimination and racism. The stories in this report highlight the silent forms of discrimination. Silent, because these forms are not immediately attributable. They generally take the form of a bureaucratic refusal for help. A welcoming society has to destroy any silent form of discriminatory behaviour.

NGOs are using different methods for having a stronger voice in the chapter. They support human rights and challenge the governments to implement the Human Rights. A necessary task, because the newcomers do indeed stress the uncertain implementation of their human rights, and the total lack of implementation of rights for undocumented migrants.

NGOs who defend the voice of vulnerable people and try to empower them, find their attempts to be curbed or else they are obliged to refocus their work, not to say to abandon their support. Some NGOs are integrated into agencies and lose their autonomy. The consequence is the loss of the voice of newcomers and undocumented people.

Enhancing human rights is only possible if vulnerable people can speak up. NGOs are in the frontline to defend this voice. This democratic function must be valued.

Newcomers do have numerous skills. They all speak different languages. But they only have access to low skilled labour (if given an opportunity to work at all). Some are doing undeclared work.

They want to be useful. But the hurdles are high. Social and labour services should consider those skills. This means also that i.e. language conditions must be customised, that foreign study results and degrees must be accepted as acquired competencies.

The children are the reason why the participants continue to fight. The participants are all particularly anxious about the future of their children. People with a history of migration and undocumented migrants are all struggling for a better world for their kin. All their hopes lie with their children. Especially for the children of undocumented migrants this struggle is a tough one: they realise that their children have to pay for their choices. Nevertheless, those very same children are all part of the Belgian society. Their only life is here. Expulsing them would make them stateless. A discussion about the rights of these children is necessary to avoid stateless people.

Regional and federal governments do not sufficiently tend to the needs of newcomers and people with a history of migration. One rarely comes across the words newcomer or people with a history of migration in their policy plans, even in the antipoverty plans. However, all official reports clearly reveal the vulnerability of people with a history of migration and newcomers. This systemic lack of attention is plunging the people with a history of migration into vulnerability and is destroying the fragile resilience of newcomers.

Local, regional and federal governments (and the European Union) must develop a migration policy based on the Human Rights and on a welcoming approach.

5.3.2 Strengthen their resilience, creating a more human society

‘A human being in peril’. This is one of the key sentences of their life stories. They are in danger. As members of a middle class, we have lost touch with the concept of peril. We have forgotten what it means to struggle every day. We must rethink what it means to be in danger, to fight each day for survival. This rethinking is only possible if we learn to listen to those who are actually struggling to survive. Not only should we listen, but we should also establish a true dialogue.

Social services are in the frontline. Social services must support people. They create the conditions for ‘can do and can become’. Newcomers confirm the support and are grateful for all the help they were given. But at the same time they don’t feel supported. They have to fight for help.

Social services have to endorse into their daily practice the right of support for everybody. Some social services have a charter that deals with the means of achieving their goals, a charter where ‘clients’ can consult their rights and entitlements. This charter needs to be introduced in the social service sector as such and has to be based on the notion of ‘a human being in peril’ and on the above mentioned dialogue.

The charter must, consequently, be translated into concrete actions that help people in peril. For example, a medical card for undocumented migrants could prevent long waiting hours and bureaucratic interventions¹⁶.

With a charter, social services will be more autonomous, free from political influences. We observed the change in support and assistance. Support is more restricted, conditional, limited, and in some cases arbitrary. Social services become an instrument for political goals. The consequences are grave. Support workers are more brutal, act in a more bureaucratic way and are, in some cases, simply discriminatory. They are obliged to limit their support or to redirect their support to other groups. They are obliged to refuse support for people in peril. This change has become obvious in the course of years.

A charter is a first step. On top of this, social services need to have the freedom to achieve their social goals.

The struggle for financial support lies at the very heart of many of their stories. The analyses show the arbitrariness of this support.

¹⁶ Different cities in Belgium have a medical card that gives undocumented migrants the possibility to get preventive and curative health care. See f.e. <http://www.ocmwgent.be/Medische-kaart-illegalen.html>. More information on medical support for undocumented migrants: <http://www.medimmigrant.be/uploads/Publicaties/Handleiding/DMH%20voor%20MZVWV%20handleiding%20voor%20OCM Wmedewerkers%20en%20zoraverstrekters%20%20basispakket%20NL.pdf>

Financial support in Belgium is limited and stays largely under the poverty threshold (AROP). Financial support must meet the ‘minimum income level’¹⁷, but reality is different.

Financial aid is necessary to live a more ‘normal’ life, to achieve ‘can do and can become’. These extras enable newcomers to rebound. These extras should be seen as an encouraging support and as a veritable right.

Most participants live in poor housing conditions. Tenant ‘rights’ are very limited. The scarcity of (decent and affordable) rental houses is huge, and the rent is high. The absence of a real social or affordable housing policy sustains and provokes the residuary house market.

The story of ‘can do and can become’ starts with a decent home. The lack of a social/affordable housing policy stifles every opportunity to live a normal life.

A lot of social support is provided by the NGOs. There are NGOs that offer support in the field of well-being (like CAW), and others that work with vulnerable people.

The very existence of NGOs working with vulnerable people is a means to meet the challenge of the concept of ‘a human being in peril’. They stand in the frontline. They are sometimes the safety net of the social system, even though that is not their first calling.

Today they are not (always) appreciated for this work. Nowadays they are more and more obliged to redefine their function as a safety net. The consequences of this refocusing are grave: people in peril are left behind.

NGOs working with vulnerable people must be appreciated for their social work, for their role as safety net, for the way they are working with vulnerable people. They need to be re-enforced.

¹⁷ The Belgium government declared that the existing minimum income schemes would be increased to 60% of the median income, and this before the end of their government term.

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The case of African immigrant women living in French suburbs

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Executive summary

This report is prepared in the framework of the Europe H2020 project ‘Rebuilding an inclusive, value based Europe of solidarity and trust through social investments’ (RE-InVEST). The project aims at evaluating the social investment strategy of the European Commission implemented in 2013 in response to the social damage of the financial crisis in 2008. The RE-InVEST consortium assesses the social damage of the crisis from human rights and capability based approaches by targetting those vulnerable groups which are mostly affected by the crisis in the 12 countries (and 13 regions) covered by the consortium. The analyses are carried out by local partners including NGOs and/or researchers.

The crisis of 2008 did not affect France in the same way as the other European countries. France was less involved into finance activities than England for instance, and did not face the bursting of such a housing bubble as in Spain or in Ireland. The crisis has affected more specifically the traditional business sectors and the situation of employment has deteriorated particularly for the least qualified workers. However, some territories resisted the crisis differently generating the emergence of unequal situations in the country, between regions and departments as well as among cities, and within cities. One refers to the unhooking of certain zones or poor areas, labelled as ‘priority areas’, and this is where the damages of the crisis appears to be the most significant. Those priority areas are, for most of them, at the heart or in the immediate vicinity of big urban areas. The poorest areas, at least in the Paris region, are also those where the immigrant population native of Africa (North and sub-Saharan Africa) is the most numerous, where there are many single-parent families, and where the social mix is limited. This is where the social difficulties are the most serious as well, causing the suburban riots in 2005 for instance, which started in the town of Clichy-sous-bois. Despite large urban renovation plans and various innovative systems designed for these areas and their population (for employment, housing, social support, security, etc.), the situation remains quite difficult. Inequalities tend to worsen since the beginning of the crisis, as the population is mostly affected by unemployment. For instance in 2014, the unemployment rate of the 15-64 year-old people reaches 27% there, compared to just 10% for the rest of the urban areas (same result at the national level). With this long-lasting crisis, the part of people in long-term unemployment strongly increases. The inactivity rate is also much higher there. One can notice, in these areas, the deepening of poverty, the drop-out and early school leaving of young people of which more than a third were neither employed nor on training, and the problems of delinquency. These issues are well documented thanks to devices like the observatories and the large surveys such as the Teo one (Trajectories and origins) (Beauchemin et al., 2016), which provides information on the trajectories of the immigrants living in France and the discriminations related to their origin.

Within the framework of the RE-InVEST project, we gave voice to several immigrant women, natives of sub-Saharan Africa and living in the priority areas of the Seine Saint Denis department which are located in the town of Aubervilliers. These women set up an association aiming at specific citizen activities such as the provision of remedial courses as homework help for children, the monitoring of teenagers in order to avoid them falling into criminal activities, the promotion of relationships between parents, the strengthening of women’s capacities by proposing literacy courses. All these activities can be analysed from the perspective of developing people’s capability to do and to be.

For these women, it is difficult to refer a precise date as the beginning of the crisis, one can rather speak about the feeling of a greater degradation of their daily life. Material difficulties are a constant cause of worries: unemployment or the lack of job security, difficult working conditions with staggered hours, difficulties for paying the house rent and even the children’s canteen, difficulties to face administrative requests once you are illiterate. Their own aspiration ‘to do and to be’, to find a job which interests them, to be more

autonomous during the administrative steps, all this requires reading and writing skills that they learn within the association. As they were born and have grown up in Western Africa where they still have relatives that they visit and help when possible, they express well, through the interviews, the conflict between cultures and the related difficulties for the education of their children. This is the results from a somewhat mythicised vision of the former education they have received from their country, which remains difficult for them to adjust in France. As many families are with single-parent and the fathers are either missing, or unemployed or stroke by long disease, they are at odds concerning their status in a culture which remains patriarchal.

The relationship to this particular area is ambivalent. On one side, these women may find solidarity thanks to the existence of various associations networks; on the other, it is also a hard life environment, due to delinquency risks which affect them, but moreover makes them to fear for their children, that they are not sure to be able to protect from a negative ripple effect. Especially because the low social mix in the area, the parents' unemployment or inactivity, the narrowness of professional perspectives and social integration contributes to a kind of despair that reaches some of the young people that have drop-out from school too early.

The crisis has exemplified these difficulties, because getting a job got worse for these populations. Other difficulties appeared more recently with negative consequences: the subsidies provide by the State to local communities are currently decreasing, reducing the support to the existing associations or cancelling the implementation of specific devices intended for the very vulnerable populations.

In their interviews, all women detailed their 'capacity to do and to be' in order to solve these issues and overcome the situation, i.e. by developing collective actions through their agency, and by improving their own potentialities through alphabetisation. However, the obstacles for the accomplishment of their aspirations are numerous and related to their individual situation (family and professional) as well as the area in which they live. Thus the role of the support devices is essential, i.e. by working directly with them, one can also expect an intergenerational benefit for the younger people.

Contents

List of figures	8
Introduction	9
1. Impact of the crisis: The deepening of inequalities, the increase of poverty and the unemployment rate	11
1.1 The manifestation of a large-scale and long-lasting crisis through unemployment and precarious work	11
1.2 A sharp increase in poverty within a context of growing disparities	12
1.2.1 Income inequality: The rich are becoming richer and the poor poorer	12
1.2.2 The living conditions: A worsening of housing related problems	13
1.3 Social and spatial inequalities: The focus on priority areas	13
1.4 The immigrant people of African origin: Crossing various vulnerabilities	14
1.4.1 A high proportion of immigrants from Africa and their descendants are in the priority areas	14
1.4.2 Gender Inequalities are greater in priority areas	15
2. The participatory research approach	16
2.1 Participatory Action Human Rights and the Capability Approach	16
2.2 Choice of the group	17
2.3 The current process	18
2.3.1 Individual interviews and discourse analysis	18
2.3.2 The focus-groups	19
2.4 The various hypotheses	19
3. From Africa to Parisian suburbs: Two women's life paths	20
3.1 Hawa's story	20
3.2 Mariam's story	22
4. Analysis: how do those African women deal with an adverse environment?	25
4.1 Diverse categories of situations and trajectories	25
4.1.1 Methodology: Textual analysis of the testimonies	25
4.1.2 Four different classes of discourse	25
4.2 The difficulties for accessing to the basic rights	27
4.2.1 A long pathway for settlement	27
4.2.2 Accommodation: a basic right not always ensured	28
4.2.3 Employment: hard work and increasing precariousness	28
4.2.4 The access to services: the risk of digital exclusion	29
4.3 Usual family patterns are changing	29
4.3.1 Gender relationships are evolving	29
4.3.2 More female heads of family	29
4.4 Inclusion: a key role for the associations	30
5. Conclusion	31
appendix 1 Main characteristics of the participants for individual interviews	33
Bibliography	35

List of figures

Figure 2.1	Resources, conversion factors, capability set and achieved fonctionnings	16
Figure 2.2	Situation of Aubervilliers, inner suburbs of Paris (source: Idé)	18
Figure 3.1	Hawa's cloud of words (analysis from the original record by Wordle software)	22
Figure 3.2	Mariam's cloud of words (analysis from the original record by Wordle software)	24
Figure 4.1	Multiple correspondance: discourse analysis	26

Introduction

This report is prepared in the framework of the Europe H2020 project ‘Rebuilding an inclusive, value-based Europe of solidarity and trust through social investments’ (RE-InVEST). The RE-InVEST project aims to contribute to a more solidary and inclusive European Union, through a powerful and effective social investment strategy implemented at the EU level. Moreover, the project itself adopts a participative approach that gives voice to the vulnerable groups and the civil society organisations. The RE-InVEST consortium is composed of members from the informal network called ‘the Alliances to fight Poverty’, a network of civil society organisations, trade unions, policy makers and academics co-ordinated by the Flemish Christian labour movement *Beweging.net*, which is committed to the setting of a more inclusive Europe. The consortium covers a broad range of European countries (12 countries and 13 regions) representing various levels of welfare and different labour market traditions. All analyses are carried out by the local partners, who cover a set of NGOs and academic researchers.

In particular, this report is one of the 13 national reports that constitute the qualitative research dimension of the RE-InVEST work package entitled ‘The social damage of the crisis’. This work package (WP3) focuses on the living experience of vulnerable people by addressing the impact of the crisis (and the crisis-related policy reform) on vulnerable groups as well as the impact of growing inequality and vulnerability on social distrust. Our two key hypothesis in this regard are the following. First, growing distrust and indeed resentment among the population may be attributed to a rejection of the neoliberal policies employed by national as well as European elites in recent years. Second, this integrated diagnosis is built on the idea that there has been, in the European Union, a disinvestment in terms of individual and collective capabilities and an erosion of the basic social rights. This implies that the experiences of insecurity, poverty and social degradation need to be assessed and deeply re-analysed from those perspectives.

Through 13 qualitative case studies, this work package provides a cross-validation of these experiences through a report describing trends in selected quantitative indicators that reflect the relation between socio-economic vulnerability, human rights and capabilities. A third element consists of a statistical analysis of the dynamic relationship between vulnerability, shifts in social policies and trust, with the objective of answering to the following questions. In which sections of the population has the trust in institutions declined most? Can different patterns between countries be observed? Can they be explained by differences in policy shifts and differences in resilience of the civil society? An European synthesis report will combine the main findings from these three types of analyses.

This qualitative research focuses on the experience of vulnerable groups in each of the 12 countries, and 13 regions, participating in the RE-InVEST project. Mixed teams of researchers, NGO and union workers, practitioners and people from vulnerable groups jointly analysed cases where the crisis has impacted on human rights and individual, as well as collective, capabilities.

In France, in order to address the issue of vulnerability related to the current crisis, we selected the members of our focus-group according to two major criteria:

1. the fact of being a woman from the immigrant population of sub-Saharan Africa (particularly from West African countries like Mali, Senegal, Guinea and Côte d'Ivoire);
2. and the fact of living in a so-called 'priority area'¹ belonging to Paris or a town within the Paris suburbs.

By processing in this way, we are addressing three different types of vulnerability, each requiring specific information, which can be then crossed together:

1. spatial vulnerability, because those 'priority areas' are concentrating various forms of poverty. They are often designed as 'difficult neighbourhoods', with a lot of problems related to poverty, i.e. the degradation of public services and infrastructure, delinquency and youth crime, etc.;
2. social vulnerability, which is directly linked to the cultural origin of immigrants, especially those coming from sub-Saharan Africa;
3. gender vulnerability. Due to the unequal access to school in their own country, girls are often less qualified than men, and many of them are illiterate. Moreover, a number of them are at the head of a mono-parental families and, therefore, the only adult in the household that is currently working.

¹ Priority Areas: Since 2014, urban policies have set up a priority list of 1,296 areas within 700 communes. These areas are defined on the basis of income, i.e. more than half the population is under 60% of the median income tax. They are the subject of targeted interventions. This unique threshold replaces various devices, including the Sensitive Urban Zones (ZUS), which were characterised by large group of buildings, deprived housing neighborhoods and imbalance between housing and employment. In practice, these 'priority areas' are defined using a grid method. It involves cutting the French metropolitan territory into several squares of 200 meters on each side and then referring to statistical information showing the concentration of poverty (data from the Observatoire national de la politique de la ville, 2016: 14).

1. Impact of the crisis: The deepening of inequalities, the increase of poverty and the unemployment rate

1.1 The manifestation of a large-scale and long-lasting crisis through unemployment and precarious work

France was less involved in the finance activity than England, for instance, and did not face the bursting of housing bubble as in Spain or in Ireland. The crisis affected only gradually the French real economy. Small businesses suffered quite early from the reduction of credits allocation, and job cuts started after 2009. The traditional business sectors, as car production, building and construction, transportation and logistics, were particularly affected. Regarding unemployment, the situation continued to deteriorate even though public investment programs played a major role to weaken the effects of the crisis (Nahapétian, 2011). Unlike other European countries, the decrease of social spending and transfers (minimum income, health, education, etc.) was not so strong. However, these devices were insufficient to halt the impoverishment of some categories of population.

The degradation of the labour market occurred in multiple forms, with important disparities among social categories and territories.² France has experienced a high unemployment rate for 30 years but it shifted from 7% in 2008 to almost 10% in 2014. The decrease observed since one year remains modest³ and indeed does not address the most precarious cases. France in 2016 counts about 3 million unemployed people, according to the ILO (International Labour Organisation) standards, of which more than a third are unemployed for more than one year (i.e. long-term unemployment). The current situation is characterised by the increase of this long-term unemployment, even very long-term unemployment (when it is more than 24 months), by an increase of job insecurity (through short contracts, part-time jobs), and by the slowing evolution of the salaries in some business sectors. Moreover, this deterioration of the labour market affects in an uneven way the various categories of population according to their gender, age, origin, qualification and living area. It triggers and enhances social and spatial inequalities.

Gender disparities are evolving. The gap, in the labour force over the last thirty years, between the activity rate⁴ of women, aged 25 to 49 years old, has been strongly reduced compared to that of men. In 2013, this gap was only 10 points, i.e. 84% for women and 94% for men. Thus the integration of women into the labour market has been regular, though such a progress stopped after 2010. Concerning the unemployment rate, the one of men was lower in 2008 than the one of women, but six years later, it is the opposite that can be noticed (Maurin, 2016). This may be explained by the employment situation in sectors already gendered, e.g. low-skilled jobs services which are mostly gathering women like cleaning-related services, services to individuals. On the contrary, some sectors largely dominated by men, such as construction or industry, have been highly affected since the beginning of the crisis. It does not necessarily mean that the quality of the female employment is always enviable as the least skilled jobs are marked by staggered hours, precariousness and part-time work, all this concerning particularly the women. Yet, the risk of long-term unemployment is 2.4 times more important for single parents, compared to people living in couples. Two thirds

2 In this part, we rely on the data of the French National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies (INSEE) and on the analysis of the French Observatory of Inequalities (2015).

3 As the French working population increases by approximately 160,000 persons every year, due to the current demographic dynamism.

4 The activity rate is expressed, for a given category of population, by the ratio between the number of active people (employed, and unemployed but wishing to be employed) and the population size of this category.

of these single-parent families are led by women, who are rather less qualified than those living in couples (Bruneau et al., 2016).

Age groups are also differently affected. As throughout the European Union, the crisis has severely struck the age group 15-24 years old, particularly the 37% of them which are not in training. Those have more difficulty to enter the labour market, especially if they are low skilled. With age, the risk of unemployment decreases. However, the difficulty to get out of unemployment increases afterwards for the seniors, i.e. people more than 55 years old.

Inequalities between territories are also quite clear. The Northern part of France, because of the deindustrialisation process, and the Mediterranean region face at the same time high unemployment and poverty rates. In priority areas, like the Seine Saint Denis, a department in Paris suburb, the long-term unemployment rate is three times more than in the rest of metropolitan France. This is due to the accumulation of difficulties, as the population is less qualified, and mainly composed of immigrants from African origin, from Maghreb or sub-Saharan, who undergo discrimination linked to this origin.

1.2 A sharp increase in poverty within a context of growing disparities

1.2.1 Income inequality: The rich are becoming richer and the poor poorer

With no surprise, the link between unemployment and poverty is clearly established. This is particularly true for those people in long-term unemployment who are receiving minimum social benefits and are reaching the end of their allowance. Therefore the number of long-term unemployed, not receiving any allowance and having only the minimum social standard to live, has been multiplied by three since 2008. However, the crisis also generated a sharp increase in the proportion of the working poor, i.e. those living under the poverty line, which is 60% of the median income. This is due to the low wages of the least qualified jobs in several sectors, to the ratio of involuntary part-time work, and to the division of jobs with alternative periods of employment, unemployment and inactivity (Observatoire des inégalités, 2015). At the end of 2015, 2.28 million households in metropolitan France benefited from the active solidarity income (RSA), a specific allowance paid to the households with low income, according to age condition, i.e. being more than 25 years old, and to the level of income and the family composition; thus, the allowance increases with the number of dependants.

During the crisis, the gap between the richest and the poorest people largely widened illustrating a sharp increase of the inequalities. Between 2008 and 2012, the number of people living under the poverty line increased by 800,000 reaching 4.8 million in 2012. 30% of the population with the lowest income experienced a strong deterioration while the 10% richest saw their revenues rise sharply (Observatoire des inégalités, 2015; Alternatives Economiques, 2015). The intermediary groups above the median, i.e. the middle class, have rather seen their income stagnated.

Poverty does not affect in the same way all age groups. The seniors, i.e. more than 60 years old, represents 10% of the poor people and are a little less concerned by poverty than the rest of the population. The children and teenagers, i.e. less than 20 years, who are already poor because they live within poor families, are particularly affected. They constitute a quarter of the 4.8 million poor people earning less than 50% of the median income. According to the UNICEF (2015), the intergenerational impact is quite strong: 'The permanence of a precarious future is a constant (...). These are paying the heaviest price for the economic crisis because poverty greatly hinders their development, increases long-term vulnerability, and makes their future uncertain'

1.2.2 The living conditions: A worsening of housing related problems

The poverty of living conditions adds up to monetary poverty based on income. In France, one of the most worrisome case is related to the housing conditions.

The country faced a very important housing crisis after the Second World War up and this until the 1970s. Some huge construction programs were implemented with the objective of reducing all precarious housing. Therefore the slums were destroyed and large accommodation estates were built mainly in the outskirts of Paris, allowing the resettlement of hundred of families.

Despite significant improvement, poor accommodation still remains an acute issue in France. According to the Abbé Pierre Foundation, the number of people poorly housed in 2015 would be 3.5 million, including 665,000 that are deprived from an adequate home. This includes the homeless, those living in very precarious housing conditions like a hut, those hosted in reception centres and those forced to live at a third party's home in difficult conditions. These figures have risen subsequently after the crisis of 2008.

The other forms of poor accommodation are linked with the lack of comfort and safety, with 2.1 million people concerned, and to overcrowding⁵ (Abbé Pierre Fondation, 2015). The increase in real estate prices as well as in the level of the rent makes the access to adequate accommodation, adjusted to the family size, harder and harder for popular categories. Those categories being already confronted to low wages and hit by the high level of unemployment. More than 50% of the immigrants native of Sub-Saharan Africa, whose incomes are low and the family large, live within overcrowded accommodation, often in those priority areas already targeted by the current urban policies (Observatoire des inégalités, 2015).

1.3 Social and spatial inequalities: The focus on priority areas

During the last four decades, many of the urban areas which were built up in the 1950s to the 1970s underwent various evolutions. Some of them deteriorated strongly and the middle-class categories left them. The people who live there at present have a density three times greater than in the rest of the country. These urban areas are concentrating a low-skilled population which is quite vulnerable. Therefore they resisted differently to the crisis, generating an increase in unequal situations and the drop-out of some neighbourhood and poor population. 'Those, who suffer the most from the damages engendered by the crisis, live mainly at the heart of urban conglomerations or immediately close to them. The remote rural and urban poverty still exists indeed, but they remain quantitatively limited. A large number of phenomena that we observe regarding inequalities are not linked to a territory effect but, before all, to the social composition of the population' (Alternatives Economiques, 2015).

These vulnerable populations are mainly concentrated in urban areas, especially in those priority areas, which have been identified in the framework of the National urban policy.⁶ These areas are defined by a single criterion, which is the concentration of low-income households in a given space, based on a precise grid of the territory.⁷ This criterion is expressed by a synthetic indicator of the social difficulties encountered. Those priority areas are mostly the neighbourhoods of large cities, particularly in the Ile de France region, but also in some smaller provincial towns. Despite many urban renewal projects related to the national urban policy, these areas are still marked by spatial inequalities in their access to local public services, to

5 An accommodation is considered as uncomfortable if there is at least one deprived element of comfort: no safety, difficult to heat or not able to be heated, without hot water, or without toilets inside. A house or a flat is considered overcrowded according to specific INSEE criteria related to its available surface related to the age and the status of its inhabitants.

6 The National urban policy is a transversal policy the priority of which is to reduce the gap between deprived areas and other neighborhoods in the city where it is implemented. It relies on the strengthening of common law policies (on education, employment, health, etc.) and the mobilisation of special devices (urban renovation, support to associations, etc.). For thirty years, the National urban policy has been acting on various levers: social, economic or urban, in order to correct the trajectories of these targeted areas and reduce their dropout from the whole city (Dariau et al., 2014).

7 The priority areas have been defined by the grid method. It involves cutting the metropolitan territory into squares of 200 meters on each side and then introducing statistical data to show the concentration of poverty.

merchant services, to adequate transport, and to good standard accommodation, and stigma. The consequences are high on the individual and collective capabilities related to mobility, to access to employment and services, as shown in the analysis of Bourdeau-Lepage and Tovar (2013).

The demographics of these priority areas reveal a younger population than in the other neighbourhoods, i.e. 25% under 14 years against 17%, with a significant share of large families (6 and more) and an over-representation of single parent families. 87% of the households are tenants against 42% in the other neighbourhoods (Dariau *et al.*, 2014).

As highlighted by the Observatory of Territories in its 2014 report: 'In fact, since 2008, the trend towards the reduction of spatial disparities in the residents' income was reversed: the gaps have widened not only between the areas but also between individuals within the same area. Regional economies that were less dynamic in the decades 1990 and 2000 suffered more, and their vulnerable population (the poorest households, the workers, the migrants, etc.) were the most affected'. Thus, unemployment hit more hardily the priority areas: in 2005, the unemployment rate was 19% for the priority areas against 8.5% at national level. In 2014, the unemployment rate (15-64 ans) reaches 27% for priority areas against 9.3% at national level (Observatoire national de la politique de la ville, 2016).

Since the beginning of the crisis, the analysts used to speak of a real 'stall' in these areas with nearly 40% of the population living below the poverty line in 2014. This is a proportion three times higher than the remaining territory of France. The difficulties encountered by the inhabitants are reflected in the reduced use of health care, the poor housing conditions, and a major school failure with a lower success rate in the corresponding colleges, and a proportion of 'neet'⁸ youngsters greater than in other neighbourhoods.

1.4 The immigrant people of African origin: Crossing various vulnerabilities

1.4.1 A high proportion of immigrants from Africa and their descendants are in the priority areas

In France, the immigration of African origin (North Africa and sub-Saharan Africa) is more recent, i.e. after 1960, than the one of European origin; currently, 37% in the descendants of immigrants are of African origin and they are younger than the overall population of immigrant descendants.⁹ At first a male labour migration, it then became a family migration due to the possibility of family gathering after 1976. The territorial distribution is quite heterogeneous; however it concentrates about 40% of this population in priority areas, notably in the Ile of France region.

If the level of training of these young descendants of African immigrants or other non-European countries is higher than that of their parents, it remains, however, below the average of the same age group. Thus, the non-graduate rate reaches 28% against 14% for the young non-immigrant. This qualification deficit is one of the main difficulties for professional insertion, to which is added the discrimination based on the personal origin and accommodation area¹⁰ (Petit *et al.*, 2016). This is shown by several studies among which one is entitled 'Living in ZUS (sensitive urban areas) and be immigrant: a double risk to access to the labour market' (Okba, 2009). At the end of schooling, professional insertion is more hectic with periods of employment, of unemployment and even inactivity. It is difficult to find a sustainable employment, at least one year continuously. However, the young immigrants and the descendants of these immigrants represent 57% of the population aged 18-29 living in priority areas of large cities (DARES, 2014 b).

⁸ Neet: Not in education, employment or training.

⁹ In 2012, in the population of 15-64 years, one estimates at 1.9 million immigrants of African origin and 1.5 million of descendants.

¹⁰ The study of Bunuel *et al.* (2014) assessed the differences between being from Paris and living in the Seine St Denis department in the access to a job interview according to the address on the candidates resume, while personal characteristics remain equivalent (diploma, name, experience). We observe a significant 'district effect' with a preference of the employers for Paris, and also a significant 'area effect', with a preference for the least deprived areas.

1.4.2 Gender Inequalities are greater in priority areas

For a long time, there has been a kind of ‘invisibility’ of the women and girls living in priority areas. Social tensions manifested by sporadic riots, for instance those particularly violent in 2005. This raises interest for the issue of the ‘young’, considered as a neutral word but, in fact, more oriented towards its masculine dimension. The reality of women and girls is still often hidden, except in the case of criminal episodes like gang rape, e.g. the ‘rotating’ behaviour in the cellars.

Gender inequalities are massive in the priority areas, largely overlapping social inequalities, and reinforcing them. They take various forms that are related to spatial inequalities expressed through a degraded habitat,¹¹ scarce public transport, and insecurity that restricts the mobility of women in the public space.¹² Even if the entire population is somehow penalised, the impact differs according to gender. For cultural reasons, women bear, more than elsewhere in the territory, all tasks related to domestic housework and the care of children. They must cope with the difficulties to access to shops and services like food procurement related to the gender division of labour. This reduced access to services is highlighted by a specific study of EGALiTER (2014). Moreover, insecurity is heavier for women who are more vulnerable to sexual assault. Regarding the access to jobs, the situation has become more precarious since the beginning of the crisis. The long-term inactivity of young people (at least one year continuously) is greater for women: ‘They are more likely to withdraw from the labour market, they are less frequently on long-term contracts and their jobs include more part time, more late hours, and Sunday work’ (Henry and Dieusaert, 2014). This type of jobs, with unsociable hours, is particularly heavy for those women who are single-parent with young children and live in areas poorly served by public transport. This finding of long-lasting inactivity of women in priority areas is particularly worrying because it is the opposite of the situation in non-priority areas. Indeed, at national level and on a short term basis, women’s employment seems to have less suffered from the crisis than men’s one, because they occupy specific segments of the labour market (Henry & Dieusaert, 2014).

In these priority areas, the share of single-parent families with at least one child under 14 years is more than double that of the rest of France; the overwhelming majority of these households are headed by women (90%); since the beginning of the crisis, poverty increased with more than a third of single-parent families now living below the poverty line, against less than one out of 6 on average for France (EGALiTER, 2014; HCE/f-h, 2014; UNICEF, 2015).

Consequently, the populations of the priority areas often accumulate various forms of vulnerability: exposure to unemployment due to their low level of qualification, discrimination linked with their origin and their place of residence (priority areas), and gender inequalities to the detriment of women.

11 Faulty elevators in real estate towers over 10 floors, stairwells degraded and occupied by gangs, etc. All urban renewal programs and specific projects are regularly addressing this issue, and this for several years.

12 A recent report from the HCE/f-h ‘diagnosed the phenomenon of gender harassment and sexual violence in transport as a massive, violent, and with significant adverse impact, particularly for the victims and witnesses. It constitutes a violation of human rights (mobility freedom and right to security), an obstacle to the equal access to public transportation services, and gender violence. This phenomenon particularly affects girls and young women. Therefore, public transport is a major vector of freedom for the women who use it more than men. This continuum of violence has a negative impact of on their own lives, generating a feeling of insecurity in the public space, a constraint to mobility, to personal dressing and behavior injunctions, fear of judgement on their look, their sexual life and their ability to please to men, etc.), as it has for the whole living together (by slowing sociability, strengthening gender stereotypes, etc.), and the maintenance of inequality and discrimination between women and men.

2. The participatory research approach

2.1 Participatory Action Human Rights and the Capability Approach

Re-InVEST aims at investigating the philosophical, institutional and empirical foundations of an inclusive Europe of solidarity and trust. To this end it draws on capability and human rights based participatory approaches. Human rights form a common European basis of values and describe at the same time core elements of what constitutes well-being and a good life. Further, human rights are transformative by empowering people.

Human rights are the basic rights and freedoms that belong to everyone. International law, including treaties, contain the provisions which give human rights legal effect. Human Rights are universally agreed basic standards that aim to ensure that every person is treated with dignity and respect; they include Civil and Political Rights, such as the right to life, the right to a fair trial and the right not to be subjected to torture; and Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, such as the right to work, to join a trade union, to health, to education, and to an adequate standard of living. They are interdependent and indivisible, they belong to all people without discrimination. For vulnerable people the usage of a rights-terminology has proven to change their perspective by making them aware of their rights and the ways in which their current situation compromises these rights.

The capability approach as developed by Sen (1999) and Nussbaum (2011) defines a person's well-being in terms of the beings and doings (the functionings) a person achieves and her capability to choose among different combinations of such functionings. For leading a life one values and has reason to value resources and conversion factors are preconditions (Figure 2.1). Resources refer to the material conditions of a person: her income, the goods and services she disposes of. Conversion factors help her converting resources into doing and being well. There are personal conversion factors such as skills and bodily features, social conversion factors such as social norms and social institutions and environmental conversion factors such as climate, geography but also public equipments. In the end both the achieved functionings as well as the freedom to choose a life one values matters.

Figure 2.1 Resources, conversion factors, capability set and achieved functionings

For assessing the capabilities of vulnerable people Re-InVEST aims at giving them a voice. Their participation is fostered by relying on participatory action research that directly results in policy recommendations. Participatory action research views participants as co-researchers who have special knowledge about their

own situation. Hence they are not only asked or interviewed on their views but take part in research by engaging in, examining, interpreting, and reflecting on their own social world, shaping their sense of identity. Crucial for this kind of knowledge generation is the ‘merging’ or ‘crossing of knowledge’ that comes from three parts: scientific knowledge as gained by researchers; knowledge which the poor and excluded have, from their first-hand experience, of the twin realities of poverty and the surrounding world which imposes it on them; and the knowledge of those who work among and with these victims in places of poverty and social exclusion. We used the methodology developed by ATD Fourth World, and specially the ‘guidelines for merging of knowledge and practices when working with people in situations of poverty and social exclusion’ (Godinot & Wodon, 2006; Fourth World-University Research, 2007).

2.2 Choice of the group

To study the impact of the crisis on vulnerable people, we choose as a target group the immigrant women native of West Africa who are living in priority areas, i.e. the poor areas of the Ile de France region, covering Paris and the Parisian suburbs. The choice of this particular group was made in connection with the city hall of the town Aubervilliers. The office in charge of the link with the associations recommended to us the association AVISA, which was recently created by several women natives of sub-Saharan Africa who were living in a priority area of this town named La Maladrerie. Those women are often illiterate and are working in low-skilled jobs, often on a part-time basis or being split into fragments of activities contributing to their precariousness; they are also facing discrimination due to their origins or the place where they live (see Part 1.4). The features of discrimination are described through TeO survey and analysed in Beauchemin *et al.*, (2016).

The main objective of AVISA is to favour the integration of these women in the French society by promoting in the same time adults’ education, i.e. alphabetisation of illiterate women, and remedial courses for their children. For these children, it constitutes preventive actions against juvenile delinquency by encouraging their school successes. It is also a way of preventing them from rambling around in the streets. Moreover, the association wishes to provide support to the economic initiatives of its members, for instance, by designing project and looking for adequate financing, even if this is not yet fully effective. AVISA has about sixty members, mainly women, but also a few men, who know to read and write, and therefore are monitoring the administrative work. Because of such commitment, we also have interviewed them.

In parallel, we started collaboration with the GRDR,¹³ which supportive activities aim at promoting capacity building programs for the migrant population in the Ile-de-France region. The GRDR, which joined recently, in 2016, the RE-InVEST consortium, conducted also a focus-group in relation to its own programs¹⁴ on the immigrant women natives of sub-Saharan Africa, living in the priority areas of the town Aubervilliers and in the northern part of Paris (19th district). This focus-group was composed of 10 women from Mali (4) Mauritania (4), Senegal (1) and Côte d’Ivoire (1).

¹³ The GRDR (Migrations - Citizenship - Development) is a French association in the field of international solidarity, which is working on issues related to migration, citizenship and development. They are currently conducting several programs on the insertion of young people of African origin in the urban priority urban areas of the 'Ile de France' region (Paris and surroundings, or suburbs). Through its agency network, the GRDR works closely with several migrants' associations, therefore monitoring social and solidarity-based activities at the local and international levels.

¹⁴ For instance: (i) the PRIF program (Program for the Strengthening of Women Initiatives), which provides support to the migrant women who are bearing associative and economic projects; and (ii) the PAPAI program (Program of Support for the Elderly Immigrants) which concerns the access to rights of the elderly immigrants.

Figure 2.2 Situation of Aubervilliers, inner suburbs of Paris (source: Idé)

2.3 The current process

2.3.1 Individual interviews and discourse analysis

We met three times with the members of the association AVISA in order to explain the objectives of the Re-InVEST project, then to talk about the main problems that they are facing, particularly since the 2008 crisis, and to have them express their own aspirations.

These meetings allowed us to highlight the big issues that are specific to the members of this group and we developed them through individual interviews. These were done through specific appointment, each interview lasting between 40 to 60 minutes, sometimes even a little more. We met in that way more than 20 persons. The interview was semi-structured: we first asked a number of specific information related to sex, age, country of origin, date of arrival in France, family situation, number of children in charge, employment status, and situation as regards with the spouse's employment if married (since there are several single-parent families led by women in this group). Then we discussed several topics related to:

- The motivations and reasons which led them to go to France and their migration pathway.
- The evolution of their employment status and conditions over the last 5 years, for them and their spouse. How has the crisis affected them? Through job losses for themselves or somebody within the family, loss of qualifying skills, aid reduction, losses of specialised services (due to cuts in the community budget).
- Their life in the neighbourhood, with its advantages and disadvantages concerning mobility, insecurity, access to services, quality of housing.
- The way they organise themselves and with the help of whom: for instance a caring neighbourhood, the support from associations, some reciprocal aid, etc. The objective being to highlight the importance of collective capabilities and agency.
- The women's aspirations
 - *At the neighbourhood level* by focussing on the equipment and infrastructure available, on the community life, their participation in meetings with the neighbourhood council, or within informal groups.
 - *At the individual level* by looking at their training patterns and agenda, the courses to which they gain access. This in order to understand how it fits with their aspirations, and what are the opportunities available for achieving these aspirations.

- Their relationship with their country of origin. Do they have a project to return there? How do they keep relationship with their family?

With contentment of the respondent, the interviews were recorded and treated by the means of a textual analysis software, named Alceste, the results of which are presented in the following analysis. Alceste stands for 'Analyse des Lexèmes Co-occurents dans les Énoncés Simples d'un Texte' (Analysis of the co-occurring lexemes within the simple statements of a text).

2.3.2 The focus-groups

The focus group was conducted by the GRDR as part of its work with immigrant women from sub-Saharan Africa, particularly the program for seniors who are looking for the access to their social rights related to health and retirement. The corresponding interviews were transcribed either in full or in the form of note taking. For the analysis, we relied on the GRDR's experience in these areas. Its work consolidates the observations which already appeared during the debate within the focus-groups.

2.4 The various hypotheses

Several group meetings combined to existing research studies allowed to suggest a series of working hypotheses on the impact of the 2008 crisis.

- First, the vulnerable populations living in priority areas did not feel the specificities of this crisis as a sudden breakdown, but rather as an extension of a deterioration of their own situation, particularly regarding their employment and living conditions.
- Second, being often not qualified or low-skilled, and illiterate, women remain confined in little gratifying jobs. This is the case for the office cleaning and work in hotels, for which the working conditions are difficult including staggered working hours, fragmented workplaces requiring many means of transport, etc. They express other aspirations, but their main issue remains the fight against illiteracy.
- Third, women project themselves through their children and they are deeply concerned by the future of these young people particularly in priority areas where they may be confronted to drugs, gangs, etc. Therefore, they take initiatives and get together, through associations like AVISA, in order to act at their own level.

3. From Africa to Parisian suburbs: Two women's life paths

3.1 Hawa's story¹⁵

Hawa is a Malian woman who is born in Mali around 1975. She grew up in Bamako, until she was 18 years old. She was a street trader. She went to a Koranic School, but not to the official public one, so she couldn't read nor write. She left Mali with a touristic visa, and then stayed in France at her sister's home, as an illegal immigrant while she was looking for a job. When the cohabitation became difficult with her sister, she decided to leave in order to avoid familial tensions:

I did not want to create problems with my sister, for she is my half-sister. With this problem, if I raised the issue in Africa, everyone would be against me (...). Actually, it is better that people in Africa should not bear about our troubles here.'

Being paperless, she stayed within precarious housing arrangements, until a social worker helped her find a place in a social welfare home. Meanwhile, she met a Malian man who was working in Germany. He was already married. She gave birth to a little girl, while still living in the welfare home.

Getting her own flat took several years, and for long it was her main worry. Meanwhile, she was able to find a work as a housemaid:

I want a place to sleep, I can work, I have two hands and two feet, I am never sick. I only want a place to sleep with my daughter'. She got an open-minded spirit from this difficult experience: 'I made friends with many people because before I have lived in social welfare homes, in several flats, usually as colocation. It makes ideas exchange, and you can discover people as well and they know more about you too.'

After many applications, the social worker was able to secure a flat for her in 2008. After that, her daughter's father came back from Germany to join her in France, where he found a work. She got three other children. She did not want her children to suffer while they were occupying the first social welfare home because it was too small. So she waited to move in this new flat before having more kids. Now, she does not complain about her housing and she appreciates the neighbourhood which is mostly composed of Malians, Arabs and Senegalese. Nevertheless, she notices that having young people wandering around in the quarter after 6 pm is quite catastrophic.

'They are dealing drugs. Those are only 12-13 year-old kids. You see them at 5-6 pm during the week-ends. It is such a pity.' She considers that leisure activities intended for the young people should not stop during the holidays in order to prevent them from wandering around.

She then obtained the French citizenship. She kept working part time, but her husband fell severely ill two years ago, while the small business he was working forgot closed for legal reasons (i.e. the non-payment of social security obligations).

'My husband has lost everything. He was on sick-leave and he lost everything. He only obtained 500 or 600€ per month. He has got the 100% CMU (universal health coverage).' Her husband's indemnities being too small, she got a permanent full-time contract as a house-maid in a hotel, but with two hours of transportation every day. *'It is far but I do not have any other solution. Lately, the work-charge got heavier. Now, I am working more. Before, I was cleaning 10 rooms, now I'm in charge of 15-20 rooms every day.'*

¹⁵ We mention here only the first name of the respondent (not the family name), who gave her verbal agreement.

Her mother who lives in Mali is sick. Hawa stayed three months there in 2014 to take care of her. They had to pay 60€ per day at the hospital. This year, she plans to go there alone if they do not have enough money to take all the children. She tries to send money to her mother when she gets some, or she buys medicines for her. She has also sent her crutches.

Hawa wishes to progress in life:

'I don't want to work in hotels until retirement. I want to change profession and work with children on language learning and training.'

She followed several trainings with various associations in order to read and write in French.

'My problem is that I know how to write but I cannot read. Before, I followed several trainings with associations which provided me French classes, but I need more time for learning.'

Therefore, working and caring for the children, prevents her from succeeding yet in learning how to read. However, she is aware of the handicap that this represents:

'In my work, one needs to read and write. They could fire me, because they need literate people. My job is not secure despite my permanent contract.' However, she tries to help her surrounding by exploiting her social network.

Then, she got involved in the creation of the AVISA association, which aims at generating relationships between people through several activities such as women's alphabetisation and homework support for school children.

'Another purpose of the association is to create relationships between the parents of the school children. If you know them, you can speak to them. It makes things change. If the children have nothing to do, they drift (...). That's why we have created this association, to move a little ahead altogether. One could see that many things happen.'

She believes that adults' alphabetisation and education for children would help the immigrants to live a better life in France.

'I think that the foreigners suffer more than the French people here. The French kids and the foreign kids do not receive the same education.'

She thinks it is important that the foreigners fit well in the French society.

'Even though we could not respect your culture 100%, we really would like to fit in, starting by knowing how to read and write in French.'

Although Malians are hard workers, they would suffer in France because they did not fit in the society. She is there referring to the Malian way of living in France, through their dressing, the communication.

Then, she looked for another job and found one at la Défense, which is still currently her job. She is a cleaning woman at the mall and works full time with a long-term contract.

'It is not exactly what I want, but I do not have any choice.'

She works from 6 am to 1 pm every day. She works with regular contract, of 3 years for instance, and moves from one company to another. She lives far from her workplace. She has to wake up at 4 am and to take the first bus and metro.

'I walk alone, I am afraid, it is very hard. But I do not have any choice because my husband does not work.'

She now has the French nationality and her real objective is to work in nursery schools for the young people or in a canteen in her own area. However, she has not found any opportunity for the moment despite the many applications that she has sent during the last three or four years via the town hall. She noticed a change in the access to work these last years: it has become more difficult to find a job, even as cleaning woman.

'But even tomorrow, if I find a better job nearer to my home, I would quit. Because here, I have to leave at 4 am.'

She also have little choice because her husband does not work, he has been sick for two years after a cerebrovascular accident. Before, he used to work as a cleaner. She benefits from the mutual health insurance and her husband is reimbursed at 100%.

Her eldest son has a job:

'But not the good one. My son distributes newspapers but it is just 2h a day. He starts at 5 am and finishes at 7 am. He is looking for another job'. He prepares himself to be a nurse for the militaries. All her kids are going to school. One who is 17 is presently in high school and is going to sit for the baccalaureate. He plans to pursue his studies after that. The younger ones are good pupils.' It is her friend Gakou who takes care of their homework as she is illiterate.

She feels good at her home place. She finds it quiet, but the only problem is that they are far from all local services; no shops, no good public transportation. She applied for a new lodging as they are on the fourth floor with no elevator. She even thought of leaving work, but she understands that getting a job is not easy at present time. Nevertheless, it becomes difficult for her to pay the rent of their flat as she did not get any supplementary allocation since her husband fell sick. She really has no explanation to the fact that they did not get any allocation.¹⁶ During six years, they could pay the rent of their previous flat because they both worked. They even used to have a big house, but they moved out in 2007. Now, she has got some new payment delay, and the social worker advices her to pay her rent little by little.¹⁷ For her, the current administrative procedures are quite complicated.

In her opinion, the issue with the young people of these areas is, first, that when the couple is away for work, the children do not hesitate to ramble out.

'Why do women have to work if men already do? This is why I resigned while I was working in the evening. There was no adult at home'. Second, it might be caused by poverty. Being jobless, they would just pick up the bags from those who are passing-by.'

She loves France and Mali as well. Her mother is still over there, and when she has enough money to buy air tickets she is used to go there,

'Because it is about my mother ... and as long as she is still alive, but that does not happen often, only every 2 or 3 years. Now that her kids are big enough, she may take them on holidays over there with her, but she cannot afford air tickets for all of them. She bothers most for the lodging and her own job. She wishes to get a job within her own Commune. That is extremely important to her as her husband's health state is not reassuring. I am afraid that my husband cannot get back to

¹⁶ Note: This is because they are indebted by their housing rent. Therefore, this allocation is directly used to repay the owner.

¹⁷ This is a good advice in order to avoid eviction.

4. Analysis: how do those African women deal with an adverse environment?

4.1 Diverse categories of situations and trajectories

4.1.1 Methodology: Textual analysis of the testimonies

The 18 individual interviews, coming from 14 women and 4 men members of the AVISA association, were treated by textual analysis with the software ALCESTE. Its methodology is based on an automated treatment of the content of the various speeches coming from the interviews. All speeches are divided into specific text units in order to understand the way the viewpoints are organised in relation with the characteristics of the interviewees¹⁸ (see in Appendix 1 for these characteristics). The program classifies these text units according to the pattern of co-occurrences of the words within these units. The objective of such an analysis is to distinguish between several word classes that express the differing forms of discourse which qualify the topic of interest.

4.1.2 Four different classes of discourse

The analysis has led us to distinguish 4 classes of discourses which are represented on the current diagram of the factorial analysis (Figure 4.1). On horizontal axis (40% of inertia), text units linked to 'social life' on the left are opposed to 'material conditions' on the right. Vertical axis (33%) is dragged down by text units linked to 'young people and insecurity'.

1. The class number 1 '**employment and welfare**', which represents 30% of the text units, is the most specific one, it is rather simple and is clearly apart from the three others within the classification; it is characterised by the key words: *to pay, employment, company, contract, social security, rent*. This class illustrates the material living conditions, which refers to such main concerns as being employed, having an employment contract, being declared to social security, and earning enough income which enables to pay one's rent. Besides these issues, there is a real difficulty to understand the processes and means of the social aid devices: despite the help from the social workers, the people feel deprived as they face a system which appears to be more and more complex and nowadays quite inaccessible with its dematerialisation, which implies that many steps are to be made online, '*Actually I have difficulty in paying the rent, because before my husband worked and so did I, the rent was not expensive, but now, my husband does not work anymore and we do not get the housing support, our files are complete, they say that these are under process.*' It may even express bitterness from the rare people, who have enough resources and who have then no more access to social benefits: '*while the others who do not work, at the end of the month, get a salary or I don't know what from the family allowance fund or from the social security, I do not know how this works.*'

18 When studying a text, which is produced by different individuals, the objective is to highlight the common points of view that are collectively shared by a group at a given time. When thinking about a topic of interest as a scientific object, there always exist different and contrasting points of view. The basic assumption of ALCESTE is that different points of view would produce different ways of talking. Therefore, the use of a specific vocabulary can be seen as a source for detecting the way of thinking about a particular topic of interest. The aim of the ALCESTE analysis is, therefore, to distinguish several 'word classes' that represent the differing forms of discourse concerning that topic of interest' (Bicquelet, 2012: 4).

- The class 2 **'education and culture'**, which covers 15% of the text units, illustrates the dilemma between the culture of the country of origin and the French culture. On the one hand, the interviewees express their will to improve their own potentialities by the elimination of illiteracy through the wording: *to read and to write, French, to learn*, which for the adults, requires belonging to associations. It would allow them to hope for a more interesting work, to follow the children's school work, to be more autonomous and reassured within a society where writing is omnipresent, even for the less qualified positions: *'Sometimes it is complicated if you cannot read, the product is for window panes while you use it for the floor, if you can read you understand that you should not touch it; this is for the window pans and this is for the floor.'*

Figure 4.1 Multiple correspondence: discourse analysis

But on the other hand, these people also express the risk of losing the Malian culture: *'it's true that we, Malian people, work much, but we need to recognise what is normal or not for us. Being able to read and write does not prevent us from praying, does not prevent us from practising our culture at home.'* They effectively live the dilemma between integration and assimilation: *'Even if people cannot respect our culture at 100%, we would like to get integrated, starting with the capacity to read and write, we would like to be able to say that we can also do this like French people, but if we think of getting integrated into another culture at 100%, we would not make it.'*

- The class 3 **'family and relationships'** is important, with 37% of the text units. The key words are related to the central role of the mother and to the family, in particular those relatives who are remaining in the country of origin (*mother, to love*). The separation triggered by the emigration constitutes a pain (*to come, to leave, to stay*). The departure was sometimes decided from a personal initiative and based on an individual project: *My friends were surprised, so I told them: 'I am going to leave for France because I was sure that I would go and then I prepared my papers, I got my visa and I arrived.'* (A woman). Some arrived as well by family

arrangement, like many women but also men: *'It is my uncle who made me come, and by making me come, let us be frank, we cannot hide the truth, he and my mother have agreed to marry me with his daughter.'* (A man).

But everyone also has to help materially their relatives remaining in the country of origin, it is the basic emigrants' responsibility, and this even when they are unemployed or in financial difficulties *'when my mom was still there, I was compelled to send some money, because even if you are jobless, in Africa, they do not know that.'* The women try to visit regularly their parents as long as they are alive, but that is quite expensive. They have to pay the plane ticket and to bring back gifts. They cannot always take their children with them even those born in France, either for economic reason, or by choice: *'I still have relatives in Ivory Coast, but I do not take my children when I go there.'*

4. The class 4 **'insecurity and young people'** represents the 18% of the classified units. It is marked by the context of the area, which is as well a priority safety areas (ZSP).¹⁹ The speech of the women relates this general atmosphere which sounds quite heavy. It is characterised by the wording: *fear, young, to come back home, morning, evening*. There is, at first, the insecurity which affects them directly, in the case of handbag or mobile snatching, and this is even more serious for those women who work staggered hours or leave early in the morning *'I am afraid, I also said to myself that I should resign but later I thought about it, if I, resigned, I would not find any job because at present time, employment is not how it used to be, it is harder. But for a woman anyway, at 4 am in the morning being in the street, it is not easy'*, or they come back late at night *'my work is in the afternoon and I come back late at night; the young people who are hanging about here in the evening cause me problems.'*²⁰

4.2 The difficulties for accessing to the basic rights

4.2.1 A long pathway for settlement

The settlement process of the immigrants in France requires three key steps: acquiring a residence permit, accessing to a personal accommodation, and getting a job. The data analysis of the 2012-2013 'Parcours' (Pathway) survey (Gosselin et al, 2016) shows that it takes several years for the immigrants from sub-Saharan Africa to acquire these three fundamental rights which contribute to their human security. These rights are naturally linked with one another: it is therefore impossible to get a stable position without a residence permit; just like it is hard to get official papers and a job without accommodation.

'My main problem, is a job and a house. I have no house. I am walking around to other homes. Only my friends. And I do not stay a long time to a friend's house. I do not stay long with a friend. I have to stay a little and go. Otherwise this is not possible. And I have not the right to work.' (Malian woman, widow, single in France).

After 6 years for the women and seven years for the men, only half of people succeed in accessing to these fundamental rights, i.e. residence, accommodation and work. And it takes respectively between 11 and 12 years to reach the proportion of 75%. The median age of arrival in France is 27 years. This means that it is during the precise time of building a family and a professional life that the migrants from sub-Saharan Africa will have to bear a long period of insecurity (Gosselin et al., 2016). The crisis, due to the increase of unemployment and the restriction in the administrative regularisation, extends this period. These same key stages, and related obstacles, are also found in the women itineraries of the focus-groups.

19 The establishment of priority safety areas (ZSP zones de sécurité prioritaires) since 2012 aims at ensuring local security in the most sensitive places. *'The ZSP provides a framework for action for these districts which are hit by the degradation of the social order and public quietness: burglaries, robberies, illegal settlement of merchants in tourist areas, drug trafficking in the building lobbies or in public squares, etc.'* (French Ministry of Interior).

20 The majority of our respondents live in the neighborhood of 'La Maladrerie' in a group of buildings the halls of which are squattered after 6 pm by young people groups, that are said not living in the neighborhood and getting involved in trafficking. A few women surveyed are living in other priority areas of Aubervilliers and are less exposed to this situation.

4.2.2 Accommodation: a basic right not always ensured

Two thirds of the inhabitants in the priority area are tenants of social lodging; however, the administrative process for accessing to this type of accommodation is quite long, because the offer is really insufficient.²¹ For the most modest categories of population, who are expecting social housing, there are other solutions: in a homeless hostel, at other people's home, in some unhealthy or too small lodgings.

'We were in a studio. We were too many inside. And it was not good as well. There was too much humidity. All the walls has become green everywhere. We suffered a little in there. Then, we found this accommodation.' (A Guinean family, 4 children).

But, even with a stable job, the difficulty for having a personal accommodation remains hard. For instance, Fanta, from Guinea, has been in France for 13 years, she works full-time as a night cleaning agent, and she and her son of 5 years old are housed by her cousin within an overpopulated flat:

'Normally, my son and I, we should not sleep together as he is a boy. Since 2010, we have been sleeping together in the same bed, it is not normal. I made an application for a social lodging but we did not get one.'

The Abbé Pierre Foundation (2015) highlights the worsening of the housing situation in France, particularly since the beginning of the crisis, and despite the new devices implemented like the DALO (Enforceable Right to Housing). The numerous consequences of bad accommodation on people's capabilities are identified as health problems, difficulties for the children in school, impacts on people's employability, and so on.

The accommodation can also be in an environment which presents security issues and difficulties for accessing to services. The right to live in a secure environment is also a fundamental right, which less ensured in priority areas, especially those which are specifically classified as 'areas of priority security' like in the town Aubervilliers. There, the feeling of insecurity is twice greater than in the other urban surroundings (quoted in Observatoire national de la politique de la ville, 2016 from the Insee survey 'Living conditions and security 2015'). This perception comes out of the interviews conducted with the women, particularly those who exposed to physical or voice violence in the public space.

4.2.3 Employment: hard work and increasing precariousness

In a global way, the migrants, men as well as women, natives from sub-Saharan Africa are confronted to precariousness which makes inclusion in the labour market more difficult, as it is currently noticed in a number of studies (INED, 2016; DARES, 2014a & b).

For the women, employment is characterised by low-skilled jobs, often on a part-time basis or being split into fragments of activities contributing to their precariousness. Besides, men are often easily excluded from the working environment, thus making the women in charge of the whole family. For the West African immigrants, who grew up in a society remaining quite patriarchal, such situation destabilises their representation of the society.

In our focus-group, several women are aspiring for jobs on-the-spot, related to childhood and early childhood. These jobs, like assistant in nursery school or at the canteen, surveillance after school for road safety, etc., would be actually accessible if they were able to read and write. They are conscious that their children, born in France or having been raised there, are now French and will not return to settle down into their country of origin. They want to stay by their children's side for they are very concerned by their future, and sometimes disarmed when facing the issue of integration. Men, on the other side seem more distant from this reality. Several of them have projects about returning to their country. Sometimes in a rather idealised and vague dream, like returning to their village, sometimes in a well-conceived reflection like for building up their own company.

²¹ According to the Abbé Pierre Foundation (2015), there are 1.8 million people who were awaiting accommodation in the social housing sector at the end of 2014. About 500,000 households were also in the situation of outstanding payments for rent, and 5.1 millions of people who are in the situation of energy insecurity.

4.2.4 The access to services: the risk of digital exclusion

The access to rights appears to more and more difficult for the people with a low literacy level particularly when they are not familiar with the new digital technology tools. The current use of them has been strongly encouraged with the State administrative reform undertaken since 2007 (through the General Review of the Public Policies).

Pôle emploi has just sent me a message. They say that there is a job in Sarcelles but I have to check it on Facebook in order to apply for it. I do not know how to do that! I can write but I do not know how to use this kind of platform. I wanted to go there, but I did not get the complete address in Sarcelles?. (Woman, single-parent family, 3 children).

For Ricardou (2016) the immigrant women express the difficulties for being ‘in connection with a qualified person who will provide the concrete information required for the administrative procedures: *We are not listened to. Once he made us trail round, he says ‘you should, you should, ...’*The great number of documents to supply, the contradictory requests from diverse departments and the waiting times are all discouraging factors encountered by the women. Therefore they turn themselves more and more towards associations who help them in the administrative process through the closeness of their support and the quality of their reception’. The administration, the staff number of which is decreasing, uses this digital transformation to outsource a part of the work towards the users themselves.

4.3 Usual family patterns are changing

4.3.1 Gender relationships are evolving

The settlement of the African immigration started at the beginning of the 1980s in a difficult economic, social and political environment. We shift from a working immigration mostly masculine to family immigration²² with all its consequences, particularly the concentration of the African households in some of the priority areas. This favoured the development of community networks based on the solidarities between the inhabitants living in a same neighbourhood. The arrival of the women generated new networks of sociability around specific activities (for the elimination of illiteracy, for setting up sewing workshops, etc.) according to the neighbourhood (Beauchemin *et al.*, 2013).

Most of the families, native from Western Africa, used to live, at first, in the rationale of an extended family, although they were de facto considered as nuclear family and therefore subjected to the current French Family Law. The fact that social workers have the right to look after these families in order to address some of the family issues is not always accepted by the men who see that as a reconsideration of their own power. The women who find there an opportunity to assert themselves in front of the men’s power, play a key role in the transforming dynamics of family relationships, just like for the relationships with institutions. The crisis, and their greater insertion into the labour market, make them in charge of more and more responsibilities to assume.

4.3.2 More female heads of family

At present, one can notice the rising number of single women raising their children. It is a significant change and a new phenomenon, which increases with the crisis, as express by the following reflection of an association leader:

Divorces and separations begin now among Africans. (...) it is an extremely important information which has to be taken into account.’

²² The right to live within a family is a constitutional right in France and is also registered in the European law. Its regular implementation and reference to began in the seventies.

These family situations often generates new difficulties that are underlined by the social workers:

'A single mother who (...) works in airports, whether in the morning or in the evening, as it is far she goes through a crazy transport itinerary (...). You never see the mother, I mean you can try to visit her, you can try to call her but you never see her.'

The kind of position that are held and the way families can put it all together with their various agenda and time obligations has to be taken into account by the various services like, for instance, the type of child care. However, beyond the real difficulties of women to reconcile their family life and their professional life, this new fact shows that the sub-Saharan family models in France are in a full transformation.²³

The consequences of these social changes on children and teenagers are crucial by raising questions on their identity, especially as their social integration is difficult because of cumulative discrimination.

4.4 Inclusion: a key role for the associations

Through this study and with the various actors that we met, women as well as men, we see the growing role of the associations for mediating, under different ways, the dialogue between the people and the institutions. It is particularly crucial for this period of crisis, for it happens at the same moment than the extensive reform in the public services.

Facilitating the participation of the women, notably via their gathering in collective structures or in diverse associations, allows to strengthen their capacities to act with the people concerned, using their agency as a lever of participation, in order to become 'the actors' of their own life and not only the beneficiaries of social support.

23 For some portraits of immigrants natives from the Sahelian countries, see Lagrange (2013).

5. Conclusion

RE-InVEST wants to emphasise the living experiences of vulnerable people, the impact of the crisis (and crisis-related policy reforms) on vulnerable groups as well as the impact of growing inequality and social vulnerability.

Indeed, unlike other countries, welfare expenditures were maintained in France and social nets allowed to weaken the consequences of the shocks. But, we are rather facing an erosion of the people's rights, especially because of a reduction in the public expenditure.

In the priority areas of Seine-St Denis, a town which has a large share of the population of African origin, the economic crisis, stereotypes, fundamentalism; identity withdrawal generate a climate of suspicion that undermines the 'Living together'. But also, as highlighted by Bacqué and Mechmache (2013): 'the reality of popular neighbourhoods appears much more diverse, and dynamic. These areas are also places of solidarity, success, innovation and creation'.

Among the populations of these areas, women encounter many difficulties in their daily life because of cumulative discrimination which reduces their capabilities space. However, they are organizing themselves and investing in the local facilities to support the initiatives of their members in the social and economic fields. By this way, they play a mediation role contributing to the fight against discrimination. The associations in which they are acting are places for the gathering of resources, for the development and promotion of skills, and for recognition. They allows the women to gain confidence in themselves and in the role that they may play in their own territory, improving by this way their ability to do and to be.

The priority areas, as identified for the urban policy framework, are often considered as laboratories of social change. Confronted to their specificities and their problems, many initiatives once supported by the public authorities, by associations and individuals, have largely answered by innovations and a great creativity. However, these various levels for action, and the corresponding actors, are themselves also affected by the current crisis through the financial collapse of local municipalities (some of them being trapped by the toxic loans), the reduction of the government budgetary aid, the reduction of resources through taxation, which adds to the decrease of people's revenue. The associations, which usually play a key role for ensuring social cohesion, are often the first affected by the lowering of their subsidies, which are perceived as the adjustment variable of a weakened budget. The evolution of the institutional landscape and the associative network has to be analysed as well as the impact that they may have on the inhabitants' conditions of living: these structures are indeed playing the key role of 'resilience tutors', particularly for the suburban youngsters having problems. It is, more generally, a way for expanding the capabilities space of the inhabitants from these areas.

appendix 1 Main characteristics of the participants for individual interviews

Gender	Age	Main preoccupation/main aspiration	Family status	Dependent children	Employment	Situation of husband/spouse	Level of education	Country of origin	Date of arrival in France
F	45	Would like to be able to write and read well, change her work, education of children	married	4	Full time, long term contract	extended sick leave	Illiterate	Mali	1999
F	37	Find her own flat because she is hosted by a third party, this is too small	monoparental	1	Full time, long term contract	absent	Illiterate	Guinea-Conakry	2003
F	45	Find a full-time job, she works only 3h/day while she has to feed 7 children	monoparental	7	3H, part time	absent	Illiterate	Mali	1991
F	45	She has health problem, but she wants to help women, she wishes to be able to work again	married	5	Jobless	Full time, long term contract	bacc + 1	Senegal	2001
F	44	Wants to change her work because workplace is too far, flat at 4th floor without lift	married	5	Full time, long term contract	Extended sick leave	Illiterate	Mali	1993
F	36	Looking for a job (jobless since 4 months) housing too small	married	3	Jobless	Temporary work employee	primary	Mali	2000
F	42	Working hours for her husband, difficulties to manage familial tasks and job	married	6	Jobless		primary	Ivory Coast	2002
F	43	Jobless since 2 years. Too small house	monoparental	3	Jobless	Absent	primary	Mali	2000
F	40	Large flat too expensive for heating, humidity. Problem of education of young people	monoparental	5	Part time, long term contract	Absent	primary	Mali	1994
F	35	Insalubrity of housing (presence of mice), workplace too far and return time too late to her place in the evening	married	4	Part time, short term contract	Jobless	primary	Mali	2001
F	40	Has not been to school, education of children	married	4	Part time, long term contract	extended sick leave	Illiterate	Mali	1999
F	45	Homeless, jobless, her son still in Mali	monoparental	3 in Africa	Jobless	deceased	primary	Burkina Faso	2014
F	50	Heath	monoparental	4	Unemployed	absent	secondary	Mali	1985
F	44	Going through divorce, unemployed, handicapped	monoparental	2	Jobless	absent	Illiterate	Mali	
F	35	She complains because they do not receive any aid unlike jobless or sick people	married	4	Full time, long term contract	Full time, long term contract	secondary	Mali	2004
F	38	Her son is handicapped, problem of housing (illegal occupation)	monoparental	2	Part time, short term contract	absent	primary	Ivory Coast	2005
H	54	Unemployed, too small housing.	married	6	Jobless	Jobless	Illiterate	Mali	2013
H	56	1) Problem with his son who wants to leave school getting 2) Project to get back to Mali.	monoparental	1	Part time short term contract	absent	bacc + 2	Mali	1989
H	56	Extended sick leave since 1 year and a half, too small house	married	4	Full time, long term contract, extended sick leave	Full time, long term contract	bacc +?	Mali	2008
H	49	His wife's health (they still do not know the disease), getting back to Africa	married	10	Part time, long term contract	Unemployed (sick)	secondary	Ivory Coast	1990

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Social disinvestment and vulnerable groups in Europe in the aftermath of the financial crisis

The case of long-term unemployed people in Germany

Rüdiger Mautz (SOFI)

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Executive summary

The *target group* of the German report consists of long-term unemployed persons. These people are being counted among the most vulnerable groups in Germany since long. Despite economic recovery long-term unemployment still is a serious structural problem of the German labour market. While the total number of jobless persons in Germany considerably went down since the crisis, the number of the long-term unemployed stagnates at about one million since 2011. German inquiries on poverty show that these people have a highly above-average risk of falling into poverty.

The study is based on *qualitative and participative empirical methods*: a three-days-workshop and personal interviews with long-term unemployed persons; all of them were participants of local bottom-up initiatives of jobless people. This methodological approach does not generate representative findings but rather aims at a deeper comprehension of the impact that crisis as well as crisis-related politics and socio-economic changes have on the lives, experiences, or personal perceptions and claims of vulnerable people.

As a *main result* it can be stated that most of the research participants have been affected by the far going turn of German labour market policy in 2005 (the introduction of the so called “Hartz reforms”) in a discriminating way: the combination of stronger activation rules on the one hand and austerity measures like the cut-down of benefits for long-term unemployed persons on the other often had – and still has – a severe impact on those people who are without a job since long. Following the labour market reform, the crisis of 2008 and the subsequent austerity measures had an additional or intensifying impact on the lives of many long-term jobless people. In sum, the outcomes of the labour market reform and of crisis-induced political measures led to social disinvestment and went hand in hand with (increasing) financial, social and psychological restraints as experienced by most participants of our study.

Our findings show that long-term unemployment is often linked to the personal experience that *human rights* are violated by the outcomes of the Hartz reforms. Due to the harsh cut-down of benefits many of the research participants see their *right of leading a decent life* and of being protected against increasing economic and social deprivation substantially violated. *Social injustice* is another main topic: the cut-down of benefits is widely seen as a kind of *disrespect* to the life-time achievements especially of those who had worked for many years and whose standard of living will be rapidly reduced to the minimum subsistence level after a certain period of unemployment. Furthermore, several of the research participants see the *right of a fair treatment by the job agencies* violated by experiences of disrespect, permanent pressure, or social incapacitation due to the measures and provisions which the job agency imposes. Last but not least, there is a common experience of *social devaluation* – an experience which affects *the right of human dignity*. Long-term unemployed people meet in many ways a social climate of incomprehension, stigmatisation or even disdain, whether in the closer social environment, in the media or the society as a whole.

Our findings make clear that the outcomes of the German Hartz reforms may restrict *the individual capabilities* of long-term unemployed people severely. These restrictions have become apparent among the participants of our study with regard to various aspects: the individual employment outlook; the financial scope concerning options and choices in everyday life; the individual choices concerning the participation in social life. In other words: the institutional resources provided by society or state are seen as insufficient in terms of facilitating the return into work, enabling a decent life, or supporting social integration. Most of the research participants criticise the factual activities and practices of the job agencies which should enable individual chances and choices on the labour market, but, in their eyes, fail in doing so. In our sample it is only a minority of foremost younger unemployed persons who consider the specific services and measures of the job agency as a helpful path of reintegration into work.

With regard to our target group another relevant finding has to be emphasised: *bottom-up initiatives of unemployed people* can be considered as collective resources which support the strengthening of individual resilience, for instance in terms of self-efficacy and self-empowerment. Moreover, such initiatives can help with the building-up of individual capabilities regarding activities or forms of social participation and integration beyond work. Last but not least, the initiatives offer different forms of self-help which may enhance individual capabilities of their participants, for instance with regard to the efforts of job seeking, or the handling of requirements and measures prescribed by the job agency.

The following *conclusions for public policy and practice* were drawn by the workshop's participants and additionally discussed in the interviews. Necessary are:

- political decisions and measures against the *cutback of public infrastructure* caused by savings or decreasing investments, especially on the local level;
- improvements for the benefit of a *secure livelihood* which should be achieved by a reformed system of social security;
- improvements concerning *social justice*: required are measures against growing social imbalances of income and wealth in German society;
- improvements concerning *employment security*: German (as well as European) labour market policy should put an end to the expansion of non-standard or low-income jobs – political and legal support should be given primarily to the generation of fair jobs, fair work, or fair payment;
- improvements concerning the *social recognition* of (long-term) unemployed people in the German public;
- more *appropriate counselling and job services* which should consider the real needs and abilities of (long-term) jobless people;
- improvements concerning the *public funding of local initiatives of unemployed people* which has decreased in Germany in recent years.

Preface

This report would not have been possible without the support and collaboration of several members of the ELAN Network in the Kassel region and the ALI initiative in Gießen. A core element of our participative research was a three-days-workshop about the issues of long-term unemployment and labour market policy. This workshop which we carried out together with several long-term unemployed people was originally initiated and moderated by protagonists of the ELAN network in collaboration with a social pedagogue of the ALI initiative. Besides all these very helpful collaborators of the research project I would particular like to thank all those participants of the ELAN and ALI initiatives who were willing to give personal interviews. These interviews were “personal” in the full sense: the interviewees talked openly about their lives and the burdening of long-term unemployment, their future expectations, hopes and fears. Such openness is in no way self-evident – and was a precondition for the accomplishment of this research project.

Rüdiger Mantz

Contents

List of figures	11
Introduction	13
1. National context	15
2. Theoretical and methodological approach	19
2.1 Theoretical approach	19
2.2 Methodological approach	21
2.2.1 Target group	21
2.2.2 The workshop	22
2.2.3 The interviews	23
2.2.4 Future activities	23
3. Two selected biographies	24
3.1 Biography of Doris	24
3.2 Biography of Otto	26
4. Analysis	29
4.1 Before the crisis: the impact of German labour market reforms (the "Hartz reforms")	29
4.2 The additional or intensifying impact of the crisis	30
4.3 Financial, social and psychological restraints	30
4.4 Treatment by/struggle with the job agency	31
4.5 Resilience	32
4.6 Impact on human rights	33
4.7 Impact on capabilities	35
5. Conclusion	38
Bibliography	41

List of figures

Figure 2.1	Resources, conversion factors, capability set and achieved functionings	20
Figure 2.2	Merging of knowledge	20

Introduction¹

This report is prepared in the framework of the Europe H2020 project ‘Rebuilding an inclusive, value based Europe of solidarity and trust through social investments’ (RE-InVEST). The RE-InVEST project aims to contribute to a more solidary and inclusive EU, through an inclusive, powerful and effective social investment strategy at EU level. Moreover, the project itself adopts a participative approach that gives voice to vulnerable groups and civil society organisations. The RE-InVEST consortium consists of members of the informal network ‘the Alliances to fight Poverty’, a network of civil society organisations, trade unions, policy makers and academics co-ordinated by the Flemish Christian labour movement *beweging.net*, and committed to a more inclusive Europe. The consortium covers a broad range of European countries, both geographically (12 countries, 13 regions) and in terms of representation of different welfare and labour market traditions. The analyses are carried out by the local partners, who consist of NGOs and/or researchers.

In particular, this report is one of the 13 national reports that make up the qualitative research of the RE-InVEST work package ‘The social damage of the crisis’. This work package focuses on the lived experience of vulnerable people, the impact of the crisis (and crisis-related policy reform) on vulnerable groups as well as the impact of growing inequality and social vulnerability on distrust. Our two key hypotheses in this regard are that:

- growing distrust and indeed resentment among the population may be attributed to (a rejection of) the neoliberal policies employed by national as well as European elites in recent years;
- this integrated diagnosis can build on the idea of the erosion of/disinvestment in (individual and collective) capabilities and basic social rights in the EU. This means that experiences of insecurity, poverty and social degradation need to be re-analyzed from those perspectives.

Next to the 13 qualitative case studies, this work package consists of a cross-validation with a report describing trends in selected quantitative indicators that reflect the relation between socio-economic vulnerability, human rights and capabilities. A third element consists of a statistical analysis of the dynamic relationship between vulnerability, shifts in social policies and trust: in which sections of the population has the trust in institutions declined most? Can different patterns between countries be observed, and can they be explained by differences in policy shifts and differences in resilience of civil society? A European synthesis report will combine the main findings from the three types of analyses.

The qualitative research focuses on the experience of vulnerable groups in each of the 12 countries (13 regions) participating in RE-InVEST. Mixed teams of researchers, NGOs and union workers, practitioners and people from vulnerable groups jointly analyzed cases where the crisis has impacted on human rights and (individual as well as collective) capabilities.

The German qualitative case study focuses on long-term unemployed people. The main reasons for choosing this target group will be explained in chapter 1 (national context). A detailed description of the empirical case study, its participants and regional focus will be given in chapter 2.2 (methodological approach).

¹ This chapter is written by Katrien Steenssens.

1. National context

Although this report is on the damage of the crisis, our starting point is the observation that problems in some segments of the German labour market reach back further in time than to 2008 only. They concern in particular long-term unemployment and low-paid work, leading to a growing poverty rate in Germany.

There was a negative impact of the *financial crisis in 2008 and following years* on the German economy, but it had – all in all – a rather short-term effect and was followed by a recovery of the national economy since then. 2009 was a year of crisis – and of public awareness that Germany had been struck by the financial crisis, too. The most visible impact of the crisis was a decrease of the German gross domestic product (GDP) by 5.6 percent from 2008 to 2009. Moreover, this was by far the heaviest slump of the Germany GDP within one year since World War II (*Statistisches Bundesamt 2015: 320-321*). However, since 2010 the German economy is moderately – but continually – growing again.² By contrast, Germany fell into an economic period of stagnation during the years *before* the financial crisis: between 2001 and 2005 economic growth rates were rather small (even negative in 2003), and unemployment reached a maximum in 2005 with 4,860,909 jobless persons (unemployment rate: 11.7 percent) – more than ever since the German reunification in 1990 (*Statistisches Bundesamt 2015: 362*). Before the breakout of the financial crisis in 2008 the volume of unemployment went down remarkably – in 2008 the official number of jobless persons was about 3,268,000 (unemployment rate: 7.8 percent) – and only moderately increased in 2009 (about 3,423,000 jobless persons; unemployment rate: 8.2 percent). Since then the official German rate of unemployment continually has gone down: to 6.0 percent in November 2015 (annual average 2015: 6.4 percent) (*Bundesagentur für Arbeit 2015: 18*).

We decided to put an emphasis on *long-term unemployed persons* in the German national report because these people are being counted among the most vulnerable groups in Germany since long. Despite economic recovery long-term unemployment is a serious structural problem of the German labour-market – a structural problem that already existed *before* the crisis of 2008. A reform of social policy (resulting in changes to the German social code) and of labour-market regulation in particular (the so called “Hartz-reforms”) was implemented between 2003 and 2006 – just a few years before the 2008 financial crisis – and considered as a measure against the crisis of the German welfare state and German economy in the early 2000s. Originally, “Hartz IV” (one of several reform packages) was introduced (on January 1st 2005) to target explicitly the group of long-term unemployed persons. Stronger activation (tighter eligibility rules, use of sanctions) and a greater use of private placement agencies were part of the reforms. However, the most incisive consequence of the reform program was the drastic cut down of benefits for many long-term unemployed persons (for more details see chapter 4.1). The German public discussed Hartz IV controversially as a measure that puts jobless people under pressure but does not lead to satisfactory results in terms of reducing the high volume of long-term unemployment. Moreover, with the “Hartz IV” measures unemployment benefits for long-term unemployed have been reduced considerably – with the result that these people suffer from increasing risks of falling into poverty.

The more the willingness of long-term unemployed persons to accept low paid or non-standard jobs has grown due to these pressures, the more their chances of getting a normally paid permanent job have went down, because many employers have become reluctant to engage a long-term jobless person within the terms of a regular and unlimited employment relationship. Scientific analysis of the development of revenues

² Growth rates of the German GDP: 2010: 4.1 percent; 2011: 3.7 percent; 2012: 0.4 percent; 2013: 0.3 percent; 2014: 1.6 percent; 2015: 1.7 percent (*Statistisches Bundesamt 2016: 1*).

in Germany show that the continuing increase of employees working in low-paid jobs already began several years before the Hartz reforms, especially during the period of economic stagnation from 2001 on (*Knuth 2014*: 61) – a trend that was promoted by the German state which since 2003 facilitated the creation of so called “Mini”- and “Midijobs” (for instance so called “400-Euro-jobs”, since 2013 “450-Euro-jobs”) by legal regulation (*Mayer-Abuja et al. 2012*: 34). With the implementation of the Hartz-reforms the share of low-paid employees (who earn hourly wages below 2/3 of the median wage) further increased from 23.3 percent in 2005 to 24.3 percent of all employees in 2008, followed by a slight decrease to 23.8 percent in 2012 (*Knuth 2014*: 61, table 21). Referring to statistical data of EU-SILC 2011 *Knuth* emphasises the fact that Germany is the European country with the second largest share of low-paid employees (behind Lithuania) and, furthermore, shows one of the sharpest increases of this trend throughout Europe since 1996 (*Knuth 2014*: 62). Thus, critics of German labour market policy emphasise that a large sector of “underemployment” has been created which has to be taken into consideration if one wants to evaluate the recent development of the German labour market appropriately.

Moreover, the official number of unemployed persons does not cover the whole “workplace gap”: there is – similar to other national labour markets in Europe and beyond – a “secret reserve”, consisting of (long-term) jobless people who are either in a qualification measure at present or – for different reasons – non-registered as an unemployed person but potentially job-seeking. Based on calculations made by the *Institut Arbeit und Qualifikation der Universität Duisburg-Essen (IAQ)*, the German secret reserve included in 2014 about 940,000 persons, or 24.5 percent of the whole “workplace gap”. The latter amounted to about 3,540,000 persons in total, whereas the official number of registered unemployed persons accounted for about 2,900,000 in the same year. The share of the secret reserve has been more or less stable since 2005 when it accounted for 24 percent.³ The official number of *long-term unemployed persons in Germany* had a maximum at 1,588,089 persons in 2005 (annual average; *Statistisches Bundesamt 2015*: 362), followed by a decrease for the next five years. This trend surely was caused by the economic rebound of Germany since 2006, but was also a result of the expanding sector of low-paid employment which absorbed a considerable share of the long-term unemployed.

However, the socioeconomic problem of long-term unemployment still remained: the total number of long-term jobless persons stagnates at about one million persons since 2011 (*Hobmeyer et al. 2015*: 10). Despite economic growth during recent years and despite a package of measures orchestrated by labour market policy a persistent share of hard-core unemployment could not be removed by now. According to the monthly report of the German Federal Labour Agency there still were 1,013,000 long-term unemployed persons in November 2015, or 38.5 percent of unemployed persons in all (2,633,000 persons). This was even a slight increase of percentage since November 2014 (from 38.3 to 38.5 percent) (*Bundesagentur für Arbeit 2015*: 15-16). In contrast, public funding and promotion of long-term jobless people went down remarkably during the crisis, for instance with regard to advanced vocational training or employment promotion by state funding (*Hobmeyer et al. 2015*: 26). In the latter case the number of promotion measures (e.g. settling-in allowances or funding of self-employment) for unemployed persons in total went down from 338,600 in 2009 to 124,365 in 2014; the funding of advanced vocational training decreased during the same period from 264,215 to 161,329 measures.⁴

Among the jobless people as a whole there are some groups who presently have very limited chances of re-entering the workforce, respectively have a high risk of suffering from enduring joblessness: About half of the long-term unemployed persons in Germany are without vocational education; furthermore there is a high rate of older people (50 or more years) and of migrants among the long-term unemployed. There are some additional characteristics which negatively affect the chances unemployed persons have of integrating into the labour-market: especially health problems, or incompatibility of family and work, mainly in the case of single parents (*ibid.*: 10-12). The Poverty Report 2014 (*Armutbericht 2014*) – published by a German

3 Source: http://www.sozialpolitik-aktuell.de/tl_files/sozialpolitik-aktuell/Politikfelder/Arbeitsmarkt/Datensammlung/PDF-Dateien/abbIV34.pdf; accessed April 28, 2016.

4 Source: http://www.sozialpolitik-aktuell.de/tl_files/sozialpolitik-aktuell/Politikfelder/Arbeitsmarkt/Datensammlung/PDF-Dateien/abbIV86_Grafik_Monat_11_2015.pdf; accessed April 28, 2016.

welfare organisation – shows that German unemployed people have a high risk of falling into poverty: the poverty rate among unemployed persons was 58.7 percent in 2013. Moreover, this rate increased considerably during the crisis (increase of 18.8 percent since 2006), especially among less qualified jobless persons (increase of 30 percent) (*Der Paritätische Gesamtverband 2015a*).⁵ In line with this the general German poverty rate increased between 2006 and 2013 from 14 percent to 15.5 percent. Poverty among young people is even on a higher level (19.2 percent in 2013, the highest rate since 2006).⁶

A persistent base of long-term unemployment, a high rate of low-paid work, an increasing rate of poverty: all these trends can be seen as manifestations of an overarching tendency in German society which is moving towards *growing social inequality*. This trend intensified since the 1990s: in Germany the Gini coefficient – a measure of uneven distribution of income – increased between 1998 and 2006 by nearly 20 percent, the rate of relative poverty increased during the same period by about 40 percent (*Mayer-Abuja 2012 et al.*: 34). Since then inequality of available income stagnates, not least due to a considerable job growth in Germany from 2005 on (*Fratzscher 2016*: 64). However, growing social inequality also becomes apparent in an increasing spread between employees earning high wages on the one hand and those working in low-paid jobs on the other. Because of the expansion of the low-pay sector (see above) there has been a “thinning” in the middle of the hourly wages’ spread. Thus, the relative frequencies at the margins of the spread have increased (*Becker 2012*: 620). Besides the growing inequality of income in Germany there is an even bigger trend since the 1990s towards an *increasing concentration of wealth* in the hands of upper income groups (*ibid.*: 616). In a recently published study about social inequality *Fratzscher* underlines with regard to the distribution of wealth that Germany is one of “the most unequal countries in Europe”, showing a considerable above-average Gini coefficient of wealth inequality within the European Union (*Fratzscher 2016*: 43-44). About 40 percent of German households “actually have no net capital at their command”. And this means: these households “have no possibility to draw on reserves if the financial situation becomes scarce in old age or in the case of illness. They have no resources that allow investing in the education of their children. Unforeseen expenditures and charges often lead these households into over-indebtedness and to further restrictions of their living standard” (*ibid.*).⁷ Combined with low income as in the case of low-wage earners and (long-term) unemployed persons, these fortuneless households bear an over-average risk of falling into poverty.

Even the predominant way how German companies tried to overcome the crisis in 2008 – mostly in cooperation with the responsible labour representatives – showed typical patterns which supported given structures of inequality within the German workforce.

A study by *Eichborst et al. (2010)* provides answers to the questions (1) why the German labour market has not been struck by the crisis as hard as several other national labour markets in Europe and (2) which groups of employees had the highest risk of losing their jobs due to the crisis. Ad (1): The German labour-market remained relatively stable during the crisis because of the “strong internal flexibility” of the German companies. “For example, in Germany working time accounts and complementary short-time work allowances helped stabilise the manufacturing sector” (*ibid.*: 31). These measures contributed greatly to protecting the core labour-market. Ad (2): However, the reverse of the medal was that “adjustments in employment” occurred “at the margins (...), i.e. non-standard workers have borne the brunt of employment losses”, for instance agency workers or employees working on a fixed-term contract (*ibid.*). As already shown above these two groups of non-standard employees expanded considerably in the years before the crisis and often were the first to be dismissed during the crisis. Moreover, these groups bear an above average risk of remaining in long-term unemployment after job loss.

In addition to social insecurity due to rarely cost-covering unemployment benefits, (long-term) unemployed persons often suffer from stigmatisation and the incriminations of a blame-the-victim culture. Drawing on a recently published report on long-term unemployment in Germany (*Heitmeyer 2012*), a German

5 In this report all households with less than 60 percent of the average German household income are counted among the poor households – according to the usual statistical practice of defining the country-specific relative poverty rate in the EU.

6 The most recent data used in this report were recorded in 2013.

7 Translated by Rüdiger Mautz.

newspaper speaks about the “new German disdain” (“*neue deutsche Verachtung*”) that jobless people are confronted with.⁸ Heitmeyer (2012) emphasises resentments and “group related misanthropy” (“*gruppenbezogene Menschenfeindlichkeit*”) among the German population and critically describes a social climate of prejudice, accusation and stigmatisation directed against unemployed persons who are often blamed as “useless”, “inefficient” or “unwilling to work”. The book is called “German Conditions” (“*Deutsche Zustände*”); its empirical findings are based on inquiries among the German population in the context of a long-term study that started in 2001. Most recent data have been gathered in 2011. The findings show that devaluation of long-unemployed people increased among the German population from 2007 to 2008, then went down during the crisis, but did increase again from 2010 to 2011.

⁸ fr-online, April 3, 2014: <http://www.fr-online.de/arbeit--unsere-religion-/langzeitarbeitslose-neue-deutsche-verachtung,30242698,30288942.html>; accessed May 20, 2015.

2. Theoretical and methodological approach

2.1 Theoretical approach⁹

RE-InVEST aims at investigating the philosophical, institutional and empirical foundations of an inclusive Europe of solidarity and trust. To this end it draws on capability and human rights based participatory approaches.

Human rights form a common European basis of values and describe at the same time core elements of what constitutes well-being and a good life. Further, human rights are transformative by empowering people. For vulnerable people the usage of a rights-terminology has proven to change their perspective by making them aware of their rights and the ways in which their current situation compromises these rights. Human rights are the basic rights and freedoms that belong to everyone. International law, including treaties, contains the provisions which give human rights legal effect. Ideas about human rights have evolved over many centuries and gained strong support after World War II when the United Nations adopted the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights - which set out for the first time the human rights and fundamental freedoms shared by all human beings without discrimination of any kind. Human Rights are universally agreed basic standards that aim to ensure that every person is treated with dignity and respect; they are interdependent and indivisible, meaning that rights are linked and not protecting one right may impact on another, they belong to all people without discrimination. Usually set out in law, through international or regional treaties, or national legislation, they form a legal statement of universally accepted principles of how the state should treat its citizens and other people living within its jurisdiction. Human Rights include Civil and Political Rights, such as the right to life, the right to a fair trial and the right not to be subjected to torture; and Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, such as the right to work, to join a trade union, to health, to education, and to an adequate standard of living. Specific groups are protected in specific treaties such as women, children, people with disabilities, minorities, and migrants. For vulnerable people the usage of a rights-terminology has proven to change their perspective by making them aware of their rights and the ways in which their current situation compromises these rights.

The capability approach as developed by Sen (1999) and Nussbaum (2011) defines a person's well-being in terms of the beings and doings (the functionings) a person achieves and her capability to choose among different combinations of such functionings. For leading a life one values and has reason to value resources and conversion factors are preconditions (Figure 2.1). Resources refer to the material conditions of a person: her income, the goods and services she disposes of. Conversion factors help her converting resources into doing and being well. There are personal conversion factors such as skills and bodily features, social conversion factors such as social norms and social institutions and environmental conversion factors such as climate and geography. In the end both the achieved functionings as well as the freedom to choose a life one values matters.

⁹ This chapter is written by Mary Murphy and Ortrud Lessmann.

Figure 2.1 Resources, conversion factors, capability set and achieved functionings

For assessing the capabilities of vulnerable people RE-InVEST aims at giving them a voice. Their participation is fostered by relying on *participatory action research* that directly results in policy recommendations. Participatory action research views participants as co-researchers who have special knowledge about their own situation. Hence they are not only asked or interviewed on their views but take part in research by engaging in, interpreting, and reflecting on their own social world, shaping their sense of identity.

It is a circle of knowledge generation that emerges from this method and includes the steps of knowledge production and sharing, empowerment by participation, newly generated knowledge and action that builds upon this knowledge (Figure 2.2). Crucial for this kind of knowledge generation is the “merging” or “crossing of knowledge” that comes from three parts: scientific knowledge as gained by researchers; knowledge which the poor and excluded have, from their firsthand experience, of the twin realities of poverty and the surrounding world which imposes it on them; and the knowledge of those who work among and with these victims in places of poverty and social exclusion (Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2 Merging of knowledge

These are the core elements of the Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach (PAHRCA) developed in RE-InVEST. PAHRCA entails seven steps (Toolkit 2016, 44-45): 1. Identify and meet partner NGO/gatekeeper, 2. Preliminary ‘meet ups’ (for trust building if necessary), 3. First meeting with participants – trust building, 4. Developmental: implement developmental human rights & capability approach, 5. Inquiry/data gathering, 6. Identifying patterns (key issues and themes of concern to the group) and 7. Undertake action/outcome using one or combination of approaches.

The concrete outlining of the approach in Germany is described in the paragraphs below.

2.2 Methodological approach

Drawing upon PAHRCA, the German study is based on *qualitative and participative empirical methods*: a *three-days-workshop* with ten participants belonging to our target group of long-term unemployed people and *qualitative interviews* with most of the workshop's participants and with an additional group of long-term unemployed persons who could be counted to our target group, too. All in all 16 personal interviews were conducted by the researcher (*Rüdiger Mautz*) – as one of the interviews was with two persons, 17 persons were interviewed in total (ten female, seven male of all ages 18+). All interviews have been transcribed in order to accomplish a comparative examination based on an interpretative approach which was guided by our research questions.

The methodological approach of this study does not generate representative findings but rather aims at a deeper comprehension of the impact that crisis as well as crisis-related politics and socio-economic changes have on the lives, experiences and personal perceptions of vulnerable people. By giving these people a voice PAHRCA can contribute to the unfolding of economic and political demands which are necessary to improve the living conditions of the most vulnerable groups in an appropriate way.

2.2.1 Target group

As already explained above, our target group consists of long-term unemployed persons. As a further selection criterion for our group of participants with experiential knowledge we only included persons who were participating in a *bottom-up initiative of jobless people*. The main reason for this was that we wanted to include an already existing group or network of unemployed people with whom we could work continually, e.g. preparing and holding a joint workshop. The second reason was that we expected some insights into *collective* capabilities and coping strategies that help with overcoming the challenges and burdening of (long-term) unemployment and go beyond the individual possibilities of doing so.

Our research focused on two initiatives, which are located in different regions of the German federal state of Hessen: The first one is the ELAN initiative (*Erwerbslosenarbeit Nordhessen*), a network of regional initiatives of unemployed people in the urban-rural Kassel region (North-Hessen); the second one is a local initiative called ALI (*Arbeitsloseninitiative Gießen e.V.*) in the medium-sized town of Gießen (Mid-Hessen).

The ELAN network was founded by some trade union and church-based activists together with some already existing or newly founded local initiatives in the early 1990s and comprises nowadays a network of local initiatives, organisations, or single actors, situated partly in *Kassel* (about 250.000 inhabitants), partly in smaller regional towns (e.g. *Eschwege*). Cooperative partners of ELAN are the Protestant Church of Kurhessen-Waldeck (Department of Economy-Labour-Social Affairs) and the regional section of the German Federation of Trade Unions (DGB). The tasks of ELAN comprise at first hand informative and advisory activities for the benefit of unemployed persons (partly with a close institutional connection to trade unions) concerning issues of labour market regulation, the rights and opportunities of unemployed people, or the handling of measures and provisions of the job agency. In short, one of ELAN's main goals aims at offering its participants help for self-help in the situation of (long-term) joblessness. Last but not least, ELAN pursues socio-political goals, for instance by commenting on labour market policy, or by informing the public about the situation, demands and disadvantages of unemployed people (including public events on the local or regional level).¹⁰

The local ALI initiative was founded in 1986 in Gießen. It is a semi-professional organisation which is based on the paid work of several employees (e.g. social workers or social pedagogues) and the commitment of numerous volunteers. Similar to ELAN, the ALI initiative cooperates with representatives of churches and trade unions (ALI is located in the "House of Trade Unions" in Gießen). At present the ALI initiative comprises a wide range of tasks and activities dedicated to the support and help of unemployed people: ALI runs a meeting point and café for jobless people, offers an advisory service, a job board (pedagogically accompanied job search), professional support concerning the personal employability, special projects of

¹⁰ See the ELAN homepage: <http://elan-nordhessen.de/index.html>; accessed April 12, 2016.

self-help (concerning the everyday life during joblessness), or cultural and media projects which can be joint by participants.¹¹

The recent developments of the *regional labour markets* which play a decisive role for the participants of our target group – North Hessen on the one hand and the Gießen district on the other – show some notable differences. However, both are in line with the general trend of decreasing unemployment rates in Germany since around 2005 combined with a persistent basis of long-term unemployment (see above: national context). The *regional labour market of North-Hessen* is marked by a remarkably positive development since 2005: at that time the Kassel region was an area of deep-going labour market crisis with a high number of job losses and closures of firms, resulting in unemployment rates above the German average. By contrast, in December 2015 the unemployment rate of Kassel city was only moderately above the German average (Kassel city: 8.5 percent; Germany: 6.1 percent), the unemployment rate of the rural district of Kassel amounted to 4.4 percent in December 2015 and was therefore even below the German average.¹² Compared to the Kassel region, the development of the *regional labour market of the Gießen district* was more in line with the average development in Germany as a whole, because Gießen was not hit as much by the German labour market crisis as the Kassel region around 2005. During the following years unemployment continually went down in the Gießen district; in December 2015 the regional unemployment rate amounted to 5.2 percent¹³, hence it was moderately below the German average of 6.1 percent.

2.2.2 The workshop

Our initial contact person was a pastor of the Protestant Church in Kassel who has since long been cooperating with the ELAN network and with whom the SOFI institute already cooperated in a former research project. The pastor is chief of the regional Church Department of Economy, Labour and Social Affairs. Together with the pastor and three other representatives of the ELAN initiative we constituted a steering group in order to prepare a workshop on long-term unemployment. We had three preparatory meetings with the steering group from July to October 2015 and worked out an invitation letter, a program for a 3-days-workshop on the issue of long-term unemployment as well as a guide-line for subsequent personal interviews.

The workshop took place in October 2015 together with about 10 members of the ELAN initiative and was jointly moderated by protagonists of the ELAN network and a social pedagogue of the ALI initiative. The workshop's location was a remote one at the edge of a small regional town near Kassel where all participants could stay overnight (in an educational institution of the Protestant Church) – so we could sit and talk in the evening, too. All workshop participants live in the Kassel region: some live directly in the town of Kassel, others in smaller regional towns or villages.

In the course of the workshop (as well as at the preparatory meetings of the steering group) *merging of knowledge* happened: the workshop enabled a mutual process of learning from each other about the experiences and burdening of long-term unemployment, about their struggles with the local job agencies (the so called “Job Centers”), their struggles with an aggravating financial situation, with loss of social recognition, with illness, with an uncertain future, etc. We also worked with some creative elements, for instance with the biographical snake we already tried out at the preparatory RE-InVEST meeting in Maynooth (Toolkit 2016: 59-60), or with designing large human figures which expressed the experiences of unemployment and a burdening life (*ibid.*: 61-62). On the last day of the workshop we intensively discussed at first individual and collective coping strategies in order to build up resilience against the burdening and disadvantages of long-term unemployment. At second we had a discussion about political solutions, mainly addressed to the German policy (on the federal as well as on the regional and local level). This discussion also served as a reaffirmation – or clarifying – of collective positions about recent German labour market policy by the

11 See the ALI homepage: www.ali-giessen.de; accessed April 12, 2016.

12 Source: <http://www.hna.de/kassel/arbeitslosigkeit-weiter-6008813.html>; accessed April 13, 2016.

13 Source: <https://statistik.arbeitsagentur.de/Navigation/Statistik/Statistik-nach-Regionen/BA-Gebietsstruktur/Hessen/Giessen-Nav.html>; accessed April 13, 2016.

present participants of the ELAN network. The initial inputs for all workshop discussions as well as the moderation were made by members of the steering group and by a social pedagogue who works for the ALI initiative. The role of the researcher mainly consisted of recording the discussions and of feeding in some information as well as occasional questions referring to the main topics of our research. The workshop was very helpful in order to further elaborate and finally complete the interview guide-line. During the workshop the researcher could learn much about the issues and problems which actually were important for the participants: for instance, their partly painful struggle with the job agencies, their fundamental discontent and disagreement with labour market regulation in general and the benefit system for long-term jobless people in particular.

2.2.3 The interviews

The workshop was a good opportunity for building up trust between the researcher and the participants. Nearly all of the participants of the workshop agreed to have a personal interview in the days following the workshop (total of nine interviewees). By a local social pedagogue we came into contact with the ALI initiative in *Gießen*. At an initial meeting in the ALI café the researcher informed the present initiative's members about the RE-InVEST project; during the following weeks, he conducted personal interviews with eight of the regular attendants of the ALI café.

Subsequently to the workshop the *interview guide-line* was completed by the researcher. The main topics of the guide-line were structured as followed:

- biographical background: development and main stages of biography until the beginning of long-term unemployment;
- experiences in the course of unemployment: development of living conditions/struggle with the job agencies, etc.;
- consequences for personal capabilities and social rights (regarding financial scope, decent living conditions, social inclusion and participation, social recognition and self-esteem, chances of getting a new job or a vocational education and training);
- perception of the 2008 crisis: the personal, societal, political consequences of the crisis;
- personal future prospects;
- discussion of societal/political demands and possible solutions.

After finishing the interviews there have been three *feedback meetings* with the steering group up to now: the first one took place in December 2015, the second one in March 2016, the third one in June 2016. Matters of discussion were (1) first sketches of the empirical findings, (2) further steps of examination to be carried out by the researcher on the basis of the interview transcripts, (3) the draft version of the German National Report (German language). The final version of the German report will be presented at an ELAN meeting in Kassel in October 2016 (and presumably at an ALI meeting in *Gießen* in autumn 2016).

2.2.4 Future activities

To undertake action as a final step in the process, the RE-InVEST team of SOFI together with the ELAN initiative are planning a *public event* on the results and political implications of the RE-InVEST work package 3. In order to combine the findings of the German national report with joint results of work package 3 as a whole we are planning to hold a conference on social policy and (long-term) unemployment in Europe in spring 2017 in Kassel.

3. Two selected biographies

The following two biographies have been selected because they illustrate that the individual path to long-term unemployment – despite quite different initial conditions especially in terms of education and qualification levels – is paved by accumulating labour market risks. Although the individual risk structure is rather distinct, the biographies have in common that a return into a “normal” employment is out of question for both Doris and Otto.¹⁴

3.1 Biography of Doris¹⁵

Doris was born in 1968. She is now 47 years old and lives in a medium-sized German town. After leaving school she did not take up vocational training but took a job as unskilled employee in the Depot store of a military base in her hometown. She was 18 years old then (1986). In the following years she married and in 1992 had a son. During pregnancy she gave up her job (in 1991). Her husband had a fulltime job at that time, so the financial situation of the family was satisfactory. This was one of the reasons why she did not experience her new situation as a state of unemployment, the more so as she could concentrate now on the roles of mother and housewife. However, she also was forced into these roles because she could not get a place in a kindergarten for her son until he was five years old, only a part-time place for three hours in the morning (from 8:30 to 11:30 am), so it was still impossible for her to find a suitable part-time job that she could combine with her family responsibilities.

In 1999 her husband lost his job and became unemployed, thus the financial situation of the family worsened considerably. The family was reliant upon the unemployment benefit of Doris’ husband now: according to the then applicable regulation her husband was entitled to receive 67 percent of his former wage for at longest 24 months, after that he received about 50 percent of his former wage for an unlimited period. That year their seven years old son started attending school and Doris was seeking for a job now. She did not get a permanent job but had casual jobs from time to time (part-time jobs, or low-paid mini-jobs), for instance in a supermarket.

In 2005 – her husband was still jobless – a reform of labour-market regulation, the so called “Hartz-reform”, was implemented by the German government (see above). This change of law led to “an extreme worsening” of the family’s living conditions. Due to the harsh cut down of benefits for long-term unemployed persons as a consequence of the Hartz-reform her husband’s unemployment benefit was reduced, so the financial restraints of the family became stricter than ever. For Doris the Hartz reform had dramatic consequences, too: At that time she had a mini-job in a supermarket (restocking deep frozen foods); due to the Hartz regulation 360 of the 390 Euros she was earning then had to be set against the social benefits for which her family had an entitlement; thus only 30 Euros remained. Furthermore, the supermarket terminated her employment two months after the Hartz reform came into force: due to the Hartz regulation she had to submit a monthly proof of earnings certificate to the job agency; however, this procedure appeared to be too cumbersome for her employer. Thus, she received the notice of termination shortly afterwards.

As a next biographical turning point Doris got divorced from her husband. She became a single mother who had to care for a teenage son and make a living by scarce Hartz benefits. Since 2005 – after being laid off by the supermarket – Doris was permanently without a job. However, in retrospect she apparently

14 Both interviewees agreed with including their anonymised biographies into this national report.

15 Pseudonym.

perceives the whole period since giving up her first job at the depot store in 1991 as a time of unemployment. In the interview she describes this period as a “twenty years long gap in my biography” – a gap that cannot be made undone anymore. From her point of view this “gap” is one important reason why she could not get a new job since then. Anyway, her experiences with job seeking and with the job agency were mostly discouraging. Since 2005 she got no job offer by the job agency at all, because “it never was fitting anyhow”, once she was “too young, once too old, once in the wrong target group”. Moreover, she reports that the job agency did not offer any reasonable education opportunities to her: the permanent answer was “no, no, no” without any explanation. The job agency only offered “a training as a nurse of dementia patients” and “a mini-training as a dishwasher” – but she was not willing to do those jobs, or to attend the training measures offered to her. In her eyes the limitation on these offers was a kind of gender-specific discrimination by the job agency. Thus, in her opinion the job agency let her down since twenty years.

Doris reports that she was not struck by the crisis in 2008 directly; however, due to the crisis “some things became more expensive, the money got tighter (...) and one became aware of the fact that it will be still more difficult to get a job, any kind of job”. She adds that she was (and is) not willing to accept a job “for 3.50 Euros/hour”, not even in times of crisis, because such a low-paid job would not help to get out of the Hartz system of social assistance. For Doris the next biographical turning point came when her son had completed school and vocational training and left the joint household: “This was much like a *cut*”¹⁶. Now she could have worked full-time again, but this turned out to be “actually impossible” because of the twenty years-long gap in her biography. She applied for a new job for several times unsuccessfully. In one of the job interviews the rejection was explained to her in the following way: “Well, you just lazed around on the couch for twenty years”. Doris reports about experiences of discrimination due to a lack of vocational education: she argues that employers nowadays are looking for skilled workers only, even in the case of basic operations. It does not play a role anymore, which actual abilities someone has at his or her command. Thus, Doris personally experienced a loss of social recognition because she remained unskilled. In her perception this trend of devaluation has been forced by politics and the media. As a consequence she sees herself branded: “These are the under-qualified people” who are not suitable for the labour market anymore. Besides such discouraging or even humiliating experiences Doris talks about some difficulties with changing her daily routines after her son had left home: “And finally all things are done and one has to restructure the day. And that isn’t easy. It is easier if you are not alone, that means if you have a purpose. (...) As mother with a child you don’t really become aware of it (*of joblessness; R.M.*) in the beginning”. Meanwhile, she even is too old for getting a vocational education grant. She reports that the job agencies offer such grants only to jobless persons who are less than 45 years old.

Since 2015 Doris participates in a measure of vocational preparation that also includes computer training – the first measure that was offered to her since 10 years. The measure is affiliated to the Gießen initiative of unemployed people (ALI) which among other things runs a café and meeting point down town. In her eyes this measure makes sense: it motivates her to go out and find new contacts in the café, to talk about problems connected to joblessness, to do something useful: being busy in the café for example (preparing brunch; operating the coffee machine, etc.). The measure is limited in time for at longest twelve months. But no matter how long the measure will last – the ALI initiative and café will be open for her in any case. This is very important for her, because in the course of her long-term unemployment she experienced a reduction of social contact as well as increasing social exclusion: she complains about not being able to keep up financially with others in her (former) social environment (friends, relatives, etc.). This severely diminished the possibilities of staying in contact with or visiting someone who does not live in the near neighbourhood, “this has worsened during the last years”. At present all of her acquaintances “receive social welfare benefits in one way or another”. She lives in a neighbourhood (in the town of Gießen) that in her eyes can be described as a “deprived area” (“*sozialer Brennpunkt*”): “We have a lot of people in this residential district who only live by Hartz benefits”. Social exclusion went along with a loss of social recognition: Doris argues

16 She used the English word „cut”.

that people who receive “Hartz IV” benefits (“Hartz IV” is part of the Hartz reform package which specifically regulates the benefit system for long-term unemployed persons) have an “extremely negative” image in the German public: “Dumb, idle, sucker, drunk, bad breeding ...”. Sometimes people say this “frankly to one’s face”. Moreover, she reports about social devaluation of Hartz IV benefit recipients by some German media (popular press; talk shows on TV): They were stereotyped as antisocial people with broken homes, or as profiteers of tax payers’ money, etc. This often was combined with a blame-the-victim culture: “All that stupid sayings like ‘who really is willing to work will get a job finally’”.

Doris describes her future prospects as rather humble: “Hartz benefits are only for bare survival”. One tries to get along with it, one learns how to exist anyhow. In the course of her long-term unemployment the situation “tightened more and more, things somehow became more and more regulated”, for instance the prescribed size and cost of the flat, or the maximum benefits for the household’s water consumption, etc. “Someday one comes to know that there is no way out of this anymore (...); one has to stay at this point until the age of 70, 80, no idea, if one gets as old, but one will keep staying at this point”. She merely has to expect a minimal pension that has to be augmented by a welfare benefit called basic security at old age (“*Grundsicherung im Alter*”). Thus, she expects harsh financial constraints and scarce living conditions for the rest of her life. Even if she would find a future job – at latest at the age of 67 or 69 “I shall be back to where I am now”.

3.2 Biography of Otto¹⁷

Otto was born in 1954. He is now 61 years old and lives in a medium-sized German town. He visited high school and made his Abitur certificate (the general qualification for university entrance). He studied psychology and received his degree in 1981. His first job lasted ten months: he worked in the mental ward of a hospital– a post which was funded by a job creation measure. Because this was a fixed-term job, Otto applied for a position as psychologist at the state welfare association and got a job in North Hessen. For nearly two years he worked in this position before he gave up on it. He did so because the job became problematic for him: he could not relax after work, “instead I took the work home with me”, so finally he decided to dismiss the job (1984). He was already married at this time, and together with his wife he started an advertising and paperwork agency, but the business did not work well. Thus, he had to seek out for a new job and started a professional retraining as a programmer at a large industrial firm. The retraining lasted for one year (1986-1987), but Otto was not successful in finding a job subsequently. He applied for positions in Germany, Switzerland and Austria but only got rejections.

This situation marks an incisive turning point in Otto’s life: He now was unemployed and, furthermore, got divorced from his wife. At the time they had two children who were one and five years. After the separation they lived with their mother. Every second weekend they stayed with Otto. He reports that he had to explain to them his restricted financial situation which did not allow him to answer to all their wishes. “Occasionally I could buy something for them, but not each time and not the most expensive stuff”.

Otto was now living alone and seeking a new job again. In autumn 1987 he got a job as a waiter in a restaurant, about 25 kilometers off his hometown. However, six months later, at Easter 1988, the restaurant building burnt down and Otto became jobless again. He went to the employment agency which offered him a fixed-term position as agency worker at an office furniture manufacturer near his hometown. After his temporary job had finished the company offered him a regular job which started in April 1989. Otto was 35 years old now and began to work as a stockman at the office furniture manufacturer. In retrospective this was a “stroke of luck” for him, the more so as in the beginning he “did not have a clue” about the things he would have to do in this job. It was a typical semi-skilled occupation with training on the job. As Otto stresses this job had nothing to do with his first profession as psychologist, nevertheless he took delight in this new job, because it better fitted to him “as mere office work”. Thus, things became better for him, the more so as he meanwhile became married to his second wife who also had two children. However, in

17 Pseudonym.

January 1993 he had a serious accident on the way to work: on this winter morning he took as usual his bicycle for the 12 kilometers long route to the firm, when he was heavily struck by a car from behind. He suffered from bad injuries, especially from a severe traumatic brain injury. Otto assumes that he nevertheless had been lucky at last, because he had a bike helmet on his head: “Without that helmet I would not have survived the accident”. He stayed for ten days at the critical care unit; after leaving the hospital he additionally had to stay for six and a half weeks at a rehab-center. Finally he could return to his workplace at the office furniture manufacturer.

Three years after, in 1996, the economic situation of the firm became problematic, because the order position had worsened. As a consequence the firm terminated the jobs of 300 employees, Otto was one of them. However, two or three weeks after that measure the firm got “a huge order”. Given this new situation the works council of the firm called for rehiring as much as possible of the dismissed employees. So Otto could come back to his workplace. However, after all that “there was something wrong with me and one year later I left”. Again he was unemployed; two or three years later the firm ultimately broke down and did not exist any longer.

Giving up his job at the office furniture manufacturer was again an incisive turning point in Otto’s life, because a period of long-term unemployment – for about seven years – subsequently began. During that period his father died; afterwards Otto often traveled by train to Bremen (about 350 kilometers away from his hometown) where he had to take care for his mother who was living now as a widow. During several years he alternately stayed for four weeks in Bremen at his mother’s home and for four weeks in his hometown. Due to periodically caring for his mother he didn’t really look for a new job during these years. And – “astonishingly” – he got hardly any job offer by the job agency as well. According to the then applicable regulation Otto received unemployment benefits (“Arbeitslosenunterstützung”) for one and a half year (at max 67 percent of his former wage), after that he received about 50 percent of his former wage for an unlimited period (“Arbeitslosenhilfe”). During this period of unemployment he got divorced from his second wife and has been living alone since then.

Otto emphasises the fact that it was very important for him to maintain a “daily structure” during his long period of joblessness: Whenever he was in fairly good health he went to the university library in order to read journals or books, for instance. Moreover, for several years he walked around at night gathering bottles (in order to get the deposit); when he came home at noon, he had to lay-down and sleep.

In 2005 – the year of the “Hartz” labour market reform (see above) – Otto decided to start something new and took over a little café in Gießen. He ran the café for six and a half years, but then, in 2012, he had to give it up due to health restrictions as well as to economic reasons (the café did not run well any longer).

After giving up the café Otto was unemployed again and had to live on Hartz IV benefits. He was 58 years old and did not get any job since then. He reports that meanwhile he was “sorted out by the job agency, because they don’t see any chances that I will get a job somewhere anymore. I am now 61”. But it was not just because of his age but of his health restrictions, too: “I have a disabled person’s pass and a 70 percent degree of disability”. Given his age and his limitations of health Otto does not expect to get a (paid) job anymore. Instead he sees himself already as a retiree (and introduces himself as such if asked).

An important aspect of Otto’s biography was and is his nearly thirty year-long membership in the ALI initiative of unemployed people. He tells that he never lost contact to the initiative, not even during times he had a job: sometimes he came around then visiting the ALI café, or saying hello. Moreover, since long he fulfills a function within the initiative: as an assessor of the managing committee. In his eyes the initiative not least serves as help for self-help, as a place to come in contact with other (unemployed) people, to have discussions, to listen to and discuss popular lectures on specific (political, social, economic, etc.) issues once a month.

From Otto’s point of view “it is difficult to say” whether the crisis of 2008 had personal consequences for him, for his living conditions or his employment opportunities. At that time he ran the little café (see above) – the fact that he had to give it up in 2012 is not attributed by him to the crisis but primarily to his worsening health back then. However, he considers indirect consequences of the crisis: “The break-down of banks (“Bankenkladderadatsch”) mostly affect the socially deprived and unemployed people, because a huge

amount of money has been spent for bank bailout – money that could have been used somewhere else instead. At present there's the problem – especially for Hartz IV people – that the funding of advanced training or re-education measures have been cut down brutally". However, as Otto adds: "This won't affect me personally anymore because they (*the job agency; R.M.*) probably would not invest money in me anyway", the more so as many people of his age group have already been sorted out by the job agencies.

Otto knows from personal experience that Hartz IV benefits leave little leeway in everyday life, as regards the provision with groceries, for instance. He indicates that he learned since long – since the days he had a wife and two children – to be money-saving when buying food or other things of everyday need. This apparently helps him to cope with the present situation. His scarce financial situation is also due to the fact that his small "reduced earning capacity pension" ("*Erwerbsminderungsrente*") of 290 Euros is fully discounted from his Hartz IV benefits and "thereby is for the birds".

Otto has acquired a specific coping strategy against resentments and social devaluation: For two times in his life he suffered from severe mental health problems. He learnt to deal openly with his disease: "Well, I don't try to make a secret out of it, because hiding it will cost too much strength and energy". The more people with mental disease would openly stand for it, Otto adds, the more other people would know about it and the stigmatisation could be reduced by this. "With unemployment it's quite similar: there are a lot of people who try to hide it. (...) In my case it's different.". Furthermore, Otto tries to release himself from social devaluation by calling himself a "retiree" – a social role which is much more accepted by the German public than the status of long-term joblessness.

The role of a "retiree" defines his future prospects as well. Otto is quite sure that he never will return into a formal employment relationship anymore – due to his age and disability. He already thought about voluntary work with refugees, or about offering piano lessons. He regrets some limitations of his everyday mobility – by two different aspects: due to his disability he cannot ride a bicycle anymore which he extensively did in former years; due to his scarce financial situation he cannot visit his mother (who is partly care-dependent) and his children as often as he wants to, the more so as he became a grandfather six months ago.

From his point of view the Hartz IV benefits hardly allow to live a decent life. He can expect only a small pension, maybe augmented by a basic security at old age ("*Grundsicherung im Alter*"). Besides his limitations of mobility he especially complains about the financially caused foregoing of cultural events, e.g. music festivals, because he cannot afford the ticket prices. However, he describes his situation not as deprived as in the case of many other jobless people, "because from time to time my mother adds something (*to his income; R.M.*); but those other people are in hard luck if they are completely alone and don't get any help or support at all".

4. Analysis

4.1 Before the crisis: the impact of German labour market reforms (the “Hartz reforms”)

The crisis of 2008 and following years was neither the initial cause of the unemployment of our interviewees nor the major factor of influence regarding their experiences during joblessness as well as the development of their living conditions in recent years. Similar to many other participants of the two initiatives (ELAN in Nordhessen and ALI in Gießen) many of the interviewees look back on an already long “career” of unemployment – for instance for ten or more years. Their status of long-term unemployment already began before the crisis broke out. In some cases long-term unemployment was interrupted by short-term periods of (minor) employment, in other cases participants have been continually without any job since many years. Most of our interviewees became unemployed by rather specific (or individual) reasons: because of a sudden or serious disease; because of becoming a single parent; because of living together with a care-dependent relative; due to a sudden insolvency of the employer; for reasons of delinquency, etc. In some cases, two or more of these factors were intertwined – such a situation made it even harder to get a new job (see the biographies above).

Not the crisis but the implementation as well as the practical consequences of the so called “Hartz-reforms” (2005) have been the most severe experience for the majority of our interviewees. A lot of them became unemployed before the Hartz-reforms came into force – since then they either experienced several subsequent periods of joblessness or look back on a still enduring phase of permanent unemployment. For most of our research participants the reform program led to a drastic cut down of their benefits: Before the Hartz-reforms became law there had been two wage-oriented benefit systems for unemployed persons: The first one (“Arbeitslosenunterstützung”) was based on the public unemployment insurance and paid at long-est during the first 24 months of unemployment (60 to 67 percent of the former wage; the duration of payments depended on the duration of former employment). The second one (“Arbeitslosenhilfe”) was tax-funded and paid after the first (at longest) 24 months of unemployment for an unlimited period (about 50 percent of the former wage). With the Hartz-reforms the first benefit system did not change substantially (now called “Arbeitslosengeld 1”/”ALG 1”). But the second benefit system had been changed radically: it is still tax-funded, but the individually paid benefits do not depend any more on the former wage. They have been adapted to the general level of social assistance (now called “Arbeitslosengeld 2”/”ALG 2”) and require a means test. In 2015 the benefits for a single person amounted to 399 Euros/month plus the rent (incl. heating costs) for an “appropriate” flat (the benefits increased slightly since 2005). In the case of multi-person households a differentiated scaling of benefits is applied.

As a result it can be stated that long-term unemployed people have been worst affected by the far going turn of German labour market policy in 2005: the combination of stronger activation rules on the one hand and austerity measures on the other like the cut-down of benefits (the introduction of “ALG 2”) or the promotion of low-paid jobs had – and still have – a severe impact on those people who are without a job since one or more years. The following chapters will deal with the consequences this kind of social disinvestment can have: concerning the financial, social and psychological restraints (chapters 4.3 and 4.4) as well as the build-up of resilience by unemployed people (4.5), or concerning the impact on their human rights (4.6) and individual capabilities (4.7). But first of all we will highlight the additional or intensifying impact of the crisis in 2008 and the subsequent austerity measures as they were experienced by our interviewees.

4.2 The additional or intensifying impact of the crisis

Some of our interviewees point to negative consequences of *austerity on the local or regional level* – consequences by which jobless (or other poor) people are hit harder than average households. For instance when it came to savings on the public infrastructure or institutions like the local public transport, communal libraries, public baths, public meeting places, community housing, etc.; or austerity through increasing communal charges, i.e. public transport fees, kindergarten charges, etc. A lot of criticism offered by our interviewees addresses the politics of *bank bailout* during the crisis: There would have been better use for the hundreds of billion Euros which were given to the banks, if the money had been spent for social investments, for instance for promotion programs in support of jobless people (or poor people in general). Some interviewees note that *older employees* have been disproportionately disadvantaged by that, because a lot of them had been “sorted out” by the firms during the crisis. Another negative consequence of the crisis, as seen by many of our interviewees, is the *increasing number of low-paid non-standard or minor jobs* on the German labour market. To be sure, this trend already started with the Hartz reforms which facilitated the offering of non-standard jobs (see above; chapter 1). However, from the viewpoint of our interviewees this trend was reinforced by the crisis and worsened chances of regaining a standard employment relationship which most jobless people are looking for. Some of the interviewees see themselves directly affected by this trend: Though their own job loss was not initiated by the crisis they value its impact on the German labour market as *one* factor besides others (age, illness, lack of qualification, long-term absence from the labour market, etc.) which – additionally – reduces their chances of getting a normal and fairly well-paid job in the future.¹⁸ Thus, they see their future prospects rather pessimistic: from their point of view future job opportunities will – if at all – be limited to the sector of precarious employment and be coupled with a (future) life of continuous poverty.

4.3 Financial, social and psychological restraints

Considering the cut down of benefits for many long-term unemployed persons due to the Hartz-reforms it is no surprise that nearly all of our interviewees experience the *financial restraints* as one of the most burdening consequences of their joblessness. To be forced to make one’s living by “ALG 2” (or “Hartz IV”¹⁹) permanently requires – as reported by the interviewees – a high degree of thriftiness, cautiousness and planning in every day life in order to get by until the end of the month (“At the end of the money there’s still much month”). Such a situation demands – painful – renuncements in numerous aspects of life. A lot of our interviewees complain about the fact that they only can afford cheap food and beverages, some of them wonder how to provide themselves and their children with healthy eating under these circumstances. Moreover, economic constraints also overshadow other aspect of provisioning, i.e. with energy (electricity, fuel), clothing, furniture, media products, etc. Every rise in prices of every day goods can lead to financial bottlenecks; severe financial risks are threatening if household appliances are damaged and have to be repaired or even replaced. Furthermore, the search for a new flat – for instance, if one’s rent contract has been terminated by the house owner – can lead to serious financial trouble as well as to quarrels with the job agency about the appropriateness of a new flat and the conditions of receiving full housing subsidies.

However, it is not only the day-to-day concern about the financial constraints one has to deal with. More generally, the common experiences of the interviewees showed that long-term unemployment severely limits their opportunities and capabilities of living a life they had sought for. In many cases their occupational career was terminated rather early and thus could not find complete expression. Besides the *long-term exclusion from employment and work life* (and from various aspects of social integration by work) the *possibilities of social participation beyond work can become limited*, too (see also Lehweß-Litzmann [2016: 32-39] on the basis of survey data). Attending cultural events, having a meal with friends in a restaurant, visiting festivities, arranging family celebrations – all these things may exceed one’s financial means and can lead to certain avoidance

18 In one case an interviewee reported about her husband who also is long-term unemployed.

19 As these benefits are generally labeled in Germany.

mechanisms. Some of the interviewees experience social marginalisation combined with a perceived *loss of social recognition*, for instance among relatives or the wider social context, by public authorities, or by society in general. They report about resentments and blame-the-victim culture in parts of the German public (including the media). Some pointed out that long-term jobless people (or other poor people who are reliant upon social assistance) are widely stigmatised as “Hartz-IV persons” (“*Hartz-Vierer*”), used as synonym for people who are unwilling to work or have bad behaviors (idleness, addiction to alcohol or drugs, trying to cheat the welfare state, etc.). In the words of one of our (female) interviewees: Hartz-IV beneficiaries are described in certain press media as “anti-social suckers” (“*asozjale Schmarotzer*”); furthermore, in her eyes a lot of people make a difference between “normal” unemployed persons and “Hartz-IV persons”: “An unemployed person is someone, who recently has lost his job, but will have a new employment tomorrow. Hartz IV is something complete different. A Hartz-IV person is a Hartz-IV person. (...) A Hartz-IV person is just idle, idle, he rather parties than goes to work, he does not want to work at all”.

Some of the interviewees report that the whole situation of long-term unemployment under the terms of Hartz-IV regulation makes them feel like “wedged in a corset”: it is seen as a situation that leaves *little room to move* even for everyday procurements, needs or activities, to say nothing of more exceptional things like improving the own housing conditions, pursuing certain hobbies, traveling for holidays, being generous with the children (clothing, toys, pocket money, etc.), participating in the local cultural life, etc. Moreover, this perception often is accompanied by the *worrisome future prospect* of being unable to get out of this “corset” anymore: some of the interviewees show the – more or less realistic – expectation that they will not leave the status of unemployment until their retirement age; others assume that they will only get precarious or minor jobs for the future. The “corset” even evokes fears of falling into a budget black hole one day by which the own living conditions could worsen dramatically. Thus, some interviewees report about permanent feelings of uncertainty (“the ground falls out from underneath your feet”).

4.4 Treatment by/struggle with the job agency

The experiences the interviewees made with the job agencies are mixed: a few of the interviewees – especially some of the younger ones – report about an all in all fair and helpful treatment by the responsible job agency which, for instance, showed an understanding in the case of long-term illness and the specific requirements that should be given regarding the re-integration into labour. In most cases, however, the interviewees express a lot of critique about the treatment by the job agencies, or report about various negative experiences they made over the years.

Many of them expressively underline the fact that the practices of the job agencies have changed severely with the Hartz-reforms. From their point of view, the restrictions imposed by the job agencies have become more and more strict since then. This especially applies to practices of sanctioning in cases of neglecting specific instructions by the job agency, or of breaking an agreement which has been made by the unemployed person and the job agency in order to force the re-integration of this person into work-life (“*Eingliederungsvereinbarung*”). Such an agreement includes duties of the job agency (e.g. job service; professional advice; funding of qualification measures, etc.) as well as the jobless person (sending in [numerous] applications for employment; to be willing to accept “reasonable” job offers as well as qualification measures recommended by the job agency). Because of the fact that limits of acceptability have been eased considerably with the Hartz-reforms, long-term unemployed persons must be willing to accept nearly any job in order to avoid sanctions by the job agency (temporary cutting of benefits [normally for 3 months] by 30 percent, or by 60 percent in the case of repeating infringements). Thus, “reasonable” jobs also include non-standard, low-paid or the so called “1-Euro-jobs”, publicly funded jobs at an hourly wage of 1 Euro, fulfilling purposes of public interest. Exceptions are only made for personal reasons, e.g. in the case of a (chronic) disease, physical deficiencies, mental illness, a home care-dependent relative, etc.

Nearly all of the interviewees experienced the outcomes of the Hartz-reforms at first hand – thus it is no surprise that they have numerous critical comments on it. Just a few examples: one interviewee characterises the Hartz-reforms as a bundle of measures which “more and more squeezes one’s throat”. Another

one argues that the Hartz-reforms “aim at creating the largest low-wage labour market in Europe”. A third interviewee experiences the Hartz IV measures as “bullying restrictions” – she and her family felt treated like “second or third-class citizens”: She reports that the job agency tried to force her daughter to leave school before doing her A-levels and complete a vocational education instead in order to contribute to the income of the family. After a lot of struggle the family finally could prevent the job agency from executing the planned measure.

A frustrating experience for numerous of the interviewees was (or still is) the fact that the pressure exerted by the job agencies is in stark contrast to the small number of job offers they actually have, let alone the tiny number of (positive) answers by firms to whom interviewees had sent a job application letter. In most cases they did not receive any answer at all. Additionally to that, some report about being forced by the job agency to attend certain qualification measures which they experienced as more or less useless or senseless in terms of enhancing their employability.

All these experiences can reinforce the dominating perception of being wedged in a corset, or being under permanent regulatory control – combined with a feeling of uncertainty about measures, directives or even sanctions that could be imposed by the job agency. For some of the interviewees all this amounts to a steadily stress-bearing situation – with negative consequences for their mental health: they complain, for instance, about adverse effects on their self-esteem, growing anxieties, or even severe mental disorder that needed medical treatment. Some report about their tremendous aversion to enter the job agency any more or to speak to the responsible person of contact (one of the interviewees called it a “brain wash”). Other interviewees feel deeply uneasy or even upset whenever the job center phones them or sends an official letter to them (e.g. with an invitation/citation for a briefing). Furthermore, some of the interviewees express their experiences with long-term unemployment as well as the treatment by the responsible job agency as a kind of social incapacitation. Thus, in their eyes the whole situation comes up to a violation of human rights – the right of a fair and respectful treatment by representatives of a public authority (see below, chapter 4.6).

4.5 Resilience

Considering the discouraging experiences with long-term unemployment as well as with the treatment by the job agency the question arises whether people are able to overcome the stresses and strains of such a situation they are confronted with. Hence, one of the issues discussed in the workshop (as well as in the interviews) was the question of *individual empowerment*. What empowers someone in order to cope with long-term unemployment? All discussants agreed that *participating in an initiative of unemployed people* can be seen as a main source of personal strengthening – or *resilience*. In detail, there are various aspects to this.

- *Experiences of social relationship, community and solidarity*: most of the interviewees perceive the initiatives (ELAN and ALI) as a means against social isolation, an opportunity to find contact, a place for the exchange of information, or an opportunity to get advice (e.g. about rights and duties regarding provisions by the job agency, or about [legal] possibilities of resistance against sanctions, etc.);
- *Experiences of self-efficacy and self-affirmation*: the initiatives offer opportunities to fulfil volunteering tasks in support of the collective (or single participants): several of the interviewees are (or have been) involved in specific projects or in advisory activities (the latter partly connected to trade unions) – a task that strengthens one’s self-confidence and supports the self-awareness of being a “useful” person, or doing things that “make sense”;
- *Structuring the daily routines*: Some of the interviewees emphasise the fact that the initiatives are not only helpful in order to get out of – or prevent from – social isolation, but also structure – or stabilise – their everyday life. This fact was reported primarily by some participants of the Gießen initiative ALI: the initiative runs a meeting place and café downtown which is open for jobless people. The opportunity of visiting the café several times a week or even every day, as reported by several interviewees, motivates oneself to get up in the morning, moving downtown by bus or bicycle, etc., sitting in the café for several hours talking to other visitors, reading newspapers, having a tea or coffee (sometimes combined with a

brunch), etc. Furthermore, some of the Gießen interviewees combine their attendance to the ALI café with some voluntary activities like preparing coffee or tea, operating the coffee machine, taking care for the brunch buffet, etc. All this helps with organizing the daily routines which lack the time schedule of formal employment and thus can be seen as a relevant coping strategy against the stresses and strains of joblessness;

- *Gaining of knowledge, competences, orientation, etc.:* Some of the interviewees – especially those who are (or have been) involved in advisory activities – see the initiative as an opportunity of getting more comprehensive knowledge about the political or societal causes and implications of unemployment. In their opinion this led to a deeper understanding of one’s own situation, too, and, moreover, enhanced their capabilities of coping with long-term unemployment. Thus it helps playing an active role in the struggle for social recognition, fair treatment by the job agencies, or better living conditions – instead of being trapped in the passive role of a victim. In addition to internal capabilities provided by the initiative’s network *external professional help* must be required in some cases in order to overcome certain problems, e.g. severe conflicts with the job agency or other local authorities (in such cases it could be very useful to have [free] juridical assistance).

Besides the benefits of participating in an initiative the interviewees report about various (and partly individualised) *strategies of self-care* that make it easier to cope with long-term joblessness: some of them mention that they intentionally try to avoid social isolation by “going out”, being among people, maintaining contacts beyond the initiative, attending social events, etc. Others report that they seek to do things they like whenever it is possible, e.g. going outdoors, cooking a fine meal, looking after the pet(s), attending a language-course or other opportunities for general education, pursuing certain voluntary activities (e.g. in a trade union or a welfare organisation, in support of a local food bank, etc.). All this contributes to the building-up of resilience in the face of long-term unemployment. Some of these strategies, especially those aiming at certain learning objectives or voluntary activities, require a supporting social or institutional environment to unlock their full potential (e.g. support or responsiveness by local authorities and social services, educational institutions, welfare organisations on site, or trade unions that are willing to cooperate with jobless people).

Last but not least, the interviewees report about certain *adaptation strategies* in everyday life which are more or less indispensable in order to overcome the situation of long-term joblessness and its consequences. This especially applies to the financial situation of the household: One has to learn how to get along with little money, otherwise one risks running into debt. Thus, one has to adapt household routines and practices to permanent financial constraints: for instance, one has to know where to buy the cheapest food or clothing, where to get appropriate (second hand) furniture, how to save costs for energy, heating, water or other things of daily provision, in short: how to manage one’s tight “Hartz IV money” over the month.

To be sure, all this means in effect that one has to adapt to (relative) poverty (see above), nevertheless such an adaptation strategy can make this situation more bearable.

4.6 Impact on human rights

For most of our interviewees the *Hartz reforms* have been an incisive experience in a quite negative way (see above). Some of them discuss this topic explicitly as a violation – or cut back – of human resp. social rights: they argue that Hartz IV benefits only allow a living at the limit of the minimum subsistence level; under these conditions they perceive high risks of suffering from shortages in everyday supply or even of slipping down into oppressive poverty. The latter can happen, if one has to take out a loan with the social assistance office, for instance for new furniture (because no bank would give a credit to a Hartz IV benefits receiver). One of our interviewees – a single mother with a disabled grown-up daughter – reports that she “effectively had to beg” for the loan; to make things worse she was forced by the office to have a monthly instalment deposit of 100 Euros, a sum that from her point of view is nearly impossible to handle: “I don’t know how to manage it”, because only “340 Euro” a month are left for herself and her daughter. In her eyes this is a

case of blatant social injustice: “Because there is money for everything, but for people who are struggling, there is no money at all”.

As a common perception of our interviewees it becomes apparent that long-term unemployment is a biographical stage of increasing economic and social deprivation, even in terms of nourishment and other basic needs. Furthermore, the Hartz reforms exacerbated the risk of deprivation and falling into poverty. Especially those people who already became long-term unemployed before 2005 perceived the implementation of the Hartz reforms as “incredibly unfair”, leading to increasing *social injustice*: one incisive consequence of the Hartz IV regulation was that even persons who had worked continually for 20 or 30 years before getting unemployed could fall into a financial hole after 12 or (if 50 years or older) at most 24 months of joblessness. After this period of receiving unemployment benefit one first has to eat up one’s savings (if existing) to a certain point, subsequently one has to live by scarce social assistance benefits (see above). Many of those affected by such a legally predefined procedure perceive this as a denial of their life-time achievement.

Moreover, *social injustice* is also perceived by some of those interviewees who either worked in non-standard jobs formerly or expect to be limited to such low-level employments in future. These interviewees see themselves discriminated regarding their employment outlook compared to those whose work biography is not (yet) marked by periods of unemployment or non-standard employment. One of our interviewees who made pertinent experiences with low-paid work and fix-term labour contracts in recent years complains about increasing insecurity of planning concerning work life as well as private life. From his point of view such kinds of employment are “demanding too much” of people because non-standard work contracts legitimise arbitrariness by the employers and therefore reduce planning certainty of the working people. When he had such jobs he was forced to do a lot of overtime to earn enough money to make a living, however, “one has the money, but no life quality anymore”; people do these jobs because they are anxious about becoming jobless or being sanctioned by the job agency. Thus he is very critical with the labour market regulation on the national German and the European level as well – a regulation that has facilitated the offering of non-standard jobs by the employers.

As already described above most of the interviewees vehemently criticise the impact which the Hartz reforms had on the *practices and services of job agencies*. Some of them explicitly report about their negative experiences as violation of fundamental rights, others do that more implicitly. The main topics as mentioned by the interviewees:

- a *disrespectful treatment* by the job agency’s person dealing with one’s case: some interviewees report about being insulted, offended, blamed or intimidated by their case worker; others perceive unfairness and arbitrariness: sometimes it depends on the “mood of the day” whether the case worker approves a specific measure or grant, or if he “has a down on someone”;
- *being under (permanent) pressure by the job agency*: several interviewees feel pressurised or harassed by the job agency’s provisions, directives or sanctioning – some of them report about serious consequences for their well-being or even for their mental or physical health (see above).

Social incapacitation: some interviewees see themselves incapacitated by bureaucratic treatments they are subjected to: it is the case worker “who rules your money, or decides whether you may buy a new pair of spectacles or not”. The perception of social incapacitation can also refer to the official practice of mobility impairments imposed by the job agency. Interviewees criticise measures of sanctioning which can be imposed by the job agency if one leaves his or her place of residence without authorisation. From their point of view the fundamental right of freedom of movement is violated by this provision. *Social devaluation* is another main topic that refers to the question of human rights, especially the right of human dignity. Most of our interviewees report about own experiences with social devaluation; for many of them this is a very emotional issue because social devaluation can overshadow various aspects of their life and affect their self-esteem negatively. Furthermore, the experience of social devaluation can become closely intertwined with the experience of social isolation: both experiences can reinforce each other. Several of the interviewees see

themselves personally “stigmatised”; for some of them the experience of stigmatisation is one of the worst things they had (or have) to go through during joblessness. The experience of social devaluation resp. stigmatisation can be made in one’s own social environment, but also via some public media which in the eyes of several interviewees draw a negative image of long-term unemployed people. All negative stereotyping is bundled in the term “Hartz IV receiver” – a stigma which is widely spread in the German public and has become a source of “group related misanthropy” (Heitmeyer 2012; see also chapter 1) towards unemployed people. The perception of social devaluation can also be forced by negative experiences with the job agency as described above. Experiences of disrespectful treatment, of being pressurised or becoming incapacitated surely can be perceived as personal devaluation and loss of social recognition. Moreover, the regulation of unemployment benefits by Hartz laws, as already described in this chapter, is widely perceived by our interviewees as a devaluation of one’s life achievement – a painful experience which also can be made when it comes to personal retirement: One of our interviewees – again the mother with the disabled daughter – complains about the fact that her small pension of 373 Euros is fully set against her Hartz IV benefit. In her eyes this is a refusal of social recognition: “But I have worked for it. Sure, I appreciate that I got money from the job agency. But nonetheless, there must be an acknowledgement that I did work; how can they take away that little bit (of money) from me, too ...”.

4.7 Impact on capabilities

We conceive “capabilities” as the range of personal choices (or the degree of freedom) people have in order to live a life they value. If subjected to the outcomes of specific austerity measures long-term unemployment must be seen as a biographical stage which in most cases is accompanied by a gradual – and finally often severe – reduction of personal capabilities. A lot of our findings described above, especially the two detailed biographies (see chapter 3) as well as the often reported perception of “being wedged in a corset” (see chapter 4.3), underline this conclusion. The term “capabilities” can be applied to several dimensions of life. In the case of long-term unemployed people the threat to individual capabilities – as indicated by the perceived narrowing of personal choices – becomes primarily visible in the following dimensions:

- *the dimension of employment outlook*: Most of the interviewees have negative experiences regarding the outcomes of job placement by the job agencies as well as the results of their own efforts to find a new job (see the two biographies in chapter 3, for instance). Many of them see their future employment opportunities mostly reduced to non-standard jobs and precarious work conditions;
- *the dimension of financial scope*: The financial constraints imposed by the Hartz IV benefit system in general and specifically the sudden and harsh reduction of benefit payments compared to the unemployment compensation during the early stage of joblessness is perceived by nearly all interviewees as a painful narrowing of options and choices in everyday life – concerning the supply on the level of basic needs as well as on the level of all kinds of consumer durables including accommodation, or concerning mobility and travelling as well as participation in social and cultural life on the local level (see chapter 4.3);
- *the dimension of personal integration into the social environment*: Individual choices concerning the participation in social life are not only restricted by financial constraints caused by long-term unemployment (see the previous paragraph). The experience of social exclusion – or of restricted opportunities regarding social contact – can also be caused by social patterns of stigmatisation or devaluation which some of our interviewees have met even in their close social vicinity (among relatives or in the neighbourhood, for instance). Stigmatisation or devaluation can foster social exclusion by two different mechanisms which possibly may reinforce each other: Firstly by a – stepwise – withdrawal into social isolation by the jobless persons themselves; secondly by certain mechanisms of alienation or withdrawal by people in one’s vicinity who more and more try to avoid coming in social contact with “Hartz IV persons”. A consequence of such mechanisms of social exclusion – as experienced by some of our interviewees – finally might be that one

comes into social contact only with other jobless people or “Hartz IV persons” (as reported by “Doris”; see chapter 3.1).²⁰

The impact of resources and conversion factors:

The predominant experience as emphasised by the interviewees is that the *institutional resources* provided by society or state are insufficient in terms of enabling a decent life, or of facilitating the return into work. They value the *financial resources* in form of Hartz IV benefit at best as a kind of basic protection against acute poverty risks. However, as several of the interviewees have been affected by (chronic) disease which reduce their chances on the labour market considerably the Hartz IV benefits in combination with other payments or measures like statutory sickness benefits, medical service, or rehabilitation measures can have an important function concerning the reintegration in to work life. For two of the younger interviewees in Gießen who both were struck by severe disease such a path of reintegration seemed to be a concrete yet not fully assured perspective by the time of the interview.

The institutional norms and administrative regulations which are formally binding for placement officers can be considered as crucial “*conversion factors*” which define how the factual activities and practices of the job agencies affect the individual chances and choices of jobless persons on the labour market. As already shown above, the functioning of the resource “job agency” is criticised by most of the interviewees: From their point of view, the job agencies do not fulfill their task of bringing back (long-term) jobless people into an acceptable new employment relationship. Furthermore, from their point of view additional measures offered by the job agencies rarely contribute to an extension of individual capabilities regarding the labour market. In contrast, several of the interviewees see themselves marginalised: as early as and in their late forties or beginning fifties they – in their own perception – are either without any chances on the labour market, or restricted to the segment of precarious jobs. Again, in the case of a few younger interviewees we find quite different perceptions concerning specific services and measures of the job agencies: From their point of view, the (temporary) transfer into a so called 1-Euro-job can be an opportunity of social participation, of making new contacts and of opening up new perspectives regarding the individual employment outlook. The two – already mentioned – younger interviewees in Gießen presently had 1-Euro-jobs which were connected to specific projects of the ALI initiative. Both minor jobs were designated for leading into a regular, however fixed-term job (for three years) at ALI subsequently.

With regard to *individual potentials resp. conversion factors* we find a typical biographical trend in our sample: the originally achieved individual potentials which were relevant for one’s own chances on the labour market, for instance based on school education, occupational skills, or acquired competencies, were thwarted in many cases of our sample by individual strokes of fate: these could be caused – as in the case of several interviewees – by a (chronic) disease²¹, but also by chronic care dependency of a close relative, or by becoming a single parent after separation, living with and taking care for a disabled child, becoming (temporary) homeless after separation from one’s husband, etc. (see also the two biographies in chapter 3). These individual restrictions are – as we know from research – highly relevant risk factors concerning chances and choices on the labour market (see above, chapter 1). It is no surprise that we have a clustering of such risk factors in our specific sample of long-term unemployed persons who partly look back on a very long period of joblessness.

Our sample shows an – intended – clustering of persons who are members of (or connected with) initiatives of unemployed people. This can be an explanation of the fact that our empirical findings point – possibly above average – to specific individual potentials resp. conversion factors which could be defined

20 Based on survey data, Lehweß-Litzmann shows: statistically, recipients of basic income possess social networks comparable in size to non-recipients. However, their share of absolutely isolated persons is higher, and basic income recipients participate significantly less often in civil society organisations like associations, trade unions, or church communities (Lehweß-Litzmann 2016: 32-39).

21 In several cases a severe disease was a cause – or even the main cause – of getting unemployed. In other cases long-term unemployment led to – or did reinforce – impairments to health, for instance various forms of mental disorder (see above, chapter 4.4).

as *perceived self-efficacy* or, referring to *Weißmann (2016: 191-232)*, as *ability to self-empowerment*. These personal attributes become apparent in different spheres of activity but share common characteristics: they refer to activities beyond (regular) employment and aim at taking on a socially accepted role – often by doing volunteer work, for instance in the context of trade union activities, local policy, a local food bank or, last not least, an initiative of unemployed people like ELAN or ALI where organised forms of self-help (e.g. advisory activities, computer workshops, cultural and media projects, job application training, running a café and meeting point, etc.) have to be maintained. Besides volunteer work there are, as reported by the interviewees, some other forms of activity which normally are perceived as socially accepted roles, too, for instance forms of adult education, forms of family work, or the planning resp. buildup of a small business enterprise (for instance as a single person). Such an orientation towards activity, as already described above, can result in reinforcing the individual resilience regarding the challenges and burdening of long-term unemployment (chapter 4.5). In our sample the two initiatives ELAN and ALI can be considered as *collective resources – or empowering organisations* – which support the strengthening of resilience as well as the development of individual capabilities regarding social participation beyond work. Furthermore, by facilitating different forms of self-help (see above, chapter 2.2.1) such initiatives may also enhance individual capabilities which help as a job seeker as well as with the handling of requirements, provisions and measures prescribed by the job agency.

5. Conclusion

What does this case study tell about the two research hypotheses set out above (see introduction)?

From the viewpoint of the participants of our target group of long-term unemployed people, the German economic and labour market crisis at the beginning of the 2000s (reaching its maximum in 2005) as well as the resulting reforms of labour market policy (the “Hartz reforms”) have been incisive experiences which motivates them to level fundamental criticism against recent labour market policy, concerning its will and ability in terms of fighting against increasing poverty risks, social discrimination and exclusion of long-term unemployed people. The members of our target group experienced a harsh worsening of their financial situation in everyday life due to a cut down of unemployment benefits and, furthermore, they were confronted with the outcomes of a deregulated labour market which led to an increasing sector of non-standard, precarious jobs. Against the backdrop of these experiences the crisis of 2008 and following years did not appear as a further incision but rather as a continuation of a political and socioeconomic development that had already been set in motion several years before. Furthermore, the comparatively fast recovery of the German economy following the last crisis and, moreover, the considerable decline of overall unemployment since then is in distinct contrast to the situation of those who still remain in (long-term) unemployment and therefore feel uncoupled from the German economic upturn which could be observed during recent years.

Our empirical findings show that long-term unemployment is often closely linked to the experience that *human rights are violated* by the outcomes of the Hartz reforms, or by the provisions and measures imposed by the job agency.

Due to the harsh cut-down of benefits for long-term unemployed persons by the Hartz reforms many of our interviewees see their *right of leading a decent life* and of being protected against increasing economic and social deprivation substantially violated; the existing benefit system, they argue, only allow a standard of living at the limit of the minimum subsistence level.

Social injustice is another main topic which many of our interviewees address concerning the Hartz reforms and its outcomes. Again it's the cut-down of benefits for long-term jobless people that comes to the fore: this measure is widely seen as a kind of *disrespect* to the life-time achievements especially of those who had worked for many years and whose standard of living will be rapidly reduced to the minimum subsistence level after a certain period of unemployment. Social injustice also finds expression, as emphasised by several interviewees, by discriminating mechanisms on the labour market in so far as job prospects of long-term unemployed were limited to low-paid or precarious work.

A third – and often reported – topic is the *right of a fair treatment by the job agencies*: several of our interviewees see this right violated by a disrespectful treatment, or by experiences of permanent pressure and social incapacitation due to the measures and provisions which the job agency imposes.

Last but not least, there is a common experience of *social devaluation* as reported by the interviewees – an experience which affects *the right of human dignity*. Long-term unemployed people meet in many ways a social climate of incomprehension, stigmatisation or even disdain, whether in the closer social environment, in the media or the society as a whole. Even though the labour market reform cannot be seen as the only cause of such a discriminating social climate there is a broad agreement among the interviewees that the Hartz reforms boosted a blame-the-victim-culture which is symbolised in the devaluating term “Hartz IV person” (“Hartz-Vierer”).

Our findings make clear that the outcomes of the German Hartz reforms may restrict *the individual capabilities* of long-term unemployed people severely. Drawing on the experiences which were reported by the

interviewees these restrictions have become apparent with regard to various aspects: the individual employment outlook; the financial scope concerning options and choices in everyday life; the individual choices concerning the participation in social life. In other words: the institutional resources provided by society or state are seen as insufficient in terms of facilitating the return into work, enabling a decent life, or supporting social integration. Most of our interviewees criticise the factual activities and practices of the job agencies which – as institutional resources – should enable individual chances and choices on the labour market, but, in their eyes, fail to do so. In our sample it is only a minority of foremost younger unemployed persons who consider the specific services and measures of the job agency as a helpful path of reintegration into work.

With regard to our target group another relevant finding has to be emphasised: bottom-up initiatives of unemployed people like ELAN and ALI can be considered as collective resources – or empowering organisations – which support the strengthening of individual resilience, for instance in terms of self-efficacy and self-empowerment. Moreover, such initiatives can help with the building-up of individual capabilities regarding activities or forms of social participation and integration beyond work. Last but not least, the initiatives offer different forms of self-help which may enhance individual capabilities of the participants, for instance with regard to the efforts of job seeking, or the handling of requirements and measures prescribed by the job agency.

In the following we sum up the *major conclusions for public policy and practice* which were drawn by the workshop's participants as well as by our interviewees as a whole. Necessary are:

- political decisions and measures against the *cutback of public infrastructure* caused by savings or decreasing investments, especially on the local level: unemployed people as well as other low-income groups are disproportionately disadvantaged by those cutbacks, for instance by the closing of a public library or public bath, by savings in the field of medical facilities, public education or kindergarten, or by drawbacks in the public transport sector;
- improvements for the benefit of a *secure livelihood* which should be achieved by a reformed system of social security. This political objective predominantly requires a substantial increase of the basic security benefits for long-term unemployed persons or poor people in general (presently based on payments by “unemployment benefit II” resp. “Hartz IV social assistance”) – what's needed is a reformed system of basic security which should also include an appropriate compensation for price increase in the field of basic requirements (food, energy, cloth, transport, etc.) as well as financial leeway if exceptional expenditures are necessary (if defective home appliances or broken furniture have to be replaced, for instance). Furthermore, unemployment benefits should allow for participation in social or cultural life (e.g. membership in clubs, attendance of sport or cultural events);
- improvements concerning *social justice*: required are measures against growing social imbalances of income and wealth in German society, for instance by appropriate tax policies (“redistribution from top to bottom” as a key term). Generally speaking, social cleavages should be reduced, not in the least by a “reform” or (partly) revocation of the Hartz reforms (which many of our interviewees hold responsible for a deepening of social cleavages in Germany in recent years);
- improvements concerning *employment security*: German (as well as European) labour market policy should put an end to the expansion of non-standard or low-income jobs – political and legal support should be given primarily to the generation of fair jobs, fair work, or fair payment (including well-aimed governmental employment programs as well as financial support for those firms which are willing to employ [long-term] jobless persons under fair conditions);
- improvements concerning the *social recognition* of (long-term) unemployed people. This should be a task for the society as a whole and for political representatives on different levels of government as well. Media should draw a more comprehensive and differentiated image of long-term unemployed people and their circumstances of life. Politicians should have more readiness to talk to jobless people, to learn about their situation, or should help to give them a voice in society;
- *more appropriate counselling and job services* which should consider the real needs and abilities of (long-term) jobless people. In detail: a higher intensity of counselling and personal advice given by the job agency in

order to help effectively with job seeking (making contact with firms, for instance) or with useful and long-acting qualification measures, under certain circumstances combined with psychological or socio-pedagogical help in order to support occupational rehabilitation. Support of jobless persons should be given without pressure or sanctions by the job agencies – in other words: the job agency has to become an institution where the jobless people can go without fear and be certain that their dignity will be respected;

- improvements concerning the *public funding of local initiatives of unemployed people*: this is an important matter for the participants of our research because financial support (e.g. by local governments) for such initiatives has decreased – under the banner of austerity – in Germany in recent years. Thus, there are fewer and fewer places (like ALI in Gießen, for instance) where unemployed people can go and meet without registration or assignment – places where they can communicate freely and easily, where they can get help, or where they can participate in various activities. Therefore improvements have to be made concerning the financial securing of initiatives and providing organisations. This would help to give these initiatives of jobless people a voice, it could extend their ability to reach their target group (also beyond members) and finally may strengthen their political influence which – at present – is perceived by our interviewees as rather limited.

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Social disinvestment and vulnerable groups in Europe in the aftermath of the financial crisis

The case of homeless people in Ireland

Mary Murphy, Zuzanna Kucharski, Paul Haughan, Emma Richardson, Kathleena Twomey & Tom Thompson

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Contents

List of tables	7
List of figures	9
Introduction	11
1. Context	12
2. Theoretical and Methodological Approach: Human Rights and Capabilities Framework	17
3. Findings	21
Bibliography	33

List of tables

Table 1.1	Poverty, deprivation and equality, 2008-2014 Source: CSO EU-SILC (various years)	12
Table 2.1	Research Participants in 3 locations AC, BD, CL	20

List of figures

Figure 1.1	Homeless adults with dependent children 09/15-10/16: Source: Dublin Housing Executive	15
Figure 2.1	Resources, conversion factors, capability set and achieved functionings	17
Figure 2.2	Merging of Knowledge	18
Figure 2.3	Peer Researchers training in Maynooth University	20

Introduction

Ireland in 2016 is experiencing economic growth, job growth and declining unemployment but the economic crisis has left profound impacts on the lives and future opportunities of many people living in Ireland and particularly on groups who experience structural marginalisation, poverty and disadvantage. This is nowhere more evident than in the thousands of men, women and children who have experienced homelessness. This report analyses the social impact of the crisis (and crisis-related policy reform) on vulnerable groups as well as the impact of growing inequality and social vulnerability on distrust. It does this through a rights and capability perspective. Our first hypothesis was that retrenchment of the state, in conjunction with rising inequality and income insecurity, may have undermined trust, especially among the poor and the 'precariat'. Our second hypothesis anticipates extensive social damage and explores this through an integrated diagnosis building on the idea of the erosion of/disinvestment in (individual and collective) capabilities and basic social rights in the EU and how experiences of insecurity, poverty and social degradation can be analysed from those perspectives.

A significant level of human rights based analysis of the Irish crisis was prompted by and gathered in the context of Ireland's reporting to the United Nations International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights and Ireland's testimony to the UN ESCR committee in June 2015. The value added of this report is the gap it fills in personal testimony, participation or voice of the people experiencing extreme disadvantage (EAPN Ireland 2014, CAN 2014), virtually no analysis from an individual 'capability perspective' and little focus on resilience strategies (Gray, 2016). This research aims to understand impact of the crisis and particularly how loss of human rights or entitlements relates to loss or gain of individual and collective capabilities. 2014 Eurobarometer research examining how Irish households coped with the economic crisis shows crisis had a tangible financial and material impact along with substantial psychological and emotional impacts, leaving people nervous, anxious, depressed and struggling to sleep. Young people were frustrated and feeling 'stuck' and unable to progress, children were either seen as the most affected group, or parents went to great lengths to try and protect their children from the effects of the crisis. The report found, for most, 'life is much worse since being affected by the crisis', with less financial and emotional stability, less possibility of planning, and less capacity to enjoy leisure. Some associate crisis with positives including having a closer social circle and people they can rely on; changing how they spend and what they value. Qualitative research data collection with in depth personal testimonials that address rights, capabilities and social investment will add value to our collective capacity to understand this impact.

1. Context

Brief sketch of overall impact of the crisis

Following external shocks, the 2008 domestic banking crisis and collapse of the Irish construction and property industries lead to a 12% reduction of GDP and €30 billion in fiscal consolidation over the period 2009-2014. Impact spread across many facets of life in Ireland, with early Budgets (2009-2010) difficult for many but progressive in their overall distributional impact, and later Budgets (2012-2015) difficult but regressive (Keane *et al* 2015:12). Austerity measures have impacted on Irish economic and social rights (ESR) and welfare (Nolan 2014:36). Ireland was the first of the countries affected by the Eurozone crisis to enter recession. It was the second, after Greece, to be subject to an IMF/ECB/EU ‘bailout’ and Troika involvement which oversaw reductions in social protection expenditure, public service employment numbers, public service pensions, expenditure on goods and services, public capital expenditure and a 12% reduction of the minimum wage. Ireland exited the crisis when it exited the bailout programme in December 2013. No formal social impact or human rights impact was carried out on the programme or budgets, but subsequent analysis shows austerity had a detrimental impact on a range of societal groups who are traditionally recognised as being disadvantaged (IHREC 2015). The cumulative effect of the post-crisis budgets has been regressive in terms of enjoyment of economic and social rights (Nolan 2014). Irish SILC data 2008-2014 (CSO 2015) shows increases in poverty across the main measurements (at risk, deprivation, and consistent) from 2008 to 2013. Deprivation rates rose from 13.8% to 24.5% between 2008 and 2011, to 32% in 2013 before decreasing, and peaked at 63% for lone parents (CSO, 2014). NESI (2013) outlines the significant social impact of the crisis: 10% of the population are estimated to experience food poverty; there is growing use of soup kitchen style food distribution and increased homelessness.

Table 1.1 Poverty, deprivation and equality, 2008-2014 Source: CSO EU-SILC (various years)

	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
At risk of poverty rate	14.4	14.1	14.7	16.0	16.5	15.2	16.3
Deprivation rate	13.7	17.1	22.6	24.5	26.9	30.5	29.0
Consistent poverty rate	4.2	5.5	6.3	6.9	7.7	8.2	8.0
Gini coefficient	30.6	29.3	31.4	31.1	31.2	31.3	31.8
Income quintile share ratio	4.5	4.3	4.8	4.9	5.0	4.8	5.0

Source Irish unemployment 2006-2015 Source CSO, Ireland 2015

Despite high levels of emigration unemployment rose from 6.4% in 2008 to nearly 15% in 2012, but dropped to 8.8% by early 2016. Long-term unemployment (over one year) rose from half of those unemployed in 2010 to 60% in 2012 and dropped to mid 50's in 2016; but 60,000 remain unemployed for more than four years. Ireland scores very high for the number of young people not in employment, education or training (Gonzalez Pandiella, 2013). House-

holds with very low work intensity rose from 14.2% to 22.9% in the period 2007 to 2011 (Watson & Maître, 2013), the highest low work intensity household rates in the EU and associated with a doubling of child poverty. Average disposable income fell from €24,380 to €21,440 in 2008-2011 (CSO, 2014), which peaked at 15%. Joblessness remains closely correlated with low education qualifications and is a largely working class experience.

Crisis had significant gendered impacts (Barry and Conroy 2013) with serious cumulative cuts for lone parents, stagnation in labour market participation by women, and an increased gender pay gap. Families with children are particularly hard pressed, especially those in housing mortgage arrears. The universal Child Benefit was reduced from €166 per month in 2010 to €130 pm in 2013 (with additional cuts to the higher payments for the 3rd + child). Social welfare dependent single families with children fared worst of all suffering cumulative annual cuts over the crisis. There were also significant generational patterns to austerity. In early budgets the working age adult social welfare payments were reduced by 8% (from €204 to €188) while social welfare pensions remained protected at €230 for assistance-based pensions while social welfare was more than halved for those under 25 (from €204 to €100). Emigration, unemployment, mortgage arrears and negative equity affect young people and younger households more than older households. There is every likelihood of significant scarring for what has become known as ‘a lost generation’.

The direct impact of recession on mental health saw admissions due to first depressive episodes increase with severe depression associated with economic recession having a higher suicide risk (Thekiso et al., 2013). Health spending has been cut by 27% since 2008, resulting in an 81% increase in the number of patients waiting on trolleys and chairs in emergency departments and reliance on adult wards for children suffering mental-health difficulties and increased waiting lists for youth mental-health services. There is now a €2.50 prescription charge, increased fees to access A&E and new fees including chemotherapy charges. High profile suicides have been linked to recession, job loss, business insolvency and eviction. The National Suicide Research Foundation found an increase in self-harm rates of 31% in men, and 22% in women, between 2008 and 2012. In 2013, 11,061 presented to hospital due to self-harm nationally (199 per 100,000). The male suicide rate is 57% higher over the period amounting to 500 additional deaths, attributed amongst other things to reductions in public expenditure, cuts to welfare, substantial healthcare cuts, falling house prices and personal debt. A Vision for Change, the national policy for mental health services launched in 2006, is unlikely to be implemented (Pillinger 2012) with community mental health services only 75 per cent of what was envisaged in 2006 (IHREC 2015).

The political climate in Ireland has been relatively stable in the context of what has been described as the most significant non-wartime collapse of a western economy. Various factors explain relative stoicism including (post colonial) psycho-cultural factors *In Ireland we have a history of internalising anger, which leads to suicide, drug addiction and alcoholism* (Mc Verry 2013:9). Hearne’s (2015) analysis of Irish ‘crisis’ protests shows less passivity than often assumed and some successful ‘single issue’ roll back in intermittent, often locally based diverse campaigns. Anti water charges mobilisations which drew up to 200,000 on the streets on 11 October 2014 contributing to an effective reversal of charges. Despite this momentum, the political climate is influenced by a traditional consensus orientation of trade union and civil society leadership

towards social dialogue relations with the state. Traditional lobbying and advocacy exists alongside street mobilisation favoured by non-traditional civil society and radical left organisations. Society appears characterised by an absence of social solidarity (Carney *et al.*, 2014),

Economic difficulties correlate with mistrust of national governments (OECD 2014:30) with the largest drops in trust in Greece, Ireland, Portugal, and Slovenia. European Social Survey data on political legitimacy found trust in Irish political institutions and satisfaction with government has declined since 2008 and that, while satisfaction with government is increasing since the 2011 election, trust in government continues to decline. Crucially they find social trust is declining for those who did not vote for the parties in power, this suggests a political marginalisation or exclusion of a significant group and a growing anti politics sentiment. Trust in 2015 is similar to levels at the height of the recession with the 2015 Edelman Trust Barometer scoring Ireland second from bottom for levels of trust in 27 countries. Overall we see core values of equality and human rights intact (IHREC 2015) but not applied to more marginalised groups including Irish Travellers, Roma and asylum seekers, and significant mistrust in politics and society stretching to NGOs and traditional media.

Figure 5. Change in means of latent concepts associated with political legitimacy

Source O Sullivan 2014 P 564

Various ex ante human rights analysis of crisis were generated in the context of the Irish report to the UN Economic, Social and Cultural Rights Committee in June 2015, (IHREC 2015, Nolan 2015, Kerr 2015). There has been less analysis from a social investment or capability perspective however Coping with the Crisis (EC, 2014) highlights various impacts on individual and family capability; loss of income, salary cuts, wages deflation, cost of living, job loss, loss of overtime payment, increases in taxes, etc. and with many relying on state and family support as well as undeclared work or small jobs to not only supplement income but also realise sense of self-worth as a way to feel ‘useful’ to society. Taking on a second job, or partners going out to work, were also common additional coping strategies as was selling or pawning personal or household items, borrowing, using savings and exchanging services or items with friends, family and acquaintances. Debt was associated with negative emotions such as fear and stress, information about choices was crucial and mobility was mixed. To avoid spending too much money people changed how and what they consumed, and spent more time shopping while cutting leisure/recreational activities and medical expenses. Collective capability has diminished through cuts in national and local institutions including the Irish Human Rights Commission and the Equality Authority, National Consultative Committee on Racism

and Interculturalism (NCCRI) and Combat Poverty Agency. Carney et al (2014), Allen (2011), O’Sullivan *et al* (2015), Harvey (2012), Murphy (2012) note, from different perspectives, a decline in the health of civil society, democracy, trust and solidarities across class, gender and generations. Competitive tendering and procurement on social inclusion and community development in Ireland along with cuts, cost savings and efficiencies have eroded collective capabilities (Community Work Ireland, 2015).

Bird’s eye perspective on impact of the crisis: Housing and Homelessness

Irish economic, social and political crises have combined to force more individuals and families into homelessness than ever before. Focus Ireland (2015b) outline two routes into homelessness: - structural/economic reasons: (e.g. insufficient housing, high rent costs, poverty) and/or - social/individual (addiction, mental health issues, relationship breakdown). Recession has caused a significant increase in the number of families becoming homeless primarily due to structural and economic reasons, especially in Dublin. Reduced incomes (CSO 2015; Maitre *et al.* 2014 p. 2), over-indebtedness, (Maitre *et al.* 2014 p. 4-5), increased housing costs and housing shortages (PRTB 2014, Maitre *et al.* 2014) manifest in the worst way in a real denial of human rights and erosion of individual and collective capabilities as people and families experience increased homelessness. A number of crisis impacts and policy responses have particular salience for homelessness.

Figure 1.1 Homeless adults with dependent children 09/15-10/16: Source: Dublin Housing Executive

Housing costs have risen as a percentage of average income. In 2004, 23 per cent of people considered ‘housing costs a heavy burden’ but by 2011, this had risen to almost 35 per cent. This combines with an overall shortage of housing units, discrimination in access to and in particular a shortage of affordable and social housing, increases in private rents and a high level of unsustainable mortgage arrears. The residential building sector has not recovered its pre-crash development capacity putting pressure on rental rates across the country. Many landlords (some in arrears and/or subject to repossession) are withdrawing from the market, or are being repossessed by banks, increasingly occasioning evictions. 20,000 new homes each year are needed in order to keep pace with overall rising demand. Government’s Social Housing Strategy 2020 has a target to deliver 18,000 additional social rented homes by 2017, and a further 17,000 homes by 2020, this target will not meet demand and is unlikely to be met.

Available 2011 Census data on homeless is out of date and we await April 2016 census data but Oct 2016 Focus Ireland analysis of new families entering homelessness in Dublin largely comprised migrants,

lone parents and young parents. 783 individual adults with 1608 dependents lived in hotels largely with no family of cooking facilities and 243 families with 502 dependants lived in homeless accommodation, a total of 1026 families with 2110 dependants in Oct 2016. Overall lone parents families comprised up to 50% of the social housing waiting lists and up to 50% of people families in emergency or homeless accommodation ... Focus Ireland (2015) detail 570 young people (July 2015) accessing emergency homeless services also become trapped in homelessness as they rely on reduced rates of social welfare paid to people under the age of 26. While often capable of moving on from emergency accommodation, inadequate income leaves them unable to locate or sustain tenancies.

Rent Supplement/Allowance is a de facto long-term housing income support that compensates for the lack of social housing. 48,000 of 71,500 Rent Supplement recipients were long-term recipients (DSP 2015) and the numbers of recipients increased 60% since 2009. Despite rent inflation the supplement was frozen in 2013 and its value was also reduced through caps on the maximum rent levels allowed. A number of austerity budgets increased the amount of own contribution a claimant must contribute from their own welfare payment. Unrealistic rent caps also mean individuals sink further into poverty as they dig deeper into their own resources to increase the rent supplement to a level adequate to cover realistic market rents. This leaves families and individuals on low incomes uncompetitive when competing for accommodation with people in work (who also appear less stigmatised to landlords). It also leaves many families simply unable to pay the rent. While policy allows a discretionary review for families at risk of homelessness due to the unaffordability of increased rent, this remains an inadequate short gap and the net effect is many families becoming homeless. Homelessness is also exacerbated by the inability to access rent supplement when one adult in the family is in employment or the likelihood of losing the supplement if an individual finds work - even though the income from employment is clearly insufficient to meet the rent. This well known poverty and unemployment trap is to be alleviated by introduction of an employment neutral Housing Assistance Payment (HAP), even though a Homeless HAP is now available overall roll out of HAP is slow and under-invested.

2. Theoretical and Methodological Approach: Human Rights and Capabilities Framework

RE-InVEST aims at investigating the philosophical, institutional and empirical foundations of an inclusive Europe of solidarity and trust. To this end it draws on capability and human rights based participatory approaches.

Human rights form a common European basis of values and describe core elements of what constitutes well-being and a good life. Human rights are the basic rights and freedoms that belong to everyone. International law, including treaties, contain the provisions which give human rights legal effect. Ideas about human rights have evolved over many centuries and gained strong support after World War II when the United Nations adopted the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights which evolved as universally agreed basic standards that aim to ensure that every person is treated with dignity and respect; they are interdependent and indivisible, meaning that rights are linked and not protecting one right may impact on another, they belong to all people without discrimination. Human Rights include Civil and Political Rights, such as the right to life, the right to a fair trial and the right not to be subjected to torture; and economic, social and cultural rights, such as the right to work, to join a trade union, to housing and health, to education, and to an adequate standard of living. Specific groups are protected in specific treaties such as women, children, people with disabilities, minorities, and migrants. Human rights are transformative. For vulnerable groups the usage of a rights-terminology has changed perspectives, by empowering people, by increasing awareness and creating tools to address compromises of these rights.

Capability approach as developed by Sen (1999) and Nussbaum (2011) defines a person’s well-being in terms of ‘what a person can do’ or ‘the beings and doings (the functionings) a person achieves and her capability to choose among different combinations of such ‘functionings’. Resources and conversion factors are preconditions or necessary for leading a life one values and has reason to value (Figure 2.1). Resources refer to the material conditions of a person: her income, the goods and services she disposes of. Conversion factors help her to convert resources into ‘doing and being well’. There are personal conversion factors such as skills and bodily features, social conversion factors such as social norms and social institutions and environmental conversion factors such as climate and geography. In the end both the achieved functionings as well as the freedom to choose a life one values matters.

Figure 2.1 Resources, conversion factors, capability set and achieved functionings

Methodology - Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach (PAHRCA)

RE-InVEST makes the links between rights and capabilities, with capabilities or resources and conversion factors understood as essential to turn abstract rights into real entitlements, ‘to have the capability to make rights real and live a life one values’. Central to such concepts are agency, participation, and voice and these can be realised at an individual and collective level. This theoretical framework translates into our choice to work, to much as possible, within a transformative and participative methodology paradigm to answer core research questions, conduct our analysis and formulate potential solutions. This qualitative, participatory research is not suitable as a means to "validate" or "prove" hypotheses and we make no such positivist claim. As a qualitative research it is combined with quantitative data to deepen understanding of precisely how austerity impacts on rights and capability. While specific choice of methods will be determined by the specific sub questions or hypotheses of research questions, key principles inform the design and delivery of the method. As a participative research the validity of our methodology lies in the co-construction of knowledge by a mixed group of researchers: academic researchers, NGO’s and people experiencing poverty working through an iterative and ongoing process of action, knowledge creation and reflection. This practical utilisation of a capability approach in research methodology is a core outcome of the project, it is not just instrumental in facilitating a more grounded empirical answer to research questions but permeates our whole project. In the Irish case the NGO or civil society organisations and the representatives of vulnerable groups participating in the process will be associated until the very end of the project, and participation will enhance not only validity but our collective ‘capabilities’ to transform social environments.

Participatory action research views participants as co-researchers who have special knowledge about their own situation. Hence they are not only ‘interviewed’ but take part in research by engaging in, examining, interpreting, and reflecting on their own social world, shaping their sense of identity. Crucial for this kind of knowledge generation is the “merging” or “crossing of knowledge” that comes from three parts: scientific knowledge as gained by researchers; knowledge which the poor and excluded have, from their firsthand experience, of the twin realities of poverty and the surrounding world which imposes it on them; and the knowledge of those who work among and with these victims in places of poverty and social exclusion (Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2 Merging of Knowledge

While flexible PAHRCA entails a process of seven steps (Murphy and Hearne 2016) including commitments to action and outcomes, to ensure PAHRCA engagement is significantly deeper than data extraction.¹ This participatory approach commits to not only document specific problems but to actively work toward change using the empowerment principles associated with PAR². This approach was utilised to engage with specific research questions analysing the social impact of the crisis (and crisis-related policy reform) on vulnerable groups as well as the impact of growing inequality and social vulnerability on distrust. The first hypotheses is that retrenchment of the state, in conjunction with rising inequality and income insecurity, may have undermined trust, especially among the poor and the ‘precariat’. The second hypotheses is that the crisis caused significant social damage and eroded investment in individual/collective capabilities and basic social rights.

In Ireland we proceeded by engaging with Focus Ireland, a registered charity that works to prevent people from becoming, remaining or returning to homelessness, and who work with over 10,000 people in Dublin, Waterford, Kilkenny, Cork, Sligo and Limerick. The NGO has a strong research tradition, a well developed research ethics and a commitment to advocacy. Having established contact in October 2015 we recruited peer researchers to collect and analyse data for the national report and to participate in subsequent RE-InVEST work (2017- 2018). The longer term ‘legacy’ aim is to embed a more participatory culture in Focus Ireland’s approach to internal customer relations and external policy and advocacy work. The four self-selected peer researchers (present and previous customers of Focus Ireland services who had experienced housing exclusion) met with the Maynooth team for six 2 hour sessions to develop peer research skills. We collected our data in one small Irish town and two cities outside Dublin, the input of four Dublin based peer researchers brought this perspective. All participants in the research were invited via contact with a Focus Ireland key worker and all access Focus Ireland housing support services. The personal testimonials are from individuals who have experienced and continue to experience vulnerability in relation to housing, poverty, unemployment and mental health. To maximise participation and voice we visited each research site twice for two hours on each occasion, once to enable reflection and collect initial data, and then two weeks later to develop our analysis and deepen participation. We used a variety of timeline exercises, cartoons, role plays, focus groups and qualitative interviews to gather data. Ethics procedures were fully observed and anonymity guaranteed. All group and individual interviews were recorded, transcribed and analysed using inductive manual coding with the active involvement of the peer researchers. In writing the national report participant voices are central and we avoid potentially exclusive scholarly language. All participants are invited to the May 2016 national launch of the research and to stay engaged with the RE-InVEST project.

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1. Identify and meet partner NGO/gatekeeper, 2. Preliminary ‘meet ups’ (for trust building if necessary), 3. First meeting with participants – trust building, 4. Developmental: implement developmental human rights & capability approach, 5. Inquiry/data gathering, 6. Identifying patterns (key issues and themes of concern to the group) and 7. Undertake action/outcome.
 2. Positive discrimination in the allocation of time and resources, with priority being given to the weakest participants in the process; effective investment in the research capacity & capability of those groups; phasing in of joint collaboration to the highest possible levels; adaptation of analytical instruments and language; interculturality (& gender, age, etc.) sensitive approaches, including mediation and training of all participants; continuity and feedback at all stages of the research; empowering, dialogical and reflexive approaches; communicative democratic decision-making.

Figure 2.3 Peer Researchers training in Maynooth University

Table 2.1 Research Participants in 3 locations AC, BD, CL

	Men	Women	Age-Range	Total
A C	6	1	21-45	7
B D	5	3	35-60	8
C L	5	1	30-60	6
Peer researchers	2	2	29-50	4

3. Findings

Findings are presented in two sections. Two biographical narratives, 1 female and 1 male, were selected from 18 participants. Their experiences portray the multidimensional accounts of the main events in the past 8-10 years and as such illustrate the vertical damage of the crisis in terms of social disinvestment, rights and capability. The subsequent thematic analysis of qualitative data is in four sections, human rights, individual capabilities, collective capabilities and resilience. Within each section findings are grouped under key headings, including social welfare, jobs, housing, and health.

Biographical Narratives

Pat

I wasn't always dependent on losing my payments or whatever. I worked since I was 13. In 2008 I was studying for my Leaving Cert and in 2009 I entered a 3 year degree course and basically I couldn't get a grant so I had to work full-time. It got really tough but I just went on with it and the middle of my third year it got to be too much. I felt like anytime when I looked any support grant wise, money wise, to pay for it, it just denied. When I graduated, I couldn't get a job after my degree so basically I just had to do job bridge internship.

Employment services, that was grand, they all were offering job bridge, jobs plus, work placement, work experience, ... etc. I mean I've graduated; I've done work experience in my course, why do I have to keep doing this. Also, it's not realistic. I couldn't have friends over during the crisis because it was all about money. When I didn't have money anymore, and the whole stress with everything, I didn't see people as often.

There was no accommodation and any accommodation that was available was too expensive. My landlord was receiving benefits and was getting cash off me, so I couldn't sign on to rent allowance, if I did he would have to get rid of me and I would lose a flat. This was the 3rd flat I moved into from the span of 4 months. It was hard. I didn't have enough money for food. I just had to deal with it, just the way it is. Prescription charges affected me. When I was receiving jobseekers, it was another thing to pay for, so I had to scrap and save. I never bought any clothes and I was wearing the same clothes all the time. It was really tight you know. Trying to figure out the cheapest places to go and buy the cheapest things. If I didn't have money for my medication. I went through a stage where I didn't want to take them anymore. I got pissed off with the whole thing and I just ..yah you know..yah.

In 2013 I had a mental breakdown, two actually. I'm at a stage now that I feel like I can move forward. The thing I'm worried about is that I feel like now I do have to depend on Disability Allowance to stay well and at the same time be able to work. I never was dependent but now with things gone ... you are in college and you think there is a job opportunity giving you hope at the end of it ... but there is no hope. What comes after that is addiction, poverty, living in and eventually going homeless. It's horrible. People commit suicide, people overdose.

I felt like I lost my self-confidence, my self-esteem and self-worth. I had to just settle for second best and I kind of feel like I just kind of wanted to escape reality all the time because I couldn't deal with it. It was too much. It reached a crisis stage, it reached a point where I didn't want to be on this planet anymore. That's when the doctors started to help me, but I kind of wish it happened sooner. It kind of doesn't make

sense, why people have to reach a crisis to get offered support and not before they reach that crisis. You have to reach to that level, that frustration, that anger, for people to genuinely help you. A lot of people throw themselves in the river and die, is that the stage you have to be at for them to help you. Over the last few years it has gotten better.

What I noticed more is that lately, because I wanna move on, I try to use my supports a lot better. I go to the patient clinic, I try to use that more, but it seems like nearly every single day I have to go to that now. Or nearly 2 times a day. It is getting a bit scary. But it is working, they work. But like I'm not the only person in recovery, there are others. These people that are supporting us, they won't be able to offer that support to everybody, and losing their benefits. I live alone, I have my own apartment, I am in recovery from severe mental health issues. When I had a few breakdowns I had to take some time off and had to focus on myself. I am doing well now.

I try to kind of stay away from people that are toxic. It's gotten a lot better and that's because I made personal decisions. Relationships with family and neighbours has improved. My trust in the government won't change, it just seems to me like whenever I watch ... they talk more about it then doing anything about it ... if you want to get more social housing, why don't you on a construction site and dig a hole instead of running around with a sheet of paper talking about how great you are. I know it sounds a bit unrealistic but that would give me a bit more hope about what they can do. Even if I participate in this election the result is that we will still end up with somebody corrupt - I think it should be an independent party. Last night I was watching a political show and there was all these politicians and they are all that talking about fantasies. There was this one guy who was independent and he just looked like the rest of us, I was just thinking if that guy is able to talk in a way we could understand.

I'm sober in recovery and sober. I think that helps me feel secure in my life. I am able to manage stress better. If I don't have that, then, it would be like a crisis. I can achieve my goals in time. I want a proper paid job and like proper money and be able to afford a car and a house. You know what I mean, that's the life my parents lived. It wasn't a high life and it was manageable ... most are suffering from some illness, so sick. Like, it's just hard ... (laughs) they should call it the great depression part 2.

Pablo

I'm Pablo, I'm 27. In 2008 I was in drug addiction and I can't remember very much but I was on job seekers allowance and rent allowance. There was no problem with my payment back then, the social welfare people didn't really care about courses and annoying me. It was still a struggle supporting myself with that amount of money. By 2009 I was in my first homeless shelter. I was only considered a statistic in the government's eyes, found it very hard to get help. Services were also harder to get.

In 2010 I found a home with a girlfriend and ended up having twins, because we were going to claim social welfare together they cut our money even more ... so we had lie to them to keep our single payments. Drugs took off then in a big way I suppose the most important for me was my drug addiction.

In 2011 rent allowance was cut. Then took 20 euros off my rent allowance, so I couldn't afford the apartment which led me to the criminal activity to afford the apartment which led me to be in trouble with the Guards, it was only then that they would help me with my addiction, because I was on probation. I came out of my first treatment and I relapsed, I lost my Community Employment (CE) scheme, my rent supplement, my dole got cut to €144. I appealed it 3 times, because even if they gave me €188, it's an extra €40, that I could of paid for my 3 children that I found it financially difficult to support ... me and my ex-partner were on and off at the time but I still had to support them, with maintenance and stuff they needed every week. To be honest it led me to criminal activity to be able to support my children. I was eventually then made homeless, I couldn't afford rent anymore, and I had to live with nuns, and a non-profit, got a place and I couldn't afford it and I ended up homeless.

Since then I have been in and out of institutions, like my girlfriend, for mental health and drug addiction, I didn't take any notice of what was going on with the government but I knew I was getting screwed.

I was hitting a brick wall. I also had to find money to pay for the treatment centre, because the government wouldn't pay for it. Because I wasn't in trouble and on probation this time around, they wouldn't pay for it and like do they want me to go smash I window to be able to get help. If I have to pay for treatment centre all in one go, I have to pay 16 grand. I'm a drug addict how am I going to find that kind of money. In 2014 I went to a charity organisation to be able to pay for the treatment, a 3 month residential one.

I've been with Focus Ireland from about 2 months before the treatment centre. I'm on the youth housing project with Focus until September and they have really helped me. No one else was listening to me. That's basically it. I'm 22 months clean and I haven't looked back since. I still find it hard today to manage it but the only thing that was able to take me out of the hole was Focus, they gave me an apartment that I was able to bring my kids to, and rent isn't astronomical, it's in the middle of town, it's from a non profit organisation and instead of ripping out a whole house and building it from scratch, you can still move into the house. I am really grateful for the apartment that Focus gave me but it's a 2 bedroom with the second room a box, so I can't fit there with three children. The government just brushed me off and I'm still pissed at them. Whereas here I have a name.

2016 I'm on Community Employment now, I didn't want to go back and sign on, I wanted to keep going. The only reason why I'm getting the extra time is because of addiction issues, and going to treatment. For a normal person, they only get a year or maybe two, but because I am a recovering drug addict, I get 3-4 or maybe 5. Why can't a normal person get it, so they can stay on it for 4 years and feel secure, you know what I mean.

It is very good for me, I have 3 kids that I mind full time and it gives me a break from them for 4 hours a day while they are in school. When I finish I go collect them from school whereas, if I had to go back and sign on, I would left with 4 hours a day because I couldn't seek full-time employment. Back to the dole then, or I would have to get full-time employment. Forcing someone to do something they don't like, and wasting that year. If you took your time and make me decide what I want to do. I still don't know what I want to do, but I'm on that road to knowing, you know. When they push you into something, you become more stressed, and for me then I may relapse and that would be more trouble for the dole whereas if you just left me on the CE scheme and a little bit of patience I would be grand. It should be that you want to stay, no problem, until you get your feet on the ground.

I would like to get a house that I can call my own. I know I can go out to work, but at the time I didn't have the capability to nor did I have the skills. I applied for numerous jobs but they say I don't have the experience. You are stuck between a rock and a hard place. I'm going to college in September, Focus Ireland has helped me to do, it costs €950 euro's, the government won't help, Focus Ireland said they would help me with the money and my CE scheme employer said he may be able to help me as well. I'm going to college, no matter what to do 'youth and community work'. My counsellor that I've been in contact since I was 13 she is going to help me as well. When I get my qualification I can go work. I have long term goals, and I'm going to make it happen.

Analysis

Impact on Human Rights

Participants identified a number of areas where they felt their rights were being eroded. These included an inadequate standard of living with decreased social welfare supports, access to proper health services especially in mental health services, access to secure and fair work, education and adequate housing.

Social Welfare UNHD Article 3: Everyone has the right to life, liberty and security of person.

Many participants felt social welfare cutbacks had impacted their own daily lives and others in their communities. Participants could not maintain an adequate standard of living and struggled with trying to pay for

food, clothing and housing. For participants under 25 years of age the social welfare cutbacks significantly impacted. Michael, Jimmy, Fiona and Pat noticed that with the cuts and growing costs of goods and increasing taxes, they had to prioritize which daily essentials to pay for and how they would be able to scrap and save.

'Signing on hit me like a ton of bricks, and there was a queue a mile long waiting to sign on. It was catastrophic, it was really a wakeup. (John)'

'There are other younger people that are living on their own now, and maybe their dole should be more because they have their own responsibilities. Like I get 144 and the heating allowance, I just about make it. (Matteusz)'

Fear of loss of their payment was a concern amongst participants who were feared also they might be switched from disability allowance over to other schemes which may not offer the same support, or not be able to access the appropriate payment.

'Last year they took a lot of people off disability allowance, just like that and it was very hard for all those people. What I would fear for myself is that they can do that again. They can leave people out in larks and I would be like crap, what can I do now. (Pat)'

'You get afraid to lose rent allowance if you get a job then you can't afford a place and go homeless. (Paul)'

Health Article 25: *Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and of his family, ...*

Prescription charge increases left participants unable to afford their medications and having to discontinue medication, managing left them in embarrassing situations. Others spoke out about hospital wait times and the need for improvements in health services.

'The prescription charges, it's scandalous what they are charging now. I was supposed to be taking medication for epilepsy and now I don't bother taking it. (Paul)'

'Prescription costs would be up to 7.50 euro and I would only have a fiver. And she would smile and say, okay maybe the next day and I would just leave. I would be standing waiting in the queue then my face would be red of embarrassment because I don't even have enough for my medication. (Anne-Marie)'

Service standards and quality in mental health care need improvement, health practitioners focus more on the use of medication and the "quick fix" approach in mental health service delivery.

'You would go see a psychiatrist and they would just say oh take that pill for a while. You would be lucky to get 10 minutes with them. You would see a different psychiatrist every time, there was no consistency. I just felt like a zombie. (Johnny)'

'Like day centres, no they didn't really offer help. They would just ask what I was doing during the week and that was that. It was a standard check-in and checkout I would spend, like 5-10 minutes, that would happen every 3 months (John).'

'They just tell you to take a tablet but won't even look at you.'

Employment: *Article 25: Everyone has the right to work, to free choice of employment, to just and favourable conditions of work and to protection against unemployment.*

Many participants lost their jobs, and experience a lack of job opportunities and training, others feel forced into inappropriate courses. Job precarity was a concern for participants who found many jobs on the market that were low pay, part-time work on a temporary contractual basis with reduced social security. For others, on disability allowance or lone parents, meaningful part-time employment was hard to find.

'I thought I would leave school and just start working. But then after 3 months I lost my job (Matteusz)'

'Every place was closing down. People were out of work. There was fucking doom everywhere. Everyone had their own problems. They didn't talk (Shawn).'

'I would win a lottery if I'm offered a contract, if it's after 6 months, then what do you do then, you go back on jobseekers, there is a cycle again of deterioration, mental break down, then drink because of how you are feeling. (Pat)'

Participants experienced multiple barriers to accessing decent employment, including transport, childcare, eligibility criteria, information and discrimination. Adult education and training through employment centres was perceived to not always lead to employment opportunities.

'You need the money for clothing for your child to go to school. What am I gonna do in September for the crèche, for 5 days it's 35 euro, how is a single parent going to afford that, I can't afford that. (Ann-Marie)'

'A lot of people are unemployed, factories closing down, you know. Not being able to afford transport to other cities. Say they wouldn't have a car and if you have children, you may have to bring them to school or something. It's just bloody unfair, it really is (Fiona).'

'They put me forward to do gardening at schools and all that. But they said because I have a criminal record, that I can't be around schools so I can't do it. What really pisses me off is that I haven't been in any trouble for the last 4 years so how long will this go on for. (Matteusz)'

Education: Article 26: Everyone has the right to education.

Nicola, James and Pat spoke about the lack of funding in education in terms of teacher and school resources and the availability of grants for students. Others felt education was not relevant or aligned with the needs of the current job markets. A number of participants who experienced homelessness continued on with school and other activities in an effort to stay productive

'I have all the qualifications on paper and it feels like toilet paper because you can't get work with it. (Jimmy)'

'I was in college while I was living in the homeless shelter. People were like to me, like you gotta get out of there, but it was grand. But umm yah it was weird like that. (Jimmy)'

Housing: Article 25: Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and his family, including food, clothing, housing, ...

Participants found it difficult to pay rent and mortgage payments for their homes and a scarcity of homes in their budget available to them. John for example experienced landlords not accepting tenants, who were on rent allowance, others lied to maintain rent allowance.

'Houses around are really hard to get, it's really tight ... The injustices like houses being reposessed and that type of thing and poor families having nowhere to go and being back at their parents, that makes me depressed. (Fiona)'

'First you ask if you accept rent allowance, they say no and that's the end of story, you know what I mean. (John)'

'I'll be telling lies now from the people I rent off, you are allowed a maximum of 375 euro a month and mine is 425, so I have to be telling lies, everyone does it. It's quite stressful. (Fiona)'

Impact on Individual Capabilities

Participants found it more difficult to cope with their everyday circumstances, experienced deteriorating mental health with some having contemplated suicide and others experiencing drug or alcohol addictions. Relations with immediate family were strained with a number of participants experiencing relationship breakups and losing contact with their children. All the participants experienced homelessness with some participants

experiencing long-term unemployment and dependency on NGO supports. Participants did demonstrate adaptive resilience and some felt able to progress in their lives, however options narrowed and dreams and wishes were reduced to short-term goals; finding security in their lives - securing long-term part-time employment, finding stable housing living within their means and keeping on with staying active within their communities.

Mental Health and Suicide

For most participants, the economic crisis affected how they felt about themselves. All reported increased feelings of stress, anxiety and the deterioration of their mental health. For a number of participants reported how crisis triggered increased thoughts of suicide.

'The crisis knocked me. It knocked my confidence. My mental health was impacted a lot. Ideas of suicide. A lot of years in my life mentally and physically and the recession did impact it. (Johnny)'

'The crisis it made me worse, it made me suicidal. I didn't want to live anymore. I found myself homeless. I couldn't understand how this happened to me. I didn't see it coming...it came. (Shawn)'

Housing

Participants experienced homelessness, many experienced feelings of helplessness and felt they wouldn't be able to manage finding a place to live without the support of a local NGO. Others in hostels found that participating in activities kept them feeling productive, and some struggled to stay in education and training while homeless.

'I would of experienced homelessness if left to my own devices. If you can't get a job, you are really struggling to negotiate with landlords. (John)'

'I was in the women's hostel. We would have activities like jewellery making and baking, not every single day but most days and that was very productive. It gives you that kind of feel good factor. When you are down and destitute, with absolutely nothing going for you, it gives your self-respect back a little bit (Fiona).'

Addiction

Many participants discussed their struggles with various forms of addiction. With job loss and homelessness addiction became an increasing challenge and a means of coping with unemployment. Some found it difficult to access help to recover from their addictions, others managed to draw on inner resources to find help in getting treatment and recover.

'When you are used to be working and all that, then you don't you feel like you have nothing to do, you just sit around all day. I started to drink more heavier to forget about all this. (Tom)'

'Some people are in addiction and they don't know how to get out of there, they want the help but they don't know who to turn to because the government doesn't tell people that there are places or treatment that you could get into. (Pat)'

Losing Family and Friendships

Many participants discussed how relationships with family came under pressure at the peak of the crisis, money and addiction being a frequently cause of conflict. Some relationships ended in divorce, and contact with children was lost. Bandit left America because he had no health insurance, his marriage was wrecked, he left behind relationships and things broke down, but he had family networks in Ireland that were important. Others felt isolated from their immediate families due to their struggles with mental health issues which they could not openly discuss.

'I kept drinking. I could see no way out. My marriage was finished. I couldn't let you know so I drank more and more.'

'Post crisis, I haven't seen my children face to face in about a year and a half (Paul).'

Emigration

Emigration was seen as a possible way of dealing with the crisis but none of the participants decided to emigrate and one had returned from living abroad.

Looking back now for me, moving back to Ireland something I regret doing. I had a better life, better social life over there. I was working all the time as well. Think if I would have known that things were so bad, I don't think I would of come back. (Tom)

I didn't want to be here, I wanted to emigrate for a better life. New beginning, new place of origin. (Johnny)

Leisure/Activities

Most participants reported adjusting their spending on leisure and social activities in response to the financial crisis. However, many participants adapted and found new activities and forms of leisure and entertainment through accessing support services such as NGO that were free for them to join.

Oh yah where I am living there are blokes where we play 45 on a Thursday, we play poker on a Friday. Every morning there are fresh coffee scones. (Paul)

For fun ... I walk the dog, I have a Yorkshire terrier, I adopted him, he's a great little fellow. I would love to go to the cinema every once in a while, but with the kids coming every week, I just can't afford it. (Fiona)

Impact on Collective Capabilities

Participants perceived there to be a number of changes within their communities, with increased rates of alcohol, drug and gambling addictions along with suicide incidents. Participants described increased hostility within their communities with growing rates of crime and violence which contributed to a climate of fear and discrimination against migrant/refugee communities. Participants perceived stigma and growing class discrimination towards the homeless or individuals with mental health illnesses. Many participants felt disenfranchised from politics but contemplated voting in elections. All participants found their comfort, structure and stability with NGO's and felt able to progress with such support services. Many joined various courses and activities delivered by non-profit organisations and most found new social networks within these organisations.

Community

Participants felt that their communities were undergoing many changes during the economic crisis including spikes in the occurrences in alcohol and drug abuse and gambling addictions, and less social activity as a result of the crisis. Others noted the frequent cases of suicide in their town and the stigma attached to the issue.

I don't know if they are related but I do feel like crisis has spiked alcohol abuse. From 2011 onwards, there have been betting shops in every small village. We see lots of gambling addictions. We never expected heroin to come to our town, and that is prevalent. (Peter)

You will see people spending much more time at home and see people walking, literally walking around the streets aimlessly with nothing to do and nowhere to go. I work in a hotel and I would see local people coming for meals during the week and then they would reduce it to once a week, to every two weeks to once a month. Even pubs for that matter, drinking and all of that a lot of it stopped. (Michael)

Safety/Crime

Many noted a growing prevalence of crime and violence during the economic crisis recounting their own experiences as victims of the violence and experiences of fear and worry. Bandit recounted his own experiences of fear of violence in his neighbourhood and how he felt 'in the sense of being mad at people's

behaviour’, when ‘they stay up until the middle of the morning talking and I can’t get a house’ He felt ‘I could get attacked myself, they could come inside the door’.

‘I think more theft is due to poverty; people are stealing because they need things. They are willing to take a day in prison for a small theft. (Peter)’

‘It was just bad you know the crime and violence, one day there was a proper altercation outside my home with shouting and screaming and it made me pretty nervous. I stayed in the home for about 2 or 3 days. I didn’t know if the garda came, I was too scared to look outside the window. (John)’

Politics

There were various levels of political participation amongst the participants across all three research sites. While most lost faith in the government, some participants distanced themselves from political activities while others got more politically involved in their communities by joining marches or political organisations.

‘I didn’t vote, I just don’t give a shit about that stuff. (Kitkat)’

‘I went to a water protest. We met up and started burning water bills and talked about how we aren’t paying it. We used skits and things like that. People were angry but it was effective and it got people’s attention. (Pat)’

‘I remember doing a course the national learning network and the government were trying to cut the benefit. All the national learning network centres wrote a letter to the government and they said okay we won’t take it away right now. (Jimmy)’

Changes in Attitudes

Some saw the economic downturn leading to a rise in negative sentiments towards migrants and refugees and perceptions migrant workers were taking over the jobs of Irish nationals. Others voiced anger at elites while others focused on the issue of class discrimination. Many participants experienced a loss in trust in various state institutions during the economic crisis.

‘I was very pissed off because the money was gone and everyone was getting unemployed...everyone..as regards to Europeans, and I have a thing here on my arm, “Guaranteed Irish”, I put that on in 2009 because I thought it was migrants that caused the crash. But it wasn’t, it was bankers that caused the crash. I am a lot better today than before and I don’t feel as ... what the word I’d be looking for..biased as I once was because when people came over here there was plenty of work and it wasn’t the Europeans fault that it went down. (Paul)’

‘I mean there is more work to be done on equal opportunities, to be politically correct about it. It’s the old school regime, if you are born into money you stay with the money, but if you aren’t born into you...well too bad. (John)’

‘All these governments and all these voting and all these politics, and stuff like that it’s for the rich. we have not seen any of it, you know what I mean. (Jimmy)’

Family/Friendships

Despite the various obstacles and hardships that the participants faced during the economic crisis, most participants learned to draw support from friends, extended family and neighbours, which they saw as foundational to being able to cope with what they were going through. Friends helped some navigate the social services needed, others had ended friendships that would impede drug recovery process

‘I have good relationships with friends, in that aspect, I have good support there. I have a lot of good people in my life and that means a lot to me. There is help out there and I will make use of the services available to me. (Johnny)’

‘Where I grew up and the people around me we would just be seen as a burden. You just have to drop those people to move on. I just don’t want to relapse and a lot of them are using. (Kitkat)’

NGOs

Participants valued services and supports from NGOs compared to state services for homelessness, albeit they saw how austerity measures challenged civil society organisation and the communities they serve. Despite the various cuts that NGOs were undergoing, participants believed that the support they were getting from such organisations were necessary in their lives, and felt NGO support meant they were able to move on and progress in their lives. Some felt like they owed their lives to NGOs.

From 2006-2011 I was working in community development projects. I struggled all the time with funding and staying employed. People felt really robbed by cuts, their voice was very squashed out. The community cuts were just horrible. (Peter)

The traveller agency groups are now gone. You get angry, I get angry from that point of view when you see the cuts in teacher supports. You want travellers to do well, and when is that going to happen. (Peter)

They give me a lot of tenancy support. They would be a voice for us tenants, because who would listen to us tenants really. They would just tell you to get out and that's the way it is (Michael)

If it weren't for Focus, I would be dead, you know, I would be dead. (Shane)

Resilience

We can distinguish between adaptive resilience (individual coping) and transformative resilience (changing society). Participants had in common an experience of or threat of homelessness often accompanied by nervous breakdown, addiction, family breakdown or suicide attempts. All survived and drew on their inner resources to tap into collective capabilities to recover and access housing. Their resilience was evident in many ways.

Leisure

Spending time on activities provided participants with feelings of comfort and sense of purpose. Jimmy became musically inspired during his time at a homeless shelter and how he has continued this passion by getting involved in a homeless choir.

People always ask me where does my music come from, and I will never forget till the day I die, I was sitting inside the room and I was listening to one of the dance beats and I just started writing lyrics. At the moment I'm involved in choir ... even if you are homeless, and there is no work, there's still activities, happy things to do out there, you just have to get yourself involved. (Jimmy)

Courses I'm doing at the moment and boat building. We actually built a boat. (Tom)

In Youthreach we would play soccer against other youth reaches, or mountain biking, so the proper activities were very good for your mental health. (Mateusz)

Autonomy/Dreams

Some had felt dependent and reliant on the organisations that supported them through their hardships while others spoke about their career goals and ways of gaining more independence and had clear hopes and dreams.

Today? I feel independent when I'm with Focus Ireland. I do my best to do my best to do things on my own, but I rely on the help of Focus. (Shane)

I would love to open up more small businesses that would give me more independence, Ireland for me is a good country because there is a sense of freedom. Freedom of movement, freedom of speech, freedom of participation and that's what I appreciate. (Michael)

I think this is the life I wanted to live, no matter how bad my head was I was always trying to do my best. I am good as can be. (John)'

Stability and Progressing in Life

While many described frequent feelings of insecurity and instability throughout the crisis, but having gone through the crisis, many participants spoke about finding stability in their lives and new feelings of structure and comfort from where they could focus on immediate goals; health, education, career as a starting point.

Hopefully have some green and buy a house and finish a course I did in the past and follow up on that and be like happily ever after, but to keep doing music, (Jimmy)'

For me my five year plan is to go back to college, and hopefully in 5 years hopefully I can get a permanent home. (Pablo)'

Like every morning I'm waking up and thinking what am I gunno do. We were in the middle of it and we are in the end of it now. (Jimmy)'

I am stable now, I sort of have a routine for each day. I have structure in my life now. (Paul)'

My health is better I suppose. The addiction is gone, I have a home, and I am trying to transfer now so fingers crossed so hopefully I'll get a house sometime. (Anne-Marie)'

Conclusion: The Social Damage of the Crisis

This report analyses the social impact of the crisis (and crisis-related policy reform) on vulnerable groups as well as the impact of growing inequality and social vulnerability on distrust. It does this through a rights and capability perspective.

The first hypothesis was that retrenchment of the state, in conjunction with rising inequality and income insecurity, may have undermined trust, especially among the poor and the 'precariat'. Our analysis confirms the findings of O'Sullivan et al (2014), the Eurobarometer (2015) and the Edelman Trust (2015) all of which found a loss of trust in national government and other key institutions. Participants experienced this loss of trust at a general level but also quite personally in a diminished trust that the state would guarantee access to social rights it was previously trusted to deliver. Attitudes to political parties and politicians were often negative however participants still voted and some participated in other political actions including protests. Social tensions were evident with negative comments about local anti-social behaviour however there was also evidence of solidarity with others experiencing cuts (young people, Travellers, lone parents). Anti-migrant sentiment was evident but so was evidence of nuanced views on migration with greater resentment for banker and elites. We find high levels of trust in NGO's and an optimistic eagerness to contribute to society.

We confirm the second key hypothesis, an integrated diagnosis building on the idea of the erosion of/disinvestment in (individual and collective) capabilities and basic social rights in the EU. The crisis and both EU and national government policy responses to the crisis has had direct impact on human rights. Basic economic, social and cultural rights in particular are more difficult to realise with real consequences for access to social protection and adequacy of income support, on access to jobs and quality of jobs, on access to and the cost of appropriate quality health services, and on access to social housing. The diminished access to rights has real consequences for people's individual capability and capacity to progress, make plans and make choices. This manifests in different ways but three consequences were frequently discussed: early intervention, access to services and the role of NGO's in generating collective and individual capability.

Early intervention

Biographic narratives highlight how personal crisis is triggered or deepened by the absence of early intervention. Across a wide range of services, including social work, mental health, child services, labour market,

education, addiction, health participants described how earlier intervention would have mitigated crisis. Services were unavailable when first needed, often on accessible when a crisis is full blown with often devastating consequences to health, family life and a persons belief in their own capability. Focus Ireland report 'Come back when you are Homeless' (2015b) also stresses the core need to prevent homelessness. The EU Social Investment Package (SIP) highlights the degree to which investment in early intervention and prevention is cost effective generating subsequent savings in public expenditure as well as gains in personal and community well being³.

Integrated and personalised service delivery

Participants related how statutory delivery of key services presented obstacles to realising rights and entitlements and offered little to enable personal capability. Statutory cost saving initiatives have removed front line personnel replacing them with automated information services and web based access points, presenting new obstacles and barriers to have individual needs heard, assessed and met. Trust in state services appears low. Insecurity about entitlement impacted on personal capabilities though less risk taking or though pressure to take up inappropriate offers of labour market programmes. These findings have relevance for design of social policy and the Social Investment Package. On the one hand SIP stresses streamlining and integration of benefit administration, these means more than One Stop Shops ⁴. However appropriate delivery requires integration at a high level in policy design. This can generate cost effective social outcomes.

NGOs, individual and collective capability

We can distinguish an empowering organisation which enables and supports the empowerment of the individuals in the organisations through building personal capability or individual conversion factors of members, clients, employees form an empowered organisation is an organisation that succeeds in achieving its goals (e.g. better living conditions for their target group) amidst other organisations and policy makers at the local and above-local level; collective conversion factors.

These 'enabling niches' as described in the empowerment literature in community psychology are pivotal in enabling capacity to realise and maintain access to key services including housing, mental health interventions, education and employment services. Key workers and anchor points seem crucial in enabling individual functioning. The NGO method of delivery with a focus on empowerment and gradual independence was seen as crucial in building personal capacity and capability. Some identified how increased pressure on NGO's to meet new needs associated with crisis meant more competition for the (diminished) resources of NGO's and that this added to their own personal crisis. The Irish crisis has been associated with a significant and disproportionate decrease in funding of NGO's particularly those working with vulnerable groups including people with disabilities, Travellers, women's refugees and migrants groups (Harvey, 2014).

Collective capability is also realised through interaction with NGO's (including Focus Ireland). We find evidence that the erosion of collective capabilities is reflected in the fragmentation and weakening of public services alongside less support for and more pressures on civil society organisations. Transformative resilience also featured in personal life stories, people grew collective capabilities, and participated in protest activity, arts, music, culture and social activity and consciously sought to restore and grow their own capability and in turn seek opportunities to add to collective capability.

3 In The Netherlands € 1 saved €2.20 in public expenditure and 2006 Social Housing evictions reduced to 70% of the 2005 level. Scottish 2010 data shows temporary accommodation costs of £5300 per household per year could be avoided through successful eviction mediation costing £600. In Austria eviction prevention cost €370 per person compared to reintegration costs of €5520 per person. SIP (2013).

4 One Stop Shops are a way of delivering social policy in an integrated fashiopn so the end user of the public services only has to engage with a limited points of service provision, for example an unemployed person can access income support, education and training and employment services from one point. SIP (2013).

Lessons for Policy and Practice

The findings reinforce the need for guaranteed rights and for social investment and a strong social state but for careful consideration of how rights are delivered and accessed. The EC Social Investment Package (2013) can be (re)designed to ensure social policies and their modes of delivery practically safeguard/strengthen individual and collective capabilities. Despite emerging recovery, Irish headline indicators (emigration, deprivation, very long term unemployment) remain high and there has been an intensification of the neoliberal model of privatised welfare. Social disinvestment, the significant decline in social investment or active disinvestment in various sectors is manifesting in significant pressure on resources.

In 2014 total investment was 17% of GDP in Ireland, the fourth lowest in the EU, government investment is less than 2% of GDP. Ireland is one of the most youthful nations in the EU-28, there is clear need to invest in the future. Absence of investment translates into severe pressure on key infrastructure including not only social housing, but broadband, transport, childcare, health and community services, and all aspects of education; this impacts significantly on individual and collective capabilities to improve participation and quality of life and translate human rights into entitlements. Below we briefly address policy recommendations in housing, health, employment and social protection.

Housing

The most immediate way to mitigate housing pressure and enable access to affordable social housing is to increase the state housing benefits 'Rent Allowance' and Housing Assistance Payment as well as to increase the stock of social housing for low income families through direct build, better allocation of voided houses, better maintenance supports, utilising ghost estates, using NAMA property, and encouraging downsizing choices for older people. Participants supported less commercial developments and more social housing as well as more homeless support special initiatives.

Health

Participants prioritised lowering prescription charges and thresholds and investment in talk led mental health services. They stressed reducing wait times, with more time for doctors with their patients to ensure full recovery, prevention of over medication and more suicide prevention programs. Policy should ensure free health care for lower income groups, waiting lists for hospitals need better management to address the trolley problem and eliminate overcrowding. Reapplication for the medical card needs to be made easier.

Jobs, training and labour market

Better career guidance information centres in schools, more apprenticeships and training centres to provide adequate training could enable transition from education into jobs. Labour market programmes should be voluntary with more options and choices and flexibility about the length to which people can be retained on programmes like Community Employment. Work experience programmes should have higher allowances, adequate monitoring and more protection for worker rights. Transition supports from welfare to work need to be enhanced, for example by reintroducing a 3 year back to work allowance. Disability allowance could be used more creatively to fund suitable quality part-time jobs, and social welfare could be used more to create quality jobs with decent contracts, and to enable support for voluntary job sharing.

Social Welfare

Capability and risk taking is enhanced by income security and by addressing concerns and anxieties about the potential loss of payments in the context of disability allowance reviews and more general sanctions in job seekers payments. There is a need to redress cuts for younger people and to restore the full rate for under 25's and other cuts (fuel allowance, Christmas bonus, phone allowance). The need to restore lone parent allowance and extend childcare was also highlighted. More generally there were appeals to assess the individual needs of people and to enhance service delivery with less forms and more accessibility.

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Social disinvestment and vulnerable groups in Europe in the aftermath of the financial crisis

The case of people with health problems in Italy

Alberto Rovere

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 649447

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This report constitutes deliverable D3.1 for Work Package 3 of the RE-InVEST project.

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Executive summary

This report is prepared in the framework of the Europe H2020 project ‘Rebuilding an inclusive, value based Europe of solidarity and trust through social investments’ (RE-InVEST). The project aims to evaluate the social investment strategy of the European Commission implemented in 2013 in response to the social damage of the financial crisis in 2008. The RE-InVEST consortium assesses the social damage of the crisis from human rights and capability based approaches with an eye to those vulnerable groups affected the most by the crisis in the 12 countries (and 13 regions) covered by the consortium. The analyses are carried out by the local partners, who consist of NGOs and/or researchers.

The RE-InVEST consortium has jointly developed the PAHRCA-methodology that combines principles of Participatory Action research with Human Rights and Capability Approaches. This qualitative, participatory research does not generate representative results but rather aims at deepening the understanding of the economic, social, cultural and political impacts of the crisis on the lives of vulnerable people by giving them a voice.

The biographies of C. and M. illustrate the marks of the crisis on individual life courses. They represent the trajectories of two vulnerable women marked by psychological problems. C. has experienced drug problems she’s been trying to overcome with a residential rehabilitation program. M. battles a psychiatric disorder and is currently host of a social housing service. These difficulties are worsened, as the report will show, by a number of difficulties involving the limitation of basic human rights.

While the biographies exemplify the effects of the crisis in the course of time, the overall analysis is based on contributions of all participants and is arranged thematically, following the core elements of Human Rights and Capability Approach.

Our analysis confirms the erosion of social rights. This erosion, partly due to disinvestment, partly due to the neo-liberal ideology, has a tremendous impact on most vulnerable people. Some of their rights are not granted anymore. The access to social protection, jobs, decent housing, health care and food has diminished.

As a consequence of the erosion of social rights the collective capability has diminished. Their capacity to support, their capacity to choose, their resources have been diminished. The erosion of social rights has real consequences for people’s individual capability.

Contents

List of figures	9
1. The Italian context	11
1.1 Socio-demographic profile of poverty in Italy	12
1.2 Which needs? Type of requests	12
1.3 The case of mental health	13
2. Theoretical and methodological approach	17
2.1 Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach	17
2.2 Aims of the research	18
2.3 Participants	18
2.4 Research instruments and methods	19
2.5 Analysis	20
3. Biographies	21
3.1 Chf.42.Tdp	21
3.2 Ma.F52.Psy	22
4. Results	25
4.1 Impact on human rights	25
4.1.1 Employment	25
4.1.2 Food	26
4.1.3 Housing	27
4.1.4 Health care	28
4.2 Impact on individual capabilities	29
4.2.1 Life and physical health	29
4.2.2 Sense, imagination and thought	29
4.2.3 Emotion	29
4.2.4 Play	30
4.2.5 Environmental control	30
4.3 Impact on 'collective capabilities'	30
4.3.1 Education, children and family	30
4.3.2 Local communities, civil society and social climate	31
4.3.3 Trust, social services and institutions.	31
4.4 The other side of the coin? Resilience of individuals, families and local communities	32
5. Conclusions	34

List of figures

Figure 1.1	Crude and age standardized rates of hospitalization for depression, anxiety and stress in Turin 2006-2010	14
Figure 1.2	Crude and age standardized rates of hospitalization for drug abuse in Turin 2006-2010	14
Figure 1.3	Growth rates of health spending (real terms) years 2004-2013 in Italy (dashed line) and mean OCSE (blue line). OECD Health Statistics, 2014	16
Figure 2.1	Resources, conversion factors, capability set and achieved functionings	17
Figure 2.2	Merging of Knowledge	18
Figure 4.1	Photo-voice data A	26
Figure 4.2	Photo-voice data B	26
Figure 4.3	Photo-voice data C	27
Figure 4.4	Photo-voice data D	28
Figure 4.5	Photo-voice data E	28
Figure 4.6	Photo-voice data F	31

1. The Italian context

In 2013, 6 million people living in Italy experienced absolute poverty, 9.9% of the total population, against the 2.4 million, or 4.1% in 2007. These numbers and the steady increase provide a snapshot on poverty in Italian society¹.

At the end of 2012, Caritas publishes a report on poverty and social marginalisation in Italy entitled 'False Partenze (those who start again)', referring to chronic and unknown poverty, but also to possible ways out from these situations of suffering. Unfortunately, after some time from that publication, it is evident that the re-start never happened. The 're-starters' did not find suitable supports to sustain their willingness to try again. And rather than re-departures 'false starts' occurred.²

At the same time, Italy faced other forms of departures: the so called brain drain with the departures of people who moved from the South to the North of the country, departures (probably without return) of foreign migrants who, in increasing number, are leaving Italy to come back to their country of origin, but also departures of businesses and capital to foreign countries in search of more favorable economic conditions.

The question is: how many people will remain at the starting blocks? Will someone arrive to the finish line, but who will take care of the newcomers and the injured?

An institutional response to poverty and social fragility is clearly lacking in Italy. There is an increasingly evident inability of the welfare system to respond to new forms of poverty, new social emergencies resulting from the economic and financial crisis. Not to mention that many of the situations of economic hardship or progressive social exclusion have been caused or at least aggravated by austerity policies and limits to public spending. These measures have resulted in a progressive drying time of public welfare, in various areas: education, healthcare, welfare and social welfare, social security, etc. Poverty in Italy is certainly not a new phenomenon. The economic and financial crisis has worsened situations of weakness which were already present or have created new ones, widely deriving from the massive loss of jobs, which reached very high levels, higher than the European average, and the growth of undeclared work.

Timely and effective means of social protection would have been necessary at this time, aimed at those who have lost their jobs or have seen their ability of fulfilling basic needs dramatically plunging. The social costs of austerity were paid mainly by individuals and families on the edge of overt poverty, excluded from public intervention, or in receipt of inadequate social interventions, more and more limited and restricted. This inefficiency of the system of income support has led to a situation where, in 2012, more than one in three Italian suffered from at least one of the three hardships that characterise the risk index of poverty or social exclusion: one in ten lives in a household with low intensity work (10.3%), one in five is at risk of poverty after social transfers (19.4%) and one in seven suffers severe material deficiencies (14.5%). The strong growth of the latter group is worrying: between 2011 and 2013 the proportion of people claiming they could not afford unexpected expenses increased from 38.6% to 42.5%, the amount of those who report that they cannot adequately heat the dwelling from 18.0% to 21.2%. The upward trend of the economic hardship of the families is confirmed by the data from Censis: in 2013, 24.3% of the families interviewed struggled to pay bills or taxes³.

1 Gori, C. (2014). La povertà in Italia. In AA.VV. Il bilancio della crisi. Le politiche contro la povertà in Italia-Rapporto 2014. (pp.9-19) Caritas.

2 Nanni, W. & De Lauso, F. (2014). False partenze. Rapporto 2014 su povertà ed esclusione sociale in Italia. Caritas.

3 Atella, V., Borgonovi, E., Collicelli, C., Kopinska, J., Lecci, F. & Maietta, F. (2015). Crisi economica, diseguglianze nell'accesso ai servizi sanitari ed effetti sulla salute delle persone in Italia. I Quaderni della Fondazione Farmafactoring, 01-2015.

If until a short time ago the term ‘poverty oscillation’ was defining new situations of poverty and socio-economic hardship mostly short-lived, with a tendency to repeat themselves several times over time, now it seems there are growing complex and potentially chronic situations.

In a long-term perspective, the risk is that situations of temporary financial difficulty, so far faced through measures of economic support and social harm reduction, slip into chronic and progressive social exclusion.

During 2013 both media and social workers were unanimous in defining the economic and financial crisis as harsh and in placing its main consequences on the level of satisfaction of basic needs: housing, work, health, clothing, food.⁴

1.1 Socio-demographic profile of poverty in Italy⁵

A simple look at the basic features of people who, in the last three years, have addressed Caritas Listening and Care Centres on the Italian territory asking for support speaks of an audience not composed entirely of marginalised or seriously homeless individuals: there is a predominant presence of women (52.4%), of people with registered address (78.4%), of parents (70.4% of users with children)⁶.

Some distinctive notes emerge on the whole:

- the overall predominance of foreigners (58.1%), next to a confirmed and growing presence of Italians (41.4%);
- the strong connotation of parenting that features a large number of beneficiaries, not always lived in the traditional ways of ‘family with depending children’(70.4%).
- strong problems linked to employment (61.7%);
- the woman as a vital player in the search path for help (52.4%);
- those who are married or in other states of marital status (50.2%);
- middle class and social groups traditionally outside the social hardship are equally affected by the economic vulnerability;
- fewer users are taken charge of by social services or other social assistance bodies.

The elements referred to confirm the trend of a progressive ‘social normalisation’ of people in need, reported in other publications, and that makes the universe of those ones seeking help less coinciding with the profiles of serious social marginalisation.

1.2 Which needs? Type of requests

At the forefront of requests for support, there is always demand for goods and material services, expressed by a large proportion of users (34.0%). Shortly after there is the large group of people (26.8%), who seeks help of individuals and third parties, both from the church and from secular/institutional settings. In some cases, these requests relate to the need for support from individual professionals; in other cases these are requests that require the activation of multiple agencies and professional skills, in both the public and private sectors. For example, in 2013, in Italy, 10.5% of users of the Listening Centers looked for health related welfare benefits, otherwise payable by the public service (+6 percentage points compared to the previous year).

4 AA.VV. (2014) Il bilancio della crisi. Le politiche contro la povertà in Italia-Rapporto 2014. Caritas.

5 De Lauso, F., & Nanno, W. (2015) Povertà plurali. Rapporto 2015 su povertà ed esclusione sociale in Italia. Caritas.

6 In Italy there are about 3,000 listening centers run by the Catholic Church through Caritas. Most of them are ‘generic’, others are dedicated to specific forms of poverty: migrants, homeless people, families, people with addictions, etc. The listening centers are a nationwide network organised on the territory. Normally each listening center is designed so that the center can respond to the specific situation on the territory where it performs its service, and develop an action plan based on the needs and available resources.

The largest share of clients at the Listening Centres is characterised by ‘insufficient income compared with a normal person’s (or family) needs’. These people are 47.4% of all those who have experienced at least one economic problem. It is the most significant micro-category of poverty, followed at a certain distance by those who report an absolute lack of income or economic revenue (28.5%). The remaining categories of poverty do not record presence of particularly relevant values.

The most common types of material assistance requested by clients is food: almost half of the people who have received material aid from Caritas (47.1%) were recipients of food aid, in the form of food packets or other kinds or more less innovative aid.

There is then a quarter of the total (25.7%) who received clothing and 12.5% who accessed one or more meals in a social welfare canteen.

Also homelessness has been growing: people, who declare that they haven’t a stable home and rely on friends, sleep in makeshift shelters, in the car or along the streets, are increasing. However those who have a lodging also face difficulties: most Caritas clients live in rented accommodation, both in private houses and, increasingly, in public housing. However, being owners of a place to live does not completely eliminate the risk of poverty: without an adequate income also home ownership can become an excessive weight to bear.

In terms of the implications for the social and relational fabric, the depletion is undoubtedly a factor of stress for the family and its members: it is rather easy to identify in poor families an higher level of conflict and relationship distress than in the overall population.

Some authors, on the contrary, indicate an improvement in the level of social relations: according to this last type of interpretation, a situation of economic difficulty does not always influence negatively the quality and the level of social relations of a family⁷.

What in any case emerges from the various analysis is the dynamic character of the system of relations, which can undergo transformations, both negatively and positively. On the one hand, with the progress of economic impoverishment, some social relations are lost, people have to give up some personal expenses or ‘social’, friends move away, causing greater isolation, etc. On the other hand a strengthening of the spirit of the body of the family, a rapprochement with some people and also a growing readiness to help the community (parish, neighbourhood, ...) can be detected.

1.3 The case of mental health

The above considerations are even more amplified within particular social categories, characterised by further specific fragility, in particular people in need for specialised healthcare such as psychiatric or psycho-social support.

There is a substantial body of research exploring how changing economic conditions affect health. In a review, Catalano et al. (2011)⁸ identified associations between health outcomes and changes in the economy. Some of the strongest evidence relates to increases in the frequency and severity of mental and behavioural disorders associated with job loss or financial difficulties, including suicide and substance abuse (Wahlbeck and McDaid 2012)⁹.

In the current crisis, mental health has been most sensitive to economic changes. There has been a notable increase in suicides in some EU countries and some evidence of an increase in the prevalence of mental disorders (Karanikolos, Reeves, Stuckler and McKee, 2015)¹⁰. Similar conclusions were found

7 Nanni, W. & De Lauso, F. (2014). False partenze. Rapporto 2014 su povertà ed esclusione sociale in Italia. Caritas.

8 Catalano, R., Goldman-Mellor, S., Saxton, K. et al. (2011) The health effects of economic decline, *Annual Review of Public Health*, 32: 431–50.

9 Wahlbeck, K. and McDaid, D. (2012) Actions to alleviate the mental health impact of the economic crisis, *World Psychiatry*, 11: 139–45

10 Karanikolos, Reeves, Stuckler and McKee. (2015). The health effects of the crisis. In Thomson, S. et Al. (2015). *Economic Crisis, Health Systems and Health in Europe. Impact and implications for policy*. WHO Regional Office for Europe. pp. 139-158. Open University Press

analyzing both general (EU) and locally-situated data (IT), referring to our geographical context (see figures at following page).

Figure 1.1 Crude and age standardized rates of hospitalization for depression, anxiety and stress in Turin 2006-2010¹¹

Figure 1.2 Crude and age standardized rates of hospitalization for drug abuse in Turin 2006-2010¹¹

What seems to emerge to date, therefore, are the effects of the economic crisis on health, especially in the short term and especially in terms of mental health. In fact, the evidence shows an increase in cases of depression and anxiety (as in some more severe cases that can result in suicides) and an increase in diseases related to stress and drug use (Costa, Marra & Salmaso, 2012)¹¹.

While the evidence generally suggests that unemployment and financial insecurity increase the risk of mental health problems, there is a lack of consistent evidence of their effects on other health outcomes. Changes in behavioural risk factors show mixed patterns, but there is evidence of increased problems among people who are already vulnerable. Vulnerable people may be more negatively affected than the population in general and these people tend to be hidden in aggregate data (Karanikolos, Reeves, Stuckler and McKee, 2015)¹².

The largest effects on health have been concentrated among those experiencing job loss and among some of the most vulnerable and least visible groups in society, including migrants, homeless people and drug users – people who are the most difficult for researchers to reach (*ibid.*).

The interaction between clinical phenomena with socio-economic ones is thus producing effects that can be dangerous to people's health. According to the WHO, such situations should lead governments to strengthen social safety nets to mitigate the negative effects on health¹³. Since the crisis began, health professionals have highlighted the human and economic costs of inadequate support for people with mental health problems (Cooper 2011; Knapp 2012; Ng et al. 2013)¹⁴. They have called for stronger social safety nets and active labour market programs; action to restrict access to the means of self-harm for vulnerable individuals; an expansion of family support programs; the provision of education, information and support programs targeting vulnerable groups; the development of community-based services; and ensuring universal access to health services.

However, on the contrary, in recent years, in many European countries (included Italy, as shown in Figure 1.3.), austerity policies have intervened substantially on social spending (Dowell-Jones, 2015, Reeves, McKee, Basu, & Stuckler, 2014):¹⁵

11 Costa, G., Marra, M., Salmaso, S. (2012). Health indicators in the time of crisis in Italy. *Epidemiol Prev* 2012; 36(6):337-366

12 Karanikolos, Reeves, Stuckler and McKee. (2015). The health effects of the crisis. In Thomson, S. et Al. (2015). *Economic Crisis, Health Systems and Health in Europe. Impact and implications for policy*. WHO Regional Office for Europe. pp. 139-158. Open University Press

13 Thomson, S., Figueras, J., Evetovits, T., Jowett, M., Mladovsky, P., Cylus, J., Karanikolos, M. and Kluge, H. (2015). *Economic crisis, health systems and health in Europe. Impact and implications for policy*. Open University Press. European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies Series.

14 Cooper, B. (2011) Economic recession and mental health: An overview, *Neuropsychiatrie*, 25: 113–7.

Knapp, M. (2012) Mental health in an age of austerity, *Evidence-Based Mental Health*, 15:54–5.

Ng, K.H., Agius, M. and Zaman, R. (2013) The global economic crisis: effects on mental health and what can be done, *Journal of the Royal Society of Medicine*, 106: 211–14.

15 Dowell-Jones, M. (2015). The Economics of the Austerity Crisis: Unpicking Some Human Rights Arguments. *Human Rights Law Review* (2015) 15(2):193-223.

Reeves, A., McKee, M., Basu, S. & Stuckler, D. (2014). The political economy of austerity and healthcare: Cross-national analysis of expenditure changes in 27 European nations 1995–2011. *Health Policy* 115 (2014) 1–8.

Figure 1.3 Growth rates of health spending (real terms) years 2004-2013 in Italy (dashed line) and mean OCSE (blue line). OECD Health Statistics, 2014

The access to health and social services has become more difficult, often creating conditions for an increase in inequalities and a tightening of difficulties encountered by disadvantaged people.¹⁶

¹⁶ For several years a number of analyzes conducted by CEIS Tor Vergata, by CENSIS and CERGAS showed that since 2008 are emerging clear signs that Italians are adapting their behavior in the consumption of 'good health'. The FBM-Censis survey of 2012 showed that 35% of Italians turned to public health facilities, accepting waiting lists longer, to achieve performance that would buy directly from private structures. A reduced availability of income would seem therefore encourage greater use of public health, accepting greater inconvenience and more time, and postponing the use of health services less urgent, as evidenced by the 18% of Italians who returned private specialist visits and dental. This behavior is consistent with what was found by the VIII Health Report of CEIS Tor Vergata, that the private health spending would be reduced by 2.7% per year between 2001 and 2007, but fell by 4, 8% between 2007 and 2009. In addition, nearly 21% of Italians, according to Censis, has reduced the purchase of medicines paid from their own pockets: more than 23% of 45-65enni, which seems to be justified the estimate of the relationship Oasis 2012 CERGAS-Bocconi that rising ticket for medicine in 2012 would be 40%.

2. Theoretical and methodological approach

2.1 Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach

RE-InVEST aims at investigating the philosophical, institutional and empirical foundations of an inclusive Europe of solidarity and trust. To this end it draws on capability and human rights based participatory approaches. Human rights form a common European basis of values and describe at the same time core elements of what constitutes well-being and a good life. Further, human rights are transformative by empowering people.

Human rights are the basic rights and freedoms that belong to everyone. International law, including treaties, contain the provisions which give human rights legal effect. Ideas about human rights have evolved over many centuries and gained strong support after World War II when the United Nations adopted the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights - which set out for the first time the human rights and fundamental freedoms shared by all human beings without discrimination of any kind.

Human Rights are universally agreed basic standards that aim to ensure that every person is treated with dignity and respect; they are interdependent and indivisible, they belong to all people without discrimination. Usually set out in law, through international or regional treaties, or national legislation, they form a legal statement of universally accepted principles of how the state should treat its citizens and other people living within its jurisdiction. Human Rights include Civil and Political Rights, such as the right to life, the right to a fair trial and the right not to be subjected to torture; and Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, such as the right to work, to join a trade union, to health, to education, and to an adequate standard of living.

Specific groups are protected in specific treaties such as women, children, and people with disabilities, minorities, and migrants. For vulnerable people the usage of a rights-terminology has proven to change their perspective by making them aware of their rights and the ways in which their current situation compromises these rights.

Figure 2.1 Resources, conversion factors, capability set and achieved functionings

The capability approach as developed by Sen (1999) and Nussbaum (2011) defines a person’s well-being in terms of the beings and doings (the functionings) a person achieves and her capability to choose among different combinations of such functionings. For leading a life one values and has reason to value resources and conversion factors are preconditions (Figure 2.1). Resources refer to the material conditions of a person: her income, the goods and services she disposes of. Conversion factors help her converting resources into doing and being well. There are personal conversion factors such as skills and bodily features, social conversion factors such as social norms and social institutions and environmental conversion factors such as

climate and geography. In the end both the achieved functionings as well as the freedom to choose a life one values matters.

For assessing the capabilities of vulnerable people RE-InVEST aims at giving them a voice. Their participation is fostered by relying on participatory action research that directly results in policy recommendations. Participatory action research views participants as co-researchers who have special knowledge about their own situation. Hence they are not only asked or interviewed on their views but take part in research by engaging in, examining, interpreting, and reflecting on their own social world, shaping their sense of identity.

It is a circle of knowledge generation that emerges from this method and includes the steps of knowledge production and sharing, empowerment by participation, newly generated knowledge and action that builds upon this knowledge (Figure 2.2). Crucial for this kind of knowledge generation is the ‘merging’ or ‘crossing of knowledge’ that comes from three parts: scientific knowledge as gained by researchers; knowledge which the poor and excluded have, from their first-hand experience, of the twin realities of poverty and the surrounding world which imposes it on them; and the knowledge of those who work among and with these victims in places of poverty and social exclusion (Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2 Merging of Knowledge

These are the core elements of the Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach (PAHRCA) developed in RE-InVEST. PAHRCA entails seven steps (Toolkit, 44-45): 1. Identify and meet partner NGO/gatekeeper, 2. Preliminary ‘meet ups’ (for trust building if necessary), 3. First meeting with participants – trust building, 4. Developmental: implement developmental human rights & capability approach, 5. Inquiry/data gathering, 6. Identifying patterns (key issues and themes of concern to the group) and 7. Undertake action/outcome using one or combination of approaches.

2.2 Aims of the research

The work has two main objectives.

The primary purpose is to explore if and in what areas of daily life of the people the economic crisis and the austerity anti-crisis policies eroded the human individual and social capabilities to represent a threat to the protection of certain basic human rights (work, health, housing, food, etc.).

Secondly, the research aims to explore a hypothetical decline of trust in the EU, in governments and institutions linked to the economic crisis as well as the neo-liberal measures implemented to deal with it.

Specifically, the answers to these questions are sought by referring to some segments of the population, the weakest and most disadvantaged, as particularly sensitive to the issues in question and need to be protected.

2.3 Participants

Given the socio-demographic characteristics of the Italian situation (unemployed, foreigners, women, parenting, etc., see p. 6), in order to explore the key issues related to the objectives of the research, researchers

have selected a group of eight women aged between 25 and 52 years living in the area of Alba, in the Piedmont region and characterised by different psycho-social vulnerability factors.

Two of them, and their children aged 4 and 5 years old, are currently engaged in a rehabilitation program for drug addiction at a facility providing in-patient treatment for mothers with children. Three women, also with dependent children, have completed since more than a year a rehabilitation program for pathological addiction similar to the previous two, and have since been living and working autonomy.

A participant has psychiatric problems and is currently a guest of the Social Housing 'Casa Pina' in Alba, receiving therapeutic support, housing and employment.

The last two participants are migrants of Romanian nationality, with dependent children, currently in need of support for living and working, guests of the Social Housing 'The Field'.

2.4 Research instruments and methods

The qualitative research used a participatory methodological approach, aimed at achieving the active involvement of participants in focus groups and individual interviews through the execution of specific visual and creative tasks.

Specifically, in addition to classic procedures of collecting data through interviews and focus groups it has been decided, with the consensus of participants, to adopt techniques of photo-voice and the snake-timeline exercise¹⁷ in order to encourage greater participation compared with standard research procedures, to promote the expression of themes and concepts in an alternative, more intuitive and immediate way and to encourage the development of empowerment, critical awareness and dialogical and communicative skills¹⁸. The critical reflection enables people to theorise about the social structures which constrain them and this is done with others who share this social world and requires collaborative reflection on the contradictions of the social world.

The research was organised around four focus groups and two individual interviews.

The first focus group aimed at getting to know the participants, encouraging a first analysis of the subjects of research; to stimulate mutual understanding, building compliance with the objectives of the research and a good group atmosphere. During the first meeting the meaning and objectives of the work were also discussed, the methodology was described but have also wanted to collect alternatives and methodological insights from the participants. At this stage the groups of women initially proposed to work together and to collect data by images, building collages from newspaper and magazines. After a group discussion, however, the choice to take pictures of situations related to their daily personal lives prevailed (photo-voice technique), in a way that shows to other people 'as we see it'.

In the second focus group participants were asked to complete the model snake timeline exercise. The cards were then the subject of a group discussion, comparison and reflection about their own and others' past and current situation. At the end of the second meeting digital cameras were distributed for women to use them for the photo project. The objectives and tasks of the photo-voice work were discussed.

In the third focus group participants shared and discussed the photographs collected during the previous weeks, representative of situations, facts, events of their daily routine connected with the economic crisis. The images depict situations, themes, daily problems as perceived by the own eyes of the participants.

The last focus group, organised after the drafting of the report, aimed at discussing with participants the main results, sharing ideas, impressions and gathering their critical comments.

In parallel with the focus group an individual development in the history of life was carried out with two people, using again the initial work with the snake-timeline exercise.

All matches were audio-recorded with the participants' agreement and only after obtaining their informed consent.

17 Cf. RE-InVEST methodological framework toolkit. Implementing PCHRM in WP3 (pp. 51-74).

18 Cf. RE-InVEST methodological framework toolkit. An overview of participatory action research (pp. 17-22).

2.5 Analysis

The audio recordings of the focus groups were transcribed and the textual material thus obtained were treated with a content analysis. This material is enriched by pictures and comments gathered from participants through the photo-voice technique. For the construction of the analytical categories of content, reference was made to the capabilities approach (individual and social) and to human rights approach (Cf. RE-InVEST methodological framework toolkit, ‘The intersection of capability and human rights approaches’, pp. 9-16).

3. Biographies

3.1 Chf.42.Tdp

In 2008 I enter a community to detox from alcohol and drugs. Before 2008 I was not at all well, I used substances ... I led an irregular and messy life. At that time I met the father of my child.'

'After about a year and a half of therapy I had an important step to accomplish, I miss the stage of re-employment. Basically I find myself at the end of my rehabilitation therapy to try to get involved in the world of work ... but that is not at all easy and that does not happen. There is no work around! Given the problems I 'm suggested to go to Milan in a community devoted specifically integration into work. The idea is that by changing the region things could be better but even there I realise immediately that the situation does not change much. Apart from small fragmented and non-continuous jobs, there is no serious job. A year passes and I'm back without anything concrete in hand. After more than two years of support from the Serd (local drug service) who supported me in the path, I have no other option than to go home to my mom. The SERD can not support me for all my life!'

'A., my son, was born in 2010. The only place where he can go is to my mother's house and then fortunately I had a mother and a brother ... otherwise I would have ended up in the middle of the street! After three months of my son's birth my mother fell ill with cancer and soon had a stroke. In 2010, apart from my son's birth, it was a really bad period because my mother was still an active and vital woman for what she could she always helped me.

I find myself therefore to stay at home, with them: my sick mother, my brother, me and A.'

'Expenses were increasing. At that time my brother had asked for help from everywhere: to have useful medical devices (for example the wheelchair form my mother to be able to move) rather than the attendance allowance, because she was no longer self-sufficient and all those kinds of things ... All things long to get, and they ask tons of bureaucracy and time-consuming. Fortunately my mother had some money aside, because he always tried to make savings throughout life, putting aside some money. Certainly, however, the expenses are raising: the costs to live, to shop for 4 people, the cost of nappies, those for medical examinations ... and at that time I still did not find work.'

'I tidy home, I take care of my mom, I clean and I'm looking for work when I can. Having a small baby, I ask the social services to help me put him in a nursery: so at least I could have a little more free time to go to look for work, I could earn some money and avoid to weigh on my mother's shoulders.'

'Unfortunately social services tell me that, since I am at home with my mother, they cannot help me: however I've got a place where to live, so I have no particular priority on other situations. Basically they do not help in the search for a day care, and so I stay at home in that situation for three years, wondering in search of a job, finding a few small jobs but then I cannot go or I lose all the time because I have to take after my son and my mom ... because who helps me with A.? Yet I was looking for work. At that time I gradually let myself go. At one point, there was nothing else to do rather than staying at home all the time to clean. Searching for work can keep you busy for half a day to a day ... and after a while you run out of places also to ask and bring curricula ... then you do not know where to go. And the remaining part of the twenty-four hours becomes long. I had no satisfaction in what I was doing, I could not help my mother except with my presence, I had no social life-like because of my little son to look after because I had no budget. It was a very stressful ... and that's why then-icing on the cake - I had a relapse on the use of substances. And I assure you that having a relapse with a child is not a good thing, you feel just like crap, drown in guilt.'

'In 2014, after three years of this kind of life and the relapse to drug use I entered the Therapeutic Community here in Alba. Here I am doing a good path. I have been in for a year and a half and now, I'm doing an internship working eight hours a week. Here we are to re-re-employment! I am very scared thinking about the future. Today they have told me that I'm on a waiting list to get a job grant From Health Services and to receive help to complete the last phase of my program, and this is good. Of course, however, the waiting times are getting longer ... the work seems that never comes. My fear in all this is the work, as happened in 2010. Even then, the issue of lack of work made me fall ... and now, unlike then, I have five more years ... I'm 43 and we know well how this could be important but also a problem on the labour market.'

'I have to think about my future and my son, I' have to find a job to support myself and grow him. Although I do not know how to do ... I'm worried because I do not know what will be: I can hardly imagine a clear future. Now I should be able to take this work support and then maybe we can think of a house ... but I can't imagine how -where-when.'

'Today compared to five years ago I am alone. Before somehow I had always been helped by my mother, or my brother. Now I have to get in this world independently ... his society is mostly in crisis! [she smiles ironically] ... and the crisis is huge and it is not a simple thing: alone, with a young son, homeless and unemployed only with my fragility to the use of substances.'

'Today I work eight hours a week. I hope that these hours will increase going forward, but today you cannot predict. Surely with 32 hours per month of work what kind of life can I rebuild? And anyway, even once the situation of the grant job will have been solved where will I go and live? I cannot be host to life of the therapeutic community! After some of the services will eventually pay the tuition and I rent me a house ... but how much money will I need? I could go to a social housing also because with a job grant a person gains about 400 or 500 € per month: with that figure you cannot do everything you want! It's not that we can live a month with that money ... Especially if you are in two and next year A. is beginning also the school year and the expenses will increase for sure.'

'Now in terms of my addiction I'm better and also A. is better. I want to come back to live and build a new life., normal and quiet: I don't ask for the moon! If you think about it, as I said, before 2008 I was not at all well, I used drugs ... I led an irregular life but I could get by doing some odd jobs here and there ... it seems almost paradoxical. I see just one big detachment between the period before 2008 and now ... or so it seems. It seems to me then that I could get along better, I could do better spending ... and I repeat that I was not well at all, I was less polished but I could get along better. Now that I'm better health and I should be able to be more effective ... I seem to get along much worse!'

'I put effort and willpower... But we also need the help of social services. And if I think of 2010, the situation of my mother and mine, I think that there social services don't care ... Sometimes I think that maybe you get to end up in the middle of a road in order to receive a minimum of help.'

3.2 Ma.F52.Psy

'To date, it seems to me that basically my life has always been a bit in crisis.'

'In 2008, this crisis started by banks ... also for me! [Laughs]. At that time they started to close the banks ... So I was doing different jobs but one of these was in a cleaning company who worked in the banks. If we cleaned 4 or 5 banks I found myself to only work only in two... And consequently to the reduction of the work has lead to an initial reduction of economic opportunities [...] It is true that then luckily I did not just work on cleaning in the banks; I had other commitments as a caregiver and assistant to some families with elderly people and I cleaned the homes of some private ... so for a while I still managed. Of course it was not easy because it was a lot of commitment fragmented as time and I slept bad ... this made me nervous and I suffered a lot.'

'Around 2009 I began to have difficulties in paying the rent. At that time I skipped some payments and began to realise that I could not pay the rent in a constant and continuous way. At the same time I found myself in trouble because I could not bring my son to study ... he was struggling to find work and I wanted him to do a training. In the late 2009 and early

2010 I just began to tighten our belts. We begin to deprive us of so many things and have to save on primary commodities: food, clothing, heating consumption. I've never had so many things but in 2010 I started to go shopping at Caritas. In that period there were the first signs of a possible eviction from the house where we lived. The house owner started to be insistent on me having to pay the arrears and, though gently, she pressed me to return the debt to her. When I did not go to Caritas to procure food, I remember that sometimes I spent time to collect what was left at the end of the markets in the square or, more rarely, happened to take the second choice in the supermarket.'

'At that time the medications weren't paid by the National Health Services so I gave up taking them... I had a lot of thyroid problems which were going to add up to my depression. For my daughter, who is celiac, we could not afford to buy what she needed to eat without getting sick, at that time I could not buy food to suit her ... she consequently did not eat much. In the same period we received clothing from Caritas.'

'In 2012 another branch of the bank where we worked, was closed and then I continued cleaning only more in a house. At the same time my health conditions got worse and the question of the payment of rents just escaped from my hands. There I just began to struggle to procure food and I also support the distribution of second hand clothes (the ones that are collected in yellow containers in the street). I see that the Social Services and the assistant who, between one thing and another I know from lifetime, failed to respond to my situation, they can't help me, without some subsidy scarce and rare, but not enough to cope with all that I have to pay. For the whole year before I asked to be helped and after a year I finally received 400 Euros divided into two instalments of 200 euros: in that situation I remember they have been very helpful... but still remained the other 10 months of rent to be paid.'

'In 2013 there was my total psychophysical downfall. Until then I had somehow kept the shot, then I got a monstrous depression, thyroid problems, I had an operation and I were hospitalised. There everything collapsed around me. It was impossible to me to hope for something and opportunities... I saw there were none ... I couldn't predict the future... there was no future. And I realise that I think again to this thing also today. At age of 50, what do you want to do? Wait for retirement? Wait for the future? The work for me ... I do not think there will be ...still tomorrow I'm going to try, I'll go and see what employment is the job they have proposed ... but I do not think there will be a real opportunity. As I told you if I'm not well [indicates head and chest], if I make a damn hard walking to reach the workplace it becomes difficult to work. Yesterday it was my turn to do the cleaning at Casa Pina (ed ...) it took me two hours ... at the end I was so exhausted that I was going to give in outburst ... I ended up go to bed and sleep four hours. I can't do it ... I only do a tremendous effort ... they don't understand this ... if I were not in these conditions it is obvious that I'd go to work out, I would have every incentive to do a lot of hours, to take something more than 200 euros a month and maybe poor I would not be at Casa Pina. Sometimes it seems to me that people believe that I have some advantages or I have fun being as I am, as if it were a situation altogether convenient when you do not have to worry too much and things will come from above.'

'In this path my family has fallen apart ... maybe finally it may seem cynical but I think money is also useful to prop up a family ... The family will break for many reasons, it is true, but money affects in a fundamental way on some of these dynamics. I split up with my husband about twenty years ago. Maybe part of the problem started from there. I've always been a little restless, melancholic ... I do not know, especially ... but I was in shock. My husband said to me 'do not worry I'll pay the rent of the house, do not worry' ... but he paid for a month and then who has seen him any more? From there I started having to organise myself and to do all those jobs in cleaning area and in elderly care. My son after our divorce was found disoriented. For as I was able to arrange he could do some 'what he wanted, maybe too much ... he grew up without references and this is the reason why I feel deeply guilty [recoils] ... I 'll never forgive myself for that. Both my children have had difficulty: my daughter slashed her wrists years ago, my son has made other nonsense, and today is a person in serious difficulty: he doesn't work, he lives along the stress and tries to get some sleep wherever it happens. For heaven's sake, he has made his mistakes, but basically he grew up without a father.'

'Then 2014 arrives. I feel a void and in that time the first deprivation of food and medicines also bench began. I am even poorer and more friendless. The mind and time are constantly absorbed by issues tied to food, to housing, to health ... and my malaise. To that I add the obsessive thought and commitment to try to do something, to find solutions to solve a few pieces.'

The people I know, called friends, are also in trouble and I can't find anyone who can help me ... well they're all walking around without a job. Some friends are in situations somewhat similar to mine: they have dependent children, an unemployed husband who obviously feels bad and useless ... so they have an impossible life they must try to survive with € 600 a month ... so they try to get by as they can ... but when you're in these situations, you can't help someone else ... you already find it hard to get by, let alone help other ... and so also relationships go to hell ...'

4. Results

The results are arranged according to the theoretical perspectives adopted and they follow the approach based on human rights and on human capabilities. The analytical categories used to organise the findings refer therefore to economic, social, cultural rights (Art. 22-27 UDHR) and to fundamental ones (Art. 1-2) to finally show some trends associated with the real capacity and ability of the interviewed women to obtain those rights, as suggested by the human capabilities approach (cf. Nussbaum's list of 'central capabilities'; Nussbaum, 2011¹⁹).

4.1 Impact on human rights

Reference is made specifically to the Universal Declaration of Human and Rights and, particularly, to economic, social, cultural rights while exploring thematic areas related to job -food - house -health. On all aspects participants told us stories of difficult times and experiences related to the current period of economic crisis, even if declined in obviously different ways from case to case.

4.1.1 Employment

The target group is characterised by different types of fragility, when it comes to work. Specifically, the group consists of two unemployed women, two trainees, a woman employed in a part-time job and the remaining three women occupied with a full time contract. Difficulties related to employment emerge clearly from all stories. In some cases difficulties are related to not finding job opportunities which can ensure a decent life:

Four or five years ago, however, I realised that even though I was sick, I could find work or pieces of work here and there, perhaps as a waitress or a few hours to clean some houses ... now I can't find even to clean the toilets as a volunteer... and if you think we are supposed to be living in a republic founded on work.' E.25.FG0.

In other cases the discomfort is associated with situations of under-employment. This is the situation of those who have got a job, but they are still far from working for a sufficient number of hours to ensure minimal wages to satisfy basic needs. There are then women who are struggling with job training and internships, which on one hand offer guarantees of protection and training opportunities, on the other hand they still not have the characteristics of real work, especially in terms of salary.

Today I work eight hours a week. I hope that going forward these hours will increase, but today I cannot predict. Surely with 32 hours per month of work what kind of life can I rebuild? [...] Also because with a job grant you gain about 400 or 500 € per month: you can't live a month with that money.'

19 Martha C. Nussbaum (2011) Capabilities, Entitlements, Rights: Supplementation and Critique, *Journal of Human Development and Capabilities: A Multi-Disciplinary Journal for People-Centered Development*, 12:1, 23-37.

Figure 4.1 Photo-voice data A

'This is Rotoalba, the company's entrance closed. The company worked a lot, with many employees ... And this is something I've seen in just the last three or four years ... A lot of demonstrations, people dismissed, until they just closed ... Now to see this abandoned place it's a bit 'sad; before there was always a bustle of people ... it was lively, there was the world inside it! Now it's all off, closed and abandoned. It's a pity because before there was a nice hedge, the entrance was well-groomed, in short, it was a pleasure to pass by, it gave you pleasure to look inside'

Even those who have managed to find a place in the job market are not without difficulties: often one job is not enough to cover expenses related to daily life and people are then forced to engage in further irregular work.

'To put together a little money, in addition to working from Monday to Friday, I go again to clean houses on the side on Saturday or Sunday ... and you can imagine what I feel like doing something in the remaining free time! ... The crisis is that you can't be home to prepare lunch for your children, and for me it would be a privilege to welcome them ... with a smile, instead of always feeling tired-worried-nervous-... after 15 hours of work a day when I have no time to go pee and maybe I'll have cystitis.'

4.1.2 Food

The participants expressed, to varying degrees, their daily difficulties in meeting their own food needs and those of their families.

'Do you know what I see the crisis from? From canned beans and broth; we started to eat a lot of beans and broth soups, at least you have the box and it does not cost much. But you know what effort it is every night to try to invent yet another different soup, with some ingredients that change at least the 'color ...' C1.43.FG0.

Figure 4.2 Photo-voice data B

'This is our bean soup, it is a little sad to see such an image ... and still good humor also depends on what you eat ... when you eat a meal like this for a few times you will see in the morning what kind of face when you wake up ... instead if you eat a steak or a nice amatriciana with a glass of wine or even a pizza or lasagna ... you feel in another way ... C1.43.FG2

Three main issues emerge from testimonies in relation to food. Some report the practical difficulties in obtaining free food in specific situations of their recent past.

'When I did not go to Caritas to procure food, I remember that sometimes I collected the leftovers of food after the markets in the square or, more rarely, I took the second choice in the supermarket [...].'

There are then difficulties related to the costs of food shopping in general and, in particular, of specific foods, including meat with the consequence of not being able to secure a healthy and balanced diet:

'Today my children tell me: 'Of course it would be nice to be able to eat but occasionally a nice and two finger thick steak And I felt so bad to hear this phrase so the next day I go shopping ... but unfortunately I realise that I usually avoid this kind of daily expenses because I cannot not afford them ... I try to not look at these steaks ... because if I buy three of them I lose immediately 20/25 euro ... and this just demoralises me.' M2. 41.FG1.

The third issue emerging from the discussion with participants has to do with the lack of variety in food.

Figure 4.3 Photo-voice data C

In the context of basic needs, nutrition plays a central role and it determines not only the survival of the person, but also the opportunity to live in good physical and mental conditions, even more for children risking not to have a full physical, mental, intellectual as well as social functioning.

4.1.3 Housing

Most of the women involved in the research (5 out of 8) today have to rely on Social Housing Services or are enrolled in residential rehabilitation programs. In either case these are temporary solutions and will require to find arrangements that today are neither easy to imagine nor to envisage in the short term.

'The teacher called me and asked why my son says that we live in a hotel' (we are in a social housing service): What should I tell my son? How can I make him understand at that age? I told him that we are in a kind of hotel, to explain why sometimes we change room (recoils) [...] Anyway how long can we stay here? We can't stay for all life! Besides you can't receive guests or can't host anyone to sleep ... in short, it is a temporary solution. And the bad thing is that it still does not feel like your home, so you can't do what you want.' A.30.FG0.

'Today I live in a single room in which I have everything; the shelves of the cabinet are made of boxes and boxes I tease and I try to clean and disinfect and dispose as if they were bricks to put my things ... and I feel lucky, because at least I have a roof over my head and now I feel safe and protected. If I think in recent years this is the only occasion where I could have my space, I do not have to share ... something that can be a house ... or something like that. And who knows what will happen later ... the years pass.' M1.52.FG2.

Only 3 out of 8 participants have a home and are able to pay a rent but once obtained, the house still needs to be preserved and maintained. Expenses related to the rent with additional expenses related to the maintenance and cleaning of the property, the administration charges, local/municipal taxes, payment of utilities, etc. It often becomes difficult to support this volume of expenditure and payments get deferred.

Now I put 150 euro aside. How can I survive the other ten days? Today for example, I've called the administrator of the house where I live, saying him I can't pay the rate of service charges and I will try to pay later ... maybe step by step. Maybe I can pay it when I receive the Christmas bonus. And then the questions, the doubts begin so I wonder if I'm wasting money? Where am I wrong?' M2.46.FG1.

Figure 4.4 Photo-voice data D

'The picture of this wall gives the idea of degradation and the cost that you incur to rearrange it ... asking someone's help to fix a wall with moisture leakage is costly ...' M2.46.FG2.

4.1.4 Health care

In addition to the difficulties linked to their work situations, housing, food and family, respondents face hardships regarding health care and self-care. Economic difficulties play a vital role in guiding their behaviors and choices in health.

'I'm not going to the dentist, I was in debt for almost a thousand Euros to fix the teeth of my son in order to help him.' C2.46.FG0.

'I'm not going to the eye doctor because then I know what he'll tell me to do ... and I do not have the money to change lenses and glasses... but I make an effort to read all those little numbers at work ...' N .45.FG0.

Figure 4.5 Photo-voice data E

'These are requirements for medical examinations. I was sick and the doctor prescribed me a lot of tests to do ...but I had to spend too much money. More or less we were around 200 euros and now I can't afford to spend money on medical tests: I just spent almost 700 for my son's school. Not to mention the fact that some of those tests require taking a day off from work and I can't afford it.' M2.46.FG2.

Choices that women take, range therefore from the postponement to not addressing health needs that, increasingly, appear less and less likely to be protected, but rather governed by the laws of the market.

If you have a minimum income you have to pay your blood tests! If you have to go to the dermatologist and you have 110 euro you can be visited immediately, after 2 minutes, but if you do not want to pay 110 euro, but only want to pay 35, you'll wait six months or eight months in Bra or in Alba. But what if it was a skin cancer? After 6 or 8 months you' could be dead! C2.46.FG1.

The consequences that this system of choices can bring in terms of quality of life and health of people are critical, as well as the implications in terms of health economics (when having to deal with acute health problems arising from neglected health care, which are more expensive to deal with) not to mention the political implications linked to the protection of fundamental rights, which appear less and less guaranteed.

4.2 Impact on individual capabilities

In addition to the human rights-based approach, results are organised following the human capabilities categories suggested by Marta Nussbaum.

4.2.1 Life and physical health

Women taking part in the research work reported an overall growth of major stressors and risk factors at the expenses of their psycho - physical well-being.

This crisis of protection and opportunities in the workplace, food, housing and health services can be seen also as a critical factor threatening the capabilities to live a full human life of normal length and to enjoy bodily health.

4.2.2 Sense, imagination and thought

A crisis in imaginative capability and difficulties to project and to forecast the future emerge through the discourses of the participants, especially with reference to working and living environment. Anxieties associated with the uncertainty are also reported.

The most terrible thing is that somehow, along with what you have in your wallet, you start to lose your inner resources ... you lose confidence in yourself, in others, in the future... or maybe you start planning an end ... it is still a kind of defeat.' M2.46.FG1.

'Sometimes, when I'm more hopeful, I think it's just a matter of developing a new form of adaptation and learning ... but I don't know how to do this and where to start...but sometimes I think it is not right to live like this.' E.25.FG0.

'If I think about the future, if I try to focus on what I will do I can't see it clearly, I can't see that far.' C2.42.FG1.

4.2.3 Emotion

In terms of subjective experiences, feelings and emotions the group reveals a mixture of frustrating experiences that range from anger, humiliation and sense of deprivation and helplessness and that generate a malaise placed halfway between the private and the public, and that seems to have an important impact on how the respondents look at themselves, at their own future and at society at large.

I'm tired, stove and angry, especially when I think that politicians from other parties eat and frolic merrily [...]. You feel a lot of anger and humiliation inside. I think the average life status should be equal for all, around a certain threshold, the threshold of what is necessary ... It is not admissible that there are people living like in Africa, and others who waste in style ...' M1.52.FG1.

It's so...even though when you see that things are moving forward and after all your son is healthy then you think that everything makes sense and that it's worth it ... But you always remain suffering ... you don't even know what it is ... and sometimes you feel bad ... Sometimes they say it's great that you're so sunny and smiling ... but you know that this is a kind of mask you wear to move forward ... What do you know how I feel inside?' A.30.FG1.

4.2.4 Play

There is clearly in the lives of the participants a reduced availability of opportunities, time and resources dedicated to recreation and leisure time. Some of the women reported a surplus of resources and energy used in an attempt to increase their own salary doing further work to cope with the economic difficulties. This strategy however runs the risk of sacrificing other needs or equally important areas of life (child care, leisure, health). There is also a reduced ability to laugh and enjoy recreational and playful activities in everyday life.

'Maybe I should have cut my hair since 3 months because I suck ... But I do not give a damn! I collect my hair in tail and with those 20 euro I save I can buy a snack for my child, a pack of cigarettes, or put money in the phone, or we take a piece of pizza.' C1.43.FG1.

'On Friday I am invited to a dinner with the group work and I had to tell them that I do not know if I will go. But I'm not going to tell them I don't have enough money ... Why do I have to go out and eat to spend € 30? I have to eat my heart, then I do not go, I'll find an excuse to do nothing.' M2.46.FG2.

4.2.5 Environmental control

All the above mentioned limitations result in reduced opportunities to control life environment at large. The difficulties faced by the women drastically reduce their capabilities to engage with the processes and choices that affect their lives:

'I wonder why can I can't be able to get what I need by myself? To be able to buy the food that I want...to be able to choose?' M1.52.FG1.

'Today they have told me that I'm on a waiting list to get a job grant From Health Services and to receive help to complete the last phase of my program, and this is good. Of course, however, the waiting times are getting longer ... the work seems to never comes and I'm worried because I do not know what will happen to me.' Ch.42.Tdp. FG2.

4.3 Impact on 'collective capabilities'

4.3.1 Education, children and family

Additional difficulties associated with the recent economic crisis are identified by the women involved in the research, in relation to child care and education of children. Some of our respondents are struggling with the dilemma of having to choose between work commitments and education of children:

'And then maybe the social services say your children are left too alone ... And it's bad because you realise that you have to choose between giving them shelter and food - so you have to run, work hard - and be with them only for limited time - or just seeing them but not being able to guarantee their basic needs: food, shelter, clothing.' N.45.FG2.

This difficulty is also linked to the fact that most the respondents are currently without a partner supporting with child care and they feel responsible for all duties related to children. Moreover, limited financial resources reduce the educational opportunities for the children more than other ones associated with the standard of living, such as clothing.

'At the same time I found myself in trouble because I could not afford my son's education ... he was struggling to find work and I wanted him to do training courses.' M1.52.I.

Figure 4.6 Photo-voice data F

*'These are my son's suits, worn and full of holes ...
I'm struggling to buy new ones.'*
C2.42.FG2.

These dynamics all together can erode the family atmosphere:

'At a time when I'm out all day to try to recover a handful of euro, the home is neglected, my husband is at home, without work, feeling a failure because his wife has to maintain him. My son suffers the mother's absence and in addition to the lack of relationship also the clothes are dirty and must be ironed ... so the dynamic of this sort of family is not beautiful ... It is difficult to handle if you are not used to.' E.25.FG1.

'In this path my family has fallen apart ... maybe finally it may seem cynical but I think money is also useful to grow a family ... The family will break for many reasons, it is true, but money affects in a fundamental way on some of these dynamics.' M1.52.I.

4.3.2 Local communities, civil society and social climate

Tracks of the disintegration - or at least fragmentation - of socio-relational ties of communities can be found in the women's words:

'One thing that I see it's that when I look at other people of other nationalities in my situation I see them more united and they are in solidarity with each other ... on the contrary we seem hyenas ... there is no solidarity ... it seems that when you're in trouble others are happy.' A.30.FG1.

Some socio-relational aspects are particularly critical, and exacerbated by the scarcity of resources and the allocation of support, for example those related to relations between different ethnic groups, where growing tensions can be experienced:

'For example, if I ask for a subsidy because I can't pay the canteen of the children they answer me, no, because you have an income, and then they give it to foreigners. It is a shame but lately I'm getting a bit 'racist'.' C2.46.FG1.

'Yes, they are making us racists! These days, the problem is that you get angry and you become racist.' N.45.FG1.

These tensions are particularly critical in an environment where coping strategies against the economic crisis are trying to encourage and stimulate community-based forms of support or otherwise to build on informal networks of support, solidarity and trust.

4.3.3 Trust, social services and institutions.

In this social climate the trust, especially in institutions and public services, are strongly questioned:

'Trust can't be recovered. For now I trust only people where I can see a living which somehow I can touch and feel on the skin. I'm afraid of social services and I do not trust those people [...].' C2.46.FG1.

In terms of the perception and evaluation of work of social services, our respondents report an evident decrease of social protection:

But the help does not arrive from where it should reach you ... as if the services formally appointed fail to meet the needs. And sometimes they treat you badly and yet they say you have so much free time and so you can wait or look for better solutions that you do not find but that they not find either [...] on the other side you rely on informal solidarity from those you don't expect. It is not a simple complaint ... it is just a fact that I see.' M1.52.FG2.

People turning to social services are decreasing, because they are fed up to go and ask for help and to feel mistreated ...' M2.46.FG1.

The system of social services is perceived in a confused and sometimes contradictory way:

It's hard to understand what the criteria are and how you can get help: sometimes they give you a grant or money, sometimes they say you can't ... bob ... sometimes you can go and ask once a month ... in other places 3 times a month ... the rules always change and become almost unpredictable... and when you can't understand that then maybe you get angry because you think it's a joke.' M1.52.FG2.

Or the perception can reach to the level of a sense of conspiracy of the system and by almost persecutory or paranoid attitudes:

I think it's a kind of game ... The great mastermind of Draghi and all other politicians are playing Risiko and say 'You know what to do now? Let's go for a bit of trouble in Spain 'and go and move from side to side ... Then they say,' Now we are interested in Greece ', and move to Greece and within two months, they put it KO. I no longer believe in anything ... Why is everything decide blindly, and fools like us are so fragile ... we are killed.' C2.46.FG2.

4.4 The other side of the coin? Resilience of individuals, families and local communities

Trying to grasp some positive elements in such a desperate picture is not easy, but clearly the rediscovery of the value of essentiality is a central aspect of great importance in terms of resilience:

I got so used to the fact that I no longer have certain things which I do not miss them anymore. It's sad but it could be a sort of remedy to this crisis today: to content ourselves and live with little [...] And here we return to the system, a system that then maybe wants to see you hanged ... but I would like to hang them ... when I think about these things, I get angry.' C2.46.FG2.

A second aspect of resilience emerging from the discourses of the participants is the development of a high tolerance to frustration and coping strategies to face difficulties. This trend seems to have also some inter-generational effects, especially on young people.

I realise that if M. [the son, ndr.] hears me talking about money, or if for 2 or 3 days we only eat vegetables or soups, then I see him worried ... so sometimes he asks: 'But ... but are we in bad shape? Do we need money? [...]' On the one hand they seem to be already more responsible and I think this thing is positive because it means growing fast; but it is also a bit sad ... because they feel the weight. I am convinced that it is right that one should know how to suffer, know how to roll up their sleeves, to adapt and be able to cope ... Also to eat little ... But sometimes maybe this is too much for them.' C1. 43. FG1.

'And those questions inside you feel as if you've beaten up. On the one hand you feel they are very wisdom ... but on the other side it seems you are not able to guarantee basic things. For heaven's sake it's right to say 'no' to them, however, when you realise that these prohibitions are increasing because you cannot afford things and not for some educational reasons, then that sounds different.' M2.46.FG2.

There is also the rediscovery of alternative forms of solidarity and proximity, related to informal networks:

In the social housing service where I live now there are also migrants coming from sub-Saharan Africa: they are kind, sometimes they cook the bread and bring me a little ... and of course it suits me and I am pleased! My family, my mother and my brother, for example, they never visit me ... and so it happens to get help from those who do not expect it from ... or

from who is in a bad shape like you ... people encountered in the street ... with a smile, a support, a hand ... and maybe you don't even know their names.' M1.52.FG2.

'The fact that there are people who give you something to eat it's ok ... I enjoy them, I feel them closer and this is a wealth ... at the same time, however, it bothers you because you wonder. Can I not be able to get what I need by myself? To be able to buy the food that I want...to be able to choose?' M1.52.FG1.

5. Conclusions

First of all the testimonies seem to suggest that the recent economic crisis and the measures currently taken to tackle it can represent a threat for the protection of certain fundamental human rights, as well as questioning of human capabilities.

Levels of trust in the social system and in some actors playing key roles in the process of protecting and promoting the needs and rights of the people are endangered and relationships with the system are ambivalent.

‘Every person you meet is fighting a battle which you know nothing about. Be gentle. Always.’, says a famous Italian film director. Respondents have shared some of the ‘daily struggles’ they have to cope with from different angles (work, home, food, children, etc.) together with emotions, thoughts and feelings experienced in relation to such events. The women’s words reported here are self explanatory in depicting the many ways in which crisis impacts on the respondents, even more heavily on women with a past of pathological addictions, psychiatric problems, stories of migration.

These stories altogether lead to three orders of reflections, partially connected to each other.

First of all difficulties faced by most vulnerable people are less and less unique and increasingly widespread. The terms ‘poverty’, ‘difficulty’, ‘fragile’ are becoming more varied: there are ‘poverties’, ‘fragilities’ and ‘difficulties’ in plural with a growing number of situations characterised by the presence of a number of different problems at the same time.

In a qualitative sense, ‘the poverty-fragility-difficulty’, together with exclusion and social marginalisation, are increasingly characterised by a mix of critical situations, deficiencies and needs found in different areas and around several vital dimensions rather than being a condition of concern limited to a single aspect or specific factor. Increasingly the phenomenology of these issues consists of employment difficulties that are intertwined with problems related to housing, food, health care and so on.

This reflection, which begins as a statement placed on a level of descriptive analysis, also extends to the plane explanatory and interpretative data. In this sense it seems useful to adopt perspectives and theoretical keys as ‘plural’ and of such complex phenomena need to be analyzed in their plural dimension, as multi-dimensional and systemic should be interventions aimed at addressing them.

A second order of reflections emerging from the data looks at the reference models of interpretation of the above phenomena, which in our case have been led by a human rights and capabilities approach.

With reference to human rights, a marked decline in the protection of the most important needs and rights has been depicted: work, rest, food, education, housing, health care and standard of living—so as fundamental ones—equality and dignity. It would appear in fact that our respondents, already vulnerable or otherwise marked by levels of fragility higher than the average of the population, are more affected by stress factors related to the lack of social and institutional protection.

The most concerning finding is linked to the erosion of set of internal resources, potential and subjective tools that make up the human baggage of devices through which people participate to the promotion and full realisation of their rights and guarantee the fulfillment of their basic needs. In other words it seems that in addition to an objective reduction of real opportunities and protections in terms of employment, housing, food, etc., there is a reduction in subjective and collective resources and human potentials, which seem to go to the direction of an impoverishment and loss of fresh skills and opportunities necessary and useful to the full satisfaction of needs and rights.

Trying to use a metaphor, not only a hypothetical and imaginary container of rights and opportunities, seem to fall, but rather the capacity of people to tap into that container. With another metaphor, there is a lack of food but also the ability of people to learn and take action to access it seem to crumble.

This set of problems and plural difficulties -connected on the one hand with the lack of opportunities and protection of rights and basic needs, and on the other hand intertwined with reduced capacity and human potential - seem to unfold an unique but not neutral social and institutional environment.

Coming to the third and final order of ideas that seem to emerge from the collected stories, in terms of perception and evaluation of the social climate and institutional agencies, the participants' discourse seem to return a frame of fluctuation between criticism and ambivalence towards different social and institutional actors. Strong criticism and mistrust emerges towards major institutions that seems directly proportional to the degree of accountability and proximity that these institutions can offer to the person: they are far away from the real life so people can't trust. In contrast, other social actors, especially those informal and closer to the daily dimension of life – like groups of peers, the networks of neighborhood, etc., seem subject to a different evaluation and perception, still marked by critical aspects but also by the discovery of unexpected closeness and solidarity.

These reflections are important, in particular if looking at the future. Given that most of the policies and operational strategies to cope with the crisis seem to move towards community-based forms of welfare and towards the strengthening of alliances and networks between institutional and informal actors, particular importance is given to the quality of the social fabric and the social capital of the community. This quality should indeed be inspired by feelings of solidarity and mutual trust in order to facilitate appropriate levels of cooperation, respect and partnership. In this sense the stories we collected seem to show some symptoms of critical and risky ambivalences that, although 'in process' and far from being clearly oriented, appear undoubtedly worthy of attention, in particular when looking at the investment of resources in care.

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The case of people with disabilities in Latvia

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 649447

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Contents

List of tables	7
List of figures	9
Introduction	11
1. The crisis and poverty and social exclusion among people with disabilities	13
1.1 An overview of the crisis: austerity measures and their effects on poverty and social exclusion in Latvia	13
1.2 The poverty and social exclusion among people with disabilities	16
1.3 The Added value of the research	17
2. The participatory research approach	18
2.1 Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach	18
2.2 The making and involving of a group of participants with experiential knowledge	19
Application of CA in respect of the disabled	19
Selection of NGO's and participants	20
Formulation of interview and data analysis guidelines	20
3. Living with disability	21
3.1 Anna's story	21
3.2 Rita's story	23
4. Analysis: women with disability in crisis	26
4.1 Impact of the crisis	26
4.1.1 Why some did not notice the crisis	26
4.1.2 Decrease of the family income	26
4.1.3 Crisis in health care	28
4.2 Capabilities of women with disabilities	29
4.2.1 Their own stereotypes and stereotypes prevailing in the society about people with disability	30
4.2.2 Fighting for rights	31
4.2.3 Feeling of unfairness and inequality	32
4.3 Collective capabilities	33
5. Conclusion	35
Bibliography	37

List of tables

Table 1.1	GDP and unemployment indicators, 2008-2014	14
Table 1.2	Monetary poverty and equality, 2008-2014	14

List of figures

Figure 2.1	Resources, conversion factors, capability set and achieved functionings	18
Figure 2.2	Merging of Knowledge	19

Introduction

This report is prepared in the framework of the Europe H2020 project ‘Rebuilding an inclusive, value based Europe of solidarity and trust through social investments’ (RE-InVEST). The RE-InVEST project aims to contribute to a more solidary and inclusive EU, through an inclusive, powerful and effective social investment strategy at EU level. Moreover, the project itself adopts a participative approach that gives voice to vulnerable groups and civil society organisations. The RE-InVEST consortium consists of members of the informal network ‘the Alliances to fight Poverty’, a network of civil society organisations, trade unions, policy makers and academics co-ordinated by the Flemish Christian labour movement *beweging.net*, and committed to a more inclusive Europe. The consortium covers a broad range of European countries, both geographically (12 countries, 13 regions) and in terms of representation of different welfare and labour market traditions. The analyses are carried out by the local partners, who consist of NGOs and/or researchers.

In particular, this report is one of the 13 national reports that make up the qualitative research of the RE-InVEST work package ‘The social damage of the crisis’. This work package focuses on the lived experience of vulnerable people, the impact of the crisis (and crisis-related policy reform) on vulnerable groups as well as the impact of growing inequality and social vulnerability on distrust. Our two key hypothesis in this regard are: 1. that growing distrust and indeed resentment among the population may be attributed to (a rejection of) the neoliberal policies employed by national as well as European elites in recent years; 2. that this integrated diagnosis can build on the idea of the erosion of/disinvestment in (individual and collective) capabilities and basic social rights in the EU. This means that experiences of insecurity, poverty and social degradation need to be re-analysed from those perspectives.

Next to the 13 qualitative case studies, this work package consists of a cross-validation with a report describing trends in selected quantitative indicators that reflect the relation between socio-economic vulnerability, human rights and capabilities. A third element consists of a statistical analysis of the dynamic relationship between vulnerability, shifts in social policies and trust: in which sections of the population has the trust in institutions declined most? Can different patterns between countries be observed, and can they be explained by differences in policy shifts and differences in resilience of civil society? A European synthesis report will combine the main findings from the three types of analyses.

The qualitative research focuses on the experience of vulnerable groups in each of the 12 countries (13 regions) participating in RE-InVEST. Mixed teams of researchers, NGO- and union workers, practitioners and people from vulnerable groups jointly analysed cases where the crisis has impacted on human rights and (individual as well as collective) capabilities.

This Latvian qualitative study focuses on women with disabilities. We would like to thank all participants of our group and the NGO “Zvaigzne” where we were hosted for their responsiveness and hospitality to discuss the situation of people (women) with disabilities and search for solutions in order to fight for their rights and development of their capabilities.

1. The crisis and poverty and social exclusion among people with disabilities

1.1 An overview of the crisis: austerity measures and their effects on poverty and social exclusion in Latvia

In 2008 – 2010 Latvia experienced the hardest economic downside among the EU member states. At the end of 2008 the state stood on the threshold of bankruptcy and it was forced to apply for assistance to international lenders (the European Community, the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund). The government implemented a restrictive fiscal policy from 2008 onwards. Six consolidation packages were adopted from 2009 until 2012 with the purpose of ensuring midterm financial sustainability. Generally, consolidation measures in the amount of 16.6 per cent of GDP were implemented from 2008 until 2011: 6.6 per cent concerned budget revenues and the remainder budget expenditure. Fiscal consolidation in Latvia was among the most severe in Europe. Within the framework of budget adjustments several changes were introduced in tax legislation which took the form of tax increases or expansion of the tax base (increased value added tax rates; abolishment of the reduced tax rate for electricity and natural gas; raised personal income tax; expansion the personal income tax base; decreased non-taxable monthly minimum as the economic situation deteriorated, increased compulsory social security contribution rate for the employed). This had a negative impact on welfare, particularly of the vulnerable segments of the population. The government provided budget adjustments mainly by increasing the employment income tax burden, which was already fairly high in Latvia (Dovladbekova, 2013).

Significant consolidation was carried out on government spending during this period. In the crisis situation significant budgetary cuts have affected education, health care, the welfare sector, transport services. The decrease of expenditures in the public sector has had a direct impact on the accessibility and the scale of many essential social services. Fiscal adjustments provided for notable cuts in funding for the Ministry of Transport, as well as the Ministries of Welfare and Health.

The government attempted to reduce the base of allowances due to the impact of the crisis. For this reason amendments to laws providing for restrictions on entitlements to unemployment benefits, sick pay, maternity, paternity or paternal benefits were adopted and remained until 2014. Adjustments in restrictions on unemployment benefits were also introduced. For example, in 2009–2011 childbirth allowances were cut by almost 35 per cent, child care and paternal benefits by 40 per cent and child care allowance for a child younger than 1 year by almost 38 per cent. The parliament adopted adjustments to the law on pensions on 14 June 2012 providing for the increase of the retirement age from 62 to 65 years by three months per year starting from 2014.

State consolidated general budget spending for 2012 is lower than in 2011 due to the restrictive fiscal policy. Spending on human capital intensive sectors as health care (–6.3 per cent), education and science (–11.2 per cent) and social security was reduced. As a result of the austerity policy the government did not have to make full use of the funds granted within the international aid programme: only 4.4 billion euros or 59 per cent were actually utilised (Dovladbekova, 2013).

The economy of Latvia went into deep recession – during the crisis the GDP decreased by ¼. Although the economy of Latvia has been growing in recent years, GDP is still by 5% lower than before the crisis - at the end of 2007. (Ministry of Economics of the Republic of Latvia, 2015).

Table 1.1 GDP and unemployment indicators, 2008-2014

	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
Real GDP growth rate (percentage change on previous year)	-3.6	-14.3	-3.8.7	6.2	4.0	3.0	2.4
Unemployment rate (%)	7.7	17.5	19.5	16.2	15.0	11.9	10.8

Source Eurostat

Even after more than a year of recovery (2011), the unemployment rate remained devastatingly high. That is mainly because the recovery was relatively weak, especially given the depth of the severe economic contraction. But the official unemployment rate does not measure the full cost of this recession and weak recovery of Latvia's labour force. If we take into account those who are involuntarily working parttime and those who have given up looking for work, we get peak unemployment/underemployment rates of 30.1 percent in 2010, declining to 21.1 percent in the third quarter of 2011. It also does not include all the people who have left the country in search of employment since the crisis began. It is estimated that the net loss of population in 2009-2011 amounts to as many as 120,000 people, or 10 percent of the labour force (Weisbrot and Ray, 2011).

Fortunately, the situation appears to improve in the latest years. According to the labour force survey data for the period from 2011 to 2015, the number of employed has increased by 45.4 thousand or on average by 9.1 thousand per year. Employment growth is based on economic recovery – since 2010, GDP has increased by a fifth. Employment growth has contributed to reduced unemployment. Over 5 years, the unemployment rate has decreased by almost a half. The unemployment rate fell to 9.6% in 2016, which was by 0.3 percentage points less than in 2015 (Ministry of Economics of the Republic of Latvia, 2016; Central Statistical Bureau of Latvia, 2017).

The decrease of expenditures in the public sector has had a direct impact on the accessibility and scale of many essential social services. During the economic crisis the capacity of local, regional and national authorities was limited as no adequate funding was allocated for policy implementation and all the above authorities experienced significant budget cuts and dismissals, and institutions responsible for the formulation and implementation of these policies have insufficient human resources (Lace, 2012).

The depth of the crisis and budget consolidation measures undertaken by the government that affected every socially relevant sector, had a negative impact on the living standards of the population by significantly increasing the depth of poverty and the number of the people living in poverty.

Table 1.2 Monetary poverty and equality, 2008-2014

	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
At risk of poverty or social exclusion	34.2	37.9	38.2	40.1	36.2	35.1	32.7
At risk of poverty rate	26.4	20.9	19.0	19.0	19.4	21.2	22.5
Severe material deprivation	19.3	22.1	27.6	31.0	25.6	24.0	19.2
Gini coefficient	37.5	37.5	35.9	35.9	35.7	35.2	35.5
Income quintile share ratio	7.3	7.4	6.8	6.5	6.5	6.3	6.5

Source Eurostat, EU-SILC data

Over the recent years there has been evidence of an improvement in the macroeconomic situation and a gradual recovery of national economy in Latvia in the wake of the 2008-2010 crisis. The stabilisation of the

economic situation has had a certain positive impact on the indicators describing the living standard of the population as well as changes in the key social indicators. Yet at the same time some negative trends have emerged that reveal the depth of the impact the economic crisis has had on certain at poverty and social exclusion risk groups of the population.

“The employment and social situation slowly improves while signs of divergence among and within Member States persist ... The number and proportion of people at-risk-of poverty or social exclusion stabilised overall in both 2013 and 2014. But social developments still point to further divergence across the EU as the scoreboard of key employment and social indicators shows in relation to at-risk-of poverty and inequality developments” (Draft Joint Employment Report 2016, 2015, p.2).

The constantly high income inequality in Latvia testifies to the inequality in the distribution of resources and income among groups of the population as well as the necessity to reconsider the redistribution models of the current social security and taxation policy with the aim of improving the living standards and income of the poorest population.

Accessibility of health care services is one of the topical policy issues in Latvia. In view of the considerable problems that exist in the health care sector and their impact on the living standards and welfare of the population, in 2014 and in 2015 Latvia has received the country specific recommendations concerning improving the cost-effectiveness, quality and accessibility of the healthcare system. Latvia has the highest proportion of the population with unmet needs for medical examination or treatment (because too expensive, too far to travel or waiting list) in EU28 member states. If during the period of 2010 – 2013 this indicator in the EU28 member states fluctuated slightly above 2%, then in Latvia it exceeded 12%. Significant differences from the average EU28 indicators can be seen in all income quintile groups in Latvia, exceeding them 5 times on the average (Eurostat, Unmet needs for medical care).

The dramatically high ratio of the poorest population with unmet needs for medical examination or treatment, even though there are discount payments for health care services or waivers of payment for the poor, shows that households with the lowest income level are more exposed to the risk of not receiving the required medical assistance than others.

The ratio of the public funding for health care in Latvia is about 60% of the total expenditure on health care while in other EU countries it fluctuates from 65% to 85% (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Latvia, 2014). Private spending for health care remains very high. As it has been emphasised in the Public Health Guidelines for 2014-2020, in Latvia the level of direct payments by patients is high in all income groups; however, households with low incomes are more likely to face proportionally high expenses for health care than households with high incomes (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Latvia, 2014).

As it has been concluded in the Public Health Guidelines, the current situation moves the health care system in Latvia even further away from the model that could be called universal due to the insufficient public funding, and the considerable private funding (and the underdeveloped system of voluntary insurance) health care is no longer equally accessible to all inhabitants and it does not have any mechanisms at work that can protect households against excessive losses in cases of diseases that require expensive and long-term treatment/care (University of Latvia, 2014).

The most important causes of the limited accessibility of healthcare services are: lack of funding, lack of human resources, high out of pocket payments, regional disparities in service provision and low solvency of patients. Costs of healthcare services is the main factor restricting the accessibility of healthcare services.

One of the main causes for this problem that is indicated by the health care policy-makers, is the low national budget funding for the sector, which was significantly reduced during the years of crises as was done in other social sectors as well. Already for years the funding as a percentage of GDP allocated for health care has been one of the lowest if not the lowest in Europe and it fluctuates from 3.3% of GDP in 2005 to 3.5% of GDP in 2012 and 3.2% in 2013 while other EU member states allocate 4.5% to 9% of GDP for health care (University of Latvia, 2014).

Alongside with the financial aspects of health care accessibility, another reason for the low accessibility is long waiting lists for medical examinations and treatments. The waiting period for out-patient health care services fluctuates from 20 days to even 680 days in respect of specific services (Ministry of Health of the

Republic of Latvia, 2014). For example, patients diagnosed with cancer have to wait on average 25 working days for treatment (chemotherapy, radiotherapy), for a rheumatologist's consultation patients have to wait up to 86 working days depending on the region (Zilvere, 2014).

1.2 The poverty and social exclusion among people with disabilities

Since the crisis began in 2008 Latvia is characterised by a significant increase in the number of disabled people - an increase in seven years of about 32% among adults and 5% among children. 8.5% of the total Latvian population are persons with disabilities in 2015.

Persons with disabilities are one of the social exclusion risk groups in Latvia whose social exclusion risk is very significantly influenced by employment and education problems as well as accessibility of health care services and the current social protection measures.

The social inclusion of people with disabilities is prevented by the many problems in health care. People with disabilities mentioned rehabilitation activities that have not been performed in due time or not performed at all, due to the social situation that individuals, in particular those who do not work, have limited financial resources for treatment and rehabilitation (Labklājības ministrija, 2014). In addition to the above the disabled also mention problems with reimbursable medication: in the new procedure the state reimburses the cheapest or reference medicine, which causes difficulties and higher costs if this particular medicine is not for sale in pharmacies.

There are also problems in the field of social services. Data at the disposal of the Ministry of Welfare show that currently on average 83% of all social care service recipients receive them at institutions. Alternative social services are received only by 17% of recipients.

Since 2009 and till 2013 the number of persons with disabilities significantly increased in the total number of people living in poverty in the country as well. A person living in poverty is eligible for receiving municipal social assistance benefits. A family (individual) is considered to be poor (needy) if the income per family member has not exceeded EUR 128.06 per month over the previous 3 months. The income threshold is the same for the whole country. The guaranteed minimum income benefit (GMI) level is set as a result of compromise and depends on the available budgetary resources of the municipalities (and partly on the political will to discuss an increase in the GMI level) (in 2016 – EUR 49.80 per person). As it has been emphasised in World Bank research, GMI eligibility is not directly linked to any calculations characterising the poverty threshold or budget standard approach; there is no obligation either to guarantee a minimum level of income or subsistence, or to increase GMI in line with wage rises or cost-of-living increases. Therefore the GMI level and the average GMI benefit amount are inadequate to keep GMI beneficiaries out of poverty. GMI programme recipients with no other income are at high risk of poverty. The other most frequently granted benefits are housing (apartment) support payments, payments for covering health care related costs, children's education and care and free-lunch payments at kindergartens and schools. No doubt, these benefits provide certain support, at the same time one has to admit that benefit amounts in various local governments can differ greatly (Lace, 2015).

Although people with disabilities were not affected by the reduction of the pension amount and social benefits, this particular group also acutely feels the impact of the economic crisis. In most part, this is related to the decline in the accessibility of health care services and rehabilitation services as the number of services paid by the state in the above areas has been significantly reduced.

It has been recognised in the "Guidelines for Implementation of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities in 2014 - 2020" that disabled people are hired by employers with certain reluctance, and according to NGOs representing interests of the disabled, there are no stimulating measures at the national level targeting employers that could promote employment of the disabled on long-term basis, not only on a temporary basis. Although the development of social entrepreneurship is a significant instrument in promoting the employment and social inclusion of social exclusion risk groups, until now no real measures have been taken in Latvia for its development. Likewise the NGOs emphasise environment

accessibility problems that are topical in stimulating employment as well as education and prevent the disabled from active participation in the life of the society (Labklājības ministrija, 2014).

Although already for years many policy planning documents approved by the government have mentioned the implementation of inclusive education for the persons with disabilities in Latvia, until now no significant progress has been observed. Problems of inclusive education include lack of appropriately adapted physical and study infrastructure at schools of general education as well as insufficient training of specialists, etc.

According to State Employment Agency (SEA) the ratio of the disabled in the total number of the registered unemployed has increased - from 5.8% in 2010 to 10.5% at the end of March 2016. According to the data of the SEA, at the end of March, 2015, more than half (52.4%) of the registered unemployed with disabilities were long-term unemployed (Nodarbinātības valsts aģentūra, 2016).

1.3 The Added value of the research

The crisis has also significantly affected research that is why there are comparatively few research studies and publications on the impact of the crisis. To better describe the situation two periods can be distinguished – the pre-crisis period (2006-2007) and the crisis and post-crisis period (currently on-going research). The pre-crisis period is characterised by in-depth research of labour market problems where one of the aspects is social exclusion and long-term unemployment. The given research has also focused on the situation of the disabled in comparison with other at social exclusion - risk groups. The post-crisis research studies are not so extensive and large-scale, and there are no specific research studies on experience of the disabled in overcoming the crisis.

Data of the opinion poll conducted among the population of Latvia at the end of 2013 show that the most significant aspects of life that have changed under the impact of the crisis, are employment and the related growth of unemployment, in particular long-term unemployment, the decline of the living standards of the population and the related growth of poverty, deepening of the gap between the ruling political elite of the society and the general public and related social inequality. In Latvia like in other EU member states the influence of the crisis was most acutely felt by women, children and youths, the unemployed, people with a low level of education and skills unsuitable for the labour market. Shared efforts in overcoming difficulties may operate as a factor that consolidates as well as splits the society. As concerns the impact of the crisis more than half (59%) of the respondents agreed to the statement that the cohesion of the society has decreased as every individual has been more focused on taking care of himself-herself and their families. On the whole, two trends emerge in the lessons gained from the crisis – prudence, caution, frugality in money matters (70%) and reliance only on oneself (60%). Reliance on oneself, a higher degree of individualisation of the society are features of a modern society, however, the individual must have at his/her disposal resource that would help to actively develop and act. If the capability and activity is not strengthened the forecast for the country is stagnation rather than a rapid development (Lāce, Rungule, 2016).

Therefore, the capability approach is important for the continuation of the research on the impact of the crisis on the society of Latvia as it is line with the essence/nature of the identified problems.

Taking into account the situation in the research of the impact of the crisis in Latvia, we have chosen a target group whose experience in overcoming the crisis has not yet been researched. The choice of the NGO for the disabled was also determined by the comparatively high self-organisation level of these organisations in identifying and defending their interests. From this point the “contribution” in the context of Latvia may be also the summary of the experience of people and organisations for the disabled.

2. The participatory research approach

2.1 Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach

RE-InVEST aims at investigating the philosophical, institutional and empirical foundations of an inclusive Europe of solidarity and trust. To this end it draws on capability and human rights based participatory approaches. Human rights form a common European basis of values and describe at the same time core elements of what constitutes well-being and a good life. Further, human rights are transformative by empowering people.

Human rights are the basic rights and freedoms that belong to everyone. International law, including treaties, contain the provisions which give human rights legal effect. Ideas about human rights have evolved over many centuries and gained strong support after World War II when the United Nations adopted the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights - which set out for the first time the human rights and fundamental freedoms shared by all human beings without discrimination of any kind.

Human Rights are universally agreed basic standards that aim to ensure that every person is treated with dignity and respect; they are interdependent and indivisible, they belong to all people without discrimination. Usually set out in law, through international or regional treaties, or national legislation, they form a legal statement of universally accepted principles of how the state should treat its citizens and other people living within its jurisdiction. Human Rights include Civil and Political Rights, such as the right to life, the right to a fair trial and the right not to be subjected to torture; and Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, such as the right to work, to join a trade union, to health, to education, and to an adequate standard of living.

Specific groups are protected in specific treaties such as women, children, and people with disabilities, minorities, and migrants. For vulnerable people the usage of a rights-terminology has proven to change their perspective by making them aware of their rights and the ways in which their current situation compromises these rights.

Figure 2.1 Resources, conversion factors, capability set and achieved functionings

The capability approach as developed by Sen (1999) and Nussbaum (2011) defines a person’s well-being in terms of the beings and doings (the functionings) a person achieves and her capability to choose among different combinations of such functionings. For leading a life one values and has reason to value resources and conversion factors are preconditions (Figure 2.1). Resources refer to the material conditions of a person: her income, the goods and services she disposes of. Conversion factors help her converting resources into doing and being well. There are personal conversion factors such as skills and bodily features, social conversion factors such as social norms and social institutions and environmental conversion factors such as

climate and geography. In the end both the achieved functionings as well as the freedom to choose a life one values matters.

For assessing the capabilities of vulnerable people RE-InVEST aims at giving them a voice. Their participation is fostered by relying on participatory action research that directly results in policy recommendations. Participatory action research views participants as co-researchers who have special knowledge about their own situation. Hence they are not only asked or interviewed on their views but take part in research by engaging in, examining, interpreting, and reflecting on their own social world, shaping their sense of identity.

It is a circle of knowledge generation that emerges from this method and includes the steps of knowledge production and sharing, empowerment by participation, newly generated knowledge and action that builds upon this knowledge (Figure 2.2). Crucial for this kind of knowledge generation is the “merging” or “crossing of knowledge” that comes from three parts: scientific knowledge as gained by researchers; knowledge which the poor and excluded have, from their first-hand experience, of the twin realities of poverty and the surrounding world which imposes it on them; and the knowledge of those who work among and with these victims in places of poverty and social exclusion (Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2 Merging of Knowledge

These are the core elements of the Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach (PAHRCA) developed in RE-InVEST. PAHRCA entails seven steps (Toolkit, 44-45): 1. Identify and meet partner NGO/gatekeeper, 2. Preliminary ‘meet ups’ (for trust building if necessary), 3. First meeting with participants – trust building, 4. Developmental: implement developmental human rights & capability approach, 5. Inquiry/data gathering, 6. Identifying patterns (key issues and themes of concern to the group) and 7. Undertake action/outcome using one or combination of approaches.

2.2 The making and involving of a group of participants with experiential knowledge

Application of CA in respect of the disabled

The capability approach (CA) cannot be applied in respect of people with disabilities without taking into consideration the specific character of this particular target group. If we discuss capability in the meaning used by Sen as the possibilities of functioning that correspond to the individual’s imagination, then it must be recognised that people with disabilities have certain health-related limited functioning. Capability of the disabled can be discussed only within the frame of this limitations. The disabled are more directly forced to take into account their possibilities of physical functioning and they also need the support of the community in expanding these possibilities. Individuals with disabilities are forced to be more acutely aware of their capabilities, the constraints imposed upon them and ways to overcome them. This ‘lived experience’ is precisely why, in our opinion 1) this group is very well suited as participants in research of social restrictions of capability, and 2) attention should be paid not only to identified changes that have taken place in the life

of the disabled during the crisis, but also to the experience of this target group in expanding and consolidating their capability. Furthermore, it can be assumed that this daily encounter with health-related capability constraints supports the ability to problematise and verbally reflect on it. For capability is easier to describe in theoretical terms than to investigate in practice: what people do and what they are (formulation by Sen) seem to be self-explanatory and most people are not used to reflect on this and talk about it.

Selection of NGO's and participants

For our research we selected and contacted two NGO's. Our "large" cooperation partner is the Latvian people with special needs co-operation organisation "SUSTENTO". It brings together 40 different organisations, whose members are more than 50 000 people with disabilities or chronic illnesses. SUSTENTO is a member organisation of the European Disability Forum (EDF), which brings together more than 80 million people with disabilities in Europe. Our "small" cooperation partner is the organisation "Zvaigzne", an organisation for women with disabilities located in Jelgava, a city not far from Latvia's capital Riga.

Participants were selected following two principles. We asked our "large" cooperation partner – the organisation SUSTENTO – to recommend individuals with disabilities for in-depth interviews who could not only talk about difficulties and problems but who could also share their experience in overcoming these difficulties. Interviews and group discussions were also undertaken with the participants of our direct "small" cooperation partner – the organisation "Zvaigzne". From September 2015 till April 2016 we organised 5 group sessions. These were complemented with individual sessions (in-depth interviews). The total number of participants being involved was 16. From these 16, 10 participants were present during all sessions. Since all participants were members of the organisation "Zvaigzne", the sessions resulted in a productive work together in a friendly atmosphere.

Formulation of interview and data analysis guidelines

As the way people think in their daily life is not as theoretically nuanced as the theoretical framework of the research, some theoretical concepts had to be simplified to bring them closer to daily life. We described individual capability as what is inherent in the individual. In the case of the disabled individuals usually judge about their capability within the frame of their health- incurred constraints, and in response to questions – do you live the life you want to live and what is missing to be able to life that way? – they indicate actual issues related to the accessibility of environment or health improvement. We looked at collective capability by looking into the capacity of organisations. It is described by testimonies of individuals about what they gain by participating in an organisation as well as by the issues addressed by organisations. Human rights are rights guaranteed by the society or the state. In the case of the disabled we pay attention to their "right" to universal human rights, services and preferential treatments that are guaranteed for this group only.

When interviews are structured in the context of the respondent's life story, the focus is on the events in the respondent' life, his/her options and choices, restrictions and ways of overcoming them. The issue of data analysis methodology is about the way how theories of Sen and Nussbaum are related to the stories of respondents. From the theoretical point of view there are three options: 1) theoretical approaches and their classifications dominate, the material of interviews is analysed and classified according to the theoretical setup; 2) theoretical approaches and the material of interviews are treated as equal in value – as discussion or argumentation from the one party and from the other party; 3) the material of interviews is considered to be primary and theoretical approaches are applied in its interpretation. With due respect to the theories of Sen and Nussbaum the third approach prevailed in our research as we assumed that then there would be fewer possibilities of incorrect interpretation and this approach would be easier to understand for our cooperation partners.

3. Living with disability

As an illustration of our data we chose two in-depth interviews with women who had different types of disability, different experience of disability and belonged to a different age groups Anna has a rare disease and restrictions caused by here disability are related to motoric disorders. Rita was given the disability status two years ago when she underwent an oncological operation, constraints caused by her disability are not visible and as such she has encountered a discriminatory attitude.

3.1 Anna's story

(46 years old, a rare disease)

Anna was diagnosed with a rare disease during her teens; however, a clear diagnosis that it was a rare and progressing disease with no cure available was given only when she attained majority. Anna has the status of a disabled person since the age of 18.

'At the time Mother said, wishing me well, that I should apply for the disability status she says – we will have money... But that is horrible! I was only 18, it was crazy, I thought: how can I agree to receive some certificate only to get some money. Well, certainly, she managed to convince me; I agreed and applied for it. Certainly, it is practical, how I perceive all this differently but at the time it seemed to me – that is the end, I am given a life sentence. The disability status for my lifetime!'

Anna has secondary vocational and higher education. She is a marketing specialist. However, as the disease progressed, the university period was particularly difficult, not because of the studies but because classes were held on the 5th or 6th floor in buildings with no elevators. Anna was helped by her closest friends; she had concealed her diseases from other fellow students. After graduation from the university she worked in a shop but as she found it increasingly more difficult to walk, she stopped working. It is not the case that Anna cannot have a salaried job, she just needs special conditions.

'In my case it is the legs, the walking, I can work with my hands, I can write. I only need a special schedule – something like part-time. I need rest, it would be fine if there was some room for recreation, some couch, so that I do not have to be in that sitting position all the time, so that I could lie down for a moment. If I could work for some three hours and then have an hour of rest.'

Anna has experienced also the situation when she was not hired because, in her view, demands set for employers when they employ people with disabilities are too strict and difficult to comply with. That is why employers are reluctant to employ individuals with disabilities. Anna believes that the law should be made more employer-friendly so that they are not afraid to employ the disabled.

'I wanted to have a job but the employers did not want to have an official employment contract. They said that the disabled were much protected. The law provides such protection for these people that the employer cannot get rid of the person even if the person cannot cope with his/her work duties. Very considerable responsibility for this person, an awful lot of documents and reports, in actual fact, employers are not at all interested.'

Anna describes how at the beginning she had resisted the wheelchair and had not wanted to accept the new identity, about her depression and desire to isolate herself from other people, what she had experienced. Her support is her husband who is also her assistant. Anna has been married for 15 years. The fact that her husband is also her assistant, makes her life much easier, her possibilities have increased while restrictions have declined.

'It is a huge relief that we have the assistants now. That the person who provides assistance can also get remuneration because in reality it is a difficult daily job. For example, if my husband went to work, I would have to hire a person who should be paid because these services are expensive. It really helps that the person who helps can be employed; it may not be the husband but somebody else.'

Anna's pension and the assistant's salary her husband receives constitute their family income; it can cover all the necessary expenses and if one is economical with money they can even save enough for brief trips.

'I have my pension. As I have in-service time it is not the minimum pension and the assistant's salary also stays in the family. If we put it together, we can pay for all services – the apartment, electricity, the internet, for food as well. If we do a bit of planning and save we can also travel somewhere. If we do everything in due time, half- a year in advance, we can get the ticket at a good price ...'

Anna's family had not felt the period of crisis in any particular way as they have to be economical all the time. Benefits were not reduced, so they did not experience any shortfall in incomes. They single out the drop in prices as a feature of the crisis period.

'I remember that everybody spoke about that crisis. However, if you are used to shifting for yourself if the rhythm of your life makes you see to it that you have enough for everything, then we did not feel anything. Perhaps it was more experienced by those who had more. Before the crisis we had those blown – up prices, they declined.'

When Anna describes opportunities in her life she emphasises that she has had to fight for them all the time and to protect her rights. She says that many people lack the determination to defend themselves and to demand something for themselves. Bureaucratic obstacles and the number of documents that must be filed prevent people from demanding services that are due to them. Anna recognises that knowledge, tenacity and determination are needed to defend one's rights.

'For example, about those assistants. The person must do a lot prior to that. However, these people are not encouraged, there are attempts to dissuade them, they are told – you will find it difficult, you will have to file documents. I am told this, for example – fine, I gladly do it and file the documents. However, people do not want to do it. To fight for yourself you must be very educated in the given field, you must know what you are entitled to and you have to go and to demand.'

Anna describes various daily situations encountered by a person in a wheelchair and what she has learnt to cope with – to take the public transport, to travel abroad, to participate in summer camps, etc.

'Yes, and I go by that trolleybus! And there are people around! It is important to be among people, that you are part of them. It is important to be together with others, not to sit in your own separate cage.'

Another significant aspect of Anna's story is related to the acceptance of her disease and the development of one's identity. Anna had divided her life and also people into the "healthy people" and "people in wheelchairs", gradually this division was overcome and the difference - "the wheelchair" – does not seem so important any more. However, in Latvia many people are still plagued by stereotypes: the healthy find it difficult to accept the disabled while people with visible disabilities keep away from others, try not to leave their homes. That is why people in wheelchairs are so seldomly seen in the streets and on the public transport.

'In my case, I spent the part of my life as a healthy person without any contact with people who had such problems. In a way I tried to dissociate myself because I did not want to belong to people in wheelchairs. I divided people in my mind into the healthy and those in wheelchairs. I wanted to think that I was not like them but that was self-deception. Some sort of psychological delusion. Later at the camp and in the organisation I met more and more of such people.'

Anna recognises that accessibility for the disabled has improved after Latvia joined the European Union.

'It seems to me the situation improved after we joined the European Union, because we can take over much more from them. Because it is required by regulations and requirements, accessibility improved.'

Family support and adapted environment are the key factors that expand the functioning options of the disabled, subsequently also their capability. Anna recognises that in Riga people who have disability status (group I) have a good life in comparison with other cities and towns in Latvia.

However, the person cannot do anything alone, family support, an adapted environment are also needed ... Yes, by the way, Riga is the best place to live for people with group I disability – we have all public transport free of charge, in addition we have the transport money, care if the pension is not high, if the person is eligible for the status of a poor person, we have compensation for the utilities. Everything is better in Riga ...'

In her future plans Anna has studies in personnel management at a college that are organised by the Social Integration Agency; she has also thought about getting a driver's licence. However, the greatest hope Anna has is that medication will be invented for her disease.

3.2 Rita's story

(52 years old, group I disability since 2014)

Rita started to work as a cook at a kindergarten already during the soviet period. She continued to work at the same place after the restoration of independent statehood when the kindergarten was turned into an orphanage. The salary was not high, work was difficult; however, Rita emphasises also several positive factors that had made her stay in one place of work for such a long time: she could easily reconcile her work and family life, the social guarantees and colleagues with whom she worked.

The work place was close to my home, the work schedule was convenient – I worked for two days and then had two days off. Another good thing was that it was a public institution – the taxes were paid, it was possible to have a sick leave, to have the annual leave [...], double payment if I worked during national holidays. I was used to it, the work team was also good – we lived like a large family.'

Rita married her husband in 1981; the family has three children, now adults. When their daughter went to England, the grandson stayed with the grandparents for some time but then their daughter took her son with her to live in England. One of the children got “in huge problems”, that Rita does not want to discuss in detail and that is why they have been bringing up their granddaughter from the age of 4 months, at present she is 12 years old. Rita and her husband are her official guardians. Rita has a total of four grandchildren, and she is very proud of her grandson who lives in England.

He is an excellent pupil at school, the best in almost the whole school, better than the English children, thus he may have the chance of getting higher education in England free of charge.'

The family lives in a four room apartment. When they both worked and her husband had good earnings, the payment for the family did not seem high; they were well-to-do, bought good clothes and attended cultural events. Now the income has declined, she stresses that the apartment “costs abnormally much – it is at least 250 Euros in winter when the heating is on” (Rita's pension is 299 Euros). The automobile was bought on credit, however, it had gotten into a traffic accident, the insurance did not cover all the repair-related costs and thus now they use an old second hand car.

The material situation of the family deteriorated concurrently with the crisis because the scale of construction shrank. Rita's husband is a professional driver with high qualifications and considerable experience – “he has got all the possible categories, he can drive all vehicles”. At the beginning of the crisis the construction company where her husband worked on the cement haulage vehicle went bankrupt. It was difficult to find a new stable job, her husband mostly had seasonal jobs in summer and “sat at home without any wages” in winter. At present her husband has an official permanent job – since September he has been working in a repair company for the railway but Rita is concerned about the news in the mass media that there might be

staff cuts at the end of the year. Rita explains it by sanctions against Russia that have resulted in the decline of transport flows.

The next blow came when Rita lost her job due to the liquidation of the kindergarten. It was at the end of 2013 and she was in 2014 already in the status of an unemployed. Rita emphasises that employees were made redundant in compliance with the procedure prescribed by law; she received the severance pay in the amount of three monthly wages and registered with the Employment State Agency to receive the unemployment benefit and to look for another job.

'Everybody was laid off "according to the law" – everybody got an advance notice, everybody was given a document to sign a month in advance. The law provided that in the event of liquidation employees with a long in-service time were to receive three monthly salaries.'

Rita started to experience health problems about 4-5 years ago. After she had lost her job, Rita decided to undergo a thorough medical examination and the required tests. The ultrasonographic examination revealed that there was suspicion of a tumour and Rita was referred to a specialist urologist – oncologist in Riga. Before the operation Rita had to undergo a whole range of examinations and tests. It was important to have them as soon as possible which is why most often she had to choose services for payment. Rita recognises that she had not counted how much it had cost her; she says that the three wages that she had got as the severance pay had come in handy. Rita did not have to pay for the operation, only for the time she had spent in hospital – about a month.

'Then we started to look for places where to get the required examinations. Other people helped, I got on the waiting list in several places – wherever I could get first. I paid for consultations. I had magnetic resonance in Riga Hospital No.1; it was the most expensive examination, about 140 Euros.'

Since July 2014, Rita has disability status (group I). She has also been given a long list with benefits and reliefs that individuals with disability status group I are entitled to. Rita has read it but she says that it is not clear, it is difficult to understand, and what is important has not been separated from the irrelevant. In her still short-term experience of disability she has observed and felt that the disabled are not equal in rights, that there is more preferential treatment for people in wheelchairs – parking lots, toilets, airplanes, assistants... Rita's disability is not visible; that is why she has to experience unpleasant moments, for example: she was denied service at the counter intended for the disabled.

'Last time when I went to have the ultrasonographic examination I was harshly reprimanded that I was standing at the counter for the disabled. I said I have Group I disability and got the answer that it was for those in wheelchairs that I had to get into the regular queue.'

Rita has been unpleasantly surprised when she found out that according to the Traffic rules, parking lots for the disabled with the special sign can not be used by any person with disability, that they are intended only for people with motoric disorders and impaired eyesight.

'At the time when I could neither sit nor stand, I as a person with Group I disability could not park my car in the parking lot for the disabled. Can you imagine what these laws are like? It is allowed only for those with motoric disorders or impaired eyesight and it is forbidden for the rest, if it is not respected – then you pay the large fine like everybody else. You must not park there! Nerdist!'

Rita had gone to England together with her friend to visit her daughter's family. Rita needs assistance at the airport and in the airplane as she cannot handle anything heavy and that is why she needed her friend's assistance.

'I read the airport rules; there are many benefits for people in wheelchairs. Very little is meant for people like me. I would need help to pick up the suitcase; I need a person to help me get on the airplane as those who see you off are not allowed to accompany you.'

According to Rita's observations, in England there is a much more benevolent attitude to the disabled. She could see a lot, for example: she had been allowed to use the Ferris wheel free of charge while her companion had paid half the price for the ticket. Rita has already examined the accessibility of several museums in Latvia and her conclusion is that rules are different in each place.

'[In Ventspils] I did not have to pay anything anywhere, we were pleasantly surprised. We do not have many such places – the Rundāle museum gives two free tickets, the Open Air Museum as well. I do not know any other places of the kind. In Tukums free tickets are given to residents of Tukums, In Cēsis one free ticket is given to the disabled person, the accompanying person does not get any free ticket. Everywhere I go – I find it out beforehand because the system is different in each place.'

Rita is surprised that in England she was better treated as a disabled person than in Latvia because here she has to know what she is entitled to and she has to fight to get these reliefs.

'Here, in Latvia, where I have worked for many years, I have three children, bring up the fourth child I am not entitled to anything, I have to fight for everything. In a foreign country I get a discount for nothing, an absolutely different attitude.'

Rita tries to receive all benefits that individuals with Group I disability are entitled to not because of principle but due to necessity. Her disease and the crisis has changed her life to a considerable degree – she has had to restrict herself, she does not attend concerts, does not do her shopping in good shops. Her youngest daughter who lives in Latvia, was a “stay at home” mother with a small child, Rita had to buy food not only for her own family but also for her daughter's family.

Rita does not think that the crisis is over – it is maintained only by newspapers. People around her have suffered from the crisis – they have either lost their jobs or their wages have been cut. Rita's friend lost her job during the crisis; she was evicted together with her two children as she could not pay the rent. She lived together with her son (18 years old) in the shed of Rita's gardening plot, while her daughter lived with Rita. When the boy graduated from school he went to England where Rita's daughter helped him to find a job. At present Rita's friend and her daughter live in a small flat, earn very little, however, her son helps her by sending money from England. Rita has her two sisters and her daughter living in different places in England. Rita believes that her daughter will stay there, her family has settled down there and they will not return to Latvia.

Rita's brief disability experience has strengthened her conviction that everybody lies in Latvia. She does not believe that in Latvia the average salary is about 800 Euros because she does not know a single person who receives such a salary. Likewise she is convinced that what is written about the disabled is one thing while the reality is just the opposite: *“While you read about discounts for the disabled it seems that everything is really fine but when you find yourself in such a situation, you see that nothing is like the description.”*

4. Analysis: women with disability in crisis

What am I able to do and be? This basic question summarises the capability and human rights approach. In its naivety it opens a whole world of feelings, experiences, wishes and potentialities. It opens a window on how people want to organise their lives, their possibility to raise their voice, to build their future. At the same time it accentuates the importance of the societal context. It focuses on the obstacles, the hurdles and the possibilities society creates.

4.1 Impact of the crisis

It is possible to speak about the impact of the crisis from several points of view: as the experience of one's personal crisis or in a wider sense – as the impact of the crisis on the family and the closest relatives and friends. People with disabilities have yet another significant aspect of the crisis – its impact on the accessibility of medical services. However, it should be discussed on a more extensive scale – as the crisis in medicine as persisting insufficient funding for this particular sector has a particularly adverse effect on people with disabilities.

4.1.1 Why some did not notice the crisis

People with disabilities have diverse experiences with the crisis. Part of them has not felt the social-economic crisis in their daily life. This is related to their low income level and the skills that they have developed in the course of their life to make both ends meet, to make do with what they have. The discussion has revealed the case of a young woman who has to survive on 86 Euros per month.

'... A woman with Group II disability since childhood, her child is four years old and attends a kindergarten. She receives a pension of 75 Euros, a child allowance of 11 Euros, a total of 86 Euros. The question is – how to survive? She has to pay 40 Euros per month for a room in the social house, leaving 46 Euros per month for other expenses.'

During the crisis the benefits were not reduced, therefore the income level for all those who do not work did not decline. They did not notice the impact of the crisis because in actual fact, they spend their daily life in a crisis situation. Anna pointed out that she has to live in a certain austerity regime all the time, to follow her expenses and to calculate what she can afford and what she cannot afford.

'I remember that everybody spoke about that crisis. However, if you are used to shifting for yourself if the rhythm of your life makes you see to it that you have enough for everything, then we did not feel anything. Perhaps it was more experienced by those who had more.'

As concerns people with disabilities there are more grounds to speak of an indirect impact of the crisis that has manifested itself in such aspects as the decrease of the total family income and the accessibility of medical services.

4.1.2 Decrease of the family income

During the crisis the family income level rapidly fell if any of the family members lost his/her employment. It was particularly acutely felt by families where the main breadwinner lost a well-paid job. Such a situation was described by one of the participant, whose husband had worked in construction before the crisis struck.

During the crisis he lost his stable employment. Unfortunately, this coincided with the loss of work by Rita herself and her illness. The fall of the family income level necessitated changes in the usual lifestyle and caused difficulties in covering housing costs.

Another aspect of the fall of the income level is the so-called “wage cut” – the reduction of salaries for employees of public institutions as an austerity measure to overcome the crisis. It was described by the mother of Beta (a 16 years old girl with the Down syndrome). When the crisis started her salary was reduced by 100 Euros. She emphasises that that will restrict her possibilities to invest in Beta’s development as she would have to reduce the scale of activities that Beta has been engaged in until now. In order to compensate for this shortfall, Beta’s mother applied to the Social Service of the Riga City Council for the special care benefit and received it. She had applied for this benefit earlier, however, she had never received as, in her own words, she had not been sufficiently persuasive in justifying the need for this benefit.

‘Yes, 100 Euros were cut off at one go and then I said that I would not have anything to invest in her development. I believe that this benefit is not for me as her mother but for her development; if she has it I give it to her.’

Beta’s mother has had to solve various problems in life therefore she does not perceive her wage cut as a big problem, she only points out that the reduced amount has not been “put back”, that a comparatively large amount of money was taken away in one go, while the wage rise is very slow, concurrently with the rise in the minimum salary. Beta’s mother also says that the decrease in incomes was the cause of emigration for many people, yet she has never considered taking such a step.

‘At the beginning when the salary was reduced it was quite tough. Many people panicked because they did not know how to survive and what to do. I have never had any thought of leaving the country. I do not want to start everything from a scratch, nor do I want to leave my relatives.’

During the discussions participants have indicated that the decline in incomes was experienced also by those pensioners who worked during the crisis because the government had taken the decision that working pensioners would receive only 50% of their salaries. Many pensioners due to that decision were forced to leave their jobs.

The decline of the family income level has had its impact on generational solidarity and mutual assistance that is particularly important for people with disabilities. To compensate for the reduced income people had to seek additional sources of income that, in its turn, affected the time devoted to their family members. For example, during the discussion one of the women pointed out that she had been denied assistance, mentioning her children who should help her, however, children are busy at work.

‘For example, wherever I go I am told - you have two children; you are not a single person. Children do not live together with me and they are employed in such jobs that they can come to me only at the end of the week.’

Likewise the families with children have found it more difficult to cover all their expenses during the crisis. One of the participant indicated during the interview that during the crisis she had helped her daughter’s family by buying food for them.

‘Children themselves work in two jobs, it is necessary to be able to send two children to school, to enable one of the children to participate in a dancing group and the other to sing (in a choir). Everything must be paid for. For medication, food and the rest.’

On the whole, people with disabilities can tell more about the impact of the crisis on their family as well as their relatives and friends rather than about their own experience of the crisis and it gives grounds to conclude that the crisis has affected them more indirectly, yet had a more profound impact on them than they themselves perceive.

4.1.3 Crisis in health care

Health and quality of life of people with disabilities are more dependent on the accessibility of health care services than for other groups of the population. Therefore they pay more attention to this particular issue than to the impact of the social economic crisis on the income level and welfare.

4.1.3.1 Queues for services

The national budget pays for certain medical services, however, the demand is higher than the allocated funding and it results in the appearance of queues for services. If the patient wants to receive the service quicker, he can do it for payment at medical institutions. Not all inhabitants can afford it and many people do not understand this system. During the discussion husband who accompanied his wife in a wheelchair told us the following:

I have a cataract in my eye, it is not a very serious operation, just 2-3 minutes but there is a long queue – I have to wait for two years. I am a former Chernobyl liquidator with Group II disability, and I asked if I could not have the operation sooner. No, I was told, I had to wait in the queue like the rest. It is two years; however, if I can pay 700 [Euros] plus something at once, then I can have the operation at once. So it means that – the operation lasts 2-3 minutes, people just go one after another ... Where does the money go? That money goes into the same health cash desk; couldn't they speed up the queue? I do not know what place we live in, if we can sink any deeper! All people over 60 have this disease. But two years!'

Rita also talks about the queues when she was diagnosed with an oncological problem and thus various urgent examinations had to be done. Before her disease Rita hadn't had much experience with the procedure for receiving medical services and she did not know that alongside the queue for services there was another queue – as she called it “the payment queue” where these services could be received sooner, however, for payment.

I was sent also for ultrasonography. It was not possible to get in all places as there was a long waiting list. At the time I did not know that ultrasonography could be received also for payment, for example, for 20 Lats without the long wait in the queue. There was no information anywhere about it ...'

Inhabitants do not have the feeling of security that they will get to the doctor when they will need it. For example, in order to get the necessary examination sooner people with disability have to sign up in several queues. It is possible that other people follow the same practice and it creates an incorrect impression about the number of people on the waiting lists. Participants also mentioned that it was not possible to register for the visit to the doctor over the phone as it was difficult to get a connection with the hospital – the telephone lines were busy, and thus people often travel to Riga only to register for the visit to the doctor.

'After that I had to go to the oncologist to ascertain the progress of my recovery. It is very difficult to get a connection with the Hospital in Riga. I have a relative in Riga; she went herself there and registered me for the visit. Other people from Jelgava go to Riga just to register for the visit. I was lucky because my relative registered me for the visit.'

The described situation applies to all inhabitants and it was recognised also during the discussion.

I want to say that the situation with medicine is not much better for ordinary people (people with no disabilities). They are as at-risk as we are.'

4.1.3.2 Cannot afford services for payment

In Latvia people with disabilities are aware that medical and rehabilitation services for payment are not accessible for them.

It is vividly revealed by the story of a woman participating in the discussion who was an assistant to another woman who had left Latvia 10 years ago and now had returned to undergo rehabilitation after a stroke and she could pay for it.

'A lady returned from England, she had had a stroke, she was paralysed down her left side – the arm, the leg, and the eyesight was also impaired. She had been a resident of my native town and had moved to England 10 years ago. She had had an operation there and a stroke. I agreed [to be her assistant]. We went to Jaunķemeri and stayed there for almost a

month. Yes, we – the disabled and the pensioners – cannot afford it. She had to pay 39 Euros per day for the treatment and 18 [Euros per day] to me. She paid for everything. She really wanted me to go with her to England, I said that I could not go; I had my own home, my family, three children. I wanted to say – it is not possible for us, just make a calculation – we stayed there from December 6 until January 7, she paid for everything 39+18 Euros per day.'

Participants of the group have also emphasised that stricter restrictions have been introduced in hospitals concerning services provided by one or another hospital. The range of services has been shrinking. Thus, if earlier operations or examinations could be performed by the local hospital, now patients have to go to Riga. It causes additional difficulties for the disabled in terms of time and expenses. Participants also admitted that the range and scale of health care services accessible free of charge have also shrunk. There are increasingly more services for payment.

Payment for medication constitutes a significant part of expenses for people with disabilities. Thus reimbursement for medication is a theme that worries people with disabilities of the retirement age. Although the total number of reimbursable medicinal products is high, still in the case of the disease of each specific person it turns out that medicinal products that the said person specifically needs are not reimbursable.

'We – the disabled pensioners – pay for medicinal products, it is not reimbursed and our pensions are below the subsistence minimum, the medicinal products are not reimbursed because we do not work, we do not pay the taxes. I spend 100 Euros per month on medicinal products, I have Group I disability.'

'When we met Parliament members, they just recited statistics, but then I ... told them that life was different from statistics, that those medicinal products were not reimbursed ...'

According to the disabled participating in discussions, in reality the reimbursable medicinal products are quite expensive. Participants of the discussion point out that they must include in these expenses a whole set of payments from their already modest budget: the visit to the family doctor (GP) to receive the prescription for the reimbursable medicinal products, payments at the pharmacy for medication (the state reimburses the cheapest medicinal products for specific diagnoses in the amount of 50%, 75% or 100% of the price), and thus they mostly have to be ready for expenditures. However, the cheapest option may not be suitable for everybody and then the difference must be paid by the patients themselves. At the pharmacies 0.71 Euro cents must be paid for every prescription of reimbursable medicinal products. The disabled are also concerned about the constant growth of prices of medicinal products.

Another problem encountered by people with disabilities is that physicians do not provide sufficient explanation concerning side effects of the prescribed medication and restrictions in the use of the specific medication. Physicians also prescribe medicinal products where the user's leaflets clearly state that the given medication must not be used by patients with the specific diagnosis. This also incurs additional expenses for people with disabilities as they have to buy new medication.

Accessibility of rehabilitation services has also declined (the part that is financed by the state or local governments). Participants of the discussion indicate that social assistance services pay for part of rehabilitation services; however, there is a waiting list for these services, they are accessibly less frequently than before the crisis and a smaller scale of services are paid for.

During interviews and discussions people with disabilities recognise that as patients they have experienced a humiliating attitude in hospitals. Physicians are reluctant to recognise mistakes in treatment or incorrect diagnoses. However, it is very important for the disabled as it influences their treatment options as well as services and benefits they are entitled to.

4.2 Capabilities of women with disabilities

People with disability must take into account certain limited functioning also in respect of their capability; they describe their capability within the frame of this limited functioning. First they have to accept their

disability and the limited capability it causes, and then they have to develop their capability to be able to live as they wish. It is well demonstrated by stories of respondents. The interviewed women differ by the type and length of disability, i.e., how long they have had to live with health disorders: Beta (16 years old) was born with the Down syndrome, her story was told by her mother, Anna (46 years old) was given the disability group at the age of 18 while Rita (52 years old) received her disability group two years ago as a result of an oncological operation.

Anna spoke of her resistance and reluctance to accept the status of disabled and to get into the wheelchair and how she had coped with it (see Anna's story). Rita indicated that prior to getting her disability group she had had an absolutely different notion about the support that was available for the disabled and this opinion changed when she herself became disabled and found out that the reality was much worse than her initial views about it (see Rita's story).

In this chapter we will focus on those social limitations that were discussed by the respondents. It covers a quite extensive range of social factors that prevent respondents from living the life they would like to have. It is important to note that they have experienced, identified and tried to overcome these limitations. Stories related by respondents can be classified in three groups: 1) their own stereotypes and stereotypes prevailing in the society about people with disability; 2) fighting for rights; 3) the feeling of unfairness and inequality.

4.2.1 Their own stereotypes and stereotypes prevailing in the society about people with disability

Beta's mother has spoken about the fact that many parents whose child has a visible disability try to protect the child and keep their child away from the public; however, it is damaging for the child's development, the child is incapable of leading an independent life as the child is used to mother's care.

Well, it is also because of the prejudices in the society. However, we ourselves are also to be blamed for that – we do not take them out into the public. A person is afraid of what he/she does not know ... [...] I was alone with Beta, I would also keep away, nobody could approach me anymore, I would want only to be left alone... I know people who sit at home with their child; the child neither goes anywhere nor does anything. And then the child turns 18 and if anything happens to his/her mother. And thus people appear who have nowhere to go – only the option of a home for the disabled.'

Anna also recognises that life in a closed environment, even though it is safer, still increases the fear of the outside. Often this is also stimulated by the inaccessibility of the environment and difficulties that must be overcome to get outside the familiar environment.

I know from my own experience that this insecurity only grows if you live in such a closed environment. At home everything is familiar while outside everything is unknown. At the beginning I was afraid to go out in the street, it seems that everybody is coming at you.'

The disabled react acutely to cases when they encounter a humiliating attitude toward them in health care. According to participants of the group, they have encountered multiple discrimination - not only on the grounds of disability but also on the grounds of old age. One of the examples that can be mentioned in this respect is the case when the physician refused to perform an operation for a disabled woman who suffered from constant strong pain. The justification of his decision was that there was no use in performing the operation as the patient was already over 60. If she had been 40 years old the operation would have been performed. At present the patient should keep taking painkillers.

It is not that the society pushes people away by its stereotypical attitude and puts obstacles to their integration into the society; in actual fact, these stereotypes exist also in the minds of people with disabilities, they themselves worry about what other people will think of them. That is why it is possible to say that stereotypes constitute one of the factors preventing the improvement of capability.

There was one moment when I thought – I will not get into any wheelchair. For the most part I thought about what other people would think about me. Because I did not see any relief there that it would help me; I saw it with such a thought in my

mind that if I was seen in such a way in the street then people would think – there is some weakling, somebody disabled... It was very much on my mind ...'

Anna also emphasises that categorisation, labelling of people, putting them into certain frames restrict development.

'A disability group for life! Now I also read about achievements in science that studies the brain and I also know that it is very bad that this information is embedded, the person is put in something like a frame. This knowledge that the person knows what frame he/she has been put in, does not allow the person to be what he/she might be if they were not what they are as it tags along... It sits in our head – I am like that, it is difficult for me. It covers everything – layer after layer. And gradually the person becomes the victim of his/her condition.'

A vicious circle develops: like in the case of the disabled in order to be eligible for social support other people also have to acquire a certain status (for example, the status of a poor person) that makes them eligible for this assistance; however, the acquisition of this status places the person in a certain category that provides the grounds for the receipt of social assistance but lowers their self-esteem and does not stimulate capability.

4.2.2 Fighting for rights

People with disability are entitled to state support prescribed by law for the compensation of their limited functioning and maintaining their capability. However, as it has been indicated in the interviews, one must fight for it to receive it.

It is not the case that the person who receives a disability group also receives a clear explanation of his/her options. For example, Rita has had Group I disability since July, 2014. She has also been given a long list with benefits and reliefs that individuals with Group I disability are entitled to. Rita has read it, however, she says that it is not clear, it is difficult to understand, and what is important has not been separated from the irrelevant.

Anna also emphasises that it is important to know the “bureaucratic system” to know what one is eligible for and how to apply for it.

'The bureaucratic system is unwieldy and complicated. When you have got into it in some way then you can also find more.'

Anna has observed that people with disability have to fight for themselves, they must know what they are entitled to and they must insist on it. Many of them are not ready for the fight and that is why they do not receive anything.

'It would be normal if the Social Service told the people – you can receive this, this and this - and then helped them. With us everything is the other way round – the person has to fight for it himself/herself. And if the person does not fight for it, if nobody else fights for the person and tells the person that this and this and this should be done, the person will not get anything.'

The story told by Beta's mother reveals the emergence of an approach that differs from the approach cultivated during the soviet period – to wait patiently when somebody will take the decision and grant the required assistance or service, and to be grateful for anything that you have managed to receive. Parents who have children with special needs try to understand the needs of their child and to protect his/her rights.

'Yes, one generation has become adults, and people know more and demand more. We are the first trailblazers and we show the young people that people can speak about it, they are not afraid to speak about it, they can demand, they can establish the needs of their child, we can identify and demand what we need. The process has started ...'

The advice of Beta's mother could be useful also for people with disability. This is done also by their organisations that follow amendments to laws, defend and explain the rights of the disabled. It is more difficult to fight for yourself individually in the role of a supplicant.

This principle of fighting for yourself by the disabled could be taken over also by other people to stimulate their capability. For example, Beta's mother also mentions options that mothers of such children can use to have some rest and restore their strength.

Mothers also have opportunities. If you take the child at special service place – the child stays there for twenty four hours. At the beginning 45 twenty four days periods were envisaged, now there are 30 days periods per year. You take the child there – you forget all about the child. You can go on an excursion, take care of yourself, you may tidy up the house, you may visit a psychologist – we do not have to pay for these consultations.'

She holds the view that such assistance would be necessary also for those mothers who bring up their children alone, receive the child benefit and make do with the minimum salary. Preferential treatment for the development of children would be required also in such cases.

'She also needs it because a normal child must also develop; she cannot offer the child to study at a music school... in my case the music school was free. There is a speech therapist at school. Will you have a speech therapist or a psychologist in an ordinary school? You will not have them. We can get a psychologist from the social services, free of charge. ... That person is given much less.'

This example reveals the approach in the provision of social assistance – not to allocate the benefit in cash that can be easily spent in a shop on the needs of the moment but to “invest it in development”, to stimulate the progress and development of the child so that the material situation of the family does not become an obstacle to the child's wholesome development.

To be able to live the life they want, the options of individual choice should be expanded for people with disabilities – not by giving something to everybody but by taking more note of the individual needs of each person, for example: Rita said that she had been offered the possibility to attend a training course to become a cook, however, this job would be physically too difficult for her.

'Is it possible to live the life you want? It would be fine if funding was allocated to people with disabilities to enable them to choose the courses themselves and to engage in work at home that they like. Not to press everybody to take the cooking courses.'

4.2.3 Feeling of unfairness and inequality

During the crisis a large part of the population in Latvia developed a strong conviction that the state did not take much care about the welfare of the population, which was also revealed by the data of surveys (Kruks et.al, 2016). This opinion emerged also in the interviews. People with disabilities compare their situation with possibilities of the disabled in other EU member states. The comparison is not in favour of the situation in Latvia. For example, a comparison is made of the accessibility of the environment.

'Yes, we were, for example, in Barcelona. They have descent ramps – a metre, a metre and a half, not special ramps, for nothing at all but they are simply there. They are covered in large tiles, there they have tiles everywhere. All people can use the ramps, also with prams. They are not as narrow as here where the people must go one after another, there they are wide. Here everything is built in such a way that suits somebody and does not suit others, to separate people.'

However, Anna also points out that there are countries where the situation is much worse than in Latvia; she emphasises the EU accession of Latvia has stimulated an improvement in the accessibility of the environment.

'I, for example, spoke to a person who had been to Thailand. There nothing has been adapted. There are such narrow pavements that if there is somebody with a pram coming towards you, then it is already a problem. While in the EU countries there are no problems.'

Rita had visited her daughter in England and she had received discounts in museums and other tourist sites. The feeling of unfairness develops in her because she is treated better in another country than at home. Rita

is surprised that in England she was better treated as a disabled person than in Latvia because here she has to know what she is entitled to and she has to fight to get these reliefs.

Here, in Latvia, where I have worked for many years, I have three children, bring up the fourth child I am not entitled to anything, I have to fight for everything. In a foreign country I get a discount for nothing, an absolutely different attitude.'

Rita is also surprised by the fact that in Latvia there is inequality among the disabled, that it is easier to receive reliefs and advantages for people with visible disability. It is not Rita's case and that is why she has been reprimanded for using advantages intended for the disabled. Rita has experienced it herself that the parking for the disabled are intended only for the disabled with motoric disorders and impaired eyesight. This issue requires more in-depth research as the right to use a parking lot is assigned to a specific vehicle, it is given for a period of ten years, for comparison – people get the disability group only for a period of two years.

The crisis in the medical system has generated uncertainty and tension in people; the disabled compare themselves with people of other vulnerable groups and treat “competitors” – the homeless, refugees and other categories – with suspicion.

We say – we do not have the funds. However, for example, a destitute is picked up in the street, taken to hospital and everything is done for him/her - magnetic resonance as well, all services are free of charge. While we have to get in the queue when we have to go for help, now we have to queue even if you pay.'

The accessibility of medical services is compared to the situation during the soviet period. Participants express a view that in soviet time accessibility for health care was better than now. It should be taken into account that at the time participants of the discussion were much younger and had different health problems and it influences the comparison. Dissatisfaction may have at its basis also communication problems between patients and the staff – failing to understand the way how the system for providing medical services functions now, people want to return back to the time when everything seemed better understandable.

Now this is the free Latvia but I remember the soviet times when you got to hospital and you were also treated there, you could get to the gynaecologist as well as the dentist. Last year I fell down on the street, bruised my legs. I was taken to hospital and when I said that I could not get to the toilet on my own, that the surgeon should come and have a look I got the answer – here you undergo treatment for blood pressure, legs will come later. Isn't it crazy?'

It is the inaccessibility of medical services that consolidates the conviction of many people about their exclusion from the state.

Prices [of medical services] do not correspond to our pensions and salaries. It is not normal, we are doomed to extinction. The state needs neither the disabled nor the pensioners.'

In view of the above limitations optimum ways should be sought to overcome them. One of them is unification for the protection of their interests and for addressing the problems.

4.3 Collective capabilities

As it has been already mentioned above, we look into collective capability on the basis of the capacity of organisations, it is described by stories of the disabled about what they gain from their involvement in the organisation and the description of the issues addressed by organisations.

Anna points out that is important that organisations participate in the legislative process – if the law applies to the disabled then their opinion should be expressed about the law, it should be considered how the law will influence people with disability. As a rule, decision-makers do know the problems as well as the people who face them on daily basis.

The task of the organisation is to inform and to educate for people to know what they should do. We can participate in the process of legislation itself. We tell and inform people. Likewise the SUSTENTO also offers to take a look from the other side – from our point view what the law will look like.'

Another aspect is addressing problems of people with disability by common effort; participants indicated that the organisation helped to purchase various aids.

'... we have organisation which is a member organisation of the "SUSTENTO". We have a very good leader; it is due to him that almost every year we receive cargos with aids. There are long waiting lists for aids. Cooperation partners in Iceland send them to us.'

The local organisation involves the disabled in various activities; remind them of important issues, for example, the disabled can apply for services necessary for the disabled. Projects were also mentioned that had been submitted to a tender which the organisation had also won. For example, they helped people with disabilities to receive psychosocial assistance, equine-assisted therapy, dolphin therapy (for children). Participants of the group recognise that they would not have been able to do it alone without the assistance of the organisation.

The local non-governmental organisation also regularly works with the social assistance service of the local government and informs them about needs of the disable. It also promotes mutual understanding and cooperation.

The organisation is also important in organising leisure activities as it offers possibilities to attend cultural events, to go on excursions in cooperation with the local government.

'Participation in the organisation is essential as you get fed up with sitting at home. And the cultural events are also too expensive. Previously I could afford more, now I have less money.'

Participation in the monthly activities of the organisation "Zvaigzne" also helped us better understand problems and interests of women participating in the organisation and to get involved in the process of addressing these problems.

5. Conclusion

RE-InVEST wants to emphasise the lived experience of vulnerable people, the impact of the crisis (and crisis-related policy reform) on vulnerable groups as well as the impact of growing inequality and social vulnerability on distrust. Our two key hypotheses in this regard are: 1. that growing distrust and indeed resentment among the population may be attributed to (a rejection of) the neoliberal policies employed by national as well as European elites in recent years; 2. That this integrated diagnosis can build on the idea of the erosion of/disinvestment in (individual and collective) capabilities and basic social rights in the EU. This means that experiences of insecurity, poverty and social degradation need to be re-analysed from those perspectives.

In this report we've translate the two hypotheses into the questions about the kind of life respondents would like to live and obstacles to do so. This basic question summarises the capability and human rights approach. If we discuss capability in the meaning used by A. Sen as the possibilities of functioning that correspond to the individual's imagination, then it must be recognised that the disabled have certain health-related limited functioning. Capability of the disabled can be discussed only within the frame of this limitations. The disabled are more directly forced to take into account their possibilities of physical functioning and they also need the support of the community in expanding these possibilities. Individuals with disabilities are forced to be more acutely aware of their capability and to try to expand it than other social groups. We tried to emphasise the experience of this particular group in overcoming constraints of their capability. Therefore, in the course of the research we examined not only the impact of the crisis but also the experience gained in overcoming restrictions.

The first hypothesis was that retrenchment of the state, in conjunction with rising inequality and income insecurity, may have undermined trust, especially among the vulnerable people.

Our analysis confirms the hypothesis of a loss of trust. It was promoted by the government's crisis management strategy, which called for very strict austerity measures that in turn lead to significant increase in depth of poverty and social exclusion. The participants feel that inequality during the crisis has increased: between the political elite and ordinary people, between the rich and the poor, between private and public patients (including people with disabilities) in the health care system. The crisis and crisis-related policies implemented by government have weakened social cohesion and trust in political institutions. The research data revealed that the level of trust in political actors and institutions is very low among the participants.

People with disabilities are paying more attention to the crisis in health care and issues of accessibility of medical services than to the socio-economic impact of the crisis, as their incomes were not high even before the crisis. They have always been living in an austerity mode, balancing on the edge of poverty.

The second hypothesis explores the idea of the erosion of (or disinvestment in) social rights and capabilities in the EU and the impact on vulnerability. Our analysis confirms the erosion of social rights. Research data reveals significant decline in the very important needs and rights of people with disabilities (health care, housing, incomes, work and equality).

Their rights are not granted, they have to fight for each right. Experience of people with disabilities shows that it is essential to fight for their rights and also to know them, otherwise they are not implemented in Latvia situation.

The support of the society in the form of social assistance is more focused on ensuring existence (survival) rather than promotion of capability. However, it is important to "invest in development". i.e., benefits

must be linked to possibilities of education and further development. Assistance should be more individualised, linked to the interests and needs of every person; benefit recipients should be more involved in the process of making decisions what they need and how to use the services and benefits.

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Social disinvestment and vulnerable groups in Europe in the aftermath of the financial crisis

The case of young people in Portugal

Graça Costa

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Portugal

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Executive summary

This report is prepared in the framework of the Europe H2020 project ‘Rebuilding an inclusive, value based Europe of solidarity and trust through social investments’ (RE-InVEST). The project aims to evaluate the social investment strategy of the European Commission implemented in 2013 in response to the social damage of the financial crisis in 2008. The RE-InVEST consortium aims to assess the social damage of the crisis drawing from human rights and capability based approaches and focuses on those vulnerable groups mostly affected by the crisis in the 12 countries (and 13 regions) (UK (=EN+SC), IE, PT, NL, RO, LV, IT, BE, DE, AT, CH) covered by the study. The analyses are carried out by the local partners, who consist of NGOs and/or research institutions.

Portugal has been particularly hard hit by the economic crisis. The high unemployment, low employment, rising of poverty and social exclusion, and declining household incomes resulted in a lack of confidence concerning to occupation safety and future economic growth. Social expenditure played a strong role in stabilising household incomes; nonetheless it was reduced due to the sovereign debt crisis. As new entrants to labour market, young people face serious difficulties to get a job. This is mostly exacerbated when they do not receive any kind of social protection and moreover are obliged to accept job offers.

The focus of the research on young unemployed is due to the fact of the unemployment being the major problem among young people under 25 years old. This group has been so severely hit by the economic crisis and so it is a great concern and a top priority¹ among EU Member States. As other countries, Portugal needs to reduce youth unemployment. According to the Monthly Employment and Unemployment Estimates (Instituto Nacional de Estatística – INE (National Statistical Institute) March 2015, the unemployment rate among young people stood at 35.0%² (unemployment of 25-64 year-olds in Portugal is 14.5% compared to the OECD average of 7.5%).

This report examines how young unemployed (18 to 30 years) well-being has been affected by the economic crisis in Portugal. Their difficulties and social constraints in getting a decent job undermine their trust in planning their future and make a smooth transition to adulthood. Young people in precarious employment face higher job insecurity and uncertainty about the future³, which are relevant negative factors affecting the possibility to plan their life and to establish their goals according to reasonable expectations about upcoming opportunities.

The RE-InVEST consortium has jointly developed the PAHRCA – a methodology that combines principles of Participatory Action research with Human Rights and Capability Approaches. This qualitative, participatory research does not produce representative results but rather aims to deepen the understanding of economic, social, cultural and political impacts of the crisis on the lives of vulnerable people and give them a voice.

The biographies of B. and Z. draw a picture of how the crisis has been affecting individual’s life stories. B illustrated her resilience to cope with her father’s emigration to Angola and the effort to not give up her studies during the economic crisis, taking care of her brothers and trying to find a decent job and not emigrating herself after finishing her nursing degree:

1 In the 2015 Annual Growth Survey, the Commission called for determined action to improve the labour market situation of young people, with the Youth Guarantee representing an ambitious way to combine different instruments to address youth unemployment effectively. Thematic fiche youth unemployment European semester (European Commission, 2015).

2 http://observatorio-lisboa.eapn.pt/ficheiro/Destaque-INE_Emprego-e-Desemprego-Março2015.pdf
<http://www.eapn.eu/images/stories/docs/EAPN-position-papers-and-reports/2014-EAPN-youth-poverty-position-paper.pdf>, p.18.

3 EAPN (2013): p. 20.

I already had job proposals from Norway and I said no! I already had proposals from Belgium, from Germany, from the UK, thousands of them...But it is difficult...I'm not a person who gives up! ...Here the jobs require young people to have lots of experience. Because of this I feel frustrated...So emigration is becoming more and more a strong option.'

Z tells the story of precarious jobs and training in a household very challenging for those who face unemployment because of the crisis:

from June 2011 to December 2015, I was employed one year and eleven months and was unemployed during two years and five months.

Preface

First of all we would like to express our gratitude to the young unemployed people who actively participated in RE-InVEST expressing their feelings, their opinions and experiences associated with unemployment during the economic crisis and their recommendations to national and European politicians and institutions. Without their participation it would not have been possible to write this report. We would like also to thank the *Associação Ecos Urbanos* for helping us to identify the young unemployed people. It is a grassroots' social organisation engaged in the fight against poverty and social exclusion particularly affecting young people. Last but not least we would also like to express our appreciation to the European Commission for financing this project.

Contents

List of figures	11
Introduction	13
1. National context	15
1.1 The impact of the economic crisis viewed by Portuguese youth	17
1.2 Material well-being and the subjective well-being of Portuguese citizens	18
2. Theoretical and methodological approach	19
3. Two selected biographies	23
3.1 First biography	23
3.2 Second biography	24
4. Analysis	26
4.1 The social consequences of the crisis on human rights of young unemployed	26
4.1.1 Education level and labour market opportunities	26
4.1.2 Quality jobs and decent work	28
4.1.3 Social Protection	30
4.1.4 Health status of participants and medical care provision	31
4.1.5 Housing conditions of participants	32
4.2 The social consequences of the crisis on (dis)trust of young unemployed	33
4.2.1 The relation with neighbourhood	33
4.2.2 The relation with family	33
4.2.3 The relation with social organisations and public services	33
4.2.4 Employment public service	33
4.2.5 Trust in politicians and political institutions	34
4.2.6 Debate about refugees rights	35
4.2.7 The young unemployed perspective about human rights	35
5. Conclusion	37
Bibliography	50

List of figures

Figure 2.1	Resources, conversion factors, capability set and achieved functionings	20
Figure 2.2	The merging of knowledge	21

Introduction

The ‘Europe 2020’ strategy is based on a vision of smart, sustainable and inclusive growth, through high levels of employment, productivity and social cohesion. Economic growth is a way of improving life standards but needs to be sustainable by reducing social inequalities and ensure that the benefits are fairly distributed across society. It aims to reduce the number of people in or at risk of poverty and social exclusion in the EU by at least 20 million and increase 75% the employment rate during the 10 years. Nonetheless, the EU is getting off-track in relation to the social inclusion target where 1 in 4 people face poverty and social exclusion (122 million) and increasing inequality between and within Member States. Unemployment and poverty increased due to the economic crisis and the social climate worsened by the cuts in social protection mainly in the southern countries. In 2013, the Commission launched a major endeavour to rebalance economic and social progress: the Social Investment Package (SIP). In the framework of Europe 2020, Portugal had aimed to reach 71% of employment rate in the active population between 20 and 64 years old in 2014 and to reach 75% in 2020. This meant a reduction of 50,000 people in 2014 and a reduction of 200,000 by 2020. The 2014 goals were not reached (the employment rate was 50.6%, and the poverty rate 26.7% after social transferences).

RE-InVEST aims to fill this gap by evaluating the SIP from a human rights and capability approach. The first stage is a diagnosis of the social damage of the crisis in terms of (erosion of) human rights, social (dis) investment, loss of (collective) capabilities, and loss of trust. In order to have a broad and representative scope of the social damage of the crisis, 12 countries are involved (13 regions) in collecting testimonies or ‘narratives of risk’ of people most affected by the crisis, illustrating how it has impacted on their basic human/social rights and how some anti-crisis policies, have reinforced these mechanisms. The current national report aims to analyse the impact of the crisis on youth unemployment (people aged 18 to 30 years old) in Portugal assuming the two project research questions:

1. the crisis has negative social consequences which undermined the human rights of vulnerable groups;
2. the negative social consequences leads to a growing distrust and loss of solidarity.

The priority issues linked with the first hypothesis that came out from young unemployed were dimensions such as: education (Section 4.1.1), employment (Section 4.1.2), social protection (Section 4.1.3); health (Section 4.1.4), and housing (Section 4.1.5). In what concerns to (dis)trust young unemployed people emphasised this subject towards neighbours (Section 4.2.1) and family (Section 4.2.2), social organisations (Section 4.2.3), public services like social security (Section 4.2.4) and public employment service (Section 4.2.4), political institutions (Section 4.2.5) their opinion about refugees (4.2.6) and the meaning of Human Rights (4.2.7). The qualitative data was gathered through a participatory research process which stresses the partnership approach and exchange of knowledge among all stakeholders involved in the project. The project reflects the experience of the most vulnerable people and expresses the personal and societal consequences of unemployment. The testimonies of the unemployed youth reflect the impact of the austerity measures on their daily lives from many points of view: how unemployment affects psychological factors (self confidence and self-esteem; depression and lack of motivation; plans for the future to have their own family as well as leaving their parents’ house), and social factors (to be out of labour market and being forced

to take low-paid jobs, to voluntary ‘downgrade’ their skills when looking and applying for a job, and to decrease the investment in the curriculum development).

This report about the social damage of the crisis experienced by young unemployed people in Portugal is structured in five sections. After the introduction, section one explores the national context and gives a picture of the main social indicators and on how austerity measures undermine individual and collective capabilities and social rights of the most vulnerable and worsen their labour market chances, particularly among young unemployed people. The second section is dedicated to the theoretical framework of the Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach (PAHRCA) under RE-InVEST in a brief way. The third section provides details of the two testimonies of unemployed youth that show how economic crisis impacted on their lives. Section four presents a detailed analysis of the testimonies based on their memories regarding education, employment, health, social protection, level of trust in politicians, social organisations, and family. Finally the fifth section presents the conclusions on how young people have been struggling with the economic crisis from the human rights perspective, capabilities and trust; and draws out some recommendations in relation to unemployed people and labour market policies.

1. National context

Between May 2011 and June 2014 Portugal was submitted to an economic adjustment programme and European assistance. The Portuguese government prioritised harsh austerity measures which have resulted in a deterioration of the labour market and the social situation in the name of fiscal consolidation.⁴ Austerity measures undermined social investment, with health reducing costs by more than 500 million euro per year and education cuts of 175 million per year.⁵ Between October 2010 and August 2014 almost 592,000 beneficiaries lost their children's social benefits. The share of people who do not receive income support is particularly high, more than 40% of people living in families with no (or almost no) work and the poor receive only up to 10% of their income as social transfers. In addition, the austerity measures undermined the responsiveness of public service provision by cutting in social protection which led to a further increase of poverty and social exclusion which deeply depended on social transferences.

Furthermore, Portugal is the 9th most unequal country among the OECD countries.⁶ The risk of poverty increased from 17.9% in 2008 to 19.5% in 2013, the highest since 2004 (27.4% of the total Portuguese population) and the poverty rate among the unemployed has reached around 40% in 2013, which amounts to double the total of the general population. The number of working poor increased around 10%. The increase of inequality in labour income was strongly influenced by the effects of unemployment. The impact of the austerity measures in fundamental rights during 2013 and 2014 was maintained or strengthened: reduction of 2% in the number of public sector workers; dismissal of workers with fixed-term contracts, reduction of compensation for overtime; increase in working hours of public employees from 35 to 40 hours a week, without additional compensation; increase of the minimum age for retirement (the normal age of entitlement to an old-age pension in 2014 and in 2015, being now 66 years); increase of the workers' contribution to the special public employees 'health insurance schemes', to 3.5%; new increase of the maximum VAT rate to 23.25% and increase of the workers' contribution to social security to 11.2%. The measures and impact on the right to work covered the main problematic areas: pay-cuts and wage setting; dismissal rules and destruction of jobs; flexible working time arrangements (bank of hours).

During the economic crisis the high cuts in the social benefits of households and the high rates of unemployment contributed mostly to reproduce the cycle of poverty in a very serious manner. The access and eligibility criteria to social benefits were endorsed and consequently the number of beneficiaries was reduced as well as the amounts received, as we can see from the latest study of EAPN Portugal.⁷ Social Insertion Income - Rendimento Social de Inserção (RSI) beneficiaries were reduced with more than 150,000 cases between 2010 and 2013 (in 2010 there were 525,723 beneficiaries and in 2013 were 360,235 beneficiaries). The average amount of benefit provided per beneficiary fell to 178.15€ in 2013 from about 189.52€ in 2010. The renewal of this provision must be requested by the beneficiaries, which in cases of forgetfulness or lack of knowledge, the recipients are automatically excluded from the measure. At the end of 2015, the number of

4 At the end of 2015, Portugal had the third highest public debt compared to GDP (128, 9%).

5 Children with special needs or disabilities have been particularly affected and the number of dropouts has increased. 38% (December 2013 to December 2014) lost social support. in OECD, 2014, Education Policy Outlook Portugal.

6 OECD, 2015, In It Together: Why Less Inequality Benefits All, OECD Publishing Paris.

7 EAPN Portugal study (2015) Social and institutional impact of economic and financial crisis in third sector organisations. For detail information about social benefits consult <http://www.seg-social.pt>

households who received the social insertion income was 134,161, with 295,668 beneficiaries. The average amount received by a beneficiary was 94.84€ and by a household was 213.89€.

Regarding the unemployment benefit, between 2010 and 2013, the number of unemployed increased from 424,966 to 562,998 and the amount of the benefit was reduced from 543.38€ to 534.83€. The access rules were changed in 2012;⁸ namely, a reduction in the period from 450 to 360 days and in the maximum amount of pay of €1,048 included no matter what the worker's salary was at the point of dismissal. Furthermore, a 10% cut in the amount of benefits was introduced, after six months of receiving the unemployment benefit.

Moreover, in the previous EAPN Portugal research about the social and institutional impact of the economic and financial crisis in Third Sector organisations, it is underlined that those organisations reported a significant increase of social vulnerability: individuals and families searching for social support; incidence of hunger cases among school children, householders with difficulties to pay support services to children and the elderly; increase of homelessness searching for support services and the increase of indebted households. At the end of 2011, the government introduced the Social Emergency Programme (Programa Social de Emergência),⁹ as a social response to reduce the social impact of the crisis through the provision of the 942 'social canteens' (up until that moment there were only 62) managed by social organisations to guarantee meals to the most vulnerable. EUR 50 million was provided for their creation. This measure came up at the same time as the much tighter control was implemented on access to social benefits such as the Social Insertion Income (RSI), the family allowance and the solidarity supplement for the elderly. As described above, this tightening of control led to a substantial fall of benefits paid out. The criticisms to the Social Emergency Programme were mainly that it should be an emergency measure, while it prevails as an assistance measure provided by social organisations.

Most indicators of the labour market and the social situation deteriorated with the unemployment rate reaching 16.7%, in 2013. Since then, it has been decreasing to 12.2% at the end of 2015.¹⁰ According to the Country Report Portugal 2016,¹¹ although it has been a recovery, the decrease of the active population due to the demographic and emigration trends explains also this fall. In 2014, the active population decreased 1, 2% (64,200 people) from the previous quarter (3rd lowest country among 28 Member States). Emigration flows reached 3.5% of approximately 10 million people during 2011 to 2013 (100,000 in 2011, 120,000 in 2012 and 128,000 in 2013). Emigration rates remained steady in 2014. Similar numbers can only be found in the 1960s, during the dictatorship and the colonial war. The qualified young people who emigrate due to the lack of jobs produced imbalances at the demographic level as well as in the contributions for social protection systems.

Moreover, in 2014 the ageing index was 141 elderly for 100 young people (Portugal has the 5th highest index among 28 Member States). The relative increase in ageing population associated with the working age population decrease brings important effects such as the increase of retirement age and increase of pensions' expenditures. In addition, the Portuguese birth rate is one of lowest in OECD countries.

As described in the Introduction the unemployment rate came to historical figures as well as youth unemployment which reached values close to 40% in 2013. In the last quarter of 2015, it amounted to 34.8%.¹² Regarding those under 25 years old, neither in employment, neither education, nor training (NEET) has also increased to levels around 14% of their age group (2013) having

8 Decree-Law n° 64/2012 of March (Decreto-Lei n° 64/2012, de 15 de Março)
http://www.dgap.gov.pt/upload/Legis/2012_dl_64_15_03.pdf

9 http://www.mercadosocialarendamento.msss.pt/programa_emergencia_social.jsp

10 According to INE data for the 4th quarter 2015

https://www.ine.pt/xportal/xmain?xpid=INE&xpgid=ine_indicadores&contecto=pi&indOcorrCod=0005599&selTab=tab0

11 http://ec.europa.eu/europe2020/pdf/csr2016/cr2016_portugal_en.pdf

12 http://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---dgreports/---dcomm/---publ/documents/publication/wcms_412015.pdf

decreased to 12.3% in 2014. Unemployment is one of the biggest problems among young people under 25 years old. The crisis brought a new situation in which educated and skilled middle-class workers, mainly young, were affected by unemployment. This has created new patterns of poverty and inequality with special focus towards households where both parents became unemployed.

The Portuguese labour market is highly segmented due to a high number of temporary contracts (19% of total employees). Furthermore, most of the jobs created are based on temporary contracts. Between 2008 and 2012 the numbers increased for young people (15–24 years old) in the labour market on part-time jobs (10.4% and 20.1%), involuntary part-time jobs (42.2%; 45.5%) and in temporary employment (54.2% 56.5%)¹³.

The labour market reflects the deterioration in the working conditions that occurred in the last years, particularly for the young entrants regarding precarious forms of integration in the labour market and difficulties in achieving a stable job. The lower the age, the worse the working conditions are. And younger women are more affected by precariousness, e.g. part-time work and temporary contracts, than younger men. Differences by economic sector and company size are noticeable, with the services sector offering worse working conditions and the smaller companies offering more permanent jobs for young employees. In general, the working conditions of young entrants in the labour market have deteriorated in Portugal over the last five years, as a result of the effects of the crisis.¹⁴ Moreover, high levels of job destruction (more than 500,000 jobs were destroyed, between 2008 and 2013) have to be associated with the difficulty of young workers to enter the labour market.

1.1 The impact of the economic crisis viewed by Portuguese youth

Youth unemployment increased the average age of young people leaving the parental household in Portugal. In 2013 the average age was 29 years old (male (30.0) and female (28.0)) – while in the EU it was 26.1 years old (male (27.2) and female (25.0)).¹⁵

Living at home longer reflects the difficulty to get a job and live an independent life, as a source of fulfilment and professional identity which allows the transition to adulthood. According to the European Youth in 2016 report,¹⁶ 86% of Portuguese young people feel excluded due to the crisis. This is the second highest share in the EU 28 (average 57%) following Greece where the share with 93% is highest. Another relevant feature is the ‘enforced mobility’, as 41% of young people feel compelled to leave Portugal because of the crisis. With regard to the perception on the adequacy of the education system and the labour market demand, 61% of young people considered training, school and university education well adapted to the current working world (EU28 average 59%). The same report states that Portuguese young people’s participation in society is less than half of the young people surveyed¹⁷ that had voted in the previous three years (shares within the range of 44% to 49%). Broadly speaking, this may be linked with the loss of trust in the political system which is stated by the participants.

13 Eurofound, 2013, Working conditions of young entrants to the labour market p. 30

14 (<http://www.eurofound.europa.eu/observatories/eurwork/comparative-information/national-contributions/portugal/portugal-working-conditions-of-young-entrants-to-the-labour-market>) Published on: 08 January 2014

15 Being young in Europe Today, 2015, Eurostat, Children and young people in family and society, p. 44-47.

16 <http://www.europarl.europa.eu/atyourservice/en/20160504PVL00110/European-youth-in-2016>

17 Being young in Europe Today, 2015, Eurostat, page 62 (Flash Eurobarometer 375, titled ‘European youth: participation in democratic life’, which was conducted in 2013).

1.2 Material well-being and the subjective well-being of Portuguese citizens

The OECD report *How's Life in Portugal 2015*¹⁸ gives a picture of the *material well-being* and the *subjective well-being* of Portuguese citizens which seems in line with the social and economic description in the previous sections. Life satisfaction in Portugal is the second lowest in the OECD. Trust in other people lies below the European OECD average (5.3 while the European OECD average stands at 5.8).

The material well-being, since 2009, average Portuguese household disposable income fell notably and this led to a significant reduction (by 8.9%) in the poverty threshold¹⁹ which reflects the difficult economic conditions currently being faced. According to the Observatory of Education and Training Policies (Observatório de Políticas de Educação e de Formação) in 2014, the biggest problem of deprivation of families was the financial level (43.3% in food and essential goods), followed by leisure (29.4% without access to cultural activities and or sports), the social sector (26.4% in the frame, comfort - there are many children living alone with also small older brothers) and Education 25.8%).²⁰

Portugal has seen improvements in housing conditions, with the share of people living in dwellings with basic sanitation increasing. However, only 46.1% of Portuguese adults perceive their health as good or very good.²¹ In terms of educational attainment, between 2009 and 2013 the share of the adult working-age population with at least an upper secondary education increased by 10.2 percentage points to 40%. However, this is still far below the OECD average of 77.2%. Moreover, 55% of the adult population between 25-64 years old did not finished the secondary education level and 45% of the work force has few or no digital skills. 34.5% of young people with 15 years old repeated a school year (13% OCED average) according with data from PISA²² 2012. Graduate people 25-64 years old are still a low proportion (29th place within the 34 countries of OCDE). High level of drop rates and lower qualifications increases the youth unemployment and worsens the NEET rate.

To sum up, the Portuguese social and economic crisis context has translated into hard life conditions to the Portuguese and especially for the young people. Young unemployed people will speak by their own in the following pages on how the crisis has affected their lives.

18 <https://www.oecd.org/portugal/Better%20Life%20Initiative%20country%20note%20Portugal.pdf>

19 <http://www.eapn.pt/o-que-e-a-pobreza>: The European Union set up a calculation formula to define who was or not in poverty risk. The poverty line is defined as '60% of the median income per equivalent adult' (INE). Thus, it would be in poverty risk an adult who in 2014 had an income below 422 euros per month.

20 The State of Education in a State operated upon Portugal 2014 (O Estado da Educação num Estado Intervencionado Portugal 2014) Observatory of Education and Training Policies (Observatório de Políticas de educação e de Formação) p.11

21 http://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/10665/170250/1/9789240694439_eng.pdf?ua=1&ua=1 World Health Statistics, 2015: Obesity rates among adults, self-reported (%): 15.4 in 2006 and 12.8 in 1999; Mortality from cardiovascular diseases (age-standardised rates per 100 000 pop.) 242.0 in 2012 and 424.9 in 2000; Mortality from cancer (age-standardised rates per 100 000 pop.) 200.7 in 2012 and 211.5 in 2000; Crude death rates for children (0–14 years old), (number of deaths per 100 000 children)2002 and 2012 Portugal (- 46 %) and the Crude death rates for young people (15–29 years old) (number of deaths per 100 000 young people) were seen in Portugal (- 53 %), Percent reduction in mortality rate of tuberculosis (among HIV negative people) a, 1990-2013, 58%

22 Programme for International Student Assessment

2. Theoretical and methodological approach

RE-InVEST aims to provide a philosophical, institutional and empirical foundation on the Social Investment Package, in order to enhance a more solidary, inclusive and trustful Europe. To reach this goal the theoretical and methodological approach proposed is through the intersection of capability and human rights approaches based on participatory action research.

The *Capability Approach* (CA) developed by Amartya Sen (1999) brought a new framework towards economic development by focusing his analysis on what people are able to be (or to do) to achieve their well-being or quality of life beyond income factors. So the core issue for Sen is not only what individuals choose, but the choices that they would make if they had the abilities/freedom to lead their lives the way they want to. Examples of capabilities can be: to be able to hold a decent job and not any job but a decent job; to be able to have leisure activities; to learn valuable things and be able to have education and be free of any kind of violence. So, quality of life does not depend only on income. Income is one of many variables, like trust in democracy, the political institutions in civil society, in the neighbourhood and in the household. In addition, the CA has an intrinsic value quite different from the practical approach more concerned with the economic growth, GDP, which potentially generates decent jobs. Speaking about human dignity and about what people consider they need and should have is very important to diagnosis social impacts on vulnerable people: ‘What am I able to do and be?’

The *Capability Approach* as developed by Sen (1999) and Nussbaum (2011) defines the person’s wellbeing in terms of beings and doings (achievements/functionings) a person achieves and her/his capability to choose among different combinations of such functionings. Functionings may be considered the basic needs as having shelter, health care, education or more complex features such as self-respect and well-being. To live a life that persons want to lead and have reason to value, the resources and conversion factors are central components (Figure 2.1.) In other words, the perception that the individual has of the quality of life depends not only on his personality or features like age or gender, but also on the resources available and the cultural values of the society where he/she is living in.

So, resources can be defined as material conditions such as income, goods and services, which have an instrumental value and are the means needed to reach functionings. Conversion factors help to convert resources into doing and wellbeing. There are a range of conversion factors: personal, social and environmental that can constrain or enable people’s capabilities. Personal conversion factors are such as skills and body features; social conversion factors are like social norms, laws, customs and traditions and social institutions and policies; finally environmental conversion factors are such as climate and geography. The achieved functionings are the way people live to be free to be able to choose things to value in life e.g. to be able to choose a decent job.

Figure 2.1 Resources, conversion factors, capability set and achieved functionings

Capabilities and human rights are directly linked by describing the core values of well-being and a good life. Besides, human rights have been developed strongly in the past century. In the 20th century key international human rights instruments were established, namely: the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) adopted by the United Nations in 1948 which states in Article 25 that 'Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and family, including food, clothing, housing and medical care and the necessary social services, and the right to security in the event of unemployment, sickness, disability, widowhood, old age or other lack of live hood in circumstances beyond his control'. In the international and national legal framework of UDHR, the states are obliged to ensure the effective exercise of the right to protection against poverty and social exclusion. As it is pointed out in the Council of Europe Revised European Social Charter, Article 30, the States must take measures 'to promote the effective access of persons who live or risk living in a situation of social exclusion or poverty, as well as their families, to, in particular, employment, housing, training, education, culture and social and medical assistance'.

Human rights are inalienable rights and fundamental entitlements by a human being as prepolitical status prior membership to a state. The Human Rights approach includes a universal and holistic perspective of the human being in terms of civil and political rights and the social and economic rights. They set up the standard of living conditions and the deprivation of needs can be as a denial of rights. In this context the Human rights discourse can emancipate and transform through collective action and participation of who is excluded by their own rights.

The Merging of Knowledge (MOK) approach involves a collective of mixed groups of researchers the co-construction of knowledge about poverty and social exclusion by discussion and reflection: people who experience poverty and social exclusion in first hand to talk about their needs. To bring a more complete and broader knowledge it is crucial to have their participation and their own voice as co-constructors of Knowledge. Academics and scholars should assume the role to them to 'Explain to us rather, Help us to think'. This process helps to raise awareness about their situation of rights denial and implies to the solution of the problem and policy recommendations. The knowledge of social workers who work with vulnerable people is a core part of the MOK perspective (figure 2).

Figure 2.2 The merging of knowledge

RE-InVEST research approach is a Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach (PAHRCA) developed in seven steps (Toolkit, 44-45):

1. identify and meet partner NGO/gatekeeper,;
2. preliminary 'meet ups' (for trust building if necessary);
3. first meeting with participants – trust building;
4. developmental: implement developmental human rights & capability approach;
5. inquiry/data gathering;
6. identifying patterns (key issues and themes of concern to the group) and;
7. undertake action/outcome using one or a combination of approaches.

According to the Portuguese context (see Section 1) we decided to work with ten young unemployed people (aged 18 and 29; 2 males and 8 females), from an urban area: S. João da Madeira, Aveiro district (see Appendix 1 for the profile participant group description). The 'Youth Association of Urban Echoes' (Associação de Jovens Ecos Urbanos) <http://www.ecosurbanos.pt/organizacao/> was the gatekeeper (step 1). It is a grassroots organisation which works with young people in poverty and social exclusion and is a member of EAPN Portugal. This status made the process quicker by explaining the aims of the project and the role of the NGO and the selection of the vulnerable group (step 2).

In November of 2015 three meetings were held at Ecos Urbanos office (19, 24 and 26 November) in order to have the group formed (step 3). In the first meeting only three females attended, in the second meeting 7 young people participated and the third meeting was attended by 10 persons. There were three brief meetings with those responsible at the NGO to discuss and to find solutions to overcome the low attendance, namely to pay the lunch and offer a coffee-break per meeting to each person; these offers were based on having the vulnerable situation in mind that we were dealing with. During the first meeting the aim of the project was presented, after the participants had introduced themselves. Furthermore, the principles of participation were discussed, namely the guarantee of confidentiality and anonymity during all the research stages. Participants filled in an applicant form which stated the confidentiality of data collected. Participants also consented to record the sessions. Last, but not least, as a first approach to freely debated youth unemployment, each of the participants made a drawing about the impacts of unemployment (feelings, attitudes, consequences) on their lives, and shared its meanings. (see Appendix 2).

The next meeting took place with 7 new persons (who met during lunch time which created a good atmosphere) to whom we briefly explained the aims of the project. In the meeting we started with a dynamic introduction of the participants (ice-break) each saying his/her name and one characteristic they like most to create trust. Then we proceeded with the drawing methodology (Appendix 2).

The last meeting in November allowed for the ten new participants to meet during lunchtime where we informally spoke about RE-InVEST, before the ice-break activity took place. Afterwards each participant showed his or her drawing and explained the meaning of it. Furthermore, the meanings were discussed and participants reflected on those features and assessed the way how the meeting went.

'Freehand Drawing' enabled participants to express visually their present constraints and future challenges about being unemployed through image interpretation and discussion, and encouraged a reflexive engagement to generate alternative perspectives.

There were more four group meetings with ten participants that took place in November, December 2015 and January 2016 with the aim to implement the developmental human rights and capability approach (step 4), inquiry/data gathering (step 5).

After discussing, reflecting and sharing feelings, attitudes and the impacts of unemployment in their well-being, the group put a great emphasis on debating about solutions for unemployment rather than focusing on the difficulties faced by the lack of work. Accordingly, a brainstorm about Rights, Trust and future plans was carried out. To deepen the social diagnosis, two focus groups were created on the living conditions and how they affect their quality of life. The group was subdivided according to the education level.

The focus group about income and living conditions was inspired on 'The Survey on Income and Living Conditions, conducted in 2015 over the previous year's income, information of INE, 18 December 2015

(https://www.ine.pt/xportal/xmain?xpid=INE&xpgid=ine_destaques&DESTAQUESdest_boui=224739104&DESTAQUESmodo=2).

With respect to data gathering, we use the toolkit (page 62) 'snake' timetable as a way of undertaking personal testimonies, by biographical memory as well as a collective exercise concerning the austerity measures and the social and economic indicators implemented in Portugal during the last ten years (see Appendix 3,4 and5).

Moreover, biographical storytelling was applied voluntarily by two participants, guided by recommended prompts from the toolkit (page 51-53) to the interview guide by the facilitator based on the: individual impacts of the crisis/changes in functionings in their individual lives; emotional/immaterial/feelings/dignity; collective trust and participation, these inform about changes at community level and changes in capabilities. The group listened and commented on the testimonies, which was a first step in identifying matters of main concern for the group as well as to identify recommendations (step 6).

The steering committee was composed of two members of the focus group, one researcher and the executive director of 'Youth Association of Urban Echoes'. They met in May 2016 main findings of the present report. It will be extended to social workers of other local NGOs which work with the group. The 'action' part of the PAR approach through rights action and MOK approaches will be implemented in the next stage of the RE-InVEST project as agreed by the Consortium. PAR implies to engage testimonies who experience social problems and work in order to find their own solutions. Agency was discussed at the first meetings and some proposals came out in the group without practical effects yet, such as: manifesto about youth unemployment to be presented to the city council (proposed by a person that in the meantime found a job); the right to work was introduced but it was pointed out that the core question is to find strategies to face unemployment which is not the aim of the project. The agency element will be a crucial point to work towards in the following group meetings.

3. Two selected biographies

3.1 First biography

I have a nursing degree and my life now is like this: if I choose the easiest way, which at the same time is very difficult, I have to emigrate. ... but it is hard to move to another country. I already had job proposals from Norway, Belgium, Germany, UK ... thousands of them. It is easy! I have lots of colleagues that went abroad. The process is to fill in all the bureaucratic documents and wait for their call. (...) But it is difficult ... I'm not a person who gives up! We hear all the time that this is bad. There are nursing strikes...it is bad, it is bad... but I cannot say that it is, if I don't try. ... But then I think 'should I stay here unemployed, attending training courses to improve the CV...Here the job's proposals require young people with lots of experience. Because of this I feel frustrated...then I think I will stay here doing volunteer work in nursing... it will be open a nursing department in the Red Cross ... but when I think more and more about the access conditions to go to the UK, one day they will be changed and the Nurses Order will demand more exams from January next year.. .and at the same time the agency's calling all the time to start the process now ... So to emigrate is becoming more and more a strong option.'

B finished her nursing degree and she is unemployed. She feels confused whether to emigrate or to stay in the country. Once forced to go abroad to have a job, she will not come back to Portugal, it will be only the country where she was born which makes her sad. With the age of 23, she pointed out that she will find a good job abroad, she will marry there, and she will have a house and a family. In the end she will build her life there, ... *'It won't be the same as my father who was forced to migrate to Angola due to the economic crisis and will return after saving some money.'* In her point of view young people should be able to choose to live in their own country but the economic crisis forces them to emigrate. The low wages are very discouraging after investing in her education. She states that there is a shortage of nurses in health services but there are no job proposals.

She tries to not give up: *'But then there's that feeling that things will change and if there is a nursing shortage it is because they need them! We have to give it time but waiting is discouraging and begins to be tiring.'*

In 2010 when she was attending secondary school she started thinking about a nursing career:

It was a valued job, so I was enthusiastic about it. I didn't have financial difficulties. In 2011 I joined the nursing college. That year TROIKA came and the subsequent measures, my father began to have difficulties in finding work (construction sector), in paying taxes... and the family/children allowance and scholarship were cut. Because of that, my father found himself in need to migrate to Angola, leaving me and my brothers behind and on our own.'

B is doing volunteering work in the local Red Cross as a way to help people in need and feel useful but she doesn't trust social public services. She has a negative view of the public servants of the social security. When her father asked for social support:

'The lady (Social Security) told my father: You are not poor.' I am not poor but I'm in economic difficulties, it's just me to care for three children. I want to know why you are withdrawing the support now when I need it most. The woman said, 'Let me see: you own a house, right? Sell it and you won't need to go abroad.' It makes no sense. For the social security employee we had to sell the house as a way to prevent us from emigrating. They don't want to know. They know that people go through difficulties but they don't care about people's problems. So my advice is to go to social organisations. For example the Red Cross that cares, that take time to listen to your story ... That's their mission and do not want anything for it... They have many volunteers from social, health areas ... They listen to your story and will try to help you.'

With her father in Angola she has to be strong and resilient and should not give up in hard times to end the higher education program and care for her brothers:

'It was a tough year for adaptation and the combination of studies/family, because the father's absence was noticeable. It was difficult to adapt...for me and for my brothers. We have to handle everything but I realised that I could not give up. My father was doing that for me. I endeavoured more. I finished my degree. At this point we were in economic constraints and we did not receive support.'

In 2014, B witnessed the deterioration of the health cuts in people's lives and how this worsened the working conditions of health professionals during her internship in public health care:

'One of the most significant memories I have during the internship was the fatigue and overwork of the health professionals, which conditioned the quality of care. Also I witnessed in Psychiatry an increasing number of admissions of people with academic training e.g. nurses, doctors, and lawyers, due to depression.'

3.2 Second biography

Z has her life routine very scheduled during her twenty four years' life time. She attended vocational training on events organisation to get the secondary level. The grades to go to college were not good enough and she had to give up of high education due to economic reasons. Dropping out of school made her losing her family allowance what does not make any sense to her. It made things even worse. Afterwards she got temporary jobs: the longest period was nine months and the shortest was one week: *'From June 2011 to December 2015, I was employed one year and eleven months and have been unemployed during two years and five months.'* Z worked in different sectors and developed different skills: in restaurants, in textile factories; in a train company and grape harvests. In between she attended training with an average duration of 50 hours per training: first aid in geriatrics; first aid hydrotherapy; child health care; Portuguese traditional cuisine; and HACCP.²³ She goes fortnightly to temporary employment agencies to renew her information and asking if there is a job for her. The same effort B uses towards the employment centre, but she has not succeeded:

'I went this morning to know my situation, if everything was all right...if there was any labour supply...The employment servant simple said 'Go to the website and see'. It is the second time they gave me the same answer.'

During the economic crisis her mother was dismissed after working many years in textile factories. Z said that several textile factories closed in the area and many people lost their jobs. Once in a while her mother does undeclared work but very seldom. Z cannot count on her because she has financial problems too. During 2013, the family environment got worse and Z was victim of domestic violence by her mother. Their relation is characterised with bad and not so bad moments. Nonetheless, in 2014, Z was unemployed and moved from her place of birth to live with her boyfriend. During last year he also became unemployed with no right to social benefit because his employer did not pay social security, something of which he was completely unaware. For a while he worked in a restaurant and was dismissed. During that period in which both were unemployed, she received unemployment benefit (around 350€ per month until November 2015 to pay all the bills). After that she had no money and asked for social support:

'I can apply for the social insertion income in March. Before that I can't have it because I have received unemployment benefits, so I am not entitled to receive it. They ask for last three months bank account... She tried different sorts to get financial support: I resorted to banks, friends, acquaintances and family. All refused. I ask for food assistance in social canteens. They just gave me an option: go to the social canteen if I want it! (...) I'll get lunch and dinner every day, at the time they want, and the food most of the time is cold. The food containers (...) spoiled ... and I don't have microwave to heat the food and it goes like ice cold for the 'little mouth ...'

²³ Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Point

Z and her boyfriend live in an old house with poor conditions with rain coming through the roof, and the walls have dampness. Z and her boyfriend do not have money to pay for gas or heater:

'If we use the heater then the electricity bill is expensive. The washing machine is from the landlady and is broken. And she won't fix it. I do the laundry in the tank by hand. The landlady has to do works on the roof... but she doesn't want to do anything (...) and when it rains, it rains inside the house.'

Without financial support Z cannot pay health exams: I don't need to pay health taxes but I have to do exams that are not covered by the National Health System and those I have to pay. My boyfriend is ill on an arm and has to do exams which costs 80€ but we don't have money to pay and we don't have any help. She felt discriminated when goes to hospital services: if you are a person with money, you are well treated. In my home town I had no complain, here I have.

As already stated, her parents got divorced when she was a baby:

'My father left me with two months...never supported me. He is abroad I don't know anything about him. I'm his daughter and I went to court a few years ago to have some financial allowance. Regarding to family support she pointed out the fact of being victim of domestic violence: If I tell my story, you stay open-mouthed. The mother who beats her own daughter...I let it happen twice, the third...I did not let her do it again and I slammed against the wall, with my grandmother watching... I called the police.'

With regards to family ties, Z added that the death of her aunt was a great loss. She had the reference role in her life:

'I cook very well because I learned with my aunt. My family says that I'm very like her...she died when I was twelve years old.'

In her words, *friends' emotional support is more important than any other kind of family support.*

She has a group of friends who meet across the country to play arrows; sometimes they friendly pay a drink, because she does not have money. This good atmosphere is essential to avoid depression:

'(...) Because of that (domestic violence), last year I had two depressions one after another and the doctor says if I stay like that I'm going to have another one. I take four different pills per day. If weren't my friends ...With my mother not so much, we had our peaks. But now friends, that's why I like to play arrows ...'

Z's level of trust in social organisations is very low because she felt nobody helped her. As she is in need, she is deeply against the refugee aid. Firstly, the welfare state should ensure social rights for national citizens before providing all kind of rights to the newcomers:

'My boyfriend is trying to get health care for free. And we can't benefit from any of that. You don't have no rights to social security, employment centre, has nothing...I also go to Syria (...) and then I come back... Why don't they go to the richest countries nearby? They have no crises...it has small crises...If I have 5 or 10 thousand euros for a trip to Greece...they have more money than us.'

One important feature that enables her to move on was when she took the driver's license in 2010. As future plans her dream is: *to work in the company that manages the arrows championships.*

4. Analysis

The current data analysis results from the empirical study based upon the participatory action research. The discussions of the focus groups were recorded and transcribed and the content analysis²⁴ was elaborated according to the two main research questions pointed out by Reinvest:

1. the crisis has negative social consequences which undermined the human rights of vulnerable groups;
2. the negative social consequences lead to a growing distrust and loss of solidarity.

The priority issues linked with the first hypothesis that came out from young unemployed testimonies were dimensions such as: education (Section 4.1.1), employment (Section 4.1.2), social protection (Section 4.1.3); health (Section 4.1.4), and housing (Section 4.1.5). In what concerns to (dis)trust young unemployed people emphasised this subject towards neighbours (Section 4.2.1) and family (Section 4.2.2), social organisations (Section 4.2.3), public services like social security (Section 4.2.4) and public employment service (Section 4.2.4), political institutions (Section 4.2.5) their opinion about refugees (4.2.6) and the meaning of Human Rights (4.2.7).

4.1 The social consequences of the crisis on human rights of young unemployed

4.1.1 Education level and labour market opportunities

The participant group is composed by members who have a degree and who attended basic and secondary school.²⁵ For both, to have a high education degree is perceived as very important to get a better job: *'More studies you have, more chances you will have to find a job.'* The education level will influence the future standard of well-being: *'I think it enhances the long-term quality of life.'* Nonetheless, educational choices are strongly shaped by the labour market pressure and household economic resources. On one hand, who have low qualifications didn't pursue their education for economic reasons and opted for attending vocational training to raise their job opportunities: *'I studied to the 9th grade but couldn't attend school to the 12th year. At that time there was no money to go to school.'* In addition some low skilled participants wish to attend university studies: *'I hope to work two years to earn some money and then go to university or work at the same time.'* On the other hand, who has a degree reported economic difficulties to finish their academic studies. One participant stopped studying one year to help their parents in a small family company and she has to apply for a bank credit to pay tuition fees: *'... the last year was very complicated in this aspect. I cannot invest in training, postgraduate courses and seminars. Turns out to be more difficult to invest on it ...'* Another participant emphasised that her father had to immigrate to Angola to help financing her studies. A third young female had a scholarship from the State, otherwise her parents couldn't afford it. In her case the lack of money doesn't allow her to

²⁴ The content analysis are based on all sessions developed, recorded, and transcribed, which includes the visual methods, like drawings, snakes individual interviews, interviews in depth. From the main and repeated topics were organised in main categories and subcategories.

²⁵ As it can be seen in annex 1 from the eleven participants three have master degree – nursing; psychology; biology - (female); four have 12th level, attended training courses/ secondary education - Beauty treatments and massage; laboratory analysis; on events organisation (female); one has 11th level; and three have 9th level – (2 male and 1 female).

move to a big city like Lisbon to look for a job more suitable to her qualification. Furthermore, they are aware of some study areas such as engineer or sciences that will increase more labour opportunities rather than humanities. In this sense, education plays an instrumental role in fostering economic growth, instead of well-being and social development as reported by young unemployed.

Having in mind the relation between education level and labour opportunities, for the **qualified participants** - that never worked before - there is an obvious imbalance between supply and demand in labour market and therefore there are too many qualified unemployed people for few jobs available. In the participants' opinions this devalues the qualifications and in this sense: *'... it is not a guarantee of work ...'* Moreover, the three master degrees unemployed female considered themselves to be overqualified to get unskilled jobs like in shopping stores: *'... I am overqualified for some things and for other I don't have experience.'* At the same time, when they apply for a job, employers require work experience. Such requirement undermines the right to work:

'... Without an opportunity how we can gain experience? The employers and society must be aware to give an opportunity to young people who don't have experience but have lots of energy, lots of ideas and we need to show that we are dynamic and not passive.'

From the point of view of **those with few qualifications** considered themselves as underqualified. The majority of them have attended vocational training to get the secondary school as a way to raise their opportunities to entry in the labour market: *'It was one reason why I attended professional training.'*

In the line of capability approach what real opportunities and freedom youth unemployment participants have to achieve education that they can have reason to value? The few jobs available limit individual choices to the ones that potentially will have more opportunities and not the ones they felt are reasonable to live: *'Today I feel that young people chose a degree not because they like it, but because they expect to get a job. It isn't an option it is a need felt by parents who pay our education.'* Furthermore, participants as young unemployed felt social pressure to not stop *'... and attending training courses to fill in a CV...'*

In this sense, young people 'felt obliged' to choose a degree according with labour market needs in first place instead of fighting for their individual wishes and dreams: *'We should think very carefully about the areas which will give employment and opt for that.'* Even being aware of the permanent change in labour market: (...) *'I chose sciences which had more opportunities. Six years later, after graduating, I realise that it's the same. Maybe it is more difficult than working as a kindergarten teacher.'* There is the perception that the economy encourages the 'practical and objective tasks' rather than reflexive ones:

'... We have to think more in practical education ... what do a philosopher does? Will teach, will write books, while an engineer knows what will work for a company like engineer... practical things, objective things. I think increasingly, the practical work is valued more than the broad knowledge degrees.'

Portugal never had before a high level of graduate population as nowadays. Nonetheless, considering the overall population it remains to make an effort to ensure high education for all and to improve the high figures of school dropout. In this sense, in one participant words, being the first household member attending college was always felt as a family dream and a way of changing life for better far from the parents' working class background. This expectation fulfilled as a fundamental assumption of democratic societies where school performed a key role of social mobility and work status. However, under the current hardest circumstances, to find a job is a 'postponed dream':

'I believed so. Now I don't know. (...) To have a degree ... it would be that change. They (parents) didn't have the opportunity to study but we were going to have. And now I see I finished higher education and after all ... nothing changed that much ... And that of course worries me.'

4.1.2 Quality jobs and decent work

The employment status of the young unemployed households are broadly speaking blue-collar jobs and temporary jobs or on social protection benefits and in kind support (see annex 1 profile participant group). We are dealing with a vulnerable group with low income which constrain the different dimensions of life, including education and leisure.

The economic crisis deteriorated the right to have a decent job. The construction sector was one of most affected by the crisis in Portugal: *'...when Troika came, my father was a self-employed worker...and he had to cancel social security to not pay, otherwise he didn't have money. Everything was still (construction sector) he couldn't find work ...'* Before the crisis was easier to find employment in blue-collar jobs: *'...even in the factories... my father was taking many jobs and he was getting little time to do other things (...) and from 2009, 2010 (...) wasn't like that.'* The job losses, the raise of unemployment to historical figures and the bad working conditions (low wages, 9, 10 working hours per day) leads to a common feeling of how difficult it is to find work within the current economic and social context. Job searching make people feel frustrated (see annex 2 Drawing). The skilled work is devalued: *'(...) it is not as valued... I think it has deteriorated. The conditions in dignity have worsened.'* and there is a feeling of unfairness having in mind the relation between high qualifications and low wages: *'We invest so much... and I see minimum wage proposals and I do not think it's fair that kind of salary for skilled labour (...) it is revolting. It makes us also refuse it.'*

In the participant's words, the huge imbalance between demand and offer of the labour market, allow employers to choose very qualified persons paying low wages. The job criteria selection became who accepts the lowest wage: *'I think they (employers) are taking advantage of the fact that we need to get work ... few proposals, I see two in per month or not even that.'* There is a common feeling of having no choice by accepting the employers' offers in a way that they play the rules of labour market conditions. Younger employed people are mostly in precarious work, poorly paid, insecure and unprotected. This kind of behaviour can lead to exploitation and discrimination from employers and increases competition for the few jobs available among. Young people have few opportunities to enter the workforce. When they have the opportunity to start their professional life, the qualified jobs are paid as no skilled jobs:

'...who has just come out of the university will earn the same as those who work in a factory. I have a friend who is working in a car factory and earns €680; I have friend who is an architect in internship and gets €550; and I know a mechanical engineer who earns €700; and I know that if I get a job is going to be around €650, €700 ...'

In the participants' opinion graduates and young professionals such as engineers from environmental, electrical, mechanical areas are low paid, receiving around 700€. 800€ is considered by the labour market as the maximum. The current amount paid on the traineeships of the job centre is 650€ and research grants wages are €755/degree and masters €980 (gross salary), stated the participants.

In the graduated unemployed participants' opinion, skilled labour was well paid in the past compared to today. Nowadays, the wages amounts are very similar to those paid in shops or factories, where workers usually have the 9th or 12th school level. For the young undergraduate unemployed participants the effective working conditions in blue collars jobs are as well badly paid: *'2, 88 €/hour in a factory.'* with long working hours:

'...8, 9, and 10 hours a day ...' and with bad working environment: '... people are very rude. For example the factory where my mother works, people do not talk to each other.' It is also: *'very precarious ...'* It is given an example: *'At the factory (x) we work during a week and in the next week or a month they no longer want you...'*

Besides the low wages, precarious jobs is the only experience some participants, who have worked before, have: *'Since I finished my studies until now, it has been 23 months working and 29 months unemployed (...) I had five or six jobs...the last one was nine months.'* Nowadays precariousness starts to be a common place, far from the idea of a lifelong job as happened in the past:

I think there's really much more precarious work, three, six contracts a year at most, for our age as far as I know. (...) I have a colleague of mine who got signed at a shopping store for six months, after six months was renewed and after the end of more six months they renewed.'

The rise of precarious work is linked somehow to the way economy is working: *'There is so much job rotation (...) because the businesses are also not healthy ...'* The fixed terms contracts allow employers easy dismissals: *'...There is more supply. Employers say ok: 'if this employee doesn't fit we have to look for another. (...) It is bad for the people (...) only serves the employer not the employee.'*

In some cases due to the hard conditions to get the first job, it is stated that young people do voluntary work by despair as a way to enter the labour market:

'...we can talk about companies that want volunteer interns and they end up taking advantage of the despair of the younger, I cannot even consider as employment conditions because this is not employment.'

The well-being was put into question at the workplace due to the rising level of unemployment:

'on the different places where I worked in, I felt that after 2008 it has been more distrust which undermines interpersonal relations, between colleagues due the insecurity felt by the possibility of becoming unemployed. Even the job situation isn't the most desirable it is better to have a job and feel uncomfortable rather than to be unemployed.'

The unemployed nurse mentioned the shortage of qualified personnel at the health services, which contrasts to the huge number of qualified unemployed people with no opportunity to work:

'... It scares me to hear the news that there are shortages of qualified personnel, ... They just take advantage of them as volunteers with no guarantee of staying. What happens is that, when they finish their volunteering work, they leave the country ...They (foreign recruitment agencies) come to us and give us exciting proposals. I speak on behalf of myself, I have turned down some proposals and the way to pull over is, "we feel insecure in getting home or ..." and they say: "We find it!"'

The right to have a job is deeply deteriorated as far as unemployed young people are concerned to get their first job: *'The hardest is to get a job without experience...And we don't have experience.'* Young unemployed participants argue that it must be given more opportunities to young people and believe in their capabilities. They ask how can we have experience if we just finished secondary school or college? *'... Experience is study, is that it? I wasn't born knowing everything. People have the first job... they need to have it...if it is the first job there isn't experience, we have to begin from somewhere. A person was not born an expert.'* In the same line of thought, it is once more emphasised that young unemployed are excluded from job opportunities when work experience is required: *'... I see a lot of offers that ask, 5, 2, 3 years' experience ... for a person who has just come out of a higher education institution it is impossible ...'* In addition, even working in less qualified jobs are not accepted because they also haven't experience: *'(...) I went to an interview at a store and the lady liked me (...) but I had no experience.'*

With the recent historical high unemployed rates (17% in 2013) were simultaneously recorded high emigration rates which have remained steady last few years (2013/14). This data can be reported by the participants' testimonies: *'My family emigrated because they had no jobs here'; '...my father felt compelled to emigrate...to Angola.'* Having in mind the pressure of the emigration issue to find a job, it was deeply discussed among participants whether it could be considered as a free option or to what extent could be faced as an enforced decision. Some of them definitely did not want to emigrate and it is assumed to not leave the country where they were born: *'I don't feel like leaving Portugal.'* Other participant wants to go abroad only for leisure time and to know different cultures: *'I'd like to do an exchange (...) I would enjoy doing it but not to work.'* Another participant assumed that: *'If we do not have opportunities here we have to try outside.'* Others would rather prefer to emigrate if they have money for the travels expenses and for the first period of time to find a job. The discussion about a wider European economic crisis came into question once it is not just a national issue but a global concern. In young people opinion's the nature of the current emigration trends were also debated:

Portugal will become the place where I was born. It won't be like my father that emigrate to earn money and will come back. I and my generation will go to live a life there... I will get a job, I will marry there I will have a house and raise my children I won't come back.'

To emigrate remains a difficult decision even when they have a good job proposal because it also means leaving their families.

4.1.3 Social Protection

To what extent social rights are met during the social and economic crisis? To what extent social policies tackle and prevent the disadvantage people to escape from poverty and social exclusion and promote the right to live a life with in dignity? As showed in part 1 the austerity measures deteriorated the Welfare State and strongly affected social benefits like the unemployment; the social insertion income. According to the participants' words social investments are replaced for neo liberal policies: *'The State cuts the protection to people in need to give to those who do not need, you know! That's a bit stupid.'*; *'It (the State) gives banks and cuts us for instances ...'* The financial crisis is explained by bankruptcy and by the State helping the banks system: *'had loans from banks either way (...) the State cannot have money for everything (...) the responsibility was accumulated by many years. It has been created a hole that now has to solve.'*

During the economic crisis many families felt their social situation changed dramatically and try to apply for the social insertion income but the eligibility conditions became very restrict:

'What I mean is that once everything was fine, we had no financial difficulties and they gave us support (family allowance; user fees, scholarships) when my father went (to Angola) and we need support they withdraw everything. My father will come back and maybe we will receive again. It doesn't makes any sense.'

The social benefits cuts in the social insertion income and the strict rules to access it are viewed as unfair:

'It was stupid because it had to do with the (...) bank accounts, I have with my sister money in a bank account due to scholarships (...) in case of being necessary to help my parents and it was mainly to pay for home, the fees...'

Indeed, young unemployed people reported that there were cuts in social benefits with the economic crisis:

'Yes, there are always cuts. My scholarship in the first year (2010) was higher than in the subsequent years. My parents received the social insertion income there was a time it went down a bit.' (...) My colleagues ran out of scholarships for debts that they didn't know they had to the Social Security for example ...'

One participant asked for that benefit but it wasn't approved:

'They ask for the last three months of the bank account and I received the partial unemployment benefit which was €380 ... My boyfriend has been unemployed for a year and also has no right.'

In addition, the conditionality of the social income benefits produce the risk of restrained incentives to take up work:

'There are things we want to do but we can't. For example we have the House of Creativity when there are events, to point the way to people. It is only possible to do some casual work with green receipts but this puts into question other types of support. It is to pay to work ...'

Furthermore, it was stated that before the troika the social benefits were higher than during the adjustment period:

'Everyone does not like Socrates but the minimum wage was the minimum wage. My parents were both unemployed and we survived. Subsidies were higher, unemployment benefits were higher.'

There are two participants who benefit from daily food support from social canteens (Social Emergency Programme (Programa Social de Emergência)) provided by social organisations. One of the participants stated that the meals have good quality, and some elements agreed that the social organisation in question is considered as having a good service. The other beneficiary claimed quite the opposite: cold food delivered in spoiled recipients. This matter was discussed among the group and the answer of the different social organisations to this particular regard.

All participants have some kind of social support due to their vulnerable context: family allowance; social minimum income; unemployed benefits; scholarships. The amount of the benefits was reduced during the economic crisis. For more detail information see the annex 1.

4.1.4 Health status of participants and medical care provision

The scope of the relatives' diseases are very linked with the unemployed effects, as a multidimensional phenomenon that affects several dimensions of the human well-being (even there is not a linear relation between causes and consequences) like depression, domestic violence and divorce as well as health problems spread among family members:

'My mother was unemployed (...) and the depression that she had due to domestic violence became worse. (...) She has problems at physical level that will not let her work. Sometimes to do easy things and she looks like an old lady of 80 years and she is only 40. (...) My younger brother after the separation of my parents became very psychologically affected... he was born with a mental disorder... He has to have more support in school (...) my sister is celiac.'

The health expenses are a burden to the family budget, and the money available is driven to the priorities:

'My sister is celiac; it is very difficult because the medicines to the disease are very expensive. My brother needs a medicine every day for his concentration. In that house everyone needs something...it is complicated. We have to choose to help one at a time... and then the others are deprived. We can't cope with everything.'

There are cases in vulnerable conditions which are due to the fact that there is no money to pay exams: *'... my boyfriend is waiting to take a medical exam to the arm but there is no money.'*

Finally, dental care is the most needed among the group, because isn't covered by National Health System NHS.

Regarding to the perception about medical care provided, indeed, there is a favourable opinion towards the NHS. From one participant's opinion, it was not felt any change in her treatment and in her mother's, before and during the crisis in terms of access to medical consultations or fees. Another participant pointed out that even health services contacted her mother to go to routine consultations. In this sense, for an unemployed graduated nurse, the NHS improved considerably for the last forty years: *'I think Portugal has given more and more emphasis to health care, primary care, (...) and I think there have been major improvements ...'* A different perspective is stated by other testimonies that do not have money to spend in doctors due to the high cost compared to their strict budgets. One participant mentioned a discriminated treatment regards who doesn't have money or social status:

'Here at São João (Hospital) it seems that it depends on the person you are. If you are a person with possessions are well treated, here I have reasons to complain ...'

In the next lines it will be given a picture of the health system through two testimonies of the group (a nurse and a clinical psychologist) during their internship in 2014. Those voices translate the negative impacts of the austerity measures in the health of the Portuguese citizens as mentioned in part 1 (national context) regards to the increase of the fees in the emergency services; the shortage of health professionals and the deterioration of quality of the care.

The increase of the emergency fees makes harder the access of the most vulnerable people to health care. Moreover it is noticed that there has been cuts in health under the effectiveness discourse and attempt to maintain the same services, with a reduction of the health professionals:

'Providing the services but without increasing the costs ... so I think that it shouldn't be cut back on staff even if the answer is fast, is effective ...'

This affects the quality of care:

'... There are people who are fortunate enough to go on the right day, at the right time and they are cared for, in my opinion, are better cared for than others in most troubled times.'

'...There is a shortage of nurses and of doctors...They worked exaggerated shifts to ensure services, they felt really tired. (...) there were nurses who worked afternoons, nights and in the following day started on the afternoon...'

The payment of overtime is covered by the 'bank of hours'. They didn't receive and then they were revolted. They worked, and worked and didn't receive by doing emergency services. Those hard working conditions led some of those professionals to depression:

'... In psychiatric services... people with depression are more and more graduated... in my time (internship) were there two nurses with depression ...by excess of work.'

To sum up in the participant words:

'It is very difficult to maintain a good level of productivity, not only productivity in terms of results but productivity in terms of the quality of what is done ...'

4.1.5 Housing conditions of participants

As education, employment and health, housing is an important dimension when talking about the social damages of the crisis among the young unemployed. They reported some housing problems mainly dampness, missing heating conditions and no money to pay the rent. Regarding dampness four participants stated to have it in their homes: *'...Dampness. It was horrible my father every year had to paint the room. It was all black.'* Concerning the heating conditions, the heater is only used in a part of the house: *'...My mom warms the room and then heats the rooms when we go there.'* Or even avoid its use: *'... We use the heater and then the electricity is expensive ...'* One participant mentioned having no heater and another one said that: *'In January and February I have to go to my father's house because of the cold weather.'*

Regarding the issue of having washing machine all participants said that they had, except one: *'The washing machine is from the landlady and is broken. And she doesn't want to fix it. I do the wash by hand.'* The same participant emphasised do not have gas for heating food and the house also needs improvements: *'The landlady has to do works on the roof... but she doesn't want to do anything (...) and it rains inside the house because of the damages on the roof.'*

What concerns to pay the rent, four participants can pay with their household's income and another four have social support to do it. One of the participants emphasised that even having social support it is difficult to manage to pay the bills:

'... There are months that for having water, electricity, my mother has to ask for help to my older brother who doesn't live with us but that sometimes has to help otherwise would be complicated.'

Another one reported that though they can pay the rent with her mother's salary: *'...there is a very small amount left over.'*

When questioned about the possibility of affording a week's vacation over the past decade with all the expenses paid, the majority of the participants mentioned that they don't afford money for holidays. One participant takes vacations with the help of relatives: *'(...) in that period both were*

employed without large incomes but we could go. Since 2009 with the situation of my parents, we go but we don't pay all things.'

4.2 The social consequences of the crisis on (dis)trust of young unemployed

4.2.1 The relation with neighbourhood

Broadly speaking participants have no strong links with the neighbourhood. In some cases the neighbours are elderly and none of them referred to do joint activities. Although, one participant stated to have the understanding and encouragement of her neighbours concerning the fact of being unemployed: *'People tell me to be calm, to be patient, 'oh it is very little time has passed since (...) This is now normal, there are many people like that, there are many young people looking for a job.'*

4.2.2 The relation with family

The majority of the testimonies highlighted having strong family's ties. Family is considered as a crucial source of support during hard times. It gives support with financial help, food or share holiday costs when are spent together. When divorce happens the older children leave school and start working to help on the family budget. Nonetheless there are other participants who don't have any family support. Quite the contrary, to whom was denied family help when it was most needed:

'I was nine years old when my mother died. My father asked for help to his family but they only thought in themselves, didn't want help others. And my father didn't have possibilities because he worked from 8 am to midnight. I left home during some time...I had a surgery to a leg and I went to one lady's home and I have been there many years. Then my father died two years ago. I stayed in my father's house with my brother.'

4.2.3 The relation with social organisations and public services

In general the provision of social organisations answers are positively perceived. They have food support and trust in the quality of services and care of people's lives. Some of them are engaged on voluntary work because they believe in the work done in helping vulnerable people. Regarding the public services like social security or public employment service are often viewed negatively. With concerns to public servants of the social security it is pointed out:

'They don't want to know (social security). They know that people go through difficulties but they don't want to listen to their problems. So my advice is to go to entities, for example the Red Cross who cares, who takes time to listen to your story ... That's their mission and do not take anything for it ...'

The same participant pointed out that:

'The lady (Social Security) told my father: "You are not poor." I am not poor but I'm in economic difficulties, it's just me to care of three children. I want to know why you are withdrawing the support now when I need it most. The woman said, "Let me see: you have a house, right? Sell it and you won't need to go abroad." It makes no sense. For the social security employee we had to sell the house as a way to not emigrate.'

4.2.4 Employment public service

From the participants' point of view there is a lack of satisfaction towards job centre professionals in providing information about traineeships and job offers:

'From the traineeships, the lady gave me the sheet that was on the internet and I ended up not realising about what were the employers charges. The lady did not know how to answer my doubts, and about the training told me to go

there Wednesday at 10 that would be an information session. There are people who cannot go there on Wednesday at 10 am.'

Another statement refers: *'I went this morning to know my situation, if everything was right, if there was any labour supply. (...) "Go to the site to see." It is the second time that gives the same answer.'*

Moreover, professional training addressed to unemployed people as an active labour market policy is regarded as a statistics matter: *'The State does not care about people, cares about numbers ...'* A relevant feature is that employer's don't value the training undertaken by the employment public service:

'... My mother attended a cooking course for a year to get the 9th grade. (...) Employers look at it and think: she hadn't learning anything. The employer doesn't value this training education. Doesn't provide a job. It is for the State say to Brussels that we are not unemployed. (...) A person goes there and squeezing it, you don't learn anything.'

Beyond that, people's participation in training is viewed as compulsory attendance with no freedom to choose the content areas more suitable with the working experience or education background: *'we get there and we can't choose between two courses... it is imposed. This should be a democracy. It's not just elections.'*

Moreover, the training offer is targeted only to low skilled people, ignoring the more qualified groups: *'... If you have a lower education level anything goes (...) there was no training for me (...) and I would not receive information ... by the fact of having a degree on the health area ...'*

4.2.5 Trust in politicians and political institutions

Young unemployed people shared their negative opinion towards politicians during the focus groups discussions. They look at politicians behaviours ruled by self-interest instead of being conducted by social welfare values and the common interest to improve people's quality of life. In the context of political youth organisations, one young unemployed participant currently belongs to the Socialist youth Party and participated already in different youth parties. He reached the conclusion that there are few people who are truly interested in solving social problems. They are interested to get a job, public recognition or social status. Another similar experience is shared with student's union and student's election: *'If at the level of an academic association is like this, I don't want to imagine how it will be politics at real stage...'* The idea of political ethics was considered to exist on the early ages of the democratic regime in Portugal after the dictatorship: *'... politicians were taken seriously. (Alvaro Cunhal – communist leader, Sá Carneiro- social democratic leader). People believed in what they did and what they wanted to do. They did it by public interest, now it is much for 'their pocket'.* The political system is viewed as being discredited:

'Nobody believes in politicians. There are few people to believe (...) there are always good politicians and they really want to do things, and they want to show...but the majority of them doesn't think like that.(...) If you ask people, they tell you that they are all equal and are all liars.'

In the context of the political elections (4th October 2015) participants were very critical to the political marketing of government parties' coalition - Social Democratic Party (PSD) and Christians Conservatives (PP-CDS):

'People say yes I want Portugal Ahead, I want to vote in Portugal Ahead. (...) "And what do you think about Passos Coelho ...? Passos Coelho I don't want to hear that name!" It was the same party. People were all voting in Portugal Ahead thinking it was another party ...Neither I did know who the Portugal Ahead was. Afterwards I realised ... Jesus!'

Even regards the attempt to solve the economic and social crisis at European level by the European institutions there isn't a favourable opinion:

'I think the crisis is the banks fault. The European institutions don't care and don't know how to manage the crisis and in the end, everything will end in a civil war. This is a bit exaggerated and I'm 'making' movies but it is my opinion.'

When participants were questioned about **what do you would like to see changed in politics?** The answer was investing in young people and citizens in general:

'Changing the vision they have about young people (...) they should emphasise our skills. Give us support ... and ... create opportunities.' and *'To help more the Portuguese people.'*

The investment should be mainly in health care and education:

'Improve the health care services! Do not cut back on the health.';
'In education as well! Because I think that young people have the potential and capacity to have good results.'

4.2.6 Debate about refugees rights

The recent wave of refugees across Europe was a controversial issue from the social and economic rights perspective in a context of social and economic crisis by who is in a vulnerable situation. Concerning refugees there is an ambivalent position: on one hand it is pointed out that it is offered many conditions to the refugees: *'a family who came to Ovar and got a whole house arranged with furniture and jobs'*, raising the question why offer so much at once if there is homeless people, nobody wants to know if they have home or not. It was added that: *'(...) I think it became an aid boom, a social project to help Portuguese wouldn't be so accepted.'* One the other hand, it is stated that there is:

'... Also people who are silly and tell them to go to other countries ... I don't think so. We should think if we were on their situation ... if Portugal had some problem we also wanted to be well accepted. I think it was a lot of confusion around this.'

Moreover, it was called the media responsibility to this issue, the information conveyed reinforces the prejudice and discrimination among native citizens towards refugees in the sense that:

'The media does not help. It gives the idea that we will give everything but it is not quite so, we will give a lot, yes we will. And people then start saying that we will give everything ...'

4.2.7 The young unemployed perspective about human rights

'I think that it's more important than having someone here to talk about what our rights are ... it would be much better to happen but there will be no changes soon in my opinion... More than that, it would be more useful if someone give us tools to deal with the current society ...'

Human Rights are viewed as an idealistic and abstract concept inscribed in legislation far from being fully implemented. From this point of view one of the social damage of the crisis is the deterioration of human rights, especially the economic and social rights by the difficulties to access work, or to have precarious jobs without social protection, as well as when young unemployed face a long period of time searching for the first job without any benefit. There is an awareness of the right to work as an entitlement that everyone should have, the fact is that there are no jobs in the labour market which constrains people freedoms and choices. In this sense, the right to have a job is being violated which raises the pressure to mobilise strategies to be well succeeded in the labour market:

Today we are so many around the same, that we have to learn strategies to sell our skills on the labour market. Why are you an added value for a company? (...) what is in our hands to do? What techniques, we young people have to overcome the situation. (...) How can we 'sell us' in this labour market?

To know the fundamental rights is viewed as an individual responsibility matter and not as an empowering tool to transform social reality through public discussion and advocacy:

'Now to talk about our rights I think it depends on each of us try to find out. If we don't worry about it we do not worry about anything.'

Finally, some of them answer the question about the meaning of Human Rights having in mind their situation as young unemployed: *'The right to be heard'; 'Freedom of speech and not to be discriminated'; 'The right to work'; 'I don't know...I never thought about that...I don't know.'* To sum up, the human rights need to be deeply debated on how can be a crucial tool in their own lives.

5. Conclusion

The global economic crisis has challenged the quality of the life standards of many people with great emphasis on the most vulnerable people. In the Portuguese context the number of poor people increased and became poorer. High unemployment, low employment, the increase on poverty and social exclusion, and declining household incomes resulted in a lack of confidence in political and economic institutions. This report aims to understand how the crisis and anti-crisis measures undermined the social rights and the disinvestment of the ten young unemployed aged 18-30 years in São João da Madeira (Portugal). The focus on the young people's testimonies aims to gather data on the social damage of the crisis through their own voices far from the purpose of being representative, having in mind the number of young people being heard. Instead, it aims to bring an overview of how people's lives have been affected by the economic crisis and show the living experience beyond statistics. However, it is important to highlight that the anxieties felt to get a job is very representative to young people to whom emigration is not a 'free choice' and reflects the structural increase of the emigration rate in the last years.

The research questions which guide this report and were formulated in chapter 4 are answered here:

Young people continue to face more difficulties in entering and remaining in the labour market, as well as in accessing quality jobs. Their capabilities were deteriorated by being forced to emigrate, to not have freedom of choice of training or the right to a decent job.

All participants or their families received RSI the social benefit that shows the degree to which poverty and social exclusion deprive their rights. Despite the level of education, all participants agreed on having more education increases the changes in the future. As unemployed people they perceived as underqualified or overqualified to integrate the labour market. The participants with low levels of education and qualification, (9th or 12th degree) did not enrol for secondary or college due to economic reasons. Instead proceed to vocation training to raise the opportunities to get a job. Who attended higher education had support from the State or a relative who has to emigrate. To have a degree as the first member of the household was viewed as a family dream and a way to have a better life far from the parents' working class background, this turned into a 'postponed dream' to find a job. Furthermore, the unemployed young people in our study feel the pressure to not stop and continue enriching their curricula as a way to fight for a job. However, their education options are deeply dependent of what the economy dictates. They do not feel free to choose the study area they want but the one the labour market needs. At this concern human rights are not being foreseen. Education is considered merely as an instrumental value to promote productivity and sees the human being as a restrict notion of human capital. According to the capability approach education is relevant in terms of individual well-being and freedom, as well as reinforcing social cohesion, democracy and human rights by reducing poverty and inequality. On the one hand, education is a vehicle for accessing better jobs which potentially create opportunities and enlarge individual freedom 'to do and to be' and realise important dimensions of well-being and of critical and active citizenship, like to be able to communicate and to participate in community's life, and ability to pursue one's life goals. On the other hand, the lack of real opportunities constraints young people to enter in the labour market affecting different well-being domains of their lives like starting by the basic material living conditions and it is a waste of knowledge that could contribute to the economic growth of a country.

Young unemployed are losing confidence in how labour market institutions rule job conditions: offering low wages, few and precarious jobs. Their right to work is constrained by the requirement of previous work experience. They call on the responsibility towards society and the economic actors for not being aware of their potential, knowledge and willingness to work. The participants of the study find it unfair that work experience of 3 or 4 years is required without having a chance to prove their value. Search for a job is perceived as very frustrating because never have a reply from a direct contact with companies or when sending CVs.

There is an ambiguous feeling about how to overcome unemployment. On one hand the participants in our research view unemployment as a structural issue and do not believe in an economic recovery in the near future. It is not considered an individual matter to which they can be blamed for. On the other hand they are aware of the need to be flexible and to accept bad work conditions as a starting point. Some of the participants with a degree try to accept blue colour jobs and not give up of trying, to earn some money and fight for the work they want in another big city, or get more training. But even for unskilled jobs it is required to have experience. When there is an opportunity to start to work according to their qualifications, jobs are paid as unskilled jobs. Concerning to low qualified young unemployed had a precarious work experience. Broadly speaking emigration is a way to get a job mainly in the nursing area where there is a huge demand from companies with a guarantee of being employed. Nonetheless it is not a free option. Young people rather prefer to stay, but they feel forced to go abroad to have a job. For an unemployed male, the undeclared work is no longer an option due to the crisis, such as in the construction or in the restaurant sector. There is a common feeling of loss of dignity of the working conditions. It became much worse during the economic crisis with the increasing work hours without payment. The participants felt they are losing trust in the labour market and in people.

With regards social protection, all participants have some kind of social support due to their vulnerable context: family allowance; social minimum income; unemployed benefits; scholarships, social house; social canteens. The amount of the benefits was reduced during the economic crisis. The Social Insertion Income decreased and the rules have been even harder to access. The conditionality of the social income benefits produce the risk of restrained incentives to take up part-time work for instance.

In participants' words social investments are replaced for neo liberal policies. The priority in bank rescue and the cuts in social benefits provoke distrust in participants.

The scope of the relatives' diseases are very linked with the unemployed effects, as a multi-dimensional phenomenon that affects several dimensions of the human well-being (even it is not a linear relation between causes and consequences) like depression, domestic violence and divorce as well as health problems spread among family members. In these cases, the health expenses are a burden to the family budget, and the money available is driven to the priority cases. Despite the fact that there were made remarkable improvements in health over last decades, the increase of the emergency fees makes harder the access of the most vulnerable people to health care and worsened the working conditions of health professionals. It was stated that there had been cuts in health under the effectiveness discourse and attempt to maintain the same services, with a reduction of the health professionals.

Relating to housing participants shared some housing problems mainly dampness, missing heating conditions in winter and difficulties to pay the rent. Almost half of the participant group can pay the rent with their household's income and another half have social support to do it. In some cases, even having social support it is difficult to manage to pay the bills. The majority of the participants do not have money to afford a week's vacation over the past decade with all the expenses paid.

With regards to the negative social consequences leads to a growing distrust and loss of solidarity of young people are concerned, firstly they have no strong links with the neighbourhood broadly speaking. Who do have it, reports a common concern with being unemployed and supports with

courage to overcome this stage in life? The family support is the one that makes the difference to cope with adversity, emotional and financial help, supplies food or share holiday costs when are spent together. When there is not a strong family support, friends are stated as the most important help she/he can have. In the same line of thought it is considered the support given by social organisations. Young unemployed trust in the quality of services and care of people's lives. Some of them are engaged on voluntary work because they believe in the work done in helping vulnerable people. A different opinion regarding the public services is shared, like social security and the public employment service which are often viewed negatively. The participants considered public servants of social security as not being interested in the personal lives or committed to solve social problems by the way clarifications are provided. The social organisations are viewed as the ones who try to solve problems to whom are in need.

With regards to employment public servants, usually they share the opinion they do not give them the information they need, instead they tell them to visit the website to search for a job or to come in another time to have a special answer when will be developed awareness and information session. When this happens they felt not being respected as unemployed. They might have also other things or commitments. Regarding the active labour market policies, the training courses are not valued by companies it is seen as a government strategy to hide high unemployed rates. Training has a compulsory attendance and in participant's words is not allowed to choose the training course which fits best to their education or professional area. This is viewed as a matter of democracy and having the free will to choose and negotiate what suites best to their professional interests. In this sense they advocate that employment public services should invest in an individualised approach to provide more efficient answers.

The participants distrust politicians and political institutions. There is the common idea that politicians run public affairs by self-interest and to win elections, putting aside the people's life conditions. This idea is interiorised even when young people participate or participated in political youth parties and students unions. They claim that politicians must invest in people's lives like education and health.

The participants in our research mostly do not have money to pay for leisure time, holidays and basic needs. Their daily routines encompass struggling with economic worries.

In the current economic crisis the refugees came to light by expressing the few social rights to vulnerable people who already live in the country. At the same time it was drawing attention to the responsible role of media to inform people about this matter and considered as issue of human rights.

The meaning of Human Rights for young unemployed is in first hand: 'the right to work'; 'the right to be heard'; 'freedom of speech and not to be discriminated'. By facing the difficulties to get a job, some of them considered themselves as a resource to companies and therefore have to mobilise different skills and be constantly updated by training to face a competitive market. Therefore, human rights are taken as abstract nature and in near future will not be achieved in the context of economic crisis.

Finally, the negative impacts of the economic crisis in human rights, individual and collective capabilities challenge concrete policies of social investment should be addressed. This brings the need to strongly debate through a public discussion an alternative to the current liberal economic system. What extend this does not imply to think about other social contract by rethinking ethically the notion of human being in terms of effective human rights; by rethinking the role welfare state and the role of the effective social responsibility of companies; by rethinking the sustainable development of generation's well-being. Social investment change society for better and active inclusion and EU must truly put people in the heart of social policy.

To sum up, the young people who participated in our research ask from political actors and institutions a real investment in people to improve their lives in education and health in order to have hope in their future. Moreover, politicians, labour market and civil society should regard

young people as an investment and promote their inclusion in having access to jobs. They could participate in society and help to improve national economy as free people without being enforced to go abroad. The current research findings of the social damages of the crises on young unemployed will be developed further in the next stages of the RE-InVEST project. The special focus for Portugal will be on Active Labour Market Policies as well as Social Protection policies.

appendix 1 Participant Profile

Name	Age	Household	Education level	Period of unemployment	Employment situation	Social support	Informal labour
A	24	Father, mother and sister	Master on ecology and degree on biology [Mother – 9 th level; Father – 12 th level RVCC; sister finishing degree]	From September 2015	Search for first employment [Mother: Invalid/ unemployed six years ago. Worked: in an office; as a maid to take care of children and the house Father: Unemployed; Worked in electricity, distribution of those VHS tapes, factory footwear]	Parents have no income from work. Social benefits: disability allowance and social minimum income; total amount is less than the minimum wage. Food support average of 4 times per year Family support in hardest times	Mother: do cleaning one afternoon at the home of a relative. Father: doing odd jobs for people they know /electricity
B	24	Mother and sister (divorced parents)	Master and degree on psychology Mother: 12th level, Accounting, Professional Training; Sister: Finishing 12 ^o	From November 2015	Search for first employment Mother: manager of a small company of shoes. worked in insurance, accounting; but always was privy footwear	Mother: Salary slightly above minimum wage. Sister: Part-time work at week-ends in bar. Started working two months Receive food by a social organisation	Not applicable
C	18	Mother, one sister two brothers (single parent family)	secondary education/ training education on events organisation	From May 2015	Search for first employment. Volunteer in Associação Ecos Urbanos; Mother unemployed for a long time; Worked in footwear, hairdresser, in sales and the last work footwear, cleanings	Social Income by social security and receive food and other kind of support by a social organisation; the pension of my father's food and family allowance.	Not applicable
D	32	Son(2 years) and wife	9 years of education	From November 2013	Unemployed Work in different jobs (shoes and car factories; restaurants, vigilant guard and was unemployed between jobs Wife: unemployed; worked in restaurants	S289 €/Social minimum income (RSI) 35€/family allowance; social housing benefits	In restaurants, not recently
E	23	One brother and one sister, father is abroad Angola; mother abandoned family	Nursing degree; Brother: didn't finish college. He stopped is studies and began as vigilant in part-time, and put his studies aside and stood in the company. Sister: attending college	From June 2015	Search for first employment	Bother: Work in shifts/ higher than the minimum wage.	Not applicable

Name	Age	Household	Education level	Period of unemployment	Employment situation	Social support	Informal labour
F	22	Mother and sister (single parent family)	Secondary education/training education on beauty treatments and massage	From April 2015	Search for 1st employment		Works during weekends and sometimes days of the week in a hairdresser
G	20	Father, mother, sister, brother	Secondary education/training education on laboratory analysis; Father: 12 th level; Mother: 4 th level	From June 2015 Father: unemployed year ago	Search for 1st employment Father: retired for disability; worked on the boats during 5 years, the contract ended and was maintenance technician in a shopping Mother: employed at a shoe factory. Before worked on restaurant.	Food assistance per month (Habitar); per year (Ecos); Social Housing benefits (due to father disease) and Family allowance of the two brothers	Not applicable
H	23	Brother (father and mother dead)	9 Years of education/training education on bakery; Brother: 6 th level	From November 2014	Unemployed; Worked in a bakery during 7 years Brother: Employed (4 years) in Shoes industry; Father worked in a car factory	Minimum wage/ Food assistance/ social canteens lunch and dinner all days of the week	Few hours last week. (shoe factory) Exception
I**	26	Daughters and the father of her Daughters	9 Years of education/training education logistics	From 2009	Temporary jobs and training courses	Minimum Wage	Not applicable
J	24	Boyfriend and his sons	Secondary education/training education on events organisation and hairdresser. Attended professional courses: first aid in geriatrics; First aid Hydrotherapy; child health care; traditional Portuguese cuisine; and HCCP; Boyfriend: 9 th level	From April 2015 Longest job duration: 9 months vs shortest job duration: week to week	Temporary jobs in restaurant, café, textile factories; quality control; grape harvest; train company. Boyfriend: started work in December 2015; Was unemployed last year (full year); worked in restaurant.	Received unemployed benefits until 16 th Nov. it will ask for RSI Without social support; received unemployment allowance November 2015. Can ask for RSI in march (to receive it ask the three months of bank account or come some money there in the least, transfers ... as I received unemployment benefits have no right ...); Food assistance by social canteens (without choice) Resorted to banks, friends, acquaintances and family. All refused.	Not applicable
L***	20	Father, mother and sister	11 years of education	From March 2015	Temporary jobs in restaurant (6 months part-time) factory		Not applicable

Identification of the group: 10 participants (2 male, 8 female)

** I member gave up of participating

***Participant L got a job in a supermarket and on 4th December 2015 left the group

appendix 2 Drawing methodology

Visual methods (Drawings) reflecting the impact of unemployment (feelings, attitudes and consequences) in young people voices²⁶:

A | Delivering the curriculum on employer's hands. The meaning was a feeling of frustration in searching for a job.

B | A clock and a person with many doubts and questions

C | Three professional stages to get a job

²⁶ The young unemployed testimonies are here presented in summarized way. The long texts are transcribed and analysed.

D| on the different places where I worked in, I felt that after 2008 it has been more **distrust and the alarmism** undermined interpersonal relations, between colleagues due the insecurity felt by the possibility to become unemployed. Even when the job is not the most desirable it is better to have a job than being unemployed. *Observation:* HC didn't deliver his drawing

E| I have a degree (nursing) and this now is my life: I could go on the easiest way but at the same time is very difficult. What I'm talking about is to emigrate...

F| My drawing means confusion....

G| The drawing talks about me. What I want is working, have a driver's license and money.

I| The meaning of drawing is to have a better future (...) to have a salary to help my family.

J| I look at me and I see my situation. And this means which future my children will have? If now is like this, how will it be in a couple of years?

L| My drawing is all the problems that I have: without support from Town Council, from employment services.... Health problems without money ... I am exempted from paying health taxes but I have to do exams and I will have to pay. My boyfriend is ill on an arm and has to do an exam which costs 80€ but I don't have money to pay and I don't have any help.

M| I became unemployed and instead of staying at home I thought in ways of making a better world. So I signed up in a political party (socialist) and became a volunteer in the Red Cross to feel better but I'm still revolted with crisis. I think the crisis is the banks fault. The European institutions don't care and don't know how to manage the crisis and in the end, everything will end in a civil war. This is a bit exaggerated and I'm 'making' movies but it is my opinion.

appendix 3 Snake timetable: presentation of the most relevant austerity measures in Portugal from 2008 to 2015

2008 nationalisation of BPN

- 7.6% Unemployment rate
- 10% Youth NEET - 'Not in Education, Employment, or Training'. (15 -24 ages)
- 15% Youth NEET - 'Not in Education, Employment, or Training'. (25 -29 ages)
- 10.4% Youth work part-time
- 17.9% Risk of poverty
- 20,357 Permanent emigrants

2010 Privatisation of ANA (Portuguese Airports)

- 21% VAT rate
- 23% Tax rate
- 1% Increase of IRS 2nd and 3rd levels
- Cut in jobless benefits

2011 MAY - TROIKA in Portugal

- Sale of EDP to Chinese company
- 15% Rising prices in transport
- 5% to 23% Increase in VAT
- Increase in the price of natural gas and electricity
- The civil service wage was frozen
- Cut on pensions above 1500 euros
- Cuts in the health sector and public companies
- Cut the holiday and Christmas subsidies to civil servants and to all senior pensioners with pensions more than a thousand euros
- TROIKA requires cuts on holiday and Christmas bonuses in the private sector
- Increase user fees: 5 € in health centres and 20 € in the emergency room

2012 Public debt reached 126.6% of GDP

- Investment Reduction in Health
- 14,000 Students in the School Feeding Programme Strengthening
- 20, 8% Dropout rate
- 20.1% Youth working part-time
- New rules for mobility for public employees will suffer a significant cut in their remuneration
- 10% cut of unemployment benefits after six months and 540 days maximum grant
- The Christmas bonuses and vacation in the civil service will only be replaced in 2015
- 14.9% Unemployment rate
- 25 to 26.5% of capital taxation income from capital and capital gains

2013

- 500,000 Jobs destroyed since 2008-2013
- 19.5% of people at risk of poverty
- 3.5% of its population emigrated between 2011 and 2013
- 31.6% Child poverty rate
- 19.5% Risk of poverty
- 17.7% Unemployment rate
- Increase from 35 to 40 hours per week in the Civil Service
- Increase the retirement age to 66 years
- Youth Average Age of leaving the parental home (M = 30 and F = 29 years)
- 15% Youth NEET - not in education, not working (15 -24 ages)
- 20% Youth NEET - not in education, not working (25 -29 ages)

JUNE 2014 | ADJUSTMENT PROGRAM END OF ECONOMIC | TROIKA

- VAT rises to 23.25%
- Single Social Tax of workers rises to 11.2%
- Minimum wage rises to 505 euros
- 35% Youth unemployment rate
- 49,572 Permanent emigrants

2015

- 12% Unemployment rate
- 60% of the unemployed are long-lasting no more than 12 months and 46% for more than 24 months
- 19% of workers with temporary work contracts
- Portugal 9th most unequal country in the OECD/May
- 592,000 beneficiaries lose access to social benefits for children between October 2010 and August

Adjustment program: reduction of expenditure involved:

- Cut of EUR 500 million per year in health
- Cut pensions above € 1,500
- Cuts in education 175 million per year

appendix 4 Snake timetable: the most relevant events of all group from 2008 to 2015 | Group exercise

appendix 5 Snake timetable: the most relevant individual episodes from 2008 to 2015 | Individual exercise

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Social disinvestment and vulnerable groups in Europe in the aftermath of the financial crisis

The case of the Romanian diaspora

Cristina Chert, Patrick Van den Nieuwenhof

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Contents

List of tables	7
List of figures	9
Preface	11
1. Introduction: stages in Romanian migration	13
2. Context: the economic crisis in Romania	18
2.1 The economic crisis in Romania (overview 2007-2012)	18
2.2 Anti-crisis and austerity measures in Romania	19
3. Theoretical and methodological approach	22
3.1 The Open Network for community development (TON): historical background	22
3.2 The Open Network for community development (TON): contemporary work	23
3.3 Methods used for the RE-INVEST Work Package 3	24
3.3.1 Literature review	24
3.3.2 Methodology	24
3.3.3 Focus groups and interviews	26
4. Selected biographies	29
4.1 H. D. (Romanian living in Belgium)	29
4.2 C. R. (Berbești, Romania)	31
5. The impact of the crisis on Romanian migrants	36
5.1 Scope of analysis	36
5.2 Decrease in inward remittances as a consequence of the crisis	36
5.3 Changing migration patterns due to the crisis	37
5.3.1 Returners	37
5.3.2 Leaving for another country	40
5.4 Syndrome Italy or the deterioration of personal capabilities	42
5.5 Impact of migration on community services	42
5.6 Impact of migration on family structures	43
5.6.1 Children – social orphans	43
5.6.2 Orphaned elderly people	44
6. Conclusion: towards entangled capabilities	45
6.1 Entangling capabilities	45
6.2 Entangled capabilities promoted by the home country Romania	46
6.3 Entangled capabilities promoted by host countries	47
6.4 First steps towards social investments	48
Bibliography	49

List of tables

Table 1.1	Evolution Romanian population by residence	13
Table 1.2	Lifting of the restrictions on the free movement of Romanian workers	16
Table 2.1	Economic indicators before, during and after the economic crisis	18
Table 3.1	Overview of interviews Berbești	27
Table 5.1	Main nationalities of foreign population in Belgium	41

List of figures

Figure 1.1	Evolution fertility Romania 1950-2020	14
Figure 1.2	Rate of natural increase per 1.000 population Romania	14
Figure 1.3	Emigration by % and country	17
Figure 3.1	Overview Flemish Romanian local groups since 1989	22
Figure 3.2	Overview Walloon Romanian local groups since 1989	23
Figure 3.3	Structure of Romanian Belgian collaboration	24
Figure 4.1	Evolution persons with monthly salary Berbești	32
Figure 4.2	Difference % domicile - residence Berbești	33
Figure 4.3	Timeline C.R. Berbești	34
Figure 5.1	Evolution of inward remittances to Romania 2006-2014	36
Figure 5.2	Numbers and rates national and non-national immigrants in Romania, 2008-2013	37
Figure 5.3	Romanian migration from and to Germany	37
Figure 5.4	Migration flow Dumitresti 2005-2014	38
Figure 5.5	Romanian migration from and to Spain	41
Figure 5.6	Number of Romanian in Belgium 1999-2015	42
Figure 5.7	Evolution of leaving Romanian doctors	43

Preface

This report is prepared in the framework of the Europe H2020 project ‘Rebuilding an inclusive, value based Europe of solidarity and trust through social investments’ (RE-InVEST). The project aims to evaluate the social investment strategy of the European Commission implemented in 2013 in response to the social damage of the financial crisis in 2008. The RE-InVEST consortium assesses the social damage of the crisis from human rights and capability based approaches with an eye to those vulnerable groups affected the most by the crisis in the 12 countries (and 13 regions) covered by the consortium. The analyses are carried out by the local partners, who consist of NGOs and/or researchers.¹ The RE-InVEST consortium has jointly developed the PAHRCA-methodology that combines principles of Participatory Action research with Human Rights and Capability Approaches. This qualitative, participatory research does not generate representative results but rather aims at deepening the understanding of the economic, social, cultural and political impacts of the crisis on the lives of vulnerable people by giving them a voice.

In comparison to other European countries involved in this project, Romania has some specific characteristics. The shift to a democratic governance at the end of 1989 is still young. The scars of the communist regime are still visible in the landscape such as huge living blocks and declining industries, the so called pearls of communism. Romania didn’t have a tradition of welfare state: structures are missing and the implementation of solidarity based concepts is very sensitive because of the connotation to forced societal involvement during the communist ‘Golden Age’. Social economy for example is still associated with communist cooperatives and civil society brings back memories to the forced volunteering work for the community. Despite a high economic growth, one of the highest in the EU, the country is facing challenges such as a high rate of people at risk of poverty (around 40%), a high degree of absolute poverty (around 10%), a growing number of in work poor (20%) and few job opportunities. In this context the Ceausescu’s New Man became an individual survivor. As a strategy to overcome these difficulties Romanians started to migrate in order to find better living conditions for themselves and others. For a long time the side effects were not taken serious and no coherent policy was developed. Only recently (February 2016), Romanian president Klaus Iohannis stated that: *‘the Romanian Diaspora is a veritable asset for the country, adding that he would like Romanians to stop leaving the country because of hardships, leaving just because they choose to do so instead. We are often talking about the loss that the Romanians’ departure abroad represents. In a different approach, however, we can also see the opportunity offered by the presence of a strong Diaspora abroad. Well engaged by a careful state, it can become an important asset for the development and modernisation of Romania, veritable capital that can be put to good use. The Romanian state has to serve all Romanians alike, from within and without the country’*. He added that a new framework, one in which attention toward the Diaspora would become a national priority, will have to be translated into public policies, programs and projects.²

The Romanian national report focuses on: the impact of migration on the Romanian society and the impact of the crisis on Romanian migrants/migration. In the first part a short introduction is giving concerning the various migration waves. The second part deals with the financial crisis of 2008/2009 and how Romania was affected. Before going to the biographies (part 4) and the analysis of the consequence of crisis related problem in contemporary Romanian migration trends (part 5), the report presents the organisation and the methodology (part 3). Finally conclusions with references to the capability approach and policy recommendations are formulated. This report would not have been possible without the input of so many

1 <http://www.re-invest.eu/>

2 <http://www.nineoclock.ro/president-iohannis-deplores-diasporas-unwillingness-to-return-proposes-partnership-consultative-council-promised-to-diaspora-to-make-first-step-in-fulfilling-its-mission/>

people. We would like to express our gratitude to the participants for sharing their 'biographical narrative' with us about their experiences with life in precarious financial circumstances.

1. Introduction: stages in Romanian migration

Huge (e)migration and a comparable internal migration can be seen as one of the strategies to overcome personal, social, economic and political needs. Different theories on the reason why people are migrating have been developed.³ A returning conclusion is that migration has a relative big impact on personal and community development, both in a positive as negative way. From an historical point of view Romania was and is a country of emigration. The 2011 resident population decreased by 1.559.333 persons compared to the previous census (2002). This illustrates the declining trend of the last 2 decades. In comparison with 1992 the Romanian resident population decreases with almost 12%.⁴ The external migration, a low fertility rate and a declining natural growth are the main causes for this trend.

Table 1.1 Evolution Romanian population by residence

Year	Population	Difference
1948	15872624	
1956	17489450	+10.2%
1966	19103163	+9.2%
1977	21559910	+12.9%
1992	22760449	+5.6%
2002	21680974	-4.7%
2005	21623849	-0.3%
2009	21469959	-0.7%
2011	20121641	-6.3%

3 See for example: MATICHESCU, Marius Lupsa, The Romanian migration: development of the phenomenon and the part played by the immigration policies of European countries, In: Revista de cercetare si interventie sociala, 2015, 50, p. 225-238.

4 Based on the national census of 2011: <http://www.recensamantromania.ro/>

Figure 1.1 Evolution fertility Romania 1950-2020

Source UN Population Division

Figure 1.2 Rate of natural increase per 1.000 population Romania

Source UN Population Division

Through more than 100 years of Romanian (e)migration different waves and motives can be distinguished. For the report a summarised overview is given.

First stage: the pre-1989 migration⁵

In the beginning of the 20th century a considerable part of the migratory flows was directly or indirectly connected with ethnic minorities. These minorities moved to states to which they had historical ties (mainly Germany and Hungary), both in reaction to general and ethnic-based discrimination in Romania, and because they hoped for a safer and better life in those states. During communist rule (1947-1989), Romanian authorities exercised restrictive exit policies. Despite this, a relatively high amount of permanent, legal emigration took place under the regime. Ethnic minorities (Jews, Germans and Hungarians) were clearly over-represented among the group of people who legally emigrated from Romania during communist rule.

Second stage: 1990-1993

Immediately after the fall of the communist regime, passport administration and international travel were liberalised. Although some measures to limit international travel were taken: taxes were imposed on border crossings and those leaving had to prove that they were in possession of a certain amount of money. However, none of these measures drastically reduced the international mobility of Romanian citizens. In the first three years after the fall of communism 170.000 persons legally emigrated from Romania. Again, ethnic minorities were overrepresented especially Germans and Hungarians. The rate of emigration was 3%.

Third stage: 1993-2001

Between 1993 and 1996 Western European countries had a restrictive visa regime for Romanian citizens, whereby westward migration had relative low levels. In this time Hungary, Turkey and Israel were destination countries. At the end of the 1990s, highly qualified, young emigrants obtained long-term, legal residence in various European countries, but mostly in the USA and Canada. Also more and more unskilled or poorly qualified persons from rural areas began seeking (mostly temporary and/or irregular) migratory arrangements with large numbers of workers going to Italy and Spain. The rate of emigration between 1996 and 2001 was 7%. In 2000 965.500 Romanians or 5% of the population is living abroad.

Fourth stage: 2002-2007

On the 1st of January 2002 when countries included in the Schengen space removed visa requirements for Romanian citizens, making a valid passport sufficient for entry. The rate of emigration increased to 28%. In 2005 1.694.500 Romanians or 8.5% of the population is living abroad.

Fifth stage: 2007-2011

Since Romania is part of the European Union (2007), free movement of Romanian workers was foreseen. However the national governments of the countries that were already part of the EU could decide whether they wanted to apply restrictions for a maximum transitional period of up to 7 years.⁶ From the 1st of January 2014 restrictions are lifted in all EU27 member states.

5 <http://focus-migration.hwwi.de/Romania.2515.0.html?&L=1>

6 <http://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?catId=466&>, http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-14-1_en.htm

Table 1.2 Lifting of the restrictions on the free movement of Romanian workers

2007	2009	2012	2014
Bulgaria	Denmark	Italy	Austria
Cyprus	Greece	Ireland	Belgium
Czech Republic	Hungary		France
Estonia	Portugal		Germany
Finland			Luxemburg
Latvia			Malta
Lithuania			Netherlands
Poland			Spain
Slovakia			UK
Slovenia			
Sweden			

Source EU Commission

The movement to West-European destinations has increased because of the improved access to many labour markets, both low and high skilled workers. The transition from a centrally planned economy to an effectively functioning market economy during the past two and a half decades provided another impetus (low employment rate, low wages, poverty) for Romanians to search for employment abroad. In 2010 the World Bank estimated that 2.769.053 Romanians are living abroad or 12% of the population.⁷

Sixth stage: 2012-...

As seen in the former stage, restrictions on Romanian workers were lifted in 2014 in the EU27 member states. In the same period the impact of the crisis on Romania and on migration can be seen. In 2012 the amount of emigrants and immigrants (mostly nationals) from and to Romania and a changing migration flow pattern can be ascertained. In 2013 the World Bank estimated that 3.430.476 Romanians are living abroad or 16% of the population.⁸

Conclusions

The above mentioned data are referring to permanent migration. Official data on the dynamics of temporary emigration are very limited. Although Romania can be called a country of emigration, it's certainly not the only European country facing emigration. The Baltic states, Bulgaria, Malta, Portugal and Ireland are in the same position of a high share of emigration.⁹

7 World Bank, Bilateral Migration Matrix 2010.

8 World Bank, Bilateral Migration Matrix 2013.

9 http://www.economica.net/romania-o-pata-rosie-pe-harta-migratiei-in-europa-3-4-milioane-de-romani-traiesc-oficial-in-alte-tari_122469.html

Figure 1.3 Emigration by % and country

Source Economica.net

The main European countries of destination for Romanian emigrants are:

- Italy – 46%¹⁰
- Spain – 34%¹¹
- Germany – 7%¹²
- UK – 4%

The high share of migration towards Italy and Spain can be explained by economic reasons and inspired linguistically. The search for job opportunities and/or better paid jobs can be clearly seen in the fact that in the age group 20-40 around 25-30% of the population is migrated.¹³

10 <http://www.istat.it/it/archivio/186978>

11 Instituto Nacional de Estadística: Population Figures at 1 July 2015, http://www.ine.es/en/prensa/np948_en.pdf

12 Zensusdatenbank - Ergebnisse des Zensus 2011

13 Census Romania 2002 - 2011

2. Context: the economic crisis in Romania¹⁴

2.1 The economic crisis in Romania (overview 2007-2012)

Romania was admitted as a full member of the European Union in 2007. At that time, the country was led by a centre-right coalition. Although Romania had been experiencing vigorous economic growth for several years, society was still affected by inequality and poverty. And although the economy had high rates of growth with an average annual increase of 6,8% in 2004-2008, most of that expansion was generated either by investments in non-marketable sectors or by the consumption of durable goods, which were mainly imported. Romania was directly affected by the crisis in the last quarter of 2008, when the evolution of economic indicators took a sudden turn for the worse. Industrial production and domestic consumption accelerated their declining tendency and budget revenues collapsed.

Table 2.1 Economic indicators before, during and after the economic crisis

	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
GDP growth rate in %								
RO	7.1	6.8	-5.6	-1.0	1.1	2.4	3.0	2.9
EU28	3.1	0.5	-4.4	2.1	1.8	-0.5	0.2	1.4
General government gross debt: annual data in % of gross domestic product (GDP)								
RO	12.7	13.2	23.2	29.9	34.2	37.4	38.0	39.9
EU28	57.8	61.0	73.0	78.4	81.0	83.8	85.5	86.8
Unemployment rate in %								
RO	6.4	5.6	6.5	7.0	7.2	6.8	7.1	6.8
EU28	7.2	7.0	9.0	9.6	9.7	10.5	10.9	10.2
Inflation rate: annual average rate of change in %								
RO	4.9	7.9	5.6	6.1	5.8	3.4	3.2	1.4
EU28	2.4	3.7	1.0	2.1	3.1	2.6	1.5	0.5
Final consumption aggregates (volumes): % change over previous period								
RO	9.6	8.7	-7.4	-1.3	1.0	1.5	0.7	-
EU28	2.1	0.9	-0.6	0.9	0.2	-0.6	0.1	-

Source Eurostat

¹⁴ The context is based on a literature review of:

- BUREAN, Tom; BADESCU, Gabriel, The effects of economic crisis and austerity measures on political culture in Romania, Cluj, 2013, 20 p.
- CARITAS EUROPE, Crisis monitoring report 2014. The European crisis and its human cost, a call for fair alternatives and solutions, 2014, 116 p (Romania: p 56-).
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The crisis had a big impact on the labour market. The layoffs in industry, construction and commerce totalled around 315.000 employees at the end of 2009, or over 85% of the total redundancies in the economy. Because of the restrictive definition of unemployment, those registered and having a social benefit, the unemployment rate of +/- 7% seems to be low. The employment rate or persons with a stable monthly income is not higher than 62%. The share of long-term unemployment is high: 45.3%. It has risen significantly from 2011: 41.9%. Youth unemployment is high: 22.8% in 2012. Furthermore, Romania has a high share of NEETs (young people neither in employment nor in education or training): 16.8% of the population aged 15-24 in 2012). One of the consequences is that purchasing power declined. While at the end of 2008 the net annual average salary in the economy experienced an annual increase of 23%, it has dropped to 7.7% in 2009 and to 1.8% in 2010. This resulted in a decrease of budget revenues, with a direct impact on the social security budget, which experienced a deficit of 2.3% of GDP in 2011. This situation only partially reflects the effects of the economic crisis, due to the problem of a high financial dependency ratio.

2.2 Anti-crisis and austerity measures in Romania

The response of the Romanian government to the economic crisis came late, but the austerity measures were among the most severe in Europe. The main effects of the global financial crisis became evident only in late 2008 and Romania was forced by circumstances to sign a Stand-By Agreement with the IMF in 2009. However, the key austerity measures were enforced only starting in 2010, when the impact of recession had become alarming: high unemployment rates, an uncontrollable budget deficit and a drastic decline in domestic demand. The political promoter of the austerity measures was a centre-right government. The policy response to the crisis, consisting of austerity measures and structural reforms, stemmed from a combination of international pressure (from the IMF), the doctrine of the centre-right governing coalition and lobbying by some major social and economic stakeholders. The austerity measures (July 2010) focused mainly on public employees and social welfare beneficiaries, while the structural 'reforms' encompassed a broad range of areas, from the labour market to social welfare and health care, as well as the privatisation of several Romanian companies:

- the standard rate of VAT increased from 19% to 24%, even though Romania already had a relatively very high proportion of indirect taxation;
- there have been changes to welfare, including cuts to the child-raising allowance, to unemployment benefit and reductions have been made in facilities for pensioners;
- a reduction in the public wage bill amounting to 8.7% of GDP in 2010;
- a nominal freeze in pensions related to end 2009 levels (except for minimum pensions which could be indexed);
- the cut to public wages in 2010 was 25% but this was partially reversed in 2011 when 15% was restored;
- cutting 15% off pensions, but this was declared unconstitutional;
- increased prices for utilities: gas prices for domestic and non-domestic consumers increased by 5% and 10% and electricity prices increased by 5%;
- a Social Assistance Law which consolidated 54 categories of social benefit into 9 groups. Changes enacted by the new consisted in imposing stricter tests for resources, defining the level of welfare benefits based on the social reference indicator instead of the minimum wage as before.¹⁵ Transferring the financial burden to the local government authorities by creating the social security fund, 30% from the state budget and 70% of local budget amounts, resulted in the widening of the gap between the poorer and richer areas of Romania;
- a Labour Code was implemented in March 2011 providing for more flexibility in employment relationships, including in fixed term contracts and providing extensions of probationary periods;

¹⁵ The reference social indicator in 2011 was 110 euro, the guaranteed minimum income was 140 euro in 2011.

- a new Social Dialogue Law (Summer 2010) imposed certain legal obstacles on trade unions by introducing stricter criteria for obtaining representativeness, complicating the administrative procedures for registration of new trade unions and eliminating the so-called professional trade unions, which were the only legal possibility for employees to establish a trade union. National collective negotiations and the national collective agreement were also eliminated;
- a process of restructuring public sector employment: in 2010 78.700 jobs were terminated, of which 60.610 were government positions, representing 55% of the total government positions eliminated in the EU;
- structural reforms also included the health care system. The cost cuts caused 67 hospitals to be shut down in 2011. A draft bill aiming to radically change the health care system was put up for public debate at the beginning of 2012: health care insurance was to be managed by private companies, while the public hospitals were either to be turned into foundations or privatised. The draft bill caused a wave of public disapproval culminating in street protests. As a result, the draft bill was abandoned, but the reform program is still silent present.

The austerity measures had negative social consequences, including persistently high unemployment, a low employment rate and a low sense of wellbeing among the population. The growing social tension and dissatisfaction caused by the austerity measures culminated in a wave of protests in January 2012, leading to the resignation of the government and the appointment of a new technocrat cabinet. The technocrat government was dismissed in April 2012, following a motion of no confidence promoted by the opposition. It was replaced by a coalition formed by social democrats, liberals and conservatives, which maintained unchanged the agreement signed with the IMF. After the elections of November 2012 and the appointment of a new social-democrat – liberal - conservative government in December 2012 some social improvement measures have been introduced:

- an increase of public sector wages so as to restore them to pre-crisis levels;
- a 4% increase in pensions;
- measures to reduce payment periods in healthcare to 60 days;
- an increase in the minimum wage from 700 lei/month (160 euro) in 2012 to 975 lei/month (+/- 220 euro) in January 2015, 1050 lei/month (+/- 236 euro) in July 2015 and 1250 lei/month (+/- 285 euro) in May 2016;
- people who are very poor in retirement (living on less than 700 lei/month) can access a program compensating them for 90% of the costs of drugs;
- in June 2015, the VAT on food items was cut from 24% to 9%. In January 2016, the general VAT was lowered from 24% to 20% and the tax on dividends will also be reduced. Further tax reductions are planned to take effect in 2017;
- the Parliament passed a law in November 2015 to raise public sector wages by 10% for groups that were not yet covered by previously-approved wage increases.

After the resignation of the government due to mass protests against generalised corruption linked to the Club Colectiv tragedy (fire accident in a nightclub with 63 deaths and 148 injured persons), an entirely technocrat government was appointed on the 10th November 2015. The new government, in general, implements further the program of the former government. The IMF's discontent with Romania's fiscal plans already led the international body not to extend its Stand-By Arrangement (SBA) with Romania after the last SBA expired in September 2015. New parliament elections will be held in November 2016. After a period of hope when Romania entered the EU in 2007, disappointment grew rapidly due to the financial crisis and the subsequent severe measures. Capabilities came under threat and migration was increasing:

- a. What are determining factors to (e)migrate? In other words what are push and pull factors?
- b. Does migration improve the capabilities of people? Fulfilment of expectations?
- c. What's the impact on the capabilities of family members, friends and communities confronted with migration? What's the relation between individual capabilities and those from others? Is the actual stress on labour mobility taking into account the social consequences?
- d. Did the crisis have an impact Romanian migrants?

3. Theoretical and methodological approach

3.1 The Open Network for community development (TON): historical background

The Open Network for community development (TON) is a Romanian umbrella organisation, which gathers local women, men and youth movements and stimulates the creation of social medical centers, stimulates social economy initiatives and involves citizens in local decisions. To fully understand some methodological choices, it's necessary to explain the history of the creation of TON.

After being elected as general secretary of the Romanian Communist Party in 1965 and consolidating his power by becoming president of the State Council, communist dictator Nicolae Ceausescu planned a large scale destruction of Romanian villages and municipalities. This communist systematisation ended a respectful relationship with the countryside and was the largest European destruction in peacetime. By the end of the 80s of the 20th century, together with the rising internal and foreign protests, Adoption Villages Romania was set up in Belgium (Flanders, 1989) to safeguard the destruction of rural communities in Romania. Started as a protest movement and a humanitarian action, the organisation evolved towards an equal bottom up collaboration. Because of the different approach in local and regional collaboration between Romania and Belgium, the word Adoption changed into Action in 2005. This resulted also in the creation of a Romanian sister organisation The Open Network for community development in April 2012.

By the beginning of 1990 around 350 Belgian towns adopted a Romanian village. In the same year on the European level around 4500 towns adopted a Romanian village. The following two figures are giving an impression on how much and where Belgian-Romanian local collaborations were created since 1989.

Figure 3.1 Overview Flemish Romanian local groups since 1989

Figure 3.3 Structure of Romanian Belgian collaboration

TON as an umbrella organisation became the engine for the further development of the civil society in Romania in a spirit of collaboration with Belgian partners. In this context quite a lot of local groups involved in TON are facing a migration trend in their community. Because of the many faces of migration, TON has chosen to focus on migration in Work Package 3 of the RE-InVEST project.

3.3 Methods used for the RE-InVEST Work Package 3

3.3.1 Literature review

In the first stage of the implementation of Work Package 3 a literature review was conducted. Specific attention was given to articles and publication about Romanian emigrants, the impact of the crisis on migration and returning Romanian migrants. An extensive bibliography can be found in Appendix 1.

3.3.2 Methodology

RE-InVEST aims to provide a philosophical, institutional and empirical foundation on the Social Investment Package, in order to enhance a more solidary, inclusive and trustful Europe. To reach this goal the theoretical and methodological approach proposed is through the intersection of capability and human rights approaches based on participatory action research.

The *Capability Approach* (CA) developed by Amartya Sen (1999) brought a new framework towards economic development by focus his analysis in what people are able to be (or to do) to achieve their well-being

or quality of life beyond income factors. So the core issue for Sen is not only what individuals choose, but the choices that they would make if they had the abilities/freedom to lead their lives the way they want to. Examples of capabilities can be: to be able to hold a decent job and not any job but a decent job; to be able to have leisure activities; to learn valuable things and be able to have education and be free of any kind of violence. So, quality of life doesn't depend only on income. Income is one of many variables, like trust in democracy, the political institutions, in civil society, in the neighbourhood, in the household. In addition, CA has an intrinsic value quite different from the practical approach more concerned with the economic growth, GDP, which potentially generates decent jobs. Speaking about human dignity and about what people consider they need and should have it is very important to diagnosis social impacts on vulnerable people: 'What am I able to do and be?'

The *Capability Approach* as developed by Sen (1999) and Nussbaum (2011) defines the person's wellbeing in terms of beings and doings (achievements/functionings) a person achieves and her/his capability to choose among different combinations of such functionings. By functionings may be considered the basic needs as having shelter; health care; education or more complex features such as self-respect and well-being. To live a life that persons want to lead and have reason to value, the resources and conversation factors are central components. In other words, the perception that the individual has of quality of life depends not only of his personality or features like age or gender but also of the resources available and the cultural values of the society where he/she is living in.

So, resources can be defined as material conditions such as income, goods and services, which have an instrumental value and are the means needed to reach functionings. Convert factors help to converting resources into doing and wellbeing. There are a range of conversion factors: personal, social and environmental that can constrain or enable people's capabilities. Personal conversion factors are such as skills and body features; social conversion factors are like social norms, laws, customs and traditions and social institutions and policies; finally environmental conversation factors are such as climate and geography. The achieved functionings are the way people live to be free to be able to choose things to value in life e.g. to be able to choose a decent job.

Capabilities and human rights are directly linked by describing the core values of well-being and a good life. Besides human rights have been developed through important historical periods, the 20th century established key international human rights instruments namely: the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) adopted by the United Nations in 1948 which states in Article 25 that 'Everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and family, including food, clothing, housing and medical care and the necessary social services, and the right to security in the event of unemployment, sickness, disability, widowhood, old age or other lack of live hood in circumstances beyond his control'. In the international and national legal framework of UDHR, the states are obliged to ensure the effective exercise of the right to protection against poverty and social exclusion. As it is pointed out in the Council of Europe Revised European Social Charter, Article 30, the States must take measures 'to promote the effective access of persons who live or risk living in a situation of social exclusion or poverty, as well as their families, to, in particular, employment, housing, training, education, culture and social and medical assistance'.

Human rights are inalienable rights and fundamental entitlements by a human being as prepolitical status prior membership to a state. The Human Rights approach includes a universal and holistic perspective of the human being in terms of civil and political rights and the social and economic rights. They set up the standard of living conditions and the deprivation of needs can be as a denial of rights. In this context the Human rights discourse can emancipate and transform through collective action and participation of who is excluded by their own rights.

The Merging of Knowledge (MOK) approach involves a collective of mixed groups of researchers the co-construction of knowledge about poverty and social exclusion by discussion and reflection: people who experience poverty and social exclusion in first hand to talk about their needs and their resilience. To bring a more complete and broader knowledge it is crucial to have their participation and their own voice as co-constructors of Knowledge. Academics and scholars should assume the role to them to '*Explain to us rather,*

Help us to think'. This process helps to raise awareness about their situation of rights denial and implies to the solution of the problem and policy recommendations. The knowledge of social workers who work with vulnerable people is a core part of the MOK perspective.

RE-InVEST research approach is a Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach (PAHRCA) developed in seven steps): 1. Identify and meet partner NGO/gatekeeper, 2. Preliminary 'meet ups' (for trust building if necessary), 3. First meeting with participants – trust building, 4. Developmental: implement developmental human rights & capability approach, 5. Inquiry/data gathering, 6. Identifying patterns (key issues and themes of concern to the group) and 7. Undertake action/outcome using one or a combination of approaches.

3.3.3 Focus groups and interviews

In the TON network two communities with a strong migrating history and population were chosen, namely Dumitresti (village) and Berbești (city). In addition some smaller testimonies are integrated. People from local authorities and civil society were involved in the focus groups. Main purpose was to map the impact of the economic crisis on the community and migrants. Based on these focus groups persons were selected for an in-depth interview. Because of migration of Romanians from Spain to Northern countries, an interview was done with a Romanian worker who migrated from Spain to Belgium. For Dumitresti 10 returning migrants were selected to do a snake in which they drawn their personal life story since the crisis. The time of migration was 2007-2012 and the countries of destination were Greece and Italy.

For Berbești an in depth qualitative analysis was conducted during a week of field research in April 2016. In total 26 persons were interviewed. To structure the interview, people could draw their own personal timeline starting from 2006. The evolution of how they perceived their personal life is presented in the following table. Parts of the interviews will be used to illustrate some societal trends. Whereas the point of view in Dumitresti was focused on returners, in Berbești a more mixed group was selected with a focus on their opinion about migration.

Table 3.1 Overview of interviews Berbești

Name	Profession	Gender	Age	Migration abroad	Relatives abroad	< 2008	2008-2012	2015	Salary < 2008	Euro 2015
AMZULOIU Simona	Teacher Geography/History	F		No	Yes	Satisfactory	Good	Very good	200	NA
CATRINA Marius	Bank Manager	M	41	No	Yes	Good	Good	Very good	175	800
CEBOTARI Liliana	Deputy director school Teacher English	F	40	Yes	No	Good	Satisfactory	Good	NA	NA
CHELCEA Mariana Nadia	Jurist Town Hall	F	36	No	NA	Very good	Bad	Very bad	300	250
CUMPANASOIU Milorad Ioan	Manager Mine	M	48	No	NA	Satisfactory	Bad	Very good	NA	NA
DAL POS Luigino	Company manager	M	72	Yes	Yes	Satisfactory	Good	Bad	NA	NA
DINCA Melania Ramona	PR Town Hall	F	39	No	NA	Very bad	Very bad	Bad	300	220
DINICA Mihaela	Teacher French	F		Yes	Yes	Very good	Satisfactory	Very good	300	480
GIOGA Dumitru	Vice Mayor	M	65	No	No	Bad	Very bad	Satisfactory	NA	NA
GULICA Florea	Forest Engineer	M	56	No	Yes	Good	Good	Bad	1300	550
GULICA Silviu	Consular Identity Cards	M	35	No	Yes	Very good	Very bad	Very good	300	500
MATEESCU Adina	Teacher primary school	F	38	Yes	No	Bad	Very bad	Satisfactory	220	500
MATEESCU Lucia	Doctor	F	60	No	No	Satisfactory	Bad	Bad	800	400
MATEIESCU Alexandru	Public Achisions inspector	M	29	NA	NA	Satisfactory	Bad	Satisfactory	300	200
MATEIESCU Sebastian	University assistant PhD	M	32	Yes	No	Good	Good	Very good	NA	NA

Name	Profession	Gender	Age	Migration abroad	Relatives abroad	< 2008	2008-2012	2015	Salary < 2008	Euro 2015
MUTU Iuliana	Unemployed	F	28	Yes	Yes	Very bad	Good	Good	300	0
PARAUSANU Rodica	Unemployed	F	47	No	No	Good	Bad	Very bad	220	100
PETRESCU Adrian	Ambulance driver	M	30	No	No	Satisfactory	Good	Good	150	200
PETRESCU Ana-Maria	Bank Officer	F	28	No	No	Satisfactory	Good	Very good	0	210
RADUCAN Mirel	Team Chef Mine	M	45	No	Yes	Bad	Satisfactory	Very good	600	900
RUSIE Constantin	Unemployed	M	39	Yes	Yes	Bad	Very bad	Very bad	NA	NA
RUSIE Mihaela	Referent Identity Cards	F	38	NA	NA	Very bad	Very bad	Bad	150	220
STANICA Ana-Maria	Teacher French	F		Yes	Yes	Satisfactory	Very good	Good	NA	NA
ZAMFIROIU Adina	Personal Assistant Mayor	F	26	Yes	Yes	Bad	Very bad	Very good	220	220
ZAMFIROIU Cristina	Inspector Identity Cards	F	30	No	No	Satisfactory	Good	Satisfactory	NA	250
ZAMFIROIU Silvia	Nurse	F	60	No	No	Good	Bad	Good	220	400

4. Selected biographies

4.1 H. D. (Romanian living in Belgium)

February 13 2016 – H. D. is welcoming me with open arms in his house in As (province of Limburg in Belgium). A man 41 years old, married and 1 child. At the time of the interview H. D. is working for a car service company and on the first sight everything seems to go well. H. D. also doubted a bit to tell his story because ‘it’s not that spectacular’. But once he starts to tell his life journey, the ‘normal’ situation is putted in a completely new light. A story of vulnerability, permanent insecurity and struggling to survive starts more the 25 years ago. H. D. was growing up in a small village, named Zagra, in the county of Bistrita-Nasaud in the Northern part of Romania. Zagra is composed of five villages: Alunişul, Perişor, Poienile Zagrei, Suplai and Zagra. At the time of his birth the village counted 4.504 inhabitants.¹⁶

The communist period (1974-1989)

During his childhood the communists were ruling the country: ‘When looking back to this period I have a double feeling. At that time, being the only child in the household, my parents had a job as teacher and had a medium salary. In that time we had our own garden for vegetables and fruits and we were growing some small animals such as chickens. So we were not really depending on what was available in the shops. Certainly during the last years of communism the shops were empty and we had to wait in the line when products arrived. Although there was no freedom of expression, we had a rather decent life and I had the opportunity to go to school. I know this sounds like a contradiction: in that time there was money in our state controlled CEC bank account but there were no products to buy. By the way today in Romania it seems to be the opposite: no money on the account and too much products that are on the market. On the other hand the communists were also controlling this area with an iron hand, while our village Zagra was safeguarded of collectivisation and forced cooperative work, people had to pay high amounts of agriculture taxes to the regime. This led to a pauperizing of the population and youngsters took the decision to go to work in the nearby industrialised city Bistrita. Again this has a double side: there was a 100% employment, but in quite a lot of cases also forced labour and not adapted to the competences of people. In the mid of the 1980’s when I started to become an adolescent, you could see and feel that societal problems were growing.’ In the 1980s the economy collapsed completely and a dark period started for the Romanian population, a period that was also known as the 3 F’s period: Frica - anxiety, Foame - hunger, Frig - cold. As an answer to the food shortages Ceausescu initiated a ‘Rational Eating Program’, being a ‘scientific plan’ for limiting the calorie intake for the Romanians, claiming that the Romanians were eating too much. It tried to reduce the calorie intake by 9-15 percent.¹⁷ Also other measures were taken. In December 1982, a reform of the salaries system was implemented: part of the wages were to be paid to the workers only if the company achieved its goals. The goals were often not achieved, so de facto this meant a decrease of the wages. The electricity and district heating were often stopped in order to save energy, leading to unbearable winters. Availability of hot water was also restricted to one day per week in most apartments. At the end of the 1980’s East European countries such as Poland, Hungary, Czechoslovakia, Bulgaria transformed from a closed communist dictatorship towards

¹⁶ http://enciclopediaromaniei.ro/wiki/Comuna_Zagra#Demografie

¹⁷ <http://www.istorie-pe-scurt.ro/cum-arata-o-cartela-pe-vremea-lui-ceausescu-programul-de-alimentatie-rationala/>

a more open democratic society. Romania under the leadership of Ceausescu seemed to become the exception in this wave of societal changes. However, this turned out to be just a façade. Several demonstrations (1983, 1986 and 1987) were coming to an accumulation point in December 1989. During the Christmas days of 1989, Ceausescu was captured and executed. According to H. D.: *'These days, I still remember them, were a period of hope: finally we could express ourselves without being afraid to end up in jail. And the world was opening for Romania. But very soon after the 'Revolution' this hope turned into a disbelief. Political arrangements, corruption at all levels, layoffs of industries, unemployment... were dominating the discussions among people on the street.'*

Post Romanian Revolution Period (1990-1999)

After the Romanian revolution in 1989, reorganisation were implemented because of financial and efficiency reasons. The industrial decline which characterised Romania after 1990 has affected an important number of cities in the region, especially the ones which have relied on a single industrial activity. As a consequence 'old' industries were shut down or are on the way to be closed. H. D.: *At that time my father was in the running to become the school director, but he didn't had the job because others were paying for the function. Even without any qualification, but with enough money you could become whatever you wanted to become. In this period I was also struggling with my own identity: what I'm going to do and how can I do something good for my country. I decided to start with Law Studies at the university in Cluj. After a while I wanted to be more in the decision making centre and moved to the capital Bucharest, where I lost one year of studies because the University of Bucharest did not accredited my studies in Cluj. To have an impact in society I took a job as a journalist for the newspaper Republica. Although, because of this function, I had some come contacts with politicians, I realised that nothing could be done without money and bribes. This caused stress and I started to have health problems (psoriasis). So I moved again to Cluj and the same story restarted: we can not accredit your studies from Bucharest. I was sick of it and this was decisive moment in my life.*

Migration to Spain (1999-2008)

In 1999 a click came up in my head and decided to leave the country. I was remembering an exchange with a school from France and still had the address of one of the boys from that school. My plan was to search him and try to stay at his place in Bessan. It was not going to be an easy way, because I was already in love with my future wife M. and had to leave her. The first obstacle was to find a way to go out of the country. I found a friend who knew a truck driver who was doing international transport to the UK. Our meeting point was Alba Iulia and from there the journey started. It was a risk for both of us, because I was not having papers to leave the country. So when we had control I had to say that I was the second driver, although I didn't have a driving license. As a miracle at the border with Hungary they were not asking for papers and let us drive. In Hungary our ways separated: the driver to the UK and I to France by train with only 50 dollars in my pocket. After several days I reached the house in France.

An unpleasant surprise was waiting there: the father of the boy was telling that his son was in hospital due to a drugs addiction and God knows the father was blaming me for this. So I was not welcome at all. I spent the night on the street, looking for parking places where I hoped to find a Romanian truck driver. And indeed I found, he told me that he could bring to Cordoba in Spain. He told me that also other Romanians were there. This was the only thing he could and wanted to do for me. When I arrived in Cordoba and having some telephone numbers of Romanians, I could reach one person who wanted to help me. From Cordoba I travelled to Motril. There I could stay in an apartment. But this situation was only temporary, because I didn't have any money for food, clothes....

As a gift from heaven: one day when I was walking in the street somebody shouted my name. It was a guy from the same region where I lived in Romania and he followed courses in my mothers' class. After this meeting everything was going fast: he helped me to find a job in picking tomatoes. For more than two years I worked in a gray situation: working on the black market, not always paid correctly, more police controls, no social security. But I didn't want to go back to Romania.

In 2002 everything changed: visa requirements were lifted and we could travel more freely. I had the opportunity to regularise my papers and my girlfriend could come over to Spain. From that point on we were able to work on a legal way and could save a bit of money to start with our own small business in tomatoes. This situation wouldn't last long, because the first signs of crisis in Spain appeared already in 2006. At that time I also started to struggle with my health. Unemployment and less money that could be spend. So we were obliged to layoff our business and to find another solution.

The Belgian period (2008- ...)

We decided to go to Belgium, because the sister of my wife married a Belgian man and moved to Belgium. So we were very lucky that this man wanted to help us in Belgium. In 2008 we could move to Belgium. It wasn't easy because we had to adapt again to a new environment and experienced some language problems. But I found a job as a seasonal worker in agriculture. After this I found a more stable job in a construction company. After postponing year after year, because of financial reasons, we decided to marry and a daughter has born. But soon after this memorable moment, the crisis reached Belgium. The construction company went in bankruptcy. After that I found a job in logistics: he had to work with products in a freezer of -20°C. Ok I said to myself: I could work in more than 40°C in Spain, I can handle also -20°C. After 1 year the company owners announced to reorganise and to relocate their activities to Poland, because of the lower salaries there. In 8 years I lost 5 jobs in Belgium and was again without work. But at the same time it was strange: although I didn't had a job my personal and family was going step by step better. I think this is not possible in Romania. Now I'm working for a big car company in logistics. This are going better now. I could make some friends and now I don't feel the necessity to go back to Romania, although I miss my relatives. Who knows what the future will bring?'

During the time H. D. was staying abroad, the population of his home village Zagra was declining from 4504 inhabitants in 1977 to 4254 in 1992, 3767 in 2002 and 3527 in 2011. A lower birth rate and emigration are the causes of this decrease in population.

4.2 C. R. (Berbești, Romania)

Berbești is a town located in Vâlcea County, Romania, about 78 km south-west from Râmnicu Vâlcea, the county capital. The town administers five villages: Berbești, Dămțeni, Dealu Aluniș, Roșioara, Târgu Gângulești and Valea Mare. During the communist time, investments were done in the heavy industries. This resulted in the creation of mono-industrial centres. The Oltenia region was characterised by investments in coal industry. The year 1956 corresponds to the opening of the first coal mines in the mining basin of Oltenia (Berbești mine: 1978). Instead of tractors and threshing machines in that area emerged huge earth-moving rotary conveyors of all kinds which brought dislodged coal at points of loading coal into railroad cars. The mining development strategy promoted in Romania before 1990 was based on the concept of economic self-support in providing the necessary mineral raw materials. Because mining wages in this branch were relatively high and enjoyed a number of social facilities (especially in providing housing) in coalfields areal a heterogeneous workforce was transferred coming from across the whole country. Workers from the Moldova region moved to the region of Oltenia. Thus, the situation came to the existence of a mining sector more developed than would be allowed under normal mineral reserves potential of the country and economically unjustified as well. In 1989, the Romanian mining branch reached its maximum development when 278 underground pit-mines and quarries were running and 350.000 people were employed directly and another 700.000 people were employed indirectly in mining industry. After the Romanian revolution in 1989, reorganisation were implemented because of financial and efficiency reasons. The industrial decline which characterised Romania after 1990 has affected an important number of cities in the region, especially the ones which have relied on a single industrial activity. As a consequence 'old' industries were shut down or are on the way to be closed. This leads also to the closing of mine suppliers companies.¹⁸ Due to the dependency on this single industry a huge unemployment appeared. The mine of Berbești

¹⁸ BULEARCA, Marius; POPESCU, Catalin, Gas and coal extractive industry during the socialist industrialisation period (1948-1989), In: Annals of the „Constantin Brâncuși' University of Târgu Jiu, Economy Series, Special Issue ECO-TREND 2015 – Performance, Competitiveness, Creativity, 9. 394-398.

underwent a huge transformation in 1996: reorganisation and job losses, which can be clearly seen in the decrease of persons with a monthly salary in Berbești¹⁹.

Figure 4.1 Evolution persons with monthly salary Berbești

The lack of jobs and no perspective for a better future resulted in an internal and external migration. In 2011 1005 persons do have a domicile in Berbești, but are living elsewhere.²⁰ This group represents almost 1/5 of the population with a domicile in Berbești. In 2002 this was only 6%. This number of 1005 can be further refined by category: around 500 persons are living and working permanently outside the country, around 100 persons are working outside the country by a season based contract and the remaining group lives elsewhere in Romania.²¹ The difference between domicile and residence is clearly found in some age categories. The biggest group not present is the young active population.²²

19 Tempo Online: FOM104D - Numarul mediu al salariatilor pe judete si localitati

20 Tempo-Online: POP107D - POPULATIA DUPA DOMICILIU la 1 ianuarie pe grupe de varsta, sexe, judete si localitati

21 Numbers provided by the Mayor of Berbesti, April 1 2016

22 Tempo-Online: FOM104D - Numarul mediu al salariatilor pe judete si localitati

Figure 4.2 Difference % domicile - residence Berbești

To illustrate the inability to keep Berbești attractive for their citizens, the Mayor says in an interview (April 1 2016): *‘My son opened a business in Finland some years, this year I already helped 50 persons from Berbești to go to work there’*. The precarious situation is not seen as a sum of individual vulnerabilities but more as a community in regression. In the context of this work package, a one week field research was done in Berbești. In total 26 people were interviewed and visits were conducted. The interviewed persons were asked to draw their personal development timeline since 2006. In a separate report the results are presented. 1996, the year of huge reorganisations in the mine, is also the year where the life story of C. R. start. His timeline and his perception of his personal development are constantly on the negative side and declining permanently.

Figure 4.3 Timeline C.R. Berbești

C. R. (Interview April 2 2016) born in 1977 and living for 20 years in Berbești: ‘Because I lost my job in 1996, I was looking for new possibilities. These I couldn’t find in Berbești or in the region because of the restructuring of the total mine industry. In that time we heard that Greece was in a deep need for low skilled labour. More specifically, workers are needed in constructions, in agriculture for collecting olives and oranges, as well as in restaurants. In other words, it needed low skilled people. In 1996 I left Berbești together with a group from our region, not exactly knowing what would come but with a hope for a better future. Some parts of the way to Greece we did by feet others by train or car. We went by train through the former Yugoslavia to Macedonia (FYROM). We got off the train 5 or 6 stops before the customs point. It was quite far from the border, the closer one got to it, the more frequent the control was. We crossed the border in Macedonia and then we took a taxi to the Greek borderline. The taxi drivers were very nice and they showed us how to go from there. we got here illegally. It was me who came first, then my wife in 1999. After a bit more than one week I arrived to my destination, a small village near Thessaloniki.’ Immigrants who came to Greece before 1998 legitimised their stay owing to the presidential decrees of 1997 which inaugurated the first regularisation program, or within the framework of the second regularisation program, under law 2910/2001. It appears that the initiative of ‘doing their papers’ belonged to the immigrants and that there were instances in which the employed immigrants were supported by their employers with the necessary procedures. This was for C. R. certainly not the case during the first years of his stay in Greece: ‘We were perceived as slaves. We had to work in the orange garden without contract and not being sure that we were getting paid. The owner instead of paying for our work was putting the police on us as if we were thieves. Living in a house without a decent roof and the risk to be captured by the police was our life during the first 2 years. In 1998 things started to change, finally I could start working for a good manager, he protected us from the police but still we had to work without papers. One year later my wife was coming to Greece. Our living conditions didn’t improved: living with 25 persons in the same house, daily work agreements and depending on seasonal work. Only in 2002 we arranged our papers, but the man who was helping with the papers was asking to work for him for free as a compensation for his help. Almost in the same period Greece banks were offering credits. It was very easy to get a loan, because the only thing needed was an identity card. We took a loan in order to buy a small house. In 2006 my wife got pregnant and in 2007 our son R. was born. During this period my wife couldn’t work officially and took some bad paid jobs as cleaner or housekeeper. All of this on the black market, so she was working without papers. And the child allowance

was only 80 euro a year. On top of this the crisis affected Greece very hard: loss of jobs, more hours for less money ... During these times our problems started to pay back the loan to the bank. After doing some smaller jobs, we decided to go back to Romania in 2013. But also here troubles were growing in Romania: we experienced difficulties to reintegrate in our 'own' home place. Certainly our son has difficulties in the school to be accepted by other children. By the end of 2015 I was engaged by Govora, the mine company, but they paid only on an irregular base my salary. So I couldn't keep this job. And still our loan needs to be paid back in Greece. We don't see many possibilities anymore for the future: our son needs to go to school and our grandmother is very ill and needs personal assistance. But we don't have resources to help our own family.' The day after our interview (April 3 2016) the couple left Romania again for Greece to find a solution for their financial duties in Greece, leaving their son and their grandmother behind not exactly knowing when they can return to Romania.

5. The impact of the crisis on Romanian migrants

5.1 Scope of analysis

It is found that on the short term emigration had a positive impact in the Romanian economy: emigration has decreased the pressure on the labour market, alleviated poverty through money remittances and has determined wage increases for those left behind. Nevertheless the negative societal consequences can and may not be denied: the pressure on family and community structures, brain drain, ageing of the population and problems related to migration in host countries. The financial crisis of 2008-2009 has enlarged the negative impacts and reduced some of the positive effects. These consequences are described more extensively below and are structured around topics:

- the impact of the crisis on Romanian migrants and migration patterns;
- the impact of the Romanian crisis measures on migration;
- the social effects of migration in the home country;
- migration policies: a sufficient answer to societal challenges?

5.2 Decrease in inward remittances as a consequence of the crisis

One of the motives to go to work abroad is the ability to earn more money than in the home country in order to save and send money home. Due to the crisis job availability and security have declined in a lot of destination countries: job loss, reduced working hours and/or financial cuts in earnings. As a consequence financial remittances started to decline from 2008.

Figure 5.1 Evolution of inward remittances to Romania 2006-2014

Source World Bank, Factbook 2016: Countries M-Z, p. 43.

The total amount of money transferred to the home country decreased with almost 65% since 2008. The lower availability of financial resources both in the home country and in the host country, also caused other negative consequences:

- the number of visits in the home country has continuously declined because of lack of money and the fear to lose the job while in Romania;
- difficulties of (grand)parents to provide basic necessities for their (grand)children;
- difficulties to keep in contact with relatives due to rise in phone and internet costs;

- in some cases relatives in Romania need to send money to relatives working/living abroad.

5.3 Changing migration patterns due to the crisis

The crisis caused many immigrants of the past decade to leave certain host countries again. What is interesting here is that the emigration flows consisted largely of migrants moving elsewhere or foreign nationals returning.

5.3.1 Returners

The returning phenomenon can be seen in the relative share of national immigrants in Romania. Romania with a share of more than 90% national immigrants, is at the first place in Europe followed by Lithuania (88%), Latvia (72%), Portugal (64%), Poland (63%) and Estonia (58%).

Figure 5.2 Numbers and rates national and non-national immigrants in Romania, 2008-2013

The growing returning trend can also be seen in Germany. Figures show a rising number of people moving back from Germany to Romania.²³

Figure 5.3 Romanian migration from and to Germany

23 <http://www.thelocal.de/20140224/thousands-bulgarians-and-romanas-leave-germany-each-month>

Dumitrești, a commune located in Vrancea County, is composed of sixteen villages. Between 2002 and 2012 the population decreased from 5278 to 4602 inhabitants (-13%). This decline is comparable to the national trend. Dumitresti is experiencing a leave and return migration. In the years before the accession of Romania to the EU (2007), a relative small negative migration can be seen in Dumitresti.²⁴ This external migration grew the first years after the EU, but slowed down in the years after the crisis.

Figure 5.4 Migration flow Dumitresti 2005-2014

Source INSSE, Temponline

During 3 focus group meetings in Dumitresti, 10 people with a migration background were brought together to draw their snake timeline and based on this 3 persons were selected to tell their migration story and why they choose to return to Dumitresti.

B. E. (43 years, woman). B.E. is coming from a neighbourhood community of Dumitresti (Vintileasca), she is married in Dumitresti and she established her household here. Because she was not having a working place in Romania, she and her husband decided to leave Romania and to go to Italy. In 2008 they were in Italy and she finds a job as a small administrator in a bread factory. In 2009 she find a job into a printing business in Valvo-Sacco but in 2010 she is coming back to Romania because she is having a baby and she decided to take care of her baby. Because the financial needs are causing problems, she decided to find a job. Because she could not find a job, she decided to continue her studies and could finish a post school in the medical-pharmaceutical field; she is doing also courses for baby-sitter; communication expert assistant and public relations. Even if she was doing so many official qualifications she cannot find a place to work in Dumitresti and she cannot go to work into the nearest big city, Focsani because she cannot afford from her eventual salary to pay a baby sitter (the child is in Class 0: between kindergarten and primary school). She is very talented in crafts, handmade knitting and hand- made jewelleries but she

²⁴ Tempo Online: POP307A - Stabiliri cu domiciliul (inclusiv migratia externa) pe judete si localitati and POP308A - Plecari cu domiciliul (inclusiv migratia externa) pe judete si localitati

does find a way to sell them for having a little income for her family. Her husband is working into the black market in Italy and sending some money home. They are not into an insurance system, pension system or health system.

T. S. (29 years old, woman). She is coming from a family with big social problems (domestic violence, under the poverty level), the father sends his family out of the house, and her mother grew by herself the 2 girls. One is T. S. because of financial reasons, she is leaving to the nearest town Focsani and she start to work as warehouse employee into a supermarket. She is decided to go for a better life and she is continued her study becoming medical assistant. Even after this school qualification she cannot find a job - not having a network and either not the resources to pay a bribe (spaga in Romanian). In 2010 she decided to leave Romania together with her husband for Greece and there she is working as cleaning lady and her husband in by hour paid jobs paid. After 1 year, after they saved a bit of money decided to come back in Romania and here, in the country side, in a very small village Fata far away from centre of they opened a small shop with all kind of products. In 2012 she is having a baby and they employed another lady as selling lady in the small shop. The shop is doing worst and worst and in 2014 they closed the shop, the husband decided to go to Focsani and work in construction. They moved to Focsani but because they cannot survive with the salary of her husband they all come back to Dumitresti, back to his old family house and live together with their older relatives. Sometimes he is working as fellow worker in construction.

B. C. (26 years, woman). She is born in Dumitresti in a very modest family together with 8 other brothers and sisters. She can finalise only 8 years of school because financial problems force her to go to work. At 18 years she is leaving Romania to Italy, her father is already working here. Here she started to wash dishes into a restaurant. Here she found her love and she married with a Romanian boy, who was working in construction without any legal papers). Until 2009 she is working into that restaurant and in 2010 she started working in a pizzeria. Because both, she and her husband do not have a proper job, proper salaries, they cannot take care of their own expenses and in 2011 they decide to return to Romania, to leave into

their family country side house because in this way they do not have to pay any more rent. In 2011 she is having her first baby and they are both employed as paid by hour cleaning employees in the school of Bicestii de Sus, a village in Dumitresti community. In 2014 she is employed half time as cleaning lady. In 2015 she is having the second child, she is taking her maternal leaving, which is 2 years in Romania and instead of her, her husband takes the half time job. She is leaving in her husband parents' house, together with her husband family. Because they live under the poverty threshold (her husband salary is 350 RON=78 EUR), they take also black market jobs.

Most of the people involved in the focus group are starting from very vulnerable situations, even living under the poverty threshold. A small set of capabilities from the starting point seems to end up in vicious circle of going down:

- no or less opportunities to study in the home town;
- lack of jobs or not having the resources to pay for a job;
- looking for a better future in a country abroad, but confronted with abuses and black market jobs;
- coming back for family reasons and trying to find a job or opening an own business;
- in the end living together with other family members to overcome financial issues.

Authorities and policy makers don't seem to succeed in the transformation of potential capabilities into real capabilities and functionings.

5.3.2 Leaving for another country

H. D. left Romania to go to work in Spain and left Spain again due to the crisis and the severe measures towards foreign workers. Spain lifted the labour market restrictions for Romanian migrants in 2009 but effectively re-imposed them in 2011 in response to serious disturbances of the labour market. This measure and employment cuts in Spain have especially affected migrant workers. While the employment of Spanish nationals fell by 14.3% between the second quarter of 2008 and the third quarter of 2012, employment of foreign workers went down by 24.9%.²⁵ In 2011 30% of Romanian workers were unemployed.²⁶ Since 2012 there are more Romanian emigrants from Spain than Romanian immigrants.²⁷ Italy seems to be a preferred country of new destination since Italy lifted the restriction for Romanian workers in 2012. This resulted in an increasing trend of Romanian immigrants in Italy.

25 <http://www.eurofound.europa.eu/observatories/eurwork/comparative-information/impact-of-the-crisis-on-working-conditions-in-europe>

26 <http://www.migrationwatchuk.org/briefing-paper/287>

27 <http://www.ine.es/jaxi/menu.do?L=1&type=pcaxis&path=%2Ft20%2Fp307&file=inebase>

Figure 5.5 Romanian migration from and to Spain

Not only Italy became a preferable country, the Northern countries became more popular among Romanian migrants already in a migration process. Job opportunities were perhaps not the first motivation either knowing some friends or relatives in the new host country who went relative well through the crisis. In Belgium for example Romanian migrants are the fastest growing group of migrants since the last decade: in comparison to 2005 in 2015 13 times more Romanians are living in Belgium.²⁸

Table 5.1 Main nationalities of foreign population in Belgium

Country	2005			2015		
	Amount	%	Ranking	Amount	%	Ranking
France	117.349	13.5	2	159.352	12.7	1
Italy	179.015	20.6	1	156.977	12.5	2
Netherlands	104.978	12.1	3	149.199	11.9	3
Morocco	81.287	9,3	4	82.009	6.5	4
Poland	14.251	1.7	11	68.403	5.4	5
Romania	5.632	0.6	16	65.768	5.2	6
Spain	43.203	5.0	5	60.386	4.8	7
Portugal	27.374	3.1	8	42.793	3.4	8
Germany	36.330	4.2	7	39.294	3.1	9
Turkey	40.403	4.6	6	36.747	2.9	10
Others	220.770	25.4		394.358	31.4	
Total	870.862	100.0		1.255.286	100.0	

Source National Statistics Belgium

Before the crisis, Belgium was not that popular for Romanians. The financial crisis was an important turning point in the Romanian migration to Belgium. It's difficult to say if the newcomers are first host country migrants or migrants already in a migration process. More research is needed to understand this pattern.

28 Data based on Algemene Directie Statistiek – FOD Economie en Kerncijfers 2015: http://statbel.fgov.be/nl/binaries/NL_kerncijfers_2015_WEB_COMPLET_tcm325-275721.pdf

Figure 5.6 Number of Romanian in Belgium 1999-2015

Source National Statistics Belgium

5.4 Syndrome Italy or the deterioration of personal capabilities

Syndrome Italy a concept used in the psychiatric hospital of Iasi (North East Romania) is referring to the phenomenon of depressed women after returning from Italy. Romanian women migrated to Italy are mainly employed in homes as cleaners and caregivers for the elderly as well as in nursing. Before the crisis host families did have enough resources to pay for more than 1 caregiver. The crisis caused a cut in family budget and less money is available for external caregivers. F. C., a psychologist at the psychiatric hospital in Iasi (Skype interview January 20 2016) gave an example of 35 year old lady who returned from Italy: *'In the first years – the years before the crisis she and another lady worked for a host family. Together they could take care of the household, the working hours and payments were reasonable. After the crisis her colleague could not stay anymore because of cuts in budgets. At that time the grandfather of the family got dementia. This resulted in less free time even worse in a 24/7 availability for the 80 year old man. During the night she has to wake up because the man needed care. After a period of almost no sleep and hard work, the lady returned back to Romania suffering depression due to the emotional and psychological pressure she experienced in Italy.'*

5.5 Impact of migration on community services

According to data provided by the College of Physicians of Romania, in 1989 Romania had 56.000 physicians with the right to practice, in 2014 their number is 39.000.²⁹ The medical brain drain has intensified after Romania's accession to the European Union. Since 2007, around 15.000 Romanian medics have migrated for work abroad. This intensification was strengthened by the anti-crisis measures: around 80% of doctors are working in the public sector and as a consequence were also affected by the cut in salaries in 2010.

²⁹ <http://www.cmr.ro/comunicat-de-presa-34/>

<http://www.cmr.ro/migratia-medicilor/>

<http://www.cmr.ro/migratia-medicilor-2012/>

FERARU, Petronela Daniela, Romania and the Crisis in the Health System. Migration of Doctors, In: Global Journal of Medical Research, 2013, 25, XIII, p. 25-32.

Figure 5.7 Evolution of leaving Romanian doctors

Source Colegiului Medicilor din România

The data of leaving Romanian doctors show a big regional difference. The biggest departure can be seen from academic centres from Bucharest, Cluj and Iasi. The most popular destinations in 2011 were: the UK (900), France (500), Germany (400) and Belgium (80). Although the migration trend of Romanian doctors was already visible in the years before the crisis, the financial difficulties and the taken measures have fastened the emigration of physicians. The spread of this trend can be seen in all medical domains: in 2014 424 of 2.450 of leaving doctors were family doctors or 1/5 of the leaving doctors and in hospitals 13.521 doctors are registered in 2014 while in 2011 this number was 20.648. Migrating doctors have a young profile and the ageing of remaining doctors starts to cause problems. One of the side effects is an immigration trend of doctors from the Republic of Moldova.³⁰ It is worrisome that Romania is actually facing a shortage of health care staff: in 2014 3.000 doctors entered while 3.500 were exiting the system (migration, pension, decease). An estimation done in March 2015 calculated that there are around 550 doctors, mainly in rural area, too few in Romania.³¹ This number is confirmed by the EHCI index 2014.³² In the same line are the results of the study ‘Building primary care in a changing Europe’ and gives an insight in the gap between urban and rural areas in Romania. In urban areas the density of family physicians is 1 family physician per 1000 population and in rural areas the density is 1 family physician per 2500–3000 population.³³ As the issue of scarce resources is prevailing, policies seem to be inefficient in order to stop, or at least slower down the medical brain drain.

5.6 Impact of migration on family structures

5.6.1 Children – social orphans

Emigration became a destabilizing factor for the family especially when children are left in Romania and brought changes with regards to the functions of the family. Children often find themselves responsible for tasks usually completed by the adult members of the family (such as housework and even agricultural work in the case of children from rural areas), leaving aside their obligations to attend school. According to official statistics, over 80.000 children living in Romania have at least one parent working abroad. However, numerous NGO’s in Romania argue that the actual size of this phenomenon is still unknown, despite the fact that efforts are made by the public authorities to determine the real number of children living in this country and having at least one parent who works abroad. The biggest concern is that of children who

30 World Health Organisation, Health workers originating from the Republic of Moldova who live and work in Romania, Republic of Moldova Health Policy Paper Series No. 13, 2014, 90 p.

31 <http://www.digi24.ro/Stiri/Digi24/Actualitate/Sanatate/Prea+putini+medici+de+familie>

32 EHCI Index 2014, p. 68.

33 Building primary care in a changing Europe – Case studies, p. 227.

remain in their home country completely deprived of parental care. In literature the term 'home alone generation' or 'left behind children' are used. According to UNICEF-Alternative Social Association (AAS) (data 2008) estimates, Romania has some 350.000 so-called children left behind. The number of left behind minors amounts to 7% of the total Romanian population between the ages of 0 and 18 years. 157.000 children have only fathers working abroad, while 67.000 have only mothers working abroad. More than one third, however, or some 126.000 children, have been deprived of both parents. Some 400.000 children have experienced that particular form of solitude for at least part of their lives. In other words, out of a total of 5 million Romanian children, some 750.000 of them have been affected to a greater or lesser extent by the departure of their parents. 52% of these so-called children left behind, in other words 180.000 children, live in rural areas where it is more common for mothers to go away, unlike in the larger cities where it is more common for fathers to leave. Half of the left behind children are younger than 10 years of age. Of these, more than half are between 2 and 6 years of age and 4% of them are less than one year old. 16% of these children have spent more than one year of their young lives far away from their parents. Indeed, 3% of them have been left for more than four years. This has an impact on the mental well-being of children: being bullied, being in conflict, depression, being ill and even suicide is more present in the group of children left behind. They cannot offer them the psychological family balance of their biological parents. Furthermore, they often drop out of school, thus the level of illiteracy and/or under-education has become alarming in the contemporary Romanian society. The counties with the highest percentages of children having at least one parent working abroad were mainly from the Nord-East development region. This is also the region with the highest poverty rate and the highest risk of social exclusion in Romania.

5.6.2 Orphaned elderly people

The lack of care is also felt by the elderly who remain in Romania, often having to take up the parents' responsibilities. Care-giving for these persons is even harder to find than it is for the minors who are left at home by migrating parents. Few women in Romania are willing to offer care-giving services given the possibility of performing the same job abroad, for a higher wage. Consequently, if we consider that Romania is undergoing more or less the same demographic trends as Italy, that is, an ageing population in need of care and low birth-rates, combined with a welfare system which is not prepared to offer adequate assistance.

To conclude this paragraph, the report refers to James Bluemel, director of Channel 4's three-part series 'The Romanians Are Coming': *'The fundamental right to free movement for EU citizens is important, correct and valuable, but let's not be blasé. Leaving your family and friends behind as you move 2,000 miles across Europe in the hope of finding a job is not a decision that anyone takes lightly. It's a scary and painful thing to do. It rips families apart and it destroys communities. It is not something that should have to happen. For many of the Romanians I met, the phrase 'freedom to move' is contradictory, as where is the freedom in having no choice but to leave your country to search for work? It's important and correct that we have that right to free movement, but let's not confuse the life of a migrant worker with freedom.'*³⁴

34 <http://www.newstatesman.com/politics/2015/02/many-romanian-migrants-phrase-freedom-move-contradictory>

6. Conclusion: towards entangled capabilities

6.1 Entangling capabilities

Previously data have demonstrated that earning more money abroad and having more job opportunities are important factors to emigrate. Calculations (September 2015) show that a Romanian employee will reach a salary of a German one in at least 30 years from now.³⁵ Currently, a company spends in Romania, with each employee, 4.6 euro for each hour worked by him, while in Germany the average labour cost is 31.4 euro per hour. Romania is the second lowest in the European Union regarding the hourly labour cost, last being Bulgaria, at a cost of 3.8 euro per hour, as the Eurostat data show. The average in the European Union is 24.6 euro per hour. So it seems that the coming decades Romania will be still confronted with emigration. Some calculations show that in between this and 20-25 years the Romanian population will further decrease to a number of 15 million people. Romania is in other words representing one of the biggest mobile groups in Europe. A trend that seems to be stimulated by the European Union: putting a strong stress on labour mobility in the latest 2014-2020 strategy. The Commission has put forward seven flagship initiatives to catalyse progress under each priority theme. Flagship 6 ‘an agenda for new skills and jobs’ mentions the following goal: facilitate and promote intra-EU labour mobility and better match labour supply with demand. Comparable with discussions concerning economic growth and financial austerity, mobility is perceived more as an economical must rather than an opportunity to personal development. This focus on individual economic ‘well-being’ causes conflicts with other internal capabilities and community demands for a sustainable development. The freedom to move as fundamental human right is narrowed to almost a moral duty and shifts away from being an instrument to a goal as such. Martha Nussbaum’s well-known list, which contains prescribed capabilities that are grouped together under 10 central human capabilities (life, bodily health, bodily integrity, senses, imagination and thought, emotions, practical reason, affiliation, other species, play and control over one’s environment) provides a grip to visualise the side and negative effects of emigration. The financial crisis of 2008-2009 strengthened these negative effects. These conflicting capabilities raises one of the major points of debate in the capability literature: which capabilities should be selected as relevant and who should decide or how a decision should be made on the (e)valuation of the various capabilities and functionings into an overall assessment. Literature has been somewhat vague in responding to the question of how to select and weight capabilities: it has been argued that each individual or group should itself select, weight, trade off, and sequence or otherwise entangle capabilities as well as prioritise them in relation to other normative considerations. In the case of a Romanian family living in a society without job potentials, decent earning and social provisions, will have to choose for one of the following functionings: to find a job and a decent income requires parents to migrate, which will generate the income needed to properly feed themselves and the family or to care for the children at home and give them all the attention, care and supervision they need. From a purely theoretical point of view both opportunities are opportunities open to the parents, but they are not both together open. The point about the capability approach is precisely to create a comprehensive or holistic approach, and ask which sets of capabilities are open, that is: can simultaneously provide for my family and properly care for and supervise children? Or are parents rather forced to make some hard, perhaps even tragic choices between two functionings which both reflect basic needs and basic moral duties? Enhancing and using one capability, in this case migration (control over one’s environment) in a narrowed one way direction, can indeed put a pressure on your own and other ones capabilities, even reduce them. Conflicting capabilities are causing challenges

35 <http://www.smartree.com/en/zf-romania-vs-eu-when-would-get-romanian-employees-similar-salaries-with-germans/>

to public and private authorities to find a balance between fundamental rights and the practical implementation of the improvement of capabilities. Improving one capability needs to be covered by an impact measurement, positive and negative. Side effects can be minimalised through framework policies so that in the end people have a freedom to choice for migration. In the context of this report, the idea of ‘entangled’ capabilities is introduced, as an overall concept of weighted, aggregated, combined and connected capabilities. Entangled capabilities can be defined as capabilities plus the external conditions that make the exercise of a function a free option. The aim of public policy is the promotion of entangled capabilities.

6.2 Entangled capabilities promoted by the home country Romania

Until now Romania has adopted 4 strategies on migration. The first one was adopted in 2004: the main objectives were to ensure the free movement of the EU citizens. The 2nd strategy of 2007 wanted to attract foreign labour force for covering the workforce deficits. Through this strategy Romania tried to cover the brain drain. Due to the crisis, the 3rd strategy had a restrictive approach towards immigration. The latest strategy has been adopted by Romania in September 2015 and wants to facilitate the entry of immigrants in order to cover workforce deficits. Romanian emigration policies is fragmented. The Romanian policy measures to promote circular migration (temporary and usually repetitive movement of a migrant worker) were not very effective, although some positive examples can be mentioned. Romania. Steps to promote a system of managed migration or forms of periodic and circular migration are taken. There were taken steps to promote a managed migration system or forms of periodic and circular migration. In the EU pre-accession period, Romania signed bilateral agreements regulating the migration of labour force with several countries. In 2002, the Labour Force Migration Office, an authority in charge with both the recruitment and mediation of Romanian labour force, was set up. This office initiated bilateral contracts with relevant state agencies from receiving countries or private. From 2006 the Romanian authorities started to offer primarily cultural assistance to Romanian emigrant communities via a special structure of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs responsible for the Romanian Diaspora, the Department for Romanians Living Abroad. The 2008-2010 Action Plan concerning the return of Romanian citizens working abroad was adopted. Jobs fairs were organised in Spain and Italy with the main goal of attracting Romanian migrants back home and informing them about their rights to social security on returning to Romania. The number of participants was rather low and the outcomes were far from what was expected. Other measures such as a bonus of 500 euro to set up a business in Romania and a reduction in VAT, didn’t had the expected results. Recently the Repatriate campaign started to attract Romanian entrepreneurs working abroad (<http://repatriot.ro/>). Also attempts to win back or to keep doctors in Romania (brain gain) were undertaken: in 2012 the Romanian government agreed to open 3.000 new positions but was immediately slowed down by austerity measures. An in October 2015 the salaries of doctors increased. Finally Romania negotiated funding through the European Social Fund and Regional Development program for returners. Besides supporting systems some restrictive measures to control out-migration were taken. By Romanian law, all parents who go to work abroad, either to search for jobs, or with a job already in place, have to notify the social assistance system, and let the authorities know who takes care of their children while they are away. This has to be done at least 40 days before leaving. The law recently changed (September 2013), as in the past, only those who left with a work contract in place had to comply with this regulation. Now it covers all parents, including those going to search for jobs, or those who end up working on the black market abroad. The law includes a fine of 500 to 1.000 Romanian lei for parents who do not inform authorities that they are leaving to work. The law also requires for local authorities to organise social assistance services, to provide counselling for six months for those who become guardians of the children whose parents work abroad. The court can decide to delegate the parental responsibilities, while the parents are away, but for no longer than a year. Romanian authorities included children affected by migration in the category of vulnerable children within the National Strategy for the Protection and Promotion of Child Rights 2014-2020, motivating that these children have low school performance and are at high risk of dropping out of school. A pilot program signed in 2013 by the Labour Ministry and the Association of Romanian Women in Italy, together with the Milan city hall,

allows children in the counties of Dolj, Gorj, Neamţ, Satu Mare and Suceava to stay in touch with their parents who work in Italy via Internet and Skype at their local libraries.

6.3 Entangled capabilities promoted by host countries

As mentioned before, when Romania entered the EU in 2007 most EU member states made use of the possibility to temporarily restrict the new EU citizens' access to their labour markets and welfare systems for up to seven years. Since 2014 these restrictions are lifted, but formed the base for an intense public debate in several countries with arguments for the prolongation of access restrictions. The UK, German, Dutch, and Austrian governments called on the European Commission to strengthen rules to protect the welfare states against being abused by migrants. However there is no evidence of widespread abuse of welfare systems by eastern European migrants. On the contrary public finances in the richer EU15 countries appear to have gained from their eastern European post-enlargement immigration, even when no access restrictions have been in place. A UK study of 2010 found that public-sector revenues from the migrants were at least 1.21 times as large as the costs in each of the fiscal years studied. These positive results were mainly due to migrants receiving substantially less in welfare benefits compared with natives, and to very few of the migrants being old. These two positive effects more than balance the negative effect of migrants earning less income and hence paying less in taxes on average compared with natives. UK figures show that 37.000 citizens from Romania and Bulgaria migrated to the UK in the year 2014, accounting for 6% of total immigration. And 27.000 of those came primarily to work. The question remains if this group of migrants is directly coming from the home country or are these arriving persons already in migration from another country, affected by the crisis such as Spain, Portugal and Ireland. The rise of the numbers can also be explained by the fact that migrants already residing in the host country, now had the opportunity to regulate irregular work. Although this growth does have an impact on the growing number of migrants from Romania, a London School of Economics study released that there was no evidence of an overall negative impact of immigration on jobs, wages, housing or the crowding out of public services.³⁶ Mobile EU workers are on average younger than the population of the host countries, which can represent a welcome demographic boost to the host countries in case these young people settle there. Among the working age population, EU mobile citizens also have a higher activity rate than nationals (77% versus 72%) and are employed at a significantly higher rate (68%) than nationals of the host countries (65%) or third country nationals (53%).³⁷ The fear and the public perception of being threatened, is one of the major challenges for policymakers. Recognizing the added value of Romanian mobility workers needs to go hand in hand with social investment measures:

- concerns often arise about so-called 'social dumping', i.e. undercutting of wages and employment standards by mobile workers. These relate in particular to the working conditions of mobile EU workers and to insufficient enforcement of labour law by national authorities in the destination countries. Mobile EU workers can be subject to abuse and exploitation, for instance when they get trapped in undeclared work or when rules on the posting of workers are not respected. Member States' enforcement authorities, especially labour inspectorates, therefore have a key role to play in order to enforce applicable conditions and terms of employment. Enhanced EU cooperation can help tackle various irregular situations of mobile EU workers as well;
- on the national and European level directives and guideline are needed to equalise the access to the labour market and social protection: this means the concrete implementation of the principle of the same access to social protection as others in the country where they are living and working. Further on the implementation of the new Enforcement Directive (May 2016) to increase the protection of workers temporarily posted abroad and enhance legal certainty;

36 <http://cep.lse.ac.uk/pubs/download/ea019.pdf>

37 Eurostat: Labour Force Survey

- at local level, inflows of mobile EU citizens may result in additional pressure on public services such as healthcare, housing, education or transport, especially when such services need to respond to a larger population over a relatively short period. The development of strategies is to invest in the provision of relevant public services, which would of course benefit the native population as well.

6.4 First steps towards social investments

Although social investment proposal will be more explored in the next stage of the project, some first steps towards social investment are proposed. These can be seen as a starting point for further discussion and exploration:

- improvement of the information base concerning Romanian migrants who work abroad. This connected to in depth research about actual migration patterns and motives of Romanian migrants according to the effects of the crisis on migration;
- promoting circular migration;
- protecting Romanian diaspora rights;
- encouraging return migration through a range of facilities for migrants and their families, such as:
 - consultancy and assistance for entrepreneurship start-up schemes (including assistance in accessing the European Social Fund);
 - participation in training programs;
 - job search support for the spouse of the migrant;
 - psychological counselling for the children;
 - recognition of professional certificates and/or informal competencies acquired abroad.
- taking into account the different needs and profiles of returners (failed, conservative and innovative returners);
- finding ways that remittances are invested in businesses, especially in the rural areas, by facilitating the access to credits for micro enterprises;
- finding ways to respond to the needs of transnational families and parenting in order to protect the rights of relatives left at home and to develop appropriate tools enabling remote parenting and supporting transnational parent–school communication. A first step can be the recognition of new family realities:
 - transnational families as families whose members live some or most of the time separated from each other, yet hold together and create something that can be seen as a feeling of collective welfare and unity, namely family hood, even across national borders’;
 - transnational parenting as adults’ parenting from a different country than the one in which their children reside.

As already mentioned this will be the subject for the next work package, in which the main attention will go to early child care and elderly care.

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Social disinvestment and vulnerable groups in Europe in the aftermath of the financial crisis

The case of lone parents in Scotland

Fiona McHardy & Peter Kelly

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 649447

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Executive summary

This report has been prepared for the European Commission Horizons 2020 funded project RE-InVEST - Rebuilding An Inclusive Value based Europe of Solidarity and Trust Through Social Investments. The economic crisis of 2008 has impacted across Europe in multiple ways through unemployment and changing labour market, poverty, and reduction in service provision. The RE-InVEST consortium is exploring the social investment strategy of the European Commission in response to the financial crisis of 2008 and the impacts on vulnerable groups.

The RE-InVEST consortium is looking at the impacts on human rights and capabilities across 12 countries (13 regions) covered by the project. RE-InVEST as project looks to provide building blocks based on solidarity, trust and social investment. An important aspect of this process is giving space to vulnerable groups through participative methods and a crossing of knowledge through lived experiences. This is conducted through the Participatory Action Research with Human Rights and Capability approaches.

This research explores the demographic group of lone parents in the city of Glasgow, Scotland. Lone parents historically have faced multiple barriers and have experienced vulnerability. This research explores the impacts of the crisis on this group.

The report outlines a number of key areas including the impact on individual and collective capabilities, resilience and human rights exploring this through pre crisis and beyond the crisis. Participatory tools such as drawing and modelling were employed to utilise the PAHCA approach. The qualitative evidence provides illustrative material on the effects and experiences of the financial crisis and includes Biographical Narrative interviews conducted with two individuals Julia and Lucy involved in the crossing of knowledge process.

- The research indicated through the crossing of knowledge process utilising PAHRCA methodology that lone parent human rights had been eroded and that peoples capabilities ‘what they were able to do and be’ had been negatively affected. This erosion had reinforced a shift where there had been a loss of trust within society and democracy however this was counter balanced within political activism across this group.
- Austerity measures and a changing social protection system had created a difficult climate for lone parents to exercise their individual and collective capabilities and to have their human rights realised. Being lone parents meant that they were under increased pressure to meet the needs of them and their families, and their choices had become restricted in terms of jobs, housing and access to support.
- The economic crash of 2009 had resulted in an increasingly precarious labour market with a rise in zero hour contracts and under employment across Scotland. Lone parents faced specific barriers such as access to child care. Obtaining and sustaining employment was very much dependent on accessing affordable childcare and an emphasis was placed on the need for employers to be flexible to individual circumstances. Lone parents faced particular pressure points with this. This was borne out against a climate of privatisation of active labour market support (ALMP) or the work programme and of increasingly conditionality in welfare support in particular activation benefits such as Jobseekers Allowance (JSA).

Contents

List of tables	8
List of figures	9
Introduction	10
1. Crisis in context- the experience of Scotland	11
1.1 Introduction: policy in Scotland and the UK	11
1.2 Responding to economic crisis: the emergence of austerity	11
1.3 Welfare and austerity	12
1.4 Lone parents and austerity	14
2. The participatory research approach	15
2.1 Participatory action human rights and capability approach	15
2.2 The crossing of knowledge process: project delivery	16
2.3 Partnership and crossing of knowledge partners	17
2.4 Reflection on the process	19
3. Biographical Narratives	20
3.1 Lucy's story	20
3.2 Julia's story	21
4. Analysis: the economic crisis and the perspective of lone parents	23
4.1 Introduction	23
4.2 Impact on individual capabilities (choices?) (short and long term effects)	23
4.3 Lone parent demographics	23
4.4 Changing welfare system	24
4.5 Health	25
4.6 Insecurity	26
4.7 Impact on human rights	27
4.8 Choosing to have a child	27
4.9 Rights in the workplace	28
4.10 Rights and living conditions	29
4.11 Rights and education	30
4.12 Collective capabilities: stigma, discrimination and community cohesion	30
4.13 Democracy and civic participation	31
4.14 Conditionality and freedom	31
4.15 Security of income	31
4.16 Access to service provision in an austerity context	32
4.17 Widening inequalities	33
4.18 Lasting Impacts	33
5. Conclusion	34

List of tables

Table 1.1 Real budget spending changes by deprivation band, Scottish Local Authorities, 2010/2011-2014-2015 13

List of figures

Figure 2.1	Merging of Knowledge	17
Figure 4.1	Drawing illustrating effects of increased conditionality	24
Figure 4.2	Picture reflecting on fears for the future	26

Introduction

This report has been produced as part of the ‘RE-InVEST’ project. The project, funded as part of the Horizon 2020 funding stream, is exploring the Social Investment Package of the European Commission in responding to the social damage as a result of the financial crisis in 2008.

RE-InVEST is a consortium of partners who are assessing the impact of social damage of the economic crisis on the vulnerable groups utilising a theoretical framework of human rights and capabilities. This report is one in a series exploring the impacts across Europe.

The economic crisis of 2008 was had an impact across Europe, but the severity of that impact and the responses to it varied considerably across Europe and within countries. In Scotland, whilst part of the UK and subject to many of the same fiscal responses to the economic crisis, was also had the opportunity to develop different responses due to the varied powers available to the devolved Scottish Parliament. In part, the report will consider what some of these differences were and what difference they made to people living on low incomes.

1. Crisis in context- the experience of Scotland

1.1 Introduction: policy in Scotland and the UK

Austerity has been the primary response in the UK to the global economic crisis that began in 2008. However, some parts of the UK and some demographic groups have been affected differentially. When considering the impact of economic change on lone parents in Scotland, and the policy responses to it, it is important to recognise the possibility of divergence in policy making in the UK.

Scotland is part of the UK and since 1999, when the Scottish Parliament was re-established, has had power over key areas of policy, including housing, health, education and justice. Other areas are reserved to the UK Parliament, most importantly taxation, the welfare benefits system, employment legislation and immigration policy. It should be noted however that the devolution of power to Scotland should be seen as a 'process' rather than a single definitive act. Since the Scottish Parliament was re-established in 1999, new areas of responsibility have been given to the Parliament. The most recent current of devolution will see more powers of social security devolved to Scotland over the next four years.¹ In addition, the Scottish Parliament will soon have the power to set and collect most taxes in Scotland (excluding VAT and corporation tax).

However, this is for the future. Despite the possibility for divergence, the reality has been that there are remarkably consistent themes and approaches throughout the majority of the period since devolution began. For example, policies related poverty and welfare have been largely focused on 'work first approaches': labour market activation coupled support for increasing conditionality. There are some good reasons for this: in key areas such as labour market policy and welfare, the extent of powers have offered policy makers in Scotland little room for the development of alternative approaches. Perhaps more significantly, the existence of a common labour market across the UK, and long standing similarities in public policy preferences and in public attitudes have to some extent, been a break on policy divergence.²

However, with the election of the Scottish National Party in 2007, the possibility for real divergence appeared to become a more tangible prospect. This prospect was short lived as the economic crisis that began in 2008 undoubtedly limited the room for significant difference to develop in relation to the economic and social policy approaches of the Scottish and UK Governments.

1.2 Responding to economic crisis: the emergence of austerity

Problems in the banking sector in 2007 presaged the wider economic downturn and the recession that would soon engulf the global economy. The UK Labour Government moved to quickly support the financial institutions that were based here, starting with the Northern Rock Bank (NRB). The NRB was eventually nationalised, and over the next two years more financial institutions were brought into part public ownership. The support for the banking sector was part of a broader emerging strategy to prevent the economy sliding into a slump. Of course, this support came at great cost: initial estimates of around £850bn support to financial institutions now seems to have been an underestimate with the cost now currently estimated at over£1,100bn.³

1 Wane, K., K. Berr, C. Kidner, N Georghiou (2016) New Social Security Powers, Scottish Parliament Information Service, http://www.parliament.scot/ResearchBriefingsAndFactsheets/S5/SB_16-45_New_Social_Security_Powers.pdf

2 J. Adams & Schmuecker, K. (eds) (2006) Devolution in Practice. London: IPPR

3 National Audit Office (2016) Taxpayer Support for UK Banks <https://www.nao.org.uk/highlights/taxpayer-support-for-uk-banks-faqs/>

Support for the banks was just one element of the UK Government's approach. In addition, the UK Government sought to give additional support to homeowners whose properties were increasingly at risk of repossession, for example by making the process of receiving state support for those who had become unemployed easier to access. Perhaps the central element of the UK Government's approach was the introduction of Quantitative Easing in 2009. By 2009, around £200bn had been injected into the UK economy in order to stimulate economic activity.⁴ Fiscal policy was also used to prevent a depression, through cuts in VAT, the slashing of interest rates, increasing capital expenditure. In addition, employment taxes (National Insurance) and the top rate of tax for higher earners were also increased.

The approach of the Labour Government between 2008-10 changed dramatically with the formation of the Conservative and Liberal Democrat Government in 2010. Instead of macroeconomic policies designed to maintain economic activity, and the use of automatic stabilisers to protect those losing jobs, the new coalition government's top priority was deficit reduction. Public spending was already being cut under the Labour Government, but this process increased significantly with the new Coalition Government. There was an initial aim to reduce the deficit by £40bn by 2014-15. The balance between spending cuts and tax increases was 80% cuts to 20% tax increases. Of the cuts to public spending, one third was to come from welfare spending.

1.3 Welfare and austerity

The impact of austerity has fallen, not surprisingly, squarely on public services and on social protection as a whole. In 2010, the UK commenced a wide ranging programme of welfare reform. This left almost no area of social protection untouched, with the exception of state pensions where spending continued to increase after 2010.⁵ Whilst aspects of the Coalition's welfare policy could be seen as a continuation of existing pre-2010 policy - the increase and extension of conditionality, the further refinement of in-work support, etc. - these changes were introduced at great speed and alongside swingeing cuts to the value of many working age benefits.

In Scotland, the Coalition Government changes to welfare since 2010 are expected to reduce benefit expenditure by 2015/16 by around £6bn.⁶ The impact of these welfare changes has been far ranging in terms of the incomes of households across Scotland. Research by Beatty and Fothergill (2013) found that the scale of the loss in Scotland, for each working age adult, is broadly on a par with the GB average and that comparatively the welfare reforms hit Scotland less than northern England or Wales. Despite this there are some key areas to note in Scotland. The most deprived local authorities in Scotland have been the hardest hit. In Glasgow, the loss to the city as a whole when welfare reforms were implemented up to 2015 were expected to be estimated to be around £270m, *equivalent to £650 a year for every adult of working age in the city.*⁷

*With welfare reform there has been a new context of conditionality emerging. Evidence has illustrated the conditions that people are expected to meet for their benefits has become more stringent. This intensification had included a change in conditionality for some in work benefit recipients.*⁸ This has included more widespread use of sanctions and workfare. In addition here has been the growth in need for crisis and emergency support resulting from welfare conditionality.

In the wider labour market there has also been changes with the increase of precarious employment, typified by the increase in the use of zero hour contracts across the UK. The number of people on these contracts has increased from around 200,000 in 2010 to more than 900,000 in 2016.⁹ Despite this there has also been some critical differences in the Scottish labour market. Prior to the 2009, the Scottish labour market was performing better than the UK as a whole, with higher rates of employment. Since then, the

4 Edmonds, Webb, D., & Long, R. (2011). *Economic crisis: policy responses*. London: House of Commons Library

5 J. Hills (2015). *The Coalition's Record on Cash Transfers, Poverty and Inequality 2010-2015* (Working Paper 11). Available at <http://sticerd.lse.ac.uk/dps/case/spcc/WP11.pdf>

6 Scottish Government (2014). *Welfare Reform (Further Provision) (Scotland) Act 2012 Annual Report 2014*.

7 Scottish Government (2013). *2nd Report, 2013 (Session 4) The Impact of Welfare Reform on Scotland*.

8 First Wave Findings: Overview: *Social security in Scotland*. Online at www.welfareconditionality.ac.uk

9 Guardian (2016). *More than 900,000 UK workers now on zero hours contracts*. Available at <https://www.theguardian.com/uk-news/2016/sep/08/uk-workers-zero-hours-contracts-rise-tuc>

Scottish labour market performance has fallen away. Unemployment rates increased across the UK from 5.2% in May 2008 to reach a high point of 8.3% in September 2011. Since then, the trend has been largely downwards, although often in a faltering manner. In contrast, the Scottish unemployment rate rose from 4.4% in 2008 to peak at 8.7% in December 2011. Within these headline trends, there are important changes at work. For example women were significantly impacted by the recession, due in part to a heavier concentration in the public sector. Whereas women’s employment has now returned to pre-recession levels, this has been due to an increase in self-employment and more part-time working.¹⁰ The long term consequences in terms of future earnings and precarity are yet to be known.

Public services within Scotland and across the UK have suffered impacts since the crisis although again on some levels Scotland has fared better than the UK as a whole. Despite this we have seen a reduction in of the block grant to Scotland amounted to a cutback of 11% in real terms between 2011/12 and 2014/15, together with a 36% cut in capital budget and public sector pension provision. This has resulted in shifts across the public sector including service reduction, closure and transfer and savings across all Scottish local authorities.¹¹

Hastings have explored analysis in Scotland on the impacts of the cuts across the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SIMD). They found that ‘the most affluent authorities saw a slightly smaller percentage reduction than the most deprived (-7.1% vs -9.4%, or -4.5% vs -7.2% excluding education), and that there was some graduation over the deprivation bands, albeit with band 4 (fairly affluent) seeing quite a large cut, compared with band 3.’¹²

Table 1.1 Real budget spending changes by deprivation band, Scottish Local Authorities, 2010/2011-2014-2015

Low Income Deprivation band	% All	% Exc Education	Per Capita All	Per Capita Exc Educ
SIMD1 (poorest)	-9.4	-7.2	-277.7	-142.7
SIMD2	-9.1	-5.9	-241.5	-92.8
SIMD3	-6.2	-1.8	-178.5	-42.9
SIMD4	-8.0	-5.8	-252.4	-122.7
SIMD 5 (most affluent)	-7.1	-4.5	-240.2	-98.2
Scotland	-7.9	-5.1	-237.1	-99.8

Source Scottish Government Provisional Outturn and budget estimates cited in Hastings et al (2015).

Darinka Asenova explored the changing risks on communities as a result of austerity and found that continued to public services and ongoing changes to welfare provision are making daily lives of in some communities increasingly challenging. The combined impact of changes is widening existing geographical inequalities between disadvantaged and affluent communities. As public services in disadvantaged communities are stripped back, those living in these communities do not have the capacity to absorb risk.¹³

10 TUC (2015). *The Impact of Recession and Austerity on Women*. Available at <https://www.tuc.org.uk/sites/default/files/WomenRecession.pdf>
 11 Asenova, D., McKendrick, J., McCann, C., & Reynolds, R. (2015). *Redistribution of Social and Societal Risk*. York: Joseph Rowntree Foundation.
 12 Hastings, A., Bailey, N., Bramley, G, Gannon M., & Watkins, D (2015). *The Costs of the Cuts: the Impact on Local Government and Poorer Communities*. York: Joseph Rowntree Foundation.
 13 Asenova, D., McKendrick, J., McCann, C., Reynolds, R. (2015). *Redistribution of Social and Societal Risk*. York: Joseph Rowntree Foundation.

1.4 Lone parents and austerity

Against this backdrop of the economic crisis, austerity, changing labour market and social protection we must consider the experiences of vulnerable and marginalised groups. In particular there has been a disproportionate impact on women and in particular those in lone parent headed families.

In the city of Glasgow, where the fieldwork for this research was conducted, four out of ten families with children are lone parent families, according to the 2011 Census.¹⁴ Across local authorities in Scotland, this represents the highest in Scotland approximately 26,454 households with an anticipated increase in the future.¹⁵ Lone parent families face a number of barriers including access to childcare, inadequate incomes and access to employment and wider health inequalities. It is important to recognise that lone parents may also face other equality characteristic intersections that may make them more vulnerable such as ethnicity or disability and its important to recognise lone parent beyond a heterogeneous category.

Lone parent households are more likely to be found in poverty partially explained by employment rates, however lone parents are also more likely to experience in work poverty.¹⁶ As a vulnerable and marginalised group lone parents have been affected by the crisis and other changes due to their demographic position and the ongoing barriers they face. Evidence from the Institute of Fiscal Studies found that lone mothers will be hardest hit by the government's programme of benefit cuts and tax rises. It estimates they will lose an average 8.5% of their income after tax by 2015. This compared with 6.5% for couples with children and 2.5% for couples without children.¹⁷

One of the most critical impacts of the context of the crisis in Scotland for lone parents has been the introduction of welfare reform. Research by McQuaid and Graham (2014) highlights the changes for lone parents in relation to conditionality and the negative experiences lone parents report at the job centre. Webster (2014) highlights that figures for lone parents experiencing a 'sanction' on Job Seekers Allowance has risen from under 200 per month prior to 2008 to 4,700 per month.¹⁸ This had gendered impacts. Evidence from Engender outlines that increased conditionality and sanctioning is problematic for lone parents who will be impacted by their caring requirements, this will impacts on the hours they can work and the type of employment they have access to.¹⁹ Engender also highlights this will lead to wider gender inequality with the patterns of current workplace employment and occupational segregation becoming entrenched by the increasing 'workfare' direction of policy.

Lone parent households will also be impacted in wider ways by the crisis, such as the increase of precarious employment in the UK, changes to public services, housing insecurity and so on. This will have impacts on lone parents resilience and their day to day of them and their families. In the next chapter of this report will now go onto highlight the PACHRA approach employed to explore the research hypothesis on lone parent families.

14 Graham, H. & McQuaid, R. (2014). *Lone parents. Exploring the impacts of the UK government's welfare reforms on lone parents moving into work*. Glasgow: Glasgow centre for Population Health.

15 *Ibid.*

16 *Ibid.*

17 J. Browne (2011). *The impact of tax and benefit reforms by sex: some simple analysis*. London: Institute for Fiscal Studies.

18 Webster, D. (2014). *Fawcett Society Who Benefits? An independent inquiry into women and Jobseekers Allowance*.

19 Engender (2013). *A Widening Gap: Women and Welfare Reform*. Edinburgh: Engender/SCVO.

2. The participatory research approach

2.1 Participatory action human rights and capability approach

The RE-InVEST project aims to contribute to a more solidary and inclusive EU, through an inclusive, powerful and effective social investment strategy at EU level. Moreover, the project itself adopts a participative approach that gives voice to vulnerable groups and civil society organisations.²⁰ The RE-InVEST project applies Human Rights approach and the Capabilities approach (PACHRA) in exploring the impacts of the Crisis on vulnerable groups. The Human Rights Act was introduced in 1998 in the UK and sought to embed into UK law the rights contained in the European Convention of Human Rights.

The rights included in the Human Rights Act are:

Article 2: Right to life
Article 3: Right not to be tortured or treated in an inhuman or degrading way
Article 4: Right to be free from slavery or forced labour
Article 5: Right to liberty
Article 6: Right to a fair trial
Article 7: Right to no punishment without law
Article 8: Right to respect for private and family life, home and correspondence
Article 9: Right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion
Article 10: Right to freedom of expression
Article 11: Right to freedom of assembly and association
Article 12: Right to marry and found a family
Article 14: Right not to be discriminated against in relation to any of the rights
Contained in the European Convention
Article 1, Protocol 1: Right to peaceful enjoyment of possessions
Article 2, Protocol 1: Right to education
Article 3, Protocol 1: Right to free elections

The project is grounded in the theoretical framework of the capabilities approach. Capabilities are based upon the work of Amartya Sen (1999) and Nussbaum (2011) and is based around trying to increase social justice for groups experiencing oppression. The framework is based upon operationalising concepts such as wellbeing and development.²¹ It explores this in terms of ‘what a person can do’, the functionings that can be achieved and their capabilities or choices across functionings.

Instead of focusing on resources such as income, wealth or legal rights, capabilities seeks to replace this with an emphasis on understanding on what people are actually able to do and be through what Sen terms functioning’s and capabilities.²²

Functioning’s refers to states of a person and what they are able to do for example literacy, health mobility etc. This relates to capabilities, which is the opportunities to achieve freedom. Resources are based around the material conditions such as income and conversion factors convert resources. Conversion factors can be defined as personal social or structural.²³ The capabilities approach embeds agency within society through this analytical lens.

²⁰ RE-InVEST (2015). Available at <http://www.re-invest.eu/>

²¹ Brunner, R., & Watson, N. (nd). *What can the capabilities approach add to policy analysis in high income countries?* (What Works Scotland working paper 3).

²² Brunner, R., & Watson, N. (nd). *What can the capabilities approach add to policy analysis in high income countries?* (What Works Scotland working paper 3).

²³ Brunner, R., & Watson, N. (nd). *What can the capabilities approach add to policy analysis in high income countries?* (What Works Scotland working paper 4).

2.2 The crossing of knowledge process: project delivery

Research sessions were held in a community venue to allow for a relaxed and informal environment for discussion. Sessions were held weekly, with a crèche and lunch provided. A support worker from the NGO attended all sessions to assist with supporting the co-researchers.

Delivery of the project involved participative processes to allow the co-researchers control and direction over the research process. A variety of techniques were used to facilitate the crossing of knowledge. This included ensuring the setup of the room allowed full participation, using interactive tools such as red cards and the use of visual techniques. The project ended with seasonal fun activities to provide an emphasis on self-care from the project.

Events of the crisis reflection and context	Using images to stimulate discussion about the impact of economic crisis and austerity on lone parents
Drawing and modelling exercise on the effects of the Crisis	The group were issued with paper and building clay materials and were asked to provide illustrations and models of the impacts of the crisis on women and lone parents. These were then discussed by the group.
Timeline – your own narrative	Snake timelines were provided for groups to populate with their own narrative with key events over the last ten years during the austerity crisis. (Used within biographical narrative interviews)
Introducing Rights and Capabilities	The concept of capabilities and human rights were introduced verbally in terms of thinking broadly about society and how it shapes our lives this was then used to explore an initial discussion around this.
Exploring Capabilities	Using Nussbaum’s concepts of capabilities these were used for exploring aspects of people’s lives using the theoretical approach of the capabilities approach.
Exploring Human Rights	Group drew up a list to define what human rights they felt had been breached in the last ten years and discussed their feelings and experiences around this.
Action Planning	Group had a discussion about next steps from the project including Interest in an exchange between other reinvest groups. To feed into Poverty Alliance and One Parent Families policy and campaigning.

This approach was drawn from the core elements of the Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach (PAHRCA) developed in RE-InVEST. PAHRCA entails seven steps (Toolkit, 44-45):

1. identify and meet partner NGO/gatekeeper;
2. preliminary 'meet ups' (for trust building if necessary);
3. first meeting with participants – trust building;
4. developmental: implement developmental human rights & capability approach;
5. inquiry/data gathering;
6. identifying patterns (key issues and themes of concern to the group) and 7. Undertake action/outcome using one or combination of approaches.

The project involved a crossing of knowledge through the project through the experiences of NGO's and of vulnerable people see diagram below. The merging of knowledge process allows the co researchers in the project to be able to reflect and shape the research and to interpret based on their own lived realities.

Figure 2.1 Merging of Knowledge

2.3 Partnership and crossing of knowledge partners

To deliver work package for the RE-InVEST project, a number of preliminary meetings were held with a partner voluntary organisation: One Parent Families Scotland (OPFS). OPFS are a charitable organisation whose primary focus is on supporting and campaigning for the needs of lone parent family organisation in Scotland. Lone parents were chosen to be the population for this study as they affected by the crisis and other changes due to their demographic position and the ongoing barriers they face. Evidence from the Institute of Fiscal Studies found that lone mothers will be hardest hit by the government's programme of benefit cuts and tax rises. It estimates they will lose an average 8.5% of their income after tax by 2015. This compared with 6.5% for couples with children and 2.5% for couples without children

The Poverty Alliance undertook this research. The Poverty Alliance is the anti-poverty network for Scotland who are involved in a range of policy, campaigning and research activities. At these preliminary discussions a number of areas including:

- Theoretical underpinnings of the RE-InVEST project and aims of RE-InVEST.
- Sampling for the project.
- Recruitment processes and materials.
- Support needs and support structures of the co researchers.
- Programme of activities.

- Policy context shaping lone parent needs.

To recruit for the project, lone parents were drawn from OPFS service delivery projects across the Glasgow. The group selected had a range of support needs and confidence levels. Support workers from the OPFS advice service approached individuals on behalf of the RE-InVEST Project and to provide a trusted point of contact within the project. A breakdown of the demographic information of the group can be found below. A total of 11 co-researchers were involved in this project.

Equalities Characteristics*	Category	Number of Participants
Gender	Female	11
	Male	0
Age	25-29	2
	30-34	4
	35-39	1
	40-44	3
	50-54	1
	No religion	5
	Christian	4
Religion/Faith	Other Roman Catholic	1
	Other Protestant	1
Sexual Orientation	Heterosexual or straight	11
Ethnicity	White Scottish	7
	Black British	1
	Scottish African	1
	White German	1
	Asian British (Nepali)	1
Disability	Physical or mental health condition or illness lasting or expecting to last 12 months or more?	4
	Does your condition or illness reduce your ability to carry out day to day activities? Yes a lot	1
	Does your condition or illness reduce your ability to carry out day to day activities? Yes a little	4
	Does your condition or illness reduce your ability to carry out day to day activities? No not at all	

* Multiple answers may be given and respondents self-define their characteristics.

The group selected were all single parents, and had a range of different experiences including mental ill health, unemployment, low waged employment, housing problems, caring responsibilities.

It was expected that some difficult personal issues for the women involved in the project would arise during the research. Discussions were had with OPFS in order to be sure that the women involved in the project were properly supported during the research. We identified issues related to the timing of the field-work, winter 2015, as potentially problematic due to the seasonal pressures that people may experience. It was also acknowledged that the nature of this phase of the project - reflecting on potentially traumatic periods from each individuals past - could be difficult.

One Parent Families Scotland provided a support worker for the session to address and identify support where needed. This allowed for a deep exploration of issues impacting on the group to be conducted in a supportive environment and to embed ethical research practice when working alongside with vulnerable groups.

2.4 Reflection on the process

The opportunity to participate in the project was viewed positively by the group. The research project provided an opportunity to collaborate and highlight issues being experienced both for them and their families. The importance of speaking out about social injustices was emphasised by the group in recognition of the context families were experiencing.

3. Biographical Narratives

The following interviews were conducted with two members of the group. These respondents were selected based on the events outlined from their life in the individual exercise of the snake timelines. The respondents agreed to share their experiences in an in-depth biographical narrative interview.

3.1 Lucy's story

Lucy – biographical narrative March 2016

Lucy* is a single parent who lives with her three children who are all under the age of 17. She outlines the events of her life below and how her life has been affected by austerity since the economic crisis.

Prior to becoming a single parent Lucy worked as a sales assistant in a large high street chain. She was employed in a concession unit within the chain. She worked a few hours per week, was paid around the National Minimum Wage and was only able to maintain this work with the support of her partner. As a result of the restructuring Lucy was transferred to another store on even fewer hours.

'We had a concession within (the retailer) which closed when we went into administration, ... they offered me another four hour contract in town which quite honestly after travelling to it wasn't worth it.'

Due to the reduced income, Lucy left the job. Shortly afterwards, her relationship broke down resulting in her becoming homeless. Although she found accommodation, her situation remained difficult, partly because of her immigration status and partly because of the health of her children.

'When I moved into temporary accommodation – that turned into a long convoluted process with DWP (Department for Work and Pensions) and housing. Obviously with a European passport [non UK], it was difficult to get things done. I was getting letters from the school to say that the kids weren't at school and finally got that all sorted out.'

The following two years were a difficult period for Lucy in which she had to be a carer for one child who was ill and support her other children, all whilst being a single parent.

'Because you have two other girls who you have to make sure in some way are still getting to school, looked after, fed, etc., all whilst running back to the hospital for the one who is actually sick.'

She also faced childcare difficulties whilst supporting her child who was in a hospital. She got financial support from a voluntary organisation to assist her with the costs of attending the hospital.

'They deal with everything, especially with their transition, ... they had all sorts of help because obviously the extra funds and taxis and bus fares were quite a lot and back and forth were quite a bit.'

During this time she was unable to obtain employment and was given some support with her living costs through the welfare system. She faced some difficulties with her housing. For example, she was unable to get necessary disability adaptations to her accommodation or assistance to help get them. This meant her having to carry her child and their wheelchair up and down stairs on a regular basis.

Her child's illness going into remission marked a new phase in Lucy's life although not one without challenges. Lucy was transferred from Income Support (a 'passive' benefit) to active labour market benefits. She was put onto the Work Programme as part of her requirements to be entitled to benefits.

Lucy felt that the organisation running the work programme failed to understand the key issues that constrained and shaped her life. These were childcare, the need for employment that was within school hours and allowed her time off during school holidays. This restricted the type of employment she could seek and she felt that the work programme was unsympathetic to her needs.

'The first advisor I got after the first few appointments she kind of realised my limitations in time and from then on tried to push going self-employed, which was really frustrating, because obviously with self-employment you need a strong plan. You need a strong idea and you need to know what direction you need. This is what she seemed to push.'

Lucy also took part in a work experience trial with a high street retailer but it did not result in a job. However, Lucy has, as a result of her volunteering, been offered sessional work for a period of time. She was advised by the work programme this would not affect her benefits but she has subsequently been investigated by the job centre regarding this. This has caused Lucy a degree of stress and anxiety.

3.2 Julia's story

Julia is a single parent with two children and a grandchild, all of whom live with her. She has been working in retail jobs for some time, in between raising her children and providing support for her new grandchild. Over the last 20 years, she has consistently encountered problems with social housing, child care and employment. Her problems in these areas have often been interconnected with her relationship status – when her relationship with her partner broke down she would often encounter problems with housing, childcare and employment.

Julia's problems with housing pre-dated the economic crisis in 2008. In fact, she had been on the waiting list for a new house (a newly built house) for 11 years:

'I finally got a house that I had been waiting on for 11 years. We were told 11 years previously that we were getting one, then they never got built. We got the keys two days before Christmas.'

Family issues meant that she and her family moved to a new part of Glasgow. However, shortly after this move her relationship with partner ended, resulting in another house move for her and the two children. She found the experience of becoming a lone parent difficult especially with the change from two incomes to just one.

'Because there was obviously two incomes coming in and it was alright, but obviously I felt it when there was only my money coming into the house.'

After a period of time she began volunteering with a local voluntary organisation to obtain experience and to build up her skills and enhance resume for employment. She found support on her own with skills rather than use the Job Centre support which she found to be insufficient.

Julia continued doing courses and volunteering and eventually obtained work as a sales assistant with a high street retail chain. This work was obtained through a specifically designed through a specialist scheme with the retailer to assist lone parents back into employment. This was beneficial for Julia who enjoyed the role and felt that it had increased her wellbeing. Despite the fact that she enjoyed the work and her income increased, there remained some problems. The job was temporary post, and when the initial training phase was completed she was offered other work but in location far from her home. This led to familiar problems with transport and accessing flexible childcare that could accommodate her shift patterns.

At this time she was living in private rented accommodation. This entailed a higher rent and led to financial problems. Julia had to take out a loan from a local charity which provided support to people on low incomes. This loan took some time to repay as she was only receiving Income Support.

The accommodation she is lives in now is in need of repair and since the birth of her grandchild is overcrowded. Julia no longer has a bedroom and has lost privacy and space within her home. She does not see a change in this situation for the foreseeable future unless she is able to find other suitable affordable accommodation. Her daughter and grandchild are unlikely to be eligible for housing support on their own

due to recent welfare benefit changes. Her daughter is 16 years old and will not qualify for Housing Benefit until she is 21 years old when the most recent changes have been applied.

Whilst she has been working in the retailer childcare has become the *de facto* responsibility of her eldest daughter who also had a baby of her own to care for. Julia felt that this was not ideal but noted she had limited options outside of this. She is concerned about the impact this may have on her daughter.

'Childcare would be right up there in terms of the things that I would need to think about. I would really need to consider if I would take another course like that, yeah at the weekend I don't want to just do weekend because I don't want to put the strain on my daughter.'

Julia is also facing challenges with the type of employment that is available in the current labour market. She is looking for employment through the Universal Job match finder in the job centre but there are difficulties with this, as it does not list jobs that fit with the hours that Julia can commit to. Finding work that can fit with school hours for her youngest child, and where she can have more time during the school holidays is particularly challenging.

Julia is also facing difficulties with her current accommodation as she is being pursued for rent arrears and has been threatened with eviction. This is causing instability for both her and her family.

4. Analysis: the economic crisis and the perspective of lone parents

4.1 Introduction

Evidence from this study indicates that the economic crisis has had far-reaching impacts on lone parents in terms of their rights and their capabilities. This section of the report will cover:

- an analysis of the social crisis from the perspective of (erosion of) human rights, social (dis)investment, loss of (individual and collective) capabilities and;
- an analysis of the social, political and cultural impact of the crisis: the relationships between the rise of poverty and social exclusion, the decline of social cohesion and trust, and the threats to democracy and solidarity in the EU.

This RE-InVEST project employed the Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach (PAHRCA). This uses the approaches of human rights and capabilities to understand the impacts of the economic crisis on vulnerable groups. By applying this approach the research was able to explore the impacts of the crisis on lone parents in Scotland. All information drawn from across the research project was coded into themes and analysed drawing upon the theoretical framework to understand the research questions.

4.2 Impact on individual capabilities (choices?) (short and long term effects)

Participants outlined a number of issues that affected their individual capabilities and functionings. Among participants there was shared consensus of the need to be able to lead a life that was healthy, safe and allowed opportunities for expression, freedom and choice at both individual level and collective levels. Participants felt that their position as single parents shaped and influenced their lives and their families in terms of what they were able to do and able to be. Their opportunities and freedoms were constrained as a result of economic crisis and austerity and shaped by these economic drivers. Participants discussed a number of themes including privatisation, the labour market, and access to services, social cohesion, and how this influenced their capabilities in life.

Through a series of exercises, participants reflected on the issue of individual capabilities (choices) and the economic crisis. It was recognised that over the last ten years the context for lone parent families had changed considerably with increased pressures for them and their families. Parents described how it had impacted on their health outcomes, their social and cultural lives and their connections with wider society.

4.3 Lone parent demographics

Within Glasgow, where this study was conducted, lone parent households now comprise four out of ten families with children. This is the highest of all 32 local authorities in Scotland, and expected to increase over the next 25 years.²⁴ The participants reflected on their position as lone parents. It was clear that they felt at a disadvantage in comparison with the 'traditional' two-parent family. The group outlined how they were supporting a family emotionally and physically on their own and faced many, often hidden, problems doing so. They felt that this was often overlooked by wider society which failed to recognise the importance

²⁴ GCPH(2014) 'Lone Parents in Glasgow'

http://www.gcph.co.uk/work_themes/theme_3_poverty_disadvantage_and_the_economy/early_years/lone_parents

of supporting single parents in order to allow them to fulfil their and their childrens' needs. Many expressed the view that this lack of recognition had increased the scapegoating and discrimination they faced as lone parents. In the face of this perceived stigmatisation and discrimination, there was an attendant lack of recognition of the value of the work lone parents carried in bringing up children. If such work was valued there would perhaps be more understanding of the needs of lone parents and support for them to access a wider range of opportunities.

Being a lone parent also limited opportunities for employment compared to two parent households especially when it came to childcare and employment.

This was exacerbated by both austerity measures and greater conditionality for those on active benefits such as Job Seekers Allowance (JSA). These made it difficult for lone parents to exercise freedom in their employment choices or career paths.

4.4 Changing welfare system

A central part of the response to economic crisis in the UK, particularly after 2010, was a growing emphasis on the 'need' to reduce welfare expenditure. Whilst many changes were already well underway in the UK prior to the crisis in 2008, there is little doubt that the pace of change picked up in the period after 2010. Lone parents were particularly susceptible to these changes.

The welfare system had significant influence over the life of lone parents involved within this study. One of the biggest changes in the welfare system that has affected lone parents is greater conditionality attached to their benefits. Webster (2014) notes that welfare policy towards lone parents has focused on getting them off benefits and into work. He argues that the sanctions system as it now operated does not serve as enabling mechanism to assist lone parents into work. Evidence from Graham and McQuaid (2014) shows that Job Seekers Allowance (JSA) led lone parents into applying for and accepting jobs that are not necessarily sustainable nor reconcilable with caring responsibilities, in order to meet their job search conditions.

In this research lone parents highlighted through use of visual materials the experiences and pressures they faced with the increased use of conditionality and sanctions. They highlighted that this led to families experiencing hardship and were often forced to access emergency food aid provision. They also discussed the nature of the relationship with job centres becoming more authoritarian and being scrutinised.

Figure 4.1 Drawing illustrating effects of increased conditionality

Labour market support has changed significantly since the start of the economic crisis. Through the Work Programme, the UK Government has contracted out labour market support to a mixture of private and voluntary sector agencies. The Work Programme replaced previous Welfare to Work support programmes.

The system operates a mandatory approach and is applied on different levels dependent on the benefit individuals receive. Evidence from the Public Accounts Committee found that only 3.6% of participants (compared to a target of 12%) had found secure employment.²⁵ Concerns were also raised the Public Accounts Committee regarding conditionality in the Work Programme system. Indeed, one report found that at one stage participants in the Work Programme were more likely to have been sanctioned than to have been placed in a job.²⁶

In this study examples were provided of the (in?)adequacy of Work Programme in supporting and providing new skills to lone parents to enable them to access the labour market. Participants spoke of the ineffectiveness of the support to enable them to secure sustained employment that fitted with the demands and responsibilities they faced as lone parents. Increased conditionality also meant increased appointments with the job centre and this again had implications in terms of childcare with some parents forced to take their children along to appointments.

4.5 Health

The impact of austerity on people's health was also a core concern. Participants discussed how the difficulties they faced on an everyday basis led to negative health outcomes on both their physical and mental health. The negative impact on health was more acute for those who were in receipt of out of work benefits especially if they had been sanctioned.

Research by Gingerbread (2014) found that in the first 21 months of the new conditionality regime ending June 2014, 145,000 single parents claiming JSA in the UK had received a sanction. This represented six per cent of all individual decisions.²⁷ The research also indicated that within all sanction levels, a higher proportion of single parents receive a non-adverse sanction decision. This indicates that single parents were being inappropriately referred for a sanction in the first instance or wrongly sanctioned as a result of the decision making process.

This was reflected in the research group, fear of sanctioning for those in receipt of in work benefit was a significant concern that governed their day-to-day lives. Concerns were raised by the women in this study about their experiences with individual advisors at the job centre and in particular the perceptions advisors may have had about lone parents. People started to worry days before their appointments, with some experiencing many sleepless nights. This prolonged pressure in their life affected their mental health and is illustrated in Figure 4.2 below.

25 Public Accounts Committee (2014). *The Work Programme*. London: The Stationary Office.

26 MacInnes, T., Aldridge, H., Bushe, S., Tinson, A., & Sefton, T. (2014). *Monitoring Poverty and Social Exclusion 2014*. London: New Policy Institute.

27 Gingerbread (2014). *Single parents and benefit sanctions November 2014*. Available at: www.gingerbread.org.uk/uploads/media/17/9340.pdf

Figure 4.2 Picture reflecting on fears for the future

Conflicts could also arise between health care and job centre appointments. Participants told of the pressure they felt (fear of being sanctioned) if a health appointment clashed with a sign on time or meeting with a job centre:

'It depends on the advisor you have got. I've got an appointment coming up ... but I've got a hospital appointment on the same day at a similar time. That appointment is for an hour so I won't be able to go the job centre appointment too, I'm trying to speak with someone from welfare rights to give me advice before I go in ... It should be about your health but it's not.'

This resulted in people having to take letters to the Job Centre with proof of appointments to meet the terms of conditionality placed upon them.

Health was also discussed in terms of the cuts and reductions in services. In particular the reduced time and care available to families by medical staff at all levels from health visitors to GP's. There was also a postcode lottery for services and waiting times across the city.

Research by Graham and McQuaid (2014) showed that lone parent families are disadvantaged relative to two parent families as lone parent households are less likely to have someone in work, and when working are more likely to experience in-work poverty.²⁸ Children living in a lone parent household are twice more likely to be in poverty than children in two parent household.

4.6 Insecurity

The economic crisis has led to greater insecurity for lone parents in the UK. This insecurity has been felt through service cuts, changes in the welfare system, and changes in the economic environment and wider issues such as housing availability. Participants felt that their lives had become more insecure as a result of some of these changes. Meeting the needs of their children shaped the way they were able to engage with the labour market. It constrained their flexibility to adapt and therefore the job choices they were able to make. This had knock-on effects on housing choices. Parents wanted properties that were accessible to

²⁸ Graham, H., & McQuaid, R. (2014). *Exploring the impacts of the UK Governments Welfare Reforms on Lone Parents Moving into Work.*

schools, near good leisure facilities and were of adequate size to meet their needs. Lack of social housing and waiting lists for a home meant that many were in private rented accommodation. Experiences of private rented accommodation were mixed and in some cases were tied to employment which increased feelings of insecurity.

The labour market was seen as having become more insecure and with available work was often short term and precarious. This is reflected in the relative increase in zero hour contracts.²⁹ Concerns were raised about conditionality and the conflict created between accepting any employment and wanting to pursue other career paths or options such as studying.

There were concerns about reduction of and insecurity around support services that provided vital support to lone parents. This was especially the case with voluntary sector organisations which although often providing more person centred support were under constant threat from funding cuts.

Insecurity in participants lives contributed to higher levels of anxiety. It also affected the aspirations they had for them and their families and wider life choices and opportunities. The insecurity they experienced made it difficult to plan long term, reducing their focus instead to meeting short term immediate needs. Long term change, for example moving house, needed to be carefully managed to deal with potential periods of financial insecurity

4.7 Impact on human rights

The economic crisis has had a number of impacts on human rights. People discussed the erosion of their rights and the reduced capacity they felt they had to exercise their rights. As lone parents, they discussed the challenges they faced as demographic group in terms of advocacy for their needs. Participants argued that their rights were upheld more when they supported trusted intermediary NGO's who understood their individual needs and circumstances. This section will outline the breaches of rights the research group had identified as a result of the economic climate.

4.8 Choosing to have a child

Choosing when to have a child is a fundamental right recognised by the UN Convention on Human Rights. Participants felt that the impact of austerity and economic crisis had influenced their thinking on whether they could/should have more children. The consensus of the group was that their opportunity or choice to have another child would now be constrained due to restrictions on support available to families.

'In the current climate I would be scared to have another baby.'

'I wouldn't bring another child into this world. I feel sorry for all the kids now being born.'

Pregnancy support, post-natal care and early years services had all been reduced. Services were perceived by participants as having fewer staff with bigger caseloads. One participant shared her experience of the maternity unit where patients were left unattended for long periods due to a combination of large caseload and staff shortage. This was a particularly difficult situation for first time mothers to learn how to care for their baby.

Several examples were provided about the inadequacy of support for breastfeeding a baby. Evidence from the NHS Scotland (2015) highlights there is a clear association between breastfeeding and deprivation. Mothers in the least deprived areas were nearly three times as likely to exclusively breastfeed at 6-8 weeks compared with mothers in the most deprived areas.³⁰

Other examples given were on post-natal support from Health Visitors. Health Visitors are a post-natal outreach service in Scotland. The support being offered was constrained by caseloads and in some cases

²⁹ Scottish Government (2015). *Zero Hours Evidence Note*. Edinburgh: Scottish Government.

³⁰ NHS Scotland/Information Services Division (2014). *Breastfeeding Statistics Scotland*. Financial Year 2014/15
Publication date: 27 October 2015.

participants did not receive any support. Delivery of post-natal support and observation of the child was expected to take place at General Practitioner surgeries instead but this had constraints in terms of available appointments and the surgeries' own caseload demands.

'2012 was when I had my young daughter and I didn't have my health visitor come to the house once because I was told there wasn't enough staff, that they didn't have time to see us.'

'My younger daughter missed her 30 month check and the health visitor said we don't have space to see her.'

'I saw my health visitor twice. I used to hear from her [the health visitor] was "I have another 300 plus clients in addition to you".'

A third issue emerged on the issue of maternity grants and the removal of support for a second child. The Sure Start Maternity Grant was a means-tested lump sum payment worth £500 per child, which was paid to low income families to assist with the cost of maternity and baby items, but was revised in 2011. Since 2011, eligibility has been restricted to first children, first multiple births or births where the other children are over 16. The value (£500) has not increased³¹ despite rising living costs. The group recognised the value of this support and disagreed with the policy changes restricting it.

'It was a grant you didn't have to pay back but you could buy preparation clothes and, that it stopped the end of 2010 ... and then that was it ... it helped first time parents just when the baby's born I bought sleep stuff and things like that. But that's been scrapped, that money.'

All of these issues, combined with the freezing of Child Benefit, influenced the participants' decision on whether to have another child.

4.9 Rights in the workplace

The right to work without discrimination is also recognised by the UN Convention on Human Rights. Article 23 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights states that:

1. everyone has the right to work, to free choice of employment, to just and favorable conditions of work and to protection against unemployment;
2. everyone, without any discrimination, has the right to equal pay for equal work;
3. everyone who works has the right to just and favorable remuneration ensuring for himself and his family an existence worthy of human dignity, and supplemented, if necessary, by other means of social protection;
4. everyone has the right to form and to join trade unions for the protection of his interests.

The status of single parents in the workplace was also discussed. Their rights as workers were seen as being regularly infringed.

Despite Article 23, participants raised several workplace issues that they felt contravened it. For research participants who were in work, points were raised on treatment and human rights in the workplace. Issues of unfair practice, restructuring, loss of employment and zero hours contracts emerged.

As lone parents accessing and sustaining work was difficult in order to meet their childcare needs and for work to be financially viable. Precarious employment placed additional pressures on lone parents due to their caring responsibilities. Fluctuations in income caused additional pressures and shortfalls were often difficult to anticipate and mitigate. Lone parents argued that employers were not able to meet their needs. They argued they were subject greater conditionality to be participating in the labor market but their rights and experiences and needs in the labour market were not recognised.

31 Maternity Action (2014). *Valuing families? The impact of cuts to maternity benefits?*

Several issues were reported on the practices of some employers. For example, some employers would issue penalties for time keeping infringements and place restrictions on toilet breaks. This placed workers under stress in their working day.

'My mum left her work through that last week. She was 3 seconds late. And the man was in her face with a penalty notice.'
'If I'm in work, you're not allowed to leave the shop floor. So if you're 3 hours in and you need the toilet, I can't go to the toilet for another hour.'

Workers' rights during a company restructuring was another issue raised by some of the participants. One restructuring resulted in staff being laid off with minimal notice or being given reduced hours or demoted posts. Their appeal to be no recourse or appeals process for the staff to challenge such developments.

Zero hour contracts were seen as exploitative. Those on zero hours contracts were seen as a completely flexible resource, and were preferred by managers to those on more traditional forms of contract:

'They have 4 member of staff in on 0 hours, the managers are using them as opposed to other staff.'

Local authority cuts had also affected those working in public services. Reduced budgets meant staff were often shifted around different services which was often mismanaged, with shortfall in shift patterns placing pressure on staff to maintain and deliver services.

4.10 Rights and living conditions

Article 25 of the Declaration of Human Rights states that:

1. everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and well-being of himself and of his family, including food, clothing, housing and medical care and necessary social services, and the right to security in the event of unemployment, sickness, disability, widowhood, old age or other lack of livelihood in circumstances beyond his control;
2. motherhood and childhood are entitled to special care and assistance. All children, whether born in or out of wedlock, shall enjoy the same social protection.

Participants spoke extensively about their standard of living being eroded. As result of welfare reform the UK's system of social protection was seen as inadequate in meeting people's needs. Having secure and habitable accommodation was seen as a priority for lone parents and their families.

Housing provided an anchor for achieving other outcomes and opportunities such as good health, and employment. The quality and sustainability of their housing was therefore critical. Participants described how the economic crisis had placed greater pressure on housing and that lone parents and other demographic groups were more likely to be facing issues such as homelessness or living in poor quality insecure housing.

This is supported by wider research. Evidence from Shelter shows that Scotland faces challenges in providing good quality housing. Their research shows that 150,000 households are on social housing waiting lists, 940,000 households experience fuel poverty and some 73,000 households are overcrowded. They also estimated that around 29,000 people are classed homeless in 2014.³²

Several of the group reported housing concerns. This included issues such as problems dealing with landlords (both private and social), waiting lists for housing and repairs to properties. Several people reported being affected by rent arrears and therefore being at increased risk of homelessness.

'I know someone who just got made homeless, she's got two kids and due to housing benefit mix up she was in arrears. She's got put out her house two weeks away from Christmas and they told her there were no homeless houses.'

32 Commission for Housing and Wellbeing (2015). *A blueprint for Scotland's future*. Available at: <http://housingandwellbeing.org/assets/documents/Commission-Final-Report.pdf>

People were being left in vulnerable situations with their children. This was often in accommodation that was infested with insects or had poor quality heating.

'They put me in a council house when I was homeless. When we moved in at daytime it looked okay but at night so many cockroaches came out. My son was nearly five and he always slept on the sofa in the living room because he thought on the sofa they won't climb.'

One participant discussed being in the homeless system with a three day old baby.

'The homeless house I got put in was awful, it was £10 a day to heat. So my daughter and me were living in the bedroom, wrapped up with one heater on. The heating ran out at 2am in the morning. I knew there was usually a backup but there wasn't anything. I had a 3 day old baby.'

Accommodation that was poorly insulated or was affected by dampness had an impact on the health of participants, including respiratory illness. Moving on from poor accommodation was seen as difficult or impossible. Choices were limited due to the increased length of social housing waiting lists and accessing alternatives such as the private rented sector held its own challenges.

4.11 Rights and education

Under Article 26 of the UN Declaration of Human Rights, everyone has the right to education. Several issues emerged concerning lone parents and the right to education. The conditionality attached to their benefits was seen as a barrier to them accessing higher education. Lack of support for childcare whilst studying was another issue. These all worked to constrain their choices and opportunities.

On a wider level, they also faced issues with their childrens educational attainment. Their ability to participate in extracurricular activities was constrained and pressures on learning spaces such as libraries had increased. Recognition within schools of barriers and access issues families may be facing was a key issue such as digital access.

4.12 Collective capabilities: stigma, discrimination and community cohesion

The issues of stigma and discrimination were raised extensively across project activities. Stigma and discrimination were perceived to have increased for communities over the last decade. The economic crisis was seen as a driver of a less cohesive society which focused more on individualism. Lone parents reported feeling that they were being judged on their economic circumstances. They argued that the media and politicians were contributing to this negative view. Gaffney, Baumberg and Bell (2012) has supported that this has been contributing factor in the UK.³³

Several members of the group reported other forms of discrimination such as racially motivated hate crime. This had been experienced when they were with their children.

'That's the worst, when you're with a child and someone makes this racist kind of comment to you or your baby. You can take racism if its juts myself but when the kids are there.'

'I got into trouble because a group of young boys spat on my daughter when she was 4 ... they called me all the names under the sun, both my daughter and myself.'

This impacted on the wider safety and security people were able to achieve in their daily lives and the connections with their communities. Community cohesion was viewed as a fragile phenomenon and that the focus on individualism was shifting people away for community support to more distrustful society. Participants discussed breakdown in social cohesion during the period of the UK riots. This had been seen as a

33 Gaffney, Baumberg and Bell (2013). *The missing dimension of Poverty Stigma*. Available at <http://www.newstatesman.com/economics/2013/02/missing-dimension-poverty-stigma>

negative form of protest but illustrated the anger and dissatisfaction people were feeling in the UK as communities came under increasing pressure to make ends meet.

A lack of community cohesion could also lead to other factors such as social isolation. Public service such as libraries and other community facilities and community projects had been reduced which restricted the ability of people to come together.

Social isolation affected lone parents particularly. For example being a lone parent often meant reduced adult company and limited time and resources to participate in wider social activities due to the pressures of bringing up children and managing a home alone and in some cases employment.

The group also discussed the way in which the economic crisis had not been experienced equally. The group acknowledged the wider inequality present in Scotland and the UK and the distance that they experienced as a result of economic disparity. One lone parent discussed how this was a barrier for her in their playground in terms of staying away from other parents who they deemed to be more affluent than her.

4.13 Democracy and civic participation

Being an active citizen was viewed as important by lone parents involved in the study. They viewed it as important for a good and cohesive society. The group recognised the limitations for lone parents to participate in public participation structures. Their opportunities to be heard or participate in policy and decision making processes were often dependent on engagement with voluntary organisations. The group also felt that the Scottish referendum on independence in 2014 had provided an opportunity for people to engage more in politics and this had a positive effect on Scotland.

Welfare reform was seen as key area and there was consensus in the group that those on a lower incomes did not have opportunities to collectively challenge the austerity climate. Many of the changes and cuts were viewed as inevitable and people described scepticism that things would change for those living in poverty.

However many in the group did engage in some types of civic participation such as volunteering and taking part in activities such as school committees. These activities provided an opportunity to 'give something back' and were viewed as important for the benefit of both the individual and the wider community. Community action was viewed as important source of change and one that was authentic to different group's needs.

4.14 Conditionality and freedom

Living on a low income limited people's freedom to live life as they wished. For example conditionality restricted how much time they could spend on activities other than job-seeking.

'The letters are very threatening. It's the format too. Emotionally it's very distressing; it's kind of like a threat. If you don't do this, this is what will happen. You feel anxious.'

'Because the [job centre] got power over you. If you say something, then that's them, they go and sanction you. They've got a hold over you. Total fear, even just walking into the jobcentre you are scared.'

Conditionality had also created a mindset where people felt guilty about how they spent their time. People spoke of feeling that they were under more scrutiny when they were in receipt of benefits and that there was a constant pressure to be achieving and fulfilling time in ways that would be deemed meaningful. Complying with conditionality also contributed to feelings of less privacy, as everything had to be documented and recorded.

4.15 Security of income

A clear factor emerged on the need for security of income. A steady, regular income was a critical factor for resilience for individuals within this study. Consistency of income was critical: being on low income required

significant day-to-day management, advance planning, and strategies for dealing with change. Inconsistent or unpredictable sources of income made these tasks much more difficult. This applied for those both in and out of paid employment. Participants discussed threats to the security of income as a result of increased conditionality within the welfare system and the changing labour market and precarious employment.

Changes in income levels, either short or long term, could result in a lower level of resilience. The impact on people's lives of having a reduced income were far reaching. These included the ability to meet basic needs such as food, heat and shelter. The ability to cope with such changes was dependent on individuals' overall confidence and wellbeing. If individuals were already feeling depressed or anxious because of their situation, then this in turn affected what support or resources individuals were able to draw upon when facing a crisis.

One participant discussed the impact that the precarious nature of employment had had on her life. She had been employed for some time on a low paid job on a zero hours contract. The fluctuations in her working hours had conflicted with welfare support such as tax credits and housing benefits.

'The employers' a nightmare. I started off at 16 hours, then to 9, now currently at 4. Making £20 at the end of every week. I have to sign on. It mucked up housing benefit then working tax credits, then they stopped it all. I owed on the tax credits. I am going to be better off on benefits until I find a job that's 16 hours or more. It left me in a load of debt.'

Research by Harkins and Egan (2013) found that there has been a rise in women working part time in Glasgow since 2008.³⁴ Evidence from Citizens Advice Scotland³⁵ drawn from frontline advice services reported evidence of zero hour contract workers being unable to meet their basic living costs and greater susceptibility to income shocks.

For those on out-of-work benefits lack of security of income was shaped by welfare conditionality especially being sanctioned. The capacity to cope with changes in income levels when on benefits was limited. This greatly affected individuals' levels of resilience mainly due to the unsustainability of these strategies. Some reported having to access emergency food aid to cope through such periods. Both the changing labour market and increased welfare conditionality were contributing to an increasingly pressurised environment for lone parents and their families. This contributed to fragility and uncertainty in their lives.

4.16 Access to service provision in an austerity context

A key factor for improving resilience was access to wider support services. Public services were felt to play a vital role in maintaining the resilience of individuals, their families and their wider communities. Access to public services varied across the research participants. Since the economic crisis, services were generally felt to be more stretched and to have longer waiting lists. Accessing support was seen as more difficult even when people were clearly able to articulate their needs. This was leading to people's problems spiralling instead of being dealt with at an early stage. This situation was particularly problematic for those who lived in more vulnerable or chaotic circumstances.

The experience with health care services varied across the group, especially the support provided by post-natal health visitors. For some in the group this meant getting only the minimum level of support due to the health visitor's heavy caseload. It was a similar situation with access to General Practitioners. Lone parents reported varying lengths of times for appointments. Cuts to service provision were viewed as disproportionately affecting the most vulnerable. Areas of deprivation were argued to be more susceptible to experiencing loss of provision despite their higher levels of need.

'I've seen cuts by the city council mostly in schools with budgets getting smaller and smaller.'

'Services available in affluent areas aren't as much of a risk of being shut down.'

34 Harkins, C., & Egan, J. (2013). *The rise in in work poverty and the changing nature of poverty and work in Scotland. What are the implications for population health?* Glasgow: Glasgow Centre for Population and Health.

35 Citizens Advice Scotland (2013). *Scottish Affairs Committee Inquiry into Zero Hours contracts response from Citizens Advice.*

Research by Unison (2014) on the impact of austerity across Scotland's public services support these views. Unison highlighted the loss of revenue for local government in Scotland. Spending in the most deprived areas has been cut by £90 per head more than in the most affluent areas. They also highlight additional pressures such as the impact on the workforce across local government of a 50,000 reduction in the number of public sectors workers since the financial crash with estimates of a further 60,000 over the next 5 years.

4.17 Widening inequalities

A core impact of the economic crisis has been growing income inequality. Lone parents discussed that this was very visible in Scotland. In their view one of the most significant indicators was the rise of food insecurity and foodbanks. Hardship had been experienced by many in the group as result of the economic crisis. Several spoke of going without and the risks they faced in regards to homelessness. One group member had accommodation tied to their employment; another had been served with eviction notices. Another spoke of having to access a homeless shelter. The group recognised the hardship they had experienced after the crisis was not the experienced by everyone in their community. This difference in experience led to a disconnect in terms of how people understood their lives and related to their circumstances.

The group emphasised how this was most acute for their children. The gap between their better off peers resulted in a reduction of leisure opportunities and holidays for children. Some in the group spoke of relying on support from family or voluntary organisations to provide holidays.

4.18 Lasting Impacts

As part of the discussion of events in their lives over the last ten years, the group produced timelines. Significant personal circumstances have combined with the crisis to contribute to a number of impacts on people's lives. When people had incurred changing life circumstances such as separation from a partner, they had become more financially vulnerable. Rebuilding a life for them and their children after the crisis had been more difficult to achieve as a result of the increased pressures on services, the precariousness of the labour market and their position as lone parents providing the main caregiving for their children. This period of their life's created long terms vulnerabilities such as an ability to save and negative impacts on health outcomes such as increased stress and anxiety.

5. Conclusion

This report highlights the experiences of the financial crisis and austerity measures on lone parents in relation to their human rights and their capabilities. The research focused on exploring how the crisis and the measures to tackle it through social investment affected lone parents.

The research indicated through the crossing of knowledge process utilising PAHRCA methodology that lone parent human rights had been eroded and that peoples capabilities ‘what they were able to do and be’ had been negatively affected. This erosion had reinforced a shift where there had been a loss of trust within society and democracy however this was counter balanced within political activism across this group.

The research illustrated that austerity measures and a changing social protection system had created a difficult climate for lone parents to exercise their individual and collective capabilities and to have their human rights realised. Being lone parents meant that they were under increased pressure to meet the needs of them and their families, and their choices had become restricted in terms of jobs, housing and access to support.

The economic crash of 2009 had resulted in an increasingly precarious labour market with a rise in zero hour contracts and under employment across Scotland. Lone parents faced specific barriers such as access to child care. Obtaining and sustaining employment was very much dependent on accessing affordable childcare and an emphasis was placed on the need for employers to be flexible to individual circumstances. Lone parents faced particular pressure points with this. This was borne out against a climate of privatisation of active labour market support (ALMP) or the work programme and of increasingly conditionality in welfare support in particular activation benefits such as Jobseekers Allowance (JSA).

Social disinvestment and vulnerable groups in Europe in the aftermath of the financial crisis

The case of early school leavers in Geneva, Switzerland

Jean-Michel Bonvin & Francesco Laruffa

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Contents

- List of figures** **6**

- Introduction** **7**

- 1. National context** **9**

- 2. Theoretical and methodological Approach** **13**

- 3. Two selected biographies** **17**
 - 3.1 First biography 17
 - 3.2 Second biography 18

- 4. Analysis** **20**
 - 4.1 Critique of classifications at school 20
 - 4.2 Critique of 'the system' 22
 - 4.3 What is the point of education? 23
 - 4.4 Scene Active: A capability-friendly intervention based on human rights 25

- 5. Conclusion** **27**
 - 5.1 Policy implications 28

- appendix 1 Pictures of participatory process** **29**

- Bibliography** **31**

List of figures

Figure 1.1	GDP growth in Switzerland 2005-2015. Source: OECD	9
Figure 1.2	Unemployment Rate in Switzerland by age group. Source: OFS	10
Figure 1.3	Socio-demographic characteristics of school drop-outs in Geneva	12
Figure 2.1	Resources, conversion factors, capability set and achieved functionings	13
Figure 2.2	Merging of Knowledge	14

Introduction¹

Although ‘inclusive growth’ is one of the pillars of the Europe 2020 strategy, the social dimension of the strategy has lost momentum with the (Euro) crisis and the ensuing priority given to macro-economic stabilisation policies. The agreed target of alleviating poverty by 20 million poor in 10 years cannot be reached anymore due to the crisis. Instead, inequalities are growing, unemployment and poverty are reaching new records, particularly in the peripheral regions of the EU. However, in 2013, the Commission launched a major endeavour to rebalance economic and social progress: the Social Investment Package (SIP). Whereas the trends in - and causes of - increased inequality and social exclusion have already been extensively studied, the economic, social, cultural and political consequences of this growing divide are less clear. RE-InVEST aims to fill this gap by evaluating the SIP from a human rights and capability perspective. The first step in this endeavour is a diagnosis of the social damage of the crisis in terms of (the erosion of) human rights, social (dis)investment, loss of (collective) capabilities, and loss of trust.

Hence, a first key working assumption of RE-InVEST is that growing distrust and indeed resentment among the population towards institutions in general and European institutions in particular may be attributed to (a rejection of) the neoliberal policies employed by national as well as European elites in recent years. In particular, it seems quite plausible that the retrenchment of the State, in conjunction with rising inequality and income insecurity, may have undermined trust, especially among the poor and the ‘precariat’ (Standing, 2011). A second key working assumption of RE-InVEST is that the social damages of the crisis can be understood through the notions of erosion of basic social rights and of disinvestment in capabilities of individuals and groups in the EU. This implies analysing experiences of insecurity, poverty and social degradation from those perspectives. Human rights (and basic economic, social and cultural rights in particular) can be seen as the cornerstone of European values and thus an essential part of our European heritage (Hart, 2010). By fragmenting and weakening public services as well as civil society organisations, trade unions etc. solidarity is undermined and the role of collectivities in enhancing individual capabilities is constrained. In order to diagnose the effects of the crisis, RE-InVEST aims at giving vulnerable people a voice and therefore has opted for using a participatory research approach. Researchers and participants jointly analyse the impact of the crisis on capabilities and human rights. At least two individual biographies per project partner are collected as testimonies of the social damage.

Our national report focuses on the case of Switzerland and, specifically, analyses the impact of the crisis on a group of young people experiencing difficulties in their transition from school to work in Geneva (Switzerland). In Switzerland, the economic crisis has hit much less hard than in other European countries. Thus, in the Swiss case, the ‘crisis’ can be interpreted in connexion with the overall structural change towards post-industrialism, increased international competition and budgetary pressures on social expenditure. The ‘crisis’ also impacts at the individual level in the life of young people faced with difficult transitions from school to work – a period of crisis also in the etymological sense of a moment for questioning, reflecting and discerning about one’s own identity and conception of the good life. There are at least two reasons for focusing on young people. First, young people are among the most vulnerable social groups in Switzerland, with the 18-25 having the highest rate of social assistance take up in the population (except the 0-18 category). While young people in general are more vulnerable within the Swiss society, it is clear that low-qualified ones represent the most vulnerable among the young people – and we therefore chose to focus on

¹ We wish to thank Emilie Rosenstein, Benoit Beuret and Nicolas Bovio for their very valuable support in conducting the empirical research underlying this report; the team of Scene Active for allowing us to conduct this study and the group of young people for actively participating to this collective research.

them. Second, the importance of concentrating the analysis on a group of NEETs (Not in Employment, Education or Training) lies in the fact that it constitutes one of the crucial targets of social investment policies. Indeed, such policies aim at the improvement of human capital and at the maximisation of the employment rate. In contrast, these young people are not in education or training, nor in work. Thus, they are excluded precisely from the activities oriented towards human capital formation and paid work, which are the two spheres most valued by the social investment paradigm. From this perspective, understating the causes of a school-dropout, the aspirations and values of such young people is especially relevant to an informed diagnosis of the crisis.

1. National context

The economic crisis in 2008 has hit Switzerland much less strongly than other European countries. An economic recession could be observed in 2009, but quickly the economy recovered and there was an increase of the employment rate together with a decrease of the unemployment rate, although the latter remained at higher levels than at the beginning of the century. The negative impact of the crisis could be contained in Switzerland mainly thanks to two anti-crisis policies: first, the prolongation from one year to two years of so-called ‘technical unemployment’ benefits (due to their firm’s economic difficulties, workers are allowed not to work full time or not to work at all but the unemployment insurance pays wages at the level of 80% and their employment contracts are preserved: thus, these workers do not appear in the unemployment figures as they are still considered as employed), second the adoption of a fixed exchange rate ceiling with the euro. The objective of the former was to support the capacity of Swiss firms to overcome a difficult period. In this way, they were allowed about three years to surmount these difficulties, by relying on the help of public unemployment insurance during the prolonged ‘technical unemployment’ period, as well as by non-renewing fixed-term contracts (that have been increasingly used in Switzerland from the mid-nineties) and by compensating extra hours. The implementation of this measure reveals that the crisis has been mainly interpreted as a contingent or cyclical fact, limited to a specific period of time rather than as a long-term and structural crisis. The economy was hit quite hardly and therefore needed a longer time to recover, but still there was no doubt that it would recover in the end. The adoption of a fixed exchange rate ceiling was meant to preserve the competitiveness of exporting industries in the face of the falling value of the Euro. Yet, this strategy was abandoned in 2015 (without previous announcement in order to avoid financial speculations on the exchange rate) because it was too expensive for the Swiss central bank to maintain the exchange rate with the Euro fixed. The abandonment of this measure implied the fluctuation of the exchange rate and a relative appreciation of the Swiss Franc towards the Euro, which is a source of great concern for exporting industries. From this perspective, it is not clear to what extent the weakening of the Euro will lead to a structural and long-term crisis of the Swiss economy.

However, despite the fact that the economy in Switzerland has not suffered from the crisis in terms of economic growth (Figure 1.1.) and that unemployment levels for the overall population remained low, it seems that young people are a particularly vulnerable social group, facing a higher and growing unemployment rate (Figure 1.2.).

Figure 1.1 GDP growth in Switzerland 2005-2015. Source: OECD

Figure 1.2 Unemployment Rate in Switzerland by age group. Source: OFS

In particular, with regard to the focus of this report on young people experiencing difficulties in the transition from school to work, it is important to note that in recent years many different transition measures have been developed, signalling an overall declining capacity of the educational system to include young people in a ‘normal’ course. Indeed, there are an increasing number of NEETs and young people passing through transition measures (i.e. not following the ‘conventional’ tracks toward dual apprenticeship or the academic path). Yet, to understand the difficulties of the young people in the transition phase between school and work it is necessary to clarify the most important characteristics of the educational system in Switzerland as well as the situation of young people in general and of those leaving school (dropouts) in particular.

The educational system in Switzerland is characterised by a high stratification between different tracks and by early tracking. At the age of 11 pupils are channelled into different tracks according to their school grades. Then, at the age of 15, they are distributed into three main paths, namely: the Collège (which gives access to university), the Ecole de Culture Générale (ECG) and the Formation Professionnelle (vocational training, with possibility to do it full time or in a dual system which involves beyond attending school also working in an enterprise). It seems that there is a ‘stigmatisation effect’ for pupils from the lower school-types (i.e. with the lowest grades at age 11) so that even after having controlled for the effective PISA-competencies, a negative effect of the early selection processes in firms persists. Furthermore, in most cantons the obligatory school ends at age 15 – which is quite early in international comparison. This means that at this point in life young people are already considered responsible for choosing their future profession - starting a vocational training - but also for stopping attending school. After compulsory education, 65% of all young people enrol in a vocational education or training program (VET), while 25 % enrol in general education schools leading to matura, which is the prerequisite for entering the university (Stalder & Nägele 2011). Early tracking and high degree of stratification result in a high level of inequality reproduction and low equality of opportunity. Indeed, Switzerland is one of the OECD countries in which the parental occupational status has the strongest effect on the literacy-scores of youngsters. Furthermore, in Switzerland the difference between the performance of native and first generation immigrants is one of the highest in OECD countries (Fuentes, 2011). Thus, it seems that the educational system is not able to compensate unequal starting conditions and actually it even reinforces initial inequalities, especially because of early

tracking. Despite some evolutions in the sense of building bridges between existing tracks, this remains a strong specificity of the Swiss educational system when compared with other EU countries.

Furthermore, another reason for the high inequality produced in the Swiss educational system is that employers are the sole gatekeepers for accessing (dual) vocational training and apprenticeships. This means that employers establish both how many apprenticeship places are available (and in which domains) as well as the criteria for accessing them, which implies that the admission to apprenticeships follows an economic (rather than educational) logic and access to most upper secondary education is operated through a market driven mechanism. This makes the offer of apprenticeships also highly dependent on the economic fluctuations of the labour-market. Thus, in contrast to Austria and Germany where the state plays an active role either in directly providing state-funded apprenticeships (Austria) or regulating the supply of apprenticeships (Germany), in Switzerland the VET systems largely relies on the free market.

At the same time, Switzerland is one of the European countries with the lowest rate of school dropouts, which is well below the OECD mean (Petrucci & Rastoldo, 2015) and the transition from school to work appears less complicated than in other countries given the comparatively low unemployment rate among young people. Yet, precisely because having obtained a diploma has become the norm, the negative consequences of lacking a qualification in terms of higher risk of unemployment and precarious employment are especially strong in Switzerland and stronger than in the other OECD countries (Ibid.). For instance, circa 70% of all social assistance recipients between 18 and 25 are without upper secondary education.

All in all, the Swiss educational and apprenticeship system has proved to be a highly selective one, where school marks act as signals for employers when they recruit candidates for an apprenticeship. This implies that youngsters with bad marks and other negative signals are disadvantaged in many ways: the lack of apprenticeship places when the economy slows down boosts selective practices, where stigmatisation by employers vis-à-vis pupils with bad school marks or displaying other signals interpreted negatively (lack of motivation, cultural differences, etc.) tend to play a crucial part. Here, market mechanisms do not seem able to solve the problem. Furthermore, the early selection mechanisms at work in the school system tend to reinforce the selectivity of the market. Hence, more than 20% of every cohort cannot find an apprenticeship place (or follow the academic path), and therefore have to enter the transition system. This situation in turn led to the quantitative extension of so-called 'bridging offers' for young people in such situations. About 20% of all youngsters and 40% of the pupils from tracks with 'basic' demands are now enrolled in such programs. Thus, the level of state intervention in Switzerland remains low and private enterprises have an essential say in all main features of the VET system: public intervention has not moved in the direction of regulating or taming the apprenticeship market (i.e. no obligations are imposed on employers to hire apprentices; or the state is not envisaged as a kind of last resort employer for apprentices that could not find a market solution), but rather in that of developing different programs and measures aimed at improving the marketability of young people. Hence, one can say that there is a form of social investment in this area, with the central objective of raising the rate of upper secondary graduates to 95%. Indeed, enhancing access to upper secondary education is widely envisaged as a silver bullet for reducing later welfare expenditure (the objective of cost containment is central to all reforms of the Swiss welfare State). Yet, the preference for market solutions is not questioned. This is the specificity of the Swiss path to social investment. In this context, supply-side adaptability is clearly privileged at the expenses of demand-side interventions.

In the specific case of Geneva, around 1,000 young people each year leave the school without having obtained a qualification (Petrucci & Rastoldo, 2015). In this population, boys, immigrants and young people from low socio-economic backgrounds are overrepresented (Figure 1.3.).

Figure 1.3 Socio-demographic characteristics of school drop-outs in Geneva

Source Petrucci and Rastoldo (2014)

It seems that the higher probability of boys to leave the school without the diploma with regard to girls is explained by their worse performance at school, their behaviour involving more often violence and criminality, their worse attitude towards teachers and their weaker affective support within the family. However, in explaining the probability of school dropout, the kind of school frequented by the young people is much more important than socio-economic and gender factors. Hence, the lower the status of the educational track in which one young person is (e.g. a transition measure like SeMo; Atelier and Accueil and, even if to a lesser extent, ECG and vocational training), the higher the probability of his or her school dropout. The same is true for the percentage of young people that goes back to school after having left it: more than $\frac{3}{4}$ of those who left the Collège start a formation in the following year against only 20% of those who left a transition measure or Accueil. Similarly, having experienced already problems at school is a strong predictor of school dropout and of non-re-start in the following year.

However, all these factors explain only a small part of the phenomenon of school dropout. Indeed, many factors influencing this choice are difficult to measure and it is extremely problematic to collect data on issues such as the lack of interest, motivation and self-esteem, the presence of personal problems within the family and the quality of relationships at school – all factors that seem to play a crucial role in the process that leads to becoming a dropout. Thus, the population of those leaving school without the diploma is highly heterogeneous and a dropout can be the result of different reasons. In particular, it seems that rather than the single risk factors, it is their combination and cumulative effect that generates situations that can end up in a dropout. Within the group of young people that we studied, these vulnerability factors were strongly present, with a large part of the group composed by young people with a migration background, a low socio-economic origin and often a very difficult family context. From this perspective, even factors that seem strongly individual-based such as ‘lack of motivation at school’ and that thus provide the basis for legitimate inequality through the notion of meritocracy can be actually largely explained by social and structural factors.

2. Theoretical and methodological Approach²

Re-InVEST aims at investigating the philosophical, institutional and empirical foundations of an inclusive Europe of solidarity and trust. To this end it draws on capability and human rights based participatory approaches. *Human rights* form a common European basis of values and describe at the same time core elements of what constitutes well-being and a good life. Further, human rights are transformative by empowering people. Human rights are the basic rights and freedoms that belong to everyone. International law, including treaties, contains the provisions which give human rights legal effect. Ideas about human rights have evolved over many centuries and gained strong support after World War II when the United Nations adopted the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights - which set out for the first time the human rights and fundamental freedoms shared by all human beings without discrimination of any kind. Human Rights are universally agreed basic standards that aim to ensure that every person is treated with dignity and respect; they are interdependent and indivisible, meaning that rights are linked and not protecting one right may impact on another, they belong to all people without discrimination. Usually set out in law, through international or regional treaties, or national legislation, they form a legal statement of universally accepted principles of how the state should treat its citizens and other people living within its jurisdiction. Human Rights include Civil and Political Rights, such as the right to life, the right to a fair trial and the right not to be subjected to torture; and Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, such as the right to work, to join a trade union, to health, to education, and to an adequate standard of living. Specific groups are protected in specific treaties such as women, children, people with disabilities, minorities, and migrants. For vulnerable people the usage of a rights-terminology has proven to change their perspective by making them aware of their rights and the ways in which their current situation compromises these rights.

The *capability approach* as developed by Sen (1999) and Nussbaum (2011) defines a person’s well-being in terms of the beings and doings (the functionings) a person achieves and her capability to choose among different combinations of such functionings. For leading a life one values and has reason to value resources and conversion factors are preconditions (Figure 2.1).

Figure 2.1 Resources, conversion factors, capability set and achieved functionings

Resources refer to the material conditions of a person: her income, the goods and services she disposes of. Conversion factors help her converting resources into doing and being well. There are personal conversion factors such as skills and bodily features, social conversion factors such as social norms and social institutions and environmental conversion factors such as climate and geography. In the end both the achieved functionings as well as the freedom to choose a life one values matter. For assessing the capabilities of

² The general presentation of the theoretical and methodological approach was written by Ortrud Lessmann.

vulnerable people Re-InVEST aims at giving them a voice. Their participation is fostered by relying on *participatory action research* that directly results in policy recommendations. Participatory action research views participants as co-researchers who have special knowledge about their own situation. Hence they are not only asked or interviewed on their views but take part in research by engaging in, examining, interpreting, and reflecting on their own social world, shaping their sense of identity. It is a circle of knowledge generation that emerges from this method and includes the steps of knowledge production and sharing, empowerment by participation, newly generated knowledge and action that builds upon this knowledge (Figure 2.2). Crucial for this kind of knowledge generation is the ‘merging’ or ‘crossing of knowledge’ that comes from three parts: scientific knowledge as gained by researchers; knowledge which the poor and excluded have, from their first-hand experience, of the twin realities of poverty and the surrounding world which imposes it on them; and the knowledge of those who work among and with these victims in places of poverty and social exclusion (Figure 2.3).

These are the core elements of the Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach (PAHRCA) developed in Re-InVEST. PAHRCA entails seven steps (Toolkit, 44-45):

1. identify and meet partner NGO/gatekeeper;
2. preliminary ‘meet ups’ (for trust building if necessary);
3. first meeting with participants – trust building;
4. developmental: implement developmental human rights & capability approach;
5. inquiry/data gathering;
6. identifying patterns (key issues and themes of concern to the group);
7. undertake action/outcome using one or combination of approaches.

Figure 2.2 Merging of Knowledge

In Geneva (Switzerland) we decided to focus on vulnerable young people, experiencing difficulties in the transition from school to work; especially school-leavers and NEETs (not in employment, education or training) who were engaged in a project (‘Scene Active’) aiming at their insertion in society. The specific methodology we applied was inspired by the method of the sociological intervention, originally developed by Alain Touraine in the 1980s to study social movements. More recently, it has been applied in different contexts. Especially relevant for our research is the work of McDonald (1999), who undertook the sociological intervention with marginal young people from the poorest neighbourhoods in Melbourne, Australia. Rather than simply collecting data, the aim of the sociological intervention is that of identifying the struggle to become an actor, whereby an actor is ‘a participant in the production of society’ (Touraine, 2000: 906).

In this context, the role of the sociologist is that of encouraging and helping the research participants to increase their awareness and capacity for action.

In particular, the sociological intervention is based on three research phases: preparation, confrontation and finalisation. The aim of the preparation phase is threefold. First, the research participants should reflect on their personal experiences and try to develop collective claims. Second, the sociologists should help them to refine their arguments, for instance providing empirical evidence supporting their claims. Third, during this phase, the research participants are invited to think about an interlocutor with whom to share their thoughts and opinions during the next phase. The purpose of the confrontation is that ‘social actors do not construct narratives in relation to researchers, but in relation to other social actors’ (McDonald, 2002: 258). In fact, the strength of the sociological intervention derives ‘from the way it locates narrative within relationships’: in contrast to conventional models of narrative ‘focused on telling stories to sociologists’, in the sociological intervention, ‘actors become engaged in a struggle to give an account of themselves to other social actors’ (Ibid.). In this process, research participants are not simply telling their stories and personal experiences but they are struggling for their recognition and their subjectivity. They are trying to become actors. As such, the sociological intervention can be seen as a *democratic practice*, a ‘social inquiry’ in the sense of Dewey, whereby common knowledge is produced through deliberation and communicative action (Habermas, 1987; Bohman, 2004). The final session (finalisation session) constitutes an arena of feedback and selection of the collectively most relevant features. The whole process is reconsidered under an evaluative stance (where did we begin? where are we now?).

Our group consisted of up to 11 young people participating in the project ‘Scene Active’. Access to the target group was given via personal knowledge of the people responsible for the implementation of the program. The project ‘Scene Active’ is a one-year program aimed at the composition of a theatre play: through the theatre and the different ateliers (for example the young people designed their own costumes and the scenography), the aim of the project is to let them (re)discover their talents and (re)gain the self-esteem the young people need to develop a professional plan. The 11 young people participating in RE-InVEST have been selected on a voluntary basis, i.e. they declared their interest to attend our meetings. In total we had one meeting with the responsible of the project, six collective meetings with the group of young people, seven individual interviews with young people belonging to the group and two ‘confrontation sessions’. The atmosphere was friendly during all collective meetings and they trusted us since the beginning. Almost all of them actively participated. They gave us the possibility to conduct individual interviews and 6 of them actively engaged in the participation to the two confrontation sessions.

In order to stimulate reflection on the individual experience and the debate on common subjects, in the first four sessions we used some visual and interactive methods. For instance, in the first session we let the young people tell the story about their personal experience and the subjects that they would like to discuss on through a drawing and then comment their drawings (see examples in the appendix). We then prepared some posters on the most important themes they wanted to work on. In another session we used some sentences, formulated as newspapers’ titles, expressing different and conflicting viewpoints on young people’s situation in a provocative way to stimulate the discussion. We also undertook games and role-taking activities, which allowed launching a collective debate on the selected topics. In the fourth session, we brought some statistical material and newspaper articles describing and commenting the situation of school-leavers in Geneva. The aim was to strengthen the coherence of young people’s arguments and to raise their consciousness and understanding of their common situation. Apart from these collective sessions, we met the young people individually and in smaller groups in order to go more in depth and help them further strengthen their own arguments.

Concerning the second phase, that of the confrontation, the youngsters had the opportunity to confront their views (issues, questions, etc.) with the invited persons. We had two confrontation sessions and the second one was public. The invited persons were selected on the basis of an initial discussion between the youngsters and the research team. Somehow, the invited persons had to symbolise the ‘adult world’ and the ‘institutional world’, such as a politician or an administration head officer, etc. At the end, we managed to invite for the first session (which took place in June 2016) two administrative heads, responsible of two

public services linked to professional guidance (the first) and information for young people on social assistance (the second). The second confrontation was organised as a public event and took place in September 2016 in the context of the so-called ‘Week of Democracy’ at the University of Geneva. The public confrontation also constituted the ‘action’ in our participatory action research design. It consisted of a public debate between six young people representing the group, the ministry in charge of the education system in the Canton of Geneva and the responsible of the cantonal employment services, aimed at supporting labour market inclusion. The group of young people not only presented their experiences at school and their difficulties in finding a job or an apprenticeship but also formulated some concrete proposals and submitted them to the politicians and high civil servants. The proposals developed by the young people included the reform of the school system towards a more inclusive and difference-sensitive school, the establishment of a guaranteed apprenticeship for all young people in search of a training, the reduction of the importance attached to school grades both within and after the school and the improvement of the supporting services in terms of psychological support and of taking care for extra-school problems such as family or migration-related legal issues. Their interlocutors were highly impressed by the maturity of their proposals and their ability to sustain a public confrontation of ideas.

Apart from this collective research, we collected two individual biographies from two young people, one girl and one boy, who volunteered for this. We met them in separate sessions from the group meetings and on an individual basis, with the two of us being present. The crucial point about story telling is that the stories have to be respected and cannot be judged as ‘right’ or ‘wrong’. The focus is on life-stories rather than discussions and debate and the participants tell whatever they want to tell the interviewers (voluntariness). From this perspective, the biographical method respects the focus on freedom characterizing the capability approach because the interviewed person is free to choose what she tells and to select what she believes to be the most important information. Furthermore, the absence of judgement and even of analytical statements by the researchers reflects the deep respect owed to each human being inherent in the human rights framework. Therefore, the objective is not to draw a true picture of these young people and their future, but to recall what they say about themselves and their future at a specific point of time.

3. Two selected biographies

3.1 First biography

H. is 17, almost 18 years old. She was born in Geneva. H. left the school because there were more and more bad gossips about her. At first it was only at school but then she started to get insulted and receive bad comments also on social media. So H. left the school. Furthermore, since H. thinks that in Geneva everybody knows each other, she did not simply want to change school and she does not want to start it again. At the beginning H. was very good at school. Even if she had to work hard on her own because no one helped her, she made the whole primary school at the highest level. She only had some difficulties later, during the orientation cycle, where she had some problems in mathematics. She did not get any help because the teacher thought it would be a waste of time to help her. In contrast, some other teachers were more careful and they offered help. Yet such help was limited to the school domain, they were not interested in her life beyond the school and in particular they could not help her in respect to familial issues, precisely where she needed most support.

In fact, at home it was never easy for H. Her mother is Philippian and she has not cared much about her family. H. has always cooked for herself and for her brother because her mother never cooked for them. With her mother H. does not really have a mother-daughter relationship: she told H. only once 'I love you' when H. was at the hospital. H.'s mother works a lot as governess and nanny in a family of rich Americans. The smallest of their children is often at H.'s home and he is like a small brother for her. Even if her mother earns enough money they are quite poor because she plays a lot. In the past, she played a lot of money at the Casino, maybe up to CHF 1,000 per week. H. sleeps in the same room with her mother. Yet her mother is never there, she comes only for sleeping. She is always in the kitchen playing cards with her friends. H.'s mother was often violent with words to her. She often humiliated her, telling that she has no value and that she cannot do anything. In particular, H. dreams to become a singer – she also had some experiences in singing in public during the *'fête de la musique'* in Geneva. However, her mother does not support her. On the contrary, when H. failed two exams for entering two schools of arts, her mother discouraged her to try again, telling her that there was no point in trying again because she is too bad for succeeding. For H.'s mother music is simply leisure and cannot be considered work. Thus, she does not want to pay for a music school for H., which would be too expensive.

With her father, things were even worse because violence was not limited to words. Her father is Egyptian and has always lived in the USA while only sometimes coming to Geneva and staying for a certain period of time at home. Last time, he lived for one year and a half at home. During this period, he has often beaten H. up. Now it is better because H. has a social worker who takes care of her. Thanks to her, H. has a dossier in the office for the protection of the child and she lived one year outside her home, where there were problems with her father. Hence, H. left and she lived first with her boyfriend, then with a cousin and later with her best friend. In this period however she was not good at school because she always went out or watched the TV with her friend. Thus, the social worker advised her to go back home. However, in order for H. to come back home, her mother had to sign a formal promise that she would have no longer contacts with her husband, who then went back to the US. Now H.'s father has no longer the right to see H. Also, thanks to the social worker H.'s mother plays less in the casino.

Yet, this kind of support would have been much more helpful for H. if it would have started sooner. She asked for help to the social worker for the first time when she discovered that she had no papers (passport or permit of residence) while she was looking for an apprenticeship. Before that moment, she did not know that she had no papers because in Switzerland you can go to school even without papers but in

order to get a work contract - even if it is only an apprenticeship contract – you must have them. Her parents never told her that she had no papers - and indeed the whole family does not have papers. H. would have preferred to know that from her parents instead of discovering it like that. It was at this point that H. asked for help to a social worker, who then became very important for her: *'the social worker changed my life' (...)* *'she is like a mum'*. For example, she brings H. to her free-time activities and she advises her on many issues. She initiated the procedure to get official documents for H. and thanks to her now also her mother and her brother - who is studying to become a hairdresser - will have soon the papers they need to live in Switzerland legally. Furthermore, it was the social worker to propose H. to go to Scene Active. She is also helping H. to find an internship. Since H. thinks that becoming a singer is a dream, which is very difficult to attain, she is looking for an internship in a kindergarten. This is a job that H. would like to do if it does not work with the plan of becoming a singer.

3.2 Second biography

M. is 20 years old and was born in Portugal. When he was 10, he came to Switzerland where his parents looked for a better future. They were employed in a restaurant but his father was very ambitious and wanted his own restaurant. So his parents left first, leaving M. and his sister (at that time 2 years old) in Portugal for one year with their grandparents. Once they found work and an apartment, M. and his sister also came to Switzerland.

At the beginning it was very difficult for M. He could not speak French and at school his schoolmates always mocked him, insulting him with words that he could not understand. He was often left apart. Furthermore, it was difficult to follow the lessons at school and he had to visit some special courses to improve his French. Yet, M. has worked hard and could manage to go to the 'normal' school after two years in the special school for foreign students. Those schoolmates who insulted M. actually made him even stronger and motivated to work hard in order to show them his value.

So, after having done the 6th and the 7th special class, he passed to the 8th in the 'normal' school (at an intermediate level). However, when he was 14 years old he started to work every day after school in the restaurant of his father. And in the weekend he had to work until 2 in the morning. He was compelled by his father to work in the restaurant. He didn't like this job and he had no motivation to do that. He also started to have some problems at school. Now that he was in the normal school, it was difficult for example with German. He never learned German before while his schoolmates started to learn German very early. He also had some difficulties in geography, biology and history. Yet, the teachers did not look for the reasons why M. had difficulties at school. They had no understanding or patience.

Hence, M. ends up in the 9th class in 'Atelier' (specific class for pupils with difficulties at school), which always gives a bad impression to employers. He wanted to go to ECG, a school aiming at preparing students with general competences - which is not considered as providing especially high qualifications - but the teacher discouraged him to do so and insisted that M. should find an apprenticeship. In particular, this teacher was firmly convinced that M. was talented for the world of selling and persuaded him to do some internships in two textile shops and an alimentary shop. However, M. did not like this experience and he quickly became aware that selling was not for him. M. wants a job where he feels that he is doing something useful, rather than simply standing there, doing nothing or doing as if he was putting things in order. After the '9 atelier' M. started the SCAI, a transition measure which lasts one year, consisting of courses in small groups (i.e. 10 people) offering a range of practical ateliers. In terms of time, it is more or less like a school, from 8am to 6 pm each day – with a free afternoon per week.

During this year, M. and his family lost first their apartment and then the restaurant. His parents have always been late to pay the rent. They paid, but they were always late. One day, M.'s mum and his sister wanted to go home but some people were changing the lock of their door. Without saying anything, the owners were simply putting them outside. Only because of the chance that his mother was there, she could ask to enter the apartment one last time just to take the most important things with her. She had only two minutes to collect her most valuable affairs. M. never saw again his play-station, TV and other stuff. The

same day M. and his family went to the office of the social assistance to ask for help but the people working there said that the office was about to close and that they could not help them. What could they do? They were on the street. Where would they have slept that night?

M., his parents and his sister started then to live in a hotel near Geneva but beyond the border, in France, where it was less expensive. They lived all four there in a double room for one year. In this period, M. was always late at school because of the long trip from the hotel to the school and the teacher instead of asking about the reasons or trying to understand, simply let him wait outside the classroom until the break. In the same period M.'s parents also lost the restaurant. After one year living in the hotel, some former clients of the restaurant, who had become friends of his parents, hosted them in their apartment. Then M.'s father found a job in a restaurant and his mother worked as housekeeper. Finally, M. and his family found an apartment that they could illegally rent.

After the SCAI, M. started to follow the 'semestre de motivation', which is another transition measure lasting one semester in which young people get some money (paid from the unemployment insurance) and can follow a plurality of ateliers. In the same period he also discovered thanks to a test that he suffered from hyperactivity, which could explain his difficulties in remaining concentrated, especially at school in a group context. Since then he takes some medicines in order to improve his concentration capacities. M. finds it strange that his teachers had never noticed his hyperactivity before.

After the 'semestre de motivation', M. spent one year doing nothing. After a while he followed a course in English and a course of singing. He also started a music venture whereby the state pays him for developing a music project (like producing a cd). Yet, M. thinks that it is impossible to work within the music domain because in Switzerland such kinds of artists are not supported. He also made two internships in the logistics sector. Working in the logistics like the post service was a very good experience and he liked very much this job. M. especially likes this job because you feel that you are useful. You have a mission, like bringing a packet to a certain address. Unfortunately however M. did not get a place of apprenticeship after the internship. Others had better grades than M. and employers preferred to have the best candidates. Since then, M. has sent a lot of applications, but he did not get one positive answer. Thus he was demotivated and he started to hang over, go around and smoke with friends. At the beginning it seemed cool to do nothing the whole day but after a certain period of time, it was very frustrating.

But then it came Scene Active and happiness started' as he puts it. It was a social worker from the social assistance - M. gets benefits from the social assistance - who proposed M. to go to Scene Active. Thanks to Scene Active, M. has discovered that one should do something because he is motivated and not because one is compelled to do that. M. thinks that also at school, it should be different: it would be important to have teachers and other professionals who explain young people why it is important to go to school. For M., one should not go to school because he is obliged to. Rather, students should understand that it is for themselves, that school will be important later to find a job. But M. thinks that this is far from clear to many young people and should be better explained. Many of them, like M. himself, have no clear answer when they ask themselves *'Why is it important to learn biology?'* Teachers should explain this and be able to answer to such questions about the sense of going to school. Furthermore, M. argues that public services should be put in place in order to help parents in supporting and motivating their children. Thanks to Scene Active, M. has learned a lot. If he had had this interview one year ago, he says, he could not have told us all these things. In fact, he changed a lot.

After Scene Active M. will return to Portugal. He will go there with his mother and his sister (recently, M.'s parents got separated). They will go to Lisbon where the new boyfriend of M.'s mother lives. M. will start there a training program in the security field. In Portugal, you have to pay for the training but then at least you have one. And later it is possible to do a career, starting with being a security guard in a supermarket, then later in a pub. If you are good and you have completed the whole training with a little bit of chance you can become a bodyguard and escort stars from the airport to their hotel. Even if *'it is a job like all others'*, it is interesting because you have to keep yourself in good shape doing sport, you have to learn a martial art and you feel useful. M. is also convinced that in Portugal he will have more possibilities in the domain of music. Indeed doing music remains his dream - at least as a hobby.

4. Analysis

Through the many group discussions with the young people, we could observe that the rights to equal respect on the one hand and to education on the other hand have been denied for many of these young people. Many have experienced marginalisation and disrespect at school; some also made explicit reference to racism and discrimination. Almost all would have needed more support instead of being subjected to competitive pressures to ‘be better’ than their peers. This pressure contributed to marginalise them through the individualisation of their difficulties, stigmatizing them for not being good enough (also frequently leading to self-blaming behaviours). This lack of support and recognition resulted in a lack of education since many left school before having completed a qualifying training program or even compulsory education. The violation of their rights to respect and education is reflected in their lack of capabilities. In fact, they have been denied the instruments for forming their own conception of the good life and the means for achieving their human potential (indeed education and respect are central preconditions for attaining both); in certain cases, their capacity to aspire seemed to have been reduced by these circumstances. It must also be emphasised that they never presented themselves as victims of circumstances, but always ‘acknowledged’ some degree of responsibility for their situation.

Furthermore, the young people reported several times their deep-seated lack of trust towards politics, politicians and more generally towards social institutions (including school). During some of our discussions, the group was characterised by political apathy, distrust towards institutions and pessimism about the possibility of any positive change or progress in their personal as well collective situation. In general, they do not trust politics, at least not in the traditional form of elections:

‘If there are three proposals but none satisfies us, what can we do? Shall we continue to look at the increase and decrease of percentages while we continue our bullshit life? (...) It is always the same story, nothing changes.’

Thus, they have a sense of impossibility to change the status quo. This feeling of powerlessness in respect to a system, which is too difficult to reform, translates then in political apathy. Yet, despite this pessimism the group was able to lucidly criticise the ‘system’ and its values of competition and classification as well as the school, which aims at preparing for such system. On the bases of such criticisms they made some proposals and suggestions while pointing to the project Scene Active as the model to follow for a reform of the educational system. In this section, we report some core subjects emerged during the group discussions and considered especially important by the young people themselves.

4.1 Critique of classifications at school

A first critique to the school system was the use of grades for classifying people. In fact, through grading, the young people felt ‘judged and categorised’. The discussion around categorisation and prejudices was very insightful. They were particularly interested in challenging the dominant principles of classification at school, such as individual merit, measured by marks and in struggling for alternative principles of classification. The problem of classification identified by the group is that it is mostly based on some forms of prejudice: *‘how can you classify people without prejudice?’* Moreover, once that you are classified as a bad student it is very difficult to improve your position later on.

Hence, for our group ‘*classifying people is bad*’. The most important reason for this is that they feel that they have no possibility to influence the criteria of the classification, which are thus imposed on them. Indeed, they argue that some people can learn one thing better than others but these other people may be better at learning other things. An example that was often invoked was the German language: why should the mark obtained at school for German determine the value of people when they candidate for an apprenticeship?

Hence: *'The fact that we had not good marks at school does not imply that we are idiots. It means simply that studying is not for us.'* One boy in particular argued that school marks are an excessively narrow informational basis to assess the value of pupils, thereby unconsciously using Sen's terminology.

More generally, the youngsters perceive that they lack the possibility to choose what really interests them at school. Teachers give them homework to do and exams and tests to overcome but:

'Without thinking, for not even a second, if this is what you want to do or if this is what you should do, or if this is what is important to you. Then we are classified and then you are out. (...) The system establishes what is good, what is not good. Then, if you get a three or a four [i.e. a bad mark], you are worth nothing.'

'The problem is that it is at school that we discover if we are going to succeed in life or not (...). For example, it is at school that it was told me that I am bullshit. You are not going to succeed and you, you are good. You have good marks then you are going to succeed, you will have a good job.'

'But who decided what we have to learn at school?'

'Who has chosen for us?'

'Who said that this is right and this is wrong?'

This discussion on the criteria of the classification and on the fact that these criteria remain beyond of control by the people involved in the process reflects the reflection done by theorists within the capability approach. These highlight the fact that public policies are always based on a certain 'informational basis' (Sen 1999), independently of the fact that this is made explicit or kept implicit. Furthermore, the process of defining the 'right' informational basis should be democratised: the people targeted by a policy should have a say on the informational basis of the policy (see e.g. Bonvin & Orton (2009) on the case of activation policies). In particular, it seems that using school grades to assess the pupils' value represents an excessive narrow informational basis.

Indeed, the education system is oriented towards the values of competition and productivity:

'They form us in order to become the best ones; we must be better than the others: there are tests, like boxing, we must be the best. But why? Who tells this? (...) What is the sense of being better? We are all equals, I mean, none is better than the other.'

In this way, the theme of classification is directly linked to that of exclusion of the weakest members of society: *'Our system structurally lets people aside, it cannot include everyone, it cannot propose everyone a positive experience. On the contrary, precisely the goal of making some people better-off requires that others are worse-off.'*

As a lightly disabled girl explained:

'I was told: we cannot create a special school for you. I was slow – I could not even walk. I was stigmatised during all my life (...) I was told: you are behind, you cannot succeed.'

The diagnosis of the problem directly translates into the solution, which is identified with a school as inclusive as possible. As the girl who went to special schools because of her light disability put it:

'I think that schools should receive everybody in the same class: no discrimination, no foreign people, everybody. If you are handicapped and on wheelchairs or a person a little fat; there is the idiot on one corner, the shy on the other, the person who seems not to have problems but actually have 40, the one who looks to have 40 problems and actually has only 26.'

Hence, the solution to the exclusion is seen in a school open to all and the same applies to the apprenticeship system:

'Employers want to hire only the best ones. (...) Those that are not good enough - those that are told not to be good enough - what do they do? (...) Everybody should have the right to a professional training, not only those that employers have chosen to be the best ones.'

The young people contested hierarchy also beyond the school:

'In our society if you are a lawyer you are like God, if you are a butcher, well I am sorry for you. But maybe the butcher is happy with what he has.'

Thus, starting with the school and their personal experiences they expanded their critique to the whole 'system'.

4.2 Critique of 'the system'

The group of young people criticised the 'system' for being driven by three ideologies:

- the 'ideology of progress', *'which implies that the new is always better than the old'*;
- the 'ideology of individualism', *'which separates human beings in order to make out of them good consumers (...) but also to make them fragile. When we are alone, in a difficult moment we are fucked-up. The ideology of competition further increases individualism and separation, encouraging the fight one against the other'*;
- the 'ideology of growth', which *'involves the will to always grow, more and more and always better': 'The objective is to be more productive, to make a product of better quality; this is the sense of our society. These are the rules of the game in which we play. (...) It is a society based on growth. In order to grow, it is necessary to produce even more'*.

In contrast, to these dominant ideologies, the youngsters oppose an utopian vision in which society is oriented towards human wellbeing, the respect of nature and solidarity:

'Do we want a world where the central value is human wellbeing or one where the most important values are productivity and profitability?'

In particular, with regard to solidarity, as opposed to individualism and competition, they emphasised 'care' and 'taking care of others'. Furthermore, they argued for example for abolishing national states and borders and for having 'a sole flag' for the 'whole humanity'.

This strong critique of the system and the dominant values in society is inherently in tension with the strong will to be part of society. In other words, there is a tension between wanting to be included in a given social order (adherence to the dominant values) and the will/desire to transform such social order. This tension has become evident when many young people in the group criticised the grade system at school. Many of the young people in our group lamented that employers gave them no chance to show their value at work because employers assess the worth of the candidates looking at their school marks. The fact that the majority of them do not have good marks discriminates against them. The negative signal coming from low marks creates a stigma, which impedes them to find an apprenticeship. Thus, most of them want actually to find an apprenticeship – which is much less 'revolutionary' and more 'system conforming' in respect to the critique that some of them made of the 'system'. In particular, they often stated that they did not know beforehand the consequences of leaving school or having bad grades. They stated that they were bad at school but now they are ready to work. Now that they are confronted with the hard reality of not finding a place in society, they are ready to work seriously. In this way they also point to structural and external factors, such as the lack of apprenticeships – that should be guaranteed to every person rather than being the privilege of those students with good marks.

In some other cases, the tension between the critique of the system and the will of being part of it becomes an explicit contradiction. For example, while on the one hand they criticised the dominant ideas of success and richness in society, on the other hand they tended to adhere to it in the formulation of their personal ambitions, such as 'becoming an influential woman'. However, generally speaking, they were firmly convinced that 'money is not important' and that 'richness is not everything and it is possible to be rich of other things, such as experiences'.

4.3 What is the point of education?

The critique of the system opened the discussion on the purposes of school and education in general. Indeed, the task of the school seems to be that of preparing the young people for the system that they criticise. Hence, many were not motivated to learn at school because they could not see the point of learning:

'We are not passionate because we cannot see the goal.'

'I think that more should be done in order that students are interested to go to school.'

'The school should show us the beauty.'

Thus, it seems that the fundamental concern for this group is twofold: how can young people find a place in society while at the same time remaining faithful to themselves? And what role should the school play in this process? The young people are pressured to become 'employable'. However, they do not want simply to become employable, they want to remain autonomous, faithful to their values, interests and goals. For example, with regard to work, the young people stressed that they do not want simply a job in order to survive but that it must be a work, which allows a certain degree of self-realisation:

'Simply having a job in order to pay the bills is not interesting. Of course, I would like to have access to some consumption goods but I would like to do something that I like.'

Thus, the desire is *'to work because of passion and not because of need'* – even if this aspiration to self-realisation through work is often disappointed by the work experiences they already had.

Yet, this desire to live authentically and autonomously is source of problems because it creates a clash between personal aspirations and the exigencies from society:

'While looking for the sense of our life, (...) we get some proposals from the context we live in, what I call the system.'

When the sense of life is not self-determined and freely chosen, it is imposed from outside:

'If the sense does not come from ourselves, it is imposed.'

Thus:

"to 'exist' etymologically means 'being outside': how can we exist if we are told that we have to be inside there, because this is the norm, this is the way you should be. In this way they impede us to exist and this is the most depressing thing on earth, we all have a dream and a mission (...) and if we don't get the chance to discover it, it is a catastrophic loss for humanity.'

The problem is then that:

'We are like circles in a society of squares (...) and the strategy that is used is that of the 'formation' - and indeed the language is important - we are formed so that we can fit in the wished form. Our society is oriented towards the formation of human beings rather than helping a person to form herself.'

The school aims at transmitting *'the information needed in order to be included in society as it is at the moment'*, that is, at forming *'people who follow the rules of the market'*.

The strong need to become oneself confirms the thesis that puts authenticity as one of the core ethical values in contemporary society (e.g. Taylor, 1989). On the other hand, for the group the value of authenticity appears to be in tension (or even in conflict) with the equally strong will to be recognised (Honneth, 1995). However, this conflict is not only present at individual level but it also emerges in the discussion on the normative function of school and education. What should be the relevant 'informational basis' in assessing the quality of the educational system? While there was agreement that this could not be simply based on the results or performance, in terms of marks, it was more complicated to positively define what the goal of the educational system was. In particular, should the school aim at adapting people to the 'system' (especially the labour market) or making them capable to participate at the transformation of the 'system' itself while discovering the sense of one's own life? The group is - at least at theoretical level - firmly convinced that the school should not simply prepare for the labour market but rather support each student to *'find the sense of his or her life'*:

'The school should provide us with the instruments to change the world.'

And with the instruments to discover the individual talent, which if it remains undiscovered would be a waste for society as a whole. Furthermore, the school should find a balance between being open to all, without discrimination, while at the same time providing individual and personalised support. Yet, the tension remained between this openly stated vision, which remained abstract and ideal, and their more concrete and pragmatic will to find an apprenticeship, to find a job, etc.

Nevertheless, the value of authenticity and of discovering oneself remains central and influenced many discussions, thereby highlighting some important limitations of the educational system in Switzerland. In particular, the task of helping one to become oneself is especially important in the orientation phase, in which teachers and consultants play a fundamental role in helping the young people to choose their way. In the group, the youngsters had a mixture of good and bad experiences with consultants. However, many pointed to the lack of support and time during the orientation phase and to the fact that it starts too early in life:

'The moment for the choice comes too early and the options available are extremely limited and constraining.'

'I think that at age 15, it is much too early to ask someone what he or she wants to do.'

Another limitation was the lack of available subjects to choose from at school. Thus, *'the school should propose different experiences'*. In particular, more room should be given to practice music and arts and it should be given more freedom of choice:

'Giving the possibility to the people to evolve in the direction they want to evolve and not in the direction where it is said one should develop.'

Hence, the system as it is fails to provide enough time and the opportunity to try different experiences in order to develop a conception of the good life, and especially of the kind of job one has reason to value. Such remarks are crucial from a capability approach perspective, which gives so much importance to the individual choice and the freedom to choose. But as a boy said:

'In fact these are non-choices (...) we did not get sufficient information to take a real decision and still this choice shapes our future life.'

In particular, having a desire or an idea about what kind of job one wants to do is not enough, one has to try it so that the possibility to access apprenticeships and internships is especially important.

The group of young people also seems to embrace some critical positions in pedagogy such as Freire's ones (Freire, 1970), when they state for instance that teachers should be in some ways *'empty'* in order to receive what others say because *'teachers are often full of things and they pour them on us so that there is no place for interaction'*. Thus, they argue for more parity, students' participation and more communication between teachers and students:

'Teachers say we do not want to learn and we say: yeah, but can you see how you teach? So the problem is that the two sides do not listen to each other. They accuse each other instead of simply looking where the problem lies.'

In the context of the two confrontation sessions, the educational system was criticised also for not taking into account pupils' extra-school problems, such as within the family or with regard to administrative and legal issues, such as obtaining a legal working or residence permit. Special schools for disabled pupils were also strongly criticised and the young people intensely argued for an inclusive school with special and individual support whenever necessary. Many also mentioned the need of more psychological support during difficult phases. In general, they argued for a school adapting to the needs of the young people instead of adapting young people to the school. From this perspective, the central mission of the school is that of allowing all, that is each and everyone, to develop his or her own specific talents. This discussion on the purposes of education is crucial from a capability and human rights perspective. Indeed, from these two

perspectives education should be seen as an end in itself and as a means for expanding human freedom rather than a mere means or a resource to be exploited for economic goals as in the human capital approach (e.g. Robeyns, 2005; Nussbaum, 2008).

4.4 Scene Active: A capability-friendly intervention based on human rights

The bad experiences done in school are contrasted to the positive one of Scene Active:

It is necessary to develop spaces of expression and of existence. Then we can change the world (...) we are in a box and we can change the form of the box: step by step permitting the existence of new and different forms. Scene Active is an example of this. (...) A space where we can do different experiences and where we can go at our own rhythm.'

In particular, the project Scene Active is seen as a great opportunity for beginning again with new forces after a period of 'crisis':

It is like starting again.'

We start again from the beginning with new shoes.'

Hence, the project Scene Active is described as a positive rupture in the crisis. A very shy girl was like transformed and now she speaks without problems in front of the group and the researchers. When some in the group are surprised, she says:

I am very shy. But they asked me to do an exercise that nobody never asked me to do before.'

Thus, in Scene Active, they feel that they are respected, recognised and welcomed as they are – see Honneth (1995) on the importance of recognition. Furthermore, they are listened to and given a voice:

Here we are listened to.'

Here the voice is given to the youngsters and this is what is missing at school', where things are not discussed: 'it is like this and cannot be different.'

'At school they do not want to know if you have a problem with your family or a certain suffering.'

'There is no time; you have to learn this and that.'

'Here we have a different motivation than at school.'

'And they give us the time we need. If we don't understand something, they explain it even 50 thousand times, they do that.'

Also with regard to the problem of classification, Scene Active was different:

'We were classified in Scene Active in four different ateliers but we did not feel to be judged by this.'

'First of all, in this case we could choose what we wanted to do.'

'We did the classification ourselves.'

Furthermore, this classification involved no hierarchy – it was not about being better but rather about differences in personal goals, competencies and interests. The group pointed out several times the relevance and the value of human diversity. This however is for the youngsters not sufficiently valued in our society and in particular at school where the same performance criteria apply to everyone. In contrast:

'I think that we should get the possibility to work at our own rhythm rather than at the rhythm of others. We should do what we are capable to do and not more because many times we have the impression we cannot cope with the tasks that we are given. Sometimes some people need more time, well it should be possible for them to take the time they need to do what they have to.'

'The teachers at school explain something and those who understand, good, and those who do not understand, they have no time. It's impossible! Not everyone learns in the same way, each of us has its own manner. They should take the time so that everybody can understand (...). I am sure there will be much less failures because I am not stupid. It is just that I was humiliated during my whole life, I did not get enough time to do the things.'

In these discussions, the project Scene Active is always presented as a model to follow and an example for the school. The project Scene Active constitutes a space of ‘care’, of respect and recognition; a space where they are listened to and where their voice is taken into account. The same should happen at school: an emancipatory school would be one that, while truly universalistic, helps each person to develop his or her own conception of the good life, following one’s own rhythm. In contrast to a school that encourages the adaptation of preferences to the status quo, this would be a school alimending the ‘capacity to aspire’ of young people (Appadurai, 2004).

Scene Active can be seen as a capability-friendly intervention also because its focus was not simply activation towards the labour market but towards a broader inclusion in society and democracy. As the director of the project said:

‘We want to help them become democratic citizens, not simply productive workers for the economy.’

This points to one of the crucial differences between activation and capacitation: while activation policies generally aim at making individuals ‘employable’ following market (employers’) criteria, a capability approach to labour market and social policies would be centred on expanding the real freedom of individuals - conceived as democratic citizens. The Project Scene Active is arguably also based on a human rights framework because of the respect accorded to each person, independently of other criteria, such as performance at school and respect of behavioural rules (e.g. punctuality). In other words, young people felt that they were ends in themselves and beings of intrinsic worth. In the human rights framework this view is made explicit in the fact that human beings are conceived as subjects of rights (rather than, say, receivers of charity or economically self-sufficient actors).

In short, the project *Scene Active* seems to play an important role in capacitating the young people, providing them with the instruments for orientation (indispensable for developing an own notion of the good life), enhancing their self-worth (a necessary precondition for the exercise of other capabilities and rights), as well as developing some professional qualities and skills. Moreover, the project may also contribute to increase their trust towards institutions (they are all very happy about how they are treated and respected in the project) and their confidence about the possibility to develop alternatives and bringing about positive change in their individual and collective lives. Finally, the research process itself and especially the two confrontation sessions have constituted a further capacitating element, especially improving young people’s agency as social and political actors (worth mentioning: our research has been presented as part of the Scene Active program to youngsters).

5. Conclusion

While the crisis has not hit Switzerland very significantly until now (although the scrapping of the exchange rate ceiling with the euro could change the situation quite dramatically in the long run), certain categories of the population have been hit more severely, among them disadvantaged youth (e.g. Meyer, 2014). There is a wide-ranging fear that these youngsters will lead long-term careers of dependence on social assistance, thus illustrating the salience of the ‘moral hazard’ and ‘dependency trap’ in the Swiss context (it has however to be noted that the rhetoric of abuse or ‘blaming the victims’ is not as present for young people as it is for older categories of benefit recipients). In the discourses and scientific analyses, the emphasis is put on the lack of qualifications of youngsters, thus focusing the attention on this factor. It has been shown that an increasing part of young people have difficulties to pass smoothly the transition from school to work. Actually, in the Swiss context, two transitions can be identified: T1, from compulsory school to tertiary education - dual apprenticeship or academic paths - and T2, from tertiary education to the labour market. The project that we studied in this research, *Scène Active*, focuses more on T1, as it strives to bring young vulnerable people back to tertiary education, mainly via dual apprenticeship.

The reason for choosing to focus on young people experiencing difficulties in the transition from school to work is not only that they are among the most vulnerable social groups in Switzerland but also that the NEETs constitutes a crucial social group in order to investigate the normative aspirations and assumptions of the social investment paradigm. In fact, this group is outside both education and work, which are the most valued activities in the social investment approach. It thus comes as no surprise that the group of the NEETs is also one of the most important targets of social investment policies. In particular, Switzerland is an example of a supply-side vision of social investment that seems to bring about good results for most categories of population, but maybe to a lesser extent for disadvantaged youth. Therefore, a study of the strategy developed for this specific group allows drawing conclusions about what does not work and why, thereby paving the way toward proposing an alternative strategy of social investment more in line with a human rights and capability approach. Indeed, the social investment strategy seems to reduce the ‘NEETs issue’ to an economic problem. In other words, the main concern is the lack of human capital investment accumulated by this social group and the consequent difficulties in entering paid employment. There is of course a social rationale behind this concern, namely the social inclusion of these young people. Furthermore, investing in education is seen as a way of breaking the intergenerational transmission of social disadvantage. Yet, the broad social inclusion objective is often reduced to labour market integration while education is also narrowly interpreted as the process leading to the acquisition of the necessary skills that permit access to paid work.

In contrast, what is needed especially for people ‘with multiple problems and needs’ is a ‘life-first approach’ (Dean, 2003). In other words, what is necessary is a place where these young people are listened to and accepted as they are; they need first of all respect and recognition of their intrinsic value and dignity as human beings. Furthermore, they need capability-friendly policies rather than activation policies oriented towards the mere integration in the labour market or the educational system. Capability-friendly policies have broader and more open-ended objectives and aim at the inclusion in a society of democratic citizens rather than the sole inclusion of workers in the economy (Bonvin & Galster, 2010). Thus, the function of education should be the formation of the democratic citizen rather than only the ‘citizen-worker’ typical of the social investment approach (Lister, 2003). Capability-oriented policies aim at encouraging young people to develop a conception of the good life and at providing the instruments to pursue such autonomously matured personal goals. We found that the project *Scene Active* comes very close to the ideal of capability-

oriented integration programmes. However, such kind of projects cannot do everything (they are not conceived as protected islets, but as bridges toward the inclusion into society) and in particular they do not control the ‘demand-side’, i.e. they cannot guarantee that a place is available for the young people when they are outside the programme: public policies should also develop strategies to assure that there are enough jobs and apprenticeships and that school becomes a ‘space of care’, where young people experiencing difficulties are given room to express their concerns and are listened to.

The discussions conducted with the young people of Scène Active concerned many different subjects but the most important and recurrent were: unequal access to the educational system; racism and discrimination; lack of respect; lack of opportunities to prove one’s value; lack of time and support in the orientation phase where one has to choose what he/she wants to do; the value of personal identity and authenticity; aspirations and desires about the future; the value of work. The group challenged some of the dominant ideologies, such as meritocracy, competition and economic interpretations of wellbeing. Even if the young people were less prepared to develop alternatives and they were sometimes contradictory in their arguments, they were capable of bringing some crucial elements in the discussion, allowing them to criticise the grading system at school, the nonsense of ‘*being better than your neighbour*’ and the narrowness of the idea of richness interpreted purely in monetary terms.

5.1 Policy implications

To conclude, one can draw some important policy implications from this study. In particular, while over the last decades the number of transition measures has substantially grown in Switzerland, these seem not be very efficient in re-integrating young people in the educational system. For instance, M. has participated in many of these transition measures without achieving this objective. This seems to be due to the fact that such measures - precisely like the school - too often tend to ignore the *causes* of these young people’s difficulties. Thus, instead of taking in charge the root-causes, the measures often focus on acting upon the symptoms. Indeed, the two biographies reveal that extra-school issues, and especially family-related ones are frequently the sources of the troubles that these young people experience at school. To be sure, this makes it difficult for public policy to intervene in such matters belonging to the ‘private sphere’ and involving a lot of informal elements, which are hard to control and regulate. However, it is clear that if public policies want to address such multidimensional and complex questions, the solution must involve many different policy fields and areas of intervention. For instance, M.’s biography points to the lack of social housing - among other issues - whereas H.’s biography illustrates the limits of a strict migration policy - again, among many other problems.

The critique that the young people we have worked with addressed to the school system and to the transition measures, and their symmetric praise of the project Scene Active suggest that what these youngsters mostly need is a place where they can find people capable of listening to them and appreciating them as they are and who are ready to patiently leave them the time to flourish, while encouraging and supporting them in this process. After all, the theatre play was a great success, thus showing that these young people are able to complete great achievements, once the appropriate enabling circumstances are provided. The approach that characterises the project Scene Active differs from the one inherent in many transition measures - and eventually more and more in the school - in a way that echoes the critique that capability and human rights theorists move to the human capital approach to education (e.g. Robeyns, 2005). From this perspective, the deepest challenge surely involves the politics of culture: what is needed is to re-establish education as an intrinsic value aiming at making people free and at preparing democratic citizens rather than conceiving them as an economic resource to be mobilised or even exploited in the global competition. In the public confrontation session, the six young people who were present showed that they are able to be full citizens and that being an active citizen can be even enjoyable. This positive result was achieved thanks to their participation in the project Scene Active and to their involvement in the research process, which succeeded in reawakening their desire to actively contribute to the construction of the future.

appendix 1 Pictures of participatory process

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The case of households that have difficulties with making ends meet in the Netherlands

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Executive summary

After the Netherlands in 2009 landed in the first of three recessions, the government, which took office in 2012, announced that spending cuts had become inevitable. Government deficits and government debts were increasing and the country no longer complied with the requirements for a stable currency union in Europe. Therefore, the Netherlands has implemented substantial spending cuts which were, among others, achieved by reforms of the social security system. An increased emphasis was placed on incentives to find work, whilst access to care facilities was made more difficult, in part by making access requirements more stringent. Now that the recessions of 2012 and 2013 are also behind us, society is confronted with an increase in both the number of social assistance benefit recipients and those living at risk of poverty. Increasing numbers of citizens are having difficulties with making ends meet (payment arrears and debts). In Rotterdam, the city heading the municipal poverty list, 17.2% of the households must survive on a low income and six per cent had had a low income for at least four consecutive years.

This study articulates the experiences of ten of Rotterdam's residents who found themselves in a financially vulnerable position at the beginning of this study. They shared their experiences via three group sessions and two in-depth interviews. It may be assumed that these experiences, within the context of the broad spending cuts implemented in the Netherlands and the resultant increases in financial problems, are relevant not only for vulnerable households in Rotterdam, but also in the Netherlands.

As framework of analysis, this participative study draws on the concepts of capability and human right. Capabilities refer to the opportunities or freedoms of persons to opt for certain beings or doings defining a person's well-being, impacted on by available resources and skills and prevailing norms and institutions. Human rights embody the universal values for well-being and a good life.

The participants in our study who have difficulty with making ends meet as a result of their low income confirm that in the past years they moved towards a less favourable financial situation than previously. Their choice options have been reduced as they experienced even more difficulties in making ends meet: being in arrears with the rent, borrowing on the credit card or being overdrawn and reaching agreement on payment schedules when repaying benefits (e.g. housing allowances), as well as being more critical toward spending. The participants also indicated that it has become more difficult to take personal initiatives. This in turn impedes their 'participation in society'.

Furthermore, the experiences of the participants reveal that the disinvestment in public facilities (public support) would appear to be eroding the social fabric in the Dutch society resulting from the erosion of social norms and social institutions in society. The participants observed an increasing impersonalisation and harshening of the social climate that could already be felt before the crisis got more grip on the Netherlands.

In addition, participants pointed out that the recipients of social assistance benefits are often no longer or not at all treated with respect. The agencies appear to be suspicious and to assume that clients do not want to cooperate. As a result, the first hypothesis of this study - the expectation that the neoliberal policy of spending cuts (disinvestment) in social assistance schemes result in growing distrust and resentment among the population - was confirmed. The recipients of assistance blamed the failing of politics. This outcome can be considered to be endorsed by the lower share of respondents that tended to have trust in the Dutch government and politics in the autumn of 2015 than of 2008, as measured by the Eurobarometer.

The second hypothesis postulates that these developments are caused by the erosion of or disinvestment in the capabilities of persons and their human rights. The participants ascribed many of the changes to the social climate (caused by changing standards and values) to the politicians who have been implementing the

spending cuts. Politicians largely determine the options available to citizens, they pointed out. Although there are individual differences, it must be concluded that many elements of the capabilities with respect to human rights have been weakened. The participants realised that in the situation at the time this study took place some of the human rights were being compromised. The question is then whether, and if so when, the bottom will be reached and both the personal resources and skills will be exhausted.

Participants were concerned that the tide could no longer be turned, on the one hand, and, on the other, that the social climate could not be allowed to get worse. The hope was also expressed that the current system will exhaust itself and create scope for a new start for a more social and charitable society. Participants converted this hope into deeds by taking part in this study and by being willing to think about the alternatives for the follow-up project.

Preface

The Dutch country study is part of the RE-InVEST project.¹ The RE-InVEST project is financed by the European Horizon 2020 programme. Our objective for RE-InVEST is to contribute to a more social and inclusive Europe based on solidarity and trust by investing in the capabilities and human rights of the citizens of the European Union.

We are doing this in cooperation with the other members of the RE-InVEST team in 12 Member States (13 regions).² NGOs and universities have joined forces to offer a forum for the experiences of vulnerable households and other actors that are involved through the implementation of a participative methodology which uses as its main ingredients in-depth interviews and group meetings.

Thirteen studies have been carried out within the context of RE-InVEST's Work package (WP)3.³ Each study provides an insight into the situation of a specific vulnerable group of citizens after the global financial crisis caused by the US mortgage market. The crisis also affected the Netherlands from 2008 onwards. The experiences and the capabilities for influencing or continuing to influence their personal life after the crisis were discussed with ten participants in Rotterdam who had difficulty with making financial ends meet in the fourth quarter of 2015.

We would like to express our gratitude to the participants for sharing their 'biographical narrative' with us about their experiences with life in precarious financial circumstances. During the feedback round in the third group meeting, in the concluding round, the participants stated that they had, to a greater or lesser extent, experienced the meetings as learning moments. The discussions and exchanges of experiences and tips resulted in the participants developing more understanding for each other's situation.

The following and last phase of the WP3 research consists of a synthesis report that will include also quantitative analyses. This will provide conclusions on socio-economic changes in the various countries participating in the study as a result of the crisis in relation to the capabilities and human rights of the citizens of the European Union.

1 <http://www.re-invest.eu/project/objectives>

2 <http://www.re-invest.eu/about-us/the-different-partners>

3 <http://www.re-invest.eu/workpackages/wp3>

Contents

List of tables	9
List of figures	11
Introduction	13
1. Context: the crisis and its impact	15
1.1 Global financial crisis and Dutch economy	15
1.2 Government measures	16
1.3 Consequences	17
2. Theoretical and methodological approach	20
2.1 RE-InVEST approach	20
2.2 Our approach	21
3. Two selected biographies	23
3.1 Angela's life story	23
3.2 Marco's life story	25
4. Analysis of experiences in practice	29
4.1 Introduction	29
4.2 Capabilities: the impact of the crisis on resources and personal conversion factors	29
4.3 Capabilities: freedom of choice for a 'decent' life based on human rights	31
4.4 Impact on society	32
5. Conclusions	36
5.1 Introduction	36
5.2 Erosion of capabilities	36
5.3 Social assistance and health care: harsher social climate	37
Appendix 1 Capabilities based on human rights	39
Bibliography	41

List of tables

Table 1.1	Economic key data for the Netherlands, 2006-2017	15
Table 1.2	Persons on benefits, December 2007-2014/5	18

List of figures

Figure 2.1 Resources, conversion factors, capability set and achieved functionings

21

Introduction

This RE-InVEST country report is focused on the experiences of vulnerable households in Rotterdam, the Netherlands that had difficulty with making financial ends meet at the end of 2015. We examine whether the participants taking part in our study were affected by the global financial crisis of 2008 and the austerity measures implemented by the central government, municipalities and non-profit organisations to combat the effects of the crisis. We focus on the follow-up question: what social damage have the participants experienced in the post-crisis era?

Work package (WP)3⁴ focuses on two hypotheses to be examined in the study. The first is the expectation that the neoliberal policy of spending cuts (disinvestment) in social assistance schemes result in growing distrust and resentment among the population. The second hypothesis postulates that these developments are caused by the erosion of or disinvestment in what are referred to as the capabilities of persons and their human rights (also designated as social disinvestment). Capabilities refer to the opportunities or freedoms of persons to opt for specific forms of functioning - beings or doings -, whilst human rights embody the universal values for well-being and a good life (Vizard & Burchard, 2007; see also Section 2.1). When capabilities and/or human rights are compromised as a result of 'disinvestment' in public facilities and those of the social 'midfield' in society, this will be detrimental to the 'good' life of the person in question, as a result of a reduced personal well-being (increased uncertainty and poverty). It will also erode the social fabric of society.

Two approaches were adopted to the testing of these hypotheses in practice. The first approach is based on a literature study of the impact of the global financial crisis on the Dutch economy, the response of the Dutch Government and the consequences for Dutch society. The results are reported in Chapter 1. Chapters 2, 3 and 4 report on the second approach to this study. Chapter 2 explains the method adopted for the 'participatory study' on the basis of capabilities and human rights. This participatory study assigns an important role to the experiences of the participants taking part in the study. The participants shared their biographical experiences with us in two ways, in in-depth interviews and in group sessions. Chapter 3 focuses on the two illustrative biographical narratives. Chapter 4 summarises for a number of topics the experiences that participants shared in the group meetings and in the biographical narratives. Chapter 5 reviews the conclusions on the basis of the two key hypotheses.

4 <http://www.re-invest.eu/workpackages/wp3>

1. Context: the crisis and its impact

1.1 Global financial crisis and Dutch economy

This chapter reports the findings from our literature study of the impact of the global financial crisis which started on the US mortgage market and which also impacted the Dutch economy. The objective is to outline a number of consequences for the Netherlands that are of importance to this study. The Netherlands entered a recession caused by the global financial crisis that began in 2008 (Haffner & van Dam, 2011; Van Ewijk & Teulings; 2009). In 2009, the Dutch economy contracted by almost four percentage points (Table 1.1). The national debt increased from 42.4% to 56.5% of GDP between 2007 and 2009, whilst the government surplus (EMU balance) of 0.2% changed into a government deficit of 5.4% of GDP in the same period. Household consumption and the level of investments both fell in 2009. Unemployment increased from 4.2% to 4.4% between 2007 and 2009. This slight (instead of a strong increase) was in part due to the various government measures designed to soften the effects on the labour market (part-time unemployment).⁵

Table 1.1 Economic key data for the Netherlands, 2006-2017

	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
Movements per annum, in %												
Gross domestic product	3.5	3.7	1.7	-3.8	1.4	1.7	-1.1	-0.5	1.0	1.9	1.8	2.0
(GDP, economic growth)	-0.3	1.9	0.9	-2.1	0.0	0.2	-1.2	-1.4	0.0	1.6	1.6	2.0
Household consumption	9.3	3.1	3.3	4.7	1.0	-0.2	-1.3	0.1	0.3	-0.3	2.0	0.2
Government spending	6.8	7.2	2.6	-10.8	-1.6	3.5	-6.2	-5.3	2.7	7.2	6.0	4.2
Investments (including stock)	5.0	4.2	3.7	4.4	5.0	5.0	5.8	7.3	7.4	6.9	6.5	6.3
Level in % GDP												
EMU balance	0.2	0.2	0.2	-5.4	-5.0	-4.3	-3.9	-2.4	-2.4	-1.9	-1.7	-1.2
EMU debt (at year-end)	44.5	42.4	54.5	56.5	59.0	61.7	66.4	67.9	68.2	66.3	65.4	64.1

* Estimate.

Source CPB, CEP (2016), Appendix 2

Interventions were also made in sectors including the financial market (takeovers of and credit guarantees to banks) and the housing market (*Tijdelijke Stimuleringsregeling Woningbouwprojecten*; [temporary housing projects incentive scheme] Holt et al., 2009; Dol et al., 2010; Haffner, 2014; Haffner et al. 2014; Oxley et al., 2015). Spending cuts and an increased burden of taxation and social security contributions were introduced gradually to avoid impeding the return to economic growth. Government deficit was gradually reduced from the peak in 2009 to 2.4% in 2013. As a result, government debt increased further to 61.7% in 2011 (Van Ewijk & Teulings 2009), as shown in Table 1.1.

This support was ultimately unable to avoid the Netherlands entering into two further recessions after 2009.⁶ Growth was once again negative in 2012 and 2013, as were household consumption and the level of investments. Unemployment reached its peak of 7.4% of the labour force in 2014, as did the EMU deficit

⁵ <http://www.hr-kiosk.nl/hoofdstuk/arbeidsinactiviteit/deeltijd-ww> (1 April 2016).

⁶ http://www.ioop.nl/economie/detail/artikel/19560_nederland_weer_in_recessie/ (1 April 2016).

at more than 68% of GDP. During this period the EMU balance in 2014 was kept at the same level of the deficit of 2.4% in 2013, and thereafter gradually reduced by the implementation of spending cuts. The following section discusses solely measures of relevance to this study.

The economic indicators listed in Table 1.1 exhibited a continual gradual recovery from 2014 on. According to the Netherlands Bureau for Economic Policy Analysis (CPB), the government deficit will fall to below 2% from 2016 on (Hers & Van der Horst, 2016). In 2016, it is also forecast that the effect of the further spending cuts the Rutte-Asscher coalition government of the Liberal Party (VVD) and Labour Party (PvdA) agreed in the coalition agreement of 2012 will be neutralised by what is referred to as the *5 miljard-pakket* (five billion euro package) that will reduce the tax burden on labour from 2016 on.⁷

1.2 Government measures

When the Rutte-Asscher coalition government took office, in 2012, the government statement made by Prime Minister Rutte (Liberal Party, VVD) on 13 November announced a €16 billion package of spending cuts and increases in the burden of taxation and social security contributions designed to achieve a budget equilibrium and a stable currency union in Europe. This €16 billion was in addition to the measures referred to by earlier governments that totalled €30 billion. In 2017, the planned savings will increase to €46 billion.⁸ The government announced measures in a wide range of policy fields (care, education and work) and will report to the public via channels including the *Wat heeft het kabinet bereikt* (what has the government achieved?) website.⁹ This website serves as the leitmotif in this report for the specification of the measures that the participants in our study raised during the discussions. These related, in particular, to changes and spending cuts in care and social assistance, tasks largely and newly assigned to the municipalities together with the associated responsibilities: ‘customised assistance’.

The government also drew attention to a new phenomenon that was referred to as ‘the participation society’ in the form of ‘modern horizontal networks’ in which ICT applications play an important role (Rutte, 2014: 1). This society requires scope for ‘more’ participation created by incentives for personal initiatives so that the government can also implement spending cuts. Rutte (2014: 3) guaranteed that the welfare state will be maintained for those who cannot take part in the participation society.

The coalition government’s government statement, of 2012, announced that everyone will be required to make an extra effort. More specifically, this means that municipalities may request a quid pro quo from persons on benefits: they are, for example, under the obligation to seek work and to take part in any work rehabilitation programmes that are offered, where relevant (Blommesteijn, 2015). Pursuant to a new requirement, persons requesting social assistance on or after 1 January 2016 must have at least a specific command of Dutch. This obligation was imposed via the Participation Act on 1 July 2016.¹⁰ Following the implementation of the Participation Act, on 1 January 2015,¹¹ municipalities are entitled to request persons a quid pro quo of some other form, for example voluntary work that, where relevant, is assigned to them.¹² The Participation Act replaces legislation including the Work and Social Assistance Act (WWB),¹³ as a result of

7 <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/regering/inhoud/wat-is-het-kabinet-van-plan/overheidsfinancie-banen-en-groei> (1 April 2016).

8 <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/regering/inhoud/wat-heeft-het-kabinet-bereikt/regeringsverklaring> (1 April 2016).

9 <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/regering/inhoud/wat-heeft-het-kabinet-bereikt/tijdlijn> (1 April 2016).

10 <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/onderwerpen/bijstand/vraag-en-antwoord/wat-is-de-taaleis-in-de-bijstand> (1 April 2016).

11 <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/onderwerpen/participatiewet> (1 March 2016): as from 1 January 2015, everyone who is able to work but also requires support is governed by the Participation Act. The Act is intended to ensure that as many persons with or without an occupational disability are at work. In addition to the Work and Social Assistance Act (WWB), the Participation Act also replaces the Sheltered Employment Act (WSW) and part of the Invalidity Insurance (Young Disabled Persons) Act (Wajong).

12 <https://perspectief.uwv.nl/forum/s/trouw-iets-terugdoen-prima-maar-papier-prikken> (1 April 2016).

13 <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/documenten/brochures/2011/12/23/de-nieuwe-wet-werk-en-bijstand> (1 April 2016). The Participation Act also places businesses and the government under the obligation to employ persons with an occupational disability (guarantee jobs). The municipalities are also expected to play a greater role (<https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/documenten/publicaties/2015/03/06/kennisdocument>; 1 April 2016).

which what was referred to as the ‘long-term extra benefit’ for persons on benefits for a ‘long’ time was abolished.

In its government statement, the Government also announced interventions that are intended both to improve the quality and to achieve cost savings. Care must be brought closer to the public, as a result of which the municipalities also play a larger role in ensuring that persons can continue to live in their own home for as long as is possible.¹⁴ The requisite arrangements were made at the beginning of 2015, in the Social Support Act (WMO).¹⁵ This ‘customised care’ must, for example, in part compensate for the abolition of a number of benefits (general chronically ill benefit and compensation for excess) within the context of the Chronically Ill and Disabled Persons (Allowances) Act (WTCG) as from 1 January 2014.¹⁶ Municipalities can opt to provide benefits of this nature via special social assistance benefits, but can also opt not to do so: the Municipality of Rotterdam, for example, has opted to abolish the personal contribution deduction.¹⁷ The municipalities have also been assigned the responsibility for the care of young persons as laid down in the Youth Act and for care and nursing at home as laid down in the Health Insurance Act (Zvw). The Long Term Care Act (Wlz) provides for long term care in institutions. The care reforms have, consequently, resulted in a distinction between home care and care in institutions (Blommesteijn, 2015).

One of the important austerity measures of the Rutte-Asscher coalition government was focused on the rented housing market and related to the introduction of a new tax on the ownership of rented housing: the *verhuurderheffing*¹⁸ (landlord levy) (Ministerie van Financiën, 2012). This tax is calculated annually as a percentage of the value for the purposes of the Valuation of Immovable Property Act (WOZ), the taxable value that is adjusted annually by the municipality and is based on estimates of the market value of the unoccupied home. The levy applies to homes with a regulated rent (monthly rent of a maximum of €710.68 at 1 July 2015; Ministerie van Binnenlandse Zaken en Koninkrijksrelaties, 2015). On 1 January 2012, 88% of the rented housing stock had a regulated rent (Haffner & Boumeester, 2015). The rate is applicable from the 11th home and increases in increments from 2013, when the tax was introduced, to 2017. The coalition government stated that this resulted in landlords with at least 11 cheaper rented homes making a contribution to the reduction of the government deficit.

This tax results in rent increases, as the landlords need funds to pay the tax. An income-dependent rent increase was introduced in 2013, whereby an extra rent increase is imposed on households with an income above the ‘target group limit’.¹⁹ The underlying objective is to give an incentive to households with a ‘higher’ income to move out of social rented dwellings so that they remain available for households in the policy target group (Ministerie van Binnenlandse Zaken en Koninkrijksrelaties, 2013: 2).

1.3 Consequences

The Netherlands’ extensive spending cuts resulted in the reform of the social security system. An increased emphasis was placed on incentives to find work, whilst access to care facilities was made more difficult, in part by increasing the stringency of the associated conditions (Blommesteijn, 2015). Groups including social assistance benefit recipients are now under the obligation to provide a quid pro quo (a command of Dutch,

14 <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/onderwerpen/zorg-in-zorginstelling/vraag-en-antwoord/organisatie-zorg-en-ondersteuning-per-2015> (1 April 2016).

15 <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/regering/nieuws/2014/07/08/van-rijn-de-nieuwe-wmo-2015-is-een-feit> (1 April 2016).

16 <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/onderwerpen/zorg-en-ondersteuning-thuis/vraag-en-antwoord/veranderingen-tegemoetkomingen-chronisch-zieken-en-gehandicapten> (1 April 2016).

17 <http://www.rotterdam.nl/Clusters/Maatschappelijke%20ontwikkeling/Document%202013/Activering%20en%20Welzijn/Ondersteuning,%20hulp%20en%20werk%20dichtbij/Wmo%20presentatie%20clientbijeenkomst%205%20nov%202014.pdf> (1 April 2016).

18 <https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/onderwerpen/huurwoning/inhoud/verhuurderheffing> (11 November 2015; Centraal Planbureau, 2012a, b; Priemus, 2014).

19 https://www.rijksoverheid.nl/onderwerpen/huurwoning/vraag-en-antwoord/maximale-huurverhoging?utm_campaign=sea-t-bouwen-wonen-en-leefomgeving-a-huurwoning-huurverhoging&utm_term=%2Bhuurverhoging&qclid=Cj0KEQIAzai0BRCs2Yydo8yptuBEiQAN3_IFW24-3QhkI7BZKTYrvv-elbwunbWT7jsVOI8s101ecaApVp8P8HAQ (1 April 2016).

the obligation to carry out voluntary work). In practice, the numbers of benefits recipients have increased (Table 1.2).

Table 1.2 Persons on benefits, December 2007-2014/5

December	Unemployment	Social assistance/ related to social assistance	Of which aged 27 to 45	Of which aged 45 to 66	Occupational disability	State old age pension**
2007	191,530	384,630	133,350	160,010	810,940	
2008	173,870	373,720	122,470	157,140	799,450	
2009	272,140	408,150	133,790	164,530	801,980	
2010	268,520	440,070	145,430	173,460	797,020	
2011	275,640	453,120	151,000	179,680	792,040	
2012	351,230	465,090	159,250	186,160	785,580	
2013	441,420	501,240	176,380	198,410	787,280	
2014*	434,090	525,960	184,870	210,440	790,560	3,301,070
2015*			187,000	221,000		3,289,040

* Provisional figures, except for age 27 through 65 in 2014.

** The state old age pension is included in these statistics since 2014: the most recent figure is from January 2015.

Source: CBS, StatLine

The global financial crisis has also resulted in increased poverty. After the increases in 2011 and 2012, the Poverty Survey (*Armoedesignalement*) 2014 revealed that poverty once again increased in 2014. The Poverty Survey determines poverty on the basis of a number of definitions and uses the Budget Survey (Sociaal en Cultureel Planbureau (SCP)/Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek (CBS), 2014).

The figures for the CBS' low income threshold²⁰ indicate that the number of households with an income below this low income threshold increased from 7.4% in 2010 (the lowest level since 2000) to 10.3% in 2013 (provisional figures). In 2013, this related to 726,000 households. In 2013, at least 192,000 households had had to survive on a low income for at least four consecutive years, an increase from 2.4% in 2010 to 3.0% (provisional figures) in 2013.

The CBS analysis in the Poverty Survey 2014 reveals that the Municipality of Rotterdam heads the municipal poverty list: 17.2% of the households had to survive on a low income and six per cent had had to survive on a low income for at least four consecutive years.

The SCP adopts a budget approach in the Poverty Survey 2014, in which a basic needs criterion is adopted.²¹ Pursuant to this definition, 3.7% of the population had an inadequate budget in 2007, prior to the crisis. In 2013, this had increased to 5.4% of the population. According to the 'modest but adequate budget' criterion²² poverty increased from 5.4% of the population in 2007 to 7.9% in 2013. The latter percentage is equivalent to almost 1.3 million persons who do not have a 'modest but adequate budget' available for their expenditure. The SCP refers to 'long term poverty' in cases in which persons live below the low income threshold for at least three consecutive years. In 2013, 1.6% of the population lived below the basic needs criterion (+0.5 since 2010) and 2.9% below the modest but adequate budget (+0.9 since 2010). This relates to 230,000 and 410,000 persons respectively.

It should be noted that 'poverty' established on the basis of one of these measures or budgets does not automatically imply that it will be impossible to make ends meet. However, the probability must be regarded

20 It is used to determine a fixed level of purchasing power over the course of time that is derived from the social assistance benefit amount for a single person in 1979.

21 This criterion encompasses the minimal expenditures on food, clothing and housing and a number of other unavoidable costs for a single person.

22 It also takes into account a number of expenses for social participation.

as greater, as is demonstrated by the following analyses carried out by the SCP using the EU-SILC database (also presented in the Poverty Survey 2014). The SCP establishes that when poverty is measured in accordance with the modest but adequate budget criterion between 11%-13% of the persons in this category live in households with payment arrears. 'Payment arrears' are defined as the failure to make at least one payment (for rent/mortgage, gas, water or electricity) in time in 2007, 2008 and 2009 respectively. In 2013, this percentage increased to 18, whilst the number of persons with sufficient disposable income pursuant to the modest but adequate budget living in households with payment arrears remained relatively stable in the years from 2007 to 2013 (an increase from 3% to 4%). In all years, the percentage of households with payment arrears is greatest for arrears in rent or mortgage payments in comparison to the payment of gas, water or electricity bills. In 2009, this related to 7% of these persons and 13% in 2013.

The SCP and CBS both identify an increase in the proportion of 'poor' persons in all risk groups, such as single parents, persons of non-Western origins and single persons below 65. Both organisations also state that social assistance benefit recipients belong to the risk groups. Zwinkels en Guiaux (2015) demonstrate, using figures from the CBS and Employee Insurance Agency (UWV), that at least 20% of social assistance benefit recipients need to incur debts to make ends meet and that a maximum of 22% are in payment arrears. These high proportions are not surprising when income falls on receiving social assistance benefits. The shares of other groups of social assistance benefit recipients, for example persons with a partial or full occupational disability or persons who are unemployed, who incur debts or are in payment arrears are slightly lower than those for social assistance benefits recipients, between 4 and 15%, whilst amongst persons who are not on benefits the risk of encountering financial problems lies between 2 and 6%.

The National Institute for Family Finance Information (Nibud) also concludes that the many years of an ailing economy have resulted in an increase in financial problems. This is based on its survey of 1,444 Dutch citizens between 18 and 70, in which three-quarters of consumers receiving benefits (social assistance/occupational disability/unemployment) state that they have difficulty making ends meet (Van der Schors et al., 2015). Although this percentage fluctuates, it was higher in 2015 than in 2005, when 61% of the respondents stated that they had difficulties in making ends meet on their income. 35% of old age pensioners have difficulties in making ends meet on their income, whilst 36% of employees and self-employed persons without personnel have these difficulties.

Zwinkels and Guiaux (2015) report, on the basis of Panteia (2013), that the number of households with problematic debts is estimated to have increased from less than one million (between 788,000 and 999,000) in 2009 to more than one million (between 1.1 and 1.3 million) in 2014. Zwinkels and Guiaux also report that according to the records of the association of debt relief agencies (NVVK), the number of requests for debt relief assistance increased to 92,000 in 2014, whilst the average debt increased by just under €2,000 to €38,500.

The estimate of about one million households with problematic debts of about seven million Dutch households in total can be regarded to coincide with the other side of the coin: the about 86% of Dutch respondents that perceived the financial situation of their household as good according to the November 2015 Eurobarometer (TNS opinion & social, 2016). Eleven percent of respondents expected the financial situation to turn worse in the 12 months following the survey.

These perceptions and expectations about the financial position go hand in hand with the decrease of trust that respondents of the Eurobarometer were measured to have in certain Dutch institutions between the autumn of 2008 and the autumn of 2015, when this research project started in the Netherlands: 58% of respondents tended to trust regional or local public authorities in the fall of 2015, which is down from 64% of respondents at the end of 2008, when the crisis impacted on the Dutch economy (TNS opinion & social, 2008; 2016). Furthermore, 52% tended to trust the national government in the fall of 2015, while it amounted to 66% of respondents at the end of 2008. The tendency of 52% of the respondents to trust the national parliament in the fall of 2015 had declined from 64% of respondents in the fall of 2008. Last but not least, the tendency to have trust in political parties went down from 51% of the respondents in the fall of 2008 to 33% in the fall of 2015.

2. Theoretical and methodological approach

2.1 RE-InVEST approach²³

Re-InVEST aims at investigating the philosophical, institutional and empirical foundations of an inclusive Europe of solidarity and trust. To this end, the research draws on capability and human rights based participatory approaches.

Human rights form a common European basis of values and describe at the same time core elements of what constitutes well-being and a good life. Further, human rights are transformative in empowering people. International law, including treaties, contain the provisions which give human rights legal effect. Ideas about human rights have evolved over many centuries and gained strong support after World War II when the United Nations adopted the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights - which set out the human rights and fundamental freedoms shared by all human beings without discrimination of any kind. Human Rights are universally agreed basic standards that aim to ensure that every person is treated with dignity and respect; they are interdependent and indivisible, meaning that rights are linked and not protecting one right may impact on another, they belong to all people without discrimination. Insofar as they are set out in law, through international or regional treaties, or national legislation, they also form a legal basis of universally accepted principles of how the state should treat its citizens and other people living within its jurisdiction. Human Rights include Civil and Political Rights, such as the right to life, the right to a fair trial and the right not to be subjected to torture; and Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, such as the right to work, to health, and to an adequate standard of living. Specific groups are protected in specific treaties such as women, children, people with disabilities, minorities, and migrants. For vulnerable people, the usage of a rights-terminology has proven to change their perspective by making them aware of their rights and the ways in which their current situation compromises these rights.

The *capability approach* as developed by Sen (1999) and Nussbaum (2011) defines a person's well-being in terms of the functionings in the form of beings and doings a person can achieve and her capability to choose among different combinations of such functionings. The (set of) capabilities (which is/are here used interchangeably with the term capability set) enables a person to lead a life she values - and has reason to value. The limits of her capabilities are determined by her resources and by given 'conversion factors' (Figure 2.1). Resources refer to the material conditions of a person: her income, the goods and services she disposes of. Conversion factors help her converting resources into doing and being well. There are personal conversion factors such as skills and bodily features, social conversion factors such as social norms and social institutions and environmental conversion factors such as climate and geography. In the end, the achieved functionings as well as the freedom to choose a life one values matter.

In assessing the capabilities of vulnerable people, Re-InVEST aims at giving them a voice in the form of group meetings. Their participation is fostered by relying on participatory action research. The core elements of the *Participatory Action, Human Rights and Capability Approach* (PAHRCA) developed in Re-InVEST entails seven steps: (1) Identify and meet partner; (2) Preliminary 'meet ups'; (3) First meeting with participants - trust building; (4) Developmental: how to implement the human rights and capability approach; (5) Inquiry/

²³ We would like to thank Ortrud Lessmann for writing this section, and Mary Murphy for her addition on human rights, and Katrien Steenssens and Idesbald Nicais for their revisions (own adaptation).

data gathering; (6) Identifying patterns: key issues and themes of concern to the group; and (7) Undertake action/outcome using one or combination of approaches.

Figure 2.1 Resources, conversion factors, capability set and achieved functionings

2.2 Our approach

Based on the project approach described in the previous section, for the Dutch case study we chose to organise group sessions and in-depth interviews. For the group sessions we implemented a so-called **focus group method**. We based it on the definitions of *'group depth interview'* en *'focus group'* that Stewart and Shamdasani (1990: 10) propose: a group of interacting participants with a common interest (to make ends meet) which share in-depth personal information facilitated by a 'moderator'. The term focus signals the limited number of topics that are shared, as in our case the impacts of the crisis (via capabilities and human rights) on the precarious financial situation of the participants. The group dynamics delivers added value.

To recruit **participants** with experiential knowledge, we were able, via a social housing landlord in Rotterdam, to come into contact (by e-mail) with tenants who were or had been active in resident participation. A poverty network helped us to find participants as well. In total ten persons were willing to participate. Most participants had indicated that they had difficulty with making ends meet. Some participants are also active in the poverty network and contributed also their professional knowledge.

Of the ten participants, six were female. The ages range from 33 to 45 years of age, second half in the 50s (three participants) and 65 years and over. The different household situations include: again single with (adult) children (three participants), married (two participants) or living together. The males also are from different age groups; 29, 60 en 61 years en 65+. The latter participant is married, while the other three are single.

We prepared for the **focus groups** by conducting **interviews to get acquainted** with most of the ten participants. Three meetings with the focus group were then held in the period from December 2015 to March 2016.

The **first meeting** of the focus group began with a discussion of the objective of the project and the focus group meetings, as well as the code of conduct. All participants concurred with the following terms of reference: all information remains confidential, in the sense that information presented in the report is anonymised and that all information remains within the group. In a further agreement we agreed to offer each other the scope to have our say without interruption and to show respect for each other, each other's opinions, situations and the choices we have made. The participants in the meetings explained how they had ended up in their financially precarious situation and the problems that they had encountered. The meetings also discussed the changes the participants observed in their financial situation that were caused by the crisis.

During the **second and third meeting** of the focus group the participants were divided into two groups to discuss the criteria to be met that we have defined for a decent (good) life. The two groups not necessarily identified the 'same' relevant experiences. We made grateful use of the capability set of the Austrian RE-InVEST team that was developed by Vizard and Burchardt (2007) on the basis of human rights and was modified for RE-InVEST (RE-InVEST Draft Methodological Toolkit: 14). Our interpretation and processing of the list are shown in Appendix 1.

As illustrations of life stories about precarious income situations, two participants shared their biographical narrative with us in an **in-depth interview**. One of these participants has recently begun to receive benefits pursuant to the Sickness Benefits Act and has a part-time job (Section 3.1). This participant has also built up a debt to the tax authorities caused by this person ‘unjustifiably’ receiving rent allowances. This is a recognised problem (see MOgroep/LORS, 2014). The second in-depth interview explores the biographical narrative of a young person with a high level of education who is on benefits (Section 3.2).

Both biographical narratives describe the experiences of the participants and their interpretations of these experiences on the basis of past events, their life experience and the influence of their social contacts (their network) (RE-InVEST Draft Methodological Toolkit: 53). We used the ‘snake method’ to assist the participants with their memories, with an emphasis placed on the last ten years.

The implemented research methods (three meetings of the focus group plus two in-depth interviews) allowed the participants to put on the table the (most) important issues that influenced their choices in making ends meet. All participants read the (longer) Dutch report to verify that it correctly describes their input in this research project.

The ‘action’ part of the study’s approach PAHRCA (step 7) continued before and after our meeting for the participants who were also active in the poverty network (see before). As the group exchanged experiences about how to make ends meet during the group meeting, the group also intends to discuss their situation and experiences with professionals at the meeting that is being organised in the fall of 2016. Last but not least, the participants showed interest to participate in the follow-up study.

3. Two selected biographies

3.1 Angela's life story

Angela finds herself at a critical point in her life. But she has been through several such moments before; she describes these times, when she had to face everything entirely alone.

I've always thought about my life in that way. There have been times when I had to just pack my suitcase and leave. That's the recurring theme; (laughing) that's the story of my life. I can always count on myself! So actually my suitcase is the story of my life: nothing more, just me and my own resourcefulness ...'

Three years ago, she moved away from the south of the Netherlands to an urban area in one of the large cities in the west of the country. She had been living in the south for a long time. Angela is a part-time care assistant (20 hours per week) and she still has a job in the south of the country. But after she moved, she had to travel a long way to work. She is currently on sickness benefits; she is recovering from two car accidents. This situation is forcing her to reappraise her life. She feels that she cannot continue in her current line of work. She cannot stand the pressure in the healthcare sector, which the patients always end up bearing the brunt of. She receives no reimbursement for her travel expenses. Her supervisor just advised her to look for a place to live that was closer to work. Angela also says that she does not have as much energy as she used to. In short, she is feeling the pressure - both from the outside and from herself - to change jobs. But Angela realises that it will be very difficult to find a permanent position. She can only ever get temporary work or, at best, a temporary contract.

But Angela is keeping her spirits up. She is back on 'the right course' now. She still has a lot to give and share with the world. She has not lost her fighting spirit, although she could use a bit more strength. She is exploring the possibility of working in the funeral care sector.

'That's a new door that is opening for me. I need to find some solutions!'

It took Angela a long time to decide to work less. But she can no longer cope with 20 hours a week. And all in all, it will not make much difference financially. She is penalised at the moment for working 20 hours. It means that she is ineligible for allowances and subsidies because she earns slightly too much. She owes a lot of money to the taxman (€7,000) because she has to repay healthcare benefit and housing benefit payments that she received over a period of two years. The only reason for her to carry on working 20 hours is because she enjoys the social contact and the role that she has in society. She is afraid that without her work, her life might start to go downhill.

Next to all these new uncertainties in her life, she is also alone again. A few years before she moved to the west, she moved in with her partner. But she left him again. He did not take her seriously - they were unable to build a balanced relationship together. Two previous relationships had also ended in break-ups.

Replying to the question of what her ideal life would be, she gives a modest reply. She wants a comfortable life. Light is very important to her. Luckily she lives in a house with plenty of light. She wants a normal life. She does not need a lot of expensive things. She wants to be able to do the shopping. Apart from that, she is satisfied with the opportunities she has and she can accept her situation. But she does want to be able to make choices in her life. She wants to be able to decide for herself and spend her own money without interference.

This need for choice in her life is down to two things: she feels the stranglehold of society from all sides, and the government that is depriving her of any control over her own life. What she wanted has always taken second place in her life, and she has already had to give up a lot - she certainly has not enjoyed that.

Let's start with that stranglehold of society and her loss of control over her own life. Even in the late 1990s, Angela was already feeling the effect of budget cuts and the associated cuts in allowances for people in a weaker position in society.

Angela just cannot understand the never-ending wave of changes to welfare benefits and allowances coming down from the government. These changes are mainly due to relentless budget cuts ... and every time her position in society gets weaker. She has extra costs to cover every time, and she finds that she can no longer make ends meet. She talks about a series of bad experiences as a result of the cuts:

- She is still outraged that she is no longer allowed to accompany her deaf son for the taxi ride to school so that she can go with him into the classroom and make sure that he gets there safely. All she can do now is entrust her child to the taxi drivers every day - and she does not trust them at all. She feels powerless.

'And what do you think they're going to say to you if you try to complain at such a big company (the taxi company): what's your problem? - it's not my problem - they select the drivers. But it's my child that has to take their taxis. So I'm dependent on them. I don't have any freedom of choice. I'm not allowed any choice. It's all done for me. And I just have to trust ...! Well my confidence has been broken 100,000 times.'

- Currently she owes a lot of money. The tax authority paid her housing and health care allowances for two years on the basis of her expected income. But she earned more than they had expected and now she has to repay €7,000 retrospectively. She thinks that the tax authority has not handled it at all well. Because of processing delays at the tax authority, the amount that she has to repay is even higher.

- Her youngest son is now an adult, but he is not only deaf but also has a muscular disease that limits what he can do considerably and means that he probably does not have long to live. Due to his disabilities, he now lives in a family care home. It is home for him now and he likes it there. Because of all the staffing cuts, however, they are not always able to take care of all the residents, so for one weekend a month they are taken home by their parents or someone else. If that is not possible for some reason, Angela's son would be transferred to a ward for severely handicapped people, which would seriously limit his freedom, and he would have to adapt and get used to his new surroundings all over again. So Angela picks up her son for one weekend a month and brings him home. Her home is not adapted for his disability. They receive no extra benefits. But she manages it. Her son sometimes says that it is a bit boring in her apartment.

- Angela had to buy a new pair of glasses. She assumed that their cost would be reimbursed when she bought them. But her entitlement had expired. Now she has glasses that cost much more than she needed to pay. Her insurance policy did not cover glasses.

'I'm assuming that things aren't going to change. It's the only thing I can do. I'm living in the here and now, and this is the situation I have to deal with. But I also have to look ahead to what is going to happen in two years' time. That's not easy for me - I'm no expert. No. Are things getting better? No. Are things getting worse? You bet they are!'

She gets really annoyed that she is constantly presented with a *fait accompli*:

'It is terribly destructive for society: we are always the last to hear. We get told after things have already happened, when the changes have been made. You never know what it means. It's the same every time there are fresh cuts. They don't know what the consequences are; they think they know it, but they don't. They only find out three years later.'

Angela would so much like to have more certainty about her future. After everything she has been through, her motto is now:

'If you try to work out in advance what something means for your personal situation, you can avoid a lot of suffering!'

The cuts mean that it is harder for her to get by now. She feels like they have chipped away at her. She needs some support - *'a life coach'*.

'If there was someone there who could help me work out what my situation might be ... what is happening here. (She points to a point on the timeline again), will be happening again here.'

She has sought help with her financial problems, but it did not work out. The waiting times were long and in the end she did not receive any help. And the advisors also send you an invoice for that help. That's

another worry - how to pay for that. But because she does not know what the future will bring, she always ends up in the same difficult situation. She cannot make the sums add up. That is the long and the short of it.

'This is what comes out of my life story.' (She indicates different points on the timeline again.) *That's what I keep coming back to: I didn't know it here, and I didn't know it here either. And I only find out now, from other people, that things could have worked out for me if only I'd know more about how do my finances and all of that ... I could have seen it coming.'*

Angela seems to chant these last sentences.

The first reason why Angela wants to be able to make her own choices is the stranglehold that she feels that she is in, as a result of her weak financial position. The second reason goes further back to her childhood and when she was a young woman. She married in the Netherlands a non-Dutch, moved to his country later and became mother three times, before she had to return to the Netherlands when her husband was imprisoned.

They went to stay with a friend in a major city in the west of the Netherlands. Fortunately, she found an organisation that supports women whose husbands are in prison, and they were able to help her. Through them, she was able to find a furnished flat in a town near to her friend's house.

'So I had somewhere to sleep.' But her new home was a criminal environment. She was attacked twice. *'It was an awful period there!'* *'But the children went back to school. I was happy about that. The divorce came through while she was there. So that was something.'*

Angela had to apply for welfare benefits. Social services wanted her to look for work. She describes it:

'But you can work! Sure I can work, but I have three traumatised children. They showed no understanding! They follow the letter of the law. I can understand it, but it's hard to find any humanity in how they handled my case.'

Finally, she received her benefits payments. They were reasonable - she was able to pay for her children to do sports. In hindsight, she says:

'I found life on welfare better than what I'm doing now – strange as that may seem. Why? It was easier.'

She was not able to go out to work. She wanted to be with her children. They had been through so much. And social services were accommodating about that.

She cannot say that she has ever really recovered in her new home in the Netherlands. She uses the words *'twilight zone, no awareness, tired'* to talk about this period. She feels exhausted and dispirited. Her welfare payments are not enough to cover all her costs and outgoings. That is how *'denial'* starts to set in.

She cannot or is unwilling to face up to her financial situation. She simply cannot make ends meet. She just lets the bills pile up; she no longer opens her electricity bills. She talks about them as *'junk'*, *'there is no solution'*. Fortunately, her brother has paid her electricity arrears for her. In this situation, she is embarking on a new relationship: *'her weakness makes her vulnerable.'* She has *'clouded vision'*. But the tide seems to be turning. They are moving to the south of the Netherlands together.

3.2 Marco's life story

Marco takes a pencil and adds some details to the timeline that represents his life. He marks the beginning - his birth - and continues up until the present. He draws a few faint lines up until his 7th birthday and then, continuing to use light strokes, he writes a few notes next to those lines, but he has so much to tell us that we quickly forget all about the timeline. He has a lot to say, and he speaks with precision - he has thought this through. He does not need to be prompted with many questions.

Marco was born in a town in South America. He is now 29 years old. The move to the Netherlands was not too much of a shock for Marco.

'It was all new to me, but I didn't really think about that at all. You just get on with it. It was just the place where we lived. I already had enough to keep me busy, you know. You discover new things. The weather is different. You have to learn a new language.' *'His new father's parents accepted him warmly into this new family.'*

Marco was 24 years old when he graduated with a Bachelor's degree in Administration. He was unemployed for a while. Then he was approached by a small ICT company. Marco started to work at the company and he designed timetables for a school for four days a week.

After eight months, he made plans to start a Master's programme in European Union Studies at university. He passed all the courses in the pre-Master's preparatory programme but his final report was not quite good enough. His grandmother, here in the Netherlands, had passed away and he was finding it difficult to concentrate. He lived off his savings for a while, and then he began studying again. But his motivation was gone and he could not get down to work. He had too many financial worries: how would he be able to repay the loan that he needed to carry on studying?

'How am I going to pay this off? I'd already borrowed €5,000 to complete my Bachelor's. That was still manageable, €5,000. But just doing the two-year pre-Master's programme had already cost me €20,000. I had a part-time job, but that came to an end and I needed to borrow some money. So in the space of two years my debts suddenly ballooned from €5,000 to €25,000. And then I thought: I have to make a decision here, because if I finish the Master's that's another two years, so then I'll have a debt of €50,000 by the time I finish. Am I going to find a job that will enable me to pay that off?! ... Then I thought: no, it's impossible, I have to quit. It cost me quite a few sleepless nights.'

When he was 27, Marco had to apply for welfare. That was two years ago. The process did not go smoothly at all. Due to some careless and stupid mistakes made by social services, his claim was not granted within the standard one-month period and it took three months before he received anything at all. He had to fight for his rights and constantly had to remind them of the administrative errors that they had made - errors that had left him in a precarious position.

He had no income during those three months and he had to borrow money from friends. He did not like to have to do this at all. But luckily, things worked out. He would never have asked his parents for money. And Marco certainly does not make a habit of borrowing. He made an arrangement with his landlord. On the internet he looked for advice about how best to cope. He had to lead a very limited life.

'You have to be creative with food and stuff. It was a really very basic existence and you find yourself getting isolated because you can't go over to a friend's house or go out for a drink together.' He became dependent on other people. *'Everything you have is right here. (He points around his home.)'* But Marco was able to deal with it. *'And I went to the library more often. Because at least there are other people around in the library. You don't want to just sit here all day because once you develop negative feelings about your own home, you will always have those associations (with hardship and being alone); so I really didn't want that to happen. Otherwise you'll just keep going round in a circle ...'*

All the problems and worries that had caused Marco to end up on welfare and the low self-esteem that affects those on welfare have affected Marco too. For a year, he suffered from health problems: anaemia, stress due to financial worries, poor digestion and heartburn. His health has improved over the past year though. Social services have absolutely no regard for the personal impact that living on welfare has on people. On the contrary, they actually stigmatise people even further. *'Social services do not take your health situation into account. They just assume that you're fine.'* They were not interested in the medical details.

Marco scrutinised his treatment by social services with his characteristic scepticism and from a professional point of view. In many respects, he doubted the legitimacy and efficiency of the requirements that he was subject to and the tasks that he was made to do. Threats and intimidation were an integral part of their way of working. The officials were often ambivalent. They did not really believe in the measures that they were being made to impose on their clients, and they were under pressure to meet their targets. There was often an arbitrary element: many of the measures had no basis in law. All of that has a stigmatising effect on those who need to live on welfare. It's all one-way traffic: there is just no scope for looking at or responding to claimants' problems. You are put in a position of dependency: you are supposed to be grateful that you are receiving any benefit payments at all. But welfare is a right! There is a reason why you are given welfare in Marco's city!

At social services, you go through three successive phases. Marco is now in the final phase.

'You have to sign a contract that includes the following statements: I will generally apply for five jobs every week; I am available 24 hours a day, 7 days a week if they call me - you have to sign to confirm that - and other similar requirements,

but I've never seen them refer to a particular legal statute to show that this is a lawful approach.' 'So I wasn't properly informed, but I either had to sign the contract or I would not receive any welfare payments. So effectively you are forced to sign under duress: there is no option of not signing. And if you decide to argue you'll have problems with your client manager, and it is the client manager who decides whether you will be punished or not; it's better to keep in your client manager's good books. He can punish you by reducing or stopping your benefits.'

The contracts include some very demanding requirements, though it is unclear whether these have any legal standing. The contract does not mention its legal basis; neither do the client managers.

'...And then there are the letters you get: "A contract is a contract!" They write you some really threatening letters. There is never a signature on those letters, or sometimes just the digital signature of the corporate director. So I don't know who writes those letters or who is responsible. But I do wonder - does the manager know what kind of letters are being sent out? And who is actually in charge there anyway? Is it the manager or is it the ordinary people in the departments who decide what happens?' ... and the computer signature: Does he know that his signature is being used for letters like that? Has he ever read this letter and approved it? Because if he hasn't, is that not a violation of standard legal procedures?'

Marco is unable to ask these questions to the staff at social services because he is afraid that there may be repercussions. However, he understands the position of the civil servants who work there. He calls them:

'The front line officials. They are also being told to do more with less money; they are also short-staffed. So it's not surprising that they're under more and more pressure and that mistakes are made, and that those mistakes are then covered up. And they're afraid too. Every day they meet people who are living on welfare. They don't want to end up on welfare too. They think that if they admit that mistakes have been made then someone could get fired more easily.' Most of them have good intentions. But either they don't have the skills or budgets are so tight that they just have to make do with what they have. And in practical terms, there's no point in me going there and give them a piece of my mind because then you're going to get into an argument.'

The overall effect of all the requirements and the meetings is very unclear. But...

'I think it's positive because you can talk to other people in the same situation. That was good, but it would have been nicer if there had been more structure around it. Not just the appearance of "we are going to help you".' Really all they want to do is get you off welfare. And ultimately that is counterproductive.'

Unintentionally or inadvertently, social services also have an important positive impact, however: they organise group meetings where those in the same situation can meet each other, support one another and develop plans together. How could social services be improved?

'For me it would have been better if they had just said at the start that it's primarily a place where people can talk to other people about their situation, because that would be much nicer. Because you might be in a situation where people do not accept you because you are living on welfare ... It affects your confidence because you are seen as worthless. It is a personal tragedy for anybody to end up on welfare, but nobody thinks about that at all. And they expect you to come along and be cheerful and pleasant to everyone and all that. But for a lot of people, when they hear that, it just makes them sick. The pretence just gets too much: It's all just words. It feels very stifling.'

The programmes organised by social services have an adverse effect. People on welfare are forced to take part in meaningless activities because of the agreements that they sign, says Marco. By forcing people to send open applications to companies and to reply to recruitment advertisements, social services think that they will get them off benefits quicker.

But applying for jobs in that way makes absolutely no sense for Marco. The recruitment advertisements are poor quality: they are very specific about who and what they are looking for and there is no sense of the real world.

'You won't even get an interview, and if you do you'll be rejected. Applicants of Arab origin, older applicants, women with children - they are all discriminated against ...'

Marco once sent two application letters for the same job advert, one with his real name and one with an adapted Dutch name. He's waiting for the results.

'When you apply, you don't know where you stand. That's possibly the worst thing for me.'

You must have experience, but you mustn't be too old: you have to be perfect. Marco has some questions.

Is that what they really need? Are they ever really going to find that? And that is ... it's very difficult for me, yes, because I can't meet those requirements. But I do try. ... But on the other hand, my heart isn't in it. I write the letters, but are they even going to read them? It is such a vague job description that I don't even know what I'm applying for.'

Marco receives no help from social services with his compulsory job applications.

In the second phase, you are allocated to a client manager. But she is unable to support Marco.

It's not very helpful. That person isn't really able to help me in a personalised way because she doesn't have the skills. She is mainly there for people who have less education. She doesn't have any contacts with the companies that I've been trained to work for and where I want to work.'

The only jobs she can offer are ones that are not suitable for Marco. And the work is very insecure.

I've just come out of a really awful situation. Why would I risk getting myself back into a bad situation, because what you often see is someone goes off to work on a zero-hours contract or a six-month contract, and then after six months they're out on their ear again? Then you need to apply for benefits all over again and you'll have another month to get through with no income at all.' If they changed it to make it possible to go straight back onto benefits in that kind of situation, it would make it much more appealing to accept those jobs.'

Marco does not understand why there are no retraining programmes any more, or work experience placements. Refurbishing houses and neighbourhoods, for example.

How does the approach of social services tie in with the requirements of the Participation Act, which says that they have to provide personalised assistance for their clients?

They are meant to provide personalised assistance, but as soon as I asked them about personalisation - do you have a list for personalisation? Which resources do you have available for personalisation? As soon as I started to ask specific questions, I would see them squirm and they couldn't answer. They were probably hoping that nobody would ask that question. But when someone does ask, they squirm like a snake and try to get out of it.'

The tasks imposed by social services are often at odds with Marco's own plans to find work. For him they actually hinder his efforts to find work, rather than helping him. They are draining. He is constantly having to concentrate on fulfilling those requirements rather than on developing his own approach. But he continues to send open applications and to reply to job advertisements because you never know.

And what is his own plan? By networking and keeping his own knowledge and skills up to date, he is trying to find a position as a research assistant or a teaching assistant, or to find individual contracts so that he can find employment that way. He is working with a volunteer organisation, in order to widen his network. He also maintains close contact with his older brother who did the same degree programme and now finds himself in the same situation. Marco and his brother are carrying out research in two cities in order to maintain the skills that they acquired. Possibly, Marco will be able to get a work experience placement. Marco is optimistic about this, but he is also staying realistic. He does not let himself get carried away by every emotion and mood.

I want to be able to work in a particular field; I have a plan about how I can get there, and I'll see what happens. So I'm up for it. I'm neither too hopeful nor desperate. I'm just going to see what happens.'

4. Analysis of experiences in practice

4.1 Introduction

This chapter places the knowledge acquired in the focus group meetings and in-depth interviews (Chapter 3) in the context of the literature study in Chapter 1. The Netherlands has implemented substantial spending cuts which were achieved by reforms of the social security system. In practice, a continually increasing number of citizens have ended up in poverty. Poverty has been measured at the highest rate of the Netherlands in Rotterdam, the city in which we conducted our study (2012; see Section 1.3).

The ten participants who took part in the Dutch RE-InVEST study explained to us how they this experienced in practice. This chapter is focused on their experiences and interpretations of the experiences that are also documented in the two biographical narratives of the previous chapter. Section 4.2 concentrates on the effects of the crisis. Section 4.3 reports on the discussions on the participants' basic rights and their associated capabilities to influence the level of those rights. Section 4.4 concludes with the impact on society that participants observe.

4.2 Capabilities: the impact of the crisis on resources and personal conversion factors

Since this RE-InVEST work package is focused on the impact of the crisis, the participants were requested to explain how the crisis has contributed to their current difficult financial situation. The explanatory note to the crisis was as follows: *'we cannot escape the fact that something is going on in the Netherlands. A bank collapsed in 2008, which was followed by a wide range of developments that we refer to as a crisis or a recession.'*

The participants stated that their prospects have deteriorated as a result of the crisis, not only in terms of finding a job, but also in terms of the opportunities to study (higher costs). Participants who have been on benefits for several years or more stated that the **spending cuts** have had a cumulative effect and have resulted in both the steady decrease in income, while costs increased resulting in diminished resources, as well as a more creative call upon personal conversion factors (see Figure 2.1).

The participants stated that following the transfer of the administration of the social assistance schemes to the municipalities the spending cuts have resulted in **falling incomes**. For example, in just one year the waiver of the waste collection levy, the long-term extra benefit, the general chronically ill benefit and special social assistance benefits (for medical costs) were all abolished (see Chapter 1). The abolition of the medical costs benefit has been compensated by a (another, lower) medical care costs benefit and a refund that must be requested via income tax. On balance, the compensation via the Social Support Act (WMO) was lower than the original care benefits granted by the national government pursuant to the Chronically Ill and Disabled Persons (Allowances) Act (WTCG) that has now been abolished (see Section 1.2). This development has been described as *'unbelievable destruction'* (man, 60, single), which was endorsed by the participants who are dependent on benefits. The waiver of the water board levy has also been reduced and participants stated that they now rarely receive special social assistance benefits.

However, the participant who has been chronically ill for many years stated that: *'My case as someone who is chronically ill is now fully documented in all dossiers. So they don't bother me all too much.'* (woman, 59, single).

Participants with a state old age pension also have experiences with their income development that differ from those of participants on benefits. They state that pensions have not kept up with price increases.

On the **cost side**, everyone experiences the healthcare insurance personal excess as a great expense when you are ill, which one participant expressed as follows: *'And then in addition to the €120 I already pay each month they fine me, they simply debit €375 from my account.'* (woman, 65+, cohabiting).

The youngest participant (man, 29, single) stated that there are also costs which are not covered by healthcare insurance: *'I would like to have my teeth examined and more besides, but I simply can't afford it. It's a choice between food and the dentist. And that's not really a choice.'*

The participants also drew up a long list of things that had become more expensive – the shopping, child-care, fixed charges, such as energy bills, study costs and public transport (for students) and the cost of the maintenance of their house.

Most participants also referred to the annual rent increases (eight of the ten participants rent their home). They noted that last year's rent increase was higher than in the previous years. One participant reached agreement with the housing corporation whereby the rent would be paid at the end of the month rather than at the beginning of the month. The social housing landlord adopted an obliging, yet flexible attitude that enabled the participant to pay the unexpectedly higher energy bill. Participants stated that they gave preference to a roof over their head. They pay the rent and 'prefer' to run up other debts.

The ability to opt for specific forms of beings and doings requires both resources and conversion factors (Figure 2.1). **Personal conversion factors** are defined as skills and physical capabilities (Section 2.1). A frequently heard statement was that it is necessary to begin by cutting your coat according to your cloth. The focus groups and biographical narratives also reveal that knowledge of the rules is regarded as the crux, as well as the skills (such as not being afraid to ask questions and writing letters) required to find your way in the bureaucracy of the agencies and mobilise help: *'You have to find your way'* (man, 29, single). When asked about submitting complaints and lodging objections, one participant replied the following counter-question: *'When it comes to the crunch I always ask myself: is it worth it all?'* (woman, 33, married, with children living at home). The participants also stated that their personal network was of great importance in mobilising help.

Seeking a rental home that needs work was suggested as one way of reducing housing costs. This requires a specific skill – carrying out DIY with *'blood, sweat and tears'* (woman, 33, married, with children living at home). Furthermore, *'calculate, calculate, calculate'* was considered a necessary skill (woman, 65+, cohabiting). Other strategies listed for coping with their deteriorating financial situation were as follows: always being one month in arrears with the rent, borrowing on the credit card or being overdrawn, reaching agreement on payment schedules when repaying benefits (e.g. housing allowances), cutting your coat according to your cloth by, for example by doing cheap but high-quality shopping (special offers, especially low-price charity or shops) or deferring expenditure (such as a visit to the dentist). Other tips were also exchanged during the focus group meetings, such as how to find the way when seeking support for the assistance of aids and the best insurance company for healthcare costs in specific circumstances.

Another proposition that most of the participants agreed with was the need to make use of your knowledge and *'Play the system a little, OK, although you have to be cut out for it.'* (woman, 33, married, with children living at home). This, in the participants' experience, was not something for everyone. Participants frequently referred to the problems that arose when the tax authorities paid too much benefit and then recovered the excess, or a high bill from the energy company at the end of the year. This is a particular problem when income fluctuates around the benefit eligibility limit or around the limit for assistance from the social service.

In some instances the room for financial manoeuvre is rapidly exhausted, for example someone is confronted with increasing debts and is unable to organise help. The ill or disabled are also at a disadvantage in exercising their skills and, consequently, in making use of their capabilities in choosing. The participants had comprehensive experience with this problem, in part because they were or had been ill, had children who were seriously ill or disabled or had experience with growing older.

On balance, the participants proposed many options for the retention of **capabilities** in the financial situation or deteriorating financial situation that are required to make the choices for a specific standard of living (Figure 2.1). A trend towards 'less' cannot last forever. *'Sooner or later, the bottom of the swimming pool will be reached'* (man, 60, single): at some point the room for manoeuvre is going to be exhausted. The required standard of living based on human rights and the capabilities required to make the choices needed to achieve this standard serves as the approach route to the next section.

4.3 Capabilities: freedom of choice for a 'decent' life based on human rights

The focus group meetings discussed the criteria to be met for a 'decent' life on the basis of the list of capabilities developed from internationally accepted human rights and principles of equality (see Appendix). The criteria for a decent (or, expressed in less moralistic terms, as suggested by one participant, 'good') life in the left column are derived from the internationally accepted human rights from two sources, the *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights* (ICCPR) and the *International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights* (ICESCR). The right column lists examples of these criteria to be met for a decent life or a life with human dignity. Formulating these in terms of capabilities for choosing for specific forms of beings and doings (Figure 2.1) brings the approaches to human rights and to capabilities together.

We conducted the discussion at municipal level, whereby we took account of influences from outside the municipality (such as regulations that govern the entire country). The discussion focused on the way in which participants experience their personal difficult financial situation and their expectations for the future. The discussion of capabilities at municipal level served as a stepping stone to exchanges of arguments about the daily functioning of the participants in terms of 'being' and 'doing' and the associated set of capabilities that enable persons to make choices (Figure 2.1). In conclusion, each participant completed the circle with the dimensions of a decent life in their personal situation (examples are enclosed in the appendix).

At the beginning of the discussion, we explained its objective in the following terms: *'to give consideration to the design of society ... in a manner that is more compatible with who we are, our situation and our capacities. ... What is a decent life? How do you determine what this requires?'* The following paragraphs give a brief summary of the discussions on each dimension of a decent life that were held by two groups during two focus group meetings. The reports focus for as far as is possible on the discussions of relevance to the precarious financial situation of the participants. These include relevant information from the first focus group meeting and the two biographical narratives (Chapter 3).

The participants discussed extensively and arrived at different standpoints on the capabilities for the choice of a specific standard of living as based on human rights. Although this discussion was not explicitly related to the crisis, participants occasionally made the link for themselves, for example when they observed that spending cuts in care and social assistance benefits result in higher costs for those concerned.

Nor were the discussions always rooted or solely rooted in the precarious financial situation of the participants. Collective violence, for example, was primarily linked to being a woman and to the changing social standards and values that are resulting in a less charitable society. In addition, for example, the development of self-respect and identity was primarily regarded as a question of 'growing up', upbringing, acquiring experience and personal development. Another example related to productive activities: work is not equally accessible to everyone and impediments confront the young, women and older persons.

The participants, on the basis of their difficulty in making ends meet, gave a great deal of information about their experiences with restrictions on their capabilities to opt for a good life on the basis of human rights.

For example, participants who have been in a financially difficult position for a longer period of time experienced that a continually increasing number of obligations (rules) are imposed on them that reduce their capabilities to opt for an adequate standard of living. Participants also indicated that the state old age pension (AOW) restricts their options.

The participants were also of the opinion that housing standards have fallen as homes have been less affordable due to the higher rent increases in recent years, as well as the more difficult access to rent allowances. Moreover, the Municipality of Rotterdam intends to replace cheap and poor quality housing with housing that is more expensive but of a better quality.

The participants observed that education and learning were increasingly dependent on household resources, which has reduced the capabilities for receiving an education. Participants were also astounded that after so many years the various types of education still do not dovetail with each other, which in turn impedes entry to the labour market.

Participants adopted a comparable reasoning for healthcare and the right to life. The higher costs of healthcare increase the risk that vulnerable households are unable to maintain their health at the required

level and fall by the wayside: although they find their lives worthwhile, their life expectancy will then be shorter.

Participants also observed that those who are in most need for the legal assistance associated with legal certainty readily fall by the wayside. Regulations are increasingly complex and impersonal/harsher.

Participants also observed that the capabilities for productive and appreciated activities have been reduced, primarily due to the imbalance between the number of unemployed and the number of vacancies and to displacement (mandatory volunteer work within the context of the Participation Act). Participants also experienced that their opportunities to exert an influence on their personal situation and social life were restricted due to their relatively low income. Moreover, participants on benefits are dependent on the rules of the benefit agencies in their design of their life, occasionally their day-to-day life. Participants experienced the opportunities to influence municipal or national decision-making as abominable.

On balance, these developments place a greater demand on **personal conversion factors**, as was also indicated in the previous section: changing skills and knowledge of the schemes are both necessary, as well as options for calling in assistance from a personal network (family and friends) for financial or moral support. Although participants indicated that things had become more difficult in recent years, due to government spending cuts, they also stated that it was still possible to exercise their discretion to a greater or lesser extent in their choice of a greater emphasis on one human right (identity and an individual life) than on another (participation and an influence on decision-making in the community). However, participants did experience a decline in their options. Perseverance was required from them.

4.4 Impact on society

The focus group discussions (this chapter) and the two biographical narratives (Chapter 3) give an insight into the impact of the spending cuts that the Dutch government implemented following the global financial crisis (Section 1.3) on households with a low income. The government's endeavours to promote a participation society in the Netherlands seem to go hand in hand with a less caring government that increasingly wishes to focus on households in danger of losing out (Rutte, 2014).

In the same period in which the cost cutting policy has been implemented and citizens have been assigned more responsibility the number of benefit recipients has increased, as has the Dutch poverty rate, in part due to the continuing poor condition of the economy in the years following 2008 (Chapter 1). The participants in the study confirmed that the implemented spending cuts, in part in response to the crisis, have had consequences for both care and social assistance, as well as on the reduction in the waiver of local charges.

The incidence of financial problems in the form of debt and payment arrears has been increasing (Section 1.3). The participants in the study, the majority of whom have had several years experience with the problems of making ends meet on a low income, confirm that they are now in a less favourable financial situation than in previous years. In the past years it has become even more difficult to make ends meet, as is manifested in the form of various financial measures (based on personal conversion factors; see Figure 2.1) such as arrears in rent payments, incurring credit card debt, renting a home that needs some work, as well as being confronted with debts due to 'unjustifiably' received benefits.

The participants were of the opinion that these are developments are also detrimental to society. They referred to the increasing number of benefit regulations (bureaucracy) that contribute to the harsher social climate with respect to care support and income benefits. The participants gave a great deal of information about their experiences with the **bureaucracy** of agencies, in particular in the social services and tax authorities. They referred to the complexity, the struggle against bureaucracy and the increasing impersonalisation that results in an increasingly harsh society. In terms of Figure 2.1 it can be observed that the social conversion factors have become less favourable. These developments were usually ascribed to politicians.

The tax authorities and social services, for example, already seem to be in the possession of specific details, but still, in the participants' opinion, unnecessarily request them for these details again. These agencies also need a great deal of information: *'They almost want to know when I've been to the toilet, I always say.'* (woman, late 50's, single).

Participants also have indications that there are problems at these agencies: *'With social assistance benefits it's all a question of OK, that's going to go wrong, they don't communicate with each other, they send me forms that they don't understand themselves but do expect me to understand, ...; I get letters they haven't read themselves'* (man, 29, single). Moreover, when mistakes are made the participants also have difficulty in getting things sorted out with the social service: *'The municipal social service is a quite a large agency, you know, and they will not readily admit that they are in the wrong – and then you need good evidence to prove that they are in the wrong'* (woman, late 50's, single). As a result, thorough preparations were required when there were disagreements. Assistance in making these preparations was not always offered by legal assistance or state appointed lawyers.

Participants also reported their experiences with the bureaucracy of the tax authorities, which burdened the recipients of benefits (like housing allowances) with yet another problem when they were 'too late' in reclaiming 'unjustifiably' received benefits, a situation that confronted Angela, for example (Section 3.1). This 'inertia' is detrimental to flexibility, although one participant did state that the tax authorities are open to a payment schedule when it is contacted about a problem (see Section 4.3).

Participants also had difficulties with situations in which income fluctuates around the income limit for rent allowances or around the social assistance benefit eligibility limit. The recipient then needs to submit a large number of changes to the relevant agencies. However, participants stated that these notifications were not enough to prevent the tax authorities from reclaiming €800, rather than paying a lower rent allowance, when the recipient's income is €5 above the limit: *'you are punished very harshly'* (woman, 65+, cohabiting). Participants, to the extent that they had the relevant experience, yearned for the former rent grant schemes that did not have these complexities, in part because the rent allowance was paid directly to the landlord.

In the participants' opinion the *'rules are rules'* (woman, late 50's, single) mentality creates a grey area in which households falling 'just' outside a scheme are nevertheless unable to foot the bills for specific costs (such as medical costs). It was noted that standards are always to some extent subjective, certainly when spending cuts result in increasingly stringent requirements on eligibility for assistance. In the previous section, one of the participants referred to this development as *'financial Darwinism'* (man, 60, single).

Another facet of bureaucracy would also appear to offer little scope for customisation, for when there are opportunities for sporadic work (for example on the market): *'However, those are often jobs for one or two days. You have to report that you had work. That results in a complete snarl up, fuss about the rent benefit and those kinds of things.'* (man, 61, single). It would appear that participants are put off by the regulations, the possible confusion that may result and the risk that the social assistance benefit may be justifiably or unjustifiably stopped. This last can occur, one participant stated, when you don't report any changes but a person with the same name *does*. One participant stated that when you wish to start as a self-employed person you are also confronted with a great deal of bureaucracy. This necessarily costs a relatively large amount of time that is detrimental to the actual work. On balance, the participants were of the opinion that the regulations did not act as an incentive for them to take personal initiatives: *'Your inner strength is emasculated by all those government rules'* (man, 65+, married). *'It makes you dependent. You don't learn it.'* (man, 61, single). The participants stated that personal initiative increasingly requires knowledge of and skills with increasingly complex and more difficult regulations, in other words strongly or more strongly developed **personal conversion factors**.

Furthermore, the participants are of the opinion that the **social conversion factors** that also influence personal capability sets (Section 2.1) are now under a less lucky star, in particular for households dependent on support in the form of a benefit or care. Social standards and social agencies increasingly appear to indicate a more impersonal and harsher social climate with respect to unemployment and care support. This was referred to as being largely due to the individualisation of society that has resulted in the hardening of social care in recent years. The participants stated that this was already in progress before the crisis.

However, the participants suggested that this individualisation was not developing in the direction of a 'participation society' that offers opportunities for personal initiative. The social assistance system, for

example, results in the recipients becoming inactive due to the bureaucratisation of choice options. It is, for example, impossible to earn some income from temporary and very short jobs without becoming ensnared in a bureaucracy and losing support that may be accompanied by a discovery that is 'too late' and which results in large debts.

The focus of the social services and the tax authorities on rules referred to several times by the participants leads to bureaucracy that results in a lack of flexibility and customisation unless those rules permit exceptions. *'You are no longer a person and you have to comply with that rule because that's what it says.'* (woman, late 50's, single). One participant suggested that the complexity of the bureaucracy is designed to get people to simply give up. An example was also given in which a participant was offered a job that was too arduous for someone in the participant's health situation. The participants stated that the social service employees must also comply with rules and meet targets. The rules have been made more stringent and they may lose their job if they don't meet the targets. *'They must achieve their production targets. This means that all the persons who are entitled to benefits are products.'* (woman, middle to late 50's, married). As a result, rules have to be given priority over customisation and flexibility. This increasing impersonalisation results in a clinical approach: *'That was what I was also afraid of ... that indifference ... if necessary, I'll just move on.'* (man, 60, single).

Moreover, participants stated that social assistance benefit recipients are often not treated with respect. They concluded that standards have shifted. Persons in financial difficulties are increasingly looked down on as if they have caused the problems. *'The point is, and I often notice that people are doing it - and you are now doing it in what you are saying to each other - that, at a certain point, people have shifted a standard in the past 20 years, a standard we must comply with. I'm not saying that you are imposing the standard, but we all help a little, the way this should be, that should be, and if you don't comply with that. Luckily, we are simply all different from each other.'* (man, 61, single).

Other statements that the participants made about this shift in the direction of the stigma which the participants believe is associated with social assistance benefit recipients (those without a job) include:

'When you are strong-willed and unemployed they imprint: 'Where there's a will, there's a way' in your mind. In other words, everyone can find a job. But you should begin by thinking strategically, that's important, that you begin by considering how low your chances are of finding a job.' (man, 60, single).

'Here in Rotterdam they're also so far with individualisation that unemployment is all in your head.' (man, 60, single).

'The negative pressure on you to give account for your being on benefits' (man, 61, single).

'Agencies treat clients as criminals. ... It's all the client's fault. So when you lose your job, it's your fault. You are doing it all completely wrong, because your little CV is not in order. Those are the kinds of things you hear. People really are treated like dirt ...' (woman, middle to late 50's, married).

'They treat you like a criminal there, because you have to justify everything: you are guilty, you have to give them proof. This will be due to the crisis, including the Participation Act, the Fraud Act that has been pushed through and makes it all easier for municipalities to accuse you.' (man, 29, single).

'Social assistance benefit recipients [are] one of the black sheep.' (man, 29, single).

'Everyone thinks that as you are on benefits you don't really want to do anything. Obviously, that's not true. You have no choice, and once you land in this situation you can't get out. That's why I think it's dreadful in Rotterdam, where absolutely no distinction is made between the chronically ill/disabled and those who would be able to work, but are confronted with the situation in which there simply are not enough jobs. They are nevertheless looked down upon in a certain manner, along the lines of "you should try harder", while there simply is no work.' (woman, 59, single).

'So you need to adopt a certain attitude, be as tough as nails to get on with your life and let everything slide off your back, don't you?' (man, 61, single).

'Only an elephant still has inner strength.' (man, 65+, married).

One participant summarised the situation as follows: *'I suspect, if I look at the last 15 to 20 years, everyone at every level, whether I have a job or am on benefits or the tax authorities or something else, everything is no longer so pleasant.'* (man, 61, single).

The participants ascribed many of the changes to **politicians**, as was also indicated in the previous paragraphs. This outcome can be considered to be backed by the lower share of respondents that tended to have trust in the Dutch government and politics in the autumn of 2015 than of 2008, as measured by the Eurobarometer (Section 1.3).

The participants in our focus group meetings explained that politicians largely determine the human rights that citizens can realise for themselves. The participants referred to the increasingly harsh social climate with respect to unemployment and care support in terms of the impression that social assistance benefit recipients commit fraud, although calculations reveal that this is not the case (a maximum of between 10 and 15% when all forms are taken into account): *'This attitude also still prevails amongst the public and the politicians also use this attitude to play the general public off against persons on benefits.'* (man, 65+, married).

Participants also stated that politicians individualise collective problems. Participants often found it difficult to influence politics, in part due to the formation of coalitions but also, as one participant commented: *'It's nothing but party politics at the moment'* (man, 65+, married).

Participants had different expectations for the future. The safe mentality and solidarity of the 60's and 70's was compared with today's mentality. Some spoke of wishing to leave Rotterdam or even emigrating, although they also referred to their ties with this chilly, damp country. The participants stated that the tide could no longer be turned, but also that from a political perspective things cannot and may not deteriorate even further. One participant defended another standpoint, namely that we must not lose hope of a swing in the social climate: *'There are also prophets, that's what I call them, who say that these are the spasms of an old system that only puts the cart before its horse or it eats its tail. However, they also say that there will be a swing, resulting in an awareness shock, which will lead to the emergence of a literally much better society, a much more charitable society.'* (man, 60, single).

5. Conclusions

5.1 Introduction

After the Netherlands in 2009 landed in the first of three recessions, the government, which took office in 2012, announced that spending cuts had become inevitable. Government deficits and government debts were increasing and the Netherlands no longer complied with the requirements for a stable currency union in the European Union. Therefore, the Netherlands has implemented substantial spending cuts which were, among others, achieved by reforms of the social security system. An increased emphasis was placed on incentives to find work, whilst access to care facilities was made more difficult, in part by increasing the stringency of the associated conditions. Now that the recessions of 2012 and 2013 are also behind us, society is confronted with an increase in both the number of social assistance benefit recipients and poverty rates. An increasing number of persons are having difficulties with making ends meet (payment arrears and debts). In Rotterdam, the city heading the municipal poverty list, 17.2% of the households must survive on a low income and six per cent had had a low income for at least four consecutive years.

This study articulates the experiences of ten of Rotterdam's residents who found themselves in a financially vulnerable position at the beginning of this study. It may be assumed that these experiences placed within the context of the broad spending cuts implemented in the Netherlands and the resultant increases in financial problems, give an insight into the harshening social climate, not only in Rotterdam, but also in other Dutch municipalities.

Two hypotheses are to be examined in the study. The first is the expectation that the neoliberal policy of spending cuts (disinvestment) in social assistance schemes result in growing distrust and resentment among the population. The second hypothesis postulates that these developments are caused by the erosion of or disinvestment in what are referred to as the capabilities of persons and their human rights (social disinvestment). Before we address the hypotheses in Section 5.3 - which focuses on the impact on society and the social climate - we begin with a discussion of capabilities in Section 5.2.

5.2 Erosion of capabilities

The consequences of the spending cuts on capabilities are addressed on the basis of the resources and conversion factors in this section. These determine the extent to which persons are in a position to opt for specific forms of beings and doings (the functionings).

The participants stated, with reference to the **resources**, that the spending cuts had resulted both in a decrease in the income of social assistance benefit recipients and recipients of care benefits and an increase in the costs incurred by all participants in recent years (for example, as a result of the gradual reduction of the waiver of local charges). Many developments were ascribed to the crisis, such as the increased price of the daily shopping and the increased costs of school and study books.

The question is then whether those in a precarious financial situation are in a position to compensate for their reduced financial opportunities by the increased or more creative deployment of their **personal conversion factors** – their skills and bodily features. A frequently heard statement was that it was necessary to cut your coat according to your cloth. The group sessions (focus groups) and in-depth interviews (biographical narratives) also reveal that knowledge of the rules is regarded as the crux, as well as the skills (such as not being afraid to ask questions and writing letters) required to find your way in the bureaucracy of the agencies to mobilise help. Participants also emphasised that assistance from a personal network was of crucial importance.

Seeking a rental home that needs work was suggested as one way of reducing housing costs. However, this does require a certain skill, the ability to carry out DIY. Other examples used by the participants included always being one month in arrears with the rent, borrowing on the credit card or being overdrawn, reaching agreement on payment schedules when repaying benefits, cutting your coat according to your cloth, for example by doing cheap but high-quality shopping (special offers, especially low-price charity or shops) or deferring expenditure (such as a visit to the dentist). Other tips were also exchanged during the focus group meetings, such as how to find the way when seeking support for the assistance of aids and the best insurance company for healthcare costs in specific circumstances.

Another proposition that was generally endorsed by the participants was that it is necessary to make use of the knowledge and opportunities offered by the system. This, in the participants' experience, was not something for everyone. Participants frequently referred to the problems that arose when the tax authorities paid too much rent allowance or child allowance and then recovered the excess, or a high bill from the energy company at the end of the year. This is a particular problem when income fluctuates around the benefit eligibility limit or around the limit for assistance from the social service.

Participants were not always able to find a solution, especially in complex situations. The ill, disabled or older are also at a disadvantage in exercising their skills and, consequently, in using their capabilities to make choices.

The participants in our study who have difficulty with making ends meet on a low income confirm that they are now in a less favourable financial situation than in the previous years. In the past years it has become even more difficult to make ends meet. The participants also indicated that it has become more difficult to take personal initiatives. This in turn impedes 'participation in society'.

5.3 Social assistance and health care: harsher social climate

The analysis of the experiences of the participants who took part in this study reveal that the disinvestment in public facilities or support would appear to be eroding the social fabric as a result of the erosion of the **social conversion factors**. The participants observed an increasing impersonalisation and harshening that could already be felt before the crisis gripped the Netherlands. In addition, participants stated that social assistance benefits recipients are often not treated with respect. The agencies are suspicious and the recipients of assistance apportion the blame to the failing politicians. As a result, the **first hypothesis** of this study - the expectation that the neoliberal policy of spending cuts (disinvestment) in social assistance schemes result in growing distrust and resentment among the population - was confirmed. This outcome can be considered to be endorsed by the lower share of respondents that tended to have trust in the Dutch government and politics in the autumn of 2015 than of 2008, as measured by the Eurobarometer.

The **second hypothesis** postulates that these developments are caused by the erosion of or disinvestment in what are referred to as the capabilities of persons and their human rights (social disinvestment). The participants referred to the increasing number of benefit regulations (bureaucracy) that contribute to and/or express the harsher social climate with respect to care support and income benefits. They also cited the complexity, the struggle against bureaucracy and the increasing impersonalisation that results in an increasingly harsh society.

The participants ascribed many of the changes to the social climate (caused by changing standards and values) to the politicians who have been implementing the spending cuts. Politicians largely determine the options available to citizens, they pointed out. Although there are individual differences, it must be concluded that many elements of the capabilities with respect to human rights have been weakened. The participants realised that in the situation at the time this study took place some of the human rights were being compromised. The question is then whether, and if so when, the bottom will be reached and both the personal resources and skills will be exhausted.

Participants more than occasionally dreamt of the mentality of the 50's to 70's, as well as leaving Rotterdam or the Netherlands. On the one hand the concern was expressed that the tide could no longer be turned and, on the other hand, that the social climate could not be allowed to get worse. The hope was also

expressed that the current system will exhaust itself and create scope for a new start for a more social and charitable society.

Participants converted this hope into deeds by taking part in this study and sharing their experiences on life in a precarious financial situation. During the meetings the participants offered each other help and exchanged tips. Understanding was developed for the various situations in which it was difficult for households to make ends meet. Last but not least, the participants were interested to take part in the follow-up study.

Appendix 1 Capabilities based on human rights

a1.1 Criteria for a 'decent' life

- The criteria are based on internationally accepted human rights and principles of equality.
- Decent is interpreted as freedom and possibility to choose to live in human dignity.

Criteria	Examples (to be considered based on vulnerable financial situation-
Adequate standard of living	My standard of living, including food and clothing, is adequate for me (and my family), as well as the access to social security/support, if needed, and especially, if there are dependent children in the household
Adequate standard of housing	My standard of housing is adequate for me (and my family), as well as the access to social security/support (housing allowances), , if needed, and especially, if there are dependent children in the household
Education and learning	I am able to access education and (to keep) learning
Productive and valued activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I undertake productive and activities - I work in just and favourable conditions, including a fair remuneration, a fair treatment during pregnancy and a health and safe place to work
Individual, family- and social life	I am able to influence my situation, the situation of my family and my social life
Participation, influence and voice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - I am able to have influence and voice by participating in the decision making of the society - As my neighbour I have equal access to public services, including infrastructure and services by the municipality
Health	I achieve the highest possible standard of physical and mental health
Legal security	I am equally being protected, as my neighbour, by rules and laws
Identity, expression and self-respect	I have an identity of my own and I can express myself, if necessary, and I have self-respect
Bodily integrity	<p>I have no fear that I will undergo individual or collective violence.</p> <p>Violence is described as a form of cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment</p>
Life	I find life worthwhile (the limitation are not such that ...) I will reach the 'normal' lifespan, because I do not have a bigger chance to be ill, neglected or injured

Source RE-InVEST draft Methodological Toolkit (2015: 14), elaboration of Vizard and Burchardt (2007), own elaboration

a1.2 Circle with criteria for a decent life: two examples of participants

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Social disinvestment and vulnerable groups in Europe in the aftermath of the financial crisis

The case of mental health care users in England

Joe Greener & Michael Lavalette

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 649447

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Executive summary

Summary of key findings

- This project applies a capabilities approach to explore the social damage caused by austerity to people suffering with mental distress.
- Those coping and managing with severe, lasting and ongoing mental health problems find themselves devoting considerable attention, time and effort to staying well. Surviving and handling day-to-day symptoms were at the front of people's minds and were more pressing than other goals such as employment or education.
- The group work uncovered three major areas within which austerity affected people's mental health. These were:
 - reducing benefit entitlements, lack of access to employment, under investment in already deprived communities and the flexibilisation of employment were all implicated in recent experiences of personal economic hardship. In certain cases, this entrenched experiences of social isolation;
 - the rolling back of provision in both mental health and social care services due to central and local government spending reductions had a direct influence on resources available for managing mental distress;
 - increasing conditionality through the use of assessment of eligibility reinforced feelings of shame and inadequacy and fear of not being seen as genuinely ill. Welfare transformation also negatively impacted on the relationship between service users and professionals, with welfare workers being seemingly more likely to treat people with suspicion.
- A range of capabilities was talked about by the group as important for managing levels of mental distress. These included both welfare services, provided through the social care and benefits system as well as mental healthcare, and sources of more informal relational factors such as family, friends and volunteering. Such was the diversity of examples given that data analysis drew four major principles which were seen as beneficial for improving the capabilities of those experiencing mental distress. It could be argued that day centre care best brings together these different principles under one roof:
 - *recognition of illness*. Having their mental health problems taken seriously by qualified professionals but also the wider community.
 - *opportunities to engage in therapeutic activities*. The research group felt that there were a whole range of activities, delivered by both formal mental health services and other informal resources existent in their communities, which they considered to be of therapeutic worth.
 - *empowered participation and resistance*. Contexts where people felt empowered to exercise real decision-making were valued. People also resisted the dominant politics of welfare by both actively constructing narratives which challenged welfare users as disingenuous and, in some cases, actively engaging in campaigning.
 - *security and safety*. People felt as though they needed spaces and places in their lives where they felt protected and sheltered from wider pressures. This was crucial during times of severe deterioration in their mental health.

Policy recommendations

- In overcoming the stigma and social seclusion often accompanying mental distress there is a need to challenge hegemonic constructions of the welfare user and revalue the contribution that people who are

out-of-work make to communities. This group of people fulfilled many social roles as carers, family members, activists, sports team members and volunteers, but still often felt inadequate.

- Dealing with mental health issues is a demanding task in itself, the freedom to engage with a range of different services and activities should be encouraged, especially in long term community based services rather than medicalised or individualised forms of support. This would include being free to be 'unwell' indefinitely and consequently resist the current 'work first' approach of policies. A capabilities analysis, however, would suggest that this also involves material investment in an infrastructure of services.
- Ensuring financial security through higher benefit entitlements, easier access to benefits, better regulation of loan companies, and better support finding work could help people with ongoing emotional or psychological difficulties.

Contents

- List of figures** **8**

- Introduction** **9**

- 1. Mental distress and Austerity** **11**
 - 1.1 Deteriorating access to material security 11
 - 1.2 Declining opportunities to access mental health support 12
 - 1.3 The strengthening of workfare principles across the welfare system 14

- 2. The participatory research approach** **16**
 - 2.1 Human Rights and Capability Approach 16
 - 2.2 Methods and Methodology 17

- 3. Biographies of austerity social policy and mental distress** **19**
 - 3.1 Ian's Story: Enforced Isolation and the 'Bedroom Tax' 19
 - 3.2 Agnes's story: Work Capability Assessments and deepening distress 20

- 4. Analysis** **23**
 - 4.1 Goals, hopes and aims: What is it that people experiencing mental distress want to do and be? 23
 - 4.2 Austerity and mental health: Enforcing poverty, eroding possibilities for recuperation and entrenching conditionality 24
 - 4.3 Improving the capabilities of people experiencing mental distress 28

- 5. Conclusion** **32**

- Bibliography** **33**

List of figures

Figure 1.1	Increase in wealth of the 1000 Wealthiest people in UK (1989-2016)	9
Figure 2.1	Merging of Knowledge	17

Introduction

‘Austerity’, a political and economic project geared towards reducing government public sector social spending, was presented to many populations of Europe as inevitable. After the global financial crisis of 2008 the population of England, and in many other European countries, have been subjected to a mainstream political narrative that sees reductions in state social spending as necessary to re-establishing and securing economic growth and security. Spending on welfare services, some of which support disabled, unemployed and sick people, have been consistently presented as a luxury that society can no longer afford. However, austerity has not been bad for everyone. Whilst Harrop and Reed (2015) estimate that 2 million more children in England will be living in poverty by 2030, if current policy trajectories remain the same, other studies have shown that the richest 1000 families in the UK have seen their wealth grow exponentially during the recession (Garside, 2015). The Sunday Times produces an annual ‘Rich List’ which plots the wealth of the 1,000 wealthiest people in the UK. Figure 1.1 shows the growth in their wealth over the period the Rich List has been running (1989-present)

Figure 1.1 Increase in wealth of the 1000 Wealthiest people in UK (1989-2016)

Source Sunday Times Rich List ,1989-2016

The richest 10% of UK population now control 45% of wealth while the bottom half of the economic strata control a meagre 8.7% (Office for National Statistics, 2015). The financial assistance provided to banks resulted in the national debt in the UK rising to 850 billion, enough to pay for the now supposedly inflated National Health Service for more than 8 years (Mendoza, 2015).

A cornerstone in this economic transformation has been a symbolic, discursive and divisive politics attempting to propagate an ‘anti-welfare common sense’ (Jensen & Tyler, 2015). Pressures on public services and benefit payments and the scarcity of better job opportunities has been blamed on excessive immigration and freeloading welfare ‘dependents’ while the financial system has largely escaped any serious critique. Not surprisingly, growing inequality, reduction in public services and an often-divisive political narrative has been accompanied with a general decline in levels of trust in political institutions in the UK and across Europe. For example, in 2007 across the EU, 57% of people claimed that they generally trusted the European Institutions whilst in 2013 this had fallen to only 31% (Eurobarometer 2013). In the UK, trust in the EU was only 19% in 2013. Distrust in both EU institutions and in national political processes has also arguably set the context for potentially the biggest political event to happen in the UK for decades: when the British public voted to leave the EU.

It is in this context of political crisis, rising inequality, reductions in spending on public sector services, mass welfare transformation and an insidious political discourse that this research takes place. The theoretical vehicles for understanding the impact of spending reductions and welfare reform on people with mental health problems is broadly a human rights perspective but pays special attention to the resources available to people to realise their objectives and life-plans (Sen, 2001). This report adds weight to other studies revealing how recent economic and social policy transformations have created a toxic environment for mental health in England (Barr *et al.*, 2015). The report sits within a broader body of literature focusing on mental distress as an experience which is clearly rooted to particular social, economic and political contexts (Psychologists Against Austerity 2016; Wilkinson & Pickett, 2010).

Based on qualitative research involving biographical interviews and focus groups the report explains some of the complex social and policy processes that have resulted in deteriorating experiences for mental health service users in Liverpool. The report will explore the major transformations that have intensified mental distress and diminished the potentialities for accessing assistance to resolve, cope with and overcome persistent mental health problems and shorter-term crises.

1. Mental distress and Austerity

Recent research has already begun to map out the direct effect that austerity, and the social policies associated with it, has on worsening or deteriorating mental health. In 2007, a World Health Organization report predicted that the economic crisis would have a serious impact on mental wellbeing across Europe (Wahlbeck *et al.*, 2007). Rising personal debt and poverty have been associated with rising mental distress across the literature (Gunnell *et al.*, 2015; O'Hara, 2007; Wahlbeck *et al.*, 2007). Mental health charity Mind published data indicating that half of the people who have called their helpline feeling suicidal because of money, housing or benefits issues (Mind, 2016). As well as an increasing risk of suicide, evidence shows that there has been a huge increase in the prescription of antidepressants. Donnelly (2014) reported information from the Health and Social Care Information Centre which showed that prescriptions for antidepressants rose by over 33% from 2013 to 2014.

It would be erroneous to conceptualise the current problem of mental distress at a societal level as something especially novel or as exclusively emerging from developments over the last few years. Nevertheless the reforms implemented by this and the previous government are clearly aimed at further entrenching, deepening and intensifying the attack on welfare systems and living standards further intensifying the pressures on people living with mental distress (Barr *et al.*, 2015; Psychologists Against Austerity, 2016). The aim of this brief literature review is to highlight the manner in which the political and economic context for living with psychological distress has changed under austerity. This review will highlight the following ways in which austerity and welfare transformations in the UK are influencing mental wellbeing through three main developments:

- *deteriorating access to material security*: precarious work, unemployment and deteriorating benefit payments are deepening and extending poverty and financial vulnerability;
- *declining opportunities to access mental health support*: the rolling back of formal mental health service provision, cuts to more local social care budgets and the wider disinvestment in often already materially deprived areas is constraining the capabilities available in communities to seek support for mental distress;
- *the strengthening of workfare principles across the welfare system*: various policy developments are reimagining what the welfare state 'is for'. These are not only imposing new forms of poverty but are also creating new social psychological pressures as people are expected to conform to narrower policy definitions of who is entitled to welfare support through new conditionality structures.

1.1 Deteriorating access to material security

Recent work done by Fitzpatrick *et al* (2016) for the Joseph Rowntree Foundation found that about 1.252 million people in the UK are currently living in destitution where they are unable to buy the essentials needed to eat, remain warm and ensure personal hygiene. This can be seen as indicative of worsening experiences of poverty since the global financial crisis. To understand the context of declining living standards in the UK, three mutually reinforcing sets of changes need to be analysed including the labour market, welfare state reform and rising costs of basic goods, such as housing.

Deteriorating pay is part of a longer term downward pressure on wages and working conditions associated with successive attempts to realise 'flexible' labour markets (Lansley & Mack, 2015; Mendoza, 2015). However, this process has consolidated further under austerity. The Enterprise and Regulatory Reform Act passed in 2013 is a prime example of the buttressing of insecure and precarious working patterns through amendments to current employment legislation (Mendoza, 2015: 126-7). Amongst other developments, the

Act also means that an individual who wishes to lodge an appeal after losing their job at Tribunal now incur much greater costs (as much as £1,200 to lodge a complaint). If employees have wages withheld, are dismissed without good reason or are subject to other injustices, they risk losing a considerable amount of money if appeals are unsuccessful. Part of this deregulation in the labour market has been the huge rise in the number of employees working in what are informally known as ‘zero hour contracts’. The possibility for employment relations to be organised along this line has existed for decades but the sharp rise under austerity reveals some of the coordinated ways in which other policies are imposing precarity. The Resolution Foundation (2013) found that people on zero hour contracts have a lower gross weekly pay of £236 compared to those not on zero hours which is £482 per week. The Office for National Statistics (2014) reported that some 1.4 million workers were in contractual arrangements which had no guaranteed hours.

Other changes to the labour market which are emblematic of the normalising of casualised, temporary and insecure work include the rise in low paid self-employment (Lansley and Mack 2014), relatively low skill apprentice schemes with no guaranteed end job (Ofsted 2015), cuts in public sector pay (O’Hara 2015) and the return of totally unpaid employment through Mandatory Work Placements. The impact of this collection of reforms is increasing financial insecurity. John Hills’ (2015) recent research aimed to break down the pervasive myth of a workless, unemployed and welfare-dependent population, and presents evidence of the extent to which those at the bottom of the income structure have to juggle a number of different work commitments and require (insufficient) welfare support to plug gaps in periods of unemployment, lack of access to satisfactory hours and changing caring responsibilities and family structure.

Economic insecurity has also been organised through transformations in the forms of support available from the welfare state. Mary O’Hara described the support available to people with longer term needs as ‘a complex package of discriminatory reforms’ (2015: 145). A more detailed analysis of these changes is discussed later but it is worth drawing out here that two pillars of this assemblage of reforms are producing a decline in living standards. Firstly, disempowering strategies embodying new forms of means testing are attempting to strip people of existing benefit payments. Secondly, there is a more generalised programme of cuts to direct financial benefits including reductions in Jobseekers Allowance, the removal of the Independent Living Fund and Disability Living Allowance and the movement to Universal Credit (O’Hara 2015: 158).

Housing has also become a topic mired in controversy and is central to understanding rising living costs in England. Through long term and tandem processes of disinvestment in state-driven social housing programmes (Mendoza, 2015: 58-59) and the financialisation of the housing market in England (New Economics Foundation, 2016) problems of rising rent and limited supply of housing define the current market. In 2015, house prices rose by 4.5% while average pay only increased 2% (Meyer & Stuart 2015). Coupled with this generalised crisis in costs and supply, there has been the introduction of the ‘under occupancy charge’, more commonly known as the ‘bedroom tax’, for households where there are ‘extra’ bedrooms in social housing. This has forced many households in social housing to give back part of their benefit derived income to the state if there are more bedrooms than occupants in a given property.

Under the guise of austerity, the last two governments have deliberately orchestrated a set of labour market and welfare reforms which impose new forms of financial insecurity and deprivation onto households and individuals. As a result, people are being forced to turn to the debt and personal financing industry based on exorbitant interest rates and catering for the needs of low income individuals who have insecure, fluctuating and unpredictable pay packets. Indebtedness has been shown to have a complex interrelationship with anxiety and depression (Davies *et al* 2015).

1.2 Declining opportunities to access mental health support

As well as rising financial insecurity, mental health problems are being exacerbated by direct cuts to mental health treatment and more generic social care services. Recent research by Community Care and the BBC obtained freedom of information requests from 43 of the 56 Mental Health Trusts in England revealing a reduction in funding of 8.25% in real terms (McNicoll 2015). In cash terms, the amount has diminished from £6.7bn in 2010-11 to an estimated £6.6bn in 2014-15. The same research has shown that community

mental health teams have seen a funding decrease of 5%. The numbers of beds in mental health hospitals has also diminished. Care Quality Commission recently warned that Approved Mental Health Practitioners (AHMPs) are being put under extreme pressure due to a lack of beds. Andy McNicoll reported that the total number of beds in mental health hospitals that has been closed since April 2011 and 2014 is 2,100 (McNicoll, 2014). Mental health hospitals in some trusts are running at 120% capacity, despite the Royal College of Psychiatrists recommending an occupancy rate of 85% (RCPsych 2011). There have even been seven suicides and one homicide directly linked to a lack of beds in hospital facilities (McNicoll, 2014a). Under the Mental Health Act in England, people can be detained in hospitals against their will if they are deemed to be a risk to themselves or others. Data from the Health and Social Care Information Centre (quoted by McNicoll, 2014b) showed that in 2015 these detentions were up by 10% from the previous year, with some suggesting that professionals were resorting to enforced detentions in order to find patients hospital beds (BBC, 2015).

Pressures on treatment services have meant that a breakdown in a person's mental health has become a more frightening and traumatic experience. Not only have hospitals become overcrowded but Trusts are increasingly resorting to out-of-area treatment options (Buchanan, 2014). This involves transporting people experiencing a downward spiralling situation in their mental health, sometimes hundreds of miles, to other facilities. The experience of transport during the initial crisis can be extremely disturbing, but can also make visiting by family and friends more problematic in the months and weeks after.

In England and the rest of the UK, social care and health care are separate policy fields with distinct modes of operation, legislative frameworks and funding sources. Social care is geared towards catering for longer term illness or disability. Whilst healthcare is largely funded through central taxation, social care is financed through local councils who raise taxes within their region and receive a proportion of funding from central government. To map out the cuts which have affected mental health services, therefore, means including Local Authority budgets, as well as the NHS mental health provision. Since the start of austerity UK local council budgets have been seriously affected. Under the previous coalition government, whose term ended in May 2015, local councils saw a 40% decrease in their central government funding. But these cuts have not been applied uniformly, indeed, it has been the most economically deprived councils which have suffered the biggest cuts. A recent study found that social care spending from 2010 to 2015 in the most well off councils has actually risen by 8% whilst it has fallen by 14% in the most economically deprived (Hastings *et al* 2015). Liverpool, where this research took place, is in the list of top ten most deprived areas in England (Department for Communities and Local Government 2015) with the latest child poverty rates indicating 32.1% of children in the city live in poverty (the majority in working households). Yet Liverpool has experienced exceptional reductions in central government funding. By 2017 Liverpool City Council will have had to make £329 million in savings which represents a 58% cut in funding in real terms since 2010 (Brindle, 2015).

Yet the cuts in mental health funding is running in tandem with transformations in how the nature of mental health support is viewed in terms of its aims, scope and foundational principles. Austerity has proved to be a convenient economic cover for promoting ideological changes. For instance, reductions in funding for community care can be neatly accompanied with more individualised interventions. Previous services have often delivered ongoing support in day centres, day hospitals and other community settings which could last months and even years. This sort of service created opportunities for long term care for those with persistent mental health problems (Bell, 2013). Yet many of these services are being replaced with alternative short-term provision with an emphasis on 'recovery'. In the Liverpool area some services previously geared towards the long term community support have been transformed into 'reablement' focused services, aimed at delivering six week intensive recovery (Carter 2016). Hospitals and day centres are moving services towards short-term recuperation models where patients are asked to resolve, often long term mental health problems, in very small periods of time.

There is also an individualising undercurrent to these transformations, where self-recovery and independence are valued above other possible views on how mental health services should be delivered. This 'responsibilisation' agenda seems to fit neatly with the context of declining funding (Brown and Baker 2012).

A model of mental health where full recovery is not only possible, but is also best achieved by the individual taking responsibility for their own health legitimates reducing or even eliminating the network of community based professionals and services.

1.3 The strengthening of workfare principles across the welfare system

As we have seen the infrastructure for mental wellbeing has been significantly dismantled and there has been a rise in levels of poverty. Lastly we consider how changes to the driving principles of the welfare state are placing new stresses, strains and anxieties on people with persistent mental health issues. This is discussed separately to cuts in living standards and mental health services in order to capture how people who use public services are increasingly treated with more suspicion and subjected to greater scrutiny regarding their entitlement to support.

Stigma, although a contested concept in social sciences, conceptualises the way that an individual's identity can be called into question, devalued and undermined with that person being seen by those around them as less than human in some way. Stigma is an inherently social concept as it is concerned with the ways that a person or a community of people are treated by others as a result of having a tarnished character. What characteristics, traits and groups of people are stigmatised can change between time and place and is therefore relational in that it is determined by specific social, cultural and political contexts. Pescosolido and Martin (2007), in their in-depth review of stigma and mental health, argue that the concept is best seen as working at a variety of different ontological levels. This means that analysing the concept requires an analysis of the full range of social, cultural, political and psychological processes at play in the lived experience of stigma. For this study, we suggest that the experience of stigma needs to be understood in a changing political climate whereby people who use certain public services or benefits, such as those relating to being out of work due to disability or infirmity, are being understood and treated differently, in turn shaping, not only how they are viewed by others around them, but also how they understand themselves.

The data presented in the following sections shows how recent welfare reform has intensified a longer term transformation in how citizenship and rights are understood. The changes implemented through the Welfare Reform Act 2012 are complex but have initiated new forms of assessing eligibility to benefits. The Act introduced, amongst other things, the Work Capability Assessment (WCA) which means that people who have been unemployed due to illness or disability are now required to undergo a test, delivered by private sector organisation, to determine whether they have entitlement to long term financial assistance. This Act also brought in a whole new system of sanctions for people who are claiming Jobseekers Allowance if they fail to meet the requirements imposed on them, such as if they are late for meetings or training or if they fail to apply for the number of jobs that is expected.

Existing research has shown how changes to the ways welfare is delivered can impact on those with mental distress and how they understand themselves. Henderson *et al* (2012) found widespread evidence that discrimination was a common experience amongst people with mental health problems in the UK. They also found a sharp rise in experiences of discrimination in 2012, which they attributed to austerity. Hansen *et al's* (2014) ethnographic study explored the effects of the 1996 welfare reforms in America and found that stigma was experienced in new ways as a result of the changing context of welfare delivery. The 1996 changes to welfare in the US are very similar to those pushed through in the Welfare Reform Act 2012 in the UK. These 'disentitling strategies' (Wacquant 2009: 91) in which those claiming benefits are consistently required to prove their 'sick' status represents a change in the experience of stigma. Hansen *et al* (2014) claimed recently that people who are in receipt of benefit payments may find themselves in a contradictory situation where on the one hand adopting a label of mental pathology entitles them to services, but on the other, this label itself is often felt to be a stigmatising social role to adopt.

As Link and Phelan (2014) argued, social and economic power are crucial for understanding how stigma-related practices are played out in daily life. As discussed in the introduction, austerity is both a political and economic project that has located the blame for Britain's debt and deficit crisis with particular marginalised groups. Whilst the logic which underpins policy reform has been the need to realise the fiscally lean and

globally competitive economy, there are indications that recent welfare reforms have actually cost the state more money than it has saved. Barr *et al* (2015), using data from the National Labour Force survey, found there to be no evidence that reassessing people who had been out of work for long periods actually increased the likelihood of finding employment. Similarly, Wright (2016) reporting findings from the National Audit Office in *The Independent*, showed that the Department for Work and Pensions had plans to hand over £1.6bn to private contractors to carry out the controversial WCA whilst the savings in benefit payments are only expected to be around £1bn.

Deeming (2015) argues that social policy in many states has moved towards an ‘active’ stance involving a reformulation of citizenship. Policy and practices no longer emphasise the rights of individuals and instead obligation and responsibility now drive welfare programmes. Poverty and unemployment are constructed differently and re-‘problematized’ (Deeming 2015) as the result of individual failure, rather than systemic processes to do with job availability and inadequate welfare. Part of this neoliberal trajectory has been to visualise the welfare state as actually reproducing deprivation through dependency, rather than as a form of protection from the ills of market society. Policy makers are increasingly concerned with coercing individuals into employment, and into accepting low paid, insecure and unrewarding work. It bolsters a more pervasive political and cultural project attempting to gain public support for an ‘anti-welfare common sense’ (Jensen and Tyler 2015). Through insidiously crafting a welfare state guided by the idea that many people may indeed be disingenuous scroungers living a lavish lifestyle from the hard earned coffers of the taxpayer, governments manufacture support for ‘innovations’ in social policy aiming to dispossess vulnerable people of the resources they rely on. This simultaneously fortifies the idea that welfare claimants might be culpable for the financial crisis whilst maintaining impunity from scrutiny for late financialised capitalism.

Psychological and emotional states are fundamentally relational in that they develop in congruence with how individuals are treated, reacted to and engage with the communities they live in. Putting the dynamics of power and inequality central in an analysis of social policy and daily life is critical for understanding current experiences of mental distress.

2. The participatory research approach

2.1 Human Rights and Capability Approach

RE-InVEST aims at investigating the philosophical, institutional and empirical foundations of an inclusive Europe of solidarity and trust. To this end it draws on capability and human rights based participatory approaches.

Human Rights are universally agreed basic standards that aim to ensure that every person is treated with dignity and respect; they are interdependent and indivisible, they belong to all people without discrimination. Usually set out in law, through international or regional treaties, or national legislation, they form a legal statement of universally accepted principles of how the state should treat its citizens and other people living within its jurisdiction. In this project, however, we aim to widen the notion of rights beyond those which are formally prescribed in international treaties and national and supranational legal frameworks. As Ted Benton (2006) notes, scepticism of conventional liberal rights has arisen because it tends to emphasise ‘formal’ rights. In other words the fact that in theory different individuals are permitted to follow their aims. In practice, consideration of how social structures deny people access to opportunities is also required, and a legalistic view of human rights is unable to achieve this. Analysis needs to focus on what people are actually able to do and to be in their everyday lives, rather than what the official sanctioned choices are. As Benton expands:

‘The life-plans we are able to devise are constrained and shaped both by our cultural horizons and by our actual placing in society, with its current pattern of fulfilments and frustrations. But in each case our ability to live out whatever plan we might devise will be conditioned by our access or lack of access to resources.’ (2006: 25)

As a solution to this problem with rights-based approaches this study employs a capabilities approach. The capabilities approach, developed by Amartya Sen (2001), argues that thinking through human development requires consideration of what resources are available to people. What are people actually able to do and to be in given social, political and economic context? This tends to open up analysis to whole range of different aspects of the social and political system to explore the full range of institutions present in a given society or locale. For Sen then, a ‘capability’ is the presence of a particular opportunity such as the existence of a local education system or the fact that homosexuality is permitted and tolerated. A ‘functioning’, on the other hand, in Sen’s language, is where a person achieves a particular state of being or activity (Burchardt, 2004). So that would be the emotional, psychological and technical capacities developed in the course of attending a educational institution. Analysis of capabilities requires exploring the full range of potentials and possibilities available to a person, while a functioning is what they actually manage to achieve and become in the course of accessing capabilities.

For assessing the capabilities of vulnerable people RE-InVEST aims to place their voices centrally within the research process. Their participation is fostered by relying on participatory action research that directly results in policy recommendations. Participatory action research views participants as co-researchers who have special knowledge about their own situation. Hence they are not only asked or interviewed on their views but take part in research by engaging in, examining, interpreting, and reflecting on their own social world, shaping their sense of identity.

Accordingly, the approach attempts to encourage the coming together of different forms of knowledge. Crucial for this kind of knowledge generation is the ‘merging’ or ‘crossing of knowledge’ that comes from

three parts: scientific knowledge as gained by researchers; knowledge which those who have suffered injustice have, from their first-hand experience; and the knowledge of those who work among and with these victims (Figure 2.1).

These are the core elements of the Participatory Action Human Rights and Capability Approach (PAHRCA) developed in RE-InVEST. PAHRCA entails seven steps (Toolkit, 44-45):

1. Identify and meet partner NGO/gatekeeper,
2. Preliminary ‘meet ups’ (for trust building if necessary),
3. First meeting with participants – trust building,
4. Developmental: implement developmental human rights & capability approach,
5. Inquiry/data gathering,
6. Identifying patterns (key issues and themes of concern to the group) and
7. Undertake action/outcome using one or combination of approaches.

Figure 2.1 Merging of Knowledge

2.2 Methods and Methodology

In recruiting respondents we exploited existing links between a university department that the researchers were based in and a local non-profit welfare providing organisation, Person Shaped Support (PSS). In conjunction with PSS the department had an existing service user group who help to deliver training, select candidates for degrees and inform the design of courses. Many of the members of the existing service user group self-identify as having a mental health problem and are in regular contact with mental health services. Two extra participants were also recruited in order to increase the size of the group. The current PSS group does have an overrepresentation of women members but some males were included. There were 13 members of the group with a reasonable age spread, although ethnically there was little diversity with all respondents being white British or Irish. There was also a gender bias in favour of women with 9 females and 4 men. One worker from PSS also participated in the meetings who is a fully qualified and registered social worker. This was partly to ensure that there was support available if any difficult issues arose for individuals in the group and to foster the merging of knowledge.

There were six research meetings altogether and the table below gives a synopsis of the first four meetings. The sixth meeting is not discussed as this was largely a planning meeting to discuss the public event that took place which was one of the outcomes of the research. The research meetings were an attempt to operationalise the different strands of the methodology discussed above and in particular intended to promote a merging of professional, academic and lay knowledge.

As well as the six research meetings there were two more in-depth biographical interviews conducted with two of the participants. The two individuals were selected mainly because their stories spoke directly to two austerity-related policies: WCAs and the under-occupancy charge.

Session one – introduction and ‘austerity snakes’	In this session the researchers explained the aims of WP3 and the wider RE-InVEST project. Each member of the group was asked to briefly introduce themselves and then blank ‘snakes’, essentially timelines, were handed to each participant. Group members were asked to fill in the snake by noting major life events since 2007. We asked them to include both personal changes in family life, changes in employment, welfare services and benefits they had received or lost and also major changes in their mental health, including periods of crisis and periods where they felt they were improving. After the snakes had been completed, a group discussion was had regarding what they felt about the exercise of reflecting on their lives since the financial crisis.
Session two – human rights	This meeting kicked off with an overview of what human rights are and, in particular, a summary of the UK Human Rights Act 1998. After this the group were asked to fill in a worksheet in which they highlighted what rights they felt were most important and whether they thought that they had experienced specific instances of human rights abuses. After this a group discussion was had where we collectively worked through the Human Rights Act 1998 to explore which rights were relevant to people experiencing mental distress and welfare service users.
Session three – capabilities	This meeting kicked off with an overview the capabilities approach. In operationalising the capabilities approach we focused on two issues. Firstly, we asked respondents to fill a worksheet reflecting on the full range of factors in their life, both in terms of informal support networks, welfare services and hobbies, which helped them in managing mental distress. Secondly, we asked them to think about what their current life plans were, how these could be achieved and what barriers they faced.
Session four – the politics of austerity	Given that in the first 4 sessions so much conversation had orientated around the ways that interactions with welfare professionals and other people in the community were often harsh, stigmatising and degrading, the group felt it was important to look further at the ways others depicted welfare users. For this session the researchers chose a selection of newspaper headings which reported negatively on disabled people and benefit recipients. These were shown to provoke a general debate about social policy reform and the political dimensions of austerity.
Session five – taking action	The action component of the research had been discussed at various points in previous meetings but in this session it was agreed that we would develop, as a group, a photo exhibition. The group were given cameras and then took photos which they felt spoke to two main themes. Firstly, what experiences in their everyday life result in deteriorating mental health and, secondly, what are the resources in their communities which allow them to survive in spite of mental distress and other forms of marginalisation.

3. Biographies of austerity social policy and mental distress

3.1 Ian's Story: Enforced Isolation and the 'Bedroom Tax'

One policy implemented through the Government's austerity agenda known to have had a socially damaging impact has been the under occupancy charge, more commonly known as the 'bedroom tax.' One of the participant's of this study, given the name Ian here, had been gravely affected by this policy change.

Ian has a long history of dealing with mental health problems. Serious problems first seemed to set in in around his mid-to-late 20s. Growing up in a deprived area of Liverpool in a large family, Ian felt that this upbringing set the context for later onset of more gravely deteriorating mental and emotional state. In one incident, when Ian was only a teenager, he was assaulted badly by a stranger who wrongly believed he had stolen a bicycle.

Ian had been relatively successful in finding work in his early life and had enjoyed being able to help his Mum out with extra cash. He also felt, however, that he could have had a better start in life, and had wished that his father had played a more significant role in his life by encouraging him to think about his long term employability.

Yet, Ian experienced a number of more traumatic events in later life which shaped the emergence of more severe forms of mental distress. Ian's mother, whom he had had a very close relationship with, died from cancer. Ian lived only a few doors away from his mother. This seemed to have brought many emotional and psychological issues to the fore for him. In the years leading up to his mother's death and in the period after, Ian had developed severe problems with agoraphobia, anxiety and panic attacks.

'To be honest with you, I wouldn't say I was depressed years ago, it was more the anxiety and the panic attacks I had, everything just happened and I ended up getting a house next door but one to my Mum. But I think it was seeing what my Mum went through that really affected me. Then, because I was next door but one to my Mum, it was like everything got left to me. 'Oh Ian's there, he'll do it'. I would do it all again if I could now. But everything got on top of me and I just broke down. Started having bad anxiety, really really bad, severe panic attacks.'

Ian also developed agoraphobia around this time and developed an inability to leave his house. After Ian's mother's death he remained in the same property but around 2011 he became subject to the Government's under occupancy charge. This disorienting strategy imposes a charge onto people who are considered to be under-occupying social housing. For example, if a person is on their own, as Ian was, then there is a charge for every extra bedroom in the property. This extra payment is to be paid, in many cases, directly out of people's already meagre benefits. This forced Ian out of his home and out of his community.

'Because of the bedroom tax I had to move my home and it was like a safe house and that's really affected me. I'm in a one bed flat now and its out of my area, for starters. I'm already stressed out to death. It's just little things, like you don't see your family and your friends. Just little things like you've got to change your GP where your GP knows all your history. It's like starting again.'

The bedroom tax had resulted in a direct and severe deterioration in his mental health by both increasing his general anxiety and removing some of the strategies he had available to him for coping with agoraphobia. For example, in his previous property he had been able to stand outside his house and see people he knew, which he felt limited the isolation he experienced.

Despite Ian's ongoing psychological problems he still shows considerable capacity to seek various forms of support, engage in the community and support others in a similar situation. Attending a local football scheme for people with mental health problems was clearly an excellent source of socialising for Ian and had a therapeutic impact:

I've got six or seven people going to this now (community football initiative) who are suffering with mental health and they'd never heard through services, they heard through me, no psychiatrists, no doctors nothing referred them ... see when I play, I give everything, that's why I am one of the best there at the time, but my head, everything just clears in my head for that hour or 2 hours ... you can go there with 150 things going in your head once you start but as soon as you finish its back.'

In the past Ian had also relied heavily on a day centre for care and support and is currently visited weekly by a psychiatric nurse, both of these help him. Yet, in many ways Ian feels the forms of support he is offered relied on were lacking in intensity and failed to really engage with his issues seriously. He had been waiting 18 months for Cognitive Behavioural Therapy at the time of the research. On another occasion he waited over 3 months for an appointment with a psychiatrist which lasted 10 minutes.

Ian's story uncovers the brutality of Government austerity agenda in relation to social housing. *Psychologists Against Austerity* (PAA 2016: 1) have argued that a key defining 'ailment' of austerity has been 'isolation and loneliness.' Ian, as just discussed, was able to resist and challenge some aspects of the mental health system, contesting certain pharmaceutical prescriptions and making use of opportunities in the community. However, social dislocation caused by the move out of his area reinforced feelings of shame, abjection and remoteness. Ian's experiences shows just how damaging the bedroom tax has been for some individuals:

Where I've moved to I'm really isolated, I feel like going worse now and I'm taking a backwards step, I'm starting to go ill again ... Since I have moved and I'm totally isolated and all I can do is sit in my little kitchen for 9 or 10 hours and I have to admit that suicidal thoughts have come into my head more in the last year than in the last 10 years of being ill. And I still think it's because I don't see a face, I don't see anyone. Without the day centres I wouldn't be here. I know for a fact that I would not be here ... you try and sit in that corner over there for 10 hours, you're going to start thinking and thinking and thinking. I mean I don't see anyone. At least when I was in the house and I did start getting down I could go and stand by the front door and you would see someone walk past and have a chat. But where I am now, there's nothing.'

3.2 Agnes's story: Work Capability Assessments and deepening distress

A further controversial developments in English social policy in recent years has been the 'work capability test' undertaken, initially, by the French company ATOS. ATOS obtained a government contract to assess people's suitability for work or whether their physical and/or mental health was such that they were incapable of holding down regular employment and would, therefore, qualify for various out of work benefits. Agnes's story reveals how deeply distressing it can be to go through the 'ATOS test' (as it has become more commonly known by service users).

Agnes is, by profession, a qualified teacher. Initially a PE teacher, she moved into 'informal education' through Youth and Community Work in the 1980s. In 1989 her husband died leaving her on her own to support two young children. At that stage she retrained as a primary teacher as the hours could be combined with her caring responsibilities.

However, after she completed her re-training she developed a medical problem (associated with her voice) which meant she was unable to work as a teacher any longer. She looked at possibly working part-time but this was also ruled out. So by the late 1990s she retired through ill-health and got a small work pension. She also qualified for incapacity benefit. The small pension and the incapacity benefit together didn't provide much but she was able to manage. But she would rather be working: 'I just felt as though I was thrown on the scrap heap'

Over the next few years Agnes developed some other medical conditions: she had bowel problems and suffered from incontinence, she had a hysterectomy, appendicitis and the removal of her appendix, she had a shoulder operation and spinal problems. As a result she was on strong medication and suffered with

depression. Her mental health problems were to become more sustained, however, as a result of the emotional turmoil and stress brought on by her experience of the 'ATOS test'.

As Agnes says, things weren't too bad 'until 2011 when ESA [Employment Support Allowance] came along.' With ESA Agnes found herself having to undergo a work capability test. 'Dear old Atos healthcare. They send you a letter, a questionnaire, so you fill that in and then they call you up for a medical'

Agnes went for her first medical assessment in 2011. She was unused to such tests and, like many people, wanted to 'put on a good show'. She wanted to show that she was trying to manage her life and her difficulties and took supporting medical evidence that explained the extent of her physical problems. As she said: 'you go to the medical and you try and do your best ... but [as she noted ruefully] that's the wrong thing to do.' She described her experience:

'Well you're sitting with a lady behind a desk and she is asking questions about what you do each day and at the time my mum had been diagnosed with dementia so she was my focus. ... So you say what you do and blab-de-blab and I took with me letters from consultants, from the spinal unit, from gastroenterology and other places. [But] they didn't ask for any supportive information. They then said they would like to do a physical examination, move you, this type of thing [raises arms]. They said get on the couch, so she said 'would you like help?' So I said 'no, just leave me, I can get on myself in my own way.' You know, I've got disc problems, I needed a new replacement so I had to put my bad leg first you know, so when I came off [I would lead] with my good leg.'

And then she got the report:

'Needed no assistance', could do this with no problem. 'Answered questions directly', 'looked at the person who is asking the questions', that's only manners isn't it? I was marked down because I was smart appearance. ... They twist your words and when I got the letter to say there's nothing wrong with you I was distraught. For many reasons, the first reason was that my income went down by £300 a month.'

Agnes lost all her benefits. She was forced to live on her small occupational pension. She quickly went through her savings and her mental health deteriorated dramatically.

She went to the voluntary sector organization the Citizen's Advice Bureau for help. But, because she was a home owner (and the value of her property was more than £100,000) she did not qualify for any support from them.

Eventually she was directed to Merseyside Welfare Rights office. They helped her appeal the ATOS decision. The Welfare Rights office said 'appeal on physical grounds, not mental health grounds, they said, because they told me 'you've got enough physical things wrong with you, so you should be OK'

Over 50% of appeals against ESA decisions are successful in England (Stone 2016). Agnes told us that, this time, she was more careful about how she answered the questions.

'I had all the paper work [from the initial test] so I knew I was marked down for being of smart appearance, so at the appeal I didn't go of smart appearance. I took my cousin with me, and in the meantime my mum had died and she died like three weeks before so I went in and there was a legal guy and a doctor, in this big room, he was there and this woman about 15 yards away, right down the other end of the room. And you're behind a desk, you have to stand up, and I said well 'I can't stand up', I said 'do you mind if I lean on the table?' 'No that's ok'. So she started asking me all these questions and I told her. She accused me of being my mum's fulltime career, but ... I wasn't able to care for my mum, I had to put my mum in a care home and that's one of the worst things that anybody's got to do. Your mum looks after you and when it's time for her to be looked after you can't do it. ... She talked about other things that I had wrong with me. Well do you go to this clinic, I said "no, I go and see the consultant." I have bowel problems and I have incontinence and she asked "do you go to the incontinence clinic?" and I said "no I don't, I go and see Mr. G--- the consultant and I see the stoma nurse." "Oh so you don't go there, so you're not incontinent then", you know and she was just horrible.'

They rejected her appeal.

Distraught Agnes went back to Welfare Rights who persuaded her to make a fresh claim. This time Agnes knew she had to emphasise her difficulties in the assessment.

I filled the form in. Then I had to go for a medical, another atos assessment. So I didn't wash my hair for a week, I went in the clothes that I do my gardening in, I took somebody with me and I hired a wheelchair from the red cross, so I got her to push me in the wheelchair. So we went in and this was a completely different thing, whether the wheelchair did it, I don't know. The lady took a chair from behind her desk and placed it there, and said right can you tell me, and I said I applied once, so I told her the story and she was horrified, she said I can't believe that you've been treated like that, I said 'well I've no reason to lie'. So the next thing is the, oh I've qualified.'

At last Agnes thought she would get her benefit support back. But the changing nature of benefit provision meant that she was in for another shock. Because she didn't have enough national insurance payments (because she had been retired early from work) she was now assessed under the means tested benefit rules. She submitted two years of bank statements but her savings (though now largely spent), her home and the fact that she had supported her son financially for a few months were used to rule out any support.

Nobody tells you when you start off that the actual benefit is, at the end of the day, means tested. Well where is the logic in that. You know it is a health benefit. You're either ill or you're not ill. And that process made me more ill. [It made my mental health much worse] Emotionally I was a wreck, because all these things were traumatic, they were traumatic events. ... I didn't know, you know, if my savings went, if I could pay my bills; luckily the savings lasted until I was 62 and a half and I got my old age pension [State pension].'

Agnes's story reveals the vindictive nature of the work capability assessment tests. Their aim, as Agnes states, 'is to save money and get vulnerable people off benefits'. But worse than this, the process makes vulnerable people more ill, it undermines their social rights of citizenship and puts barriers in place which undermine people's capabilities and ability to engage, even in limited ways, in the social life of the community.

4. Analysis

4.1 Goals, hopes and aims: What is it that people experiencing mental distress want to do and be?

Part of the uniqueness of the capabilities approach, arguably, is it puts life plans, aims and objectives first and foremost in any analysis of the power or failure of social systems to promote social justice (Brunner and Watson; Burchardt 2004; Sen 2001). Capabilities are seen to be those opportunities that are available to people in a given context, while functionings are the actual achievements that result as a consequence.

One of the tasks given to the group was to identify what they felt were their long and short term aspirations. However, this can be conceptually difficult in relation to mental distress for a number of reasons. Firstly, mental distress is often intertwined with people's life, in its entirety, so any step forward in terms of personal relationships, educational or employment experiences, improvements in physical health and so on, can all potentially, by consequence, improve the experience of mental health. Secondly mental distress is both enigmatic and deep-rooted. Any individual's psychological and emotional wellbeing is constantly shifting but exactly what leads to improvements and what to deterioration is not stable or predictable. Lastly, what professionals feel is beneficial and positive might not actually be what service users feel is most supportive. This sort of problem is embodied in the notion of 'recovery' (Anthony, 1993). The term is widely thought by service user movements to have some traction when it first appeared as a potential concept for driving positive change (Wallcraft 2005). However, there is a tension between conceptions of recovery developed by service user/survivor movements and clinical models utilised by mental health professionals (Secker et al, 2002). The latter tend to biomedicalise mental health, promoting simplistic ideas that distress is an easily categorised illness that can then be 'treated' through pharmaceutical and psychological intervention. Alongside this, there has been a tendency to use models of recovery which emphasise forms of individual responsibility (Harper and Speed, 2012). A recent service user led activist movement, Recovery in the Bin (Recovery in the Bin 2016), have argued that 'recovery' became colonised by various nefarious interests and reshaped to meet the aims of punitive welfare agencies.

It cannot be assumed that people with mental health problems have overcoming their diagnosis at the forefront of their minds when considering their life plans and options. For some in the group getting well, staying well and surviving was put before many other life goals and aims. As Peter described when the group were reflecting on where they would be in 5 years, he wanted to put most of focus onto staying 'well':

'The last 5 years since those three admissions (to psychiatric hospitals) I have just been trying to rebuild and give myself enough support and care from people around me from people who love me and recognise those things ...In 5 years time I hope I'm still alive, I hope have a decent standard of living, I hope I haven't had any more episodes in the next 5 years, I hope I can be involved with people whether that's a job I can cope with or just having friends and family around me, or volunteering that would be great, whatever it is, that's all I want, that would be great.'

Furthermore some in the group felt that true recovery was not possible. As Rob said, 'I don't think you can ever recover ...You might think you're getting better but then you just hit rock bottom again, out of the blue.' All told a story of how their wellbeing had continually revolved between periods where it was significantly better and other periods when their emotional state deteriorated dramatically, often with the onset of intense and frightening symptoms.

As a result of the periodic, fluctuating nature of mental wellbeing, analysing the capabilities of people with mental distress and how these have been damaged under austerity requires a nuanced analysis of the full range of dynamics helping and hindering mental wellbeing. The rest of the report focuses on the full range

of life-world factors that the group felt were important for coping and managing with mental health, and is not intended to be a crass claim that offers solutions to the current mental health crisis through a collection of neat and tidy policy recommendations. Our more tentative claim is that some policy manifestations of the austerity project are directly impacting on people's mental wellbeing but also that it is possible to identify the forms of assistance that are most useful for enhancing people's capabilities.

4.2 Austerity and mental health: Enforcing poverty, eroding possibilities for recuperation and entrenching conditionality

Unjust outcomes for people with ongoing mental health difficulties emerge from a range of structural configurations of discrimination, many of which unambiguously predate the current austerity phase of social policy. From this research, however, there was a clear indication that recent changes seem to have had a direct impact on people's capacity to manage their mental health problems, sometimes creating new sources of distress. There are three main dimensions to this. First, the rolling back of sources of assistance, including day centre provision and greater difficulty accessing other mental health services. Second, increased problems with financial and material poverty including difficulties with access to and conditions within the labour market. Last, heightened experiences of stigma as people were required to go through new hurdles to remain eligible for support.

The group described growing financial hardship under austerity, which often placed growing strains on both people's emotional state and their family life more generally. Kay described how brutal the benefit system had become in recent years and the pressure of paying the under occupancy charge:

*I went to the bank to get my money out and all I had was 8 pounds. I rang them **(the DWP)** and they told me that they had stopped payments because I owed them money from 7 years ago. It turned out that they couldn't change it for six weeks ... When I told the benefits officer that I have a disabled son and asked her how I was supposed to live for the next weeks she said "you can always go to the foodbank.". I said "pardon" ... And it was like, I am in a situation now, I've got bedroom tax bounding me, and it's mounting up. So I am going to have to apply to the water board to have any money left squashed off, at that point I owed 3000 pound to the water board and they squashed 2000 pound off, that was two years ago. I applied to the gas board for EON to squash anything off that bill. I applied for a bus pass ... So I've had to go through all this rigmarole to get things wiped off to keep my home. They **(the DWP)** sent me letter saying I owed them £105 for bedroom tax and they're going to take me to court ... How does it feel when you write a letter saying you're going to take my home away for £105? How many people have lost their homes through the bedroom tax? Do they realise how vulnerable people are?'*

As well as increased material disadvantage being imposed through benefit cuts and new charges, Sophie here describes the pressures emanating from her husband's precarious employment situation on a zero-hours contract.

The only work my husband has now is ... agency work. You can't live on agency work, you can't live on zero hours, you've got to know what you've got coming in. You've got to know that you can pay your mortgage, you're main debt, you're main priorities ... One day my husband was out shopping with me and he got a phone call saying "can he come in at three?" "No, I can't I am out in town, I'll be in tomorrow", he said. They replied "I can't tell you that you can work tomorrow, you'll have to wait for a phone call." So I went through all that with him where he was getting up at 4 in the morning to see if he was going to be in at 6. So up at 4, no phone call at six, go back to bed to see if get your afternoon shift. "No, you may as well stay up now." So you're watching that man, my husband, walking round from room to room, checking his phone, not going outside the door to see if the afternoon call comes to see if he has the afternoon shift. That call doesn't come. You're not allowed to phone them by the way, they won't tell you if you're in the next day, you've got to wait for the call. Then he waits to see if he gets the night shift. He's been up since 4 in the morning. And then he's on his knees, there is no work that day, he'll get up tomorrow and he'll do the same thing all over again. In the end he had to stop. As I say these zero hour contracts are no good ...'

Others in the group also thought that austerity had brought increased deprivation to their wider community. A number of the respondents were from one particular part of Liverpool, Speke, known to be economically and socially disadvantaged. In the years leading up to the financial crash the city council undertook some building projects in the area including a new school, with sports facilities and a football field. Work had ceased on these projects and the group argued this reinforced the socially deprived status of the community:

Rob: *'We've got full sized pitches in Speke, we used to have a park, then they put up a shopping centre and built football pitches but it is all sealed off, you can't use it.'*

Sophie: *'I would like to know how many people live in Speke and we haven't even got a bank, we haven't had a bank for years ... Our Doctor's surgery is a portacabin, we got told 6 years ago that we're getting a surgery built, but it's still a portacabin.'*

Jacky argued that, due to its low socio-economic position, the whole community had long term problems with mental distress:

'I think ... so many people are finding it difficult, it's touching everybody in one way or another, breakdowns, my mother had three nervous breakdowns when I was a child and the doctor used to have the prescription pad written out when she walked through the door ... You know in Speke alone ... I would say at least 70% of people are on some sort of antidepressant.'

The group argued that austerity had impacted on them and many people they know as a result of the downward pressure it had placed on material living standards. Other factors cited was the movement to Universal Credit, the introduction of new charges for community services and the difficulty in finding work. Yet, improving their personal economic situation was not always recognised as that significant in terms of improving their capabilities. For instance, many emphasised the fact that their health and family life was more significant than increasing wealth, although when bills could not be paid or homes came under threat then the impact on levels of distress was severe:

Emma: *'You need enough to live on and pay the bills.'*

Rob: *'My independence, and to be where I want to be, which isn't here. It involves getting my health back to normal, I suppose my health is most important, but also I would like to be working ... you can have money and not be happy, and that's been myself most of my life, I always said I have money and I am still not happy.'*

Sophie: *'My priorities are my health and the health of my family. Without your health, I don't think you have anything, no matter how much money you have in the bank. As long as we can get by, as long as we can pay the mortgage, keeping a roof over our heads, pay the bills, food, anything else is a luxury really, it's just about getting by and staying well.'*

This was further reflected in the fact that those who wanted to work wanted to do so because of the social status and personal gratification of work, rather than monetary gain. Three of the respondents revealed that work related stresses had featured prominently in the onset of initial mental health crises but a number in the group still felt that their ultimate goal was to re-enter the paid labour market.

Ian: *'I would love to work myself, I love being round people me, I love people, but I just find would someone take me on having been out of work for so long. I worked loads when I was younger. I would love to work again.'*

Two in the group also described instances of rejection from potential job posts after admitting they suffered with mental health problems, Rob's example was very recent:

'I went for a job interview last week for a company, ... as soon as I mentioned that I have mental health problems and I suffer from Asperger's syndrome they literally switched off and didn't want to know. And that really upset me, and I walked out of the interview and I knew I hadn't got the job. As soon as I mentioned that [my mental health situation] they were just like they didn't want to know ... This raises the question of whether you do risk it in job interviews. The problem I find now is that I have been away from work for a year and half and they ask question 'why did you leave your employer?' What do I say now?'

Since the financial crash the group exposed instances where personal finances had deteriorated and some indicated that finding work had become more challenging. However, the group were probably more concerned about the dwindling mental health services available to them. This seems to fit with some of the claims made within the capabilities approach, that it is not only an individual's personal finances and wealth that are important. Analysis should be widened to include what a society provides in terms of opportunities to flourish, prosper and grow. For the research group, the most talked about concern regarding the impact of austerity on their mental distress was the reduction in services intended to support people with mental health problems in the Liverpool area. People described many different forms of reductions to both whole services and to certain cherished aspects of services.

However, the struggle to access forms of support clearly preceded the latest phase of austerity and the group frequently told stories about not being taken seriously or being unable to contact better forms of support. Here Sophie remembers her discharge from hospital following a suicide attempt, noting the total absence of support:

I've never had a social worker, I left hospital without a social worker, no after care, basically I got told 'you've got a husband, you've got 2 daughters at home, you've got somebody there for you – get on with.' As you start to improve your psychiatrist says you don't need to come here anymore. And when you do need to go back, you've got to go through the whole system again. They tell you that they don't keep records – I think that is a load of rubbish. And then also I have had my psychiatrist in the past changed for almost every appointment, I've never really got to see the same one.'

This was interlinked with the predominant medical model of delivering mental health services. Whilst those in the group were frequently denied or had to wait a great deal of time for talking therapies, the prescribing of anti-depressants and anti-psychotics was the main form of support offered:

Rob: *'When I go to the GP and ask for help they always start looking at my drugs and saying they want to change my prescriptions. I don't need drugs, I just need someone to talk to ... Do you know the side effects? Loss of sex drive, weight gain.'*

Some had been unable to access forms of talking therapy or when they had, the periods of engagement had been so short they were not deemed to be useful:

Emma: *'Things that could be provided, it's all this supposed improved this LAPT [NHS Programme Improved Access to Psychological Therapies] thing bollocks ... I've not seen this on the ground at all, this improved access to psychotherapy? My partner has still been waiting 18 months, that's not happening for him. Maybe counselling through the doctor or whatever but even that's not enough.'*

Agnes had also been attending, at the time of the meetings, a group therapy session which attempted to deliver mental health support through lectures:

'There's like 25 of us in a hall, two women who couldn't organise a piss up in a brewery, they've got a computer going onto the big screen and they're just reading it out. It takes them ten minutes to set the computer up. We don't get a cup of tea, the place is really really hot and we're all falling asleep. One man in the first session said 'this is no good to me, aren't we allowed to talk about our feelings, and how we're feeling, have we just got to sit here and listen to you.' And at the end of the session they gave us a 69 page booklet to read.'

Here we see principles of responsabilisation at work – service users effectively being told to sit through a lecture, read a booklet and resolve their own mental distress.

What concerned the group more than anything were changes to day centre support. This topic was mentioned more than anything else by the group and was identified as something of great value. Cuts to local authority budgets had resulted in day centre closures and the trimming down of the activities available.

As Peter explained, he felt that day centre provision across the city had been declining for some while:

'The support I've had in the day centres has been incredible, places where I listen and talk to other people. That's being cut, there used to be 20 odd centres in Liverpool, and now it's 2 or 3. Of those left, spaces are limited, it's going to be a short term contract for the services. The staff have had their hours cut.'

And Jacky described how the full range of services at the day centre she used had diminished:

'They were talking about funding acupuncture, massage, relaxation, colour therapy, counselling. A big pool table for the men, a little kitchen if you wanted to make a coffee, art, music, days out ... and all different things and then of course everything went. The massage went, used to love that, and the colour therapy and all that, and creative writing and all kinds of stuff. Slowly and surely things went.'

The day centre used by Jacky has now been forced to rent out half of the building to a private sector company – which raised issues of privacy and security as both employees of the tenant business and day centre users shared the same kitchen.

The struggles to access forms of support for their mental health had been taking place prior to austerity: in the UK welfare retrenchment has a longer history than that since the post-2008 financial crisis of these longer term welfare transformations the group were most concerned about changes in the intensity of community forms of support, first and foremost, and secondly in the reduction in talking therapies. In this sense austerity has been used as a mechanism to entrench further notions of individualised responsibility and medicalised modes of mental health support, limiting more community and collective forms of service.

Budgetary pressures on locally and centrally funded public services, have increasingly been coupled with a more generalised policy project which attempts to narrow who is defined as entitled to services in the first place (Roulstone 2015). A recent article in *The Independent* showed WCAs, as Agnes experienced, are costing more than they are saving (Wright 2016). The current and previous UK Government has rolled out a system of welfare based on stricter conditionality often requiring greater expenditure than the money saved, seemingly contradicting its own rhetoric of austerity as a rational economic logic concerned with bringing down the deficit as quickly as possible.

The last identifiable way in which the group felt that austerity was worsening the experiences of mental health is through rising experiences of stigma. The general politics of the day and some important social policy changes have reinforced feelings of shame associated with mental health difficulties. Increasing conditionality throughout the welfare system in tandem with a generalised political narrative which attempts to locate the underlying causes of austerity as a result of 'worklessness', 'scrounging' and 'welfare dependency' (Wiggan 2012), are promoting a perspective which suggests that people who are out of work should be held individually culpable and responsible for their own 'failure' to access employment. Crucially policy changes and political narrative are crafting pervasive anti-welfarist ideas, in turn shaping relations between actors.

Most of the participants in this study were subject to new forms of assessment and evaluation by different parts of the welfare system. Even in day centre care a new mandatory payment scheme had been established. As noted earlier, because Liverpool City Council has received massive reductions in the amount of central Government funding it has been forced to find extra savings in the social care services it offers. In trying to achieve this the Council instigated the Benefits Maximisation Team (BMT). Part of the BMT's role has been to assist people to ensure that they are claiming all the central government benefits that they are entitled to (an arguably positive development). But in addition, the BMT was assessing whether certain individuals are able to contribute payments for social care services they receive. Two people in this study were subject to assessment led by the BMT over whether they should make payments in order to access certain therapies and activities offered in day centres. These were intrusive evaluations of their spending and had required them to submit bank statements for scrutiny. Sophie stated that she stopped attending the day centre service after the introduction of charges, as she felt that other people probably needed the service more.

In this study many of the respondents made it clear they wanted to work. However, they felt unable to as employers were unable to accommodate their needs, and in some cases due to outright discrimination. This seemed to add an extra pressure to our group to make a case that they fell into the 'deserving' category. Reflecting the current dominant discourse about claimants, some in the group felt that there was a problem of 'others' dishonestly cheating the welfare system and that, as a result, the new system of conditionality may be justified; though none of them thought anyone in the group – or amongst their immediate friends and families – was anything other than 'deserving' of support. The invisible nature of mental health difficulties and other health problems was seen as socially problematic because others in their community might

not be sympathetic or accept that their entitlement to benefits and services was credible. So for instance, Jacky described how her conditions were imperceptible to others: 'You can't see them so I'd have to walk round with a placard on saying these are my illnesses'. She went on to recount how she was fearful, at times, about whether other people felt she deserved the help she received from public sources.

I mean I get in the taxi here and you get worried that your neighbours are watching you getting taxis because I get a taxi to the places, to my church café and they must think where she's going. If she's able to go out, but when you're on DLA it's for helping you get around. If you can't get around, drive and what have you, your DLA helps with taxis and can't remember anyone carrying five bags of shopping from Morrisons and not paying 2.20 for a taxi round the corner, do you know what I mean. It's that on the bus now if you haven't got a bus pass. But it's just suspicion.'

Rob also reflected similar anxieties when he stated that 'everybody judges you, why aren't you working, what's wrong with you. You don't want to go into it, you don't want to tell everyone why you're not working.'

The shame associated with having to seek support from the state was compounded in various interactions the group had with welfare professionals. When Agnes appealed the decision she received from the fitness-to-work assessment the lawyer asked a colleague at the beginning of the tribunal 'have we got another mental?' A GP laughed at Sophie when he had mistakenly thought she had spent time at Broadmoor, a renowned high security unit known for having incarcerated infamous serial murderers.

The increasing importance of evaluating assessment, constant checks on credibility and a political and media campaign which has constantly constructed people in receipt of welfare as feckless, workshy 'benefit scroungers' is, at heart, why our respondents constantly felt the need to justify their own entitlement to services (Jenson and Tyler 2016). While some, especially those with a clearer connection to service user political movements, were able to actively resist some of the dominant binary constructions of deserving/undeserving, others were compelled to engage in accounts which was geared towards displaying their status as an ill person who warranted help and support and was excusably out-of-work. The politics of austerity is deeply insidious in promoting certain social stereotypes and caricatures of welfare users, which in turn frame interactions with others in their community. People with mental health problems, as we will go on to see, are faced with a difficult conundrum: that welfare and mental health services, which are often a source of deteriorating mental health for people, are also often one of the few options available for those seeking support. So whilst they are profoundly critical of much of the assistance that they have received they also often argue for easier access and more services.

In a nutshell, the role of austerity has deepened the longer term neoliberal project which attempts to individualise and stigmatise the experience of being a welfare user. This has resulted in new forms of isolation and deepened previously existing modes of exclusion.

4.3 Improving the capabilities of people experiencing mental distress

The capabilities approach asks us to focus on the resources that are available to individuals in order to achieve their goals, aspirations and hopes. It also requires a transcendence of a conventional human rights approach which is inclined to focus only on what a state should resist from doing (Benton 2006), in other words negative freedoms, and that attention should be targeted at how societies can promote human development (Brunner and Watson 2016; Sen 2001). This section examines what the current capabilities are available to people when they are seeking to improve their lives, and what conceivable developments people felt could be useful. Four main themes emerged from the discussions around what was seen to be beneficial, including comments concerning what they found particularly useful in surviving with mental distress. These included:

- having their illness recognised by others, including friends and family but also from trained professionals;
- opportunities to engage in constructive therapeutic activities;
- active participation in social locations defined by decision making and opportunities to resist dominant understandings that welfare users are disingenuous or workshy;

- places in people's life defined by security and safety.

The first principle was that people needed to feel that they were taken seriously, that their status as mentally distressed was *recognised* both by professionals and others in their lives. For instance, Jacky felt that part of the stigma of having a mental illness was that other people did not realise you were sick. Peter explained the importance of receiving expert guidance from trained professionals:

'Acknowledgement of illness, an opportunity to talk to professionals, and for me that's my own way of looking at symptoms that I've got, fears that I've got, experiences that I've been through that play on my own mind a lot and helping me understand my own symptoms, what that means to be myself, what that means to other people, what that means to the rest of the world.'

Others linked the lack of recognition to the amount of pharmaceuticals they were taking. As noted earlier, most members of the research group complained at both the lack of support and the need to continuously skirmish with formal services, whether it be primary care or mental health services, in order to get assistance. The point being, that others recognising that they were ill and especially receiving support after having illness recognised, was important to the group. This has relevance for broader debates about the importance of recognition in understanding social justice and injustice (Garrett 2010). Recent changes have tended to promote ideas that those who are entitled to benefits are disingenuous or have become 'dependent' on welfare representing a misrecognition. Opportunities to have illness taken seriously can help people to overcome pervasive negative stereotypes but also represents entitlement to real beneficial forms of services.

Across the group there was a desire to have access to some form of talking therapy but the problems in accessing this form of support were continually discussed. Talking therapies were most valued when it was with a trained professional, they were longer lasting and they represented serious engagement with a therapist exploring the complex and lifelong biographies which underpinned mental distress.

On the whole the mental health system was not talked about positively although on many occasions people thought that it could help if it was designed differently. The system failed to provide any longer term service outside of a crisis or sectioning situation and this seemed to be its primary weakness. A number in the group described frustration at not being able to have regular contact with a psychiatrist. Others described the unhelpful support from community psychiatric nurses and especially not having sufficient time to talk through problems and symptoms. Emma summed up the importance of both internal and external acceptance and recognition of mental distress:

'Actually accepting that you need help is the biggest step because for years I blagged it, I'm fine, I'm fine, the more you do that the more you spectacularly crack at the end. But obviously you can't then get anywhere without access to services, day centres, day hospitals are brilliant. The biggy is talking to somebody who's got empathy, somebody who understands. Whether that be a fellow service user or a professional. Psychotherapy certainly helped me but you wait forever to get it.'

Secondly, the participants valued tangible opportunities in their lives to engage in various forms social, cultural, spiritual and physical activity. Sometimes these were therapeutic activities participated in through their engagement with mental health services and in other instances they were hobbies and interests engaged with in the course of their everyday lives. Two of the male respondents regularly played football in a programme specially set up for people with ongoing mental health problems. Many had engaged in arts and crafts through day centres and other support groups. A number were actively engaged in churches and one was a follower of paganism. Pet ownership, keeping an allotment, reading, popping bubble wrap, cycling, gym membership, amongst a range of other hobbies and interests, were seen as beneficial to coping with mental distress.

However, one service was repeatedly noted as being especially advantageous for improving people's lives. Day centre care had the potential to be transformative for some. This did not necessarily entail a complete overcoming of mental distress altogether but rather allowed them to find a sense of normality and routine in their life. Sophie, Jacky, Peter and Ian all described the way that day centres provided people with a place to meet and somewhere to go. The value of day centre care seemed to be double fold in that on the one hand, it provided a safe, secure and stigma-free space within which to develop social relationships with

other services users and staff, but on the other, it also provided social purpose and stimulation. Peter reflected on the importance of accessing day centre care for the first time some years ago:

I had always struggled to talk about my illness and events that took place. But the service, we did bee-keeping, we did gardening, we did eco-world projects, we did interior design projects, we did DIY, and it would be with like skilled workers and there'd be a small group of people that worked with them and did these activities. And it was just a joy, a quiet joy, it was really kind of under the surface all the good it was doing and you know it was stopped me from having that cycle of admissions to hospital, it helped me to have better relationships with my family again, it gave me security, it gave me a positive outlook on life, it gave me confidence, it gave me support, and it gave me an understanding of my mental health. And one of the key workers I had while I was there, you know I learned things about bee-keeping, I learned things about the allotment, plants and flowers, and I learned things about politics. You know it was just brilliant, it was like university all over again without the pressure and all the essays to hand in, just the social side, and I'm still supported by it now.'

Opportunities for political action and reflection on the biographical and systemic nature of mental health was the third area of capabilities for coping with distress. There were four major examples of this. Firstly, the engagement with a University's Service User Involvement Team (USUC), which the majority of the research group were active in and had been the major point of contact for recruitment in this study; secondly a recent local activist campaign challenging the proposed closure of a day centre (see Moth *et al* 2015); thirdly, the setting up of a service user organisation and; lastly, one member was participating in an anti-psychiatry campaign group. These four examples, it is contended here, were cherished because they assisted people to comprehend both their current mental health situation but also develop a political consciousness around the forms of injustices they had been subject to over the lifecourse: they were social and political spaces where 'conscientisation' took place (Friere 1970). In all these forms of engagement real empowered decision making also existed, although not always easily.

The involvement with USUC allowed people to contribute to teaching, assisting with course development and design, and, most frequently, making decisions on candidate selection for social work degree. So for instance, both Agnes and Rob were in agreement in one of the research meetings that involvement with the University gave them a social purpose:

Agnes: *I think the work at Hope has helped me, because you feel that you're of use, you know you're not thrown on the scrapheap.'*

Rob: *It makes you feel like there's purpose to life, your valued by someone, same with football now, you get to know that there's people out there like you, you're not different, you're normal. Just cause you've got mental health problems doesn't mean you're any different to anyone else.'*

Similarly, Sophie noted that one of the principle positive impacts of engaging with this scheme was that it gave the 'opportunity to give something back'. This reflects the fact that the opportunities where people felt empowered and valued combated both the pervasive stereotypes that mental illness was about personal or moral failure. Emma said 'So I think campaigning can do that, or the teaching, or doing the interviews [for entry to the social work programme], it's just not feeling a useless piece of shit but unfortunately that is what mental illness does and how others treat you'.

Opportunities such as USUC, local campaigning or participation in community groups also help the respondents to develop a critical understanding of their mental health. All valued the opportunity to learn from others, both those who had experienced similar experiences and professionals, which assisted them to understand that their mental illness was the result of systemic factors with class and gender both being mentioned. As noted in earlier sections, the group, on the whole, were aware and critical about how both the welfare system and the nature of mental health support could be frightening, counterproductive and unquestionably cruel.

The last major theme to emerge from the research activities was the notion of *safety and security*. This, again, undoubtedly emerged from the fact that previous experiences in mental health services were often frightening.

Peter: *‘[The day centre] was real safe place, it was fantastic. That’s the security element... And with a garden as well you feel like you’ve got your own sanctuary and you feel active and you’re doing things and you’re talking about things and feel good about yourself, being physically active and talking about things and doing things with friends, making friends as well, socially, it’s a real sanctuary. From the liberty aspect my mental health felt liberated, I had the support, I felt so much better about myself, I just felt safe, that gave me freedom in its self, freedom in my mind, freedom in myself with my mental health.’*

This short discussion of the key capabilities feeds into some of the wider thinking about the approach. The emphasis on individual freedom appears to be backed up by the respondents apparent desire to access different forms.

5. Conclusion

This project has employed a participative methodology to explore the social damage that austerity has meted out on people with mental distress. Transformations that have occurred in the last seven years have not only placed greater demands on people's material access to finances, but has also identifiably promoted negative constructions of people who are out-of-work due to ill mental health. A number of policy recommendations emerge from our report which will also serve as concluding remarks.

1. The group revealed that their experiences were increasingly contextualised in a political context promoting an 'anti-welfare common sense' (Jensen and Tyler 2015). This framed interactions with welfare professionals but also how they saw themselves. Resisting these dominant constructions of people who use public services as disingenuous or workshy would negate feelings of shame about 'being on the scrapheap', potentially improving people's self-worth. Transforming the dominant political narratives could create a psychological and interactional environment more conducive with improvements in mental health. This would include the removal or decreasing importance of assessments and conditionality across the welfare system, including the WCA.
2. The group developed a strong critique of current mental health services, and especially those which were more individualised and medicalised in their approach. They believed that services which were most beneficial were those which allowed active participation, constructive therapeutic opportunities, offered security and shelter and also allowed for the development of critical thinking and direct challenges to their place in the world. Support from trained professionals, however, who recognised the severity of their distress was also important to them. All this points to the importance of community mental health services, and day centre support in particular, as a critical pillar of in the long term support for mental distress.
3. Rising household and personal financial precarity since austerity was clearly emanating from a range of sources including casualised employment contracts, decreasing benefits, under investment in communities and new charges such as the bedroom tax. Securing better material security would also free people to give better attention to managing and coping with their mental distress.

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CNRS • Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique • France
SOFI • Soziologisches Forschungsinstitut Goettingen e.V. • Germany
IFZ • Internationales Forschungszentrum für Soziale und Ethische Fragen • Austria
UCL • Université Catholique de Louvain • Belgium
NUIM • National University of Ireland Maynooth • Ireland
Loughborough University • United Kingdom
EUR • Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam • the Netherlands
TU Delft • Technische Universiteit Delft • the Netherlands
Liverpool Hope University • United Kingdom
IRD • Institut de Recherche pour le Développement • France
OSE • Observatoire Social Européen asbl • Belgium
UNIGE • Université de Genève • Switzerland
RSU • Rigas Stradina Universitate • Latvia
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The Poverty Alliance • United Kingdom
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